

Water Resources Data Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands Water Year 1988

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY WATER-DATA REPORT PR-88-1
Prepared in cooperation with the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico,
the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and other agencies

CALENDAR FOR WATER YEAR 1988

1987

OCTOBER

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
				1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17
18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	31

NOVEMBER

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30					

DECEMBER

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
		1	2	3	4	5
6	7	8	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19
20	21	22	23	24	25	26
27	28	29	30	31		

1988

JANUARY

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
					1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30
31						

FEBRUARY

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	8	9	10	11	12	13
14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27
28	29					

MARCH

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
		1	2	3	4	5
6	7	8	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19
20	21	22	23	24	25	26
27	28	29	30	31		

APRIL

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
					1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30

MAY

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	31				

JUNE

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
				1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17
18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	

JULY

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
					1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30
31						

AUGUST

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	8	9	10	11	12	13
14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27
28	29	30	31			

SEPTEMBER

S	M	T	W	T	F	S
					1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30

Water Resources Data Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands

Water Year 1988

by R.E. Curtis, Jr., Z. Aquino, P.L. Diaz, and R.J. Vachier

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY WATER-DATA REPORT PR-88-1

Prepared in cooperation with the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico,
the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and other agencies

DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR

MANUEL LUJAN, JR., Secretary

U.S. GEOLOGICAL SURVEY

Dallas L. Peck, Director

**For additional information on the water resources investigation programs
in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands write to:**

Chief, Caribbean District, Water Resources Division

U.S. Geological Survey

GPO Box 4424

San Juan, PR 00936

(Telephone: (809) 749-4346)

PREFACE

This annual hydrologic data report of Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands is one of a series of annual reports that document hydrologic data gathered from the U.S. Geological Survey's surface- and ground-water data-collection networks in each state, Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and the other Trust Territories. These records of streamflow, ground-water levels, and quality of water provide the hydrologic information needed by state, local and Federal agencies, and the private sector for developing and managing our Nation's land and water resources.

The report is the culmination of a concerted effort by dedicated personnel of the U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division who collected, compiled, analyzed, verified, and organized the data, and who typed, edited, and assembled the report. In addition to the authors, who had primary responsibility for assuring that the information contained herein is accurate, complete and adheres to Geological Survey policy and established guidelines, the following personnel contributed significantly to the collection, processing and tabulations of the data:

José M. Agis	Senén Guzmán-Ríos
George Arroyo	Karl G. Johnson
Angel Class-Cacho	Sandra Lagares
Iris M. Concepción	Julio Oms
Angel G. Ferrer	Ana V. Sánchez
Carlos Figueroa	José René Sánchez
Eduardo Figueroa	Luis Santiago-Rivera
Javier García	Luis Soler
René García	José A. Torres
Ralph González	Heriberto Torres-Sierra
Evelyn S. Guevara	Ahmed Valencia

This report was prepared in cooperation with agencies of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands, and with other federal agencies under the general supervision of Allen L. Zack, District Chief, Caribbean District, San Juan, Puerto Rico.

REPORT DOCUMENTATION PAGE	1. REPORT NO. USGS/WRD/HD-89/280	2.	3. Recipient's Accession No.
4. Title and Subtitle Water Resources Data for Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands Water Year 1988		5. Report Date August 1989	
7. Author(s) Russell E. Curtis, Jr., Zaida Aquino, Ricardo J. Vachier, Pedro L. Diaz		8. Performing Organization Rept. No. USGS-WDR-PR-88-1	
9. Performing Organization Name and Address U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division GPO Box 4424 San Juan, Puerto Rico 00936		10. Project/Task/Work Unit No. 11. Contract(C) or Grant(G) No. (C) (G)	
12. Sponsoring Organization Name and Address U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Division GPO Box 4424 San Juan, Puerto Rico 00936		13. Type of Report & Period Covered Annual-Oct. 1, 1987 to Sept. 30, 1988 14.	
15. Supplementary Notes Prepared in cooperation with the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the Government of the U.S. Virgin Islands and other agencies.			
16. Abstract (Limit: 200 words) Water-resources data for surface-water, quality-of-water, and ground-water records for the 1988 water year for Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands, consists of records of discharge, water quality of streams, and water levels of wells. This report contains discharge records for 52 streamflow-gaging stations; stage records for 5 reservoirs; water quality records for 16 streamflow-gaging stations, 42 ungaged streamsites, 11 lake sites, 2 lagoons, and 1 bay; and water-level records for 63 observation wells. These data represent that part of the National Water Data System collected by the U.S. Geological Survey and cooperating local and federal agencies in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.			
17. Document Analysis a. Descriptors *Surface water, *Water quality, *Ground water, Aquifers, Chemical analysis, Gaging stations, Hydrologic data, Sediments, Streamflow, Water analysis, Water Levels, Lakes. b. Identifiers/Open-Ended Terms Puerto Rico, U.S. Virgin Islands, Sampling sites. c. COATI Field/Group			
18. Availability Statement: NO RESTRICTION ON DISTRIBUTION		19. Security Class (This Report) UNCLASSIFIED	21. No. of Pages 474
		20. Security Class (This Page) UNCLASSIFIED	22. Price

CONTENTS

	Page
Preface.....	iii
List of surface-water and water-quality stations, in downstream order, for which records are published.....	viii
List of ground-water wells, by basin, for which records are published.....	xii
Introduction.....	1
Cooperation.....	2
Summary of hydrologic conditions.....	2
Precipitation.....	2
Surface water.....	3
Ground water.....	7
Water quality.....	9
Special networks and programs.....	11
Explanation of records.....	11
Station identification numbers.....	11
Downstream order system.....	19
Latitude-longitude system.....	19
Records of stage and water discharge.....	20
Data collection and computation.....	20
Data presentation.....	22
Identifying estimated daily discharge.....	25
Accuracy of the records.....	25
Records of surface-water quality.....	25
Classification of records.....	26
Arrangement of records.....	26
On-site measurements and sample collection.....	26
Water temperature.....	27
Sediment.....	28
Laboratory measurements.....	28
Data presentation.....	28
Remark codes.....	30
Records of ground-water levels.....	30
Data collection and computation.....	30
Data presentation.....	31
Records of ground-water quality.....	32
Data collection and computation.....	32
Data presentation.....	33
Access to WATSTORE data.....	33
Definition of terms.....	34
Publications on Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations.....	48
Surface- and quality-of-water records for Puerto Rico.....	51
Water-quality at partial-record stations in Puerto Rico.....	377
Ground-water records for Puerto Rico.....	389
Surface-water records for the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	431
Ground-Water records for the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	439
Index.....	457

ILLUSTRATIONS

	Page
Figure 1. Graph showing monthly-mean discharge of selected streams in Puerto Rico.....	4
2. Graph showing ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	8
3. Map showing location of fecal coliform bacteria concentration at sampled sites.....	12
4. Map showing location of fecal streptococci bacteria concentration at sampled sites.....	13
5. Map showing location of continuous surface-water stations in Puerto Rico.....	14
6. Map showing location of water-quality stations in Puerto Rico.....	15
7. Map showing location of ground-water stations in Puerto Rico.....	16
8. Map showing location of surface-water stations in U.S. Virgin Islands.....	17
9. Map showing location of ground-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	18
10. Grid showing system for numbering wells and miscellaneous site (latitude and longitude).....	19
11. Map showing the Río Guajataca basin.....	53
12. Map showing the Río Camuy basin.....	63
13. Map showing the Río Grande de Arecibo basin.....	69
14. Map showing the Río Grande de Manatí basin.....	93
15. Map showing the Río Cibuco basin.....	113
16. Map showing the Río de la Plata basin.....	121
17. Map showing the Río Hondo to the Río Puerto Nuevo basins.....	135
18. Map showing the Río Grande de Loíza basin.....	155
19. Map showing northeastern river basins the Río Herrera to the Río Antón Ruíz basins.....	281
20. Map showing southeastern river basins the Río Humacao to the Río Seco basins.....	301
21. Map showing south coast river basins the Río Salinas to the Río Jacaguas basins.....	317
22. Map showing south coast river basins the Río Inabón to the Río Loco basins.....	325
23. Map showing the Río Guanajibo basin.....	343
24. Map showing the Río Yagüez and the Río Grande de Añasco basins.....	359
25. Map showing the Río Culebrinas basin.....	369

TABLES

	Page
Table 1. Island-wide monthly precipitation and annual averages for 1988 water year and the 30-year reference period, 1951-80.....	3
2. Peak discharges during November 26-27 and December 6-7, 1987 and previously recorded maximum at selected streamflow gaging stations in Puerto Rico.....	6
3. Maximum ground-water levels in 1988 water year and highest water levels of record in feet below land-surface, at selected ground-water wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.....	7
4. Surface-water quality stations throughout Puerto Rico with the highest concentration of selected constituents during water year 1988.....	9
5. Maximum suspended-sediment concentration and load at each station within the Río Grande de Loíza basin.....	10
6. Factors for conversion of chemical constituents in milligrams per liter to milli-equivalents per liter.....	39

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED**

(Letter after station name designates type of data:
(d) discharge, (c) chemical, (b) biological,
(s) sediment, (p) pesticide, (e) elevation)

	Page
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN	
Río Guajataca at Lares (c,b).....	54
Río Guajataca above Lago Guajataca (d).....	56
Canal Principal de Diversiones at Lago Guajataca (c,b).....	58
Río Guajataca above mouth near Quebradillas (d,c,b).....	60
RIO CAMUY BASIN	
Río Camuy near Bayaney (d).....	64
Río Camuy near Hatillo (d).....	66
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN	
Lago Garzas near Adjuntas (e).....	70
Río Grande de Arecibo near Adjuntas (c,b).....	71
Río Grande de Arecibo near Utuado (c,b).....	73
Río Caonillas above Lago Caonillas near Jayuya (c,b).....	75
Río Grande de Arecibo below Lago Dos Bocas near Florida (c,b).....	77
Río Grande de Arecibo above Arecibo (d).....	79
Río Tanamá near Utuado (d,c,b,s).....	81
Río Tanamá at Charco Hondo (d).....	88
Río Grande de Arecibo at Central Cambalache (c,b).....	90
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN	
Río Orocovis near Orocovis (c,b).....	94
Río Grande de Manatí near Morovis (d,c,b).....	96
Lago El Guineo at Damsite (e).....	99
Lago Matrullas at Damsite (e).....	100
Río Grande de Manatí at Ciales (d).....	101
Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 149 at Ciales (c,b).....	103
Río Cialitos at Highway 649 at Ciales (c,b).....	105
Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 2 near Manatí (d,c,b,p).....	107
LAGUNA TORTUGUERO BASIN	
Laguna Tortuguero Outlet near Vega Baja (c,b).....	112
RIO CIBUCO BASIN	
Río Cibuco below Corozal (d,c,b).....	114
Río Cibuco at Vega Baja (d,c,b).....	117
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN	
Río de La Plata at Proyecto La Plata (d,c,b).....	122
Río de La Plata near Comerio (c,b).....	125
Río Guadiana near Naranjito (c,b).....	127
Río de La Plata at Toa Alta (c,b,s,p).....	129
Río de La Plata at Highway 2 near Toa Alta (d).....	132
RIO HONDO BASIN	
Río Hondo at Flood Channel near Cataño (c,b).....	136

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED--Continued**

	Page
RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN	
Lago de Cidra at Damsite near Cidra (e).....	138
Río de Bayamón near Aguas Buenas (c,b).....	139
Río Guaynabo near Bayamón (c,b).....	141
Río de Bayamón at Flood Channel at Bayamón (c,b,p).....	143
RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN	
Río Piedras:	
Río Piedras at El Señorial (d).....	145
Río Piedras near Río Piedras (d,c,b,p).....	146
Río Piedras at Río Piedras (d).....	148
Río Piedras at Hato Rey (c,b).....	149
Quebrada Josefina at Piñeiro Avenue (d).....	151
Laguna San José:	
Laguna San José No.2 at San Juan (c,b).....	152
Bahía de San Juan:	
Bahía de San Juan No.5 at San Juan (c,b).....	153
QUEBRADA BLASINA BASIN	
Quebrada Blasina near Carolina (c,b).....	156
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN	
Río Grande de Loíza at Quebrada Arenas (d).....	158
Quebrada Blanca at El Jagual (d,s).....	160
Quebrada Salvatierra near San Lorenzo (d,s).....	168
Río Cayaguas at Cerro Gordo (d,s).....	178
Río Turabo at Borinquen (d,s).....	189
Río Grande de Loíza at Caguas (d,c,b,s).....	199
Río Caguitas at Highway 30 at Caguas (c,b).....	219
Río Bairoa near Caguas (c,b).....	221
Río Gurabo:	
Quebrada Caimito near Juncos (s).....	223
Río Valenciano near Juncos (d,s).....	231
Quebrada Mamey near Gurabo (d,s).....	242
Río Gurabo at Gurabo (d,s).....	252
Río Gurabo near Gurabo (c,b).....	271
Lago Loíza at Damsite (c,b,e).....	273
Río Grande de Loíza below Damsite (d).....	275
Río Grande de Loíza below Trujillo Alto (c,b).....	276
Río Canóvanas near Campo Rico (d).....	278
RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN	
Quebrada Sonadora near El Verde (d).....	282
Quebrada Toronja at El Verde (d).....	284
Río Espíritu Santo near Río Grande (d,c,b).....	286
RIO MAMEYES BASIN	
Río Mameyes near Sabana (d).....	289
RIO SABANA BASIN	
Río Sabana at Sabana (d).....	291

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED--Continued**

	Page
RIO FAJARDO BASIN	
Río Fajardo near Fajardo (d,c,b,s,p).....	293
Río Fajardo below Fajardo (c,b).....	296
RIO BLANCO BASIN	
Río Icacos near Naguabo (d).....	298
RIO HUMACAO BASIN	
Río Humacao at Las Piedras (d).....	302
Río Humacao at Highway 3 at Humacao (c,b).....	303
RIO GUAYANES BASIN	
Río Guayanés at Yabucoa (c,b,p).....	305
Río Guayanés above mouth at Playa de Guayanés (c,b).....	307
RIO MAUNABO BASIN	
Río Maunabo at Maunabo (c,b).....	309
RIO CHICO BASIN	
Río Chico at Providencia (c,b).....	311
RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN	
Río Grande de Patillas near Patillas (d,c,b,s).....	313
RIO COAMO BASIN	
Río Coamo near Coamo (c,b).....	318
RIO DESCALABRADO BASIN	
Río Descalabrado near Los Llanos (d).....	320
RIO JACAGUAS BASIN	
Río Jacaguas at Juana Díaz (d).....	322
RIO INABON BASIN	
Río Inabón at Real Abajo (d).....	326
RIO BUCANA BASIN	
Río Bucaná:	
Río Cerrillos near Ponce (c,b).....	328
Río Bucana at Hwy 14 Bridge near Ponce (d).....	330
RIO PORTUGUES BASIN	
Río Portugués near Ponce (d,c,b).....	332
Río Portugués at Ponce (c,b,p).....	335
RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN	
Río Guayanilla near Guayanilla (d).....	337
Río Guayanilla at Central Rufina (c,b,p).....	339
RIO LOCO BASIN	
Río Loco at Guánica (c,b,p).....	341

**SURFACE-WATER AND WATER-QUALITY STATIONS, IN DOWNSTREAM ORDER,
FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED--Continued**

	Page
LAGUNA JOYUDA BASIN	
Quebrada Mamey at Joyuda (d).....	344
RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN	
Río Guanajibo near San Germán (c,b).....	346
Río Rosario near Hormigueros (d,c,b,s).....	348
Río Guanajibo near Hormigueros (d,c,b,p).....	355
RIO YAGUEZ BASIN	
Río Yagüez near Mayagüez (c,b).....	360
RIO GRANDE DE AÑASCO BASIN	
Río Grande de Añasco near Lares (c,b).....	362
Río Grande de Añasco near San Sebastián (d,c,b,s).....	364
Río Grande de Añasco near Añasco (c,b,p).....	367
RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN	
Río Culebrinas near San Sebastián (c,b).....	370
Río Culebrinas at Highway 404 near Moca (d).....	372
Río Culebrinas near Aguada (c,b,p).....	374
ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Bonne Resolution Gut at Bonne Resolution (d).....	432
Turpentine Run at Mariendal (d).....	434
ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Guinea Gut at Bethany (d).....	435
ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Jolly Hill Gut at Jolly Hill (d).....	436

GROUND-WATER WELLS, BY BASIN, FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED

	Page
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN	
Well 182422067015100 Local number 165.....	390
Well 182647066552400 Local number 202.....	391
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN	
Well 182737066370900 Local number 204.....	392
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN	
Well 182544066341500 Local number 205.....	393
Well 182757066325600 Local number 206.....	394
Well 182710066303700 Local number 207.....	395
Well 182534066283000 Local number 208.....	396
Well 182634066262500 Local number 209.....	397
Well 182308066260400 Local number 210.....	398
RIO CIBUCO BASIN	
Well 182647066201700 Local number 70.....	399
Well 182615066235300 Local number 211.....	400
Well 182515066194000 Local number 212.....	401
Well 182330066185700 Local number 213.....	402
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN	
Well 182746066170800 Local number 214.....	403
Well 182530066135400 Local number 216.....	404
Well 182655066142400 Local number 217.....	405
RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS	
Well 182623066111000 Local number 218.....	406
Well 182441066082600 Local number 219.....	407
Well 182413066044000 Local number 220.....	408
Well 182436066031200 Local number 221.....	409
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN	
Well 182515065594100 Local number 222.....	410
RIO HUMACAO TO RIO SECO BASINS	
Well 175858066100200 Local number 6.....	411
RIO GUAYANES BASIN	
Well 180415065513900 Local number 96.....	412
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS	
Well 175829066232200 Local number 87.....	413
Well 180002066132200 Local number HW-TW-01.....	414
Well 180017066132100 Local number HW-TW-02.....	415

GROUND-WATER WELLS, BY BASIN, FOR WHICH RECORDS ARE PUBLISHED

	Page
Well 180001066122000 Local number HW-TW-03.....	416
Well 180000066125200 Local number HW-TW-04.....	417
Well 175947066130601 Local number HW-TW-05B.....	418
Well 180006066123700 Local number HW-TW-07.....	419
Well 175939066121400 Local number HW-TW-08.....	420
Well 175950066125200 Local number HW-TW-10.....	421
Well 180012066125500 Local number HW-TW-11.....	422
Well 175957066123400 Local number HW-TW-13.....	423
Well 175946066102000 Local number HW-TW-14.....	424
Well 175955066103000 Local number HW-TW-15.....	425
RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS	
Well 180133066503300 Local number 132.....	426
RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN	
Well 180132067033800 Local number 143.....	427
RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN	
Well 182018066593200 Local number 83.....	428
Well 182442067091700 Local number 200.....	429
ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Well 174225064471900 Local number 1.....	440
Well 174225064472000 Local number 2.....	441
Well 174243064475100 Local number 3.....	442
Well 174245064475800 Local number 4.....	443
Well 174308064484400 Local number 6.....	444
Well 174525064460600 Local number 7.....	445
Well 174527064460100 Local number 8.....	445
Well 174532064460300 Local number 9.....	446
Well 174329064454700 Local number 10.....	446
ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Well 182050064580400 Local number 1.....	447
Well 182138064543100 Local number 2.....	447
Well 182138064542500 Local number 3.....	447
Well 182136064541900 Local number 4.....	448
Well 182029064535200 Local number 5.....	448
Well 182038064550300 Local number 6.....	449
ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS	
Well 182010064472600 Local number 1.....	450
Well 182109064460300 Local number 2.....	450
Well 182116064451000 Local number 3.....	451
Well 182042064454500 Local number 5.....	452
Well 182044064454600 Local number 6.....	453
Well 182044064454800 Local number 7.....	453
Well 182044064454900 Local number 8.....	453
Well 182044064455000 Local number 9.....	454
Well 182044064455200 Local number 10.....	454
Well 181956064464500 Local number 11.....	455

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

INTRODUCTION

The Water Resources Division of the U.S. Geological Survey, in cooperation with local and federal agencies obtains a large amount of data pertaining to the water resources of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico and the Territory of the U.S. Virgin Islands each water year. These data, accumulated during many water years, constitute a valuable data base for developing an improved understanding of the water resources of the area. To make these data readily available to interested parties outside the Geological Survey, the data are published annually in this report series entitled "Water Resources Data for Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands, 1988."

This report includes records on both surface and ground water. Specifically, it contains: (1) Discharge records for 52 streamflow-gaging stations, stage records for 5 reservoirs; (2) water-quality records for 16 streamflow-gaging stations, and for 42 ungaged streamsites, 11 lake sites, 2 lagoon, and 1 bay; and (3) water-level records for 63 observation wells.

Water-resources data for Puerto Rico for calendar years 1958-67 were released in a series of reports entitled "Water Records of Puerto Rico". Water-resources data for the U.S. Virgin Islands for the calendar years 1962-69 were released in a report entitled "Water Records of U.S. Virgin Islands." Included were records of streamflow, ground-water levels, and water-quality data for both surface and ground water.

Beginning with the 1968 calendar year, surface-water records for Puerto Rico were released separately on an annual basis. Ground-water level records and water-quality data for surface and ground water were released in companion reports covering periods of several years. Data for the 1973-74 reports were published under separate covers. Water-resources data reports for 1975-76, 1977, 1978, 1979-80, 1981-82, 1983, 1984, 1985, 1986, and 1987 water years consist of one volume each and contain data for streamflow, water quality and ground water.

Publications similar to this report are published annually by the Geological Survey for all States. These official Survey reports have an identification number consisting of the two-letter State abbreviation, the last two digits of the water year, and the volume number. For example, this volume is identified as "U.S. Geological Survey Water-Data Report PR-88-1". These water-data reports are for sale in paper copy or in microfiche by the National Technical Information Service, U.S. Department of Commerce, Springfield, Virginia, 22161.

Additional information, including current prices, for ordering specific reports may be obtained from the District Chief at the address given on back of title page or by telephone (809) 783-4660.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988**COOPERATION**

The U.S. Geological Survey has had cooperative agreements with organizations of the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico and the Territory of the U.S. Virgin Islands for the systematic collections of water resources data since 1958. Organizations that supplied data are acknowledged in the station descriptions. Organizations that assisted in collecting data through cooperative agreements with the Survey are:

Puerto Rico Environmental Quality Board
Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority
Puerto Rico Department of Agriculture
Puerto Rico Industrial Development Company
Puerto Rico Department of Public Works
Puerto Rico Highway Authority
Puerto Rico Department of Natural Resources
Puerto Rico Department of Health
Puerto Rico Electric and Power Authority
Puerto Rico Rice Corporation
Puerto Rico Administration for Agricultural Development
Puerto Rico Land Administration
Center for Energy and Environment Research, University
of Puerto Rico
Water Resources Research Institute, University of
Puerto Rico
Water Resources Research Institute, College of the
Virgin Islands
Department of Public Works of the U.S. Virgin Islands

Funds were also provided by the Corps of Engineers, U.S. Army, for the collection of records at five gaging stations published in this report. Ground-water quality data at selected sites was collected with support from the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.

SUMMARY OF HYDROLOGIC CONDITIONS**Precipitation**

Precipitation was higher than usual in the 1988 water year. Precipitation averaged about 122 percent of normal, islandwide, varying from 135 percent of normal in the eastern part of the island to 99 percent of normal in the western part of the island. Monthly average precipitation islandwide for water year 1988 and the 30-year (1951-80) normal as reported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration are listed in table 1.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Table 1. Island-wide monthly precipitation and annual averages for 1988 water year and the 30-year reference period, 1951-80.

Month	Water year 1988 (inches)	30-year normal (inches)
Oct.	7.41	7.74
Nov.	13.22	5.95
Dec.	7.54	4.32
Jan.	3.10	3.08
Feb.	3.03	2.35
Mar.	2.36	2.62
Apr.	5.29	4.63
May	5.26	6.48
June	5.13	5.58
July	5.20	5.48
Aug.	11.56	7.28
Sept.	7.85	7.78
TOTAL	76.95	63.29

Surface Water

Streamflow in Puerto Rico was above normal during water year 1988. A comparison of 1988 streamflow at 4 index or representative gaging stations to their long-term median and extreme monthly flows is shown in figure 1. Flows during October were below normal throughout much of the island. The October mean flow for the Río Grande de Anasco gaging station, which is in the western part of the island, was only 53 percent of the median monthly flow. In November, an upper level trough became stationary over the eastern portion of the island. Heavy rain was developed during November 26, causing severe flooding over the eastern interior portion of Puerto Rico. Monthly mean flows at all four of the index stations were above the long term median in this month. At the Río Fajardo gaging station in the eastern part of the island, the mean flow for the month was 297 percent of the long term median, and was the third highest November mean flow recorded since the station was installed in 1962. The floods in November 1987 resulted in three deaths and forced the evacuation of about 350 people. A total of about 2,850 houses in 21 municipios received flood damage. Damages to roads and highways due primarily to landslides associated with the flooding were reported in 27 municipios. Damages in terms of cost were estimated near \$6 million.

Unshaded area indicates range between highest and lowest monthly mean discharges for the period of record

Figure 1.—Monthly mean discharge of selected streams in Puerto Rico.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

One week after the November 26-27 floods, a combination of an approaching cold front and a southeastern flow of moist tropical air induced intense showers and thunderstorms over southeastern and eastern interior parts of Puerto Rico. High rainfall amounts in combination with saturated soil conditions produced by the previous rains ten days before, resulted in severe flash flooding. This caused the death of one person, forced the evacuation of 1,276 people, and damaged or destroyed 13 bridges. During this period, streamflow at the four index recording stations was above average. The monthly mean flow at the Río Fajardo gaging station was 246 percent of the long term median and the monthly mean flow of Río Inabón was 200 percent of normal. Damages associated with this flood were estimated near \$5 million. Peak discharges for the floods of November and December are given for 10 stations in the affected areas in table 2.

In January, above average flows continued, specially along the north coast, where the index station at the Río Grande de Manatí recorded the largest monthly mean flow for January since the station was installed. The mean flow for January at this site was 235 percent of the long term median. At the gaging station on Río Fajardo, the monthly mean discharge in January was 148 percent of the median. The station on the Río Grande de Añasco in the western part of the island was the only index station with a monthly mean discharge below the median.

During February and March, streamflows in the southern and western parts of the island showed a seasonal decline. In the northern and eastern areas, flows continued above normal during February and began to decline in March.

Flows for April and May showed a seasonal increase in response to increased rainfall. At most index stations, the monthly means were above the long term median.

During June and July streamflow decreased seasonally and continued within the normal range for the season. Streamflows in the eastern and southern parts of the island were below the long term median.

In August, increased rainfall produced higher flows islandwide. The monthly mean discharge was 246 percent of the long term median at the Río Grande de Manatí, 194 percent of the median at the Río Fajardo station, and 162 percent of the median at the Río Inabón.

In September, flows began to decrease in the northern and eastern parts of the island, but continued to increase in the western and southern parts of the island. In general, streamflow islandwide was above the normal range.

In the U.S. Virgin Islands, precipitation and streamflow patterns generally were similar to those in Puerto Rico. Precipitation was well above normal from November to February and June to September. The highest flows were during November when rainfall was 254 percent above normal.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Table 2. Peak discharges during November 26-27 and December 6-7, 1987 and previously recorded maximum at selected streamflow gaging stations in Puerto Rico

Station number and name	Peak discharge		Maximum discharge of record (cubic feet per second)	Water Year	Period of Record
	Nov.26-27 (cubic feet per second)	Dec.6-7 (cubic feet per second)			
50051310 Río Cayaguas at Cerro Gordo	8,990	9,610	13,200	1979	10-77 to 9-88
50053050 Río Turabo at Borinquen	13,800	3,600	11,600	1985	12-83 to 9-88
50055000 Río Grande de Loíza at Caguas	28,900	28,000	71,500	1960	12-59 to 9-88
50056400 Río Valenciano near Juncos	27,500	40,000	25,700	1985	1-71 to 9-88
50056900 Quebrada Mamey near Gurabo	2,740	2,190	1,190	1985	12-83 to 9-88
50057000 Río Gurabo at Gurabo	45,000	50,600	74,600	1960	10-59 to 9-88
50061800 Río Canóvanas near Campo Rico	12,500	8,920	15,000	1982	3-67 to 9-88
50063440 Quebrada Sonadora near El Verde	635	2,230	1,410	1984	3-83 to 9-88
50063800 Río Espíritu Santo near Río Grande	9,330	20,000	12,400	1984	8-66 to 9-88
50067000 Río Sabana at Sabana	3,940	1,830	9,010	1983	10-79 to 9-88
50081000 Río Humacao at Las Piedras	6,580	20,000	20,800	1960	7-74 to 9-77 10-87 to 9-88

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

Ground-water levels in many aquifers throughout the island increased during November and December 1987 and by May, August, and September of 1988 in response to above-normal rainfall. New record-high water levels were recorded at several wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands (table 3).

Ground-water levels in wells in the north coast limestone aquifers of Puerto Rico remained practically unchanged during the first half of the water year but increased slightly in April, May and August as a result of above normal rainfall (fig. 2).

Ground-water levels in the south coast alluvial aquifers followed a cyclic pattern associated with rainfall and ground-water withdrawals for public supply, industrial, and irrigation uses. Above normal precipitation during late November and early December caused the water levels to rise significantly. Water levels increased 6.0 ft at the Alomar index well, and 9.0 ft at the Yauco PPG-4 index well. The water levels generally decreased as a result of pumpage from December to August. During late August and early September this trend was reversed as above normal rainfall returned to the area.

Ground-water levels fluctuations in the U.S. Virgin Islands (St. Thomas, St. Croix, and St. John) were similar to those in Puerto Rico. The water level in observation well 11 at Guinea Gut, on St. John Island increased 15.7 ft. during November 1987 and 10.7 ft. in September 1988 in response to above-normal precipitation, but declined during much of the intervening period (fig. 2).

Table 3. Maximum ground-water levels in 1988 water year and highest water levels of record (in feet below land-surface) at selected ground-water wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands

Well Name	Local number	Location	1988 extreme	Date	Previous extreme	Date	Period of Record
Salto 1	165	PR	44.06	09-30-88	47.62	09-30-87	1-82 to 9-88
Plazuela 2	206	PR	3.75	09-11-88	3.86	05-16-87	10-85 to 9-88
Hyde Park TW-10	221	PR	1.34	04-16-88	1.48	04-12-87	12-85 to 9-88
Yabucoa 7	96	PR	13.10	12-02-87	13.39	11-18-85	04-78 to 9-88
Aguadilla Cement	200	PR	2.24	08-25-88	2.85	05-14-87	10-85 to 9-88
Fairplains 2	2	St. Croix	20.82	01-22-88	20.91	11-27-85 11-29-85	6-83 to 9-88
Golden Grove 6	3	St. Croix	13.73	12-12-88	14.76	03-25-82	3-82 to 9-88
Concordia 14	7	St. Croix	10.76	01-19-88	12.54	06-17-87	3-82 to 9-88
Concordia 1	8	St. Croix	14.03	01-19-88	16.68	11-13 -84	3-82 to 9-88
Mahogany 16	3	St. Thomas	10.25	01-21-88	17.52	07-01-86	3-82 to 9-88

Figure 2 .--Ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Water Quality

In the 1988 water year, the U.S. Geological Survey, in cooperation with local government agencies, completed the fourth year of sampling for the constituents listed in table 4. These constituents were added to the water quality monitoring program in 1985 and are in addition to the major chemical constituents and physical properties monitored in the continuing water quality monitoring program in Puerto Rico. The highest concentration of selected constituents detected during the 1988 water year along with the station at which these concentrations were detected are summarized in table 4.

Table 4. Surface-water quality stations throughout Puerto Rico with highest concentration of selected constituents during water year 1988
[All constituent concentrations are in milligrams per liter.
MBAS: Methylene blue active substance]

Station Number	Station name	Constituent	Concentration
50035500	Río Grande de Manatí at Hwy 149 at Ciales	Sulfide	0.8
50047530	Río Hondo at Flood Channel near Cataño	Boron	.23
50091000	Río Maunabo at Maunabo	Manganese	2.2
50091000	Río Maunabo at Maunabo	Iron	47
50055250	Río Caguitas at Hwy 30 at Caguas	Zinc	.79
50055250	Río Caguitas at Hwy 30 at Caguas	Cyanide	.2
50091800	Río Chico at Providencia	Phenols	.03
50091800	Río Chico at Providencia	MBAS	3.8

The presence of high concentrations of fecal coliform (FC) and fecal streptococci (FS) bacteria continued to be the principal surface water quality problem in Puerto Rico during water year 1988. Bacteria concentration exceeding one million colonies per hundred milliliters of raw water were found at several stations including Río Piedras at Hato Rey (50049100), Quebrada Blasina near Carolina (50050300), Río Bairoa near Caguas (50055400), Río Chico at Providencia (50091800), and Río Culebrinas near Aguada (50149100). These sites are located near urban zones, industrial parks, and suburban zones and receive the effluent of the sewage treatment plants.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Four sediment stations were operated during the water year. These stations are Río Tanamá near Utuado (50028000), Río Grande de Loíza at Caguas (50055000), Río Gurabo at Gurabo (50057000), and Río Rosario near Hormigueros (50136400). Maximum sediment concentrations were 3,440 milligrams per liter (mg/L) at the Río Tanamá site, 4,880 mg/L at the Río Grande de Loíza site, 9,220 mg/L at the Río Gurabo site, and 3,380 mg/L at the Río Rosario site. Maximum sediment loads at these sites were 16,200 tons per day (ton/d) at Río Tanamá site, 227,000 (ton/d) at Río Grande de Loíza site, 686,000 (ton/d) at Río Gurabo site, and 6,160 (ton/d) at Río Rosario site.

From October 1983 to September 1986, an investigation was conducted in one of the most important basins in Puerto Rico; Río Grande de Loíza. During the study suspended-sediment samples were collected at nine stations within the basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loíza, the most important water-supply reservoir in the area. Maximum suspended-sediment concentration and load at each station are summarized in table 5.

Table 5. Maximum suspended-sediment concentration and load at each station within the Río Grande de Loíza Basin.
[--, insufficient data to establish a relation of suspended-sediment concentration and discharge.]

Station name	Station number	Maximum sediment concentration (mg/L)			Maximum sediment loads (tons per day)		
		1984	1985	1986	1984	1985	1986
Quebrada Blanca at El Jagual	50051150	--	6,720	7,320	--	25,800	15,200
Qbda. Salvatierra near San Lorenzo	50051180	2,350	2,570	2,430	15,400	15,500	12,300
Río Cayaguas at Cerro Gordo	50051310	1,400	5,180	2,790	9,840	77,800	17,900
Río Turabo near Borinquen	50053050	3,510	7,420	5,300	19,600	106,000	39,400
Río Grande de Loíza at Caguas	50055000	1,860	2,870	7,470	9,840	77,800	17,900
Quebrada Gaimito near Juncos	50055650	247	1,040	1,040	26	702	777
Río Valenciano near Juncos	50056400	593	1,580	1,600	4,990	46,300	25,100
Quebrada Mamey near Gurabo	50056900	328	528	643	224	1,060	684
Río Gurabo at Gurabo	50057000	732	1,870	1,670	7,030	93,200	60,800

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

SPECIAL NETWORKS AND PROGRAMS

National Stream Quality Accounting Network (NASQAN) is a nationwide data-collection network designed by the U.S. Geological Survey to meet many of the information needs of government agencies and other groups involved in natural or regional water-quality planning and management. The 500 or so sites on NASQAN are generally located at the downstream ends of hydrologic accounting units designated by the U.S. Geological Survey Office of Water Data Coordination in consultation with the Water Resources Council. The objectives of NASQAN are (1) to obtain information on the quality and quantity of water moving within and from the United States through a systematic and uniform process of data collection, summarization, analysis, and reporting such that the data may be used for, (2) description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of data from this and other programs, (3) detection of changes or trends with time in the pattern of occurrence of water-quality characteristics, and (4) providing a nationally consistent data base useful for water-quality assessment and hydrologic research.

EXPLANATION OF THE RECORDS

The surface-water and ground-water records published in this report are for the 1988 water year that began October 1, 1987 and ended September 30, 1988. A calendar of the water year is provided on the inside of the front cover. The records contain streamflow data, water-quality data for surface and ground water, and ground-water-level data. The locations of the stations and wells where the data were collected are shown in figures 3 to 9. The following sections of the introductory text are presented to provide users with a more detailed explanation of how the hydrologic data published in this report were collected, analyzed, computed, and arranged for presentation.

Station Identification Numbers

Each data station, whether streamsite or well, in this report is assigned a unique identification number. This number is unique in that it applies specifically to a given station and to no other. The number usually is assigned when a station is first established and is retained for that station indefinitely. The systems used by the U.S. Geological Survey to assign identification numbers for surface-water stations and for ground-water well sites differ, but both are based on geographic location. The "downstream order" system is used for regular surface-water stations and the "latitude-longitude" system is used for wells.

Figure 3.--Location of fecal coliform bacteria concentration at sampled sites.

Figure 4.--Location of fecal streptococci bacteria concentration at sampled sites.

Figure 5.--Location of continuous surface-water stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 6.--Location of water-quality stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 7.--Location of ground-water stations in Puerto Rico.

Figure 8.--Location of surface-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

Figure 9.--Location of ground-water stations in the U.S. Virgin Islands.

Downstream order system

Since October 1, 1950, the order of listing hydrologic-station records in Survey reports is in a downstream direction along the main stream. All stations on a tributary entering upstream from a main-stream station are listed before that station. A station on a tributary that enters between two main-stream stations is listed between them. A similar order is followed in listing stations in first rank, second rank, and other ranks of tributaries.

As an added means of identification, each hydrologic station and partial-record station has been assigned a station number. These are in the same downstream order used in this report. In assigning station numbers, no distinction is made between partial-record stations and other stations; therefore, the station number for a partial-record station indicates downstream order position in a list made up of both types of stations that may be established; hence, the numbers are not consecutive. The complete 8-digit number for each station such as 50028000, which appears just to the left of the station name, includes the 2-digit part number "50" plus the 6-digit downstream order number "028000."

Latitude-Longitude System

The 8-digit downstream order station numbers are not assigned to wells and miscellaneous sites where only random water-quality samples or discharge measurements are taken.

The well and miscellaneous site numbering system of the U.S. Geological Survey is based on the grid system of latitude and longitude. The system provides the geographic location of the well or miscellaneous site and a unique number for each site. The number consists of 15 digits. The first 6 digits denote the degrees, minutes, and seconds of latitude, the next 7 digits denote degrees, minutes, and seconds longitude, and the last 2 digits (assigned sequentially) identify the wells or other sites within a 1-second grid. The numbers shown in the grid correspond to the local numbers assigned to each well as visited in the field. An example is well 16 (fig. 10).

Figure 10.--Grid showing system for numbering wells and miscellaneous sites (latitude and longitude).

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988Records of Stage and Water Discharge

Records of stage and water discharge may be complete or partial. Complete records of discharge are those obtained using a continuous stage-recording device through which either instantaneous or mean daily discharges may be computed for any time, or any period of time, during the period of record. Complete records of lake or reservoir content, similarly, are those for which stage or content may be computed or estimated with reasonable accuracy for any time, or period of time. They may be obtained using a continuous stage-recording device, but need not be. Because daily mean discharges and end-of-day contents commonly are published for such stations, they are referred to as "daily stations."

By contrast, partial records are obtained through discrete measurements without using a continuous stage-recording device and pertain only to a few flow characteristics, or perhaps only one. The nature of the partial record is indicated by table titles such as "Crest-stage partial records," or "Low-flow partial records." Records of miscellaneous discharge measurements or of measurements from special studies, such as low-flow seepage studies, may be considered as partial records, but they are presented separately in this type of report. Location of all complete-record and crest-stage partial-record stations for which data are given in this report are shown in figures 5 and 8.

Data Collection and Computation

The data obtained at a complete-record gaging station on a stream or canal consists of a continuous record of stage, individual measurements of discharge throughout a range of stages, and notations regarding factors that may affect the relationships between stage and discharge. These data, together with supplemental information, such as weather records, are used to compute daily discharges. The data obtained at a complete-record gaging station on a lake or reservoir consist of a record of stage and of notations regarding factors that may affect the relationship between stage and lake content. These data are used with stage-area and stage-capacity curves or tables to compute water-surface areas and lake storage.

Continuous records of stage are obtained with analog recorders that trace continuous graphs of stage or with digital recorders that punch stage values on paper tapes at selected time intervals or electronic satellite data collector platforms that receive stage values at selected time intervals. Measurements of discharge are made with current meters using methods adapted by the Geological Survey as a result of experience accumulated since 1880. These methods are described in standard textbooks, in Water-Supply Paper 2175, and in U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations, Book 3, Chapter A6.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

In computing discharge records, results of individual measurements are plotted against the corresponding stages, and stage-discharge relation curves are then constructed. From these curves, rating tables indicating the approximate discharge for any stage within the range of the measurements are prepared. If it is necessary to define extremes of discharge outside the range of the current-meter measurements, the curves are extended using: (1) logarithmic plotting; (2) velocity-area studies; (3) results of indirect measurements of peak discharge, such as slope-area or contracted-opening measurements, and computations of flow-over-dams or weirs; or (4) step-backwater techniques.

Daily mean discharges are computed by applying the daily mean stages (gage heights) to the stage-discharge curves or tables. If the stage-discharge relation is subject to change because of frequent or continual change in the physical features that form the control, the daily mean discharge is determined by the shifting-control method, in which correction factors based on the individual discharge measurements and notes of the personnel making the measurements are applied to the gage heights before the discharges are determined from the curves or tables. This shifting-control method also is used if the stage-discharge relation is changed temporarily because of aquatic growth or debris on the control.

At some stream-gaging stations the stage-discharge relation is affected by the backwater from reservoirs, tributary streams, or other sources. This necessitates the use of the slope method in which the slope or fall in a reach of the stream is a factor in computing discharge. The slope or fall is obtained by means of an auxiliary gage set at some distance from the base gage. At some stations the stage-discharge relation is affected by changing stage; at these stations the rate of change in stage is used as a factor in computing discharge.

In computing records of lake or reservoir contents, it is necessary to have available from surveys, curves or tables defining the relationship of stage and contents. The application of stage to the stage-content curves or tables gives the contents from which daily, monthly or yearly changes then are determined. If the stage-content relationship changes because of deposition of sediment in a lake or reservoir, periodic surveys may be necessary to redefine it. Even when this is done, as time between the last survey increases, the contents computed may increase in error. Discharges over lake or reservoir spillways are computed from stage-discharge relationships much as other stream discharges are computed.

For some gaging stations there are periods when no gage-height record is obtained, or the recorded gage height is so faulty that it cannot be used to compute daily discharge or contents. This happens when the recorder stops or otherwise fails to operate properly, intakes are plugged, the float is loose in the well, or for various other reasons. For such periods, the daily

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

discharges are estimated from the recorded range in stage, previous or following record, discharge measurements, weather records, and comparison with other station records from the same or nearby basins. Likewise, daily contents may be estimated from operator's logs, previous or following record, inflow-outflow studies, and other information. Information explaining how estimated daily-discharge values are identified in station records is included in the next two sections, "Data Presentation" (REMARKS paragraph) and "Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge."

Data Presentation

The records published for each gaging station consist of two parts, the manuscript or station description and the data table for the current water year. The manuscript provides, under various headings, descriptive information, such as station location; period of record; average discharge; historical extremes; record accuracy; and other remarks pertinent to station operation and regulation. The following information, as appropriate, is provided with each continuous record of discharge or lake content. Comments to follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the station description.

LOCATION.--Information on locations is obtained from the most accurate maps available. The location of the gage with respect to the cultural and physical features in the vicinity and with respect to the reference place mentioned in the station name is given.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Drainage areas are measured using the most accurate maps available. Drainage areas are updated as better maps become available.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This indicates the period for which there are published records for the station or for an equivalent station. An equivalent station is one that was in operation at a time that the present station was not, and whose location was such that records from it can reasonable be considered equivalent with records from the present station.

REVISED RECORDS.--Published records, because of new information, occasionally are found to be incorrect, and revisions are printed in later reports. Listed under this heading are all the reports in which revisions have been published for the station and the water years to which the revisions apply. If a revision did not include daily, monthly, or annual figures of discharge, that fact is noted after the year dates as follows: "(M)" means that only the instantaneous maximum discharge was revised; "(m)" that only the instantaneous minimum was revised; and "(P)" that only peak discharges were revised. If the drainage area has been revised, the report in which the most recently revised figure was first published is given.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

GAGE.--The type of gage in current use, the datum of the current gage, and a condensed history of the types, locations, and datums of previous gages are given under this heading.

REMARKS.--All periods of estimated daily-discharge record will either be identified by date in this paragraph of the station description for water-discharge stations or flagged in the daily-discharge table. (See next section, "Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge.") If a remarks statement is used to identify estimated record, the paragraph will begin with this information presented as the first entry. The paragraph is also used to present information relative to the accuracy of the records, to special methods of computations, to conditions that affect natural flow at the station and, possibly, to other pertinent items. For reservoir stations, information is given on the dam forming the reservoir, the capacity, outlet works and spillway, and purpose and use of the reservoir.

COOPERATION.--Records provided by a cooperating organization or obtained for the Geological Survey by a cooperating organization are identified here.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--The discharge value given is the arithmetic mean of the water-year mean discharges. It is computed only for stations having at least 5 water years of complete record, and only water years of complete record are included in the computation. It is not computed for stations where diversions, storage, or other water-use practices cause the value to be meaningless. If water developments significantly altering flow at a station are put into use after the station has been in operation for a period of years, a new average is computed as soon as 5 water years of record have accumulated following the development. The median of yearly mean discharges also is given under this heading for stations having 10 or more water years of record, if the median differs from the average given by more than 10 percent.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Extremes may include maximum and minimum stages and maximum and minimum discharges or content. Unless otherwise qualified, the maximum discharge or content is the instantaneous maximum corresponding to the highest stage that occurred. The highest stage may have been obtained from a graphic or digital recorder, a crest-stage gage, or by direct observation of a nonrecording gage. If the maximum stage did not occur on the same day as the maximum discharge or content, it is given separately. Similarly, the minimum is the instantaneous minimum discharge, unless otherwise qualified, and was determined and is reported in the same manner as the maximum.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Included here is information concerning major floods or unusually low flows that occurred outside the stated period of record. The information may or may not have been obtained by the U.S. Geological Survey.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Extremes given here are similar to those for the period of record, except the peak discharge listing may include secondary peaks. For stations meeting certain criteria, all peak discharges and stages occurring during the water year and greater than a selected base discharge are presented under this heading. The peaks greater than the base discharge, excluding the highest one, are referred to as secondary peaks. Peak discharges are not published for canals, ditches, drains, or streams for which the peaks are subject to substantial control by man. The time of occurrence for peaks is expressed in 24-hour local standard time. For example, 12:30 a.m. is 0030, and 1:30 p.m. is 1330. The minimum for the current water year appears below the table of peak data.

REVISIONS.--If a critical error in published records is discovered, a revision is included in the first report published following discovery of the error.

Although rare, occasionally the records of a discontinued gaging station may need revision. Because, for these stations, there would be no current or, possibly, future station manuscript published to document the revision in a "Revised Records" entry, users of data for these stations who obtained the record from previously published data reports may wish to contact the District office to determine if the published records were ever revised after the station was discontinued. Of course, if the data were obtained by computer retrieval, the data would be current and there would be no need to check because any published revision of data is always accompanied by revision of the corresponding data in computer storage.

Manuscript information for lake or reservoir stations differs from that for stream stations in the nature of the "Remarks" and in the inclusion of a skeleton stage-capacity table when daily contents are given.

The daily table for stream-gaging stations gives mean discharge for each day and is followed by monthly and yearly summaries. In the monthly summary below the daily table, the line headed "TOTAL" gives the sum of the daily figures. The line headed "MEAN" gives the average flow in cubic feet per second during the month. The lines headed "MAX" and "MIN" give the maximum and minimum daily discharges, respectively, for the month. Discharge for the month also is usually expressed in cubic feet per second per square mile (line headed "CFSM"), or in inches (line headed "IN."), or in acre-feet (line headed "AC-FT"). Figures for cubic feet per second per square mile and runoff in inches are omitted if there is extensive regulations or diversion or if the drainage area includes large noncontributing areas. In the yearly summary below the monthly summary, the figures shown are the appropriate discharges for the calendar and water years.

Data collected at partial-record stations follow the information for continuous-record sites. Data for partial-record discharge stations are presented in two tables. The first is a table of annual maximum stage and discharge at crest-stage stations, and the second is a table of discharge measurements at low-flow partial-record stations.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Identifying Estimated Daily Discharge

Estimated daily-discharge values published in the water-discharge tables are identified by flagging individual daily values with the letter symbol "e" and printing a table footnote, "e Estimated."

Accuracy of the Records

The accuracy of streamflow records depends primarily on: (1) The stability of the stage-discharge relation or, if the control is unstable, the frequency of discharge measurements; and (2) the accuracy of measurements of stage, measurements of discharge, and interpretation of records.

The accuracy attributed to the records is indicated under "REMARKS." "Excellent" means that about 95 percent of the daily discharges are within 5 percent of the true; "good," within 10 percent; and "fair," within 15 percent. Records that do not meet the criteria mentioned, are rated "poor." Different accuracies may be attributed to different parts of a given record.

Daily mean discharges in this report are given to the nearest hundredth of a cubic foot per second for values less than 1 ft³/s; to the nearest tenth between 1.0 and 10 ft³/s; to whole numbers between 10 and 1,000 ft³/s; and to 3 significant figures for more than 1,000 ft³/s. The number of significant figures used is based solely on the magnitude of the discharge value. The same rounding rules apply to discharges listed for partial-record stations and miscellaneous sites.

Information used in the preparation of the records in this publication, such as discharge-measurement notes, gage-height records, temperature measurements, and rating tables are on file in the Caribbean District office. Also, most of the daily mean discharges are in computer-readable form and have been analyzed statistically. Information on the availability of the unpublished information or on the results of statistical analyses of the published records may be obtained from the District office.

Records of Surface-Water Quality

Records of surface-water quality ordinarily are obtained at or near stream-gaging stations because interpretation of records of surface-water quality nearly always requires corresponding discharge data. Records of surface-water quality in this report may involve a variety of types of data and measurement frequencies.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Classification of Records

Water-quality data for surface-water sites are grouped into one of three classifications. A continuing-record station is a site where data are collected on a regularly scheduled basis. Frequency may be once or more times daily, weekly, monthly, or quarterly. A partial-record station is a site where limited water-quality data are collected systematically over a period of years. Frequency of sampling is usually less than quarterly. A miscellaneous sampling site is a location other than a continuing or partial-record station, where random samples are collected to give better areal coverage to define water-quality conditions in the river basin.

A careful distinction needs to be made between "continuing records" as used in this report and "continuous recordings," which refers to a continuous graph or a series of discrete values punched at short intervals on a paper tape. Some records of water quality, such as temperature and specific conductance, may be obtained through continuous recordings; however, because of costs, most data are obtained only monthly or less frequently. Locations of stations for which records on the quality of surface water appear in this report are shown in figure 6.

Arrangement of Records

Water-quality records collected at a surface-water daily record station are published immediately following that record, regardless of the frequency of sample collection. Station number and name are the same for both records. Where a surface-water daily record station is not available or where the water quality differs significantly from that at the nearby surface-water station, the continuing water-quality record is published with its own station number and name in the regular downstream-order sequence. Water-quality data for partial-record stations and for miscellaneous sampling sites appear in separate tables following the table of discharge measurement at miscellaneous sites.

On-site Measurements and Sample Collection

In obtaining water-quality data, a major concern needs to be assuring that the data obtained represent the in situ quality of the water. To assure this, certain measurements, such as water temperature, pH, and dissolved oxygen, need to be made onsite when the samples are taken. To assure that measurements made in the laboratory also represent the in situ water, carefully prescribed procedures need to be followed in collecting the samples, in treating the samples to prevent changes in quality pending analysis, and in shipping the samples to the laboratory. Procedures for onsite measurements and for collecting, treating, and shipping samples are given in publications on "Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations," Book 1, Chap. D2; Book 3, Chap. C2; Book 5, Chap. A1, A3, and A4. Detailed information on collecting, treating, and shipping samples may be obtained from the Geological Survey District office.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

One sample can define adequately the water quality at a given time if the mixture of solutes throughout the stream cross section is homogeneous. However, the concentration of solutes at different locations in the cross section may vary widely with different rates of water discharge, depending on the source of material and the turbulence and mixing of the stream. Some streams must be sampled through several vertical sections to obtain a representative sample needed for an accurate mean concentration and for use in calculating load. All samples obtained for the National Stream Quality Accounting Network (see definitions) are obtained from at least several verticals. Whether samples are obtained from the centroid of flow or from several verticals, depends on flow conditions and other factors which must be evaluated by the collector.

Chemical-quality data published in this report are considered to be the most representative values available for the stations listed. The values reported represent water-quality conditions at the time of sampling as much as possible, consistent with available sampling techniques and methods of analysis. In the rare case where an apparent inconsistency exists between a reported pH value and the relative abundance of carbon dioxide species (carbonate and bicarbonate), the inconsistency is the result of a slight uptake of carbon dioxide from the air by the sample between measurement of pH in the field and determination of carbonate and bicarbonate in the laboratory.

For chemical-quality stations equipped with digital monitors, the records consist of daily maximum, minimum, and mean values for each constituent measured and are based upon hourly punches beginning at 0100 hours and ending at 2400 hours for the day of record. More detailed records, when available, (hourly values) may be obtained from the U.S.G.S. District office whose address is given on the back of the title page of this report.

Water Temperature

Water temperatures are measured at most of the water-quality stations. In addition, water temperatures are taken at time of discharge measurements for water-discharge stations. For stations where water temperatures are taken manually once or twice daily, the water temperatures are taken at about the same time each day. Large streams have a small diurnal temperature change; shallow streams may have a daily range of several degrees and may follow closely the changes in air temperature. Some streams may be affected by waste-heat discharges.

At stations where recording instruments are used, either mean temperatures or maximum and minimum temperatures for each day are published. Water temperatures measured at the time of water-discharge measurements are on file in the District office.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Sediment

Suspended-sediment concentrations are determined from samples collected by using depth-integrating samplers. Samples usually are obtained at several verticals in the cross section, or a single sample may be obtained at a fixed point and a coefficient applied to determine the mean concentration in the cross sections.

During periods of rapidly changing flow or rapidly changing concentration, samples may have been collected more frequently (twice daily or, in some instances, hourly). The published sediment discharges for days of rapidly changing flow or concentration were computed by the subdivided-day method (time-discharge weighted average). Therefore, for those days when the published sediment discharge value differs from the value computed as the product of discharge times mean concentration times 0.0027, the reader can assume that the sediment discharge for that day was computed by the subdivided-day method. For periods when no samples were collected, daily discharges of suspended sediment were estimated on the basis of water discharge, sediment concentrations observed immediately before and after the periods, and suspended-sediment loads for other periods of similar discharge.

At other stations, suspended-sediment samples were collected periodically at many verticals in the stream cross section. Although data collected periodically may represent conditions only at the time of observations, such data are useful in establishing seasonal relations between quality and stream-flow and in predicting long-term sediment-discharge characteristics of the stream.

In addition to the records of suspended-sediment discharge, records of the periodic measurements of the particle-size distribution of the suspended sediment and bed material are included for some stations.

Laboratory Measurements

Sediment samples, samples for biochemical-oxygen demand (BOD), samples for indicator bacteria, and daily samples for specific conductance are analyzed locally. All other samples are analyzed in the Geological Survey laboratories in Denver, Co. or Ocala, Fla. Methods used in analyzing sediment samples and computing sediment records are given in TWRI, Book 5, Chap. C1. Methods used by the Geological Survey laboratories are given in TWRI, Book 1, Chap. D2; Book 3, Chap. C2; Book 5, Chap. A1, A3, and A4.

Data Presentation

For continuing-record stations, information pertinent to the history of station operation is provided in descriptive headings preceding the tabular data. These descriptive headings give details regarding location, drainage area, period of record, type of data available, instrumentation, general remarks, cooperation, and extremes for parameters currently measured daily. Tables of chemical, physical, biological, radiochemical data, and so forth, obtained at a frequency less than daily are presented first, and tables of "daily values" of specific conductance, pH, water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and suspended sediment then follow in sequence, when these parameters are studied.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

In the descriptive headings, if the location is identical to that of the discharge gaging station, neither the LOCATION nor the DRAINAGE AREA statements are repeated. The following information, as appropriate, is provided with each continuous-record station. Comments that follow clarify information presented under the various headings of the station description.

LOCATION.--See Data Presentation under "Records of Stage and Water Discharge;" same comments apply.

DRAINAGE AREA.--See Data Presentation under "Records of Stage and Water Discharge;" same comments apply.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This indicates the periods for which there are published water-quality records for the station. The periods are shown separately for records of parameters measured daily or continuously and those measured less than daily. For those measured daily or continuously, periods of record are given for the parameters individually.

INSTRUMENTATION.--Information on instrumentation is given only if a water-quality monitor temperature record, sediment pumping sampler, or other sampling device is in operation at a station.

REMARKS.--Remarks provide added information pertinent to the collection, analysis, or computation of the records.

COOPERATION.--Records provided by a cooperating organization or obtained for the Geological Survey by a cooperating organization are identified here.

EXTREMES.--Maximums and minimums are given only for parameters measured daily or more frequently. None are given for parameters measured weekly or less frequently, because the true maximums or minimums may not have been sampled. Extremes, when given, are provided for both the period of record and for the current water year.

REVISIONS.--If errors in published water-quality records are discovered after publication, appropriate updates are made to the Water-Quality File in the U.S. Geological Survey's computerized data system, WATSTORE, and subsequently by monthly transfer of update transactions to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's STORET system. Because the usual volume of updates makes it impractical to document individual changes in the State data-report series or elsewhere, potential users of U.S. Geological Survey water-quality data are encouraged to obtain all required data from the appropriate computer file to insure the most recent updates.

The surface-water-quality records for partial-record stations and miscellaneous sampling sites are published in separate tables following the table of discharge measurements at miscellaneous sites. No descriptive statements are given for these records. Each station is published with its own station number and name in the regular downstream-order sequence.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Remark Codes

The following remark codes may appear with the water-quality data in this report:

<u>PRINTED OUTPUT</u>	<u>REMARK</u>
E	Estimated value
>	Actual value is known to be greater than the value shown
<	Actual value is known to be less than the value shown
K	Results based on colony count outside the acceptance range (non-ideal colony count)
L	Biological organism count less than 0.5 percent (organism may be observed rather than counted)
D	Biological organism count equal to or greater than 15 percent (dominant)
&	Biological organism estimated as dominant

Records of Ground-Water Levels

Only ground-water level data from a basic network of observation wells are published herein. This basic network contains observation wells so located that the most significant data are obtained from the fewest wells in the most important aquifers.

Data Collection and Computation

Measurements of water levels are made in many types of wells under varying conditions, but the methods of measurement are standardized to the extent possible. The equipment and measuring techniques used at each observation well ensure that measurements at each well are of consistent accuracy and reliability.

Each well is identified by means of (1) a 15-digit number that is based on latitude and longitude and (2) a local number that is provided for local needs. See figure 10.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Water-level records are obtained from direct measurements with a steel tape or from the graph or punched tape of a water-stage recorder. The water-level measurements in this report are given in feet with reference to land-surface datum (lsd). Land-surface datum is a datum plane that is approximately at land surface at each well. If known, the elevation of the land-surface datum is given in the well description. The height of the measuring point (MP) above or below land-surface datum is given in each well description. Water levels in wells equipped with recording gages are reported for every day and as an instantaneous observation at noon.

Water levels are reported to as many significant figures as can be justified by the local conditions. For example, in a measurement of a depth to water of several hundred feet, the error of determining the absolute value of the total depth to water may be a few tenths of a foot, whereas the error in determining the net change of water level between successive measurements may be only a hundredth of a few hundredths of a foot. For lesser depths to water, the accuracy is greater. Accordingly, most measurements reported to a hundredth of a foot, but some are given to a tenth of a foot or a larger unit.

Data Presentation

Each well record consists of two parts, the station description and the data table of water levels observed during the water year. The description of the well is presented first through use of descriptive headings preceding the tabular data. The comments to follow clarify information presented under the various headings.

LOCATION.--This paragraph follows the well-identification number and reports the latitude and longitude (given in degrees, minutes, and seconds); a landline location designation; the hydrologic-unit number; the distance and direction from a geographic point of reference; and the owner's name.

AQUIFER.--This entry designates by name (if a name exists) and geologic age the aquifer(s) open to the well.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--This entry describes the well in terms of depth, diameter, casing depth and/or screened interval, method of construction, use, and additional information such as casing breaks, collapsed screen, and other changes since construction.

DATUM.--This entry describes both the measuring point and the land-surface elevation at the well. The measuring point is described physically (such as top of collar, notch in top of casing, plug in pump base and so on), and in relation to land surface (such as 1.3 ft above land-surface datum). The elevation of the land-surface datum is described in feet above mean sea level datum, if available. It is reported with precision depending on the method of determination.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

REMARKS.--This entry describes factors that may influence the water level in a well or the measurement of the water level. It should identify wells that also are water-quality observation wells, and may be used to acknowledge the assistance of local (non-survey) observers.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--This entry indicates the period for which there are published records for the well. It reports the month and year of the start of publication of water-level records by the U.S. Geological Survey and the words "to current year" if the records are to be continued into the following year. Periods for which water-level records are available, but are not published by the Geological Survey, may be noted.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--This entry contains the highest and lowest water levels of the period of published record, with respect to land-surface datum, and the dates of their occurrence.

A table of water levels follows the station description for each well. Water levels are reported in feet below land-surface datum and all taped measurements of water level are listed. For wells equipped with recorders, daily values tables are published for the instantaneous water-level observation at noon. The highest and lowest water levels of the water year are shown on a line below the table. Because all values are not published for wells with recorders, the extremes may be values that are not listed in the table. Missing records are indicated by dashes in place of the water level.

Records of Ground-Water Quality

Records of ground-water quality in this type of report differ from other types of records in that for most sampling sites they consist of only one set of measurements for the water year. The quality of ground water ordinarily changes only slowly; therefore, for most general purposes one annual sampling, or only a few samples taken at infrequent intervals during the year, is sufficient. Frequent measurement of the same constituents is not necessary unless one is concerned with a particular problem, such as monitoring for trends in nitrate concentration. In the special cases where the quality of ground water may change more rapidly, more frequent measurements are made to identify the nature of the changes.

Data Collection and Computation

The records of ground-water quality in this report were obtained mostly as a part of special studies in specific areas. Consequently, a number of chemical analyses are presented for some counties but none are presented for others. As a result, the records for this year, by themselves, do not provide a balanced view of ground-water quality Statewide. Such a view can be attained only by considering records for this year in context with similar records obtained for these and other counties in earlier years.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Most methods for collecting and analyzing water samples are described in the "U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations" manuals listed on a following page. The values reported in this type of report represent water-quality conditions at the time of sampling as much as possible, consistent with available sampling techniques and methods of analysis. All samples are obtained by trained personnel. The wells sampled are pumped long enough to assure that the water collected comes directly from the aquifer and has not stood for a long time in the well casing where it would have been exposed to the atmosphere and to the material, possibly metal, comprising the casings.

Data Presentation

The records of ground-water quality, when available, are published in a section titled QUALITY OF GROUND WATER immediately following the ground-water level records. Data for quality of ground water are listed alphabetically by County, and are identified by well number. The prime identification number for wells sampled is the 15-digit number derived from the latitude-longitude locations. No descriptive statements are given for ground-water-quality records; however, the well number, depth of well, date of sampling, and other pertinent data are given in the table containing the chemical analyses of the ground water. The REMARK codes listed for surface-water-quality records are also applicable to ground-water-quality records.

ACCESS TO WATSTORE DATA

The National WATER Data STORAGE and RETRIEVAL System (WATSTORE) was established for handling water data collected through the activities of the U.S. Geological Survey and to provide for more effective and efficient means of releasing the data to the public. The system is operated and maintained on the central computer facilities of the Survey at its National Center in Reston, Virginia.

WATSTORE can provide a variety of useful products ranging from simple data tables to complex statistical analyses. A minimal fee, plus the actual computer cost incurred in producing a desired product, is charged to the requester. Information about the availability of specific types of data, the acquisition of data or products, and user charges can be obtained locally from each of the Water Resources Division's District offices (see address given on the back of the title page).

General inquiries about WATSTORE may be directed to:

Chief Hydrologist
U.S. Geological Survey
437 National Center
Reston, Virginia 22092

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Terms related to streamflow, water-quality, and other hydrologic data as used in this report, are defined below. See also the table for converting inch-pound units to the International System of units (SI) on the inside of the back cover.

Acre-foot (AC-FT, acre-ft) is the quantity of water required to cover 1 acre to a depth of 1 foot and is equal to about 326,000 gallons or 1,233 cubic meters.

Adenosine triphosphate (ATP) is an organic, phosphate-rich, compound important in the transfer of energy in organisms. Its central role in living cells makes it an excellent indicator of the presence of living material in water. A measure of ATP therefore provides a sensitive and rapid estimate of biomass. ATP is reported in micrograms per liter of the original water sample.

Algae growth potential (AGP) is the maximum algal dry weight biomass that can be produced in a natural water sample under standardized laboratory conditions. The growth potential is the algal biomass present a stationary phase and is expressed as milligrams dry weight of algae produced per liter of sample.

Aquifer is a geologic formation, group of formations, or part of a formation that contains sufficient saturated permeable material to yield significant quantities of water to wells and springs.

Artesian means confined and is used to describe a well in which the water level stands above the top of the aquifer, tapped by the well. A flowing artesian well is one in which the water level is above the land surface.

Bacteria are microscopic unicellular organisms, typically spherical, rodlike, or spiral and threadlike in shape, often clumped into colonies. Some bacteria cause disease, while others perform an essential role in nature in the recycling of materials; for example, by decomposing organic matter into a form available for reuse by plants.

Total coliform bacteria are a particular group of bacteria that are used as indicators of possible sewage pollution. They are characterized as aerobic or facultative anaerobic, gram-negative, nonspore-forming, rod-shaped bacteria which ferment lactose with gas formation within 48 hours at 35°C. In the laboratory these bacteria are defined as all the organisms which produce colonies with a golden-green metallic sheen within 24 hours when incubated at 35°C ± 1.0°C on M-Endo medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Fecal coliform bacteria are bacteria that are present in the intestines or feces of warm-blooded animals. They are often used as indicators of the sanitary quality of the water. In the laboratory they are defined as all organisms which produce blue colonies within 24 hours when incubated at $44.5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ on M-FC medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Fecal streptococcal bacteria are bacteria found also in intestines of warm-blooded animals. Their presence in water is considered to verify fecal pollution. They are characterized as Gram-positive, cocci bacteria which are capable of growth in brain-heart infusion broth. In the laboratory they are defined as all the organisms which produce red or pink colonies within 48 hours at $35^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ on KF-streptococcus medium (nutrient medium for bacterial growth). Their concentrations are expressed as number of colonies per 100 mL of sample.

Bed material is the unconsolidated material of which a streambed, lake, pond, reservoir, or estuary bottom is composed.

Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is a measure of the quantity of dissolved oxygen, in milligrams per liter, necessary for the decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms, such as bacteria.

Biomass is the amount of living matter present at any given time, expressed as the mass per unit area or volume of habitat.

Ash mass is the mass or amount of residue present after the residue from the dry mass determination has been ashed in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 500°C for 1 hour. The ash mass values of zooplankton and phytoplankton are expressed in grams per cubic meter (g/m^3), and periphyton and benthic organisms in grams per square meter (g/m^2).

Dry mass refers to the mass of residue present after drying in an oven at 105°C for zooplankton and periphyton, until the mass remains unchanged. This mass represents the total organic matter, ash and sediment, in the sample. Dry-mass values are expressed in the same units as ash mass.

Organic mass or volatile mass of the living substance is the difference between the dry mass and the ash mass and represents the actual matter. The organic mass is expressed in the same units as for ash and dry mass.

Wet mass is the mass of living matter plus contained water.

Bottom material: See Bed material.

Cells/volume refers to the number of cells of any organism which is counted by using a microscope and grid or counting cell. Many planktonic organisms are multicelled and are counted according to the number of contained cells per sample, usually milliliters (mL) or liters (L).

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Chemical oxygen demand (COD) is a measure of the chemically oxidizable material in the water, and furnishes an approximation of the amount of organic and reducing material present. The determined value may correlate with natural water color or with carbonaceous organic pollution from sewage or industrial wastes.

Chlorophyll refers to the green pigments of plants. Chlorophyll a and b are the two most common green pigments in plants.

Color unit is produced by one milligram per liter of platinum in the form of the chloroplatinate ion. Color is expressed in units of the platinum-cobalt scale.

Contents is the volume of water in a reservoir or lake. Unless otherwise indicated, volume is computed on the basis of a level pool and does not include bank storage.

Control designates a feature downstream from the gage that determines the stage-discharge relation at the gage. This feature may be a natural constriction of the channel, an artificial structure, or a uniform cross section over a long reach of the channel.

Control structure as used in this report is a structure on a stream or canal that is used to regulate the flow or stage of the stream or to prevent the intrusion of salt water.

Crest-stage station is a special form of partial-record station that records the highest stage of the stream that occurred between periodic visits to the station. A stage-discharge relation for each gage may be developed from discharge measurements made by indirect methods or by current meter.

Cubic foot per second (cfs) is the rate of discharge representing a volume of 1 cubic foot passing a given point during 1 second and is equivalent to 7.48 gallons per second or 448.8 gallons per minute or 0.02832 cubic meters per second.

Cubic foot per second-day (cfs-day) is the volume of water represented by a flow of 1 cubic foot per second for 24 hours. It is equivalent to 86,400 cubic feet, approximately 1.9835 acre-feet, about 646,000 gallons, or 2,445 cubic meters.

Cubic feet per second per square mile (CFSM) is the average number of cubic feet of water flowing per second from each square mile of area drained, assuming that the runoff is distributed uniformly in time and area.

Discharge is the volume of water (or more broadly, volume of fluid plus suspended sediment), that passes a given point within a given period of time.

Instantaneous discharge is the discharge at a particular instant of time.

Mean discharge (MEAN) is the arithmetic mean of individual daily mean discharges during a specific period.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Dissolved refers to that material in a representative water sample which passes through a 0.45 um membrane filter. This is a convenient operational definition used by Federal agencies that collect water data. Determinations of "dissolved" constituents are made on subsamples of the filtrate.

Dissolved-solids concentration of water is determined either analytically by the "residue-on-evaporation" method, or mathematically by totaling the concentrations of individual constituents reported in a comprehensive chemical analysis. During the analytical determination of dissolved solids, the bicarbonate (generally a major dissolved component of water) is converted to carbonate. Therefore, in the mathematical calculations of dissolved-solids concentration, the bicarbonate value, in milligrams per liter, is multiplied by 0.492 to reflect the change.

Diversity index is a numerical expression of evenness of distribution of aquatic organisms. The formula for diversity index is:

$$\bar{d} = - \sum_{i=1}^s \frac{n_i}{n} \log_2 \frac{n_i}{n}$$

Where n_i is the number of individuals per taxon, n is the total number of individuals, and s is the total number of taxa in the sample of the community. Diversity index values range from zero, when all the organisms in the sample are the same, to some positive number, when some or all of the organisms in the sample are different.

Drainage area of a stream at a specified location is that area, measured in a horizontal plane, enclosed by a topographic divide from which direct surface runoff from precipitation normally drains by gravity into the stream above the specified point. Figures of drainage area given herein include all closed basins, or noncontribution areas, within the area unless otherwise noted.

Drainage basin is a part of the surface of the earth that is occupied by a drainage system, which consists of a surface stream or a body of impounded surface water together with all tributary surface streams and bodies of impounded surface water.

Gage height (G.H.) is the water-surface elevation referred to some arbitrary gage datum. Gage height is often used interchangeably with the more general term "stage," although gage height is more appropriate when used with a reading on a gage.

Gaging station is a particular site on a stream, canal, lake, or reservoir where systematic observations of hydrologic data are obtained.

Ground-water station is a well at which observations of ground-water level are made, either continuously by recorder, or periodically by hand. In addition, various chemical or physical parameters may be obtained, usually on a periodic basis.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Hardness of water is a physical-chemical characteristic that is commonly recognized by the increased quantity of soap required to produce lather. It is attributable to the presence of alkaline earths (principally calcium and magnesium) and is expressed as equivalent calcium carbonate (CaCO_3).

Hydrologic Bench-Mark Network is a network in small drainage basins around the country whose purpose is to provide consistent data on the hydrology, including water quality, and related factors in representative undeveloped watersheds nationwide, and to provide analyses on a continuing basis to compare and contrast conditions observed in basins more obviously affected by the activities of man.

Hydrologic unit is a geographic area representing part or all of a surface drainage basin or distinct hydrologic feature as delineated by the Office of Water Data Coordination on the State Hydrologic Unit Maps; each hydrologic unit is identified by an eight-digit number.

Land-surface datum (lsd) is a datum plane that is approximately at land surface at each ground-water observation well.

Measuring point (MP) is an arbitrary permanent reference point from which the distance to the water surface in a well is measured to obtain the water level.

Metamorphic stage refers to the stage of development that an organism exhibits during its transformation from an immature form to an adult form. This developmental process exists for most insects, and the degree of difference from the immature stage to the adult form varies from relatively slight to pronounced, with many intermediates. Examples of metamorphic stages of insects are egg-larva-adult or egg-nymph-adult.

Methylene blue active substances (MBAS) are apparent detergents. The determination depends on the formation of a blue color when methylene blue dye reacts with synthetic anionic detergent compounds.

Micrograms per gram ($\mu\text{g/g}$) is a unit expressing the concentration of a chemical element as the mass (micrograms) of the element per unit mass (gram) of material analyzed.

Micrograms per liter ($\mu\text{g/L}$, ug/L) is a unit expressing the concentration of chemical constituents in solution as mass (micrograms) of solute per unit volume (liter) of water. One thousand micrograms per liter is equivalent to one milligram per liter.

Milligrams per liter (MG/L , mg/L) is a unit for expressing the concentration of chemical constituents in solution. Milligrams per liter represent the mass of solute per unit volume (liter) of water. Concentration of suspended sediment also is expressed in mg/L , and is based on the mass of sediment per liter of water-sediment mixture. Conversion of chemical concentrations in Mg/L to milliequivalents per liter can be done by using the factors in table 6.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Table 6. Factors for conversion of chemical constituents in milligrams per liter to milliequivalents per liter.

<u>Ion</u>	<u>Multiply by</u>	<u>Ion</u>	<u>Multiply by</u>
Aluminum (Al+3)*.....	0.11119	Iodide (I-1).....	0.00788
Ammonia as NH ₄ +1.....	.05544	Iron (Fe+3).....	.05372
Barium (Ba+2).....	.01456	Lead (Pb+2).....	.00965
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ -1)....	.01639	Lithium (Li+1).....	.14411
Bromide (Br-1).....	.01251	Magnesium (Mg+2)....	.08226
Calcium (Ca+2).....	.04990	Manganese (Mn+2)*...	.03640
Carbonate (CO ₃ -2).....	.03333	Nickel (Ni+2).....	.03406
Chloride (Cl-1).....	.02821	Nitrate (NO ₃ -1)....	.01613
Chromium (Cr+6)*.....	.11539	Nitrite (NO ₂ -1)....	.02174
Cobalt (Co+2)*.....	.03394	Phosphate (PO ₄ -3)...	.03159
Copper (Cu+2)*.....	.03148	Potassium (K+1).....	.02557
Cyanide (CN-1).....	.03844	Sodium (Na+1).....	.04350
Fluoride (F-1).....	.05264	Strontium (Sr+2)....	.02283
Hydrogen (H+1).....	.99209	Sulfate (SO ₄ -2)....	.02082
Hydroxide (OH-1).....	.05880	Zinc (Zn+2)*.....	.03060

*Constituent reported in micrograms per liter; multiply by factor and divide results by 1,000.

National Stream Quality Accounting Network (NASQAN) is a nationwide data-collection network designed by the U.S. Geological Survey to meet many of the information needs of government agencies and other groups involved in natural or regional water-quality planning and management. The 500 or so sites in NASQAN are generally located at the downstream ends of hydrologic accounting units designated by the U.S. Geological Survey office of Water Data Coordination in consultation with the Water Resources Council. The objectives of NASQAN are (1) to obtain information on the quality and quantity of water moving within and from the United States through a systematic and uniform process of data collection, summarization, analysis, and reporting such that the data may be used for, (2) description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of description of the areal variability of water quality in the Nation's rivers through analysis of data from this and other programs, (3) detection of changes or trends with time in the pattern of occurrence of water-quality characteristics, and (4) providing a nationally consistent data base useful for water-quality assessment and hydrologic research.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

National Trends Network (NTN) is a network for sampling atmospheric deposition in the United States. The purpose of the network is to determine the variability, both in location and in time, of the composition of atmospheric deposition, which includes snow, rain, dust particles, aerosols, and gases. The core from which the NTN was built was the already-existing deposition-monitoring network of the National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP).

Organism is any living entity.

Organism count/area refers to the number of organisms collected and enumerated in a sample and adjusted to the number per unit area habitat, usually square meters (m²), acres, or hectare. Periphyton, benthic organisms, and macrophytes are expressed in these terms.

Organism count/volume refers to the number of organisms collected and enumerated in a sample and adjusted to the number per sample volume, usually milliliters (mL) or liters (L). Numbers of planktonic organisms can be expressed in these terms.

Total organism count is the total number of organisms collected and enumerated in any particular sample.

Parameter Code is a 5-digit number used in the U.S. Geological Survey computerized data system, WATSTORE, to uniquely identify a specific constituent. The codes used in WATSTORE are the same as those used in the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency data system, STORET. The Environmental Protection Agency assigns and approves all requests for new codes.

Partial-record station is a particular site where limited streamflow and/or water-quality data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrologic analyses.

Particle-size is the diameter, in millimeters (mm), of a particle determined by either sieve or sedimentation methods. Sedimentation methods (pipet, bottom-withdrawal tube, visual-accumulation tube) determine fall diameter of particles in either distilled water (chemically dispersed) or in native water (the river water at the time and point of sampling).

Particle-size classification used in this report agrees with recommendations made by the American Geophysical Union Subcommittee on Sediment Terminology. The classification is as follows:

<u>Classification</u>	<u>Size (mm)</u>	<u>Method of analysis</u>
Clay.....	0.00024 - 0.004	Sedimentation
Silt.....	.004 - .062	Sedimentation
Sand.....	.062 - 2.0	Sedimentation or sieve
Gravel....	2.0 - 64.0	Sieve

The particle-size distributions given in this report are not necessarily representative of all particles in transport in the stream. Most of the organic matter is removed and the sample is subjected to mechanical and chemical dispersion before analysis in distilled water. Chemical dispersion is not used for native water analysis.

Percent composition is a unit for expressing the ratio of a particular part of a sample or population to the total sample or population, in terms of types, numbers, mass or volume.

Periphyton is the assemblage of microorganisms attached to and living upon submerged solid surfaces. While primarily consisting of algae, they also include bacteria, fungi, protozoa, rotifers, and other small organisms.

Pesticides are chemical compounds used to control undesirable organisms. Major categories of pesticides include insecticides, miticides, fungicides, herbicides, and rodenticides.

Picocurie (PC, pCi) is one trillionth (1×10^{-12}) of the amount of radioactivity represented by a curie (Ci). A curie is the amount of radioactivity that yields 3.7×10^{10} radioactive disintegrations per second. A picocurie yields 2.22 dpm (disintegrations per minute).

Plankton is the community of suspended, floating, or weakly swimming organisms that live in the open water of lakes and rivers.

Phytoplankton is the plant part of the plankton. They are usually microscopic and their movement is subject to the water currents. Phytoplankton growth is dependent upon solar radiation and nutrient substances. Because they are able to incorporate as well as release materials to the surrounding water, the phytoplankton have a profound effect upon the quality of the water. They are the primary food producers in the aquatic environment, and are commonly known as algae.

Blue-green algae are a group of phytoplankton organisms having a blue pigment, in addition to the green pigment called chlorophyll. Blue-green algae often cause nuisance conditions in water.

Diatoms are the unicellular or colonial algae having a siliceous shell. Their concentrations are expressed as number of cells per milliliter (cells/mL) of sample.

Green algae have chlorophyll pigments similar in color to those of higher green plants. Some forms produce algae mats or floating "moss" in lakes. Their concentrations are expressed as number of cells per milliliter (cells/mL) of sample.

Zooplankton is the animal part of the plankton. Zooplankton are capable of extensive movements within the water column and are often large enough to be seen with the unaided eye. Zooplankton are secondary consumers feeding upon bacteria, phytoplankton, and detritus. Because they are the grazers in the aquatic environment, the zooplankton are a vital part of the aquatic food web. The zooplankton community is dominated by small crustaceans and rotifers.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Primary productivity is a measure of the rate at which new organic matter is formed and accumulated through photosynthetic and chemosynthetic activity of producer organisms (chiefly, green plants). The rate of primary production is estimated by measuring the amount of oxygen released (oxygen method) or the amount of carbon assimilated by the plants (carbon method).

Milligrams of carbon per area or volume per unit time [$\text{mg C}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{time})$] for periphyton and macrophytes and [$\text{mg C}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{time})$] for phytoplankton are units for expressing primary productivity. They define the amount of carbon dioxide consumed as measured by radioactive carbon (carbon 14). The carbon 14 method is of greater sensitivity than the oxygen light and dark bottle method, and is preferred for use in unenriched waters. Unit time may be either hour or day, depending on the incubation period.

Milligrams of oxygen per area or volume per unit time [$\text{mgO}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{time})$] for periphyton and macrophytes and [$\text{mgO}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{time})$] for phytoplankton are the units for expressing primary productivity. They define production and respiration rates as estimated from changes in the measured dissolved-oxygen concentration. The oxygen light and dark bottle method is preferred if the rate of primary production is sufficient for accurate measurements to be made within 24 hours. Unit time may be either the hour or day, depending on the incubation period.

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) are industrial chemicals that are mixtures of chlorinated biphenyl compounds having various percentages of chlorine. They are similar in structure to organochlorine insecticides.

Radiochemical program is a network of regularly sampled water-quality stations where samples are collected to be analyzed for radioisotopes. The streams that are sampled represent major drainage basins in the conterminous United States.

Recoverable from bottom material is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after a representative sample of bottom material has been digested by a method (usually using an acid or mixture of acids) that results in dissolution of readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all bottom material is not achieved by the digestion treatment and thus the determination represents less than the total amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent in the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures would be required of all laboratories performing such analyses because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Return period is the average time interval between occurrences of a hydrological event of a given or greater magnitude, usually expressed in years. May also be called recurrence interval.

Runoff in inches (IN, in) shows the depth to which the drainage area would be covered if all the runoff for a given time period were uniformly distributed on it.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Sediment is solid material that originates mostly from disintegrated rocks and is transported by, suspended in, or deposited from water; it includes chemical and biochemical precipitates and decomposed organic material, such as humus. The quantity, characteristics, and cause of the occurrence of sediment in streams are influenced by environmental factors. Some major factors are degree of slope, length of slope, soil characteristics, land usage, and quantity and intensity of precipitation.

Bed load is the sediment that is transported in a stream by rolling, sliding, or skipping along the bed and very close to it. In this report, bed load is considered to consist of particles in transit within 0.25 ft of the streambed.

Bed load discharge (tons per day) is the quantity of bed load measured by dry weight that moves past a section as bed load in a given time.

Suspended sediment is the sediment that at any given time is maintained in suspension by the upward components of turbulent currents or that exists in suspension as a colloid.

Suspended-sediment concentration is the velocity-weighted concentration of suspended sediment in the sampled zone (from the water surface to a point approximately 0.3 ft above the bed) expressed as milligrams of dry sediment per liter of water-sediment mixture (mg/L).

Mean concentration is the time-weighted concentration of suspended sediment passing a stream section during a 24-hour day.

Suspended-sediment discharge (tons/day) is the rate at which dry mass of sediment passes a section of a stream or is the quantity of sediment, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes a section in a given time. It is calculated in units of tons per day as follows: concentrations (mg/L) x discharge ft^3/s x 0.0027.

Suspended-sediment load is a general term that refers to material in suspension. It is not synonymous with either discharge or concentration.

Total sediment discharge (tons/day) is the sum of the suspended-sediment discharge and the bed-load discharge. It is the total quantity of sediment, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes a section during a given time.

Total-sediment load or total load is a term which refers to the total sediment (bed load plus suspended-sediment load) that is in transport. It is not synonymous with total-sediment discharge.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Sodium-adsorption-ratio (SAR) is the expression of relative activity of sodium ions in exchange reactions within soil and is an index of sodium or alkali hazard to the soil. Waters range in respect to sodium hazard from those which can be used for irrigation on almost all soils to those which are generally unsatisfactory for irrigation.

Solute is any substance that is dissolved in water.

Specific conductance is a measure of the ability of a water to conduct an electric current. It is expressed in microsiemens per centimeter at 25°C. Specific conductance is related to the type and concentration of ions in solution and can be used for approximating the dissolved-solids content of the water. Commonly, the concentration of dissolved solids (in milligrams per liter) is about 65 percent of the specific conductance (in micromhos). This relation is not constant from stream to stream, and it may vary in the same source with changes in the composition of the water.

Stage-discharge relation is the relation between gage height (stage) and volume of water per unit of time, flowing in a channel.

Streamflow is the discharge that occurs in a natural channel. Although the term "discharge" can be applied to the flow of a canal, the word "streamflow" uniquely describes the discharge in a surface stream course. The term "streamflow" is more general than "runoff" as streamflow may be applied to discharge whether or not it is affected by diversion or regulation.

Substrate is the physical surface upon which an organism lives.

Natural substrate refers to any naturally occurring emersed or submersed solid surface, such as a rock or tree, upon which an organism lives.

Artificial substrate is a device which is purposely placed in a stream or lake for colonization of organisms. The artificial substrate simplifies the community structure by standardizing the substrate from which each sample is taken. Examples of artificial substrates are basket samplers (made of wire cages filled with clean streamside rocks) and multiplate samplers (made of hardboard) for benthic organism collection, and plexiglass strips for periphyton.

Surface area of a lake is that area outlined on the latest U.S.G.S. topographic map as the boundary of the lake and measured by a planimeter in acres. In localities not covered by topographic maps, the areas are computed from the best maps available at the time planimetered. All areas shown are those for the stage when the planimetered map was made.

Surficial bed material is that part (0.1 to 0.2 ft) of the bed material that is sampled using U.S. Series Bed-Material Samplers.

Suspended (as used in tables of chemical analyses) refers to the amount (concentration) of the total concentration in a water-sediment mixture. It is associated with the material retained on a 0.45-micrometer filter.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Suspended, recoverable is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after the part of a representative water-suspended sediment sample that is retained on a 0.45 um membrane filter has been digested by a method (usually using a dilute acid solution) that results in dissolution of only readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all the particulate matter is not achieved by the digestion treatment and thus the determination represents something less than the "total" amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent present in the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures are required of all laboratories performing such analyses because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Determinations of "suspended, recoverable" constituents are made either by analyzing portions of the material collected on the filter or, more commonly, by difference, based on determinations of (1) dissolved and (2) total recoverable concentrations of the constituent.

Suspended, total is the total amount of a given constituent in the part of representative water-suspended sediment sample that is retained on a 0.45 um membrane filter. This term is used only when the analytical procedure assures measurement of at least 95 percent of the constituent determined. A knowledge of the expected form of the constituent in the sample, as well as the analytical methodology used, is required to determine when the results should be reported as "suspended, total."

Determinations of "suspended, total" constituents are made either by analyzing portions of the material collected on the filter or, more commonly, by difference, based on determinations of (1) dissolved and (2) total concentrations of the constituent.

Taxonomy is the division of biology concerned with the classification and naming of organisms. The classification of organisms is based upon a hierarchical scheme beginning with Kingdom and ending with Species at the base. The higher the classification level, the fewer features the organisms have in common. For example, the taxonomy of a particular mayfly, Hexagenia limbata, is the following:

Kingdom.....	Animal
Phylum.....	Arthropoda
Class.....	Insecta
Order.....	Ephemeroptera
Family.....	Ephemeridae
<u>Genus</u>	<u>Hexagenia</u>
<u>Species</u>	<u>Hexagenia limbata</u>

Thermograph is an instrument that continuously records variations of temperature on a chart. The more general term "temperature recorder" is used in the table heading and refers to any instrument that records temperature whether on a chart, a tape, or any other medium.

WATER RESOURCES DATA FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Time-weighted average is computed by multiplying the number of days in the sampling period by the concentrations of individual constituents for the corresponding period and dividing the sum of the products by the total number of days. A time-weighted average represents the composition of water that would be contained in a vessel or reservoir that had received equal quantities of water from the stream each day for the year.

Tons per acre-foot indicates the dry mass of dissolved solids in 1 acre-foot of water. It is computed by multiplying the concentration of the constituent, in milligrams per liter by 0.00136.

Tons per day (T/DAY) is the quantity of a substance in solution or suspension that passes a stream section during a 24-hour period.

Total is the total amount of a given constituent in a representative water-suspended sediment sample, regardless of the constituent's physical or chemical form. This term is used only when the analytical procedure assures measurement of at least 95 percent of the constituent present in both the dissolved and suspended phases of the sample. A knowledge of the expected form of the constituent in the sample, as well as the analytical methodology used, is required to judge when the results should be reported as "total." (Note that the word "total" does double duty here, indicating both that the sample consists of a water-suspended sediment mixture and that the analytical method determined all of the constituent in the sample.)

Total discharge is the total quantity of any individual constituent, as measured by dry mass or volume, that passes through a stream cross-section per unit of time. This term needs to be qualified, such as "total sediment discharge," "total chloride discharge," and so on.

Total, recoverable is the amount of a given constituent that is in solution after a representative water-suspended sediment sample has been digested by a method (usually using a dilute acid solution) that results in dissolution of only readily soluble substances. Complete dissolution of all particulate matter is not achieved by the digestion treatment, and thus the determination represents something less than the "total" amount (that is, less than 95 percent) of the constituent present in the dissolved and suspended phases of the sample. To achieve comparability of analytical data, equivalent digestion procedures are required of all laboratories performing such analyses, because different digestion procedures are likely to produce different analytical results.

Tritium Network is a network of stations which has been established to provide baseline information on the occurrence of tritium in the Nation's surface waters. In addition to the surface-water stations in the network, tritium data are also obtained at a number of precipitation stations. The purpose of the precipitation stations is to provide an estimate sufficient for hydrologic studies of the tritium input to the United States.

WATER RESOURCES FOR PUERTO RICO AND THE U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS, 1988

Water year in Geological Survey reports dealing with surface water supply is the 12-month period, October 1 through September 30. The water year is designated by the calendar year in which it ends and which includes 9 of the 12 months. Thus, the year ending September 30, 1980, is called the "1980 water year."

WDR is used as an abbreviation for "Water-Data Report" in the REVISED RECORDS paragraph to refer to State annual hydrologic-data reports (WRD was used as an abbreviation for "Water-Resources Data" in reports published prior to 1976).

Weighted average is used in this report to indicate discharge-weighted average. It is computed by multiplying the discharge for a sampling period by the concentrations of individual constituents for the corresponding period and dividing the sum of the products by the sum of the discharges. A discharge-weighted average approximates the composition of water that would be found in a reservoir containing all the water passing a given location during the water year after thorough mixing in the reservoir.

WSP is used as an abbreviation for "Water-Supply Paper" in references to previously published reports.

PUBLICATIONS ON TECHNIQUES OF WATER-RESOURCES INVESTIGATIONS

The U.S. Geological Survey publishes a series of manuals describing procedures for planning and conducting specialized work in water-resources investigations. The material is grouped under major subject headings called books and is further divided into sections and chapters. For example, Section A of Book 3 (Applications of Hydraulics) pertains to surface water. The chapter, the unit of publication, is limited to a narrow field of subject matter. This format permits flexibility in revision and publication as the need arises.

The reports listed below are for sale by the U.S. Geological Survey, Books and Open-File Reports Section, Federal Center, Box 25425, Denver, Colorado 80225 (authorized agent of the Superintendent of Documents, Government Printing Office). Prepayment is required. Remittance should be sent by check or money order payable to the U.S. Geological Survey. Prices are not included because they are subject to change. Current prices can be obtained by writing to the above address. When ordering or inquiring about prices for any of these publications, please give the title, book number, chapter number, and "U.S. Geological Survey Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations."

- 1-D1. Water temperature--influential factors, field measurement, and data presentation, by H. H. Stevens, Jr., J. F. Ficke, and G. F. Smoot: USGS--TWRI Book 1, Chapter D1. 1975. 65 pages.
- 1-D2. Guidelines for collection and field analysis of ground-water samples for selected unstable constituents, by W. W. Wood: USGS--TWRI Book 1, Chapter D2. 1976. 24 pages.
- 2-D1. Application of surface geophysics to ground-water investigations, by A. A. R. Zohdy, G. P. Eaton, and D. R. Mabey: USGS--TWRI Book 2, Chapter D1. 1974. 116 pages.
- 2-E1. Application of borehole geophysics to water-resources investigations, by W. S. Keys and L. M. MacCary: USGS--TWRI Book 2, Chapter E1. 1971. 126 pages.
- 3-A1. General field and office procedures for indirect discharge measurements, by M. A. Benson and Tate Dalrymple: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A1. 1967. 30 pages.
- 3-A2. Measurement of peak discharge by the slope-area method, by Tate Dalrymple and M. A. Benson: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A2. 1967. 12 pages.
- 3-A3. Measurement of peak discharge at culverts by indirect methods, by G. L. Bodhaine: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A3. 1968. 60 pages.
- 3-A4. Measurement of peak discharge at width contractions by indirect methods, by H. J. Matthai: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A4. 1967. 44 pages.
- 3-A5. Measurement of peak discharge at dams by indirect methods, by Harry Hulsing: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A5. 1967. 29 pages.
- 3-A6. General procedure for gaging streams, by R. W. Carter and Jacob Davidian: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A6. 1968. 13 pages.
- 3-A7. Stage measurements at gaging stations, by T. J. Buchanan and W. P. Somers: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A7. 1968. 28 pages.
- 3-A8. Discharge measurements at gaging stations, by T. J. Buchanan and W. P. Somers: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A8. 1969. 65 pages.
- 3-A9. Measurement of time of travel and dispersion in streams by dye tracing, by E. F. Hubbard, F. A. Kilpatrick, L. A. Martens, and J. F. Wilson, Jr.: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A9. 1982. 44 pages.
- 3-A10. Discharge ratings at gaging stations, by E. J. Kennedy: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A10. 1984. 59 pages.
- 3-A11. Measurement of discharge by moving-boat method, by G. F. Smoot and C. E. Novak: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A11. 1969. 22 pages.
- 3-A12. Fluorometric procedures for dye tracing, by J. F. Wilson, Jr., E. D. Cobb, and F. A. Kilpatrick: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A12. 1986. 41 pages.
- 3-A13. Computation of continuous records of streamflow, by E. J. Kennedy: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A13. 1983. 53 pages.
- 3-A14. Use of flumes in measuring discharge, by F. A. Kilpatrick and V. R. Schneider: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A14. 1983. 46 pages.
- 3-A15. Computation of water-surface profiles in open channels, by Jacob Davidian: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A15. 1984. 48 pages.
- 3-A16. Measurement of discharge using tracers, by F. A. Kilpatrick and E. D. Cobb: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A16. 1985. 52 pages.
- 3-A17. Acoustic velocity meter systems, by Antonius Laenen: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter A17. 1985. 38 pages.
- 3-B1. Aquifer-test design, observation, and data analysis, by R. W. Stallman: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter B1. 1971. 26 pages.

PUBLICATIONS ON TECHNIQUES OF WATER-RESOURCES INVESTIGATIONS--Continued

- 3-B2. Introduction to ground-water hydraulics, a programmed test for self-instruction, by G. D. Bennett: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter B2. 1976. 172 pages.
- 3-B3. Type curves for selected problems of flow to wells in confined aquifers, by J. E. Reed: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter B3. 1980. 106 pages.
- 3-B5. Definition of boundary and initial conditions in the analysis of saturated ground-water flow systems--An introduction, by O. L. Franke, T. E. Reilly, and G. D. Bennett: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter B5. 1987. 15 pages.
- 3-B6. The principle of superposition and its application in ground-water hydraulics, by T. E. Reilly, O. L. Franke, and G. D. Bennett: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter B6. 1987. 28 pages.
- 3-C1. Fluvial sediment concepts, by H. P. Guy: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter C1. 1970. 55 pages.
- 3-C2. Field methods for measurement of fluvial sediment, by H. P. Guy and V. W. Norman: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter C2. 1970. 59 pages.
- 3-C3. Computation of fluvial-sediment discharge, by George Porterfield: USGS--TWRI Book 3, Chapter C3. 1972. 66 pages.
- 4-A1. Some statistical tools in hydrology, by H. C. Riggs: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter A1. 1968. 39 pages.
- 4-A2. Frequency curves, by H. C. Riggs: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter A2. 1968. 15 pages.
- 4-B1. Low-flow investigations, by H. C. Riggs: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter B1. 1972. 18 pages.
- 4-B2. Storage analyses for water supply, by H. C. Riggs and C. H. Hardison: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter B2. 1973. 20 pages.
- 4-B3. Regional analyses of streamflow characteristics, by H. C. Riggs: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter B3. 1973. 15 pages.
- 4-D1. Computation of rate and volume of stream depletion by wells, by C. T. Jenkins: USGS--TWRI Book 4, Chapter D1. 1970. 17 pages.
- 5-A1. Methods for determination of inorganic substances in water and fluvial sediments, by M. W. Skougstad and others, editors: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A1. 1979. 626 pages.
- 5-A2. Determination of minor elements in water by emission spectroscopy, by P. R. Barnett and E. C. Mallory, Jr.: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A2. 1971. 31 pages.
- 5-A3. Methods for analysis of organic substances in water, by D. F. Goerlitz and Eugene Brown: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A3. 1972. 40 pages.
- 5-A4. Methods for collection and analysis of aquatic biological and microbiological samples, edited by P. E. Greeson, T. A. Ehlke, G. A. Irwin, B. W. Lium, and K. V. Slack: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A4. 1977. 332 pages.
- 5-A5. Methods for determination of radioactive substances in water and fluvial sediments, by L. L. Thatcher, V. J. Janzer, and K. W. Edwards: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A5. 1977. 95 pages.
- 5-A6. Quality assurance practices for the chemical and biological analyses of water and fluvial sediments, by L. C. Friedman and D. E. Erdmann: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter A6. 1982. 181 pages.
- 5-C1. Laboratory theory and methods for sediment analysis, by H. P. Guy: USGS--TWRI Book 5, Chapter C1. 1969. 58 pages.
- 6-A1. A modular three-dimensional finite-difference ground-water flow model, by M. G. McDonald and A. W. Harbaugh: USGS--TWRI Book 6, Chapter A1. 1988. 586 pages.
- 7-C1. Finite difference model for aquifer simulation in two dimensions with results of numerical experiments, by P. C. Trescott, G. F. Pinder, and S. P. Larson: USGS--TWRI Book 7, Chapter C1. 1976. 116 pages.
- 7-C2. Computer model of two-dimensional solute transport and dispersion in ground water, by L. F. Konikow and J. D. Bredehoeft: USGS--TWRI Book 7, Chapter C2. 1978. 90 pages.
- 7-C3. A model for simulation of flow in singular and interconnected channels, by R. W. Schaffranek, R. A. Baltzer, and D. E. Goldberg: USGS--TWRI Book 7, Chapter C3. 1981. 110 pages.
- 8-A1. Methods of measuring water levels in deep wells, by M. S. Garber and F. C. Koopman: USGS--TWRI Book 8, Chapter A1. 1968. 23 pages.
- 8-A2. Installation and service manual for U.S. Geological Survey manometers, by J. D. Craig: USGS--TWRI Book 8, Chapter A2. 1983. 57 pages.
- 8-B2. Calibration and maintenance of vertical-axis type current meters, by G. F. Smoot and C. E. Novak: USGS--TWRI Book 8, Chapter B2. 1968. 15 pages.

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Surface
and
Quality-of-Water Records
for
Puerto Rico

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 11.--Río Guajataca basin.

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010500 RIO GUAJATACA AT LARES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'01", long 66°52'24", at bridge on Highway 111 (km 32.9), 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Anon, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of Lares plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.16 mi² (8.18 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATUR-ATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987											
29...	0940	3.6	198	7.40	23.0	6.1	7.9	94	12	K6600	25000
DEC											
14...	1020	5.0	244	7.20	22.0	4.8	7.7	90	40	2600	4100
FEB 1988											
02...	1050	1.7	246	7.20	21.5	0.70	7.7	89	21	2700	22000
APR											
11...	1115	0.87	250	7.10	23.0	1.2	8.7	104	27	2600	2000
JUN											
07...	1030	2.8	249	6.90	23.5	2.3	7.4	89	55	1900	1600
AUG											
02...	0945	2.0	252	6.70	22.5	0.90	7.5	88	17	30000	4100

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
SEP 1987											
29...	89	10	26	5.9	12	0.6	2.4	79	<0.5	8.0	11
DEC											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	92	--	--	--
APR											
11...	98	0	28	6.8	13	0.6	2.3	92	<0.5	12	12
JUN											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--
AUG											
02...	94	0	27	6.5	12	0.6	2.1	89	--	9.8	10

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
29...	0.20	31	140	1.40	1	1.59	0.01	1.60	0.03	0.17
DEC										
14...	--	--	--	--	5	1.69	0.01	1.70	0.02	1.5
FEB 1988										
02...	--	--	--	--	1	1.16	0.04	1.20	0.02	0.28
APR										
11...	0.30	30	167	0.04	3	--	<0.01	0.50	0.02	--
JUN										
07...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<0.01	1.10	0.03	--
AUG										
02...	0.20	30	155	0.84	1	1.09	0.01	1.10	0.02	0.28

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010600 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE LAGO GUAJATACA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'57", long 66°55'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) off road 451, 3 mi (5 km) south of Lago Guajataca, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) east of Eneas and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) west of Piletas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 565 ft (172 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 2,600 ft³/s (73.6 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 12.03 ft (3.667 m), from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on the basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 1.9 ft³/s (0.054 m³/s), Feb. 11, 17, 1986, Feb. 9, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	1615	*2,450	69.4	*11.77	3.587	Sept. 20	1730	1,600	45.3	10.20	3.109
May 26	1645	2,190	62.0	11.33	3.453						

Minimum discharge, 1.9 ft³/s (0.054 m³/s), Feb. 9.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.5	15	8.7	70	9.1	4.7	2.6	22	35	39	12	117
2	87	6.8	62	54	7.1	5.3	2.8	14	25	32	9.7	80
3	37	6.6	32	24	8.6	5.0	2.9	26	20	65	30	55
4	107	6.4	14	18	8.2	4.4	3.2	24	16	36	32	40
5	43	5.6	17	16	6.3	4.3	3.4	25	15	92	13	36
6	21	5.3	85	15	5.8	4.1	9.6	12	13	64	12	29
7	340	15	45	14	5.4	4.2	3.8	9.9	13	34	11	36
8	108	7.9	25	12	5.2	4.5	3.4	8.8	13	26	10	27
9	43	14	20	12	3.3	4.2	3.4	66	12	21	9.1	28
10	72	9.4	18	11	6.3	4.2	3.0	67	10	20	8.7	36
11	54	22	16	10	7.2	4.2	3.9	245	20	17	8.6	37
12	32	11	83	10	12	4.0	11	108	100	15	8.3	51
13	26	21	49	9.5	7.6	3.9	5.9	53	85	62	7.9	24
14	36	7.9	23	9.2	11	5.0	3.6	36	55	46	32	21
15	32	16	19	9.6	7.3	4.6	44	46	44	28	26	24
16	23	12	18	8.5	6.8	6.1	37	82	36	19	11	19
17	20	86	16	17	6.5	4.7	11	55	27	27	31	17
18	31	23	14	9.3	6.1	4.9	62	31	23	33	84	14
19	20	9.2	57	12	6.0	4.6	78	22	18	25	22	13
20	15	7.6	60	7.8	5.7	3.7	102	20	17	20	48	209
21	14	7.3	36	7.3	5.2	3.8	116	17	13	16	37	85
22	13	5.9	26	7.0	5.3	4.0	86	55	104	14	21	110
23	13	5.9	20	6.8	5.6	3.7	37	44	62	14	18	240
24	13	39	17	6.9	5.8	3.9	28	26	202	13	247	142
25	11	29	19	6.5	5.0	3.9	26	18	125	13	314	84
26	11	14	15	6.8	6.6	3.7	18	334	63	13	110	66
27	10	53	14	6.3	10	6.4	13	146	44	13	148	56
28	9.6	34	15	6.0	6.5	16	59	157	78	12	131	43
29	8.9	14	14	8.4	5.2	6.5	58	134	84	18	80	36
30	8.9	11	17	6.9	---	3.1	45	81	55	15	54	32
31	53	---	44	6.2	---	2.8	---	51	---	11	60	---
TOTAL	1321.9	520.8	918.7	424.0	196.7	148.4	882.5	2035.7	1427	873	1646.3	1807
MEAN	42.6	17.4	29.6	13.7	6.78	4.79	29.4	65.7	47.6	28.2	53.1	60.2
MAX	340	86	85	70	12	16	116	334	202	92	314	240
MIN	8.9	5.3	8.7	6.0	3.3	2.8	2.6	8.8	10	11	7.9	13

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 11364.9 MEAN 31.1 MAX 340 MIN 3.0
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 12202.0 MEAN 33.3 MAX 340 MIN 2.6

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50010600 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE LAGO GUAJATACA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 06	1039	19.8	351	23.5	APR, 11	1050	3.34	340	23.5
DEC, 17	0917	17.2	362	22.5	MAY, 30	1238	11.2	378	24.5
JAN, 12	1420	10.7	316	22.5	JUN, 06	1139	14.1	367	25.5
FEB, 18	1131	5.72	309	22.0	JUL, 11	1255	16.2	350	25.5
MAR, 07	1435	4.59	366	22.0	AUG, 01	1050	9.55	324	25.0

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011000 CANAL PRINCIPAL DE DIVERSIONES AT LAGO DE GUAJATACA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'02", long 66°55'27", off Highway 476 at Lago Guajataca outlet, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) southwest of Segunda Unidad Baldorioty de Castro, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) south of Quebradillas Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-64, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECALE, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECALE, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987											
29...	1130	55	291	6.90	26.5	0.80	1.7	21	20	52	30
DEC 14...	1205	55	292	6.80	25.5	0.90	1.3	16	40	110	130
FEB 1988											
02...	1230	60	315	6.90	25.0	--	2.1	26	--	K4	K15
APR 11...	1320	75	299	7.00	26.0	0.50	3.9	48	17	K37	170
JUN 07...	1230	E1	273	7.50	28.0	0.90	10.3	133	28	300	80
AUG 02...	1140	75	315	6.50	25.5	0.40	1.8	22	20	K2	K2

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD MG/L AS CaCO3	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
SEP 1987											
29...	130	3	47	3.8	5.6	0.2	2.0	130	<0.5	11	7.0
DEC 14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR 11...	130	0	46	4.5	6.4	0.3	2.0	120	<0.5	11	9.1
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG 02...	150	9	53	3.6	5.1	0.2	1.6	130	--	11	7.6

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
29...	0.10	8.1	170	25	1	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.08	0.42
DEC 14...	--	--	--	--	5	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.50	0.40
FEB 1988										
02...	--	--	--	--	2	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.13	0.77
APR 11...	0.20	8.8	169	34	3	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.05	0.15
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	1	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.05	0.35
AUG 02...	0.10	7.0	172	35	2	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.03	0.27

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011400 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE MOUTH NEAR QUEBRADILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'31", long 66°57'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank at ford 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from bridge on Highway 2, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) west of Quebradillas plaza, 2.1 mi (3.4 km) upstream from the Atlantic Ocean, and 6.6 mi (10.6 km) downstream from Lago Guajataca.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February to May 1969 (monthly measurements only), July 1969 to December 1970, April 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 0.0 ft (0.0 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharge, which are poor. Flow regulated by lago Guajataca 6.6 mi (10.6 km).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 6,200 ft³/s (176 m³/s), May 13, 1986, estimated based on a mean daily discharge correlation with station 50011200, 6.5 miles upstream; minimum discharge, 6.2 ft³/s (0.176 m³/s), Sept. 4, 9-12, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum discharge, 2,090 ft³/s (59.2 m³/s), June 27, gage height, 6.59 ft (2.009 m); minimum discharge, 15 ft³/s (0.42 m³/s), Jan. 28, 29.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e21	23	18	e110	e16	e18	e18	18	233	645	18	26
2	e20	18	e18	e110	e18	e18	e18	16	234	605	18	33
3	e20	e18	e18	e110	e20	e18	17	23	234	588	18	112
4	e19	24	e18	120	e30	e18	17	32	234	571	18	41
5	e19	20	e18	152	e20	e18	17	18	219	457	18	38
6	e19	19	e18	146	e17	e18	19	17	22	37	17	36
7	e22	19	30	129	17	e18	19	16	e18	21	18	58
8	e38	26	e25	21	e16	e18	e18	16	e18	19	17	97
9	22	e21	e22	e20	e16	e18	e18	16	e17	18	17	270
10	e21	19	e21	19	e16	e18	e17	32	17	18	16	1110
11	e20	17	e21	19	e16	e19	e17	483	17	18	16	818
12	e19	17	e85	19	16	e19	e17	80	17	18	16	553
13	19	17	e263	19	e16	e19	e16	27	17	18	16	317
14	61	e17	32	19	e16	e19	e16	21	18	18	16	439
15	57	e17	46	18	e16	e19	e22	20	32	19	16	169
16	e26	e17	34	18	e16	e19	e19	19	34	19	17	34
17	e24	95	e29	e18	e16	e19	e17	20	69	19	17	31
18	22	54	e26	e18	e17	e19	e25	18	141	19	20	29
19	21	26	e25	e18	e17	e19	e22	17	31	18	18	29
20	20	30	e50	e17	18	e19	27	17	24	18	17	31
21	e20	19	e37	e17	18	e19	206	18	22	18	e16	43
22	e20	18	e31	e17	e18	19	105	16	21	18	16	33
23	e19	e18	e28	17	18	18	21	24	24	18	e16	93
24	e19	e18	27	16	e18	18	17	41	26	17	e19	173
25	e19	e19	27	16	18	18	16	20	31	17	168	161
26	e18	e18	e26	16	18	18	17	18	25	18	31	146
27	18	e18	e25	16	19	19	18	53	541	21	21	163
28	17	e18	e24	15	e18	19	16	232	1110	18	23	161
29	17	e18	e24	e15	e18	21	17	230	786	18	19	152
30	17	18	e24	e15	---	21	27	230	690	19	19	146
31	17	---	e43	e15	---	19	---	230	---	19	18	---
TOTAL	711	696	1133	1295	513	579	836	2038	4922	3364	710	5542
MEAN	22.9	23.2	36.5	41.8	17.7	18.7	27.9	65.7	164	109	22.9	185
MAX	61	95	263	152	30	21	206	483	1110	645	168	1110
MIN	17	17	18	15	16	18	16	16	17	17	16	26

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 16373.2 MEAN 44.9 MAX 1190 MIN 6.2
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 22339 MEAN 61.0 MAX 1110 MIN 15

e Estimated

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

50011400 RIO GUAJATACA ABOVE MOUTH NEAR QUEBRADILLAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987										
29...	1515	21	443	7.20	26.0	0.5	8.5	104	10	K49 160
DEC 14...	1440	31	380	7.40	25.0	6.5	8.2	98	28	3200 3900
FEB 1988										
02...	1520	E0	399	7.10	24.5	--	6.7	79	--	310 470
APR 11...	1600	E0	475	6.90	25.5	0.5	6.4	78	28	300 K10
JUN 07...	1550	19	461	7.00	27.0	1.2	8.6	106	29	K20 K51
AUG 02...	1420	18	475	7.00	25.5	0.6	11.1	133	<10	K29 K20

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
SEP 1987											
29...	209	24	73	7.2	15	0.4	1.1	180	<0.5	9.4	25
DEC 14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
APR 11...	210	3	71	7.4	12	0.4	1.3	190	<0.5	7.9	19
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
AUG 02...	200	13	68	7.2	15	0.5	1.1	180	--	8.9	25

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SI02)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
29...	0.10	6.6	250	14	1	1.39	0.01	1.40	0.03	0.27
DEC 14...	--	--	--	--	5	1.29	0.01	1.30	0.02	0.18
FEB 1988										
02...	--	--	--	--	1	1.38	0.02	1.40	0.02	0.18
APR 11...	0.10	7.0	249	--	<1	1.78	0.02	1.80	0.03	0.17
JUN 07...	--	--	--	--	1	1.49	0.01	1.50	0.04	0.16
AUG 02...	0.10	6.1	244	12	<1	1.49	0.01	1.50	0.02	0.68

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

Figure 12.--Río Camuy basin.

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50014800 RIO CAMUY NEAR BAYANEY, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'48", long 66°49'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on left bank at Highway 488, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) southeast of school at Santiago, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) northwest from Escuela Manuel A. Rivera at Bayaney and 9.1 mi (14.6 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 341 ft (104 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 6,450 ft³/s (183 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 17.66 ft (5.383 m), from rating curve extended above 300 ft³/s (8.50 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 28 ft³/s (0.79 m³/s), Mar. 15-17, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,000 ft³/s (56.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Apr. 21	1815	*2,910	82.4	*13.52	4.121	Sept. 23	2130	2,070	58.6	11.60	3.536
May 10	2030	2,640	74.8	12.92	3.938						

Minimum daily discharge, 31 ft³/s (0.878 m³/s), Mar. 25-27.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	59	82	70	315	56	38	34	104	82	121	51	196
2	87	58	146	286	54	43	33	86	73	98	50	149
3	82	138	168	136	106	39	35	79	69	88	54	106
4	67	91	87	105	95	38	33	72	64	81	77	90
5	62	60	91	92	60	37	34	66	60	173	58	81
6	57	53	119	85	53	37	38	64	59	179	52	76
7	142	52	113	80	50	36	37	58	57	97	62	119
8	193	69	84	77	50	36	34	55	57	83	50	95
9	104	70	76	74	48	36	36	122	58	77	47	89
10	72	76	72	69	48	33	35	595	57	75	46	135
11	73	59	69	66	47	36	35	686	57	72	47	118
12	71	56	69	65	45	35	49	382	64	69	44	117
13	71	88	106	62	46	36	60	210	138	63	43	129
14	158	65	74	61	58	35	39	147	120	66	40	106
15	116	57	78	66	45	35	40	146	94	69	49	88
16	73	84	70	59	44	36	95	200	69	62	43	81
17	65	189	64	72	44	37	98	187	93	61	45	76
18	73	117	67	68	45	36	151	118	74	80	98	75
19	117	79	137	62	44	35	268	100	66	67	69	73
20	119	70	202	56	43	33	244	98	74	58	50	428
21	81	64	153	55	41	33	845	98	61	57	85	384
22	69	58	102	53	40	32	486	87	499	54	54	177
23	61	56	85	52	39	34	150	81	374	54	49	581
24	66	77	79	51	39	32	99	76	255	53	285	397
25	60	129	99	51	39	e31	97	72	300	53	706	191
26	60	84	81	49	40	e31	97	76	162	52	264	154
27	55	143	76	48	50	31	95	158	105	52	220	168
28	53	167	70	48	41	88	163	140	276	51	262	152
29	50	94	66	49	39	87	212	194	351	52	263	120
30	50	78	63	50	---	45	177	104	218	67	155	110
31	64	---	183	47	---	40	---	88	---	57	113	---
TOTAL	2530	2563	3019	2509	1449	1211	3849	4749	4076	2341	3531	4861
MEAN	81.6	85.4	97.4	80.9	50.0	39.1	128	153	136	75.5	114	162
MAX	193	189	202	315	106	88	845	686	499	179	706	581
MIN	50	52	63	47	39	31	33	55	57	51	40	73

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 31951 MEAN 87.5 MAX 472 MIN 31
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 36688 MEAN 100 MAX 845 MIN 31

e Estimated

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50014800 RIO CAMUY NEAR BAYANEY, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS JUNE 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 07	1401	53.7	299	24.5	APR, 12	1248	36.4	326	24.0
DEC, 14	1323	73	310	23.5	MAY, 05	1215	108	326	24.0
JAN, 13	1223	61	301	23.5	JUN, 08	1159	52.6	341	24.5
FEB, 17	1222	43.5	309	23.0	JUL, 13	1144	61.5	336	24.5
MAR, 08	1249	35.3	363	23.0	AUG, 03	1241	50.3	319	24.5

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50015700 RIO CAMUY NEAR HATILLO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'44", long 66°49'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southwest of Hatillo plaza, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) southeast of Camuy plaza, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of Planta de Purificacion, and 3.3 mi (5.5 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 13 ft (4 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 10,500 ft³/s (297 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 24.75 ft (7.544 m), from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 36 ft³/s (1.02 m³/s), Mar. 19, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Apr. 21	2300	6,170	175	20.58	6.273	Aug. 25	0300	3,090	87.5	15.96	4.865
May 11	0100	*7,540	214	*22.07	6.727	Sept.20	2345	3,320	94.0	16.40	5.000
June 22	2000	4,500	127	18.39	5.605	Sept.24	0015	3,220	91.2	16.21	4.941

Minimum daily discharge, 37 ft³/s (1.05 m³/s), Apr.10.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	65	133	90	596	85	51	45	120	86	150	64	e350
2	76	90	190	782	79	54	43	99	80	121	62	e225
3	98	265	310	234	201	50	42	91	75	109	62	e180
4	74	391	110	158	223	49	41	87	71	101	81	e140
5	72	89	92	139	101	48	40	80	67	221	68	e120
6	68	76	140	127	83	48	41	76	69	313	62	e110
7	148	73	153	119	75	48	40	70	65	125	72	e170
8	262	101	101	112	70	47	41	69	63	106	73	e120
9	182	87	87	107	66	46	39	106	63	96	61	e110
10	103	104	82	98	66	46	38	e2500	61	93	60	e200
11	101	75	78	90	65	45	39	3560	60	89	60	e180
12	97	71	112	90	63	45	48	1440	72	84	57	e150
13	100	127	164	82	60	46	74	458	119	80	56	e180
14	210	85	87	80	71	47	48	280	106	82	55	e160
15	200	76	152	85	61	46	45	197	110	85	62	155
16	112	95	109	78	59	46	105	262	78	76	60	132
17	103	766	87	89	58	47	114	260	98	75	57	121
18	96	234	83	90	57	46	236	139	172	91	108	115
19	140	125	260	84	55	44	433	117	82	85	85	116
20	206	104	551	76	54	43	399	113	81	73	62	466
21	131	94	328	71	53	42	1410	130	70	71	87	836
22	105	85	166	69	53	42	1670	104	1050	69	67	265
23	94	78	128	69	52	41	193	95	725	66	62	568
24	97	80	111	67	52	42	120	90	370	65	195	865
25	99	180	155	67	52	41	115	85	385	65	1710	240
26	107	109	123	66	54	41	123	82	248	64	357	176
27	92	147	110	65	67	41	120	156	131	64	295	182
28	85	280	101	63	57	73	175	127	293	64	361	196
29	89	125	95	65	53	114	265	193	510	67	e400	138
30	93	101	85	68	---	58	267	114	366	81	e230	127
31	90	---	232	64	---	48	---	92	---	70	e170	---
TOTAL	3595	4446	4672	4050	2145	1525	6409	11392	5826	3001	5261	7093
MEAN	116	148	151	131	74.0	49.2	214	367	194	96.8	170	236
MAX	262	766	551	782	223	114	1670	3560	1050	313	1710	865
MIN	65	71	78	63	52	41	38	69	60	64	55	110

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 51109 MEAN 140 MAX 1480 MIN 37
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 59415 MEAN 162 MAX 3560 MIN 38

e Estimated

RIO CAMUY BASIN

50015700 RIO CAMUY NEAR HATILLO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 07	1005	65.5	310	24.5	APR, 12	0833	46.9	336	24.0
DEC, 14	1044	88.9	299	24.0	MAY, 05	0852	79.8	347	23.5
JAN, 13	0911	77.2	326	22.5	JUN, 08	0853	62.3	362	24.0
FEB, 17	0906	57.1	337	22.0	JUL, 13	0842	79.9	355	24.0
MAR, 08	0908	46.6	396	22.5	AUG, 03	0903	60.5	341	24.5

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 13.--Río Grande de Arecibo basin.

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50020100 LAGO GARZAS NEAR ADJUNTAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'20", long 66°44'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, in power gate tower of Garzas Dam on Rio Vacas, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from Rio Garzas, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) southwest of Adjuntas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.6 mi² (40.4 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 2,337.82 ft (712.567 m) above mean sea level; gage readings have been reduced to elevations above mean sea level. Prior to May 25, 1988 and May 25 to July 13, 1988, at datums 38.98 ft and 20.18 ft higher.

REMARKS.--Satellite data collection platform at station. Lake is formed by earthfill dam completed in 1943. Outflow from lake controlled by vertical-lift sluice gate and fixed-crest concrete spillway. Spillway elevation, 2,415.0 ft (736.09 m). Lake is used for irrigation and power production. Operated by P.R. Electric Power authority.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Maximun elevation 2,414.35 ft (735.894 m), Feb. 1; minimun elevation, 2,364.79 ft (720.788 m), Aug. 23, but may have been lower during period of no gage-height record Aug. 23-29.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,364	660	2,394	2,250
2,382	1,500	2,415	4,082

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1				---	2414.08	2412.90	2403.82	2400.81	2382.71	A	2383.01	2393.59
2				---	2413.62	2412.55	2403.72	2400.43	2382.28		2383.28	A
3				---	2413.62	2412.25	2403.61	2399.98	2382.88		2383.05	
4				---	2413.83	2411.93	2403.52	2399.67	2383.13		2382.95	
5				---	2413.78	2411.60	2403.42	2399.24	2383.69		2382.36	
6				---	2413.90	2411.20	2403.31	2398.74	2383.92		2382.26	
7				---	2414.10	2410.87	2403.21	2397.70	2383.36		2381.79	
8				---	2414.16	2410.02	2403.09	2397.63	2382.37		2379.88	
9				---	2413.48	2409.92	2402.98	2397.32	2381.30		2379.35	
10				---	2413.33	2409.37	2402.86	2396.38	2381.11		2379.63	
11				---	2413.29	2409.28	2402.74	2395.81	2380.95		2378.76	
12				---	2412.92	2408.90	2402.63	2395.14	2381.39	A	2378.24	
13				---	2412.46	2409.11	2402.51	2394.56	2381.46	2383.99	2378.27	
14				---	2412.46	2408.84	2402.40	2393.84	2383.62	2383.89	2378.30	
15				---	2412.48	2408.20	2402.40	2393.23	2383.95	2383.35	2378.52	
16				---	2412.48	2407.23	2402.34	2392.82	2384.25	2384.70	2378.10	
17				---	2412.48	2406.36	2402.50	2392.30	2384.49	2385.48	2379.10	
18				---	2412.50	2405.42	2402.48	2391.68	2385.28	2385.89	2380.08	
19				---	2412.50	2404.42	2402.39	2391.03	2385.68	2385.64	2380.79	
20				---	2412.52	2403.49	2402.70	2390.72	2386.05	2385.32	2381.26	
21				---	2412.52	2403.77	2402.68	2389.03	2385.55	2385.38	2381.66	
22				---	2412.82	2403.94	2402.77	2387.66	2384.89	2385.19	2382.22	
23				2413.55	2413.00	2404.11	2402.14	2386.20	2384.51	2385.50	2364.89	
24				2413.78	2413.17	2404.27	2402.64	2385.85	2384.20	2385.66	A	
25				2413.67	2413.35	2404.03	2402.11	2384.80	2384.48	2385.93		
26				2413.64	2413.18	2403.83	2401.22	2384.34	2385.47	2385.22		
27				2413.62	2413.39	2403.84	2401.19	2383.97	2385.07	2384.66		
28				2413.90	2413.56	2404.00	2401.15	2383.44	2388.10	2384.17		
29				2413.89	2413.28	2404.06	2400.58	2383.06	A	2383.86	A	
30				2414.08	---	2404.02	2400.77	2382.48	A	2383.39	2394.16	A
31				2414.31	---	2403.93	---	2382.52	---	2383.74	2393.58	---
MEAN				---	2413.18	2407.34	2402.53	2392.01	---	---	---	---
MAX				---	2414.16	2412.90	2403.82	2400.81	---	---	---	---
MIN				---	2412.46	2403.49	2400.58	2382.48	---	---	---	---

A No gage-height record.

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50020500 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO NEAR ADJUNTAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'54", long 66°44'12", at Highway 135 bridge, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream from Lago Adjuntas, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northwest of Adjuntas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.7 mi² (32.9 km²) this does not include 6.0 mi² (15.6 km²) above Lago Garzas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
20...	1545	27	286	7.60	27.0	6.1	7.8	103	<10	K1200	2500
DEC											
21...	1430	32	237	7.50	24.5	0.5	8.9	106	18	470	550
FEB 1988											
23...	1040	14	307	7.90	22.0	0.6	10.3	122	11	250	200
APR											
21...	1005	11	329	7.40	25.0	0.4	9.0	113	<10	4800	780
JUN											
22...	0910	12	390	7.00	23.0	1.4	7.6	92	14	K1700	800
AUG											
22...	0915	12	597	7.60	23.5	4.0	7.2	89	<10	K1300	5600

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
20...	100	8	26	8.9	17	0.8	2.1	94	<0.5	12	17
DEC											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
APR											
21...	110	5	29	9.7	19	0.8	0.80	100	<0.5	10	25
JUN											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG											
22...	130	9	32	11	57	2	3.4	110	--	12	94

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TOMS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
20...	0.10	32	171	12	11	1.22	0.08	1.30	0.06	0.34
DEC										
21...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.30	0.10	1.40	0.08	0.12
FEB 1988										
23...	--	--	--	--	4	0.98	0.12	1.10	0.07	0.43
APR										
21...	0.20	29	187	5.6	<1	0.89	0.11	1.00	0.01	0.29
JUN										
22...	--	--	--	--	3	0.91	0.09	1.00	0.11	0.49
AUG										
22...	0.10	30	309	10	<1	0.98	0.12	1.10	0.14	0.36

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50025000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO NEAR UTUADO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'11", long 66°41'59", at bridge near Highway 10 at km 56.4, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) downstream from Rio de Caguana, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) north of Utuado plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--66.0 mi² (170.9 km²) this excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²) upstream from Lago Garzas to Rio Guayanes in the Rio Tallaboa basin.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
20...	1230	114	225	7.50	29.0	68	7.2	93	250	K16000	K12000
DEC 21...	1155	144	248	7.20	25.5	4.1	7.9	96	<10	28000	7800
FEB 1988											
22...	1100	227	304	7.00	23.5	36	9.2	107	33	29000	28000
APR 20...	1000	81	252	7.10	25.5	18	7.7	93	<10	K11000	4500
JUN 21...	0910	107	194	6.80	24.0	120	7.8	92	<10	25000	24000
AUG 22...	1140	44	304	7.90	27.5	6.8	7.2	46	<10	29000	11000

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
20...	87	13	23	7.1	13	0.6	2.3	74	<0.5	16	10
DEC 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	79	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	72	--	--	--
APR 20...	85	9	22	7.2	12	0.6	1.9	67	<0.5	22	11
JUN 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	57	--	--	--
AUG 22...	110	15	28	8.6	16	0.7	2.3	89	--	26	18

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C. SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
20...	0.10	27	143	44	14	1.17	0.03	1.20	0.08	0.82
DEC 21...	--	--	--	--	17	1.25	0.05	1.30	0.09	0.21
FEB 1988										
22...	--	--	--	--	--	1.02	0.08	1.10	0.59	0.41
APR 20...	0.20	24	146	32	26	1.57	0.03	1.60	0.07	0.33
JUN 21...	--	--	--	--	148	1.08	0.02	1.10	0.04	1.20
AUG 22...	0.10	27	180	21	6	1.11	0.09	1.20	0.20	0.50

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50026050 RIO CAONILLAS ABOVE LAGO CAONILLAS NEAR JAYUYA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°13'26", long 66°38'22", 300 ft (91 m) off Highway 531, 700 ft (213 m) upstream from Lago Caonillas, 3.3 mi (5.3 km) northwest of Jayuya plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--40.4 mi² (104.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
21...	0730	105	160	7.40	23.5	3.2	8.0	96	<10	600	K1200
DEC											
22...	0740	75	154	7.10	22.0	0.6	8.3	98	<10	390	K1200
FEB 1988											
23...	1405	28	225	7.80	25.0	0.9	7.9	98	13	K20	K45
APR											
21...	1315	36	200	7.40	27.5	1.8	7.1	97	<10	K760	270
JUN											
22...	1205	35	196	7.30	26.0	26	7.5	93	13	2100	410
AUG											
23...	0820	E200	173	7.80	24.0	1.0	8.3	101	<10	4200	4800

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
21...	62	8	16	5.3	10	0.6	1.5	54	<0.5	13	7.6
DEC											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	53	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--
APR											
21...	69	5	18	5.9	10	0.5	1.4	56	<0.5	15	11
JUN											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	62	--	--	--
AUG											
23...	64	0	17	5.3	8.8	0.5	1.3	59	--	16	10

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
21...	0.10	24	110	31	4	0.69	0.01	0.70	0.02	0.18
DEC										
22...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.68	0.02	0.70	0.01	0.19
FEB 1988										
23...	--	--	--	--	3	0.48	0.02	0.50	0.02	0.28
APR										
21...	0.10	23	123	12	92	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.05	0.25
JUN										
22...	--	--	--	--	7	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.03	0.27
AUG										
23...	0.10	21	131	--	5	0.19	0.01	0.20	0.04	0.26

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027250 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BELOW LAGO DOS BOCAS NEAR FLORIDA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'50", long 66°40'02", at pedestrian bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from Lago Dos Bocas and 6.6 mi (10.6 km) west of Florida plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--169 mi² (436 km²) does not include 6.0 mi² (15.6 km²) above Lago Garzas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1970-71, 1974 to current year.

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
20...	1000	E1000	199	6.80	26.5	17	4.5	56	<10	290	280
DEC											
21...	1000	E1500	172	6.40	25.0	23	5.1	61	<10	660	980
FEB 1988											
22...	1245	E1700	212	6.50	24.5	--	4.5	54	--	K27	K100
APR											
20...	1235	E1900	198	6.60	25.5	28	4.9	59	<10	K710	K1400
JUN											
21...	1125	35	250	6.40	27.0	5.7	5.1	64	<10	K70	K190
AUG											
23...	1130	87	237	7.30	28.5	15	5.4	69	16	K150	920

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
20...	77	8	21	5.9	11	0.6	2.4	69	<0.5	11	9.4
DEC											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	54	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	61	--	--	--
APR											
20...	72	4	19	5.9	10	0.5	2.0	61	<0.5	15	9.7
JUN											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	77	--	--	--
AUG											
23...	90	29	24	7.4	12	0.6	2.0	84	--	11	8.6

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
20...	0.10	22	124	--	102	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.08	0.62
DEC										
21...	--	--	--	--	16	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.02	0.18
FEB 1988										
22...	--	--	--	--	29	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.02	0.28
APR										
20...	0.10	19	121	--	36	0.48	0.02	0.50	0.14	0.16
JUN										
21...	--	--	--	--	11	0.17	0.03	0.20	0.22	0.28
AUG										
23...	0.10	23	125	29	35	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.14	0.36

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'29", long 66°41'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream from Rio Tanama, 4.0 mi (6.4 km) south of Arecibo and 6.7 mi (10.8 km) above mouth, and 10.2 mi (16.4 km) downstream from Lago Dos Bocas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--200 mi² (520 km²), approximately, of which an undetermined amount does not contribute directly to surface runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 30 ft (9 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Flow regulated by Lago Dos Bocas Dam 10.2 mi (16.4 km) upstream.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--6 years (1983-88), 476 ft³/s (13.48 m³/s), 32.32 in/yr (821 mm/yr), 344,900 acre-ft/yr (425 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 45,800 ft³/s (1,300 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 18.22 ft (5.553 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 2,400 ft³/s (68.0 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 30 ft³/s (0.850 m³/s), Mar. 20, 1986.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 4,300 ft³/s (122 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	2215	*9,680	274	*12.99	3.959						

Minimum discharge, 36 ft³/s (1.020 m³/s), Oct. 11.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	145	111	1160	660	662	752	63	423	79	67	432	215
2	276	59	949	1200	809	115	51	685	86	61	257	178
3	92	198	831	451	928	64	51	178	139	809	88	218
4	245	321	708	815	544	56	368	545	185	386	86	957
5	153	400	175	469	727	56	232	520	66	509	147	239
6	107	542	186	331	243	125	335	329	163	116	306	147
7	270	106	781	459	170	509	109	115	299	585	68	100
8	331	72	1500	751	585	218	105	95	129	228	397	218
9	525	299	1180	572	113	115	358	102	321	842	227	691
10	1020	676	849	107	55	98	529	860	369	290	170	681
11	398	117	584	418	570	252	424	1940	93	88	172	471
12	573	451	200	715	577	576	93	1260	70	65	101	381
13	1080	642	276	441	329	146	497	1220	65	381	77	86
14	781	125	190	409	186	534	405	402	78	157	67	81
15	701	244	86	504	337	661	346	170	71	499	86	141
16	681	803	409	489	123	109	501	429	68	170	288	395
17	575	872	377	268	171	64	328	583	435	117	172	390
18	92	607	426	312	105	157	461	639	111	76	581	171
19	702	222	293	438	518	67	662	726	70	73	117	532
20	847	296	1040	299	84	54	921	144	66	306	761	829
21	127	140	740	372	202	525	1380	561	246	218	300	958
22	85	59	862	479	528	516	1360	837	483	421	78	1150
23	834	537	717	101	674	61	674	562	593	367	533	977
24	285	780	757	73	441	63	503	128	462	105	363	730
25	103	633	184	738	627	54	80	82	95	74	2920	517
26	158	162	278	493	628	54	129	76	71	396	1710	883
27	524	1960	203	241	642	63	646	79	91	91	357	757
28	413	3190	589	503	208	139	564	70	750	440	208	876
29	487	964	457	251	628	128	789	110	417	113	868	797
30	739	1020	403	135	---	536	1000	297	121	330	1810	723
31	504	---	279	59	---	291	---	212	---	120	937	---
TOTAL	13853	16608	17669	13553	12414	7158	13964	14379	6292	8500	14684	15489
MEAN	447	554	570	437	428	231	465	464	210	274	474	516
MAX	1080	3190	1500	1200	928	752	1380	1940	750	842	2920	1150
MIN	85	59	86	59	55	54	51	70	65	61	67	81
AC-FT	27480	32940	35050	26880	24620	14200	27700	28520	12480	16860	29130	30720
CFSM	3.19	3.95	4.07	3.12	3.06	1.65	3.32	3.31	1.50	1.96	3.38	3.69
IN.	3.68	4.41	4.69	3.60	3.30	1.90	3.71	3.82	1.67	2.26	3.90	4.12

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 151217 MEAN 414 MAX 3190 MIN 38 AC-FT 299900 CFSM 2.96 IN. 40.18
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 154563 MEAN 422 MAX 3190 MIN 51 AC-FT 306600 CFSM 3.02 IN. 41.07

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50027750 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO ABOVE ARECIBO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1982 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 15	1032	108.43	243	26.5	APR, 14	1026	79.6	240	25.0
DEC, 16	1107	99.8	290	25.0	MAY, 10	1002	86.4	276	25.5
JAN, 20	1017	49.3	224	23.5	JUN, 02	1032	63.0	286	27.5
FEB, 22	1027	98.9	229	24.0	JUL, 06	1009	98.8	263	26.0
MAR, 14	1043	56.5	307	25.0	AUG, 05	1025	65.9	252	27.5

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'02", long 66°46'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on downstream side of left abutment of bridge on Highway 111, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from natural tunnel, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) northeast of Angeles, and 5.8 mi (9.3 km) northwest of Utuado.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.4 mi² (47.7 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1944 to June 1958 (daily stage and two to four measurements per month by Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority), November 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 938.32 ft (286.00 m) above mean sea level. Datum of gage was lowered 3.00 ft (0.914 m) on Oct. 1978. Prior to Nov. 17, 1966, non-recording gage and Nov. 17, 1966 to Sept. 30, 1978 recording gage, both at present site.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--28 years (1961-88), 48.3 ft³/s (1.368 m³/s), 35.65 in/yr (906 mm/yr), 34,990 acre-ft/yr (43.1 hm³/yr) median of yearly mean discharges, 48 ft³/s (1.36 m³/s), 34,800 acre-ft/yr (43 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 12,190 ft³/s (345 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 17.45 ft (5.319 m) new datum in use, from floodmark and recorder, from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 6.6 ft³/s (0.187 m³/s), June 12, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov.27	1600	*2,910	82.4	*11.55	3.520						

Minimum discharge, 12 ft³/s (0.340 m³/s), June 4-11.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	23	61	52	84	42	28	19	20	14	22	16	140
2	54	37	66	67	39	27	18	19	14	21	16	e60
3	28	35	50	44	41	22	18	18	14	21	27	e45
4	24	29	45	39	34	21	18	18	13	20	25	e41
5	23	26	86	37	31	21	21	18	13	46	17	e39
6	22	25	79	36	30	20	23	17	12	27	17	38
7	81	81	54	35	29	20	18	17	13	20	17	40
8	140	42	48	33	28	20	17	16	13	19	17	37
9	45	33	44	33	27	19	17	23	12	19	17	42
10	57	28	42	32	27	19	16	73	12	19	18	61
11	63	26	41	32	27	19	21	56	25	19	21	58
12	39	27	39	31	29	19	28	31	68	19	16	67
13	29	29	38	30	29	19	23	22	49	24	15	46
14	63	29	36	65	29	19	17	22	26	26	18	40
15	43	37	37	44	26	18	45	22	21	18	30	73
16	35	29	39	35	25	18	38	18	22	19	21	60
17	28	53	35	42	24	19	33	17	20	147	36	56
18	39	32	34	35	24	19	86	16	54	e41	68	47
19	31	27	111	36	23	17	38	16	51	e24	23	44
20	26	24	84	33	24	17	97	16	44	21	38	93
21	43	24	50	31	23	17	108	15	42	21	31	167
22	47	23	41	31	23	16	83	14	30	22	25	107
23	53	24	37	31	23	16	42	14	25	19	29	213
24	35	90	36	30	23	16	28	14	30	18	403	119
25	27	53	51	30	23	16	23	14	68	20	265	104
26	25	36	35	29	25	16	21	20	40	18	105	189
27	26	351	34	29	34	26	20	26	28	18	98	e98
28	24	113	33	29	23	70	27	54	31	20	84	e70
29	69	67	32	35	22	31	30	32	25	31	55	e60
30	70	57	32	30	---	21	23	17	23	19	46	e52
31	95	---	70	29	---	21	---	15	---	17	60	---
TOTAL	1407	1548	1511	1157	807	667	1016	710	852	815	1674	2306
MEAN	45.4	51.6	48.7	37.3	27.8	21.5	33.9	22.9	28.4	26.3	54.0	76.9
MAX	140	351	111	84	42	70	108	73	68	147	403	213
MIN	22	23	32	29	22	16	16	14	12	17	15	37
AC-FT	2790	3070	3000	2290	1600	1320	2020	1410	1690	1620	3320	4570
CFSM	2.47	2.80	2.65	2.03	1.51	1.17	1.84	1.24	1.54	1.43	2.93	4.18
IN.	2.84	3.13	3.05	2.34	1.63	1.35	2.05	1.44	1.72	1.65	3.38	4.66

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 13146 MEAN 36.0 MAX 351 MIN 14 AC-FT 26080 CFSM 1.96 IN. 26.58
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 14470 MEAN 39.5 MAX 403 MIN 12 AC-FT 28700 CFSM 2.15 IN. 29.25

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1968 to current year.

REMARKS.--Sediment samples were collected by a local observer on a weekly basis and during high flow events. Estimates for period of missing daily record were made from a sediment transport curve developed from a period of record over 5 years.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 20,400 mg/L November 27, 1968; minimum daily mean, 0 mg/L during water year 1985.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 167,000 tons (152,000 tonnes) May 18, 1985, minimum daily, 0.0 ton (0.0 tonne) several days during many years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 1,760 mg/L June 02, 1987; minimum daily mean, 2.0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 5,930 tons (5,380 tonnes) June 02, 1987; minimum daily, 0.08 ton (0.07 tonne) several days.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEARS OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
02...	1115	23	160	8.00	24.5	6.7	9.0	110	16	430	320
DEC											
16...	1220	38	154	7.90	23.5	3.4	9.1	109	34	210	200
FEB 1988											
04...	1400	35	154	7.90	23.5	2.3	8.8	106	<10	K880	K170
APR											
14...	1150	17	166	7.50	23.0	22	9.0	107	29	K730	600
JUN											
09...	1315	13	179	7.80	27.5	3.4	8.2	106	29	K80	380
AUG											
04...	1400	20	163	7.40	27.0	22	7.9	101	<10	K1100	52

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
02...	65	8	16	6.0	8.2	0.5	1.9	57	<0.5	13	7.9
DEC											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	54	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52	--	--	--
APR											
14...	61	6	15	5.6	8.2	0.5	2.1	48	<0.5	14	8.4
JUN											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	56	--	--	--
AUG											
04...	63	7	16	5.6	7.8	0.4	2.0	57	--	12	8.2

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	23	27	1.7	61	250	41	52	90	13
2	54	156	64	37	55	5.5	66	229	107
3	28	37	2.8	35	60	5.7	50	100	14
4	24	30	1.9	29	40	3.1	45	70	8.5
5	23	27	1.7	26	36	2.5	86	463	382
6	22	26	1.5	25	32	2.2	79	317	168
7	81	438	554	81	388	460	54	100	15
8	140	1160	2910	42	70	7.9	48	80	10
9	45	150	18	33	40	3.6	44	70	8.3
10	57	152	61	28	25	1.9	42	65	7.4
11	63	245	88	26	15	1.1	41	60	6.6
12	39	70	12	27	15	1.1	39	60	6.3
13	29	40	4.2	29	12	.94	38	57	5.8
14	63	204	124	29	25	2.0	36	56	5.4
15	43	100	12	37	107	30	37	60	6.0
16	35	50	4.7	29	40	3.1	39	60	6.3
17	28	38	2.9	53	109	40	35	55	5.2
18	39	70	7.4	32	40	3.5	34	50	4.6
19	31	50	4.2	27	35	2.6	111	352	206
20	26	35	2.5	24	32	2.1	84	250	57
21	43	124	51	24	30	1.9	50	75	10
22	47	153	45	23	29	1.8	41	60	6.6
23	53	150	53	24	30	1.9	37	55	5.5
24	35	60	5.7	90	268	133	36	55	5.3
25	27	35	2.6	53	150	21	51	116	24
26	25	32	2.2	36	30	2.9	35	52	4.9
27	26	30	2.1	351	3440	16200	34	52	4.8
28	24	30	1.9	113	349	128	33	50	4.5
29	69	358	376	67	130	24	32	45	3.9
30	70	318	255	57	100	15	32	45	3.9
31	95	364	219	---	---	---	70	177	45
TOTAL	1407	---	4892.0	1548	---	17149.34	1511	---	1160.8

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	84	199	58	42	30	3.4	28	25	1.9
2	67	154	35	39	35	3.7	27	35	2.6
3	44	62	7.4	41	22	2.4	22	27	1.6
4	39	59	6.2	34	10	.92	21	25	1.4
5	37	55	5.5	31	9	.75	21	22	1.2
6	36	52	5.1	30	8	.65	20	22	1.2
7	35	50	4.7	29	9	.70	20	20	1.1
8	33	50	4.5	28	8	.60	20	19	1.0
9	33	47	4.2	27	8	.58	19	17	.87
10	32	45	3.9	27	8	.58	19	12	.62
11	32	42	3.6	27	7	.51	19	12	.62
12	31	40	3.3	29	5	.39	19	11	.56
13	30	40	3.2	29	6	.47	19	11	.56
14	65	223	154	29	7	.55	19	10	.51
15	44	60	7.1	26	8	.56	18	10	.49
16	35	50	4.7	25	8	.54	18	10	.49
17	42	49	5.6	24	10	.65	19	10	.51
18	35	47	4.4	24	10	.65	19	10	.51
19	36	45	4.4	23	10	.62	17	10	.46
20	33	42	3.7	24	12	.78	17	10	.46
21	31	42	3.5	23	11	.68	17	10	.46
22	31	42	3.5	23	11	.68	16	10	.43
23	31	40	3.3	23	10	.62	16	9	.39
24	30	40	3.2	23	10	.62	16	9	.39
25	30	40	3.2	23	10	.62	16	9	.39
26	29	40	3.1	25	10	.68	16	8	.35
27	29	39	3.1	34	10	.92	26	30	2.1
28	29	39	3.1	23	10	.62	70	215	111
29	35	37	3.5	22	10	.59	31	50	4.2
30	30	33	2.7	---	---	---	21	20	1.1
31	29	30	2.3	---	---	---	21	15	.85
TOTAL	1157	---	363.0	807	---	26.03	667	---	140.32

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	19	15	.77	20	25	1.4	14	12	.45
2	18	12	.58	19	20	1.0	14	12	.45
3	18	12	.58	18	20	.97	14	12	.45
4	18	11	.53	18	20	.97	13	11	.39
5	21	20	1.1	18	20	.97	13	11	.39
6	23	60	3.7	17	20	.92	12	10	.32
7	18	42	2.0	17	20	.92	13	10	.35
8	17	40	1.8	16	20	.86	13	10	.35
9	17	35	1.6	23	35	2.2	12	10	.32
10	16	30	1.3	73	384	584	12	10	.32
11	21	30	1.7	56	144	38	25	45	9.0
12	28	40	3.0	31	50	4.2	68	289	232
13	23	40	2.5	22	20	1.2	49	160	21
14	17	20	.92	22	15	.89	26	35	2.5
15	45	121	37	22	15	.89	21	25	1.4
16	38	80	8.2	18	15	.73	22	20	1.2
17	33	60	5.3	17	15	.69	20	25	1.4
18	86	391	338	16	15	.65	54	142	54
19	38	50	5.1	16	15	.65	51	130	29
20	97	628	934	16	15	.65	44	87	14
21	108	323	207	15	15	.61	42	60	6.8
22	83	288	164	14	15	.57	30	40	3.2
23	42	70	7.9	14	15	.57	25	45	3.0
24	28	35	2.6	14	15	.57	30	50	4.1
25	23	30	1.9	14	15	.57	68	236	207
26	21	25	1.4	20	33	3.6	40	70	7.6
27	20	25	1.4	26	60	4.2	28	40	3.0
28	27	40	2.9	54	244	161	31	45	3.8
29	30	50	4.1	32	35	3.0	25	18	1.2
30	23	35	2.2	17	20	.92	23	10	.62
31	---	---	---	15	15	.61	---	---	---
TOTAL	1016	---	1745.08	710	---	818.98	852	---	609.61

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028000 RIO TANAMA NEAR UTUADO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	22	10	.59	16	18	.78	140	1080	2580
2	21	10	.57	16	18	.78	60	160	26
3	21	10	.57	27	35	2.6	45	100	12
4	20	10	.54	25	35	2.4	41	75	8.3
5	46	129	54	17	20	.92	39	60	6.3
6	27	40	2.9	17	18	.83	38	55	5.6
7	20	28	1.5	17	18	.83	40	55	5.9
8	19	24	1.2	17	18	.83	37	50	5.0
9	19	22	1.1	17	18	.83	42	50	5.7
10	19	20	1.0	18	18	.87	61	120	20
11	19	20	1.0	21	27	1.5	58	105	16
12	19	20	1.0	16	17	.73	67	160	29
13	24	35	2.3	15	15	.61	46	80	9.9
14	26	50	3.5	18	20	.97	40	65	7.0
15	18	20	.97	30	50	4.1	73	295	215
16	19	20	1.0	21	20	1.1	60	125	20
17	147	1140	3650	36	82	24	56	120	18
18	41	120	13	68	172	51	47	100	13
19	24	50	3.2	23	22	1.4	44	70	8.3
20	21	20	1.1	38	97	35	93	508	471
21	21	25	1.4	31	50	4.2	167	814	2200
22	22	30	1.8	25	35	2.4	107	419	355
23	19	25	1.3	29	60	4.7	213	1130	2510
24	18	22	1.1	403	3270	14600	119	363	163
25	20	22	1.2	265	1790	3370	104	302	144
26	18	21	1.0	105	295	95	189	1580	6440
27	18	21	1.0	98	376	183	98	350	93
28	20	20	1.1	84	256	93	70	200	38
29	31	61	13	55	110	16	60	130	21
30	19	22	1.1	46	80	9.9	52	100	14
31	17	20	.92	60	150	24	---	---	---
TOTAL	815	---	3765.96	1674	---	18534.28	2306	---	15460.0
YEAR	14470		64665.40						

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50028400 RIO TANAMA AT CHARCO HONDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'52", long 66°42'52", on right bank at abandoned power house at Charco Hondo, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) upstream from mouth, and 4 mi (6 km) south of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--57.6 mi² (149.2 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1969 to June 1971, October 1981 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 60 ft (18 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Diversion 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream for municipal supply of Arecibo.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--8 years (1970,1982-88), 91.0 ft³/s (2.578 m³/s), 21.45 in/yr (545 mm/yr), 65,930 acre-ft/yr (81.3 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 15,000 ft³/s (425 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 17.95 ft (5.471 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 14 ft³/s (0.396 m³/s), Mar. 30, 31, 1987.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,000 ft³/s (56.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	1800	*2,830	80.2	*11.21	3.417	Aug. 24	2115	2,600	73.7	10.93	3.331

Minimum discharge, 8.7 ft³/s (0.246 m³/s), Mar. 4.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	34	118	55	210	41	17	16	38	20	e38	e30	164
2	57	54	71	229	37	24	14	29	18	e37	e28	129
3	67	54	165	109	63	17	14	27	14	e36	e28	87
4	56	48	64	72	72	16	14	29	14	e35	e50	62
5	43	38	82	60	35	16	13	20	13	e34	e30	54
6	41	37	115	56	30	15	19	18	13	e77	25	52
7	114	64	83	51	25	15	13	17	21	e46	26	47
8	242	87	62	47	25	15	12	17	35	e34	33	56
9	163	58	53	44	25	14	11	51	39	e32	25	55
10	89	66	48	42	23	14	10	228	38	e32	22	89
11	124	37	46	41	22	14	11	280	41	e32	27	99
12	99	34	47	41	22	14	17	155	76	e32	22	85
13	68	37	43	39	22	13	23	92	e112	e32	20	76
14	163	33	41	49	24	14	13	85	e80	e41	19	61
15	228	37	43	72	21	14	21	100	e43	e44	25	70
16	132	46	44	39	20	13	76	62	e35	e30	29	88
17	78	84	40	44	19	14	38	41	e37	e32	23	57
18	65	55	38	40	19	14	91	32	e34	e250	83	57
19	75	40	128	39	17	12	93	26	e90	e86	36	47
20	60	33	164	36	17	12	207	23	e86	e70	26	146
21	54	31	104	33	17	12	314	21	e74	e36	43	235
22	84	29	64	31	17	12	222	20	e70	e36	29	158
23	74	29	53	30	17	11	122	26	e50	e37	29	259
24	85	74	49	28	18	12	58	27	e42	e33	366	148
25	56	116	69	29	18	11	49	20	e54	e31	703	130
26	46	53	50	27	19	11	49	19	e113	e34	178	202
27	40	391	45	27	30	16	49	61	e68	e31	134	182
28	38	214	43	27	21	47	46	43	e47	e31	134	172
29	49	83	41	33	18	45	70	57	e52	e35	122	112
30	87	64	41	33	---	21	52	24	e42	e55	109	89
31	103	---	103	28	---	19	---	21	---	e35	82	---
TOTAL	2714	2144	2094	1686	754	514	1757	1709	1471	1444	2536	3268
MEAN	87.5	71.5	67.5	54.4	26.0	16.6	58.6	55.1	49.0	46.6	81.8	109
MAX	242	391	165	229	72	47	314	280	113	250	703	259
MIN	34	29	38	27	17	11	10	17	13	30	19	47
AC-FT	5380	4250	4150	3340	1500	1020	3490	3390	2920	2860	5030	6480
CFSM	1.52	1.24	1.17	.94	.45	.29	1.02	.96	.85	.81	1.42	1.89
IN.	1.75	1.38	1.35	1.09	.49	.33	1.13	1.10	.95	.93	1.64	2.11

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 21141 MEAN 57.9 MAX 478 MIN 14 AC-FT 41930 CFSM 1.01 IN. 13.65
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 22091 MEAN 60.4 MAX 703 MIN 10 AC-FT 43820 CFSM 1.05 IN. 14.27

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN
 50028400 RIO TANAMA AT CHARCO HONDO, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS MARCH 1983 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 15	1238	226	242	24.5	APR, 14	1208	11.7	278	24.0
DEC, 16	1313	47.4	270	23.5	MAY, 10	1234	66.5	287	24.0
JAN, 20	1313	34.3	255	22.5	JUN, 02	1329	15.4	283	26.0
FEB, 22	1256	15.8	275	22.0	JUL, 06	1248	196	255	24.5
MAR, 14	1329	12.5	297	24.5	AUG, 05	1257	28.8	271	26.0

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

50029000 RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO AT CENTRAL CAMBALACHE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'20", long 66°42'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at bridge on unimproved road, about 500 ft (152 m) upstream from Central Cambalache, near Highway 2, 8.3 mi (13.4 km) downstream from Dos Bocas Reservoir, 1.9 mi (3.1 km) downstream from Rio Tanama, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) southeast of Arecibo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--200 mi² (520 km²), approximately.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1963-66, 1969 to current year.

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
19...	1100	187	299	7.50	26.0	7.4	7.2	88	<10	1100	540
DEC 18...	0945	202	224	7.00	24.0	12	7.9	93	33	K150	400
FEB 1988											
22...	1500	122	265	7.40	26.0	--	9.5	116	--	220	K54
APR 25...	1035	155	282	7.20	25.5	12	8.3	99	<10	460	240
JUN 17...	1015	E200	298	6.90	27.0	4.0	8.3	102	<10	600	K140
AUG 23...	1015	167	272	6.80	26.5	2.0	7.8	95	13	480	200

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
19...	140	14	49	5.3	7.9	0.3	1.7	130	<0.5	10	11
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	84	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	98	--	--	--
APR 25...	130	13	41	5.6	7.9	0.3	1.7	100	<0.5	14	9.4
JUN 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
AUG 23...	110	11	35	6.6	9.3	0.4	1.6	110	--	12	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
19...	0.10	15	178	90	7	0.69	0.01	0.70	0.04	0.16
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	14	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.02	0.18
FEB 1988										
22...	--	--	--	--	--	0.49	0.01	0.50	0.02	0.28
APR 25...	0.10	15	162	68	60	0.68	0.02	0.70	0.03	0.17
JUN 17...	--	--	--	--	6	0.39	0.01	0.40	0.01	0.59
AUG 23...	0.10	17	162	73	7	0.39	0.01	0.40	0.02	0.28

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 14.--Río Grande de Manatí basin.

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN
50030700 RIO OROCOVIS NEAR OROCOVIS, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'20", long 66°22'58", at flat low bridge about 300 ft (91 m) northwest of Highway 568, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) north of Orocovis plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--10.1 mi² (26.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987	08...	0740	7.4	289	7.60	1.5	7.8	94	28	K890	2550
DEC 09...	1355	14	234	7.70	23.0	0.8	7.7	94	10	2900	--
FEB 1988	16...	1315	13	273	8.40	17	8.8	107	10	K960	330
APR 07...	1345	8.9	287	8.10	25.5	5.5	8.4	108	14	K770	330
JUN 02...	1150	5.9	332	7.50	26.5	1.7	8.2	104	33	590	320
AUG 18...	1120	11	245	7.10	24.0	36	8.0	98	21	53000	25000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB TOT (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987	130	12	33	12	14	0.5	2.0	120	<0.5	11	13
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	89	--	--	--
FEB 1988	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
APR 07...	130	7	31	12	13	0.5	1.5	110	<0.5	9.2	14
JUN 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
AUG 18...	100	9	25	10	12	0.5	2.1	85	--	12	12

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987	0.20	32	189	3.8	7	0.89	0.01	0.90	0.01	0.29
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	14	0.99	0.01	1.00	0.01	0.19
FEB 1988	--	--	--	--	17	1.18	0.02	1.20	0.01	0.49
APR 07...	0.20	34	187	4.5	1	0.89	0.01	0.90	0.02	0.28
JUN 02...	--	--	--	--	6	1.19	0.01	1.20	0.03	0.17
AUG 18...	0.10	28	158	4.6	30	0.78	0.02	0.80	0.22	0.08

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'45", long 66°24'47", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) downstream from Quebrada Perchas, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) upstream from Rio Sana Muerto, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) south of Morovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--55.2 mi² (143.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1965 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 440 ft (134 m), from topographic map. Feb. 2, 1966 to Apr. 27, 1967, staff gage read twice daily.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Public water-supply pumpage, about 300 ft (91 m) above the station, influences low-flow discharges.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--23 years (1966-88), 106 ft³/s (3.002 m³/s), 26.08 in/yr (662 mm/yr), 76,800 acre-ft/yr (94.7 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 90 ft³/s (2.55 m³/s), 65,200 acre-ft/yr (80 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 48,000 ft³/s (1,359 m³/s), May 18, 1985, gage height, 17.89 ft (5.453 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of computations of flow over broad-crested weir and step-backwater analysis; minimum discharges, 4.4 ft³/s (0.125 m³/s), Apr. 15, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,500 ft³/s (99.1 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov.27	1445	*4,540	129	*5.73	1.747

Minimum discharge, 23 ft³/s (0.651 m³/s), Aug. 3.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39	37	95	862	389	69	49	60	39	44	27	46
2	34	36	82	450	413	79	46	58	37	50	25	47
3	34	e34	73	208	444	65	44	55	38	46	36	41
4	69	e50	68	154	289	61	43	53	36	36	113	40
5	70	37	77	134	163	59	43	53	35	35	38	39
6	36	92	81	121	127	58	63	51	35	32	29	37
7	32	65	63	113	110	58	61	52	36	32	27	36
8	95	47	74	108	100	57	44	50	35	31	29	41
9	117	39	61	103	92	55	41	67	34	30	29	44
10	46	37	55	102	88	55	40	199	33	30	30	93
11	37	35	55	97	85	54	40	184	37	30	56	329
12	42	35	102	94	82	54	58	117	44	34	31	204
13	35	47	65	89	82	54	46	75	40	30	27	117
14	33	36	55	93	80	56	42	68	36	31	25	82
15	35	33	61	85	79	52	59	64	41	30	24	66
16	38	33	65	81	78	52	141	63	46	27	27	57
17	40	66	52	120	76	59	334	56	37	28	52	56
18	139	106	49	105	76	56	413	54	34	33	261	51
19	132	72	98	100	72	50	392	52	34	31	70	46
20	59	49	304	87	71	48	231	52	34	29	41	61
21	191	41	199	81	69	48	194	50	36	27	34	49
22	157	40	136	77	68	46	350	50	40	28	63	117
23	71	39	111	73	68	44	170	47	38	28	135	282
24	56	317	93	71	72	48	112	47	46	27	705	212
25	57	332	157	73	67	46	91	46	82	30	558	102
26	47	138	108	69	66	61	79	45	88	27	209	80
27	41	1020	97	66	149	56	72	44	46	27	116	178
28	41	435	87	77	87	65	67	42	39	28	81	72
29	42	175	78	141	73	71	66	42	37	31	63	88
30	48	119	70	92	---	64	62	44	36	28	55	75
31	39	---	308	98	---	63	---	42	---	27	49	---
TOTAL	1952	3642	3079	4224	3715	1763	3493	1982	1229	977	3065	2788
MEAN	63.0	121	99.3	136	128	56.9	116	63.9	41.0	31.5	98.9	92.9
MAX	191	1020	308	862	444	79	413	199	88	50	705	329
MIN	32	33	49	66	66	44	40	42	33	27	24	36
AC-FT	3870	7220	6110	8380	7370	3500	6930	3930	2440	1940	6080	5530
CFSM	1.14	2.20	1.80	2.47	2.32	1.03	2.11	1.16	.74	.57	1.79	1.68
IN.	1.32	2.45	2.07	2.85	2.50	1.19	2.35	1.34	.83	.66	2.07	1.88

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 35756 MEAN 98.0 MAX 1310 MIN 23 AC-FT 70920 CFSM 1.77 IN. 24.10
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 31909 MEAN 87.2 MAX 1020 MIN 24 AC-FT 63290 CFSM 1.58 IN. 21.50

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50031200 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI NEAR MOROVIS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1968 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
08...	1100	31	250	8.00	27.0	7.5	8.5	107	23	800	K120
DEC											
09...	1110	61	245	7.60	24.0	6.7	8.3	99	15	K1000	K240
FEB 1988											
16...	1050	78	260	7.80	23.0	71	8.4	99	<10	K90	K170
APR											
07...	1100	60	242	7.90	24.5	16	9.4	114	<10	K16000	K180
JUN											
02...	0920	39	192	7.30	26.5	1.7	7.0	88	29	K80	K73
AUG											
18...	0910	263	140	6.20	23.0	300	8.4	99	98	K93000	100000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
08...	100	3	24	10	12	0.5	2.0	98	<0.5	9.8	13
DEC											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	94	--	--	--
APR											
07...	100	2	24	10	12	0.5	2.0	92	<0.5	8.6	14
JUN											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	94	--	--	--
AUG											
18...	56	16	13	5.8	9.6	0.6	3.5	36	--	17	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
08...	0.20	29	159	13	17	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.07	0.13
DEC										
09...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.01	0.19
FEB 1988										
16...	--	--	--	--	60	1.67	0.03	1.70	0.06	1.4
APR										
07...	0.20	28	158	25	16	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.02	0.28
JUN										
02...	--	--	--	--	5	0.39	0.01	0.40	0.02	1.4
AUG										
18...	0.10	16	100	71	177	1.19	0.11	1.30	0.25	2.5

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

99

50032290 LAGO EL GUINEO AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'41", long 66°51'48", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, at damsite on Rio Toro Negro, 3.0 mi (4.8 km) northwest from Villalba plaza and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) northeast of Cerro Maravillas. The reservoir itself fixes the territorial limits between the Municipality of Ciales and Orocovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.64 mi² (4.248 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1988 to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder and Data Collection Platform. Datum of gage is 2,900.00 ft (883.920 m) above mean sea level; gage readings has been adjusted to elevations above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Guineo was completed in 1931. It provides a maximum storage of approximately 2,180 ac-ft (2.688 hm³) for power and irrigation. Waters are discharged through an outlet power tunnel into the Toro Negro river and conveyed to the head water works of Toro Negro Hydroelectric Plant No.2, for energy generation at Toro Negro Hydroelectric plant No.1, and are discharged into the Guayabal Reservoir to be later used for irrigation at South Coast Irrigation System. The dam is rockfill with a vertical concrete corewall, rock toes, and riprap facing of upstream slope, with a total length of 565 ft (172 m), a maximum structural height of 125 ft (38.1 m) to top of corewall. The uncontrolled morning-glory tunnel spillway crest has an elevation of 2,966 ft (904.03 m) above mean sea level and a design capacity of 7,000 ft³/s. The dam is owned by Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Maximum elevation, 2,943.67 ft (897.23 m), Aug. 26; minimum elevation, 2,919.79 ft (899.95 m), May 27.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,872	0	2,943	1,029
2,919	361	2,950	1,308
2,925	491	2,960	1,798

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1								---	2927.52	2927.00	2926.51	2942.37
2								---	2926.81	2927.34	2926.60	2941.78
3								---	2926.15	2927.53	2926.97	2942.05
4								---	2924.87	2927.84	2927.11	2942.28
5								---	2924.99	2928.06	2927.20	2941.38
6								---	2924.45	2927.79	2927.28	2940.56
7								---	2923.83	2926.84	2927.37	2939.75
8								---	2923.54	2926.99	2926.76	2939.09
9								---	2923.46	2927.12	2926.85	2938.35
10								---	2922.98	2925.94	2927.71	2937.85
11								---	2923.26	2926.07	2927.83	2939.13
12								---	2925.64	2926.19	2927.92	2940.11
13								---	2925.33	2926.20	2928.01	2939.72
14								2933.32	2923.96	2926.44	2928.38	2939.55
15								2933.38	2923.93	2926.55	2928.53	2939.05
16								2932.88	2923.98	2926.76	2928.21	2938.60
17								2932.23	2924.10	2926.91	2929.08	2938.92
18								2931.73	2924.22	2927.03	2930.02	2939.17
19								2931.53	2924.34	2927.14	2930.16	2938.72
20								2931.02	2924.56	2927.25	2930.28	2938.20
21								2931.12	2924.76	2927.35	2930.38	2937.78
22								2931.20	2925.11	2927.02	2931.37	2938.09
23								2930.49	2925.43	2927.12	2930.48	2938.19
24								2929.85	2925.83	2927.25	2942.43	2939.30
25								2929.06	2926.01	2927.35	2943.52	2939.69
26								2928.41	2926.23	2927.46	2943.07	2939.80
27								2927.85	2926.42	2927.56	2942.12	2938.94
28								2927.95	2926.57	2927.35	2942.43	2939.23
29								2928.03	2926.69	2927.44	2941.51	2939.50
30								2928.16	2926.48	2927.60	2940.64	2940.13
31								2927.59	---	2926.93	2942.48	---
TOTAL								---	87751.45	90739.42	90889.21	88187.28
MEAN								---	2925.05	2927.08	2931.91	2939.58
MAX								---	2927.52	2928.06	2943.52	2942.37

WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 410313.16 MEAN 2930.81 MAX 2943.52

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50032590 LAGO DE MATRULLAS AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'46", Long 66°28'50", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, in concrete house at damsite, and 5.80 mi (9.28 km) southwest of the town of Orocovis.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.46 mi² (11.55 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1988 to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 2,355.95 ft (718.1 m) above National Geodetic Vertical Datum of 1929; gage readings has been adjusted to elevations above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago Matrullas was completed in 1934. The dam is an earthfill structure about 120 ft. high, a top width of 30 ft. and a length of 710 ft., and has a maximum storage capacity of about 4,274 ac-ft. at top of dam elevation. The Matrullas Dam is owned by the Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority and is part of the of the Toro Negro Hydro-electric Project; a project developed by the P.R.E.P.A. for the primary purpose of generating electric power. Discharges from the Power Plants are collected by the Jacaguas River which flows into Guayabal Dam, at which dam they are regulated for irrigatin of lands served by the Juana Diaz Canal.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Maximum elevation, 2,404.98 ft (733.0 m), Aug. 26; minimum elevation 2,399.00 ft (731.2 m), Aug. 20.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
2,338	2	2,399	1,845
2,360	302	2,415	2,945

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1								---	2403.36	2402.02	2400.58	2404.10
2								---	2403.22	2402.15	2400.43	2404.09
3								---	2403.06	2402.30	2400.32	2404.18
4								---	2402.76	2402.31	2400.28	2404.30
5								---	2402.71	2402.25	2400.17	2404.02
6								---	2402.69	2402.17	2400.20	2403.62
7								---	2402.58	2401.96	2400.31	2403.23
8								---	2402.45	2401.80	2400.15	2402.89
9								---	2402.36	2401.84	2399.89	2402.48
10								---	2402.29	2401.93	2399.61	2402.35
11								---	2402.43	2401.87	2399.43	2402.82
12								---	2402.63	2401.77	2399.31	2402.84
13								2404.15	2402.57	2401.62	2399.34	2402.58
14								2404.16	2402.35	2401.49	2399.41	2402.27
15								2404.29	2402.06	2401.38	2399.32	2401.96
16								2404.21	2401.72	2401.41	2399.16	2401.60
17								2404.08	2401.34	2401.49	2399.03	2401.72
18								2404.01	2401.29	2401.48	2399.12	2401.99
19								2403.92	2401.37	2401.40	2399.01	2401.77
20								2403.81	2401.32	2401.28	2399.04	2401.41
21								2403.88	2401.33	2401.16	2399.11	2401.65
22								2403.98	2401.30	2401.01	2399.16	2402.03
23								2403.90	2401.26	2401.04	2399.17	2401.90
24								2403.78	2401.33	2401.12	2402.29	2402.07
25								2403.62	2401.62	2401.09	2404.86	2402.34
26								2403.46	2402.15	2401.00	2404.79	2402.94
27								2403.29	2402.31	2400.92	2404.48	2404.06
28								2403.34	2402.28	2400.82	2404.52	2404.36
29								2403.49	2402.21	2400.73	2404.40	2404.36
30								2403.49	2402.13	2400.79	2404.18	2404.83
31								2403.43		2400.77	2403.91	
TOTAL								---	72064.48	74446.37	74424.98	72086.76
MEAN								---	2402.15	2401.50	2400.81	2402.89
MAX								---	2403.36	2402.31	2404.86	2404.83
MIN								---	2401.26	2400.73	2399.01	2401.41

WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 338694.88 MEAN 2402.09 MAX 2404.86 MIN 2399.01

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

101

50035000 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT CIALES, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'26", long 66°27'36", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on left bank, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream from Hwy 145 bridge, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) downstream from Quebrada Saliente, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) upstream from Quebrada Cojo Vales, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southeast of Ciales.

DRAINAGE AREA.--128 mi² (332 km²), excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²), the runoff from which is diverted through El Guineo and de Matrullas reservoirs.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1946 to September 1953, May 1956 to December 1957 (unpublished, available in files of Caribbean District Office and in the National Water Data Storage and Retrieval System, Washington, D.C.); February 1959 to September 1960 (monthly discharge measurements only); October 1960 to current year. Equivalent record from January 1971 to December 1972 published as 50035200 Rio Grande de Manatı at Highway 145 at Ciales at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) downstream, drainage area 132 mi² (342 km²).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 140 ft (43 m), from topographic map. Prior to Apr. 1, 1962, staff gage, read twice daily, at site 100 ft (30 m) upstream at same datum. January 1971 to December 1972 at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) downstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--28 years (1961-88), 225 ft³/s (6.372 m³/s), 28.01 in/yr (711 mm/yr), 191,300 acre-ft/yr (236 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 239 ft³/s (6.77 m³/s), 173,000 acre-ft/yr (214 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 125,000 ft³/s (3,540 m³/s), Oct. 9, 1970, gage height, 24.0 ft (7.32 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurements of peak flow at gage heights 13.2 ft (4.02 m), 15.0 ft (4.57 m), 19.0 ft (5.79 m), and 24.0 ft (7.32 m), datum then in use; minimum discharge, 20 ft³/s (0.566 m³/s), Apr. 20, 21, 1984.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate gage heights of major floods, pointed out by local residents are as follows: August 1899, 50 ft (15.2 m), September 1928, 36 ft (11.0 m), and September 1932, 34 ft (10.4 m) at site 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 7,000 ft³/s (198 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	1500	*36,400	1,030	*14.13	4.307	Aug. 24	2000	9,310	264	7.53	2.295
May 10	1715	8,500	241	7.22	2.201						

Minimum discharge, 29 ft³/s (0.82 m³/s), Aug. 21.

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50035000 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT CIALES, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	99	119	269	2770	715	141	98	e120	83	72	68	151
2	103	112	228	1490	885	172	90	e110	79	82	67	173
3	116	102	201	477	1050	137	89	e100	73	84	78	110
4	304	120	178	337	763	126	88	e96	70	70	183	97
5	298	106	202	290	367	120	87	e92	67	66	80	89
6	128	287	280	272	280	115	101	93	67	84	62	85
7	144	175	220	247	235	114	95	103	76	66	55	82
8	620	162	224	226	207	111	86	113	84	64	56	95
9	497	135	191	210	198	108	83	197	71	64	56	92
10	196	116	169	213	187	106	81	1220	67	63	55	144
11	431	104	193	201	180	106	80	888	71	63	72	457
12	384	103	335	194	176	104	118	387	117	64	55	301
13	173	221	208	186	177	102	93	192	90	63	48	193
14	150	126	178	192	177	105	81	190	74	65	45	141
15	158	112	175	179	167	103	140	179	71	67	42	129
16	133	103	176	172	162	100	275	157	73	61	46	111
17	130	150	141	228	153	105	911	134	69	61	67	105
18	258	204	134	220	161	110	927	126	66	66	381	107
19	395	156	210	209	149	98	948	119	63	66	76	95
20	200	122	572	199	147	95	499	119	65	64	44	166
21	679	109	420	189	142	95	387	100	74	64	36	120
22	546	104	281	180	138	93	516	104	69	64	43	455
23	244	101	244	169	136	91	269	107	70	63	120	678
24	198	597	223	160	142	95	175	106	190	61	2150	338
25	164	993	323	159	140	93	151	95	318	66	1540	210
26	143	322	240	157	135	108	134	97	242	65	325	331
27	140	6840	220	155	284	106	128	87	144	65	176	477
28	133	1740	208	160	179	115	e130	76	91	68	130	183
29	309	552	188	248	144	121	e160	77	77	75	114	201
30	180	361	170	221	---	118	e180	80	68	71	105	234
31	136	---	707	188	---	112	---	77	---	68	94	---
TOTAL	7789	14554	7708	10498	7976	3425	7200	5741	2839	2085	6469	6150
MEAN	251	485	249	339	275	110	240	185	94.6	67.3	209	205
MAX	679	6840	707	2770	1050	172	948	1220	318	84	2150	678
MIN	99	101	134	155	135	91	80	76	63	61	36	82
AC-FT	15450	28870	15290	20820	15820	6790	14280	11390	5630	4140	12830	12200
CFSM	1.96	3.79	1.94	2.65	2.15	.86	1.87	1.45	.74	.53	1.63	1.60
IN.	2.26	4.23	2.24	3.05	2.32	1.00	2.09	1.67	.83	.61	1.88	1.79

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 100995 MEAN 277 MAX 6840 MIN 43 AC-FT 200300 CFSM 2.16 IN. 29.35
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 82434 MEAN 225 MAX 6840 MIN 36 AC-FT 163500 CFSM 1.76 IN. 23.96

e Estimated

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS 1979 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 09	1152	423.5	150	26.5	APR, 08	1046	84.7	240	26.0
DEC, 17	1433	141.4	210	26.5	MAY, 06	0931	90.4	108	26.5
JAN, 19	1048	208.8	213	23.0	JUL, 05	1028	64.1	238	28.5
FEB, 18	1034	146	235	23.0	AUG, 04	1052	253	230	27.5
MAR, 15	1026	112	287	24.0					

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

103

50035500 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 149 AT CIALES, RP

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'46", long 66°28'06", at bridge on Highway 149, about 800 ft (244 m) upstream from confluence with Rio Cialitos, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Ciales plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--136 mi² (352 km²) this excludes the 6 mi² (15.5 km²) upstream from Lago El Guineo and Lago de Matrullas, flow from which is diverted to Rio Jacaguas.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, (PERCENT SATURATION) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECALE, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECALE, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1987											
22...	0930	E350	135	7.80	25.0	220	8.0	96	14	41000	79000
DEC 22...	0830	170	229	6.90	23.5	13	8.1	94	<10	480	590
FEB 1988											
19...	0930	135	253	7.20	23.5	--	8.3	98	--	250	380
APR 20...	0920	E1700	158	7.60	24.0	390	7.7	91	31	22000	59000
JUN 23...	0840	52	247	7.80	26.5	1.6	8.1	100	<10	200	K140
AUG 10...	0900	79	262	8.0	25.5	4.8	7.5	91	<10	K180	K1700

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
22...	53	5	13	4.9	8.5	0.5	2.8	48	<0.5	14	5.9
DEC 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	70	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	96	--	--	--
APR 20...	53	9	13	5.1	8.3	0.5	1.9	48	0.8	17	10
JUN 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	92	--	--	--
AUG 10...	95	1	23	9.1	14	0.6	2.3	90	--	11	13

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
22...	0.10	20	98	--	351	0.74	0.06	0.80	0.14	0.46
DEC 22...	--	--	--	--	5	0.88	0.02	0.90	0.02	0.18
FEB 1988										
19...	--	--	--	--	<10	0.49	0.01	0.50	0.03	0.17
APR 20...	0.10	20	102	--	535	0.95	0.05	1.00	0.12	0.48
JUN 23...	--	--	--	--	5	0.29	0.01	0.30	0.03	0.37
AUG 10...	0.10	29	158	34	10	0.19	0.01	0.20	0.01	0.19

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

105

50035950 RIO CIALITOS AT HIGHWAY 649 AT CIALES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'18", long 66°28'28", 100 ft (30 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 649, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) upstream from mouth, and about 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Ciales plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.0 mi² (44.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-71, 1974 to current year.

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
22...	1150	40	185	8.20	25.0	44	7.0	84	<10	K18000	27000
DEC 22...	1120	33	216	6.80	23.0	0.4	8.7	102	<10	460	2200
FEB 1988											
19...	1130	24	228	7.30	22.0	--	9.2	104	--	K630	K1800
APR 20...	1110	65	204	8.0	24.0	18	8.2	97	<10	K910	4300
JUN 23...	1140	14	248	8.3	25.5	2.3	8.6	104	<10	K900	K1300
AUG 10...	1105	9.0	252	8.2	26.5	3.0	8.7	108	<10	K7000	820

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
22...	71	4	21	4.6	8.8	0.5	2.5	67	<0.5	13	7.4
DEC 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	95	--	--	--
APR 20...	81	8	25	4.6	8.6	0.4	1.6	75	<0.5	13	11
JUN 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	98	--	--	--
AUG 10...	100	0	29	7.6	13	0.6	1.6	100	--	7.6	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
22...	0.10	22	120	13	40	1.18	0.02	1.20	0.04	0.16
DEC 22...	--	--	--	--	4	0.98	0.02	1.00	0.02	--
FEB 1988										
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	<0.01	0.60	0.02	0.18
APR 20...	0.10	22	130	23	<1	1.48	0.02	1.50	0.04	--
JUN 23...	--	--	--	--	24	--	<0.01	0.70	0.02	--
AUG 10...	0.10	31	164	4.0	4	--	<0.01	0.50	0.01	0.19

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'52", long 66°31'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, at bridge on Highway 2, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) west of Manati.

DRAINAGE AREA.--197 mi² (510 km²), approximately, of which about 38 mi² (98 km²) is partly or entirely noncontributing, excludes 6.0 mi² (15.5 km²) upstream from Lago El Guineo and Lago de Matrullas.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1963-68 (annual maximum discharge only), February 1970 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 14 ft (4 m), from topographic map. Prior to 1968 crest-stage gage at same site and datum 3.57 ft (1.088 m) lower.

REMARKS.--Records fair.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--18 years (1971-88), 394 ft³/s (11.16 m³/s), 27.16 in/yr (690 mm/yr), 285,500 acre-ft/yr (352 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 370 ft³/s (10.5 m³/s), 268,000 acre-ft/yr (330 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 97,200 ft³/s (2,750 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 33.79 ft (10.299 m) from rating curve extended above 15,000 ft³/s (425 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurements of peak flow; minimum discharge, 33 ft³/s (0.935 m³/s), May 12, 1984.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate gage heights to gage datum of major floods, pointed out by local residents, are as follows: Sept. 13, 1928, 36.6 ft (11.16 m), Sept. 27, 1932, 36.3 ft (11.06 m), and Aug. 4, 1945, 34.3 ft (10.45 m).

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 9,000 ft³/s (255 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	2030	*43,000	1,218	*31.75	9.677	Aug. 25	0145	16,500	467	29.10	8.870
May 10	2315	13,300	377	28.60	8.717						

Minimum discharge, 90 ft³/s (2.549 m³/s), Aug. 15, 16.

REVISIONS.--The peak discharges and annual maximum (*) reported for some water years have been revised as shown in the following table. They supersede figures published in the reports for 1970, 1971, 1975-76, 1979-80, 1981-82, 1983, 1984 and 1985.

Water Year	Date	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Water Year	Date	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
1970	Nov. 9, 1969	*68,100	1,930	32.85	10.013						
1971	Oct. 9, 1970	*81,800	2,360	33.30	10.150	1983	Sept. 13, 1982	21,200	600	29.96	9.132
1975	Oct. 23, 1974	21,000	595	29.92	9.120		Apr. 21, 1983	*30,200	855	30.84	9.400
	Sept. 16, 1975	*21,400	606	29.99	9.141		May 14, 1983	18,700	530	29.52	8.998
1979	July 19, 1979	19,000	538	29.57	9.013	1984	Sept. 11, 1984	8,600	244	27.36	8.339
	Aug. 31, 1979	*34,500	977	31.18	9.504	1985	Nov. 3, 1984	17,300	490	29.26	8.918
1982	Dec. 13, 1981	*31,000	878	30.91	9.421		May 17, 1985	37,300	1,060	31.38	9.565
							May 18, 1985	*90,000	2,550	33.54	10.2

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	139	193	591	3160	1000	203	158	211	136	146	100	241
2	133	177	490	3670	1510	238	145	136	131	155	95	316
3	165	165	436	967	1670	210	138	177	130	157	100	220
4	172	169	385	632	1610	191	135	166	128	133	261	180
5	546	164	366	502	761	183	133	161	127	119	159	160
6	221	291	558	436	526	179	150	164	124	144	112	149
7	168	280	434	399	408	176	149	153	127	119	100	143
8	385	292	424	355	338	174	140	149	140	110	98	149
9	1060	210	377	326	306	172	129	272	130	104	103	170
10	345	183	343	309	282	169	126	2120	122	103	103	221
11	235	166	353	294	270	166	127	2910	125	100	117	572
12	689	156	503	281	262	164	144	877	188	102	118	641
13	283	270	424	269	256	164	193	444	159	101	100	353
14	215	217	351	275	251	168	135	346	141	101	95	259
15	236	167	339	259	243	164	246	330	137	107	92	221
16	200	153	353	245	237	175	356	280	162	96	97	200
17	196	198	303	271	222	161	792	234	137	94	128	186
18	212	340	282	330	222	174	1890	208	119	108	504	179
19	532	273	350	275	212	161	1650	196	115	106	249	162
20	337	203	936	262	208	151	1400	188	113	100	143	194
21	357	172	825	244	204	148	786	176	124	96	114	297
22	1080	160	508	231	201	143	768	170	134	98	110	283
23	393	154	406	226	201	140	558	159	130	96	207	1130
24	313	257	343	217	205	148	331	154	194	92	1800	773
25	254	1540	461	213	205	147	277	148	360	99	5570	402
26	222	490	372	204	197	160	234	145	520	100	904	280
27	202	10500	335	197	345	166	211	143	290	97	428	1040
28	207	6380	308	197	299	186	215	140	200	95	303	467
29	276	1100	292	252	222	188	265	142	233	119	246	298
30	387	751	265	326	---	190	317	143	166	111	219	359
31	235	---	652	238	---	178	---	142	---	102	189	---
TOTAL	10395	25771	13365	16062	12873	5337	12298	11434	5042	3410	12964	10245
MEAN	335	859	431	518	444	172	410	369	168	110	418	341
MAX	1080	10500	936	3670	1670	238	1890	2910	520	157	5570	1130
MIN	133	153	265	197	197	140	126	140	113	92	92	143
AC-FT	20620	51120	26510	31860	25530	10590	24390	22680	10000	6760	25710	20320
CFSM	1.70	4.36	2.19	2.63	2.25	.87	2.08	1.87	.85	.56	2.12	1.73
IN.	1.96	4.87	2.52	3.03	2.43	1.01	2.32	2.16	.95	.64	2.45	1.93

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 163394 MEAN 448 MAX 13900 MIN 90 AC-FT 324100 CFSM 2.27 IN. 30.85
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 139196 MEAN 380 MAX 10500 MIN 92 AC-FT 276100 CFSM 1.93 IN. 26.28

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)
SEP 1987											
28...	1105	127	299	7.70	29.0	5.8	7.1	130	K8700	6700	140
DEC											
08...	1130	452	235	6.90	25.0	17	7.7	92	5700	--	100
FEB 1988											
01...	1140	1560	224	7.00	24.0	53	8.1	94	20000	20000	98
APR											
04...	1145	1070	312	7.10	25.5	3.6	7.9	96	K1400	640	140
JUN											
01...	0915	137	355	6.90	27.0	10	7.0	86	24000	9100	150
AUG											
01...	0925	99	309	6.80	27.0	6.3	6.9	85	K11000	2200	140

DATE	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD MG/L AS CAC03	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CAC03	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SI02)
SEP 1987											
28...	9	43	8.0	11	0.4	7.5	130	9.0	11	0.1	21
DEC											
08...	5	31	6.5	9.1	0.4	2.0	93	8.6	11	0.3	21
FEB 1988											
01...	7	27	7.4	13	0.6	2.4	81	11	16	0.2	24
APR											
04...	7	42	8.2	12	0.5	1.5	120	9.6	12	0.2	22
JUN											
01...	8	47	8.3	12	0.4	2.2	140	10	13	0.3	22
AUG											
01...	4	44	7.9	12	0.5	1.6	130	8.9	14	0.2	20

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS-PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHOROUS DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHOROUS ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHATE, ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P04)
SEP 1987											
28...	184	193	66	0.73	0.05	0.06	0.5	0.10	0.01	0.05	0.15
DEC											
08...	145	153	187	0.86	0.04	0.05	0.2	0.09	0.05	0.06	0.18
FEB 1988											
01...	157	160	637	0.89	0.09	0.12	0.3	0.17	0.08	0.06	0.18
APR											
04...	190	190	551	0.81	0.04	0.05	0.4	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.15
JUN											
01...	220	205	74	0.68	0.09	0.12	0.5	0.18	0.14	0.12	0.37
AUG											
01...	199	194	52	0.38	0.07	0.09	0.6	0.12	0.09	0.07	0.21

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	ALUM- INUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL- LIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)
SEP 1987 28...	10	<1	43	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	3	12	<5
DEC 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 01...	40	<1	38	<0.5	2	<1	<3	4	41	<5
APR 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 01...	20	2	48	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	2	9	<5
AUG 01...	50	1	48	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	4	21	5

DATE	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
SEP 1987 28...	<4	24	<0.1	<10	3	<1	<1	190	6	14
DEC 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 01...	<4	13	0.2	<10	3	<1	<1	130	7	21
APR 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 01...	9	39	<0.1	<10	2	<1	<1.0	200	7	28
AUG 01...	<4	41	<0.1	<10	5	<1	<1.0	210	7	4

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 01...	0915	<0.1	<0.01	<0.1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.13	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 01...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 01...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

50038100 RIO GRANDE DE MANATI AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR MANATI, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDED (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDED (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
DEC 1987					
08...	1120	452	152	153	82
FEB 1988					
01...	1155	1560	411	1730	73
APR					
04...	1145	1070	77	223	69
JUN					
01...	0910	137	71	26	84
AUG					
01...	0915	99	87	23	85

LAGUNA TORTUGUERO BASIN
50038200 LAGUNA TORTUGUERO OUTLET NEAR VEGA BAJA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°28'29", long 66°26'50", at bridge on Highway 686, 4.2 mi (6.8 km) northeast of Manati, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northwest of Vega Baja plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964-66, 1969-71, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987										
06...	1145	23	1130	7.80	30.5	8.3	110	52	20	70
DEC										
07...	1300	23	1140	7.70	28.5	7.0	90	22	K17	52
FEB 1988										
08...	1345	26	1160	7.80	26.5	8.1	100	49	K8	120
APR										
06...	1340	17	1260	7.80	28.5	7.9	101	24	K4	K25
JUN										
13...	1435	28	1140	7.40	31.0	7.5	100	44	K15	48
AUG										
09...	0850	18	1200	8.00	29.0	7.0	90	13	K10	K30

DATE	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CAC03	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
06...	130	<0.5	5	0.68	0.02	0.70	0.13	0.97	1.1	1.8
DEC										
07...	120	--	4	0.70	0.10	0.80	0.12	0.38	0.5	1.3
FEB 1988										
08...	130	--	3	0.98	0.02	1.00	0.08	0.62	0.7	1.7
APR										
06...	110	<0.5	<1	0.68	0.02	0.70	0.13	0.77	0.9	1.6
JUN										
13...	120	--	<1	0.68	0.02	0.70	0.10	0.70	0.8	1.5
AUG										
09...	110	--	4	0.49	0.01	0.50	0.14	1.20	1.3	1.8

DATE	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY-LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1987										
06...	7.8	0.01	60	10	60	<10	<10	<0.01	3	0.05
DEC										
07...	5.8	0.01	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988										
08...	7.5	0.01	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
06...	7.1	<0.01	40	<10	40	<10	<10	<0.01	6	0.1
JUN										
13...	6.6	0.01	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG										
09...	8.0	0.02	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

K = non-ideal count

Figure 15.--Río Cibuco basin.

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50038320 RIO CIBUCO BELOW COROZAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'13", Long 66°20'07", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, on right bank, 150 ft (46 m) downstream from Rio Corozal, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) northwest of Corozal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.1 mi² (39.1 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1969 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 195 ft (59 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--19 years (1970-88), 30.2 ft³/s (0.855 m³/s), 27.16 in/yr (690 mm/yr), 21,880 acre-ft/yr (27.0 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 34 ft³/s (0.96 m³/s), 24,600 acre-ft/yr (30 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 13,600 ft³/s (385 m³/s), Nov. 7, 1979, gage height, 19.80 ft (6.035 m), from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of float and slope-area measurements of peak flow; minimum daily discharge, 1.3 ft³/s (0.037 m³/s), July 24-26, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Nov. 28	1545	4,100	116	12.83	3.911	Sept. 20	1530	2,940	83.3	11.39	3.472
Apr. 16	2045	*7,940	225	*16.45	5.014						

Minimum discharge, 5.1 ft³/s (0.145 m³/s), Aug. 3.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	11	14	e26	433	231	21	18	20	14	16	8.3	11
2	10	13	23	128	153	25	15	19	14	17	6.6	11
3	10	11	22	60	220	21	14	19	13	12	29	10
4	11	11	21	46	100	20	13	20	13	10	28	9.1
5	12	11	22	40	56	20	14	20	13	10	10	8.4
6	10	12	19	36	44	19	14	19	13	10	7.8	8.5
7	9.6	43	47	32	39	18	13	18	12	10	6.8	8.7
8	147	16	23	30	36	18	13	18	12	8.3	7.5	9.2
9	30	12	19	27	34	17	11	70	12	7.6	8.4	30
10	15	11	18	26	33	17	11	119	11	12	19	36
11	11	11	17	26	32	17	13	125	25	12	13	125
12	10	12	17	25	32	16	62	41	18	10	8.7	58
13	10	12	16	26	33	16	22	30	14	9.3	7.5	27
14	9.6	10	16	26	30	17	20	28	12	10	7.8	19
15	18	11	22	23	31	16	114	25	14	7.5	8.1	16
16	12	11	17	22	29	16	1220	24	13	7.7	11	16
17	21	55	15	34	28	23	167	22	12	14	16	16
18	29	31	15	24	28	17	266	21	13	12	24	18
19	17	19	57	24	27	15	111	21	13	7.9	11	14
20	13	14	131	22	26	16	115	20	13	7.2	9.5	259
21	27	13	85	20	25	15	117	19	16	7.5	7.9	44
22	18	13	33	20	24	15	87	18	13	10	11	31
23	20	17	26	20	25	14	45	18	12	7.1	14	113
24	15	95	28	19	26	18	35	17	12	7.8	180	51
25	14	56	48	20	24	16	30	17	14	12	128	30
26	12	35	30	18	32	20	31	16	14	7.3	38	22
27	11	182	25	18	45	27	26	16	10	7.2	23	19
28	10	259	24	23	24	33	24	16	10	9.1	19	19
29	139	53	21	54	22	25	23	16	10	11	14	34
30	35	e33	24	26	---	39	22	16	9.5	9.3	13	23
31	17	---	153	57	---	33	---	15	---	7.6	12	---
TOTAL	734.2	1096	1060	1405	1489	620	2686	883	394.5	306.4	707.9	1095.9
MEAN	23.7	36.5	34.2	45.3	51.3	20.0	89.5	28.5	13.1	9.88	22.8	36.5
MAX	147	259	153	433	231	39	1220	125	25	17	180	259
MIN	9.6	10	15	18	22	14	11	15	9.5	7.1	6.6	8.4
AC-FT	1460	2170	2100	2790	2950	1230	5330	1750	782	608	1400	2170
CFSM	1.57	2.42	2.26	3.00	3.40	1.32	5.93	1.89	.87	.65	1.51	2.42
IN.	1.81	2.70	2.61	3.46	3.67	1.53	6.62	2.18	.97	.75	1.74	2.70

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 14425.3 MEAN 39.5 MAX 1240 MIN 5.0 AC-FT 28610 CFSM 2.62 IN. 35.54
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 12477.9 MEAN 34.1 MAX 1220 MIN 6.6 AC-FT 24750 CFSM 2.26 IN. 30.74

e Estimated

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50038320 RIO CIBUCO BELOW COROZAL, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1969-76, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	
OCT 1987											
05...	0940	11	317	7.60	25.5	4.2	7.5	86	23	4800	2000
DEC											
03...	0900	22	335	7.30	23.5	2.9	8.9	90	33	520	270
FEB 1988											
05...	0935	58	286	7.40	22.0	--	8.4	95	--	K7200	2400
APR											
08...	0915	13	352	7.20	23.0	9.0	7.7	89	15	2500	K1600
JUN											
03...	0920	14	371	6.90	25.5	2.5	6.8	82	20	4500	690
AUG											
08...	1020	8.7	372	6.70	26.0	1.8	6.6	81	<10	1500	1400

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB TOT FLD (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
05...	130	18	33	11	18	0.7	3.1	110	<0.5	15	20
DEC											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	96	--	--	--
APR											
08...	120	6	28	11	17	0.7	2.9	120	<0.5	15	20
JUN											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
AUG											
08...	140	15	35	12	19	0.7	2.9	120	--	16	22

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
05...	0.2	33	199	7.0	2	1.05	0.05	1.10	0.11	0.69
DEC										
03...	--	--	--	--	5	1.14	0.26	1.40	0.74	0.66
FEB 1988										
05...	--	--	--	--	--	1.26	0.04	1.30	0.24	0.56
APR										
08...	0.2	30	189	6.8	2	0.97	0.23	1.20	1.10	1.2
JUN										
03...	--	--	--	--	10	0.71	0.19	0.90	0.92	0.18
AUG										
08...	0.2	32	212	5.0	11	0.65	0.15	0.80	0.92	2.0

K = non-ideal count

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039500 RIO CIBUCO AT VEGA BAJA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'53", long 66°22'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010002, on right bank, at bridge on Hwy 2. 0.6 mi (1.0 km) downstream from Rio Indio, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) east of Vega Baja.

DRAINAGE AREA.--99.1 mi² (256.7 km²), of which 25.4 mi² (65.8 km²), does not contribute directly to surface runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1973 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 7.79 ft (2.37 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--15 years (1974-88), 135 ft³/s (3.823 m³/s), 18.50 in/yr (470 mm/yr), 97,810 acre-ft/yr (121 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 143 ft³/s (4.05 m³/s), 104,000 acre-ft/yr (128 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 34,000 ft³/s (963 m³/s), Dec. 13, 1981, gage height, 19.10 ft (5.822 m), from rating curve extended above 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) on the basis of indirect measurements; minimum discharge, 6.1 ft³/s (0.173 m³/s), July 24, 25, 1977.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Flood of Dec. 11, 1965 reached a stage of 26.2 ft (7.99 m), datum unknown, discharge about 28,000 ft³/s (793 m³/s).

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,200 ft³/s (90.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Apr. 17	0300	*16,600	470	*17.70	5.395	May 11	0445	5,460	155	16.23	4.947

Minimum daily discharge, 28 ft³/s (0.793 m³/s), Aug. 14.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e54	46	102	1400	698	80	79	110	57	71	56	80
2	e52	41	87	1140	594	86	61	97	55	80	55	75
3	e48	38	81	439	693	74	53	88	56	71	94	63
4	e75	35	77	297	595	69	51	80	53	50	301	59
5	e108	35	75	244	215	66	49	80	54	44	73	56
6	e69	37	93	222	133	65	55	75	52	47	48	52
7	e43	146	119	192	175	65	49	70	52	74	36	54
8	e39	128	124	167	162	63	48	80	53	64	34	53
9	e90	50	87	150	147	61	43	228	53	42	31	e220
10	e160	43	82	134	133	60	42	1020	53	56	54	e350
11	e88	40	79	131	124	61	43	2280	75	57	95	e780
12	e56	39	78	124	123	58	120	442	91	61	39	e490
13	e65	47	79	113	127	55	189	226	68	46	29	e290
14	e46	42	76	126	124	59	36	165	66	50	28	132
15	37	40	107	105	108	55	852	129	108	46	29	100
16	48	44	91	97	107	55	1230	108	129	39	32	91
17	29	201	78	133	95	76	5120	94	123	47	72	91
18	58	295	75	111	97	76	908	83	121	64	159	120
19	53	95	105	109	90	62	976	75	139	52	67	106
20	98	68	726	88	88	56	675	74	133	44	43	462
21	148	59	743	73	82	53	542	69	131	41	43	614
22	235	60	232	71	79	51	781	66	150	49	48	260
23	52	59	142	69	80	49	382	62	123	50	78	375
24	51	174	110	64	91	55	286	60	76	44	603	370
25	47	403	253	84	82	60	235	57	83	68	1080	190
26	38	113	195	64	79	73	200	58	125	74	332	152
27	34	580	166	59	199	79	174	56	69	57	259	142
28	31	856	118	74	113	159	148	55	71	50	232	158
29	128	558	106	172	85	140	135	60	62	78	126	187
30	165	154	99	122	---	138	123	64	57	86	90	164
31	51	---	516	106	---	160	---	60	---	62	76	---
TOTAL	2296	4526	5101	6480	5518	2319	13685	6271	2538	1764	4342	6336
MEAN	74.1	151	165	209	190	74.8	456	202	84.6	56.9	140	211
MAX	235	856	743	1400	698	160	5120	2280	150	86	1080	780
MIN	29	35	75	59	79	49	36	55	52	39	28	52
AC-FT	4550	8980	10120	12850	10940	4600	27140	12440	5030	3500	8610	12570
CFSM	.75	1.52	1.66	2.11	1.92	.75	4.60	2.04	.85	.57	1.41	2.13
IN.	.86	1.70	1.91	2.43	2.07	.87	5.14	2.35	.95	.66	1.63	2.38

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 71267 MEAN 195 MAX 10000 MIN 20 AC-FT 141400 CFSM 1.97 IN. 26.75
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 61176 MEAN 167 MAX 5120 MIN 28 AC-FT 121300 CFSM 1.69 IN. 22.96

e Estimated

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

50039500 RIO CIBUCO AT VEGA BAJA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCOCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
06...	0850	51	427	7.40	26.5	3.1	4.0	49	47	5000	770
DEC											
07...	1030	82	440	7.20	25.0	5.3	5.8	70	19	K9800	1000
FEB 1988											
08...	1110	160	403	7.40	23.0	--	7.5	87	--	K1700	K2000
APR											
06...	1010	59	430	7.20	25.0	4.5	4.9	54	13	K400	K450
JUN											
13...	1110	75	407	6.80	26.5	5.9	5.3	65	18	K6700	800
AUG											
09...	1245	42	466	7.80	27.5	1.7	4.5	57	<10	K770	340

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
06...	180	15	60	8.4	16	0.5	3.2	170	<0.5	17	21
DEC											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
APR											
06...	180	10	55	9.3	17	0.6	2.6	160	<0.5	17	21
JUN											
13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	15	--	--	--
AUG											
09...	200	12	63	9.4	16	0.5	2.8	180	--	16	21

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
06...	0.20	19	247	34	4	1.11	0.09	1.20	0.19	0.51
DEC										
07...	--	--	--	--	10	0.69	0.01	0.70	0.15	0.05
FEB 1988										
08...	--	--	--	--	--	1.27	0.03	1.30	0.09	0.41
APR										
06...	0.20	19	241	39	7	1.42	0.08	1.50	0.25	0.25
JUN										
13...	--	--	--	--	6	1.14	0.06	1.20	0.15	0.25
AUG										
09...	0.20	19	258	30	4	1.21	0.09	1.30	0.17	0.73

K = non-ideal count

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 16.--Río de la Plata basin.

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50043000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT PROYECTO LA PLATA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'37", long 66°13'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at upstream side of bridge on Highway 173, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of Proyecto La Plata, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) upstream from Rio Usabon.

DRAINAGE AREA.--54.8 mi² (141.9 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.1 km²) upstream from Carite Reservoir, the flow of which is diverted to Rio Guamani.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1958 (occasional measurements only), February 1959 to March 1960 (monthly measurements only), April 1960 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 850 ft (259 m), from topographic map. Prior to Mar. 29, 1961, wire-weight gage read twice daily at same site and datum.

REMARKS.--Records are fair. The Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority operates a pumping plant about 5 mi (8 km) upstream which can divert as much as 23 ft³/s (0.65 m³/s) into Cidra Reservoir.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--28 years (1961-88), 110 ft³/s (3.115 m³/s), 27.26 in/yr (692 mm/yr), 79,700 acre-ft/yr (98.3 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 91 ft³/s (2.58 m³/s), 65,900 acre-ft/yr (81 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 59,600 ft³/s (1,690 m³/s), Aug. 27, 1961, gage height, 32.21 ft (9.818 m), from rating curve extended above 7,000 ft³/s (198 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement; minimum daily discharge, 2.6 ft³/s (0.074 m³/s), July 25, 1974.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 4,000 ft³/s (113 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Nov. 27	1715	*4,420	125	*10.41	3.173						

Minimum discharge, 4.0 ft³/s (0.113 m³/s), May 6.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	23	11	255	600	74	25	15	5.4	11	380	254	73
2	14	11	173	356	79	29	13	8.3	11	643	197	62
3	9.8	8.6	129	178	213	29	13	5.5	9.3	493	216	53
4	12	9.8	107	137	112	26	15	5.3	8.9	181	400	48
5	15	24	109	143	74	25	15	5.0	9.0	95	170	45
6	13	251	107	131	71	23	35	6.5	8.7	67	118	37
7	11	87	581	123	59	22	54	19	8.9	152	95	40
8	16	26	1220	115	50	23	16	7.1	9.5	69	103	74
9	13	17	357	96	46	20	10	5.4	9.0	43	81	98
10	9.3	14	219	106	44	20	10	107	8.9	42	88	198
11	8.3	12	209	111	42	19	8.6	31	9.1	43	492	1030
12	8.8	11	206	132	50	19	8.7	18	9.5	36	254	938
13	8.8	13	148	94	80	17	9.1	17	11	30	169	692
14	8.0	13	118	108	51	17	8.8	13	12	28	130	677
15	10	9.0	104	74	51	16	10	13	104	25	95	384
16	26	8.7	100	64	46	16	12	19	98	20	89	330
17	53	14	86	65	39	17	52	18	20	20	194	222
18	991	17	81	60	37	17	74	16	13	20	500	169
19	304	14	90	57	34	16	20	16	13	22	226	135
20	48	15	178	51	33	18	8.2	23	15	22	159	175
21	26	11	181	46	36	21	6.9	20	22	13	136	107
22	20	9.2	258	43	29	16	12	24	25	10	284	88
23	17	22	164	42	27	18	9.1	15	32	18	613	100
24	16	1320	123	42	34	19	7.7	14	24	16	665	88
25	20	767	139	41	38	18	6.6	12	20	12	752	81
26	19	331	94	42	34	17	7.9	12	36	7.9	520	76
27	26	1590	104	39	50	20	6.7	11	27	13	261	72
28	36	1410	91	39	38	31	6.5	11	18	183	215	66
29	38	852	101	39	28	26	5.0	11	14	380	165	62
30	22	377	78	58	---	20	5.2	13	33	373	133	56
31	15	---	129	42	---	16	---	12	---	397	102	---
TOTAL	1857.0	7275.3	6039	3274	1599	636	481.0	513.5	649.8	3853.9	7876	6276
MEAN	59.9	243	195	106	55.1	20.5	16.0	16.6	21.7	124	254	209
MAX	991	1590	1220	600	213	31	74	107	104	643	752	1030
MIN	8.0	8.6	78	39	27	16	5.0	5.0	8.7	7.9	81	37
AC-FT	3680	14430	11980	6490	3170	1260	954	1020	1290	7640	15620	12450
CFSM	1.09	4.43	3.55	1.93	1.01	.37	.29	.30	.40	2.27	4.64	3.82
IN.	1.26	4.94	4.10	2.22	1.09	.43	.33	.35	.44	2.62	5.35	4.26

CAL YR 1987	TOTAL	27518.3	MEAN	75.4	MAX	1590	MIN	8.0	AC-FT	54580	CFSM	1.38	IN.	18.68
WTR YR 1988	TOTAL	40330.5	MEAN	110	MAX	1590	MIN	5.0	AC-FT	80000	CFSM	2.01	IN.	27.38

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

123

50043000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT PROYECTO LA PLATA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
07...	1120	11	428	7.90	28.5	6.8	9.1	120	30	480	K67
DEC											
02...	1030	179	250	7.30	25.0	6.3	8.0	99	28	2700	3200
FEB 1988											
11...	0955	41	390	7.80	24.0	--	9.3	113	--	K180	260
APR											
05...	1200	15	437	7.80	27.0	3.5	10.3	132	100	K140	K220
JUN											
14...	1010	11	540	7.60	28.0	7.6	7.8	102	42	210	K220
AUG											
11...	1035	594	116	7.40	26.5	190	5.5	70	19	K100000	410000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
07...	160	10	41	14	31	1	2.7	150	<0.5	19	31
DEC											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	89	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR											
05...	170	0	43	16	37	1	2.4	160	<0.5	20	35
JUN											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
AUG											
11...	36	0	8.6	3.6	9.6	0.7	1.8	41	--	9.8	10

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
07...	0.20	26	255	7.4	20	2.04	0.06	2.10	0.06	0.44
DEC										
02...	--	--	--	--	7	0.95	0.05	1.00	0.06	0.34
FEB 1988										
11...	--	--	--	--	--	1.25	0.05	1.30	0.03	0.37
APR										
05...	0.30	25	284	12	4	1.93	0.07	2.00	0.06	0.64
JUN										
14...	--	--	--	--	6	1.83	0.07	1.90	0.03	0.57
AUG										
11...	0.10	12	79	126	27	0.24	0.06	0.30	0.15	1.8

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

125

50044000 RIO DE LA PLATA NEAR COMERIO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'33", long 66°12'28", at bridge on Highway 156, 0.56 mi (0.9 km) upstream from dam, about 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast of Comerio plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--139 mi² (360 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.1 km²) upstream from Carite Reservoir, the flow of which is diverted to Rio Guamaní.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATUR-ATION	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
15...	1150	34	399	7.90	27.5	3.7	8.8	112	<10	940	600
DEC 11...	1035	297	272	7.50	25.5	9.6	7.9	97	16	1400	800
FEB 1988											
19...	0815	28	406	7.80	23.0	--	6.6	77	--	570	460
APR 19...	0850	E800	245	7.10	24.0	130	7.6	91	23	K17000	22000
JUN 16...	0900	E480	436	7.20	26.5	23	7.5	94	<10	K12000	4200
AUG 22...	0850	66	318	6.80	26.0	14	7.4	92	43	K1900	K540

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH TOT (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
15...	160	11	38	16	26	0.9	2.8	150	<0.5	20	27
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR 19...	81	6	19	8.1	15	0.7	3.2	69	<0.5	17	15
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG 22...	110	2	25	11	23	1	2.4	96	--	23	75

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
15...	0.20	31	251	23	7	0.86	0.04	0.90	0.07	0.43
DEC 11...	--	--	--	--	2	--	<0.01	0.80	<0.01	--
FEB 1988										
19...	--	--	--	--	--	0.87	0.03	0.90	0.06	0.44
APR 19...	0.20	19	141	--	186	1.51	0.09	1.60	0.15	0.75
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	36	0.71	0.09	0.80	0.17	1.03
AUG 22...	0.10	25	248	44	18	0.87	0.03	0.90	0.04	0.36

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50044850 RIO GUADIANA NEAR MARANJITO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°18'39", long 66°13'28", at steel-cross-bridge 0.8 mi (1.3 km) northwest of Highway 164, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from mouth and about 2.0 mi (3.2 km) northeast of Maranjito plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.0 mi² (10.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water year 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
15...	0855	5.9	335	7.60	25.0	3.4	7.7	92	<10	390	900
DEC											
11...	1255	7.9	343	7.80	26.0	1.4	7.9	97	12	K650	470
FEB 1988											
19...	1020	15	319	7.70	24.0	0.4	8.9	99	<10	240	280
APR											
19...	1055	33	285	7.50	25.0	17	8.0	96	35	21000	4700
JUN											
16...	1045	7.4	333	7.50	26.0	0.7	7.8	95	<10	K830	550
AUG											
22...	1100	6.2	338	7.20	26.0	2.0	7.4	90	31	230	650

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
15...	150	25	35	14	18	0.7	2.3	120	<0.5	16	22
DEC											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
19...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	92	--	--	--
APR											
19...	100	10	22	12	13	0.6	2.3	82	<0.5	17	15
JUN											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
AUG											
22...	130	13	29	14	17	0.7	2.1	110	--	16	22

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TOMS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
15...	0.20	29	208	3.3	3	1.38	0.02	1.40	0.06	0.14
DEC										
11...	--	--	--	--	2	1.79	0.01	1.80	0.01	0.19
FEB 1988										
19...	--	--	--	--	--	1.28	0.02	1.30	0.08	0.32
APR										
19...	0.20	25	163	14	8	1.38	0.02	1.40	0.03	0.47
JUN										
16...	--	--	--	--	10	0.96	0.04	1.00	0.03	0.77
AUG										
22...	0.10	27	197	3.3	2	0.98	0.02	1.00	0.01	0.29

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT TOA ALTA, PR
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°15'39", at Highway 2, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) downstream from Rio Lajas, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Toa Alta, 11.3 mi (18.2 km) downstream from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²), exclude 8.2 mi² (21.2 km²) upstream from Lago Carite, flow from which is diverted to Rio Guamani.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PERCENT SATURATION)	COLIFORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)
OCT 1987											
14...	1035	20	465	7.10	28.5	2.2	7.0	90	K1100	210	220
DEC											
04...	0930	208	225	6.80	26.0	69	6.4	78	K440	K450	94
FEB 1988											
12...	1000	123	411	7.00	25.5	12	6.2	75	4000	260	160
APR											
18...	1000	1130	235	7.20	26.0	49	7.4	90	5600	4100	130
JUN											
06...	1310	19	454	7.70	33.0	16	15.6	211	K920	<10	230
AUG											
08...	0935	54	372	7.20	28.5	1.4	3.6	46	4300	2600	150

DATE	HARDNESS NONCARB WH TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WAT WH TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFATE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)
OCT 1987											
14...	29	65	13	24	0.7	3.6	180	20	31	0.2	20
DEC											
04...	13	26	7	12	0.6	2.3	81	17	13	0.2	670
FEB 1988											
12...	15	47	11	19	0.7	2.8	140	16	22	0.2	18
APR											
18...	0	32	11	17	0.7	2.0	120	16	19	0.2	16
JUN											
06...	29	69	13	23	0.7	2.1	190	22	30	0.3	18
AUG											
08...	10	43	11	19	0.7	2.0	140	15	20	0.2	19

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOSPHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOSPHOROUS DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOSPHOROUS ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOSPHATE, ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)
OCT 1987											
14...	287	294	16	0.80	0.12	0.15	1.0	0.27	0.26	0.24	0.74
DEC											
04...	150	806	453	2.80	0.12	0.15	0.4	0.13	0.08	0.05	0.15
FEB 1988											
12...	229	228	76	0.53	0.24	0.31	--	0.18	0.18	0.16	0.49
APR											
18...	194	189	577	0.13	0.06	0.08	0.6	0.16	0.06	0.05	0.15
JUN											
06...	300	298	15	0.32	0.02	0.03	0.7	0.26	0.24	0.20	0.61
AUG											
08...	241	218	32	0.42	0.20	0.26	0.8	0.11	0.09	0.09	0.28

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT TOA ALTA, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	ALUM- INUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYL- LIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)
OCT 1987 14...	<10	2	53	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	3	11	10
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 12...	60	1	46	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	4	11	<5
APR 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 06...	130	<1	49	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	27	74	<5
AUG 08...	50	2	52	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	2	20	<5

DATE	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1987 14...	<4	150	<0.1	<10	3	<1	1	270	6	4
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 12...	6	56	<0.1	<10	4	<1	<1	180	9	8
APR 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
JUN 06...	12	39	0.2	<10	4	<1	<1.0	280	8	18
AUG 08...	<4	140	<0.1	<10	1	<1	1.0	170	<6	8

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 06...	1310	<0.1	<0.01	<0.1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 06...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 06...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.1	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046000 RIO DE LA PLATA AT TOA ALTA, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1987					
14...	1030	20	61	3.3	65
FEB 1988					
12...	0955	123	112	37.2	87
APR					
18...	1000	235	166	105	94
JUN					
06...	1310	19	102	5.2	89
AUG					
08...	0935	54	78	11	89

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046900 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR TOA ALTA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°15'39", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 2, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) downstream from Rio Lajas, and 1.6 mi (2.6 km) northwest of Toa Alta, 11.3 mi (18.2 km) downstream from Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²), excludes 8.2 mi² (21.2 km²) upstream from Lago Carite, flow from which is diverted to Rio Guamaní. Area at site used prior to September 25, 1984, 200 mi² (518 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1959 (measurement only), January 1960 to current year. Prior to October 1984, published as Rio de la Plata at Toa Alta, P.R.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 17.00 ft (5.182 m), below mean sea level (Puerto Rico Department of Public Wones Benchmark). Prior to Sept. 25, 1984, at site about 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream at mean sea level datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Regulation at all stages by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority reservoir upstream from gage.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--28 years (1961-88), 282 ft³/s (7.986 m³/s), 19.15 in/yr (486 mm/yr), 204,300 acre-ft/yr (252 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 246 ft³/s (6.97 m³/s), 180,000 acre-ft/yr (222 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 95,500 ft³/s (2,700 m³/s), Sept. 6, 1960, gage height, 36.35 ft (11.079 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 12,000 ft³/s (340 m³/s) on basis of contracted-opening measurement of peak flow at site 1.0 mi upstream and different datum; minimum discharge, 2.2 ft³/s (0.062 m³/s), Apr. 25, 1984.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate discharges and elevations of major floods, as pointed out by local residents are as follows: Sept. 13, 1928, 120,000 ft³/s (3,400 m³/s), gage height, 37.4 ft (11.40 m); June 16, 1943, 82,000 ft³/s (2,320 m³/s), gage height, 34.4 ft (10.48 m), at site 1.0 mi upstream and different datum.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 6,000 ft³/s (170 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Nov. 25	0200	12,600	357	16.53	5.038	Aug. 24	2400	19,000	538	18.19	5.544
Nov. 27	2245	*29,200	827	*20.43	6.227	Sept.11	1930	8,850	251	13.83	4.215
May 10	2215	8,060	228	13.34	4.066						

Minimum discharge, 11 ft³/s (0.312 m³/s), June 18, 29, 30.

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

50046900 RIO DE LA PLATA AT HIGHWAY 2 NEAR TOA ALTA, PR--Continued

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	35	41	479	e2600	841	91	78	66	18	26	24	229
2	30	27	329	e4600	955	76	59	51	17	487	25	152
3	25	22	248	e900	1170	70	49	44	19	997	145	109
4	22	20	205	e500	934	67	45	38	19	340	189	86
5	20	19	193	e420	449	58	41	33	17	373	215	71
6	19	90	278	e370	287	51	39	32	16	177	113	58
7	20	410	222	e340	219	49	49	27	21	101	95	56
8	19	204	1320	e310	185	49	102	25	23	65	55	54
9	21	86	836	e290	158	44	64	146	18	66	40	359
10	24	47	441	e280	139	45	45	878	16	68	89	476
11	18	29	295	e270	135	42	35	486	22	52	110	3930
12	18	26	369	e260	189	41	63	196	29	48	175	2840
13	19	20	299	245	217	38	154	133	29	35	169	1450
14	21	16	218	233	170	49	75	100	20	32	107	847
15	36	16	234	214	147	45	1460	61	19	22	69	590
16	35	19	210	167	138	38	546	36	18	20	52	422
17	24	130	169	176	121	60	844	26	15	31	62	489
18	286	123	137	200	111	60	988	22	13	39	418	539
19	1140	76	257	182	99	47	757	19	22	34	367	274
20	317	56	e1300	145	92	38	597	17	32	23	171	462
21	164	35	e500	127	85	36	355	17	54	22	97	341
22	144	26	e350	111	81	34	527	15	35	22	252	224
23	113	26	e300	103	76	33	197	17	25	21	410	158
24	104	2040	e250	97	83	35	142	14	16	19	4350	458
25	83	5360	e400	114	85	39	129	19	19	29	7640	202
26	47	1040	e300	101	82	46	112	17	25	38	1450	139
27	37	7640	e250	96	289	68	94	17	16	37	878	117
28	32	8770	e230	122	209	255	68	18	15	29	448	116
29	30	1740	e210	295	126	165	61	19	14	67	296	151
30	54	765	e200	259	---	207	56	17	16	48	214	117
31	58	---	e1800	188	---	141	---	19	---	27	178	---
TOTAL	3015	28919	12829	14315	7872	2117	7831	2625	638	3395	18903	15516
MEAN	97.3	964	414	462	271	68.3	261	84.7	21.3	110	610	517
MAX	1140	8770	1800	4600	1170	255	1460	878	54	997	7640	3930
MIN	18	16	137	96	76	33	35	14	13	19	24	54
AC-FT	5980	57360	25450	28390	15610	4200	15530	5210	1270	6730	37490	30780
CFSM	.49	4.82	2.07	2.31	1.36	.34	1.31	.42	.11	.55	3.05	2.59
IN.	.56	5.38	2.39	2.66	1.46	.39	1.46	.49	.12	.63	3.52	2.89

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 119424 MEAN 327 MAX 9060 MIN 14 AC-FT 236900 CFSM 1.64 IN. 22.21
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 117975 MEAN 322 MAX 8770 MIN 13 AC-FT 234000 CFSM 1.61 IN. 21.94

e Estimated

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 17.--Río Hondo to Río Puerto Nuevo basins.

RIO HONDO BASIN

50047530 RIO HONDO AT FLOOD CHANNEL NEAR CATANO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'13", long 66°09'36", at Rio Hondo Channel, 800 ft (245 m) below junction with Rio Hondo, 0.9 mi (1.5 km) downstream from bridge on de Diego Expressway and 1.1 mi (1.8 km) above mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987										
26...	0710	--	1960	7.50	26.0	24	2.8	34	24	40000 310000
DEC 17...	1425	--	21600	8.50	30.0	3.3	15.8	208	36	5100 K1200
FEB 1988										
25...	0810	E150	12000	7.40	24.0	3.6	5.6	66	22	K65000 3300
APR 26...	0845	E0	3700	8.40	27.5	4.2	8.1	102	41	K4000 K1000
JUN 20...	0915	E20	6500	7.40	27.5	4.8	1.9	24	68	K97000 K910
AUG 19...	0845	E0	4600	7.40	28.0	9.5	4.4	55	18	K15000 K1000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
26...	260	170	44	37	300	8	15	96	<0.5	87	520
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
25...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
APR 26...	440	300	59	72	560	12	22	140	<0.5	170	980
JUN 20...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
AUG 19...	580	440	76	94	770	14	28	150	--	220	1400

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG, C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
26...	0.10	8.8	1070	--	28	0.16	0.04	0.20	1.00	0.90
DEC 17...	--	--	--	--	12	0.18	0.12	0.30	2.00	3.5
FEB 1988										
25...	--	--	--	--	16	0.16	0.14	0.30	1.50	3.9
APR 26...	0.30	14	1960	--	18	--	0.01	<0.10	0.06	0.74
JUN 20...	--	--	--	--	18	--	0.02	<0.10	1.60	3.6
AUG 19...	0.20	12	2680	--	14	0.03	0.07	0.10	2.50	0.30

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50047550 LAGO CIDRA AT DAMSITE NEAR CIDRA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat18°11'57", long 66°08'29", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at Lago de Cidra Dam on Rio de Bayamon, 1.9 mi (3.0 km) northeast of Plaza de Cidra and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northwest of Escuela Segunda Unidad de Bayamon.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.26 mi² (21.4 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1988 to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 1,337.58 ft (407.694 m) above mean sea level; gage readings has been adjusted to elevations above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Lago de Cidra was completed in 1946. The maximum storage is 5,300 ac-ft (6.53 hm³) and provides supplemental water to metropolitan San Juan. The dam is a concrete gravity and earthfill structure approximately 541 ft (165 m) long between abutments with a maximum structural height of about 78.7 ft (24.0 m). The spillway portion of the dam, length 131 ft (40.0 m) and crest elevation 1,322 ft (403 m), is an ungated ogee crest located 131 ft (40.0 m) from the right abutment. This dam is owned by Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

EXTREMES OBSERVED FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Maximum elevation, 1,323.99 ft (403.552 m), Feb. 3; minimum elevation, 1,308.61 ft (398.864 m), Aug. 17.

Capacity Table
(based on data from Puerto Rico Electric Power Authority)

Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet	Elevation, in feet	Contents, in acre-feet
1,306	2,010	1,319	4,400
1,309	2,610	1,322	5,200
1,312	3,100	1,324	5,800

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1				---	1323.79	1323.62	1321.47	1320.79	1317.40	A	1309.47	A
2				---	1323.82	1323.61	1321.42	1320.68	1317.23		1309.30	
3				---	1323.77	1323.59	1321.36	1320.57	1316.99		1309.58	
4				---	1323.61	1323.58	1321.29	1320.44	1316.70		1309.58	
5				---	1323.58	1323.57	1321.22	1320.29	1316.43		1309.52	
6				---	1323.55	1323.54	1321.22	1320.24	1316.13		1309.38	
7				---	1323.53	1323.48	1321.25	1320.09	A		1309.27	A
8				---	1323.53	1323.46	1321.19	1319.93		A	1309.16	1316.14
9				---	1323.53	1323.43	1321.13	1319.80		1313.31	1309.04	1316.43
10				---	1323.54	1322.36	1321.04	1320.04		1313.12	1309.03	1316.91
11				---	1323.54	1322.27	1320.97	1320.04		1312.97	1309.19	1320.89
12				---	1323.54	1322.17	1320.88	1320.00		1312.81	1309.08	1322.28
13				---	1323.54	1322.08	1320.78	1319.94		1312.66	1308.94	1322.50
14				---	1323.54	1322.99	1320.68	1319.88		1312.49	1308.79	1322.62
15				---	1323.57	1322.96	1320.59	1319.79		1312.33	1308.69	1322.70
16				---	1323.54	1322.95	1320.47	1319.66		1312.11	1308.63	1322.74
17				---	1323.54	1321.94	1321.44	1319.56		1311.92	1309.45	1322.76
18				---	1323.53	1321.90	1321.62	1319.44		1311.69	1309.79	1322.77
19				---	1323.53	1321.85	1321.58	1319.31		1311.50	1309.86	1322.83
20				---	1323.53	1321.83	1321.55	1319.19		1311.29	1309.78	1322.86
21				---	1323.51	1321.79	1321.65	1319.11		1311.10	1309.65	1322.81
22				---	1323.53	1321.73	1321.59	1318.95		1310.97	1310.36	1322.69
23				---	1323.52	1321.64	1321.53	1318.80		1310.82	1310.97	1322.57
24				---	1323.52	1321.56	1321.46	1318.64		1310.65	1314.96	1322.45
25				---	1323.51	1321.51	1321.37	1318.48		1310.48	1317.14	1322.31
26				---	1323.59	1321.45	1321.28	1318.33		1310.36	1317.27	1322.14
27				---	1323.68	1321.46	1321.16	1318.17		1310.22	1317.35	1321.97
28				---	1323.63	1321.46	1321.06	1318.00		1310.14	1317.32	1321.82
29				1323.69	1323.62	1321.47	1320.95	1317.84		1309.98	1317.18	1321.72
30				1323.69	---	1321.49	1320.84	1317.69	A	1309.80	1317.03	1321.63
31				1323.72	---	1321.50	---	1317.55		1309.61	1316.85	---
TOTAL				---	38383.76	40994.24	39636.04	40901.24	---	---	40651.61	---
MEAN				---	1323.58	1322.39	1321.20	1319.39	---	---	1311.34	---
MAX				---	1323.82	1323.62	1321.65	1320.79	---	---	1317.35	---
MIN				---	1323.51	1321.45	1320.47	1317.55	---	---	1308.63	---

A No gage-height record.

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

139

50047600 RIO DE BAYAMON NEAR AGUAS BUENAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'39", long 66°08'39", at bridge on Highway 156, and 2.9 mi (4.7 km) west of Aguas Buenas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.5 mi² (47.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-65, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
16...	1010	36	260	7.60	25.0	4.4	8.0	99	<10	K400	940
DEC											
02...	1410	28	200	7.40	25.0	45	7.4	91	32	830	1100
FEB 1988											
11...	1330	38	255	7.80	24.0	--	8.6	104	--	490	470
APR											
05...	1550	31	260	7.40	24.0	8.8	7.5	91	37	360	560
JUN											
14...	1410	30	270	7.50	29.5	5.5	8.1	102	41	200	590
AUG											
11...	1230	E60	230	8.40	27.0	8.0	9.1	117	10	2000	K150

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT WH FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
16...	99	3	23	10	19	0.9	2.5	96	<0.5	6.4	17
DEC											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	67	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	87	--	--	--
APR											
05...	94	0	22	9.5	16	0.7	1.8	89	<0.5	8.4	16
JUN											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	89	--	--	--
AUG											
11...	82	0	19	8.5	17	0.8	2.1	87	--	11	15

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
16...	0.10	26	162	16	3	0.29	0.01	0.30	0.02	0.28
DEC										
02...	--	--	--	--	18	1.47	0.13	1.60	0.33	0.27
FEB 1988										
11...	--	--	--	--	9	--	<0.01	0.50	<0.01	--
APR										
05...	0.20	25	158	13	7	0.27	0.03	0.30	0.01	0.29
JUN										
14...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<0.01	0.20	<0.01	--
AUG										
11...	0.10	22	147	--	11	0.24	0.06	0.30	0.15	0.05

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

141

50047990 RIO GUAYNABO NEAR BAYAMON, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'32", long 66°07'59", at bridge on Highway 833, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Rio de Bayamon, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) southeast of Bayamon plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--73.2 mi² (189.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1964, 1971-73, 1976, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
13...	1140	17	435	7.20	29.5	1.8	5.2	68	--	K67000	2400
DEC 04...	1240	34	404	7.10	27.5	4.4	5.6	70	24	K6700	1000
FEB 1988											
18...	0905	29	411	6.90	23.0	--	6.6	76	--	K13000	K1800
APR 22...	0810	30	475	6.80	25.0	1.4	4.5	54	<10	45000	5100
JUN 10...	0935	11	465	6.90	28.5	4.5	6.2	78	22	K12000	2900
AUG 08...	1350	19	414	6.80	31.0	16	6.4	86	63	K16000	2300

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
13...	150	0	39	12	26	1	3.6	160	<0.5	14	32
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
APR 22...	170	2	45	13	27	0.9	3.2	150	<0.5	21	31
JUN 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
AUG 08...	150	0	40	12	25	0.9	3.0	150	--	14	26

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
13...	0.20	29	252	12	17	0.23	0.07	0.30	1.20	0.70
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	12	0.70	0.10	0.80	0.46	0.54
FEB 1988										
18...	--	--	--	--	9	0.62	0.08	0.70	0.17	0.63
APR 22...	0.20	27	266	22	21	0.34	0.06	0.40	0.78	0.62
JUN 10...	--	--	--	--	8	0.41	0.09	0.50	0.25	0.55
AUG 08...	0.20	26	236	12	31	0.52	0.08	0.60	0.25	0.55

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50048510 RIO DE BAYAMON AT FLOOD CHANNEL AT BAYAMON, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'29", long 66°09'04", at bridge on Highway 890, 1.0 (1.6 km) downstream from bridge on Highway 2, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) above mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--71.9 mi² (186.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

REMARKS.--Prior to 1979 sampling site was 0.8 mile (1.3 km) downstream but was changed because of flood channel construction.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
05...	1255	40	392	7.30	30.5	14	6.2	82	29	K17000	K450
DEC 03...	1155	75	388	7.10	26.5	28	6.1	75	26	22000	3900
FEB 1988											
05...	1300	162	313	6.90	24.5	--	6.6	79	--	89000	4900
APR 08...	1240	46	428	6.90	29.5	110	4.8	63	23	29000	4700
JUN 03...	1215	41	435	6.80	31.5	2.1	6.0	82	150	K97000	K290
AUG 08...	1240	38	383	7.20	32.0	17	5.0	67	~10	K14000	K600

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
05...	150	14	40	13	23	0.8	2.9	140	<0.5	18	26
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
APR 08...	150	8	40	13	25	0.9	2.6	130	<0.5	22	27
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
AUG 08...	150	4	39	12	22	0.8	2.9	140	--	16	24

DATE	FLUORIDE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
05...	0.20	29	236	26	15	0.36	0.14	0.50	0.56	1.20
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	61	0.74	0.06	0.80	0.11	0.29
FEB 1988										
05...	--	--	--	--	--	0.76	0.04	0.80	0.18	0.62
APR 08...	0.30	27	244	30	126	0.52	0.08	0.60	0.24	0.36
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	15	0.15	0.05	0.20	0.10	0.10
AUG 08...	0.20	25	227	24	9	0.40	0.10	0.50	0.42	0.48

K = non-ideal count

RIO DE BAYAMON BASIN

50048510 RIO DE BAYAMON AT FLOOD CHANNEL AT BAYAMON, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1987 05...	1.8	2.3	6.8	0.32	1	<100	50	<1	3	10
DEC 03...	0.4	1.2	5.3	0.13	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 05...	0.8	1.6	7.1	0.10	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 08...	0.6	1.2	5.3	0.36	1	100	<10	<1	6	30
JUN 03...	0.2	0.4	1.8	0.20	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 08...	0.9	1.4	6.2	0.20	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1987 05...	1600	<5	290	<0.10	2	<1	10	<0.010	6	0.05
DEC 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 08...	8500	5	490	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	<1	0.03
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 03...	1215	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.06	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 03...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01P

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHEME, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 03...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048770 RIO PIEDRAS AT EL SENORIAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'51", long 66°03'56", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, in the Riberas del Senorial Housing area, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) west of Highway 176 and 2.7 mi (4.3 km) southwest of Rio Piedras Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.49 mi² (19.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORDS.--March 1988 to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage in 98.4 ft (30.0 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Maximum discharge, 4,680 ft³/s (132 m³/s), Aug. 24, gage height, 16.08 ft (4.901 m), from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 4.8 ft³/s (0.14 m³/s), Aug. 9.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Apr. 14	2230	2,530	71.6	13.21	4.026	Aug. 24	1500	*4,680	132	*16.08	4.901
May 9	1415	1,950	55.2	12.20	3.709	Sept. 1	1430	1,030	29.2	10.10	3.078
May 10	1730	1,330	37.7	10.87	3.313	Sept. 11	1130	1,560	44.2	11.40	3.475

Minimum discharge, 4.8 ft³/s (0.14 m³/s), Aug. 9.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	
1						---	9.5	7.6	8.7	15	7.0	110	
2						---	9.2	7.2	8.1	10	6.4	33	
3						---	7.8	7.1	7.9	8.0	17	22	
4						---	8.4	6.8	7.6	8.8	9.3	19	
5						---	8.3	7.0	7.4	13	6.9	17	
6						---	7.8	6.8	7.2	9.7	6.0	16	
7						---	9.4	6.5	7.1	22	13	17	
8						---	9.0	6.4	7.0	7.3	6.7	48	
9						---	7.7	160	7.6	7.8	7.5	e70	
10						---	7.5	132	7.2	7.6	53	27	
11						---	9.9	47	11	7.7	17	237	
12						---	14	17	13	8.4	9.7	68	
13						---	9.8	13	10	11	8.6	30	
14						---	156	14	9.6	18	17	e47	
15						---	85	11	14	7.9	10	e45	
16						---	23	10	9.6	7.2	20	e35	
17						---	34	9.6	8.8	35	21	e25	
18						---	84	9.7	8.7	26	12	e18	
19						---	61	11	8.9	12	8.9	e19	
20						---	21	11	14	8.2	8.6	e14	
21						---	15	12	36	7.1	8.4	e11	
22						---	13	11	12	13	15	e130	
23						---	11	e7.8	9.0	11	28	e35	
24						---	20	e7.0	15	9.2	251	e ⁰	
25						---	25	12	e6.8	9.3	8.1	56	e17
26						---	25	11	9.1	8.4	28	e13	
27						---	36	9.2	7.7	7.7	6.6	53	e12
28						---	36	8.1	8.1	8.8	8.0	28	e10
29						---	53	7.9	8.8	7.2	17	23	e9.2
30						---	46	7.6	9.7	6.8	15	15	e9.0
31						---	13	---	8.7	---	8.1	39	---
TOTAL						---	697.1	597.4	303.6	362.1	810.0	1183.2	
MEAN						---	23.2	19.3	10.1	11.7	26.1	39.4	
MAX						---	156	160	36	35	251	237	
MIN						---	7.5	6.4	6.8	6.6	6.0	9.0	
AC-FT						---	1380	1180	602	718	1610	2350	
CFSM						---	3.10	2.57	1.35	1.56	3.49	5.27	
IN.						---	3.46	2.97	1.51	1.80	4.02	5.88	

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50048800 RIO PIEDRAS NEAR RIO PIEDRAS, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°22'15", long 66°03'40", at bridge on Winston Churchill Avenue in the El Senorial Housing area, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) west of Highway 176, and 2.5 mi (4.0 km) southwest of Rio Piedras plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.17 mi² (20.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987										
13...	0805	10	345	7.90	25.0	15	4.8	58	36	29000 K13000
DEC										
04...	1100	12	375	7.30	26.0	25	6.8	83	30	370000 97000
FEB 1988										
17...	0830	16	387	7.20	22.0	--	6.8	77	--	690000 800000
APR										
25...	0930	12	370	7.90	25.0	81	6.7	80	13	140000 K110000
JUN										
13...	0920	9.2	372	7.70	26.0	170	6.1	75	41	K91000 63000
AUG										
10...	0835	6.6	393	6.80	24.0	780	7.7	90	<10	K90000 53000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
13...	120	0	30	11	23	0.9	2.9	120	<0.5	13	24
DEC											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR											
25...	130	5	34	12	22	0.9	2.4	130	<0.5	19	25
JUN											
13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
AUG											
10...	140	4	36	12	29	1	2.2	130	--	18	25

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
13...	0.20	29	205	5.8	10	0.72	0.08	0.80	0.30	0.90
DEC										
04...	--	--	--	--	33	0.85	0.05	0.90	3.1	2.5
FEB 1988										
17...	--	--	--	--	--	0.76	0.04	0.80	3.6	0.70
APR										
25...	0.20	28	220	7.2	147	0.76	0.04	0.80	0.47	0.33
JUN										
13...	--	--	--	--	248	0.58	0.12	0.70	0.67	0.53
AUG										
10...	0.10	31	234	4.2	642	0.66	0.04	0.70	0.41	0.29

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50048800 RIO PIEDRAS NEAR RIO PIEDRAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1987 13...	1.2	2.0	8.9	0.24	1	100	70	<1	5	10
DEC 04...	5.6	6.5	29	1.70	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 17...	4.2	5.0	11.6	0.60	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 25...	0.8	1.6	7.1	0.10	15	100	<10	1	1	20
JUN 13...	1.2	1.9	8.4	0.19	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 10...	0.7	1.4	6.2	0.34	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1987 13...	1300	<5	100	<0.10	2	<1	<10	<0.010	9	0.04
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 25...	6700	27	240	<0.10	<1	<1	30	<0.010	<1	0.03
JUN 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 13...	0920	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.04	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 13...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 13...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049000 RIO PIEDRAS AT RIO PIEDRAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'48", long 66°03'24", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 1, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) southwest of the plaza in Rio Piedras, and 0.4 mi (0.6km) downstream from diversion for water supply.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.5 m² (32.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1958 (maximum discharge measurement only), 1959-64 (annual low-flow measurements only), July 1971 to September 1982, October 1987 to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 50 ft (15.2 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges which are poor. Low flow affected by diversions for water supply.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--12 years (1972-82,1988), 28.1 ft³/s (0.796 m³/s), 30.53 in/yr (775 mm/yr), 20,360 acre-ft/yr (25.10 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 25 ft³/s (0.71 m³/s), 18,100 acre-ft/yr (22 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge 10,000 ft³/s (283 m³/s), Dec. 11, 1975, gage height, 21.02 ft (6.407 m), from rating curve extended above 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurements; minimum daily, 0.26 ft³/s (0.007 m³/s), May 19, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,800 ft³/s (79.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Apr. 14	2400	6,620	187	13.75	4.191	Aug. 24	1545	*9,570	271	*16.86	5.139
May 9	1545	5,650	160	12.66	3.859	Sept. 11	1200	3,210	90.9	9.43	2.874
May 10	1800	3,150	89.2	9.34	2.847	Sept. 22	1645	3,680	104	10.13	3.088

Minimum discharge, 5.2 ft³/s (0.147 m³/s), Apr. 6.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e14	18	103	159	102	18	17	24	13	24	14	218
2	e18	15	55	76	48	20	16	24	13	14	13	45
3	e50	17	21	40	122	18	14	22	12	11	35	33
4	e30	17	14	32	56	17	15	20	12	12	19	26
5	e70	14	54	34	34	17	14	21	12	17	13	27
6	e25	16	35	24	27	17	11	21	13	13	13	22
7	e18	15	316	24	22	18	15	21	13	108	23	24
8	e17	18	e290	21	22	16	14	21	17	12	14	83
9	e18	15	e30	19	22	17	13	485	15	11	17	126
10	e16	13	e25	20	20	15	11	276	14	11	167	60
11	e16	13	e22	23	20	14	14	121	19	11	30	417
12	e15	13	e20	20	27	18	18	43	26	12	16	88
13	e14	30	e19	29	25	15	13	26	23	14	11	47
14	e14	13	17	25	19	15	256	36	27	36	22	83
15	e25	8.1	54	19	30	14	408	22	35	14	14	79
16	e30	15	20	18	20	23	79	18	30	13	24	61
17	e50	55	15	21	21	25	100	18	20	61	35	40
18	e40	42	13	24	22	13	172	16	17	44	20	32
19	21	16	32	32	18	14	106	16	26	20	13	34
20	15	11	123	18	18	14	46	18	35	15	13	23
21	28	9.1	84	18	19	11	46	15	73	13	10	20
22	14	8.6	35	16	19	12	37	15	27	31	38	222
23	25	38	27	15	18	11	34	13	16	19	58	38
24	36	172	24	16	19	63	111	12	39	16	885	29
25	59	86	26	22	20	36	46	12	16	19	109	25
26	18	133	53	15	19	53	40	14	14	17	48	20
27	15	445	34	14	34	49	34	13	12	14	90	17
28	21	84	30	36	21	48	30	14	37	16	45	16
29	18	31	23	98	18	73	27	14	13	27	44	15
30	15	18	22	29	---	67	27	15	12	28	27	15
31	19	---	104	37	---	23	---	14	---	17	65	---
TOTAL	784	1398.8	1740	994	882	784	1784	1420	651	690	1945	1985
MEAN	25.3	46.6	56.1	32.1	30.4	25.3	59.5	45.8	21.7	22.3	62.7	66.2
MAX	70	445	316	159	122	73	408	485	73	108	885	417
MIN	14	8.1	13	14	18	11	11	12	12	11	10	15
AC-FT	1560	2770	3450	1970	1750	1560	3540	2820	1290	1370	3860	3940
CFSM	2.02	3.73	4.49	2.57	2.43	2.02	4.76	3.66	1.74	1.78	5.02	5.29
IN.	2.33	4.16	5.18	2.96	2.62	2.33	5.31	4.23	1.94	2.05	5.79	5.91

WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 15057.8 MEAN 41.1 MAX 885 MIN 8.1 AC-FT 29870 CFSM 3.29 IN. 44.81

e Estimated

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50049100 RIO PIEDRAS AT HATO REY, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'34", long 66°04'10", at bridge on Avenida Piniero at Expreso Las Americas, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) southwest of Hato Rey.

DRAINAGE AREA.--15.4 mi² (39.9 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1971 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
13...	1210	20	431	7.80	31.0	3.6	4.0	53	68	K610000	83000
DEC 04...	0815	31	416	7.10	25.0	4.7	5.6	68	58	220000	30000
FEB 1988											
17...	1145	23	430	7.00	25.0	--	6.0	72	--	K110000	63000
APR 25...	1210	42	374	7.70	27.0	34	6.6	82	10	260000	200000
JUN 13...	1135	18	453	7.40	29.0	12	1.7	22	69	K1160000	910000
AUG 10...	1055	12	441	6.90	26.5	40	6.0	73	10	K86000	K1160000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT WH FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
13...	140	0	39	11	30	1	4.4	160	<0.5	16	31
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
APR 25...	140	0	39	10	23	0.9	3.3	160	<0.5	21	24
JUN 13...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
AUG 10...	150	2	40	12	30	1	3.0	160	--	15	30

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
13...	0.20	29	257	14	10	0.34	0.16	0.50	2.10	1.7
DEC 04...	--	--	--	--	13	0.58	0.12	0.70	1.10	0.60
FEB 1988										
17...	--	--	--	--	--	0.82	0.18	1.00	1.70	1.0
APR 25...	0.20	21	225	25	44	0.72	0.08	0.80	0.75	0.85
JUN 13...	--	--	--	--	12	0.40	0.10	0.50	4.90	1.4
AUG 10...	0.10	29	248	8.4	180	0.70	0.10	0.80	0.80	0.50

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

151

50049310 QUEBRADA JOSEFINA AT PINERO AVENUE

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'34", long 66°04'31", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank, 75 ft (23 m) downstream from bridge at highway 17, Piñero Avenue, 1.6 mi (2.6 km), northwest from Rio Piedras Plaza, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) north from University of Puerto Rico Medical Center and 0.4 mi (0.64 km) upstream from confluence with Rio Piedras.

DRAINAGE AREA.--19.0 mi² (49.2 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1988 to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage 13.1 ft (4.0 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Record fair.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,200 ft³/s (34.0 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Apr. 14	2400	1,420	40.2	5.27	1.606	July 7	0245	1,320	37.4	5.11	1.557
Apr. 24	1400	1,830	51.8	5.86	1.786	Aug.24	1530	*3,420	96.8	*7.77	2.368
May 9	1330	1,720	48.7	5.71	1.740						

Minimum discharge, 1.2 ft³/s (0.04 m³/s), Aug. 17.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1					---	6.0	5.7	4.7	5.7	7.1	2.9	2.9
2					---	6.2	4.6	4.9	4.6	2.4	4.0	2.7
3					---	4.3	4.3	4.8	4.1	3.1	18	2.5
4					---	4.3	4.3	4.4	4.6	3.3	2.7	2.6
5					---	4.3	4.7	4.1	4.6	8.9	2.4	2.7
6					---	4.0	4.7	3.6	3.8	6.7	2.8	2.6
7					---	4.2	7.1	3.1	3.7	87	11	2.1
8					---	4.3	3.6	3.1	4.8	1.6	2.8	22
9					---	4.1	4.4	152	3.1	1.6	4.3	70
10					---	4.2	5.0	70	4.7	2.5	33	28
11					---	4.3	5.8	34	5.2	4.0	4.5	86
12					---	3.7	8.5	3.3	6.1	3.0	2.0	25
13					---	3.6	3.0	3.6	5.8	4.0	2.0	16
14					---	3.2	49	14	15	9.1	6.8	33
15					---							
16					---	3.0	21	2.4	4.6	2.5	6.7	10
17					---	8.8	49	3.1	5.0	4.0	13	6.5
18					---	3.6	49	3.5	4.0	9.7	2.0	6.7
19					---	5.5	25	4.3	8.6	4.0	1.7	9.3
20					---	6.6	11	12	25	3.9	1.6	6.7
21					---	4.3	7.0	2.6	7.9	3.9	2.6	8.6
22					---	2.7	4.3	8.0	3.4	2.0	10	21
23					---	5.0	4.6	9.1	6.7	1.9	7.4	5.1
24					---	4.9	22	92	7.3	7.1	-2.5	344
25					---	5.1	4.4	13	5.6	3.3	2.3	14
26					---	4.6	18	8.0	5.7	1.8	3.8	5.7
27					---	9.2	20	6.0	4.1	2.2	1.8	16
28					---	3.8	11	4.4	4.8	59	1.9	12
29					---	4.3	35	5.9	4.6	2.2	5.1	19
30					---	---	8.9	6.1	5.5	2.0	5.5	2.5
31					---	---	3.6	---	4.9	---	2.8	7.0
TOTAL					---	227.4	620.2	392.3	216.7	212.3	573.5	430.3
MEAN					---	7.34	20.7	12.7	7.22	6.85	18.5	14.3
MAX					---	35	191	152	59	87	344	86
MIN					---	3.0	3.0	2.2	1.8	1.6	1.6	2.1
AC-FT					---	451	1230	778	430	421	1140	853
CFSM					---	.39	1.09	.67	.38	.36	.97	.75
IN.					---	.45	1.21	.77	.42	.42	1.12	.84

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN

50049820 LAGUNA SAN JOSE NO. 2 AT SAN JUAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'46", long 66°02'10", 0.2 mi (0.3 km) east of Caño de Martín Peña, and 650 ft (200 m) south of Isla Guachinango.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOCATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANSPARENCY (SECCHI DISK (IN))	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, SATURATION (%)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	ALKALINITY TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)
OCT 1987											
23...	1000	1.00	21000	8.20	30.0	13.2	1.6	21	60000	25000	150
DEC 17...	1005	1.00	14700	8.20	27.5	18.0	8.4	106	K11000	K1800	120
FEB 1988											
25...	1010	1.00	22000	9.00	26.5	14.4	9.0	112	K6500	K1600	120
APR 26...	1050	1.00	11500	8.90	28.0	14.0	9.9	126	K17000	K640	88
JUN 20...	1015	1.00	23000	8.90	29.0	10.0	7.3	93	5800	<100	120
AUG 19...	1045	1.00	22300	8.70	28.5	17.5	10.1	128	K1400	K100	110

DATE	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOSPHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CARBON, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS C)
OCT 1987											
23...	6	--	0.02	<0.10	0.85	2.3	3.1	--	--	0.53	16
DEC 17...	8	--	0.03	<0.10	0.97	2.0	3.0	--	--	0.43	13
FEB 1988											
25...	27	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	--	1.9	--	--	0.47	30
APR 26...	30	0.12	0.08	0.20	1.50	0.9	2.4	2.6	12	0.33	25
JUN 20...	9	--	0.03	<0.10	0.11	1.8	1.9	--	--	0.26	17
AUG 19...	16	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.10	2.7	2.8	--	--	0.43	21

K = non-ideal count

RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASIN
50049920 BAHIA DE SAN JUAN NO. 5 AT SAN JUAN, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION--Lat 18°26'37", long 66°05'11", 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Puente de la Constitución, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) south from U.S. Naval Reservation.

DRAINAGE--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD--Water years 1974 to present.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOCATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANSPARENCY (SECCHI DISK (IN))	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, PERCENT SATURATION	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	ALKALINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)
OCT 1987 23...	1150	1.00	32000	8.20	31.0	16.6	2.4	32	32000	4100	140
DEC 17...	1215	1.00	27000	7.60	28.5	24.0	3.7	47	32000	2600	140
FEB 1988 25...	1200	1.00	29000	7.40	27.5	25.2	6.5	82	270000	2300	140
APR 26...	1145	1.00	13000	7.30	27.0	18.0	2.3	29	340000	23000	120
JUN 20...	1140	1.00	31000	7.90	29.5	29.6	2.8	36	K70000	3000	130
AUG 19...	1245	1.00	>50000	7.50	30.0	9.0	2.2	29	K150000	5600	130

DATE	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOSPHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CARBON, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS C)
OCT 1987 23...	3	--	0.04	<0.10	1.00	0.9	1.9	--	--	0.28	11
DEC 17...	5	0.20	0.10	0.30	1.30	1.9	3.2	3.5	15	0.31	6.8
FEB 1988 25...	25	0.14	0.06	0.20	0.97	0.93	1.9	2.1	9.3	0.42	10
APR 26...	37	0.07	0.03	0.10	1.70	1.5	3.2	3.3	14	0.31	6.4
JUN 20...	6	--	0.03	<0.10	1.20	0.7	1.9	--	--	0.38	7.7
AUG 19...	8	--	0.02	<0.10	1.20	1.5	2.7	--	--	0.50	9.5

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050300 QUEBRADA BLASINA NEAR CAROLINA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'27", long 65°58'28", at bridge on Highway 3, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) south of Valle Arriba Heights housing area, and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) west-southwest of Carolina plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.96 mi² (7.67 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1973 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATUR-ATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
06...	1245	5.0	558	7.80	30.0	2.3	3.6	47	48	290000	3000
DEC											
02...	1145	7.9	426	7.00	26.0	21	2.7	33	20	210000	8800
FEB 1988											
11...	1210	5.7	776	7.00	26.5	4.4	0.6	7	34	K1500000	K1300000
APR											
05...	1200	5.2	576	7.60	27.0	15	1.6	20	110	K600000	K600000
JUN											
01...	1150	6.5	640	7.20	30.0	1.5	2.0	26	55	2300000	310000
AUG											
09...	1125	2.6	512	6.60	28.5	2.2	0.8	10	34	K2300000	330000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
06...	190	1	60	10	35	1	4.0	190	<0.5	23	54
DEC											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
APR											
05...	180	0	54	9.8	49	2	3.8	200	<0.5	18	46
JUN											
01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
AUG											
09...	170	0	53	9.1	42	1	3.5	180	--	17	49

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
06...	0.20	25	325	4.4	4	0.79	0.11	0.90	0.65	0.55
DEC										
02...	--	--	--	--	29	0.83	0.07	0.90	0.51	0.89
FEB 1988										
11...	--	--	--	--	2	0.17	0.13	0.30	3.30	1.7
APR										
05...	0.20	25	327	4.6	<1	0.11	0.09	0.20	0.43	1.7
JUN										
01...	--	--	--	--	11	0.09	0.11	0.20	2.60	2.3
AUG										
09...	0.20	27	312	2.2	5	0.07	0.03	0.10	2.80	1.6

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050900 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT QUEBRADA ARENAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'10", long 65°59'22", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at intersection of Highways 181 and 9990, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from confluence with Rio Emajagua and about 7.1 mi (11.4 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.00 mi² (15.54 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1977 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 640 ft (195 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--11 years (1978-88), 31.4 ft³/s (0.889 m³/s), 71.07 in/yr, (1,805 mm/yr), 22,750 acre-ft/yr (28.05 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 29 ft³/s (0.82 m³/s), 21,000 acre-ft/yr (26 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 11,700 ft³/s (331 m³/s), Nov. 5, 1983, gage height, 14.78 ft (4.505 m), from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 2.8 ft³/s (0.079 m³/s), May 5, 6, 1979.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,000 ft³/s (56.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov.24	1800	2,770	78.4	9.03	2.752	Aug. 10	2015	2,010	56.9	8.21	2.502
Nov.27	0930	*6,510	184	*11.95	3.642	Aug. 24	1415	2,710	76.7	8.97	2.734
Nov.28	0815	2,390	67.7	8.64	2.633	Aug. 25	0700	2,330	66.0	8.57	2.612
Dec. 7	2315	4,380	124	10.44	3.182	Sept. 11	0815	3,500	99.1	9.71	2.960
July 2	0800	3,720	105	9.90	3.018						

Minimum discharge, 4.2 ft³/s (0.119 m³/s), Apr. 28, 29, May 5.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	20	13	38	54	19	11	7.7	22	6.0	168	23	26
2	12	12	78	31	29	11	7.7	7.0	6.2	892	19	23
3	30	11	30	33	39	10	7.5	5.9	6.5	54	29	20
4	20	39	25	39	19	9.9	7.6	5.1	6.6	34	23	19
5	22	110	23	31	23	9.9	7.5	4.6	6.2	26	17	18
6	13	46	42	27	16	9.9	7.7	23	6.1	39	17	17
7	11	25	629	24	14	9.9	7.7	7.3	6.1	95	18	20
8	9.7	20	263	23	13	9.6	7.1	5.5	6.7	26	16	17
9	9.9	18	57	25	15	9.1	6.7	4.9	6.7	26	17	34
10	9.4	15	42	27	15	8.9	6.0	6.1	6.6	43	228	90
11	8.6	14	39	33	13	8.8	5.8	7.7	7.5	28	96	566
12	8.3	13	32	26	21	8.8	5.9	15	6.9	23	37	263
13	7.8	12	27	29	30	8.7	5.6	6.3	9.2	21	24	106
14	25	12	25	23	15	9.1	5.3	6.3	22	44	20	79
15	59	11	24	19	14	8.5	11	6.8	173	21	20	54
16	55	17	20	18	14	8.3	8.1	7.5	48	18	24	42
17	131	15	19	17	13	8.3	6.5	11	15	18	33	35
18	346	19	17	16	13	8.1	6.5	9.3	14	29	34	30
19	53	14	18	15	12	7.6	5.6	8.1	37	22	20	75
20	26	12	21	14	19	13	5.2	20	39	18	18	31
21	20	11	23	14	13	8.6	5.2	30	49	15	16	25
22	16	11	44	14	12	7.8	5.0	11	62	29	229	24
23	15	16	20	14	12	7.5	4.8	8.4	42	28	63	22
24	15	958	17	13	15	7.4	4.8	7.0	24	16	451	20
25	18	136	16	14	12	9.8	4.8	6.4	19	15	225	18
26	22	271	17	14	17	10	5.2	6.8	39	23	53	17
27	15	1180	18	17	19	28	5.5	6.8	21	16	46	16
28	78	500	25	14	12	24	4.6	6.7	17	129	39	16
29	25	85	18	23	11	11	5.1	8.2	16	34	34	14
30	15	50	17	14	---	9.4	4.7	8.8	70	113	34	14
31	15	---	27	14	---	8.1	---	7.0	---	31	27	---
TOTAL	1130.7	3666	1711	689	489	320.0	188.4	296.5	794.3	2094	1950	1751
MEAN	36.5	122	55.2	22.2	16.9	10.3	6.28	9.56	26.5	67.5	62.9	58.4
MAX	346	1180	629	54	39	28	11	30	173	892	451	566
MIN	7.8	11	16	13	11	7.4	4.6	4.6	6.0	15	16	14
AC-FT	2240	7270	3390	1370	970	635	374	588	1580	4150	3870	3470
CFSM	6.08	20.4	9.20	3.70	2.81	1.72	1.05	1.59	4.41	11.3	10.5	9.73
IN.	7.01	22.73	10.61	4.27	3.03	1.98	1.17	1.84	4.92	12.98	12.09	10.86

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 12444.6 MEAN 34.1 MAX 1180 MIN 5.7 AC-FT 24680 CFSM 5.68 IN. 77.16
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 15079.9 MEAN 41.2 MAX 1180 MIN 4.6 AC-FT 29910 CFSM 6.87 IN. 93.50

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50050900 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT QUEBRADA ARENAS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 14	1209	42.6	94	26.5	MAR, 02	1315	11.0	148	23.0
NOV, 13	1100	12.4	148	25.0	APR, 05	1045	7.81	148	24.0
DEC, 09	0812	61.1	114	23.0	MAY, 06	1139	78.1	134	24.0
JAN, 04	1108	55.4	131	23.0	JUN, 03	1330	6.63	153	28.0
FEB, 01	1252	16.3	143	23.5	JUL, 12	1315	23.12	130	27.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'40", long 65°58'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from bridge on Highway 181, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.25 mi² (8.42 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 459 ft (140 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 7,400 ft³/s (210 m³/s), May 17, 1985, gage height, 14.58 ft (4.44 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 400 ft³/s (11.3 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 0.46 ft³/s (0.013 m³/s), May 3, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	unknown	2,620	74.2	10.41	3.173	Aug. 24	1400	*2,910	82.4	10.76	3.280
Dec. 7	1630	2,810	79.3	10.65	3.246	Aug. 25	0715	1,350	38.2	8.77	2.673
July 2	0745	1,480	41.9	8.97	2.734						

Minimum discharge, 1.2 ft³/s (0.034 m³/s), many days.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	2.4	2.8	7.0	28	3.6	6.8	1.8	1.4	1.5	28	2.6	5.3
2	1.6	2.2	34	13	3.6	14	1.8	1.4	1.4	192	2.3	4.4
3	2.7	1.9	5.9	7.8	6.8	4.9	1.9	1.2	1.4	11	4.2	3.6
4	2.4	2.1	5.1	7.5	3.8	3.8	1.9	1.2	1.4	4.9	3.9	3.1
5	1.7	5.1	4.1	9.4	4.1	3.3	1.8	1.2	1.3	3.5	3.0	2.7
6	1.5	4.2	6.6	9.4	3.7	3.1	2.1	4.7	1.3	10	2.7	2.5
7	1.7	2.8	457	7.7	3.4	3.0	2.0	1.8	1.2	52	4.6	2.5
8	1.3	2.2	168	7.8	3.4	3.0	1.9	1.4	1.3	5.0	4.0	2.4
9	1.4	2.0	32	8.1	3.6	2.8	1.9	1.4	1.6	3.6	2.9	6.0
10	1.4	2.0	19	6.9	3.5	2.6	1.8	16	1.8	5.7	75	6.9
11	1.3	1.9	13	9.0	3.4	2.5	1.7	2.5	1.4	6.0	16	156
12	1.3	3.4	9.4	7.7	8.9	2.3	1.7	1.6	1.3	4.2	5.8	62
13	1.2	2.0	7.8	9.0	20	2.4	1.7	1.5	1.8	3.6	4.0	24
14	2.7	1.7	6.7	7.0	3.3	2.5	1.5	1.5	2.2	5.4	3.3	15
15	13	1.6	6.4	5.4	3.1	2.0	3.7	2.0	15	3.2	3.1	10
16	21	12	5.7	4.7	3.0	2.0	2.4	1.4	12	2.9	5.6	7.7
17	61	4.1	5.3	4.3	2.9	1.9	4.6	1.4	2.7	2.9	15	5.7
18	167	2.9	4.8	3.8	2.9	2.0	2.5	1.3	1.8	11	23	4.8
19	24	2.3	5.8	3.6	2.8	1.9	1.7	1.4	1.6	4.7	5.4	16
20	7.0	2.0	10	3.4	3.1	2.1	1.6	2.2	15	3.2	4.0	5.0
21	4.1	1.9	8.1	3.3	2.7	2.1	1.5	1.9	10	2.7	3.4	3.9
22	3.2	1.9	40	3.1	2.5	1.9	1.4	1.6	5.6	5.1	9.2	3.3
23	2.8	8.9	11	3.1	2.6	1.9	1.5	1.5	2.4	3.1	4.8	3.0
24	2.7	e320	8.8	3.2	2.7	1.9	1.4	1.5	2.0	2.6	229	2.9
25	3.2	e24	7.0	3.2	2.8	2.0	1.4	1.4	18	2.5	113	2.6
26	3.6	e100	6.8	3.0	24	2.0	1.4	1.5	15	2.8	18	2.4
27	10	e400	5.9	2.9	15	4.4	1.9	1.5	4.2	2.4	14	2.2
28	25	e100	6.6	2.9	4.3	2.4	1.4	1.4	2.5	3.7	18	2.1
29	5.0	e35	5.7	3.5	3.6	1.9	1.2	1.8	2.2	7.7	13	2.0
30	3.2	e20	4.9	2.8	---	1.9	1.2	3.0	2.4	4.0	8.6	1.8
31	2.9	---	14	2.9	---	1.9	---	1.7	---	2.9	6.2	---
TOTAL	383.3	1072.9	932.4	197.4	153.1	93.2	56.3	67.3	133.3	402.3	627.6	371.8
MEAN	12.4	35.8	30.1	6.37	5.28	3.01	1.88	2.17	4.44	13.0	20.2	12.4
MAX	167	400	457	28	24	14	4.6	16	18	192	229	156
MIN	1.2	1.6	4.1	2.8	2.5	1.9	1.2	1.2	1.2	2.4	2.3	1.8
AC-FT	760	2130	1850	392	304	185	112	133	264	798	1240	737
CFSM	3.80	11.0	9.25	1.96	1.62	.93	.58	.67	1.37	3.99	6.23	3.81
IN.	4.39	12.28	10.67	2.26	1.75	1.07	.64	.77	1.53	4.60	7.18	4.26

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 4009.3 MEAN 11.0 MAX 457 MIN 1.2 AC-FT 7950 CFSM 3.38 IN. 45.89
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 4490.9 MEAN 12.3 MAX 457 MIN 1.2 AC-FT 8910 CFSM 3.78 IN. 51.40

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--JANUARY 1985 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 05	1148	1.75	258	28.0	MAR, 03	1106	4.41	226	24.0
NOV, 18	1013	2.95	255	25.5	APR, 06	0930	1.90	287	24.5
DEC, 09	1217	29.8	172	26.0	MAY, 06	1431	7.09	260	28.0
JAN, 05	1100	9.06	227	24.5	JUN, 02	1050	1.42	283	27.8
FEB, 02	1024	3.81	245	23.0	JUL, 11	0933	6.97	221	26.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR-Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1985 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1984 to September 1986.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir. The suspended-sediment data for May 17, 1985, October 6, 1985, May 8, 1986, and May 13, 1986 are estimated.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 7,300 mg/L Oct.06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 25,800 tons (23,400 tonnes) May 17, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 tons (0.01) tonne several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1985-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1985	6,720 (May 18)	1 (several days)	25,800 (May 17)	0.01 (several days)
1986	7,300 (Oct. 06)	1 (several days)	15,200 (Oct. 06)	0.01 (several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)									
										OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
										1	9.0	100	2.4	26	362	123	2.4	5
2	8.0	95	2.1	69	994	582	15	252	68									
3	16	224	34	265	4110	8870	4.1	7	.08									
4	7.4	70	1.4	82	1110	276	2.8	4	.03									
5	10	135	9.7	169	2480	1920	2.4	1	.01									
6	7.0	100	1.9	160	2240	1270	2.3	1	.01									
7	8.0	100	2.2	105	1350	471	2.5	1	.01									
8	6.0	70	1.1	55	731	125	3.5	3	.03									
9	55	795	744	35	450	43	3.9	2	.02									
10	10	80	2.2	21	400	23	4.1	2	.02									
11	8.0	60	1.3	11	150	4.5	14	229	78									
12	7.0	70	1.3	8.2	40	.89	4.5	400	4.9									
13	22	325	73	7.2	20	.39	3.1	18	.15									
14	95	1540	2000	14	134	12	2.6	28	.20									
15	8.1	100	2.2	13	144	7.7	2.4	22	.14									
16	20	336	118	8.0	20	.43	2.2	19	.11									
17	14	250	9.5	7.0	3	.06	2.0	8	.04									
18	5.0	45	.61	6.1	3	.05	1.6	5	.02									
19	4.5	28	.34	5.6	3	.05	1.7	5	.02									
20	4.3	20	.23	5.0	3	.04	1.6	2	.01									
21	4.2	20	.23	4.5	3	.04	1.6	4	.02									
22	4.5	20	.24	4.3	3	.03	1.5	5	.02									
23	5.0	18	.24	4.5	3	.04	1.4	5	.02									
24	4.4	15	.18	3.8	3	.03	1.9	5	.03									
25	9.0	46	.88	3.7	6	.11	3.4	30	.28									
26	5.9	20	.32	4.4	30	.92	2.6	18	.13									
27	5.5	15	.22	3.1	5	.04	2.9	16	.13									
28	5.9	10	.16	2.8	5	.04	3.1	15	.13									
29	5.6	8	.12	2.6	5	.04	2.0	14	.08									
30	8.2	34	.95	2.5	5	.03	2.4	12	.08									
31	6.4	25	.43	---	---	---	1.9	11	.06									
TOTAL	388.9	---	3011.45	1108.3	---	13730.43	103.4	---	152.81									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR-Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	5.9	88	11	1.1	5	.01	1.7	4	.02
2	4.7	74	1.3	1.0	5	.01	1.5	4	.02
3	2.5	6	.04	.96	4	.50	1.6	4	.02
4	2.3	4	.02	.92	4	.20	1.6	4	.02
5	1.8	3	.80	.92	4	.01	2.1	14	.12
6	1.8	3	.50	.90	4	.01	3.3	31	.32
7	1.7	3	.01	.85	4	.01	5.2	89	.77
8	1.5	3	.01	.89	4	.01	2.3	15	.09
9	1.4	3	.01	.99	3	.80	1.6	9	.50
10	1.6	3	.01	1.1	3	.70	1.2	9	.20
11	1.7	3	.01	1.2	3	.70	1.1	9	.20
12	1.8	3	.01	1.3	3	.70	1.0	9	.02
13	2.2	3	.02	1.5	3	.90	.94	9	.02
14	2.5	2	.90	1.8	3	.90	.87	9	.02
15	2.8	2	.80	2.0	3	.90	.81	8	.80
16	2.4	2	.50	1.9	3	.90	.78	8	.50
17	2.2	2	.01	1.7	3	.80	.79	8	.20
18	1.8	1	.90	1.6	3	.80	2.5	28	.46
19	1.6	1	.70	1.7	4	.02	1.1	12	.04
20	1.4	1	.50	1.5	4	.02	.86	12	.03
21	1.2	1	.30	1.1	4	.01	.84	12	.03
22	1.0	1	.20	.94	4	.01	.83	12	.03
23	1.1	1	.00	1.0	4	.01	.81	12	.03
24	1.1	1	.20	1.1	4	.01	.80	12	.03
25	.89	1	.80	1.1	4	.01	.77	10	.02
26	1.0	2	.01	1.2	4	.01	.78	10	.02
27	.96	2	.20	2.4	4	.03	.80	10	.02
28	1.0	3	.01	2.2	4	.02	.76	10	.02
29	.97	3	.50	---	---	---	33	669	362
30	.99	4	.01	---	---	---	2.5	25	.17
31	1.0	4	.70	---	---	---	2.1	15	.09
TOTAL	56.81	---	20.98	36.87	---	9.01	76.84	---	366.83
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	1.5	10	.04	.79	4	.01	3.9	4	.04
2	1.6	6	.80	.69	4	.01	3.6	4	.04
3	1.7	5	.02	.67	4	.01	4.1	4	.04
4	1.7	4	.90	.61	3	.90	9.6	4	.10
5	1.6	4	.80	.60	3	.70	5.4	4	.06
6	1.6	4	.50	.58	3	.50	3.1	4	.03
7	1.5	4	.20	.55	3	.20	3.0	4	.03
8	1.2	4	.10	.51	3	.00	3.0	4	.03
9	1.0	4	.01	.63	3	.01	2.8	4	.03
10	.91	3	.70	.53	3	.00	2.8	4	.03
11	.86	3	.40	.56	2	.80	2.9	4	.03
12	.81	3	.01	1.5	22	.27	2.8	4	.03
13	.94	3	.01	1.6	20	.33	2.5	4	.03
14	.81	3	.01	12	181	13	2.4	4	.03
15	.83	3	.01	111	2790	2810	2.3	4	.02
16	.98	3	.01	16	225	15	2.1	4	.02
17	.87	3	.01	308	5780	25800	2.0	4	.02
18	1.0	5	.01	382	6720	15500	2.0	4	.02
19	.94	6	.02	40	90	9.7	2.0	4	.02
20	.68	3	.90	19	20	1.0	2.2	4	.02
21	.82	3	.50	12	5	.50	2.2	4	.02
22	.73	3	.30	12	5	.16	2.0	4	.02
23	48	807	489	11	4	.90	2.0	4	.02
24	11	206	25	9.0	4	.50	2.0	4	.02
25	35	641	442	6.3	4	.80	1.8	3	.90
26	4.4	50	.59	5.6	4	.50	1.8	3	.50
27	1.5	18	.07	5.1	4	.20	1.7	3	.01
28	1.0	7	.02	4.9	4	.05	1.7	2	.80
29	.97	4	.01	4.6	4	.05	1.7	2	.50
30	.89	4	.01	4.3	4	.05	1.6	2	.20
31	---	---	---	4.1	4	.04	---	---	---
TOTAL	127.34	---	962.96	976.72	---	44156.19	83.0	---	3.66

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR-Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	1.8	2	.01	1.6	12	.05	3.0	20	.16
2	1.7	2	.01	1.7	12	.06	9.8	217	24
3	1.8	2	.01	1.7	11	.05	3.8	25	.26
4	1.9	2	.01	1.5	10	.04	2.6	20	.14
5	1.6	2	.01	1.5	10	.04	2.2	20	.12
6	1.4	2	.50	1.6	10	.04	2.1	20	.11
7	1.4	2	.70	1.6	10	.04	1.9	20	.10
8	1.4	3	.01	1.5	10	.04	8.0	109	9.0
9	1.3	3	.50	1.5	10	.04	4.5	40	.49
10	1.2	3	.90	1.5	10	.04	2.7	20	.15
11	1.4	4	.20	1.5	10	.04	2.8	20	.15
12	1.3	5	.02	1.6	12	.06	97	628	714
13	1.3	5	.30	3.0	29	.42	69	1030	337
14	1.2	6	.02	1.9	17	.09	25	280	19
15	7.4	119	6.8	1.7	16	.07	14	180	6.8
16	5.9	75	1.8	1.5	15	.06	7.5	70	1.4
17	7.5	111	4.7	1.4	15	.06	5.8	50	.78
18	2.4	30	.19	1.5	14	.06	4.6	45	.56
19	2.3	29	.70	1.4	14	.05	4.1	40	.44
20	12	175	12	1.4	13	.05	3.6	35	.34
21	4.0	6	.50	1.5	13	.05	3.4	30	.28
22	2.4	6	.04	1.4	13	.05	3.2	30	.26
23	2.3	6	.04	1.4	12	.05	3.4	30	.28
24	3.0	6	.05	1.3	12	.04	16	230	52
25	2.2	6	.04	1.4	11	.04	87	2980	4940
26	2.7	6	.50	1.5	11	.04	14	140	5.3
27	2.0	6	.80	16	299	32	7.7	80	1.7
28	2.9	17	.19	4.3	40	.46	9.9	138	6.8
29	2.3	15	.09	2.6	20	.14	6.3	70	1.2
30	1.9	14	.07	2.1	20	.11	5.4	50	.73
31	1.7	13	.06	2.4	30	.19	---	---	---
TOTAL	85.6	---	31.77	68.5	---	34.57	430.3	---	6123.55
YEAR	3542.58		68604.21						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR-Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	6.3	63	1.2	15	170	6.9	4.8	1	.01
2	15	200	23	10	110	3.0	4.6	1	.01
3	11	118	4.6	8.6	95	2.2	4.6	1	.01
4	23	276	29	8.0	88	1.9	4.4	1	.01
5	31	423	46	10	110	3.0	7.1	38	1.6
6	434	7300	15200	8.0	88	1.9	5.5	3	.04
7	237	4120	8320	7.2	65	1.3	4.8	1	.01
8	70	774	287	6.7	65	1.2	4.4	1	.01
9	20	150	8.1	6.5	65	1.1	4.4	1	.01
10	15	120	4.9	6.2	60	1.0	4.9	1	.01
11	11	110	3.3	6.1	60	.99	5.0	1	.01
12	10	100	2.7	17	284	32	5.4	1	.01
13	9.0	100	2.4	9.3	100	2.5	4.4	1	.01
14	7.9	90	1.9	8.3	80	1.8	4.2	1	.01
15	7.1	80	1.5	32	403	82	4.2	1	.01
16	6.9	78	1.5	15	200	8.1	4.0	1	.01
17	6.9	75	1.4	14	184	14	3.9	1	.01
18	49	638	84	48	681	304	4.0	1	.01
19	110	1540	457	15	77	3.8	4.0	1	.01
20	10	112	3.0	13	30	1.1	4.3	1	.01
21	8.0	88	1.9	15	146	13	4.0	1	.01
22	7.0	76	1.4	9.1	40	.98	3.8	1	.01
23	70	940	178	8.0	30	.65	3.8	1	.01
24	80	1090	235	7.0	30	.57	3.9	1	.01
25	40	510	55	6.4	25	.43	3.9	1	.01
26	45	580	70	6.0	25	.41	3.7	1	.01
27	25	300	20	5.6	20	.30	3.6	1	.01
28	19	220	11	5.4	20	.29	3.7	1	.01
29	34	430	39	5.0	18	.24	3.5	1	.01
30	20	230	12	5.4	15	.22	3.4	1	.01
31	45	580	70	---	---	---	3.4	1	.01
TOTAL	1483.1	---	25175.8	336.8	---	490.88	133.6	---	1.93

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR-Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	3.8	1	.01	4.0	3	.03	2.1	1	.01
2	3.8	1	.01	3.1	1	.50	2.1	1	.01
3	3.5	1	.01	3.3	1	.01	2.0	1	.01
4	3.6	1	.01	5.6	35	1.8	1.8	1	.00
5	3.3	1	.01	4.5	3	.04	1.8	1	.00
6	3.1	1	.01	3.5	1	.01	1.8	1	.00
7	3.1	1	.01	3.2	1	.01	1.7	1	.00
8	3.3	1	.01	2.9	1	.01	1.7	1	.00
9	13	144	15	2.8	1	.01	1.7	1	.00
10	5.0	1	.50	2.7	1	.01	1.7	1	.00
11	3.7	1	.01	2.8	1	.01	1.8	1	.00
12	3.3	1	.01	2.7	1	.01	1.7	1	.00
13	3.1	1	.01	2.6	1	.01	1.9	1	.01
14	2.9	1	.01	2.5	1	.01	2.1	4	.08
15	2.9	1	.01	2.4	1	.01	3.4	26	.42
16	2.8	1	.01	2.4	1	.01	1.8	6	.03
17	4.7	24	.79	2.5	1	.01	1.6	3	.01
18	3.2	1	.50	2.7	1	.01	1.5	3	.01
19	2.8	1	.01	2.7	1	.01	1.5	3	.01
20	2.6	1	.01	2.4	1	.01	1.5	2	.70
21	2.8	1	.01	2.4	1	.01	1.4	2	.20
22	2.6	1	.01	2.2	1	.01	1.4	1	.50
23	2.5	1	.01	2.2	1	.01	1.4	1	.20
24	2.7	1	.01	2.2	1	.01	1.4	1	.00
25	2.4	1	.01	2.2	1	.01	1.6	1	.00
26	2.3	1	.01	2.2	1	.01	1.9	1	.01
27	2.2	1	.01	2.1	1	.01	1.6	1	.00
28	2.2	1	.01	2.2	1	.01	1.4	1	.00
29	6.3	66	4.8	---	---	---	4.6	47	1.4
30	3.4	20	.18	---	---	---	2.3	7	.04
31	9.2	65	5.5	---	---	---	2.1	6	.03
TOTAL	116.1	---	27.51	79.0	---	2.61	58.3	---	3.68
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	2.3	5	.50	5.9	81	8.6	3.7	20	.20
2	1.8	5	.02	2.6	20	.14	3.8	20	.21
3	2.0	5	.03	2.1	17	.10	3.0	18	.15
4	5.3	77	4.5	1.9	14	.07	2.5	18	.12
5	5.3	51	1.1	1.8	10	.05	2.2	16	.10
6	3.6	30	.29	2.2	20	.12	2.1	16	.09
7	2.3	28	.17	3.6	25	.24	2.1	16	.09
8	3.2	30	.26	121	2850	7370	2.3	15	.09
9	2.9	30	.23	20	238	18	3.0	25	.20
10	2.0	4	.02	43	585	166	12	199	46
11	1.8	1	.50	47	661	131	2.5	25	.17
12	1.7	1	.30	13	15	.53	2.2	20	.12
13	1.6	1	.00	161	3740	12200	4.3	50	.58
14	1.5	1	.00	78	1710	6320	4.7	40	.51
15	1.6	1	.00	7.3	70	1.4	3.2	25	.22
16	1.7	1	.00	4.7	50	.63	3.0	6	.05
17	1.6	1	.00	4.0	50	.54	3.0	3	.02
18	1.4	1	.00	17	240	26	2.4	3	.02
19	1.4	1	.00	6.8	90	1.7	2.7	3	.02
20	1.6	1	.80	4.6	50	.62	2.2	3	.02
21	1.6	2	.01	4.0	35	.38	2.1	3	.02
22	1.4	2	.01	3.7	30	.30	2.0	3	.02
23	1.3	1	.90	2.8	28	.21	1.9	3	.02
24	1.3	1	.80	2.5	25	.17	1.9	3	.02
25	1.3	1	.80	2.2	20	.12	1.8	3	.01
26	1.3	1	.60	2.2	20	.12	1.8	3	.01
27	1.6	1	.50	2.1	20	.11	1.8	3	.01
28	2.4	10	.06	2.1	18	.10	1.8	3	.01
29	35	720	374	2.6	19	.13	1.8	3	.01
30	5.1	50	.69	2.1	19	.11	1.8	3	.01
31	---	---	---	26	436	240	---	---	---
TOTAL	98.9	---	387.09	599.8	---	2647.49	85.6	---	49.12

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051150 QUEBRADA BLANCA AT EL JAGUAL, PR-Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	1.8	3	.01	1.9	1	.70	3.1	30	.25
2	1.8	3	.01	1.9	1	.50	2.3	3	.02
3	1.9	3	.02	1.9	1	.50	1.8	2	.50
4	1.8	3	.01	1.9	1	.01	1.7	2	.01
5	1.8	3	.01	2.0	1	.50	1.6	1	.50
6	3.5	27	.70	2.0	1	.50	1.6	1	.00
7	2.2	5	.03	2.7	3	.04	1.5	0	.50
8	1.9	3	.02	2.5	4	.03	1.4	0	.50
9	1.8	3	.01	2.1	2	.20	1.4	0	.50
10	1.8	3	.01	3.6	17	.91	1.4	0	.80
11	2.5	3	.02	4.4	48	.83	1.3	1	.00
12	2.4	3	.02	2.5	25	.17	1.3	1	.00
13	1.9	3	.02	4.3	40	.46	1.5	3	.01
14	2.4	10	.06	3.5	30	.28	1.4	3	.01
15	2.1	4	.02	2.4	5	.03	1.3	2	.60
16	1.9	3	.50	2.1	3	.02	1.4	1	.00
17	1.8	3	.50	1.9	2	.80	1.3	1	.00
18	1.8	3	.20	1.8	2	.50	1.4	1	.00
19	1.9	3	.02	1.8	2	.50	1.3	1	.00
20	2.0	3	.02	1.6	2	.01	1.3	1	.00
21	2.2	3	.02	1.6	2	.01	1.4	1	.00
22	1.9	3	.02	1.8	2	.01	1.5	1	.00
23	1.8	3	.01	2.1	2	.01	1.7	1	.00
24	1.8	3	.01	1.9	2	.01	12	130	4.2
25	1.8	2	.80	1.8	2	.01	8.0	80	1.7
26	1.8	2	.50	1.8	2	.01	3.5	30	.28
27	1.8	2	.50	1.8	2	.01	2.5	20	.14
28	1.9	2	.20	5.9	86	3.3	1.8	1	.50
29	1.8	2	.20	77	1520	1410	1.7	1	.50
30	2.5	2	.01	4.1	45	.50	1.8	1	.50
31	2.2	1	.90	2.5	25	.17	---	---	---
TOTAL	62.5	---	5.38	151.1	---	1421.53	67.2	---	12.02
YEAR	3272.0		54065.04						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'24", long 65°58'38", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left downstream side of bridge on Highway 181, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southwest of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.74 mi² (9.69 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 330 ft (100 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 9,320 ft³/s (264 m³/s), May 17, 1985, gage height, 17.10 ft (5.212 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 0.69 ft³/s (0.020 m³/s), Apr. 9-13, 15, 16, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	0430	4,430	125	12.87	3.923	Aug. 24	1415	4,560	129	12.95	3.947
Dec. 7	1630	*4,740	134	*13.06	3.981						

Minimum discharge, 0.87 ft³/s (0.025 m³/s), May 5.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e1.2	e1.9	20	24	3.6	e4.0	2.0	e1.1	1.3	33	2.3	e6.0
2	e1.2	e1.7	26	15	3.5	e5.4	1.8	e1.2	1.3	105	2.1	e5.4
3	e1.4	e1.6	21	8.1	5.6	e3.4	1.8	e1.1	1.3	16	2.6	e5.4
4	e1.3	e1.7	19	7.6	2.8	e3.0	1.8	e1.0	1.3	11	2.9	e5.2
5	e1.2	e2.1	18	15	2.8	e2.8	1.6	e1.1	1.2	10	2.0	e5.6
6	1.1	e3.0	22	13	2.6	e2.6	2.4	2.9	1.2	11	1.9	e6.0
7	1.1	e2.4	332	9.1	2.4	e2.5	e1.8	1.3	1.2	e68	2.8	e6.4
8	1.1	e2.0	e91	8.6	2.5	e2.3	e1.7	1.0	1.1	e19	2.4	e7.0
9	1.1	e1.6	e20	11	2.4	e2.2	e1.7	1.0	1.6	e13	2.0	e10
10	1.1	e1.5	9.9	9.6	2.6	e2.2	e1.6	12	2.2	e9.0	34	e7.0
11	1.1	e1.4	6.9	10	2.4	e2.3	e1.6	2.3	1.4	e6.4	17	101
12	1.1	e2.0	5.6	8.6	4.1	e2.4	e1.7	1.4	1.4	4.2	6.2	75
13	1.1	e1.5	4.8	7.7	13	e2.7	e1.7	1.3	1.8	3.3	4.3	21
14	1.4	e1.4	4.4	7.1	e2.7	e2.2	e1.6	1.3	1.7	4.5	3.5	9.8
15	1.6	e1.3	4.4	5.5	e2.5	e2.0	e5.7	1.4	11	2.7	3.3	7.6
16	3.1	e4.0	4.1	4.4	e2.3	1.9	e2.3	1.1	6.3	2.3	5.0	6.2
17	25	e2.6	3.8	3.8	e2.2	1.8	e13	1.1	2.6	2.2	8.4	5.1
18	102	e2.1	3.6	3.8	e2.2	1.7	e2.8	1.1	1.8	4.5	20	4.5
19	20	1.7	4.5	3.5	e2.1	1.8	e2.2	1.2	1.6	3.7	5.2	19
20	4.9	1.7	8.4	3.1	e2.1	2.2	e1.9	2.6	4.4	2.6	4.0	6.3
21	3.6	1.6	6.3	3.0	e2.0	1.9	e1.7	2.3	3.9	2.2	3.4	4.8
22	e3.2	1.6	15	2.9	e1.9	1.8	e1.6	1.5	3.1	10	6.2	4.4
23	e2.9	3.8	6.4	2.9	e2.0	1.7	e1.5	1.4	2.6	3.4	5.3	e4.3
24	e2.7	247	5.8	2.8	e2.1	1.8	e1.4	1.3	2.6	2.7	155	e4.0
25	e2.8	24	5.0	2.6	e2.1	2.0	e1.3	1.2	31	2.5	e87	e3.8
26	e2.9	96	4.9	2.6	e16	1.9	e1.4	1.2	25	5.2	e17	e3.6
27	3.2	472	4.1	2.8	e14	2.9	e1.3	1.2	18	3.1	9.9	e3.5
28	15	58	4.1	2.7	e3.3	2.0	e1.2	1.2	12	3.7	10	e3.3
29	4.0	35	3.9	2.8	e2.8	1.9	e1.1	1.4	11	4.9	8.3	e3.1
30	e2.4	25	3.8	2.9	---	2.3	e1.1	2.3	10	3.7	e7.2	e2.9
31	e2.0	---	17	2.9	---	2.2	---	1.6	---	2.6	e6.4	---
TOTAL	217.8	1003.2	705.7	209.4	112.6	73.8	66.3	55.1	166.9	375.4	447.6	357.2
MEAN	7.03	33.4	22.8	6.75	3.88	2.38	2.21	1.78	5.56	12.1	14.4	11.9
MAX	102	472	332	24	16	5.4	13	12	31	105	155	101
MIN	1.1	1.3	3.6	2.6	1.9	1.7	1.1	1.0	1.1	2.2	1.9	2.9
AC-FT	432	1990	1400	415	223	146	132	109	331	745	888	709
CFSM	1.88	8.94	6.09	1.81	1.04	.64	.59	.48	1.49	3.24	3.86	3.18
IN.	2.17	9.98	7.02	2.08	1.12	.73	.66	.55	1.66	3.73	4.45	3.55

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 3122.99 MEAN 8.56 MAX 472 MIN .95 AC-FT 6190 CFSM 2.29 IN. 31.06
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 3791.0 MEAN 10.4 MAX 472 MIN 1.0 AC-FT 7520 CFSM 2.77 IN. 37.71

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS FEBRUARY 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 05	1412	1.15	371	28.0	MAR, 03	1323	3.37	287	24.0
NOV, 18	1151	2.07	350	26.0	APR, 06	1046	1.81	426	26.5
DEC, 09	1350	20	213	25.5	MAY, 05	1239	1.01	417	30.5
JAN, 05	1258	34.9	242	23.5	JUN, 02	1322	1.26	388	28.0
FEB, 02	1228	3.85	366	23.0	JUL, 11	1204	5.40	265	27.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1984 to September 1986.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 2,570 mg/L May 17, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 15,500 tons (14,060 tonnes) May 17, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 tons (0.01) tonne several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1984-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1984	2,350 (Jun. 10)	1 (several days)	15,400 (Jun. 10)	0.00 (several days)
1985	2,570 (May 17)	1 (several days)	14,060 (May 17)	0.01 (several days)
1986	2,430 (Oct. 06)	0 (several days)	12,300 (May 14)	0.00 (several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	2.0	---	---	1.7	3	.60	1.6	4	.02
2	1.8	---	---	1.5	3	.20	1.6	4	.02
3	1.7	---	---	1.5	3	.01	1.6	3	.90
4	1.6	---	---	1.9	3	.02	1.5	3	.60
5	1.5	---	---	1.6	3	.01	1.5	3	.20
6	1.5	---	---	1.5	3	.01	1.5	3	.20
7	1.5	---	---	1.5	3	.01	1.5	3	.20
8	1.5	---	---	1.5	3	.01	1.4	3	.20
9	1.6	---	---	1.9	3	.20	1.4	3	.20
10	1.8	---	---	4.2	4	.05	1.4	3	.20
11	1.6	---	---	3.7	4	.50	1.3	3	.01
12	3.2	---	---	8.8	61	15	1.3	3	.01
13	14	89	16	33	152	32	1.3	3	.01
14	12	30	.97	11	75	2.2	1.4	2	.50
15	3.8	14	.14	106	1040	2250	1.3	2	.50
16	2.6	4	.02	88	593	1020	1.2	2	.50
17	2.0	4	.02	6.6	25	.45	1.2	2	.50
18	1.7	3	.01	3.3	10	.09	1.2	2	.50
19	1.7	2	.01	2.3	6	.04	1.2	2	.20
20	14	72	7.8	1.9	5	.03	1.1	2	.01
21	3.5	10	.09	1.7	4	.50	1.1	2	.01
22	1.8	4	.01	1.6	4	.02	1.1	2	.01
23	1.7	3	.80	1.6	4	.02	1.2	2	.01
24	1.8	3	.80	1.6	4	.02	1.2	2	.01
25	1.8	3	.80	1.6	4	.02	1.1	2	.01
26	1.7	3	.80	1.6	4	.02	1.0	2	.01
27	1.7	3	.80	1.7	4	.02	1.0	2	.01
28	1.9	3	.70	1.7	4	.02	.97	2	.01
29	1.7	3	.70	1.6	4	.02	.96	2	.01
30	1.6	3	.60	---	---	---	.91	1	.80
31	1.6	3	.60	---	---	---	.88	---	---
TOTAL	93.9	---	31.67	298.1	---	3322.09	38.92	---	6.37

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
.1	.86	1	.50	.96	1	.00	1.8	3	.50
2	.86	1	.40	.93	1	.00	1.5	2	.60
3	.86	1	.40	.97	1	.00	1.2	2	.20
4	.81	1	.60	1.0	1	.00	1.3	2	.01
5	.80	1	.60	.93	1	.00	1.2	2	.01
6	.82	1	.70	.93	1	.00	10	3	.02
7	.84	1	.50	.97	1	.00	26	189	29
8	.85	1	.50	1.0	1	.00	9.8	60	1.6
9	.74	1	.30	.97	1	.00	5.3	20	.29
10	.71	1	.30	1.1	1	.00	295	2350	15400
11	.72	1	.20	1.2	1	.00	15	70	2.8
12	.71	1	.20	1.1	1	.00	7.0	30	.57
13	.72	1	.00	1.8	1	.00	20	112	14
14	.74	1	.00	2.1	1	.01	9.9	25	.67
15	.74	1	.00	1.4	1	.00	5.9	15	.24
16	.73	1	.00	1.3	1	.00	5.9	25	.40
17	.77	1	.00	1.2	1	.00	5.3	20	.29
18	.80	1	.00	1.1	1	.10	3.8	10	.10
19	.79	1	.00	1.1	1	.10	3.2	7	.50
20	.80	1	.00	1.1	1	.20	2.6	6	.04
21	.86	1	.00	1.1	1	.20	2.3	5	.50
22	.93	1	.00	1.0	1	.10	2.1	4	.80
23	.93	1	.00	1.1	1	.00	1.8	4	.50
24	.93	1	.00	1.1	1	.00	1.7	4	.02
25	.90	1	.00	2.0	1	.20	1.6	3	.50
26	.93	1	.00	14	55	14	1.8	3	.01
27	1.4	1	.00	2.1	4	.02	1.5	2	.50
28	1.7	1	.00	2.2	4	.02	1.4	2	.01
29	1.1	1	.00	1.5	4	.02	2.0	1	.80
30	1.0	0	.00	18	70	9.6	1.6	1	.50
31	---	---	---	3.1	6	.50	---	---	---
TOTAL	26.35	---	5.20	70.36	---	25.07	449.5	---	15455.98
		JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER	
1	1.9	1	.30	4.1	15	1.7	2.2	5	.03
2	2.3	1	.01	6.2	---	---	1.8	5	.02
3	1.4	1	.00	1.4	3	.01	1.7	5	.02
4	30	255	183	6.6	81	10	1.9	5	.03
5	64	345	102	2.3	5	.03	16	118	31
6	6.2	25	.42	1.3	2	.50	5.4	25	.36
7	2.8	7	.05	1.1	2	.01	2.7	7	.05
8	2.0	4	.50	.99	2	.01	2.1	5	.03
9	1.7	4	.02	.95	1	.80	2.2	7	.04
10	1.8	3	.60	.86	1	.50	2.6	8	.06
11	1.5	3	.01	.83	1	.30	2.3	7	.04
12	1.3	2	.50	.83	1	.20	4.7	26	.74
13	1.1	2	.01	.82	1	.20	19	126	28
14	1.5	2	.01	.82	1	.20	86	503	419
15	1.5	2	.01	.84	1	.20	10	60	1.6
16	1.2	2	.01	1.0	1	.20	11	60	1.8
17	1.1	2	.01	.92	1	.20	24	151	19
18	.97	2	.01	.89	1	.20	54	391	178
19	1.0	2	.01	.89	1	.10	41	198	31
20	1.1	2	.01	1.1	1	.10	95	657	520
21	1.6	2	.01	1.0	1	.10	38	150	15
22	1.3	2	.01	.87	1	.10	13	55	1.9
23	1.2	2	.10	.87	1	.10	7.3	25	.49
24	1.0	2	.50	.82	1	.10	5.2	20	.28
25	.98	3	.01	.84	1	.10	4.2	18	.20
26	1.1	3	.01	2.8	12	.09	3.7	15	.15
27	.98	4	.01	3.8	5	.05	3.4	12	.11
28	.99	3	.80	2.4	4	.03	3.7	12	.12
29	1.7	5	.02	1.7	3	.01	3.1	10	.08
30	2.3	8	.05	16	91	29	5.0	10	.14
31	1.3	3	.01	4.1	15	.17	---	---	---
TOTAL	140.82	---	289.02	69.94	---	45.31	472.2	---	1249.29
YEAR	1660.09		20430.00						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	3.5	10	.09	6.2	24	.40	3.0	6	.05
2	3.0	7	.50	12	53	1.7	28	139	.39
3	4.3	17	.37	60	360	58	7.0	27	.51
4	3.9	12	.13	20	100	5.4	4.3	12	.14
5	3.1	9	.08	246	981	825	3.7	10	.10
6	3.5	9	.09	158	1020	657	3.4	10	.09
7	2.7	7	.05	102	760	493	3.2	10	.09
8	2.7	7	.05	46	209	46	14	149	.42
9	28	201	68	26	180	13	4.4	12	.14
10	7.9	25	.53	18	90	4.4	3.5	10	.09
11	4.3	13	.15	6.1	35	.58	2.	223	.206
12	3.4	10	.09	4.1	35	.39	4.2	17	.19
13	22	200	75	3.1	35	.29	3.3	10	.09
14	98	709	678	7.3	64	3.7	3.3	10	.09
15	12	60	1.9	12	64	4.2	3.1	8	.07
16	7.3	30	.59	4.1	13	.14	3.3	8	.07
17	7.0	40	.76	3.4	7	.50	2.9	7	.05
18	4.5	14	.17	3.2	4	.03	2.5	6	.50
19	3.3	9	.10	2.9	3	.02	2.7	7	.05
20	3.2	7	.06	2.6	2	.01	2.7	6	.50
21	3.1	9	.08	2.5	2	.01	2.5	6	.04
22	3.2	10	.09	2.7	2	.01	2.4	6	.04
23	2.4	6	.50	4.0	15	.16	2.4	5	.80
24	2.1	6	.03	2.8	5	.04	3.0	6	.05
25	7.2	57	4.5	2.9	5	.04	4.7	8	.10
26	2.5	6	.04	5.6	20	.30	4.2	8	.09
27	2.1	3	.50	3.2	8	.07	4.0	8	.09
28	2.0	2	.01	3.0	8	.06	3.7	7	.07
29	1.9	1	.50	3.0	8	.06	2.8	6	.50
30	14	118	32	3.0	8	.06	3.5	6	.06
31	2.2	5	.60	---	---	---	3.0	5	.90
TOTAL	270.3	---	865.56	775.7	---	2114.57	160.7	---	292.56

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

JANUARY		FEBRUARY		MARCH					
1	6.7	5	.09	1.6	2	.01	1.8	3	.60
2	5.4	4	.20	1.5	2	.01	1.5	3	.50
3	3.3	4	.04	1.5	2	.01	1.4	3	.01
4	3.6	4	.04	1.4	2	.01	1.4	2	.50
5	3.4	4	.04	1.4	2	.01	1.8	3	.01
6	3.3	4	.04	1.4	2	.01	2.2	3	.90
7	2.7	4	.03	1.4	2	.01	3.9	5	.05
8	2.5	3	.80	1.4	2	.01	2.4	4	.03
9	2.3	3	.80	1.3	2	.01	1.8	4	.02
10	2.4	3	.20	1.2	2	.01	1.6	4	.02
11	2.2	2	.20	1.3	2	.01	1.5	3	.80
12	2.1	2	.01	1.3	2	.01	1.6	3	.01
13	2.0	2	.01	1.2	2	.01	1.6	3	.01
14	2.0	2	.01	1.4	2	.01	1.5	2	.80
15	2.1	2	.01	1.4	2	.01	1.5	2	.60
16	2.0	2	.01	1.4	2	.01	1.5	3	.01
17	2.0	2	.01	1.4	2	.01	1.5	3	.20
18	2.0	2	.01	1.3	2	.01	2.7	3	.90
19	2.0	2	.01	1.5	2	.01	1.7	3	.50
20	1.8	2	.01	1.8	2	.10	1.5	3	.01
21	1.7	2	.01	1.6	2	.10	1.5	2	.50
22	1.7	2	.01	1.5	2	.20	1.4	2	.01
23	1.7	2	.01	1.5	2	.20	1.4	2	.01
24	1.7	2	.01	1.6	2	.01	1.4	2	.01
25	1.7	2	.01	1.7	2	.01	1.4	2	.01
26	1.8	2	.01	1.7	2	.20	1.4	2	.01
27	1.7	2	.01	2.8	3	.02	1.5	2	.10
28	1.7	2	.01	2.7	4	.03	1.5	2	.20
29	1.6	2	.01	---	---	---	83	558	454
30	1.6	2	.01	---	---	---	13	65	12
31	1.5	2	.01	---	---	---	12	60	1.9
TOTAL	74.2	---	2.68	43.2	---	1.06	155.9	---	475.23
APRIL		MAY		JUNE					
1	3.1	8	.07	1.4	2	.20	2.7	4	.03
2	2.1	2	.50	1.3	2	.20	2.7	4	.03
3	1.7	2	.01	1.3	2	.01	2.7	4	.03
4	1.5	2	.01	1.2	2	.01	2.7	3	.80
5	1.4	2	.01	1.3	2	.01	2.6	3	.50
6	1.4	2	.01	1.2	2	.01	2.6	3	.02
7	1.8	2	.01	1.1	2	.01	2.6	2	.80
8	1.4	2	.01	1.1	2	.01	2.7	2	.30
9	1.2	2	.01	1.3	2	.01	2.6	2	.20
10	1.1	2	.01	1.2	3	.01	2.6	2	.01
11	1.2	2	.01	1.4	4	.10	2.5	2	.01
12	1.2	2	.01	2.1	5	.80	2.4	2	.01
13	1.3	2	.01	1.5	5	.02	2.1	1	.90
14	1.2	2	.01	15	139	17	2.0	1	.90
15	1.3	2	.01	172	1050	1540	2.0	1	.80
16	1.9	2	.01	62	214	90	2.0	1	.50
17	1.4	2	.01	400	2570	15500	1.9	1	.50
18	1.4	2	.01	356	2410	5670	1.9	1	.50
19	1.8	2	.01	29	170	13	1.8	1	.00
20	1.2	2	.01	9.6	35	.91	1.9	1	.01
21	1.4	2	.01	7.9	30	.64	1.9	1	.50
22	1.2	2	.01	6.3	25	.43	1.7	2	.01
23	78	468	413	4.9	17	.22	1.7	2	.01
24	33	279	74	4.5	14	.17	1.6	4	.02
25	36	229	96	4.4	12	.14	1.4	3	.60
26	9.1	25	.61	4.1	10	.11	1.6	3	.20
27	3.3	8	.07	3.9	7	.07	1.4	3	.01
28	2.1	4	.02	3.3	5	.04	1.4	3	.01
29	1.7	3	.80	3.1	4	.60	1.4	2	.50
30	1.6	3	.01	2.9	4	.20	1.4	2	.01
31	---	---	---	2.7	4	.03	---	---	---
TOTAL	198.0	---	585.28	1109.0	---	22834.96	62.4	---	8.72

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

		JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	1.3	2	.01	1.4	1	.30	2.7	2	.01	
2	1.2	2	.01	1.9	1	.30	6.2	24	1.4	
3	1.4	2	.10	1.4	1	.30	4.0	5	.05	
4	1.4	2	.10	1.4	1	.20	2.5	5	.03	
5	1.2	2	.10	1.3	1	.00	2.2	5	.03	
6	1.1	2	.10	1.3	1	.00	2.6	5	.04	
7	.99	2	.20	1.3	1	.00	2.1	5	.03	
8	1.0	2	.20	1.3	1	.00	8.1	24	1.4	
9	.99	2	.50	1.3	1	.00	6.3	25	.43	
10	.93	2	.50	1.2	1	.00	3.1	10	.08	
11	1.1	2	.80	1.1	1	.00	2.8	9	.07	
12	1.1	3	.01	1.2	1	.50	82	969	2150	
13	.93	3	.01	2.8	6	.05	91	643	271	
14	.89	3	.50	1.6	2	.01	23	143	12	
15	6.5	61	4.1	1.5	1	.70	12	48	1.6	
16	9.6	80	9.6	1.3	1	.60	7.2	30	.58	
17	7.1	67	5.0	1.3	1	.60	5.5	20	.30	
18	2.0	7	.04	1.3	1	.30	4.7	18	.23	
19	1.4	4	.02	1.3	1	.20	4.2	15	.17	
20	6.8	30	.55	1.2	1	.20	3.9	12	.13	
21	2.4	4	.03	1.2	1	.20	3.7	12	.12	
22	1.6	1	.50	1.2	1	.10	3.5	11	.10	
23	1.5	1	.50	1.1	1	.00	3.8	11	.11	
24	2.2	4	.50	1.1	1	.00	11	102	30	
25	1.6	4	.50	1.2	1	.00	87	1230	1450	
26	2.3	6	.04	1.4	1	.20	10	50	1.4	
27	1.6	3	.60	13	85	7.7	5.9	30	.48	
28	2.8	8	.06	5.3	12	.17	9.8	72	4.9	
29	2.0	2	.50	2.6	2	.01	6.1	28	.46	
30	1.7	1	.70	2.0	2	.01	4.8	25	.32	
31	1.4	1	.60	2.0	2	.01	---	---	---	
TOTAL	70.03	---	26.98	60.5	---	12.66	421.7	---	3927.47	
YEAR	3401.63		31147.73							

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	5.1	---	---	15	6	.24	2.9	2	.02
2	7.3	---	---	9.6	4	.50	2.8	2	.02
3	9.2	---	---	7.6	3	.06	3.4	1	.70
4	16	---	---	6.5	2	.50	4.2	1	.80
5	28	193	28	8.4	3	.07	6.8	2	.04
6	353	2430	5280	6.5	2	.50	5.8	2	.03
7	143	1210	2750	5.3	2	.03	4.9	2	.20
8	26	181	29	4.8	1	.70	4.2	2	.50
9	20	50	2.7	4.4	1	.50	4.1	4	.04
10	13	20	.70	4.3	1	.50	4.1	4	.04
11	10	8	.22	4.2	1	.40	4.4	4	.20
12	8.0	2	.04	16	111	17	4.2	4	.20
13	6.6	1	.20	7.9	45	.96	3.7	4	.50
14	5.8	1	.02	12	77	6.3	3.5	5	.05
15	5.4	1	.01	72	463	278	3.6	4	.50
16	5.0	0	.90	22	150	8.9	3.5	4	.50
17	5.2	0	.90	14	75	3.5	3.3	4	.20
18	10	26	.03	56	256	79	3.4	4	.04
19	5.6	3	.05	13	55	1.9	3.4	3	.50
20	5.2	1	.30	9.6	20	.52	3.7	3	.20
21	5.0	1	.01	22	111	27	3.2	3	.03
22	4.9	0	.80	7.3	30	.59	3.0	3	.02
23	86	922	1250	5.6	20	.30	3.2	3	.03
24	94	705	312	4.6	15	.19	3.5	3	.03
25	40	200	22	4.1	12	.13	3.3	3	.10
26	45	381	223	3.8	10	.10	3.1	3	.03
27	30	190	15	3.5	7	.07	2.8	3	.02
28	19	100	5.1	3.3	4	.50	2.8	3	.02
29	34	286	42	3.1	3	.50	2.6	3	.02
30	21	90	5.1	3.2	2	.50	2.5	3	.02
31	57	345	275	---	---	---	2.5	3	.02
TOTAL	1123.3	---	10243.08	359.6	---	429.96	112.4	---	5.62

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

	JANUARY				FEBRUARY				MARCH			
1	3.0	3	.02	3.4	10	.09	1.3	1	.00			
2	3.3	3	.03	2.4	4	.50	1.3	1	.00			
3	2.7	3	.50	2.7	3	.02	1.1	1	.00			
4	3.0	3	.60	2.4	3	.02	1.2	1	.00			
5	2.6	4	.03	2.4	3	.02	1.4	1	.00			
6	2.5	4	.50	2.0	3	.02	1.3	1	.00			
7	2.4	5	.03	2.0	2	.90	1.3	1	.00			
8	2.6	5	.10	1.9	2	.80	1.2	1	.00			
9	10	65	5.7	1.8	2	.60	1.2	1	.00			
10	5.5	15	.22	1.8	2	.60	1.2	1	.00			
11	3.6	9	.09	1.9	2	.40	1.3	1	.00			
12	2.9	6	.05	1.9	2	.30	1.2	1	.00			
13	2.8	5	.04	1.7	2	.30	1.4	1	.00			
14	2.6	5	.04	1.6	2	.20	1.5	1	.00			
15	2.5	5	.03	1.6	2	.10	5.8	---	---			
16	2.4	5	.03	1.6	2	.01	1.8	3	.50			
17	7.2	39	2.5	1.7	2	.01	1.5	1	.00			
18	3.3	9	.08	1.8	1	.90	1.4	1	.00			
19	2.6	4	.50	1.7	1	.80	1.4	1	.00			
20	2.5	2	.50	1.5	1	.60	1.3	1	.00			
21	2.6	2	.01	1.5	1	.50	1.3	1	.00			
22	2.4	2	.01	1.4	1	.20	1.3	1	.00			
23	2.0	2	.01	1.4	1	.10	1.3	1	.00			
24	2.1	2	.01	1.4	1	.00	1.3	1	.00			
25	2.0	2	.01	1.4	1	.00	1.6	1	.00			
26	1.9	2	.01	1.4	1	.00	2.0	1	.01			
27	1.8	2	.01	1.3	1	.00	1.5	1	.00			
28	1.8	2	.01	1.4	1	.00	1.3	1	.00			
29	2.9	10	.08	---	---	---	5.2	30	.21			
30	2.3	5	.03	---	---	---	1.8	2	.50			
31	11	59	7.6	---	---	---	1.7	1	.00			
TOTAL	102.8	---	19.38	51.0	---	7.99	51.4	---	1.22			
	APRIL				MAY				JUNE			
1	1.8	1	.00	2.9	6	.05	6.2	25	.42			
2	1.4	1	.00	1.9	3	.02	5.8	20	.31			
3	2.7	7	.12	1.7	1	.50	5.2	12	.17			
4	2.6	7	.05	1.6	1	.00	3.7	12	.12			
5	6.2	19	.83	1.5	1	.00	3.2	11	.10			
6	3.3	10	.09	2.6	8	.06	2.8	10	.08			
7	1.7	4	.02	6.3	23	.76	2.8	9	.07			
8	4.4	35	2.9	74	914	2090	2.7	8	.06			
9	2.4	6	.04	15	65	2.6	13	121	33			
10	1.5	3	.50	27	108	17	34	233	151			
11	1.4	3	.01	32	151	24	4.1	12	.13			
12	1.3	3	.01	12	60	1.9	3.2	6	.05			
13	1.5	3	.01	146	1440	6730	9.2	30	.75			
14	1.3	3	.01	100	1870	12300	9.6	30	.78			
15	1.2	2	.70	15	25	1.0	4.1	15	.17			
16	1.5	2	.30	7.8	20	.42	3.7	7	.07			
17	1.6	2	.00	5.5	18	.27	3.1	3	.50			
18	1.2	1	.60	26	146	18	2.6	2	.01			
19	1.2	1	.50	12	15	.49	3.2	1	.20			
20	1.2	1	.20	7.2	13	.25	2.1	1	.10			
21	1.3	1	.00	5.6	12	.18	1.9	1	.10			
22	1.2	1	.00	4.8	12	.16	1.7	1	.10			
23	1.2	1	.00	4.0	11	.12	1.8	1	.00			
24	1.2	1	.00	3.3	9	.08	2.1	1	.01			
25	1.2	1	.00	3.1	8	.07	1.8	1	.00			
26	1.2	1	.00	2.9	7	.60	1.8	1	.00			
27	1.7	1	.00	2.7	7	.05	1.8	1	.00			
28	3.3	1	.01	2.6	6	.30	1.8	1	.20			
29	36	222	107	4.5	6	.07	1.6	1	.20			
30	6.9	20	.37	3.4	6	.06	1.6	1	.50			
31	---	---	---	26	271	107	---	---	---			
TOTAL	96.6	---	114.27	560.9	---	21296.01	142.5	---	189.20			

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051180 QUEBRADA SALVATIERRA NEAR SAN LORENZO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

		JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
1	1.7	1	.80	1.4	2	.01	3.5	20	.19	
2	1.7	1	.90	1.5	2	.01	2.0	15	.08	
3	2.2	1	.90	1.2	2	.01	1.8	12	.06	
4	1.6	2	.01	1.1	2	.01	1.7	11	.05	
5	1.5	2	.01	1.0	2	.01	3.0	10	.08	
6	3.0	2	.02	1.1	2	.01	2.0	10	.05	
7	1.9	2	.01	1.8	2	.50	1.7	10	.05	
8	1.5	2	.01	2.2	4	.02	1.5	9	.04	
9	1.4	2	.01	1.5	2	.01	1.3	8	.03	
10	1.4	2	.01	2.8	5	.04	1.2	8	.03	
11	1.7	2	.01	7.5	25	.51	1.3	8	.03	
12	2.0	2	.01	2.2	8	.05	1.1	8	.02	
13	1.4	2	.01	8.6	82	26	1.5	7	.03	
14	1.5	2	.01	4.7	4	.05	1.2	7	.02	
15	1.7	2	.01	2.3	3	.02	1.1	9	.03	
16	1.4	2	.01	1.7	2	.80	1.2	---	---	
17	1.4	2	.01	1.4	2	.50	1.2	---	---	
18	1.4	2	.01	1.3	2	.40	1.1	---	---	
19	1.2	2	.01	1.3	2	.20	1.1	---	---	
20	1.3	2	.01	1.2	2	.01	1.1	---	---	
21	1.5	2	.01	1.1	2	.01	1.2	---	---	
22	1.2	2	.01	3.0	5	.04	1.1	---	---	
23	1.1	2	.01	1.7	4	.02	1.7	---	---	
24	1.1	2	.01	1.4	3	.01	12	---	---	
25	1.2	2	.01	2.1	5	.03	9.7	---	---	
26	1.1	2	.01	1.2	2	.01	3.9	---	---	
27	1.3	2	.01	1.1	2	.01	3.0	---	---	
28	1.5	2	.01	3.8	5	.05	2.0	---	---	
29	1.4	2	.01	73	508	296	1.7	---	---	
30	2.7	2	.01	5.9	25	.40	1.6	---	---	
31	1.9	2	.01	2.5	15	.10	---	---	---	
TOTAL	48.9	---	2.89	144.6	---	325.85	69.5	---	0.79	
YEAR	2863.5		32636.26							

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'13", long 65°57'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at downstream side on bridge on Highway 912, at Barrio Cerro Gordo, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) south of San Lorenzo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--10.2 mi² (26.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1977 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 490 ft (150 m), from topographic map. Prior to Oct. 1, 1983, at site 2,000 ft (610 m) downstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--11 years (1978-88), 49.8 ft³/s (1.410 m³/s), 66.3 in/yr (1,684 mm/yr), 36,080 acre-ft/yr (44.49 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 40.6 ft³/s (1.15 m³/s), 29,400 acre-ft/yr (36.2 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 13,200 ft³/s (374 m³/s), Aug. 31, 1979, gage height, 9.44 ft (2.877 m), site and datum then in use, from rating curve extended above 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) on the basis of slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 7.1 ft³/s (0.201 m³/s), Feb. 4, May 3, 1981, Apr. 12, 13, 16, 17, 1983.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 18	1900	3,860	109	15.23	4.642	Dec. 7	1815	*9,610	272	*21.05	6.416
Nov. 24	1815	3,070	86.9	14.15	4.313	Aug.24	1445	3,580	101	14.84	4.523
Nov. 27	0430	8,990	255	20.55	6.264						

Minimum discharge, 7.2 ft³/s (0.204 m³/s), June 29, 30.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	18	19	101	67	40	e25	21	15	14	19	21	66
2	17	17	145	62	38	e30	22	14	14	235	20	66
3	22	16	94	59	46	22	20	13	14	29	22	64
4	22	27	86	57	35	21	20	13	13	22	22	60
5	16	116	87	63	37	21	18	13	13	21	21	55
6	15	69	108	58	34	22	18	33	13	27	21	54
7	13	30	1690	54	32	24	16	14	14	48	24	54
8	12	24	798	53	32	24	15	13	14	26	23	46
9	14	22	130	52	31	24	17	13	15	25	25	46
10	12	19	118	51	43	22	16	17	15	40	127	45
11	11	19	114	51	33	20	17	17	16	29	77	371
12	11	18	100	50	36	22	e15	16	16	28	38	157
13	10	18	99	47	49	22	e13	13	18	31	34	91
14	39	18	97	49	33	22	e16	15	20	42	34	93
15	42	18	95	45	34	22	e18	14	40	31	37	75
16	32	19	91	44	35	20	e15	14	41	28	42	72
17	176	23	83	43	29	21	e16	14	e19	27	47	69
18	651	28	79	41	29	21	e14	14	e16	30	48	68
19	134	23	78	42	29	19	e13	13	e22	27	41	113
20	45	22	82	40	31	20	e14	16	37	25	42	76
21	31	20	78	40	28	18	e12	14	34	24	42	67
22	23	20	109	38	28	18	e12	13	30	27	66	68
23	20	26	76	38	28	20	e16	13	18	25	88	68
24	15	1400	69	38	32	20	e14	13	14	22	531	58
25	22	320	66	38	30	21	e12	15	11	23	276	50
26	38	429	67	37	40	22	e11	17	13	23	78	47
27	33	2410	69	39	42	27	e11	17	11	22	77	44
28	29	420	67	36	28	25	e12	18	9.4	46	79	44
29	24	162	62	36	e27	21	e13	18	8.5	29	73	43
30	19	114	58	35	---	20	13	21	9.0	28	69	40
31	20	---	62	35	---	21	---	15	---	21	68	---
TOTAL	1586	5886	5058	1438	989	677	460	478	541.9	1080	2213	2270
MEAN	51.2	196	163	46.4	34.1	21.8	15.3	15.4	18.1	34.8	71.4	75.7
MAX	651	2410	1690	67	49	30	22	33	41	235	531	371
MIN	10	16	58	35	27	18	11	13	8.5	19	20	40
AC-FT	3150	11670	10030	2850	1960	1340	912	948	1070	2140	4390	4500
CFSM	5.02	19.2	16.0	4.55	3.34	2.14	1.50	1.51	1.77	3.42	7.00	7.42
IN.	5.78	21.47	18.45	5.24	3.61	2.47	1.68	1.74	1.98	3.94	8.07	8.28

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 22542.8 MEAN 61.8 MAX 2410 MIN 8.1 AC-FT 44710 CFSM 6.06 IN. 82.21
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 22676.9 MEAN 62.0 MAX 2410 MIN 8.5 AC-FT 44980 CFSM 6.07 IN. 82.70

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 14	1445	66.6	91.1	27.0	APR, 05	1337	17.9	137	30.0
NOV, 13	1338	18.0	100	28.0	MAY, 05	0953	17.2	139	26.5
JAN, 04	1347	57.4	121	25.5	JUN, 03	1018	13.9	138	26.5
FEB, 01	1611	35.8	129	24.0	JUL, 12	1040	26.9	131	26.5
MAR, 02	1624	24.8	132	24.0					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1983 to September 1986.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-49 and automatic sediment sampler.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 5,180 mg/L May 18, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 77,800 tons (70,580 tonnes) May 18, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.06 tons (0.05) tonne several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1984-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1984	1,220 (Nov. 05)	2 (several days)	9,840 (Feb. 15)	0.06 (several days)
1985	5,180 (May 18)	5 (several days)	77,800 (May 18)	0.22 (several days)
1986	2,790 (Oct. 06)	4 (several days)	17,990 (Oct. 06)	0.16 (March 19)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)									
										OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
										1	53	30	4.3	188	391	866	29	30
2	33	20	1.8	54	100	15	306	806	3080									
3	29	18	1.4	29	35	2.7	52	70	9.8									
4	27	16	1.2	440	840	1650	39	45	4.7									
5	27	15	1.1	478	1220	5650	36	40	3.9									
6	27	18	1.3	194	349	267	39	38	4.0									
7	29	17	1.3	74	110	22	34	35	3.2									
8	29	18	1.4	52	65	9.1	28	30	2.3									
9	41	25	2.8	42	52	5.9	25	29	2.0									
10	31	20	1.7	37	45	4.5	26	26	1.8									
11	27	15	1.1	35	42	15	26	26	1.8									
12	27	16	1.2	33	40	3.6	24	25	1.6									
13	31	40	3.3	32	39	3.4	23	25	1.6									
14	31	40	3.3	32	38	3.3	23	24	1.5									
15	31	40	3.3	33	40	3.6	26	25	1.8									
16	33	45	4.0	32	40	3.5	33	35	3.1									
17	25	30	2.0	30	40	3.2	31	35	2.9									
18	23	22	1.4	30	40	3.2	31	35	2.9									
19	37	50	5.0	30	40	3.2	29	35	2.7									
20	22	22	1.3	30	40	3.2	32	35	3.0									
21	22	21	1.2	30	35	2.8	25	35	2.4									
22	25	21	1.4	29	35	2.7	23	27	1.7									
23	21	21	1.2	29	35	2.7	23	22	1.4									
24	20	20	1.1	29	35	2.7	22	22	1.3									
25	20	20	1.1	28	32	2.4	22	23	1.4									
26	24	20	1.3	28	32	2.4	22	23	1.4									
27	20	20	1.1	29	32	2.5	23	23	1.4									
28	19	20	1.0	28	32	2.4	29	30	2.3									
29	25	25	1.7	28	30	2.3	25	30	2.0									
30	31	35	2.9	27	30	2.2	40	30	3.2									
31	21	25	1.4	---	---	---	75	60	12									
TOTAL	861	---	59.6	2190	---	8562.5	1221	---	3167.4									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	35	45	4.3	27	30	2.2	22	22	1.3
2	26	35	2.5	26	30	2.1	22	22	1.3
3	24	28	1.8	29	25	2.0	22	22	1.3
4	23	23	1.4	32	28	2.4	21	20	1.1
5	22	23	1.4	29	28	2.2	21	20	1.1
6	22	23	1.4	31	30	2.5	22	20	1.2
7	22	20	1.2	30	30	2.4	21	20	1.1
8	21	21	1.2	27	30	2.2	22	20	1.2
9	24	25	1.6	27	30	2.2	26	22	1.5
10	38	30	3.1	30	35	2.8	24	18	1.2
11	22	23	1.4	29	32	2.5	22	10	.59
12	24	25	1.6	100	198	199	23	5	.31
13	130	46	6.6	129	239	143	25	5	.34
14	85	75	17	48	56	9.8	37	5	.50
15	40	55	5.9	567	1140	9840	29	5	.39
16	35	45	4.3	464	976	4050	31	5	.42
17	33	32	2.9	52	70	9.8	36	5	.49
18	33	40	3.6	32	38	3.3	30	5	.41
19	31	40	3.3	25	30	2.0	25	5	.34
20	49	60	7.9	23	30	1.9	23	7	.43
21	33	40	3.6	23	30	1.9	21	6	.34
22	37	35	3.5	22	28	1.7	20	8	.43
23	32	35	3.0	22	23	1.4	22	8	.48
24	31	35	2.9	22	23	1.4	19	8	.41
25	38	35	3.6	22	23	1.4	18	8	.39
26	34	35	3.2	22	23	1.4	17	8	.37
27	32	35	3.0	23	22	1.4	17	7	.32
28	33	35	3.1	23	22	1.4	17	5	.23
29	29	32	2.5	22	22	1.3	18	4	.19
30	28	30	2.3	---	---	---	17	4	.18
31	27	30	2.2	---	---	---	16	4	.17
TOTAL	1093	---	107.3	1958	---	14297.6	706	---	20.03
		APRIL		MAY			JUNE		
1	16	5	.22	11	2	.06	51	69	13
2	15	5	.20	11	2	.06	26	35	2.5
3	15	5	.20	11	2	.06	21	22	1.2
4	15	5	.20	11	2	.06	27	20	1.5
5	15	5	.20	11	2	.06	20	20	1.1
6	15	5	.20	12	2	.06	44	65	21
7	15	5	.20	11	2	.06	195	402	461
8	14	5	.19	11	2	.06	74	85	17
9	14	4	.15	11	2	.06	42	58	6.6
10	13	4	.14	13	2	.07	542	1400	8290
11	13	4	.14	11	2	.06	99	110	29
12	13	4	.14	11	2	.06	62	90	15
13	13	3	.11	12	2	.06	72	105	23
14	13	3	.11	12	3	.10	47	50	6.3
15	13	3	.11	11	3	.09	34	40	3.7
16	13	3	.11	11	3	.09	66	101	40
17	14	3	.11	11	3	.09	48	60	7.8
18	13	3	.11	11	3	.09	37	42	4.2
19	13	3	.11	11	3	.09	37	40	4.0
20	12	3	.10	11	3	.09	33	40	3.6
21	13	3	.11	12	8	.26	32	35	3.0
22	13	3	.11	12	10	.32	30	32	2.6
23	13	3	.11	17	10	.46	29	32	2.5
24	12	2	.06	13	12	.42	28	30	2.3
25	12	2	.06	26	35	2.5	26	30	2.1
26	12	2	.06	30	35	2.8	27	29	2.1
27	13	2	.07	19	25	1.3	27	29	2.1
28	17	2	.09	27	40	2.9	27	25	1.8
29	13	3	.11	27	35	2.6	28	25	1.9
30	11	2	.06	132	228	151	34	35	3.2
31	---	---	---	39	60	6.3	---	---	---
TOTAL	406	---	3.89	579	---	172.29	1865	---	8975.1

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	35	45	4.3	32	46	8.3	19	20	1.0
2	34	40	3.7	43	55	6.4	18	18	.87
3	27	25	1.8	28	32	2.4	18	18	.87
4	126	336	604	105	372	553	27	30	2.2
5	167	327	212	33	40	3.6	46	87	37
6	38	46	4.7	23	24	1.5	43	60	7.0
7	29	32	2.5	24	23	1.5	21	22	1.2
8	26	30	2.1	23	22	1.4	21	22	1.2
9	25	30	2.0	22	20	1.2	18	22	1.1
10	24	30	1.9	20	20	1.1	22	30	1.8
11	24	30	1.9	21	20	1.1	47	55	7.0
12	24	28	1.8	21	20	1.1	39	85	9.0
13	24	25	1.6	21	25	1.4	64	135	48
14	26	25	1.8	25	20	1.4	155	303	251
15	26	25	1.8	22	20	1.2	41	70	7.7
16	24	25	1.6	25	30	2.0	29	40	3.1
17	23	25	1.6	19	20	1.0	118	274	239
18	23	25	1.6	19	20	1.0	89	179	51
19	24	30	1.9	21	19	1.1	70	95	21
20	25	30	2.0	18	18	.87	332	692	1830
21	27	30	2.2	19	18	.92	94	120	30
22	30	30	2.4	16	18	.78	46	55	6.8
23	31	30	2.5	17	18	.83	37	48	4.8
24	26	30	2.1	14	18	.68	33	42	3.7
25	24	30	1.9	14	18	.68	31	40	3.3
26	24	30	1.9	17	41	6.0	31	35	2.9
27	24	30	1.9	51	77	13	30	35	2.8
28	23	30	1.9	22	20	1.2	36	35	3.4
29	27	30	2.2	18	12	.58	32	35	3.0
30	34	30	2.8	20	12	.65	40	35	3.8
31	25	31	2.1	18	16	.78	---	---	---
TOTAL	1069	---	880.5	791	---	618.67	1647	---	2585.54
YEAR	14386		39450.42						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

183

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	33	40	3.6	142	224	134	36	50	4.9
2	33	40	3.6	243	544	692	74	161	66
3	39	50	5.3	1010	3030	16900	45	150	18
4	33	40	3.6	248	519	562	37	80	8.0
5	32	38	3.3	650	1510	5090	39	70	7.4
6	36	40	3.9	694	1580	5160	37	68	6.8
7	45	63	9.2	355	560	825	37	62	6.2
8	51	68	11	123	210	70	37	60	6.0
9	272	783	1950	84	180	41	44	55	6.5
10	90	115	28	74	145	29	38	50	5.1
11	53	80	11	62	120	20	47	96	32
12	40	50	5.4	55	100	15	39	80	8.4
13	63	98	31	52	90	13	36	35	3.4
14	350	811	1650	74	116	28	35	30	2.8
15	71	120	23	62	100	17	34	30	2.8
16	69	140	72	47	70	8.9	38	30	3.1
17	76	200	41	46	65	8.1	39	28	2.9
18	43	50	5.8	44	60	7.1	33	28	2.5
19	41	50	5.5	43	58	6.7	34	15	1.4
20	40	50	5.4	42	50	5.7	34	15	1.4
21	40	50	5.4	41	50	5.5	32	15	1.3
22	41	50	5.5	43	50	5.8	31	15	1.3
23	38	50	5.1	45	55	6.7	30	15	1.2
24	37	46	4.6	40	52	5.6	35	15	1.4
25	56	116	21	42	60	6.8	44	55	6.5
26	114	234	105	68	150	36	34	45	4.1
27	65	90	16	39	60	6.3	34	32	2.9
28	52	50	7.0	38	50	5.1	32	31	2.7
29	51	35	4.8	37	49	4.9	30	30	2.4
30	47	28	3.6	37	50	5.0	34	30	2.8
31	41	28	3.1	---	---	---	29	30	2.3
TOTAL	2092	---	4052.7	4580	---	29720.2	1158	---	224.5

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
JANUARY									
1	29	27	2.1	20	5	.27	21	30	1.7
2	33	25	2.2	19	5	.26	19	25	1.3
3	29	22	1.7	17	5	.23	26	22	1.4
4	42	50	5.7	16	5	.22	18	20	.97
5	28	20	1.5	16	5	.22	15	20	.81
6	29	20	1.6	16	5	.22	18	60	2.9
7	26	16	1.1	15	9	.36	48	110	14
8	26	10	.70	16	10	.43	42	55	6.2
9	25	10	.68	15	10	.41	25	20	1.4
10	26	10	.70	15	10	.41	22	10	.59
11	26	9	.63	15	10	.41	20	10	.54
12	26	10	.70	16	10	.43	20	9	.49
13	26	10	.70	18	12	.58	19	9	.46
14	25	10	.68	18	25	1.2	22	9	.53
15	25	9	.61	23	20	1.2	19	8	.41
16	25	10	.68	20	22	1.2	19	9	.46
17	27	12	.87	17	25	1.1	20	9	.49
18	27	10	.73	19	25	1.3	46	63	13
19	26	10	.70	30	40	3.2	22	46	2.7
20	25	9	.61	30	70	5.7	19	12	.62
21	25	5	.34	22	35	2.1	21	8	.45
22	26	5	.35	22	25	1.5	19	8	.41
23	25	5	.34	20	20	1.1	19	8	.41
24	24	9	.58	21	16	.91	21	8	.45
25	22	8	.48	20	15	.81	16	5	.22
26	22	8	.48	21	15	.85	18	8	.39
27	20	5	.27	68	157	59	22	8	.48
28	20	5	.27	28	45	3.4	19	8	.41
29	19	5	.26	---	---	---	332	850	1560
30	19	5	.26	---	---	---	44	125	15
31	19	5	.26	---	---	---	39	80	8.4
TOTAL	792	---	28.78	593	---	89.02	1070	---	1637.59
APRIL									
1	23	35	2.2	17	20	.92	44	88	10
2	19	30	1.5	18	20	.97	42	85	9.4
3	19	25	1.3	20	20	1.1	41	83	9.2
4	18	22	1.1	19	20	1.0	39	83	8.7
5	19	20	1.0	20	20	1.1	38	75	7.7
6	19	20	1.0	20	20	1.1	37	50	5.0
7	20	19	1.0	21	20	1.1	35	35	3.3
8	21	18	1.0	21	20	1.1	35	30	2.8
9	18	10	.49	24	20	1.3	34	25	2.3
10	18	9	.44	23	20	1.2	34	28	2.6
11	20	8	.43	31	20	1.7	34	28	2.6
12	19	8	.41	40	50	5.4	32	30	2.6
13	26	9	.63	32	40	3.5	30	30	2.4
14	21	9	.51	199	430	415	29	30	2.3
15	20	9	.49	958	1990	11300	28	30	2.3
16	36	60	5.8	240	524	809	26	29	2.0
17	28	30	2.3	396	775	1330	25	28	1.9
18	36	30	2.9	1890	5180	77800	24	25	1.6
19	26	28	2.0	134	200	71	24	22	1.4
20	23	25	1.6	83	100	22	25	20	1.4
21	29	25	2.0	64	100	17	25	20	1.4
22	40	55	5.9	60	100	16	24	20	1.3
23	454	1230	5640	59	100	16	25	20	1.4
24	191	430	416	57	100	15	26	20	1.4
25	95	166	69	57	100	15	26	20	1.4
26	41	60	6.6	55	100	15	27	22	1.6
27	23	30	1.9	52	100	14	24	25	1.6
28	20	20	1.1	50	100	13	24	25	1.6
29	19	20	1.0	49	98	13	24	29	1.9
30	18	20	.97	47	95	12	23	29	1.8
31	---	---	---	45	90	11	---	---	---
TOTAL	1379	---	6172.57	4801	---	91925.49	904	---	96.9
MAY									
JUNE									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
		JULY							
1	26	29	2.0	24	30	1.9	27	30	2.2
2	28	30	2.3	24	30	1.9	26	29	2.0
3	28	30	2.3	22	30	1.8	23	29	1.8
4	28	30	2.3	20	28	1.5	22	25	1.5
5	25	30	2.0	17	25	1.1	23	25	1.6
6	23	30	1.9	21	25	1.4	25	25	1.7
7	23	25	1.6	22	21	1.2	25	25	1.7
8	22	22	1.3	22	19	1.1	39	50	5.3
9	23	20	1.2	20	15	.81	40	65	7.0
10	23	21	1.3	24	15	.97	30	42	3.4
11	24	21	1.4	21	15	.85	35	45	4.3
12	23	22	1.4	23	17	1.1	393	990	4460
13	22	22	1.3	32	18	1.6	286	543	743
14	22	22	1.3	29	15	1.2	72	70	14
15	66	101	28	28	15	1.1	42	50	5.7
16	90	135	55	26	15	1.1	31	45	3.8
17	212	542	1060	23	15	.93	33	45	3.4
18	38	40	2.7	23	15	.93	25	35	2.4
19	25	25	4.2	22	15	.89	27	32	2.3
20	62	110	22	24	15	.97	26	31	2.2
21	27	75	5.5	23	12	.75	25	30	2.0
22	22	60	3.6	21	11	.62	24	30	1.9
23	21	55	3.1	22	10	.59	24	30	1.9
24	32	52	4.5	25	10	.68	35	30	2.8
25	26	50	3.5	31	9	.75	390	936	3240
26	47	70	8.9	26	9	.63	64	97	23
27	28	40	3.0	139	317	356	40	48	5.2
28	29	38	3.0	143	420	353	73	108	27
29	29	35	2.7	28	45	3.4	41	45	5.0
30	27	31	2.3	23	33	2.0	40	40	4.3
31	26	31	2.2	22	30	1.8	---	---	---
TOTAL	1147	---	1237.8	970	---	744.57	2001	---	8582.4
YEAR	21467		144512.52						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	60	80	15	98	160	42	40	25	2.7
2	67	90	16	87	120	28	31	25	2.8
3	61	72	12	83	120	27	37	25	2.5
4	70	83	18	75	120	24	31	28	2.3
5	101	131	37	77	110	23	44	29	3.4
6	1530	2790	17900	65	100	18	45	29	3.5
7	664	879	2320	61	110	18	39	28	2.9
8	171	200	92	59	110	18	36	28	2.7
9	76	100	21	56	108	16	37	28	2.8
10	58	60	9.4	56	107	16	38	28	2.9
11	45	45	5.5	59	105	17	35	28	2.6
12	48	40	5.2	84	128	33	60	28	4.5
13	49	39	5.2	88	140	33	42	30	3.4
14	37	35	3.5	68	110	20	38	30	3.1
15	30	32	2.6	84	95	22	40	30	3.2
16	35	30	2.8	72	85	17	39	30	3.2
17	55	73	15	67	95	17	33	30	2.7
18	68	102	27	141	251	121	31	30	2.5
19	51	70	9.6	66	95	17	34	30	2.8
20	35	45	4.3	64	83	14	36	30	2.9
21	38	40	4.1	59	75	12	33	30	2.7
22	37	40	4.0	48	65	8.4	35	30	2.8
23	360	699	1350	44	55	6.5	46	30	3.7
24	644	1410	4300	42	50	5.7	53	30	4.3
25	173	250	117	40	50	5.4	35	30	2.8
26	120	150	49	41	37	4.1	32	30	2.6
27	117	140	44	41	28	3.1	30	30	2.4
28	105	140	40	39	27	2.8	32	30	2.6
29	277	629	1370	39	26	2.7	31	30	2.5
30	124	100	33	44	25	3.0	32	30	2.6
31	150	300	121	---	---	---	28	30	2.3
TOTAL	5456	---	27953.2	1947	---	594.7	1163	---	90.7

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

187

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	30	30	2.4	18	12	.58	15	12	.49
2	35	30	2.8	17	12	.55	14	12	.45
3	40	29	3.1	17	12	.55	16	12	.52
4	50	30	4.1	28	11	.83	17	15	.69
5	35	30	2.8	39	12	1.3	20	15	.81
6	27	30	2.2	20	15	.81	19	14	.72
7	25	28	1.9	18	12	.58	17	12	.55
8	30	27	2.2	19	12	.62	15	11	.45
9	74	123	60	18	12	.58	16	11	.48
10	60	25	4.1	19	15	.77	16	10	.43
11	30	22	1.8	21	12	.68	18	9	.44
12	22	22	1.3	19	12	.62	17	8	.37
13	21	21	1.2	16	12	.52	25	8	.54
14	25	22	1.5	19	12	.62	27	5	.36
15	23	22	1.4	18	15	.73	37	5	.50
16	27	22	1.6	18	15	.73	16	5	.22
17	41	57	15	21	15	.85	14	5	.19
18	27	21	1.5	22	15	.89	14	5	.19
19	20	22	1.2	63	64	17	15	4	.16
20	19	21	1.1	31	16	1.3	16	4	.17
21	30	25	2.0	20	14	.76	16	5	.22
22	24	25	1.6	18	15	.73	15	5	.20
23	19	25	1.3	17	15	.69	15	5	.20
24	23	22	1.4	15	15	.61	15	8	.32
25	18	20	.97	15	15	.61	14	8	.30
26	16	18	.78	16	15	.65	20	9	.49
27	15	15	.61	19	16	.82	15	8	.35
28	24	14	.91	15	12	.49	13	8	.28
29	20	15	.81	---	---	---	174	355	306
30	22	15	.89	---	---	---	51	80	11
31	20	14	.76	---	---	---	27	25	1.8
TOTAL	892	---	125.23	596	---	36.47	740	---	329.89
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	62	85	27	25	15	1.0	20	40	2.2
2	26	25	1.8	20	8	.43	28	30	2.3
3	15	20	.81	25	8	.54	23	25	1.6
4	19	20	1.0	17	8	.37	21	25	1.4
5	38	50	5.1	24	7	.45	22	20	1.2
6	31	35	2.9	38	8	.82	20	20	1.1
7	16	20	.86	40	15	1.6	18	20	.97
8	28	47	15	48	32	5.9	16	40	1.7
9	58	79	22	22	15	.89	28	60	4.5
10	16	22	.95	254	779	1680	217	569	1130
11	13	20	.70	208	335	291	21	30	1.7
12	14	18	.68	65	120	21	16	25	1.1
13	16	15	.65	346	1520	5810	29	25	2.0
14	15	10	.41	495	681	1750	39	28	2.9
15	15	10	.41	62	130	22	52	72	19
16	15	10	.41	38	70	7.2	55	60	8.9
17	15	8	.32	28	60	4.5	40	40	4.3
18	15	7	.28	591	1400	9330	29	40	3.1
19	15	7	.28	88	128	35	35	40	3.8
20	14	6	.23	37	80	8.0	28	35	2.6
21	15	6	.24	30	70	5.7	23	35	2.2
22	15	6	.24	60	70	11	21	35	2.0
23	14	7	.26	30	45	3.6	19	35	1.8
24	16	8	.35	26	30	2.1	17	32	1.5
25	13	7	.25	24	25	1.6	16	32	1.4
26	13	7	.25	23	20	1.2	19	30	1.5
27	18	7	.34	24	20	1.3	25	30	2.0
28	45	43	14	22	20	1.2	27	25	1.8
29	693	1300	11200	60	20	3.2	20	25	1.4
30	81	124	52	23	30	1.9	19	22	1.1
31	---	---	---	273	936	3920	---	---	---
TOTAL	1379	---	11349.72	3066	---	22923.50	963	---	1213.07

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50051310 RIO CAYAGUAS AT CERRO GORDO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	30	20	1.6	23	32	2.0	24	23	1.5
2	22	20	1.2	20	30	1.6	16	22	.95
3	22	20	1.2	18	27	1.3	14	20	.76
4	19	20	1.0	18	27	1.3	16	20	.86
5	19	20	1.0	17	22	1.0	41	40	4.4
6	65	76	18	16	22	.95	19	18	.92
7	35	45	4.3	33	42	7.3	17	15	.69
8	23	40	2.5	51	55	7.6	15	12	.49
9	20	35	1.9	20	21	1.1	16	12	.52
10	19	30	1.5	26	32	4.2	14	12	.45
11	46	61	9.9	61	82	18	13	12	.42
12	37	60	6.0	22	23	1.4	12	12	.42
13	24	50	3.2	42	45	5.1	19	15	.77
14	26	45	3.2	51	30	4.1	24	15	.97
15	37	39	3.9	25	27	1.8	15	15	.61
16	27	37	2.7	18	25	1.2	17	15	.69
17	25	35	2.4	17	25	1.1	17	18	.83
18	25	31	2.1	16	25	1.1	18	18	.87
19	21	30	1.7	15	25	1.0	19	18	.92
20	22	28	1.7	15	20	.81	18	15	.73
21	27	28	2.0	14	20	.76	17	15	.69
22	20	27	1.5	15	20	.81	23	15	.93
23	19	26	1.3	16	18	.78	45	23	3.2
24	20	24	1.3	15	17	.69	70	52	8.6
25	18	23	1.1	14	16	.60	50	30	4.1
26	18	23	1.1	13	15	.57	30	28	2.3
27	21	22	1.2	12	15	.53	17	22	1.0
28	24	22	1.4	80	15	.49	15	20	.81
29	21	22	1.2	200	158	112	14	15	.57
30	63	91	24	59	50	8.0	13	15	.53
31	38	55	5.6	36	45	6.9	---	---	---
TOTAL	853	---	112.7	998	---	196.09	659	---	41.50
YEAR	18712		64966.77						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

189

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'10", long 66°02'37", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at right upstream end of bridge on Highway 765, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) south of Villa Borinquen, and 7.3 mi (11.7 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--7.89 mi² (20.44 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 430 ft (131 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 13,800 ft³/s (391 m³/s), Nov.27, 1987, gage height, 18.02 ft (5.492 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 1.4 ft³/s (0.040 m³/s), Oct. 11, 1987.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 24	unknown	4,100	116	unknown		July 2	0530	2,940	83.3	10.13	3.088
Nov. 27	unknown	*13,800	391	*18.02	5.492	Aug. 24	1430	1,610	45.6	8.33	2.539
Dec. 7	unknown	3,600	102	unknown		Sept.11	0815	2,030	57.5	8.95	2.728

Minimum discharge, 1.4 ft³/s (0.040 m³/s), Oct. 11 .

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	8.5	8.7	e35	e70	e38	17	9.0	18	6.5	111	12	24
2	4.8	6.1	e50	e45	e46	22	6.6	9.7	6.5	504	11	22
3	7.1	5.8	e28	e36	e30	17	8.8	7.4	0.6	78	30	21
4	6.8	5.7	e25	e35	e24	14	8.0	7.1	6.4	43	17	20
5	6.2	39	e23	e36	e22	14	8.2	7.3	5.9	28	10	19
6	4.4	58	e30	e35	e20	14	13	18	5.8	39	9.9	20
7	3.3	29	e540	e33	e18	13	10	9.6	5.5	84	19	21
8	2.8	18	e390	e33	e18	13	8.2	7.6	5.9	32	17	20
9	2.5	15	e62	e32	e23	13	8.0	7.8	6.0	27	15	35
10	2.2	12	e45	e31	e20	12	7.9	26	6.1	37	150	53
11	2.0	10	e36	e32	e17	12	7.7	17	5.9	30	82	308
12	3.3	e8.0	e34	e31	e25	12	7.5	18	5.7	25	28	213
13	5.0	e6.8	e32	e30	e23	12	7.6	9.9	6.7	22	19	110
14	15	e6.5	e31	e29	e19	11	7.0	18	7.4	23	17	83
15	52	e6.3	e31	e27	e18	11	9.2	13	51	19	17	67
16	36	e6.3	e30	e26	e16	11	9.1	9.7	23	19	22	51
17	106	e11	e30	e26	e14	11	54	12	8.4	19	35	41
18	327	e9.7	e36	e25	e14	11	18	11	7.9	23	40	37
19	80	e7.2	e38	e25	e13	11	12	8.6	8.4	26	19	39
20	44	e6.5	e40	e24	e13	14	9.3	10	11	22	16	33
21	30	e5.6	e64	e23	e13	11	9.0	18	11	20	15	29
22	24	e5.0	e50	e23	e12	11	8.3	9.3	20	29	41	28
23	19	e20	e38	e22	e13	11	7.9	7.8	13	32	31	27
24	22	e620	e36	e22	e14	11	8.2	7.3	19	20	293	25
25	18	e130	e37	e22	e16	11	7.9	7.1	10	17	210	24
26	23	e250	e37	e22	e35	11	8.2	7.0	8.9	23	61	22
27	16	e2000	e36	e23	36	20	8.2	7.0	7.9	18	49	21
28	29	e350	e34	e23	19	13	7.4	6.8	7.2	43	47	21
29	32	e90	e33	e23	16	11	7.3	14	8.3	15	37	20
30	17	e45	e55	e23	---	11	8.0	8.3	70	22	31	19
31	14	---	e115	e35	---	9.7	---	7.5	---	13	27	---
TOTAL	962.9	3791.2	2101	922	605	395.7	311.5	345.8	371.9	1463	1427.9	1473
MEAN	31.1	126	67.8	29.7	20.9	12.8	10.4	11.2	12.4	47.2	46.1	49.1
MAX	327	2000	540	70	46	22	54	26	70	504	293	308
MIN	2.0	5.0	23	22	12	9.7	7.0	6.8	5.5	13	9.9	19
AC-FT	1910	7520	4170	1830	1200	785	618	686	738	2900	2830	2920
CFSM	3.94	16.0	8.59	3.77	2.64	1.62	1.32	1.41	1.57	5.98	5.84	6.22
IN.	4.54	17.87	9.91	4.35	2.85	1.87	1.47	1.63	1.75	6.90	6.73	6.94

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 12671.8 MEAN 34.7 MAX 2000 MIN 1.7 AC-FT 25130 CFSM 4.40 IN. 59.75
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 14170.9 MEAN 38.7 MAX 2000 MIN 2.0 AC-FT 28110 CFSM 4.91 IN. 66.81

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS JANUARY 1985 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 16	1022	21.4	132	26.0	APR, 08	1102	8.97	163	27.5
NOV, 12	1355	10.8	155	29.0	MAY, 10	0928	7.92	174	25.0
DEC, 09	1559	73.5	135	27.0	JUN, 02	0827	7.16	165	24.0
JAN, 12	1505	33.5	146	25.0	JUL, 07	1400	47.70	117	26.5
MAR, 14	1420	11.6	157	30.5					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

191

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1984 to September 1986.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-49 and automatic sediment sampler.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 7,420 mg/L May 17, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 106,000 tons (96,160 tonnes) May 17, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.00 tons (0.00) tonne several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1984-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1984	3,510 (Feb. 15)	3 (several days)	19,600 (Feb. 15)	0.05 (several days)
1985	7,420 (May 17)	1 (several days)	106,000 (May 17)	0.00 (several days)
1986	5,530 (Oct. 06)	3 (several days)	39,400 (Oct. 06)	0.06 (several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)									
										JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
										1	11	8	.50	7.4	4	.40	13	12
2	9.1	6	.20	7.1	4	.10	13	12	.42									
3	8.5	5	.50	7.6	4	.60	12	11	.36									
4	8.5	5	.50	9.8	5	.20	12	11	.36									
5	8.4	5	.50	7.4	4	.80	13	10	.35									
6	9.6	7	.20	7.0	4	.50	13	10	.35									
7	8.8	5	.80	7.4	4	.20	13	10	.35									
8	8.8	5	.80	6.6	4	.07	13	10	.35									
9	9.2	6	.40	18	30	1.5	13	10	.35									
10	9.3	6	.60	27	40	2.9	13	10	.35									
11	9.1	6	.20	20	35	1.9	12	9	.50									
12	11	8	.24	116	952	1740	12	9	.29									
13	89	534	1210	184	1020	1360	12	8	.80									
14	36	55	5.3	50	90	12	14	8	.50									
15	23	25	1.6	325	3510	19600	12	8	.26									
16	19	25	1.3	208	1440	2190	12	7	.50									
17	25	30	2.0	33	28	2.5	13	7	.25									
18	29	38	3.0	23	25	1.6	12	6	.50									
19	22	30	1.8	19	22	1.1	12	6	.19									
20	48	65	8.4	17	21	.96	12	5	.50									
21	28	36	2.7	16	20	.86	12	5	.16									
22	24	28	1.8	16	18	.78	13	4	.80									
23	15	15	.61	15	15	.61	16	4	.50									
24	9.2	6	.50	14	15	.57	15	4	.16									
25	24	25	1.6	14	15	.57	13	3	.80									
26	11	7	.21	14	15	.57	16	3	.50									
27	8.4	5	.40	14	15	.57	18	3	.50									
28	12	11	.36	14	15	.57	17	3	.14									
29	8.1	5	.10	14	15	.57	17	3	.14									
30	7.9	4	.90	---	---	---	16	3	.13									
31	7.6	4	.60	---	---	---	12	3	.10									
TOTAL	557.5	---	1248.62	1231.3	---	24923.00	416	---	11.88									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	11	3	.09	7.3	3	.06	31	40	3.3
2	11	3	.09	8.1	3	.20	26	40	2.8
3	12	3	.10	8.5	3	.50	20	30	1.6
4	13	3	.11	7.7	3	.70	16	30	1.3
5	15	3	.12	7.4	4	.08	14	20	.76
6	14	3	.11	7.3	4	.08	25	40	2.7
7	11	3	.09	7.0	4	.08	53	100	14
8	9.9	3	.08	7.0	4	.08	43	60	7.0
9	9.7	3	.08	8.6	4	.10	29	30	2.3
10	9.3	3	.08	9.8	4	.10	430	3060	18400
11	9.7	3	.08	8.7	4	.09	50	70	9.5
12	8.4	3	.07	9.3	4	.10	33	50	4.5
13	8.2	3	.07	18	30	1.5	44	60	7.1
14	9.1	3	.07	9.9	10	.27	28	30	2.3
15	9.0	3	.07	9.4	6	.15	21	25	1.4
16	8.6	3	.10	8.8	5	.50	96	867	1550
17	8.8	3	.20	8.9	5	.50	29	45	3.5
18	8.0	3	.80	7.2	5	.20	19	30	1.5
19	7.7	4	.08	7.0	5	.20	26	50	3.5
20	8.2	4	.09	8.0	5	.10	17	16	.73
21	9.0	4	.10	8.8	5	.50	15	12	.49
22	9.6	4	.10	10	7	.19	14	9	.34
23	12	4	.13	22	26	1.5	13	8	.28
24	11	4	.12	20	21	1.1	11	8	.24
25	11	4	.12	26	26	1.8	11	8	.24
26	7.7	3	.80	52	181	73	11	8	.24
27	14	10	.38	38	65	6.7	10	8	.22
28	7.3	5	.10	36	65	6.3	10	8	.22
29	6.3	3	.05	37	65	6.5	11	8	.24
30	6.6	3	.05	101	486	288	13	8	.28
31	---	---	---	37	60	6.0	---	---	---
TOTAL	296.1	---	4.53	561.7	---	397.18	1169	---	20022.58
		JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER	
1	19	8	.41	6.4	5	.09	10	8	.22
2	17	8	.37	16	15	.65	10	8	.22
3	12	8	.26	10	10	.27	19	21	2.5
4	110	268	445	28	45	3.4	15	18	.73
5	396	2730	8570	19	24	1.2	69	610	792
6	41	65	7.2	17	21	.96	31	60	5.0
7	29	42	3.3	16	19	.82	15	10	.41
8	26	40	2.8	16	15	.65	11	8	.24
9	25	38	2.6	15	14	.57	13	15	.53
10	24	30	1.9	14	11	.42	11	15	.45
11	23	30	1.9	14	10	.38	11	15	.45
12	22	28	1.7	10	9	.24	14	18	.68
13	20	25	1.4	11	8	.50	14	15	.57
14	22	25	1.5	9.9	7	.80	25	38	4.2
15	20	22	1.2	11	8	.24	19	30	3.6
16	18	22	1.1	11	6	.18	23	55	7.0
17	17	22	1.0	9.1	6	.20	96	549	471
18	18	21	1.0	8.2	5	.20	87	466	179
19	16	18	.78	8.2	5	.20	74	246	70
20	18	18	.87	8.9	5	.90	128	558	870
21	23	18	1.1	8.9	5	.90	49	100	13
22	22	15	.89	7.4	4	.40	25	30	2.0
23	24	10	.65	7.4	4	.08	19	20	1.0
24	17	8	.37	6.9	4	.07	17	18	.83
25	17	8	.37	6.8	4	.07	16	17	.73
26	15	9	.36	27	59	8.8	15	16	.65
27	12	9	.29	20	20	1.1	15	16	.65
28	10	10	.27	11	6	.18	14	16	.60
29	16	22	.95	8.1	5	.10	14	16	.60
30	16	15	.65	10	8	.22	15	16	.65
31	8.0	8	.17	10	8	.22	---	---	---
TOTAL YEAR	1073.0 7056.6	---	9052.36 58121.01	382.2	---	25.01	894	---	2429.51

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	14	26	.98	62	342	283	14	3	.11
2	13	26	.91	123	496	328	54	15	6.3
3	14	25	.95	611	3610	22500	27	12	1.0
4	12	24	.78	182	37	22	19	6	.31
5	12	24	.78	335	54	68	18	4	.19
6	13	26	.91	279	46	39	16	4	.17
7	12	26	.84	196	46	37	16	4	.17
8	12	26	.84	114	24	7.4	20	8	.64
9	51	40	16	80	20	4.3	19	6	.31
10	16	27	1.2	64	18	3.1	19	6	.31
11	13	25	.88	54	18	2.6	17	6	.28
12	12	26	.84	46	18	2.2	16	7	.30
13	12	28	.91	43	19	2.2	15	7	.28
14	26	40	4.8	51	27	7.9	15	8	.32
15	14	31	1.2	34	28	2.6	16	8	.35
16	18	33	2.2	28	18	1.4	22	12	.96
17	18	36	1.7	24	14	.91	14	9	.34
18	14	31	1.2	22	12	.71	12	10	.32
19	13	30	1.1	21	8	.45	12	10	.32
20	13	30	1.1	19	5	.26	11	10	.30
21	15	31	1.4	18	5	.24	9.0	9	.22
22	16	32	1.4	17	5	.23	8.5	9	.21
23	15	33	1.3	18	5	.24	8.4	9	.20
24	13	29	1.0	16	4	.17	9.7	9	.24
25	23	26	1.6	16	5	.32	21	25	5.1
26	19	23	1.2	31	15	1.9	12	11	.36
27	16	20	.86	19	5	.26	12	10	.32
28	19	18	.92	15	4	.16	11	9	.27
29	14	14	.53	15	4	.16	9.2	9	.22
30	58	571	1410	15	3	.12	12	10	.32
31	17	26	1.2	---	---	---	10	9	.24
TOTAL	547	---	1461.53	2568	---	23316.83	494.8	---	20.98

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	17	13	1.1	10	7	.19	20	15	.81
2	17	12	.73	9.6	8	.21	18	14	.68
3	13	8	.28	9.4	8	.20	19	16	.82
4	18	13	1.1	9.7	9	.24	17	13	.60
5	12	8	.26	9.1	10	.25	18	12	.58
6	17	13	1.2	8.9	10	.24	29	136	31
7	12	8	.26	7.6	11	.23	38	18	1.8
8	11	8	.24	7.6	12	.25	30	15	1.5
9	11	8	.24	7.7	12	.25	22	11	.65
10	12	8	.26	8.0	13	.28	18	8	.39
11	10	8	.22	8.7	13	.31	16	5	.14
12	9.4	8	.20	8.9	13	.31	17	4	.18
13	9.3	7	.18	8.6	13	.30	15	4	.16
14	9.9	7	.19	10	13	.35	14	3	.11
15	11	6	.18	9.6	12	.31	13	3	.11
16	11	6	.18	9.0	8	.19	13	2	.07
17	11	6	.18	8.6	8	.19	13	2	.07
18	11	6	.18	8.4	8	.18	55	20	6.0
19	10	6	.16	22	19	1.1	23	12	.75
20	10	6	.16	20	18	.97	17	8	.37
21	9.7	6	.16	17	16	.73	16	5	.22
22	9.7	5	.13	14	13	.49	15	5	.20
23	9.4	5	.13	13	12	.42	15	5	.20
24	9.5	5	.13	15	11	.45	13	5	.18
25	9.7	4	.10	15	14	.57	13	5	.18
26	10	4	.11	16	14	.60	12	5	.16
27	9.2	4	.10	42	29	5.2	12	5	.16
28	9.3	4	.10	25	20	1.4	12	5	.16
29	8.9	5	.12	---	---	---	67	35	12
30	8.9	6	.14	---	---	---	24	32	2.2
31	9.2	6	.15	---	---	---	24	22	2.1
TOTAL	346.1	---	8.87	358.4	---	16.41	648	---	64.55
		APRIL		MAY			JUNE		
1	14	10	.38	6.0	12	.2	11	6	.18
2	12	9	.29	5.7	10	.2	11	6	.18
3	11	8	.24	5.6	9	.1	11	6	.18
4	11	8	.24	5.2	8	.1	11	6	.18
5	11	6	.18	5.3	6	.1	10	5	.14
6	11	4	.12	5.1	6	.1	10	5	.14
7	12	4	.13	5.3	5	.1	9.7	5	.13
8	12	4	.13	4.8	4	.1	9.8	4	.11
9	9.3	3	.08	5.3	4	.1	9.2	4	.10
10	8.2	3	.07	4.8	3	.0	10	4	.11
11	8.7	2	.05	5.5	2	.0	11	4	.12
12	8.3	2	.04	8.2	2	.0	12	4	.13
13	11	2	.06	6.8	1	.0	14	4	.15
14	9.0	2	.05	202	2180	1690	13	4	.14
15	8.0	1	.02	205	1200	2050	13	4	.14
16	14	6	.23	146	1330	3810	12	4	.13
17	12	5	.16	1300	7420	106000	11	4	.12
18	15	8	.32	900	5900	14300	11	5	.15
19	11	4	.12	50	95	13	11	5	.15
20	9.1	2	.05	16	14	.6	12	5	.16
21	18	10	1.1	10	10	.3	11	5	.15
22	10	4	.11	9.4	10	.3	12	5	.16
23	228	1340	4280	9.1	9	.2	12	5	.16
24	52	174	49	9.0	8	.2	12	5	.16
25	109	1010	2970	9.9	8	.2	12	5	.16
26	31	66	10	10	7	.2	11	5	.15
27	11	14	.42	11	6	.2	11	5	.15
28	8.6	14	.33	11	6	.2	11	4	.12
29	7.2	13	.25	11	6	.2	12	4	.13
30	6.4	12	.21	11	6	.2	11	4	.12
31	---	---	---	11	6	.2	---	---	---
TOTAL	698.8	---	7314.38	3005.0	---	127867.1	337.7	---	4.30

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	13	4	.14	12	8	.26	12	16	.52
2	12	4	.13	12	8	.26	12	16	.52
3	12	4	.13	11	8	.24	12	16	.52
4	12	4	.13	11	8	.24	11	15	.45
5	11	4	.12	11	8	.24	15	18	1.1
6	10	4	.11	11	8	.24	13	14	.49
7	9.2	4	.10	10	8	.22	11	13	.39
8	9.3	4	.10	10	8	.22	18	17	1.5
9	9.3	4	.10	9.5	8	.21	18	19	.92
10	9.3	4	.10	9.3	8	.20	14	14	.53
11	10	4	.11	10	8	.22	12	10	.32
12	9.7	4	.10	12	8	.26	49	462	525
13	9.1	4	.10	17	8	.37	53	160	78
14	9.3	4	.10	14	8	.30	22	21	1.5
15	19	15	.77	13	9	.32	17	15	.69
16	18	20	.97	12	9	.29	14	12	.45
17	29	40	3.1	12	9	.29	12	11	.36
18	13	6	.21	13	9	.32	11	10	.30
19	12	6	.19	12	9	.29	11	9	.27
20	11	6	.18	11	10	.30	9.7	8	.21
21	9.7	6	.16	12	10	.32	9.7	9	.24
22	11	7	.21	13	11	.39	9.7	10	.26
23	12	7	.23	12	12	.39	10	8	.22
24	13	7	.25	12	12	.39	16	28	3.6
25	11	6	.18	14	12	.45	31	76	16
26	14	8	.30	13	12	.42	14	16	.60
27	12	7	.23	30	29	3.9	12	15	.49
28	13	7	.25	23	23	1.7	12	16	.52
29	14	8	.30	14	16	.60	11	14	.42
30	13	8	.28	13	16	.56	10	14	.38
31	12	8	.26	13	16	.56	---	---	---
TOTAL YEAR	381.9 10269.6	---	9.64 160736.33	401.8	---	14.97	482.1	---	636.77

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	61	182	78	44	70	8.3	21	21	1.2
2	54	100	15	39	66	6.1	20	20	1.1
3	54	100	15	36	60	5.8	20	19	1.0
4	58	150	23	33	59	5.3	20	19	1.0
5	70	150	28	35	52	4.9	22	19	1.1
6	989	5530	39400	31	48	4.0	20	18	.97
7	338	1910	2330	30	43	3.5	20	18	.97
8	255	1490	1510	29	42	3.3	19	17	.87
9	134	400	145	29	42	3.3	19	17	.87
10	93	250	63	28	40	3.0	19	17	.87
11	73	160	32	27	40	2.9	19	17	.87
12	65	130	23	59	150	24	25	15	1.0
13	61	120	20	33	40	3.6	19	15	.77
14	58	120	19	45	100	12	18	14	.68
15	57	120	18	85	200	46	18	10	.49
16	56	110	17	51	100	14	17	8	.37
17	58	110	17	43	70	8.1	17	8	.37
18	81	200	44	73	150	30	17	8	.37
19	59	120	19	47	120	15	17	8	.37
20	54	110	16	42	70	7.9	17	8	.37
21	53	100	14	52	120	17	17	8	.37
22	52	100	14	34	50	4.6	16	8	.35
23	152	844	956	30	40	3.2	16	7	.30
24	131	548	277	27	35	2.6	18	7	.34
25	85	300	69	25	30	2.0	18	6	.29
26	137	824	1870	24	29	1.9	17	7	.32
27	82	200	44	23	29	1.8	16	7	.30
28	67	200	36	21	26	1.5	17	7	.32
29	95	250	64	21	25	1.4	16	7	.30
30	60	100	16	22	22	1.3	15	8	.32
31	60	70	11	---	---	---	15	8	.32
TOTAL	3702	---	47203	1118	---	248.3	565	---	19.14

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	17	7	.32	14	9	.34	8.0	4	.09
2	17	7	.32	13	7	.25	8.0	4	.09
3	18	7	.34	25	127	57	8.2	4	.09
4	21	5	.28	19	15	.77	9.0	4	.10
5	17	5	.23	17	12	.55	10	5	.14
6	15	4	.16	14	10	.38	8.4	5	.11
7	15	6	.24	14	9	.34	7.8	4	.08
8	15	8	.32	13	8	.28	7.4	4	.08
9	27	9	.66	13	7	.25	7.0	4	.08
10	17	9	.41	12	5	.16	8.0	5	.11
11	14	8	.30	12	4	.13	7.0	5	.09
12	14	7	.26	12	4	.13	6.9	5	.09
13	14	7	.26	11	4	.12	7.6	5	.10
14	13	7	.25	9.0	4	.10	8.2	4	.09
15	13	6	.21	8.2	4	.09	10	4	.11
16	12	6	.19	8.4	4	.09	6.4	4	.07
17	16	8	.35	8.8	3	.80	7.0	4	.08
18	14	7	.26	35	4	.38	6.5	4	.07
19	13	7	.25	25	5	.34	6.4	4	.07
20	13	5	.18	15	5	.20	6.4	4	.07
21	13	5	.18	10	4	.11	6.2	4	.07
22	11	5	.15	9.2	4	.10	6.0	4	.06
23	8.9	5	.12	8.8	4	.10	6.0	4	.06
24	12	5	.16	8.4	4	.09	7.0	5	.09
25	9.0	5	.12	9.0	4	.10	9.1	6	.15
26	8.5	5	.11	8.4	4	.09	9.6	6	.16
27	7.3	5	.10	8.6	4	.09	8.7	6	.14
28	7.6	5	.10	8.4	4	.09	8.8	6	.14
29	18	60	21	---	---	---	26	25	1.8
30	13	12	.42	---	---	---	13	10	.35
31	16	10	.43	---	---	---	12	8	.26
TOTAL	439.3	---	28.68	369.2	---	63.47	266.7	---	5.09
		APRIL		MAY			JUNE		
1	11	8	.24	19	15	.77	25	12	.81
2	9.8	8	.21	13	10	.35	30	12	.97
3	15	9	.36	18	10	.49	23	11	.68
4	20	10	.54	13	10	.35	20	10	.54
5	20	10	.54	12	10	.32	23	9	.56
6	17	8	.37	11	12	.36	20	8	.43
7	13	7	.25	26	92	31	19	7	.36
8	12	7	.23	157	861	3420	17	7	.32
9	9.8	7	.19	42	80	9.1	20	8	.43
10	9.7	8	.21	50	80	11	100	1290	2160
11	9.3	8	.20	67	150	27	20	55	3.0
12	9.2	7	.17	31	40	3.3	17	20	.92
13	8.8	5	.12	251	2210	12400	30	82	23
14	8.8	5	.12	151	1490	9650	32	67	9.1
15	11	5	.15	29	50	3.9	29	54	8.0
16	11	6	.18	18	20	.97	34	93	14
17	10	7	.19	18	15	.73	23	30	1.9
18	10	8	.22	120	747	774	18	25	1.2
19	11	8	.24	29	45	3.5	26	23	1.6
20	11	8	.24	16	18	.78	16	18	.78
21	11	8	.24	15	10	.41	14	12	.45
22	13	8	.28	60	10	1.6	14	8	.30
23	11	9	.27	30	10	.81	13	5	.18
24	11	9	.27	26	8	.56	12	5	.16
25	11	9	.27	24	7	.45	11	4	.12
26	11	9	.27	23	7	.43	11	4	.12
27	13	9	.32	24	7	.45	12	7	.23
28	17	10	.46	22	5	.30	12	7	.23
29	75	478	789	56	10	1.5	12	7	.23
30	48	168	68	22	8	.48	11	5	.15
31	---	---	---	90	457	313	---	---	---
TOTAL	458.4	---	864.35	1483	---	26657.91	664	---	2230.77

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50053050 RIO TURABO AT BORINQUEN, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	12	5	.16	15	3	.12	16	20	.86
2	11	4	.12	15	3	.12	15	18	.73
3	12	5	.16	16	3	.13	14	15	.57
4	10	5	.14	16	3	.13	13	15	.53
5	11	5	.15	15	3	.12	19	15	.77
6	31	129	.49	14	5	.19	13	12	.42
7	13	8	.28	17	10	.46	10	10	.27
8	10	6	.16	23	20	1.2	8.4	10	.23
9	9.5	8	.21	17	5	.23	9.1	10	.25
10	8.3	8	.18	20	8	.43	8.5	10	.23
11	22	20	1.2	44	102	34	8.4	10	.23
12	15	8	.32	24	20	1.3	9.9	12	.32
13	11	5	.15	79	279	132	11	12	.36
14	16	5	.22	68	200	37	9.4	12	.30
15	17	5	.23	40	70	7.6	8.6	11	.26
16	14	5	.19	30	40	3.2	7.9	10	.21
17	12	4	.13	22	25	1.5	7.0	9	.17
18	12	4	.13	19	18	.92	6.8	5	.09
19	11	5	.15	14	10	.38	6.8	5	.09
20	14	6	.23	11	10	.30	6.6	5	.09
21	14	6	.23	9.7	10	.26	6.2	5	.08
22	8.4	5	.11	17	10	.46	6.6	5	.09
23	9.8	5	.13	14	8	.30	8.0	9	.19
24	12	4	.13	18	9	.44	57	209	105
25	13	4	.14	10	8	.22	31	10	.84
26	9.0	3	.07	8.6	8	.19	16	5	.22
27	14	5	.19	6.8	8	.15	11	5	.15
28	17	5	.23	67	794	531	9.5	5	.13
29	12	3	.10	270	1920	4760	8.3	5	.11
30	14	3	.11	27	45	3.3	9.2	5	.12
31	16	3	.13	20	20	1.1	---	---	---
TOTAL YEAR	411.0 10834.9	---	55.08 83008.45	987.1	---	5518.75	371.2	---	113.91

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR

LOCATION --Lat 18°14'33", long 66°00'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank 250 ft (76 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 189, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) downstream from Rio Turabo, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) east of Plaza de Caguas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--89.8 mi² (232.6 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1959 (low-flow measurement only), February to November 1959 (monthly measurements only), December 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 143.28 ft (43.672 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGES.--28 years (1961-88), 226 ft³/s (6,400 m³/s), 34.18 in/yr (868 mm/yr), 163,700 acre-ft/yr (202 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 215 ft³/s (6.09 m³/s), 156,000 acre-ft/yr (192 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 71,500 ft³/s (2,020 m³/s), Sept. 6, 1960, gage height, 31.17 ft (9.501 m), from rating curve extended above 6,000 ft³/s (170 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement; minimum daily discharge, 10 ft³/s (0.283 m³/s), Apr. 5, 10, 29, 1968.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 8,000 ft³/s (227 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Nov. 24	1900	16,000	453	16.50	5.029	Aug. 24	1545	21,400	606	18.36	5.596
Nov. 27	0545	*28,900	818	*20.65	6.294	Aug. 25	0845	10,600	300	14.22	4.334
Dec. 7	1830	28,000	793	20.37	6.209	Sept.11	1230	13,800	391	15.60	4.755
July 2	0715	15,300	433	16.23	4.947						

Minimum discharge, 18 ft³/s (0.510 m³/s), Oct. 13, 14.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	131	103	439	705	174	e138	62	53	48	657	129	194
2	73	91	636	486	186	e129	60	59	44	4220	108	e170
3	95	79	357	328	331	e113	59	39	42	396	119	e160
4	119	101	326	300	189	101	59	33	40	199	200	e150
5	83	250	296	394	163	94	58	33	37	142	111	e145
6	64	354	394	349	173	93	101	124	36	228	94	e140
7	57	165	7030	294	141	90	104	80	36	1210	171	e130
8	44	115	4480	286	140	89	63	42	35	240	139	139
9	47	93	776	294	147	85	59	37	47	167	101	292
10	48	86	540	304	168	80	53	161	52	256	1090	326
11	29	77	448	300	133	80	55	122	40	203	983	3810
12	25	76	381	312	140	82	50	83	41	187	262	2560
13	24	81	332	271	e385	81	52	58	48	141	168	834
14	136	65	301	297	e155	89	48	55	47	281	134	646
15	250	64	289	223	e147	76	65	66	409	132	129	437
16	236	92	274	203	e140	73	98	52	348	117	138	367
17	812	143	252	204	e123	74	137	50	117	107	229	291
18	3160	124	238	189	e123	72	114	60	69	179	477	255
19	711	92	315	186	e116	70	63	53	60	162	172	472
20	234	82	406	176	e129	88	43	92	185	128	133	310
21	160	66	376	165	e115	82	39	101	194	100	119	231
22	125	60	587	157	e112	72	42	86	199	223	328	208
23	111	108	322	153	e110	66	36	54	157	169	587	196
24	109	7860	281	153	e121	63	41	47	105	134	4290	192
25	127	1650	270	149	e117	66	37	43	208	111	2620	180
26	159	2990	249	149	e300	74	34	42	185	132	533	166
27	162	14500	263	147	e400	116	46	46	151	122	373	160
28	259	2890	273	153	e150	112	36	43	81	284	360	153
29	189	905	256	153	e145	96	31	53	80	254	324	150
30	123	554	222	159	---	75	35	75	198	281	255	144
31	104	---	514	140	---	70	---	75	---	162	211	---
TOTAL	8006	33916	22123	7779	4973	2689	1780	2017	3339	11324	15087	13608
MEAN	258	1131	714	251	171	86.7	59.3	65.1	111	365	487	454
MAX	3160	14500	7030	705	400	138	137	161	409	4220	4290	3810
MIN	24	60	222	140	110	63	31	33	35	100	94	130
AC-FT	15880	67270	43880	15430	9860	5330	3530	4000	6620	22460	29930	26990
CFSM	2.88	12.6	7.95	2.79	1.91	.97	.66	.72	1.24	4.07	5.42	5.05
IN.	3.32	14.05	9.16	3.22	2.06	1.11	.74	.84	1.38	4.69	6.25	5.64

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 110674 MEAN 303 MAX 14500 MIN 19 AC-FT 219500 CFSM 3.38 IN. 45.85
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 126641 MEAN 346 MAX 14500 MIN 24 AC-FT 251200 CFSM 3.85 IN. 52.46

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./ 100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
05...	0955	89	216	7.60	28.0	22	6.4	81	20	K19000	K1100
DEC 07...	0930	272	281	6.30	25.5	15	7.7	93	16	K15000	2100
FEB 1988											
12...	1005	131	220	7.00	25.0	29	7.2	87	13	50000	2800
APR 06...	1045	58	272	7.70	27.0	35	6.8	85	11	9400	450
JUN 03...	0945	42	278	7.40	29.5	28	6.5	85	28	5300	320
AUG 05...	1015	113	209	6.50	26.5	97	7.6	94	<10	60000	K1400

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
05...	64	0	16	5.9	19	1	2.8	85	<0.5	14	16
DEC 07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	52	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	69	--	--	--
APR 06...	77	0	18	7.7	23	1	1.7	84	<0.5	18	20
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	83	--	--	--
AUG 05...	61	0	15	5.7	17	1	1.8	56	--	12	14

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
05...	0.10	29	154	37	25	0.62	0.08	0.70	0.13	0.37
DEC 07...	--	--	--	--	4	1.34	0.06	1.40	0.12	0.68
FEB 1988										
12...	--	--	--	--	39	0.43	0.07	0.50	0.17	0.33
APR 06...	0.20	33	171	27	54	0.52	0.08	0.60	0.19	0.41
JUN 03...	--	--	--	--	43	0.61	0.09	0.70	0.15	0.15
AUG 05...	0.10	29	135	41	157	0.42	0.08	0.50	0.20	0.50

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1983 to September 1986.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-49 and automatic sediment sampler.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 7,470 mg/L May 13, 1986; Minimum daily mean, 11 mg/L August 12, 1985.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 290,000 tons (263,090 tonnes) May 13, 1986; Minimum daily mean, 1.3 tons (1.2) July 14, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1984-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1984	1,860 (Nov. 05)	19 (several days)	91,400 (Nov. 05)	1.6 (April 25)
1985	2,870 (May 18)	11 (August 12)	115,000 (May 18)	1.3 (July 14)
1986	7,470 (May 13)	22 (several days)	290,000 (May 13)	2.1 (several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)									
										OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
										1	340	253	361	187	136	176	100	75
2	181	125	61	193	178	195	1330	672	6680									
3	277	208	312	110	90	27	219	160	95									
4	165	140	62	2390	1090	10300	139	100	38									
5	122	95	31	6500	1860	91400	122	95	31									
6	110	85	25	1700	796	8640	165	95	42									
7	110	80	24	400	270	292	127	92	32									
8	109	80	24	286	190	147	114	88	27									
9	150	123	58	225	165	100	105	82	23									
10	122	90	30	194	145	76	103	82	23									
11	104	82	23	175	130	61	108	80	23									
12	108	80	23	160	120	52	98	75	20									
13	115	85	27	150	112	45	90	70	17									
14	137	95	35	141	108	41	86	65	15									
15	117	98	33	136	105	39	87	65	15									
16	150	119	55	140	105	40	91	68	17									
17	110	90	27	131	100	35	91	70	17									
18	103	90	25	124	95	32	94	72	18									
19	151	130	67	122	92	30	86	70	16									
20	99	85	23	116	90	28	82	65	14									
21	113	85	22	110	88	26	82	65	14									
22	137	105	38	107	85	25	80	70	15									
23	94	78	20	103	81	23	88	72	17									
24	84	70	16	102	80	22	79	65	14									
25	81	65	14	102	80	22	75	60	12									
26	87	62	15	100	78	21	75	61	12									
27	79	60	13	97	75	20	80	62	13									
28	74	60	12	96	73	19	82	65	14									
29	86	70	16	93	75	19	82	63	14									
30	136	92	34	103	75	21	100	88	28									
31	121	85	28	---	---	---	114	104	38									
TOTAL	3972	---	1554	14593	---	111974	4374	---	7374									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	124	90	30	66	55	9.8	89	70	17
2	83	70	16	67	55	9.9	85	68	16
3	73	61	12	67	60	11	82	68	15
4	75	60	12	85	70	16	82	68	15
5	74	70	14	82	70	15	77	66	13
6	70	59	11	81	65	14	81	66	14
7	70	59	11	77	63	13	76	65	13
8	71	59	11	72	62	12	74	60	12
9	72	59	11	109	93	33	78	70	15
10	93	62	16	137	115	46	81	70	15
11	74	65	13	125	95	32	70	65	12
12	67	63	11	293	176	592	66	60	11
13	354	237	669	951	588	2610	67	56	10
14	340	236	313	307	170	141	86	58	13
15	143	110	42	1830	803	18100	72	52	10
16	107	90	26	2300	841	11700	70	50	9.5
17	131	105	37	324	180	157	70	50	9.5
18	122	110	36	211	150	85	75	50	10
19	115	100	31	166	125	56	63	50	8.5
20	207	128	87	142	110	42	58	50	7.8
21	135	105	38	129	95	33	56	50	7.6
22	109	90	26	119	90	29	59	50	8.0
23	98	84	22	110	88	26	71	55	11
24	86	70	16	104	82	23	63	45	7.7
25	107	70	20	100	79	21	55	30	4.5
26	87	70	16	98	76	20	53	20	2.9
27	87	70	16	97	75	20	52	20	2.8
28	83	68	15	94	75	19	49	20	2.6
29	77	65	14	91	70	17	48	22	2.9
30	71	60	12	---	---	---	48	22	2.9
31	68	55	10	---	---	---	47	22	2.8
TOTAL	3473	---	1614	8434	---	33902.7	2103	---	302.0
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	48	22	2.9	34	30	2.8	158	98	42
2	44	22	2.6	33	30	2.7	124	100	33
3	46	22	2.7	33	30	2.7	85	78	18
4	44	25	3.0	34	30	2.8	97	67	18
5	47	25	3.2	34	30	2.8	72	65	13
6	50	25	3.4	33	30	2.7	262	192	210
7	51	26	3.6	36	31	3.0	668	428	1110
8	46	25	3.1	35	31	2.9	343	220	204
9	43	22	2.6	35	35	3.3	198	170	91
10	44	22	2.6	44	38	4.5	4100	1300	47900
11	46	22	2.7	42	32	3.6	443	260	311
12	45	25	3.0	36	33	3.2	239	190	123
13	41	22	2.4	67	55	16	445	377	799
14	38	21	2.2	71	52	10	255	140	96
15	38	21	2.2	50	53	10	173	115	54
16	35	20	1.9	39	35	3.7	270	192	313
17	35	21	2.0	32	31	2.7	264	210	150
18	35	21	2.0	30	20	1.6	153	112	46
19	34	20	1.8	31	21	1.8	150	110	45
20	34	20	1.8	30	20	1.6	131	105	37
21	38	20	2.1	30	20	1.6	116	90	28
22	42	20	2.3	30	20	1.6	105	82	23
23	35	19	1.8	63	56	15	95	78	20
24	34	19	1.7	55	42	6.2	90	78	19
25	31	19	1.6	80	65	19	87	71	17
26	40	20	2.2	202	144	138	86	70	16
27	80	50	26	136	120	44	81	70	15
28	104	70	20	139	114	51	77	68	14
29	46	32	4.0	102	83	23	95	68	17
30	37	31	3.1	713	428	1230	103	75	21
31	---	---	---	245	160	106	---	---	---
TOTAL	1331	---	116.5	2574	---	1719.8	9565	---	51803

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	120	101	38	94	88	56	90	78	19
2	142	95	36	247	180	120	93	55	14
3	90	78	19	100	90	24	84	45	10
4	380	359	2090	277	205	347	148	100	51
5	1900	666	5820	172	130	60	408	234	740
6	276	180	134	100	82	22	283	120	92
7	171	130	60	87	65	15	113	80	24
8	138	105	39	77	62	13	87	68	16
9	132	100	36	74	50	10	93	70	18
10	121	100	33	72	49	9.5	131	90	41
11	110	95	28	68	48	8.8	133	140	67
12	102	88	24	65	50	8.8	176	118	65
13	92	82	20	62	149	25	319	174	250
14	116	114	49	61	52	8.6	957	901	4230
15	131	105	37	61	53	8.7	253	165	113
16	92	80	20	73	53	10	322	195	283
17	83	70	16	65	52	9.1	781	373	1800
18	79	69	15	58	50	7.8	983	379	1640
19	76	65	13	56	49	7.4	716	201	440
20	79	65	14	61	48	7.9	1720	949	12500
21	86	65	15	66	45	8.0	673	490	890
22	102	65	18	57	45	6.9	326	220	194
23	104	65	18	55	42	6.2	243	170	112
24	85	65	15	53	42	6.0	197	140	74
25	77	65	14	50	42	5.7	173	125	58
26	73	62	12	128	90	99	157	115	49
27	82	62	14	300	173	160	146	105	41
28	71	62	12	111	90	27	152	105	43
29	89	60	14	76	68	14	135	105	38
30	172	126	72	436	282	1130	177	115	55
31	93	82	21	149	120	48	---	---	---
TOTAL	5464	---	8766	3411	---	2289.4	10314	---	23967
YEAR	69608		245382.4						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TOMS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TOMS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TOMS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TOMS/DAY)
1	152	49	20	456	265	483	166	122	55
2	132	21	7.5	1180	560	3510	423	256	491
3	155	62	33	5950	2360	56100	287	203	188
4	155	46	21	1960	951	5780	193	148	77
5	143	43	26	4120	1740	29900	176	150	71
6	207	93	70	3790	1630	21900	168	150	44
7	145	59	23	2700	934	9260	159	153	66
8	151	45	18	1150	340	1090	165	160	71
9	930	432	3440	890	366	1080	209	213	136
10	392	217	258	621	148	257	189	188	96
11	243	128	84	434	112	131	334	262	453
12	179	91	44	363	92	90	225	255	170
13	265	129	137	320	80	69	167	219	99
14	1180	561	3190	434	144	240	144	190	74
15	331	151	139	483	251	343	141	194	74
16	254	145	107	308	92	77	158	195	83
17	335	150	132	290	79	62	165	187	83
18	195	70	37	267	156	112	140	181	68
19	169	51	2.2	241	144	94	135	180	66
20	161	52	23	226	149	91	146	176	69
21	184	70	36	214	151	87	126	168	57
22	177	50	19	211	156	89	121	160	52
23	143	39	15	237	179	115	118	160	51
24	129	30	10	214	159	92	137	160	59
25	221	86	58	195	145	76	183	159	79
26	236	99	71	327	225	229	167	129	58
27	221	105	65	200	150	81	159	128	55
28	217	96	63	187	138	70	162	125	55
29	193	75	43	180	132	64	132	105	37
30	473	237	761	172	131	61	152	116	48
31	220	168	111	---	---	---	144	106	41
TOTAL	8288	---	9063.7	28320	---	131633	5491	---	3126

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	129	105	37	68	82	15	100	93	25
2	224	165	107	71	87	17	75	62	14
3	146	110	43	65	89	16	77	60	12
4	174	173	84	59	88	14	68	58	11
5	143	116	45	59	85	14	66	56	10
6	141	110	38	57	85	13	91	120	38
7	128	111	38	55	84	12	208	143	85
8	115	110	34	56	83	13	220	149	95
9	110	109	32	55	84	12	107	82	24
10	113	108	33	54	84	12	81	62	14
11	109	102	30	55	82	12	68	56	10
12	101	99	27	56	80	12	65	52	9.1
13	97	90	24	54	80	12	69	59	11
14	92	89	22	62	80	13	61	55	9.1
15	94	91	23	76	83	17	58	48	7.5
16	87	83	19	75	81	16	58	50	7.8
17	86	82	19	60	80	13	58	52	8.1
18	84	82	19	57	68	10	219	160	148
19	88	89	21	73	70	14	105	92	31
20	82	80	18	107	82	24	69	23	4.3
21	80	79	17	75	62	13	60	72	12
22	75	77	16	66	58	10	59	71	11
23	76	76	16	62	50	8.4	57	69	11
24	77	79	21	66	55	9.8	54	68	9.9
25	73	82	16	66	55	9.8	51	66	9.1
26	85	87	20	68	59	11	51	66	9.1
27	80	88	19	229	230	171	53	65	9.3
28	74	84	17	166	240	91	60	71	12
29	69	83	15	---	---	---	1410	649	3930
30	66	82	15	---	---	---	236	182	145
31	65	82	14	---	---	---	315	241	247
TOTAL	3163	---	899	2072	---	605.0	4329	---	4979.3
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	127	100	34	132	108	38	155	73	31
2	93	76	19	124	96	32	147	51	20
3	83	67	15	124	95	32	142	32	12
4	76	60	12	126	97	33	136	30	11
5	74	59	12	123	92	31	131	28	9.9
6	76	62	13	121	92	30	127	23	7.9
7	83	70	16	117	91	29	125	20	6.8
8	81	69	15	118	92	29	127	21	7.2
9	70	60	11	119	92	30	124	20	6.7
10	63	55	9.4	132	103	37	120	22	7.1
11	67	56	10	142	113	43	111	21	6.3
12	72	61	12	178	142	68	114	25	7.7
13	79	69	15	189	162	70	97	26	6.8
14	76	61	13	1070	569	2290	92	28	7.0
15	68	58	11	3280	1940	47500	88	29	6.9
16	111	89	27	1500	820	5020	87	30	7.0
17	103	80	22	5620	2480	77300	84	30	6.8
18	150	111	45	10400	2870	115000	83	35	7.8
19	109	85	25	3170	726	7350	78	40	8.4
20	84	69	16	518	344	481	75	42	8.5
21	119	97	40	374	249	251	76	45	9.2
22	131	102	47	303	212	173	71	55	11
23	1680	624	7160	262	183	129	70	60	11
24	1100	564	2110	237	170	109	69	67	12
25	864	569	3400	225	170	103	67	71	13
26	433	301	412	207	169	94	66	80	14
27	238	166	107	192	162	84	63	82	14
28	184	134	67	184	151	75	56	88	13
29	155	122	51	173	147	69	57	81	12
30	144	113	44	163	122	54	52	75	11
31	---	---	---	157	99	42	---	---	---
TOTAL	6793	---	13790.4	29780	---	256626	2890	---	313.0

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	56	72	11	90	20	4.9	122	100	33
2	80	81	17	108	19	5.5	125	105	35
3	72	79	15	94	19	4.8	125	108	36
4	84	82	19	82	21	4.6	81	69	15
5	62	73	12	74	20	2.9	119	97	56
6	49	69	9.1	73	20	3.9	99	87	23
7	43	62	7.2	87	21	4.9	64	55	9.5
8	39	59	6.2	75	21	4.3	147	100	72
9	39	53	5.6	72	19	3.7	235	179	143
10	26	42	2.9	63	16	2.7	92	75	19
11	37	41	4.1	59	15	2.4	85	71	16
12	30	31	2.5	55	11	1.6	1270	787	15700
13	30	22	1.8	167	90	41	1970	1160	10400
14	23	21	1.3	130	71	25	707	420	850
15	270	203	331	99	50	13	492	320	432
16	531	411	1030	75	30	6.1	318	218	187
17	787	574	4320	62	22	3.7	264	190	135
18	224	162	98	62	28	4.7	237	174	111
19	139	110	41	69	32	6.0	220	164	97
20	375	258	352	54	41	6.0	209	159	90
21	189	120	61	63	46	7.8	197	148	79
22	135	80	29	61	54	8.9	188	140	71
23	117	70	22	51	58	8.0	193	140	73
24	180	114	64	48	56	7.3	312	259	286
25	155	92	39	56	57	8.6	1650	894	7530
26	217	128	88	79	67	14	465	317	424
27	141	82	31	502	312	643	368	259	301
28	147	83	33	525	343	629	392	266	319
29	153	80	33	167	130	59	305	211	174
30	116	61	19	112	90	27	261	188	132
31	97	39	10	98	81	21	---	---	---
TOTAL	4643	---	6715.7	3412	---	1585.3	11312	---	37848.5
YEAR	110493		467184.9						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	329	209	236	456	300	369	185	140	70
2	411	269	375	376	250	254	176	140	67
3	379	189	191	334	230	207	172	140	65
4	461	285	425	308	210	175	164	130	58
5	749	456	1020	314	220	187	202	150	82
6	8560	4270	171000	285	200	154	198	160	86
7	7600	2240	99600	258	180	125	180	130	63
8	2190	1050	8900	244	160	105	161	130	57
9	908	550	1350	238	160	103	164	125	55
10	672	370	671	226	155	95	165	125	56
11	530	348	498	221	160	95	167	120	54
12	447	320	386	335	317	548	193	120	63
13	396	290	310	447	306	435	180	150	73
14	363	260	255	457	306	508	157	120	51
15	338	250	228	1630	841	8320	153	120	50
16	323	245	214	581	400	627	146	120	47
17	398	312	402	352	255	316	135	120	44
18	675	507	1340	1270	746	4470	138	125	47
19	455	320	393	391	280	296	147	120	48
20	319	225	194	358	420	1780	153	120	51
21	297	220	176	893	396	806	136	100	37
22	289	272	215	310	220	184	133	105	38
23	2020	1340	15200	273	200	52	130	110	39
24	2760	1360	13700	253	170	116	140	110	42
25	1060	668	2930	234	165	104	130	110	39
26	1450	849	9960	223	160	96	132	100	36
27	807	470	1020	215	160	93	117	100	32
28	512	343	570	204	150	83	118	100	32
29	1260	701	3590	197	140	74	113	100	31
30	552	300	447	194	140	73	111	100	30
31	944	553	2040	---	---	---	105	100	28
TOTAL	38454	---	337836	12077	---	20850	4701	---	1571

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	117	105	33	101	70	19	61	47	7.7
2	147	110	44	78	58	12	54	45	6.6
3	128	110	38	98	71	21	51	40	5.5
4	156	110	46	143	109	47	53	40	5.7
5	140	105	40	182	80	39	65	38	6.7
6	115	105	33	100	72	19	64	35	6.0
7	105	100	28	83	70	16	57	32	4.9
8	200	105	57	79	65	14	48	32	4.1
9	450	100	121	80	65	14	51	35	4.8
10	190	100	51	68	58	11	51	35	4.8
11	150	100	40	67	55	9.9	57	32	4.9
12	120	100	32	71	57	11	64	50	8.6
13	110	95	28	72	52	10	69	50	6.5
14	100	95	26	61	52	8.6	84	65	15
15	100	97	26	66	52	9.3	195	149	95
16	96	95	25	60	52	8.4	100	85	23
17	156	100	42	60	55	8.9	64	55	9.5
18	140	100	38	77	59	12	54	40	5.8
19	104	70	20	105	80	23	48	35	4.5
20	87	70	16	113	75	23	46	25	3.1
21	105	75	21	76	58	12	44	22	2.6
22	102	70	19	65	52	9.1	39	22	2.3
23	89	80	19	70	52	9.8	36	25	2.4
24	109	90	26	58	51	8.0	37	25	2.5
25	122	90	30	58	51	8.0	35	25	2.4
26	88	80	19	58	50	7.8	61	30	4.9
27	78	70	15	58	46	7.2	57	32	4.9
28	76	70	14	59	46	7.3	40	35	3.8
29	94	70	18	---	---	---	480	253	483
30	102	80	22	---	---	---	180	125	61
31	95	80	21	---	---	---	108	90	26
TOTAL	3971	---	1008	2266	---	405.3	2453	---	828.5
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	142	110	42	278	213	247	222	150	90
2	97	75	20	144	110	43	177	140	67
3	110	98	48	102	90	25	203	130	71
4	238	195	287	98	85	22	160	100	43
5	226	184	146	95	75	19	132	90	32
6	198	105	56	160	129	74	118	80	25
7	98	52	14	545	605	3420	115	70	22
8	162	113	123	1980	1330	32000	135	90	33
9	193	149	106	630	558	2180	363	244	453
10	83	62	14	1060	504	3150	946	478	2820
11	61	55	9.1	1310	685	3380	203	150	82
12	52	50	7.0	308	205	170	160	120	52
13	48	48	6.2	2870	7470	290000	249	190	229
14	44	40	4.8	1320	671	3590	280	197	165
15	51	40	5.5	457	250	308	178	175	90
16	87	80	19	292	200	158	245	200	132
17	57	48	7.4	238	190	122	194	120	63
18	37	35	3.5	1940	1040	11600	168	120	54
19	33	31	2.8	482	225	293	222	180	108
20	93	82	52	296	200	160	174	115	54
21	62	60	10	266	200	144	147	105	42
22	39	40	4.2	289	256	260	132	100	36
23	42	38	4.3	206	140	78	126	100	34
24	33	35	3.1	180	120	58	126	95	32
25	32	35	2.7	160	115	50	108	90	26
26	28	31	2.3	150	110	45	103	89	25
27	39	35	3.7	138	110	41	126	90	31
28	124	90	30	132	100	36	121	90	29
29	1830	1640	22600	180	150	73	108	85	25
30	460	417	1130	163	120	53	100	82	22
31	---	---	---	1040	714	7570	---	---	---
TOTAL	4799	---	24763.6	17509	---	359369	5841	---	4987

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	103	82	23	76	50	10	165	120	53
2	103	82	23	83	50	11	247	190	127
3	103	81	23	67	49	8.9	117	82	26
4	93	80	20	66	49	8.7	101	80	22
5	88	74	18	65	49	8.6	143	85	33
6	179	117	71	54	50	7.3	109	88	26
7	129	120	42	61	50	8.2	99	80	21
8	98	90	24	146	94	42	83	65	15
9	85	75	17	68	62	11	78	60	13
10	80	69	15	62	65	11	75	46	9.3
11	118	91	39	218	154	119	65	50	8.8
12	155	100	42	113	70	21	61	50	8.2
13	100	80	22	131	87	53	64	50	8.6
14	100	80	22	241	159	121	84	55	12
15	121	100	33	115	75	23	55	45	6.7
16	121	90	29	82	55	12	46	40	5.0
17	95	75	19	63	45	7.7	41	38	4.2
18	89	70	17	55	40	5.9	34	32	2.9
19	81	65	14	52	40	5.6	29	28	2.2
20	77	65	14	46	38	4.7	29	27	2.1
21	90	65	16	43	38	4.4	31	25	2.1
22	75	65	13	46	45	5.6	37	30	3.0
23	67	65	12	115	90	28	61	50	8.2
24	65	60	11	94	85	22	549	338	1130
25	69	59	11	81	60	13	350	250	236
26	66	52	9.3	58	50	7.8	211	170	97
27	65	50	8.8	49	43	5.7	130	90	32
28	76	50	10	136	85	31	89	70	17
29	66	50	8.9	2940	1320	18800	63	55	9.4
30	99	70	23	316	150	128	54	45	6.6
31	136	71	28	215	120	70	---	---	---
TOTAL	2992	---	678.0	5957	---	19615.1	3300	---	1947.3
YEAR	104320		773858.8						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	60	35	5.7	76	43	8.8	119	65	21
2	55	32	4.8	86	48	11	121	62	20
3	49	29	3.8	86	48	11	156	80	34
4	49	29	3.8	85	48	11	155	80	33
5	44	27	3.2	164	89	48	150	70	28
6	44	27	3.2	232	129	109	124	65	22
7	49	30	2.3	239	128	89	189	90	46
8	50	30	4.1	330	176	186	132	50	18
9	185	89	68	198	109	61	140	50	19
10	169	92	47	191	87	42	152	80	33
11	89	55	13	412	215	325	333	150	181
12	96	45	12	2860	1080	14800	220	115	68
13	64	40	6.9	887	434	1470	169	90	41
14	82	45	10	340	125	126	215	115	67
15	85	45	10	374	197	237	160	85	37
16	319	158	220	655	336	1280	185	95	47
17	159	84	36	954	454	2500	139	80	30
18	105	57	16	446	226	329	131	70	25
19	80	45	9.7	248	110	74	112	65	20
20	64	37	6.4	198	80	43	116	68	21
21	59	34	5.4	177	65	31	121	70	23
22	176	93	44	170	52	24	100	60	16
23	99	54	14	158	45	19	91	52	13
24	142	76	29	140	38	14	86	48	11
25	311	160	134	167	60	27	108	55	16
26	219	114	67	167	90	41	99	55	15
27	162	86	38	269	131	118	100	55	15
28	120	65	21	159	80	34	171	85	39
29	88	49	12	150	75	30	112	65	20
30	86	48	11	143	70	27	95	50	13
31	83	46	10	---	---	---	96	50	13
TOTAL	3442	---	871.3	10761	---	22125.8	4397	---	1005

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	84	48	11	174	110	52	70	38	7.2
2	80	45	9.7	118	70	22	68	38	7.0
3	78	42	8.8	100	60	16	84	45	10
4	81	50	11	88	52	12	173	80	37
5	223	112	83	88	48	11	205	100	55
6	179	104	62	95	45	12	97	55	14
7	336	160	178	85	45	10	76	40	8.2
8	232	114	103	74	45	9.0	63	35	6.0
9	206	123	81	71	42	8.1	59	32	5.1
10	119	65	21	69	38	7.1	58	32	5.0
11	109	55	16	732	340	1000	54	32	4.7
12	100	50	13	163	140	62	132	70	25
13	89	45	11	638	293	1080	68	35	6.4
14	89	45	11	350	189	225	57	31	4.8
15	140	60	23	315	161	166	55	32	4.8
16	100	55	15	152	80	33	90	55	13
17	86	48	11	126	70	24	166	100	45
18	92	50	12	113	65	20	104	65	18
19	83	46	10	98	59	16	60	30	4.9
20	79	45	9.6	88	50	12	45	28	3.4
21	81	46	10	80	45	9.7	42	22	2.5
22	74	39	7.8	69	40	7.5	40	21	2.3
23	158	90	38	70	40	8.0	35	20	1.9
24	150	80	32	70	35	6.6	29	16	1.3
25	102	57	16	69	35	6.5	47	19	2.4
26	88	47	11	66	32	5.7	35	18	1.7
27	78	42	8.8	94	38	9.6	27	12	.87
28	72	40	7.8	80	40	8.6	24	12	.78
29	72	40	7.8	---	---	---	24	12	.78
30	483	262	503	---	---	---	21	11	.62
31	202	108	66	---	---	---	20	11	.59
TOTAL	4145	---	1408.3	4335	---	2859.4	2128	---	300.24

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	20	11	.59	24	12	.78	80	35	7.6
2	19	10	.51	43	20	2.3	71	30	5.8
3	22	11	.65	55	30	4.5	134	81	56
4	21	11	.62	76	45	9.2	173	100	65
5	40	25	2.7	52	35	4.9	97	55	14
6	111	55	31	208	104	75	82	48	11
7	157	68	41	71	40	7.7	95	50	13
8	48	27	3.5	34	20	1.8	85	25	5.7
9	31	18	1.5	31	18	1.5	100	40	11
10	22	15	.89	29	17	1.3	80	40	8.6
11	37	20	2.0	76	40	8.2	100	40	11
12	595	284	1060	180	90	44	60	38	6.2
13	366	203	295	70	45	8.5	95	50	13
14	315	156	138	51	35	4.8	80	45	9.7
15	207	110	61	31	19	1.6	290	173	271
16	125	58	20	25	12	.81	270	122	111
17	109	55	16	22	12	.71	95	58	15
18	91	45	11	27	12	.87	100	50	13
19	71	30	5.8	338	148	489	270	135	128
20	54	25	3.6	379	174	203	2340	902	9670
21	45	22	2.7	1360	537	3890	3240	1590	32500
22	42	22	2.5	544	271	471	4000	1050	20600
23	41	21	2.3	277	149	133	690	160	166
24	37	20	2.0	206	104	63	331	160	166
25	28	17	1.3	225	152	177	319	140	121
26	28	16	1.2	471	202	297	254	120	82
27	24	12	.78	276	137	104	334	180	162
28	24	12	.78	162	80	35	284	140	107
29	24	12	.78	124	60	20	333	180	162
30	23	12	.75	102	48	13	314	160	136
31	---	---	---	89	40	9.6	---	---	---
TOTAL	2777	---	1710.45	5658	---	6083.07	14849	---	64647.6

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	213	120	69	269	169	163	180	90	44
2	202	100	55	145	50	20	141	70	27
3	210	110	62	452	182	386	110	55	16
4	201	161	233	222	120	72	81	40	8.7
5	467	207	383	198	120	64	100	50	13
6	221	60	36	166	80	36	64	38	6.6
7	204	100	55	116	60	19	58	35	5.5
8	201	100	54	100	50	13	90	55	13
9	172	90	42	100	50	13	9	37	6.9
10	185	90	45	95	45	12	85	40	9.2
11	168	80	36	84	46	10	84	40	9.1
12	148	80	32	76	45	9.2	64	32	5.5
13	139	70	26	74	40	8.0	50	30	4.1
14	134	70	25	82	40	8.9	104	55	15
15	394	210	383	124	80	27	65	35	6.1
16	206	66	43	143	70	27	56	25	3.8
17	155	40	17	103	55	15	119	59	46
18	130	40	14	117	65	21	176	98	61
19	120	35	11	136	70	26	415	215	556
20	107	30	8.7	154	80	33	148	80	32
21	436	217	497	120	70	23	58	35	5.5
22	165	120	53	89	50	12	144	70	27
23	115	70	22	81	45	9.8	92	50	12
24	95	70	18	75	42	8.5	106	55	16
25	130	70	25	70	38	7.2	70	40	7.6
26	135	80	29	89	40	9.6	45	27	3.3
27	136	70	26	69	35	6.5	35	25	2.4
28	156	70	29	60	32	5.2	32	22	1.9
29	120	70	23	60	32	5.2	97	50	13
30	115	80	25	59	30	4.8	118	60	19
31	272	148	195	101	55	15	---	---	---
TOTAL	5852	---	2571.7	3829	---	1089.9	3056	---	996.2

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	131	62	22	103	28	7.8	439	195	231
2	73	35	6.9	91	27	6.6	636	321	982
3	95	50	13	79	27	5.8	357	180	174
4	119	60	19	101	48	13	326	160	141
5	83	40	9.0	250	119	134	296	160	128
6	64	30	5.2	354	174	231	394	200	213
7	57	29	4.5	165	80	36	7030	2470	134000
8	44	25	3.0	115	65	20	4480	1220	34300
9	47	25	3.2	93	55	14	776	200	419
10	48	25	3.2	86	45	10	540	200	292
11	29	20	1.6	77	45	9.4	448	190	230
12	25	15	1.0	76	40	8.2	381	180	185
13	24	12	.78	81	50	11	332	170	152
14	136	73	39	65	40	7.0	301	150	122
15	250	122	129	64	37	6.4	289	150	117
16	236	129	99	92	50	12	274	150	111
17	812	363	908	143	65	25	252	140	95
18	3160	1120	14400	124	60	20	238	125	80
19	711	343	1090	92	50	12	315	150	128
20	234	125	79	82	40	8.9	406	190	208
21	160	85	37	66	38	6.8	376	190	193
22	125	65	22	60	35	5.7	587	220	349
23	111	58	17	108	60	17	322	170	148
24	109	60	18	7860	2590	71500	281	140	106
25	127	70	24	1650	799	6780	270	140	102
26	159	85	36	2990	1210	21600	249	130	87
27	162	85	37	14500	4880	227000	263	140	99
28	259	131	71	2890	1210	12700	273	140	103
29	189	80	41	905	405	1120	256	140	97
30	123	30	10	554	230	344	222	110	66
31	104	28	7.9	---	---	---	514	268	551
TOTAL	8006	---	17157.28	33916	---	341671.6	22123	---	174209

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	705	338	869	174	95	45	138	45	17
2	486	210	276	186	90	45	129	60	21
3	328	70	62	331	175	183	113	30	9.2
4	300	40	32	189	95	48	101	30	8.2
5	394	120	128	163	80	35	94	20	5.1
6	349	200	188	173	90	42	93	18	4.5
7	294	150	119	141	75	29	90	15	3.6
8	286	160	124	140	70	26	89	10	2.4
9	294	120	95	147	75	30	85	10	2.3
10	304	120	98	168	80	36	80	10	2.2
11	300	80	65	133	65	23	80	10	2.2
12	312	150	126	140	60	23	82	10	2.2
13	271	140	102	385	221	358	81	10	2.2
14	297	145	116	155	95	40	89	10	2.4
15	223	110	66	147	80	32	76	10	2.1
16	203	100	55	140	75	28	73	10	2.0
17	204	100	55	123	60	20	74	10	2.0
18	189	95	48	123	50	17	72	10	1.9
19	186	90	45	116	35	11	70	10	1.9
20	176	90	43	129	28	9.8	88	10	2.4
21	165	85	38	115	20	6.2	82	10	2.2
22	157	80	34	112	18	5.4	72	10	1.9
23	153	80	33	110	10	3.0	66	10	1.8
24	153	80	33	121	10	3.3	63	10	1.7
25	149	75	30	117	10	3.2	66	10	1.8
26	149	72	29	300	101	450	74	10	2.0
27	147	72	29	400	170	184	116	20	6.3
28	153	75	31	150	60	24	112	15	4.5
29	153	75	31	145	50	20	96	10	2.6
30	159	80	34	---	---	---	75	10	2.0
31	140	75	28	---	---	---	70	10	1.9
TOTAL	7779	---	3062	4973	---	1779.9	2689	---	125.5

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	62	10	1.7	53	30	4.3	48	30	3.9
2	60	10	1.6	59	25	4.0	44	28	3.3
3	59	10	1.6	39	22	2.3	42	25	2.8
4	59	10	1.6	33	20	1.8	40	25	2.7
5	58	10	1.6	33	20	1.8	37	25	2.5
6	101	40	11	124	70	23	36	22	2.1
7	104	50	14	80	45	9.7	36	21	2.0
8	63	35	6.0	42	25	2.8	35	21	2.0
9	59	32	5.1	37	22	2.2	47	22	2.8
10	53	32	4.6	161	78	95	52	25	3.5
11	55	30	4.5	122	70	23	40	25	2.7
12	50	30	4.1	83	45	10	41	22	2.4
13	52	30	4.2	58	40	6.3	48	22	2.9
14	48	30	3.9	55	32	4.8	47	22	2.8
15	65	35	6.1	66	35	6.2	409	209	337
16	98	45	12	52	32	4.5	348	156	171
17	137	78	70	50	32	4.3	117	65	21
18	114	65	20	60	32	5.2	69	38	7.1
19	63	30	5.1	53	32	4.6	60	30	4.9
20	43	25	2.9	92	35	8.7	185	81	46
21	39	25	2.6	101	50	14	194	104	71
22	42	22	2.5	86	45	10	199	100	56
23	36	21	2.0	54	31	4.5	157	80	36
24	41	21	2.3	47	30	3.8	105	60	17
25	37	22	2.2	43	30	3.5	208	106	110
26	34	20	1.8	42	30	3.4	185	94	64
27	46	20	2.5	46	29	3.6	151	70	29
28	36	20	1.9	43	28	3.3	81	45	9.8
29	31	20	1.7	53	35	5.0	80	38	8.2
30	35	20	1.9	75	40	8.1	198	107	94
31	---	---	---	75	40	8.1	---	---	---
TOTAL	1780	---	203.0	2017	---	291.8	3339	---	1120.4

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055000 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA AT CAGUAS--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	657	346	930	129	65	23	194	95	50
2	4220	2860	66700	108	56	16	170	85	39
3	396	174	208	119	60	19	160	80	35
4	199	100	54	200	100	54	150	70	28
5	142	70	27	111	60	18	145	70	27
6	228	130	106	94	50	13	140	70	26
7	1210	489	2920	171	100	46	130	70	25
8	240	120	78	139	65	24	139	70	26
9	167	80	36	101	55	15	292	124	105
10	256	125	86	1090	716	7830	326	169	231
11	203	100	55	983	663	4260	3810	1360	26700
12	187	100	50	262	100	71	2560	940	8400
13	141	75	29	168	75	34	834	390	924
14	281	140	106	134	70	25	646	220	384
15	132	65	23	129	65	23	437	200	236
16	117	60	19	138	80	30	367	195	193
17	107	60	17	229	136	126	291	150	118
18	179	100	48	477	249	437	255	130	90
19	162	90	39	172	80	37	472	230	454
20	128	65	21	133	70	25	310	160	134
21	100	50	13	119	60	19	231	130	81
22	223	100	60	328	165	300	208	120	67
23	169	85	39	587	296	748	196	100	53
24	134	70	25	4290	1620	61500	192	100	52
25	111	65	19	2620	1180	18300	180	95	46
26	132	65	23	533	259	416	166	90	40
27	122	65	21	373	185	186	160	85	37
28	284	151	350	360	180	175	153	80	33
29	254	129	98	324	170	149	150	80	32
30	281	150	149	255	130	90	144	70	27
31	162	85	37	211	110	63	---	---	---
TOTAL	11324	---	72386	15087	---	95072	13608	---	38693
YEAR	126641		745771.48						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

219

5005250 RIO CAGUITAS AT HIGHWAY 30 AT CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'11", long 66°01'26", at Highway 30 bridge, and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) east of Caguas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--14.1 mi² (36.5 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1972 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
09...	1140	27	492	7.50	29.0	31	3.2	41	63	26000	5900
DEC											
14...	0935	41	500	6.60	25.0	3.8	3.7	45	44	K130000	76000
FEB 1988											
12...	1225	31	557	7.10	27.0	--	2.8	35	--	K750000	70000
APR											
08...	1130	22	583	7.60	28.0	9.3	4.8	61	50	5100	K1200
JUN											
17...	1100	30	408	7.20	30.0	6.2	3.0	39	38	37000	K1800
AUG											
29...	0845	33	522	7.30	28.0	3.0	3.5	44	28	410000	70000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
09...	140	7	35	12	44	2	7.1	130	<0.5	48	41
DEC											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
12...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
APR											
08...	150	0	39	13	44	2	6.2	150	<0.5	58	45
JUN											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
AUG											
29...	150	35	38	13	35	1	6.3	170	--	41	35

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TOMS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
09...	0.80	30	296	21	65	3.70	0.20	3.90	5.9	1.3
DEC										
14...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.83	0.17	1.00	4.8	0.5
FEB 1988										
12...	--	--	--	--	--	0.88	0.22	1.10	8.0	1.4
APR										
08...	0.50	30	331	19	16	0.87	0.23	1.10	8.0	5.0
JUN										
17...	--	--	--	--	13	0.21	0.09	0.30	7.6	1.5
AUG										
29...	0.20	30	267	24	6	0.49	0.11	0.60	5.0	1.6

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

221

50055400 RIO BAIROA NEAR CAGUAS, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'28", long 66°02'13", at bridge on Highway 1, about 2.5 mi (4.0 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) north of Caguas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--5.4 mi² (14.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1962-66, 1973-74, 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATUR-ATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
09...	0840	7.4	390	7.60	25.0	69	4.2	50	66	K1600000	840000
DEC											
14...	1145	7.8	420	7.20	25.0	1.2	6.2	75	50	360000	K120000
FEB 1988											
16...	0900	7.1	378	6.90	22.0	2.2	8.4	95	27	K79000	28000
APR											
22...	0925	4.1	425	7.90	25.0	3.1	7.5	90	<10	2300	K1900
JUN											
17...	0905	3.3	436	7.50	25.5	32	5.1	62	<10	31000	23000
AUG											
29...	1015	6.6	479	7.30	28.0	4.5	3.1	39	55	K3300000	410000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
09...	110	0	26	10	24	1	6.2	120	<0.5	22	28
DEC											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
APR											
22...	160	22	38	15	24	0.9	3.0	130	<0.5	25	37
JUN											
17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG											
29...	140	0	32	15	36	1	5.8	160	--	27	33

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
09...	0.30	22	210	4.2	71	0.94	0.06	1.00	6.20	--
DEC										
14...	--	--	--	--	<1	1.55	0.05	1.60	1.30	1.0
FEB 1988										
16...	--	--	--	--	1	0.98	0.12	1.10	7.10	6.9
APR										
22...	0.20	30	253	2.8	25	1.48	0.02	1.50	0.07	--
JUN										
17...	--	--	--	--	13	1.07	0.03	1.10	0.20	0.40
AUG										
29...	0.20	28	273	4.9	13	0.99	0.11	1.10	5.80	2.4

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1984 to September 1986.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,040 mg/L few days; Minimum daily mean, 0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 777 tons (705 tonnes) October 06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.00 tons (0.00) tonne several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1984-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1984	247 (Sep. 20)	0 (several days)	26 (Sep. 20)	0.00 (several days)
1985	1,040 (May 18)	0 (several days)	702 (May 18)	0.00 (several days)
1986	1,040 (Oct. 06)	0 (several days)	777 (Oct. 06)	0.00 (several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	---	---	---	.00	---	---	.00	0	.00			
2	---	---	---	.00	---	---	.00	0	.00			
3	---	---	---	.00	---	---	.00	0	.00			
4	---	---	---	.00	---	---	.00	0	.00			
5	---	---	---	.00	---	---	.00	0	.00			
6	---	---	---	.00	---	---	.00	0	.00			
7	---	---	---	.17	13	.02	.00	0	.00			
8	---	---	---	.03	3	.00	.00	0	.00			
9	---	---	---	.30	14	.03	.00	0	.00			
10	---	---	---	.33	16	.01	.00	0	.00			
11	---	---	---	.32	16	.01	.00	0	.00			
12	---	---	---	.35	20	.02	.00	0	.00			
13	---	---	---	1.5	50	.43	.00	0	.00			
14	---	---	---	.59	33	.05	.00	0	.00			
15	---	---	---	2.2	64	2.0	.00	0	.00			
16	---	---	---	3.3	81	1.1	.00	0	.00			
17	---	---	---	.77	35	.07	.00	0	.00			
18	---	---	---	.44	20	.02	.00	0	.00			
19	---	---	---	.29	17	.01	.00	0	.00			
20	---	---	---	.18	12	.01	.00	0	.00			
21	---	---	---	.10	8	.00	.00	0	.00			
22	---	---	---	.01	1	.00	.00	0	.00			
23	---	---	---	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00			
24	---	---	---	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00			
25	.00	---	---	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00			
26	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00			
27	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00			
28	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00			
29	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00			
30	.00	0	.00	---	---	---	.00	0	.00			
31	.00	0	.00	---	---	---	.00	0	.00			
TOTAL	0.00			10.88	---	3.78	0.00	---	0.00			

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.09	7	.00
2	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.07	4	.00
3	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.03	2	.00
4	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
5	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
6	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
7	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.32	14	.06
8	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.36	20	.02
9	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.19	14	.01
10	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.65	31	.08
11	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.49	10	.01
12	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.28	2	.50
13	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.17	2	.00
14	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.11	2	.00
15	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
16	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
17	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
18	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
19	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
20	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
21	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
22	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
23	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
24	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
25	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
26	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
27	.01	12	.84	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
28	.09	7	.00	.41	21	.06	.00	0	.00
29	.00	0	.00	.05	2	.00	1.2	42	.99
30	.00	0	.00	.16	12	.01	.56	30	.05
31	---	---	---	1.2	41	.72	---	---	---
TOTAL	0.10	---	0.84	1.82	---	0.79	4.52	---	1.72
		JULY		AUGUST		SEPTEMBER			
1	.17	18	.01	.44	12	.15	.00	0	.00
2	.07	5	.00	1.3	48	.22	.00	0	.00
3	.00	0	.00	.49	25	.03	.00	0	.00
4	.95	24	.59	.27	15	.01	.00	0	.00
5	1.9	57	.33	.16	10	.00	.13	7	.01
6	.94	38	.10	.01	1	.00	.15	10	.01
7	.48	23	.03	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
8	.23	13	.01	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
9	.11	7	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
10	.01	1	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
11	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
12	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.34	16	.02
13	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	1.6	45	.95
14	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	1.4	38	.15
15	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.77	32	.07
16	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	5.8	101	7.6
17	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	4.6	108	1.5
18	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	3.5	82	.82
19	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	2.6	47	.33
20	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	17	247	26
21	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	7.0	147	3.0
22	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	2.8	70	.53
23	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	1.4	45	.17
24	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.94	40	.10
25	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.72	30	.06
26	.00	0	.00	7.4	117	15	.58	28	.04
27	.00	0	.00	2.4	69	.77	.47	25	.03
28	.00	0	.00	.52	30	.04	.46	22	.03
29	1.4	28	.71	.27	15	.01	.41	22	.02
30	.56	25	.04	.13	10	.00	.43	20	.02
31	.15	10	.00	.09	7	.00	---	---	---
TOTAL YEAR	6.97 90.87	---	1.82 66.64	13.48	---	16.23	53.10	---	41.46

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.33	20	.02	.48	22	.03	.43	4	.20
2	.50	25	.03	1.0	44	.24	1.4	25	.22
3	1.1	41	.21	12	244	17	.54	6	.01
4	.51	25	.03	12	234	27	.42	2	.60
5	.44	20	.02	31	383	50	.38	2	.00
6	.45	25	.03	68	724	174	.33	2	.00
7	.33	20	.02	41	437	67	.33	2	.00
8	.29	18	.01	17	230	12	.33	2	.00
9	1.8	54	.72	12	220	8.5	.34	2	.00
10	1.6	55	.32	6.3	120	2.0	.33	2	.20
11	1.2	45	.15	3.4	80	.73	.31	2	.50
12	.86	35	.08	1.8	60	.29	.29	2	.80
13	.64	27	.05	1.1	50	.15	.25	3	.00
14	16	260	59	2.6	60	.42	.23	3	.00
15	2.8	80	.60	2.8	60	.45	.24	3	.20
16	1.1	40	.12	1.7	35	.16	.33	3	.20
17	.80	32	.07	1.7	12	.06	.46	3	.50
18	.64	27	.05	1.2	8	.03	.28	3	.50
19	.50	25	.03	1.0	7	.02	.27	4	.00
20	.46	25	.03	.91	7	.02	.25	4	.00
21	.45	25	.03	.79	6	.80	.23	4	.00
22	.37	20	.02	.71	6	.50	.24	4	.00
23	.32	18	.02	.77	6	.01	.24	4	.00
24	.26	17	.01	.72	5	.50	.30	4	.00
25	.53	25	.04	.70	5	.01	.34	4	.00
26	.33	20	.02	.62	5	.01	.29	4	.00
27	.28	18	.01	.52	5	.01	.38	4	.00
28	.38	20	.02	.48	4	.70	.41	4	.00
29	.49	27	.04	.42	4	.50	.29	3	.70
30	.32	20	.02	.41	4	.20	.38	3	.20
31	.25	17	.01	---	---	---	.40	3	.00
TOTAL	36.33	---	61.83	225.13	---	363.34	11.24	---	4.83

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.56	20	.03	.10	2	.20	.15	6	.00
2	2.1	65	2.4	.07	2	.00	.04	2	.00
3	.00	0	.00	.05	1	.90	.00	0	.00
4	.05	4	.50	.04	1	.30	.00	0	.00
5	.04	4	.30	.02	0	.90	.07	5	.00
6	.04	4	.00	.01	0	.50	.05	6	.00
7	.07	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.14	3	.00
8	.09	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.21	2	.00
9	.11	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.16	2	.00
10	.16	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.06	1	.00
11	.23	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
12	.23	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
13	.21	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
14	.21	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
15	.20	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
16	.20	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
17	.20	4	.10	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
18	.20	4	.10	.01	0	.00	.03	2	.00
19	.17	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
20	.16	3	.90	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
21	.14	3	.60	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
22	.14	3	.40	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
23	.13	3	.20	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
24	.13	3	.20	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
25	.13	3	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
26	.14	2	.90	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
27	.12	2	.80	.11	8	.00	.00	0	.00
28	.12	2	.60	.60	29	.22	.07	5	.00
29	.10	2	.50	---	---	---	6.8	159	11
30	.09	2	.30	---	---	---	.41	20	.02
31	.08	2	.20	---	---	---	.25	12	.01
TOTAL	6.55	---	9.03	1.01	---	3.02	8.44	---	11.03
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	.14	10	.00	.06	5	.00	.25	1	.10
2	.10	8	.00	.12	20	.01	.22	1	.20
3	.06	5	.00	.10	25	.01	.20	1	.50
4	.03	2	.00	.08	4	.50	.19	1	.60
5	.00	0	.00	.07	4	.20	.17	2	.00
6	.00	0	.00	.07	4	.00	.15	1	.70
7	.01	0	.00	.05	3	.50	.13	1	.50
8	.00	0	.00	.04	3	.00	.12	1	.30
9	.01	0	.00	.03	3	.00	.11	1	.00
10	.00	0	.00	.02	2	.00	.09	1	.00
11	.00	0	.00	.02	2	.00	.08	0	.80
12	.00	0	.00	.08	4	.00	.05	0	.50
13	.01	0	.00	.04	3	.00	.03	0	.20
14	.00	0	.00	.64	37	.39	.00	0	.00
15	.01	2	.00	57	766	372	.00	0	.00
16	.20	5	.00	15	99	7.4	.00	0	.00
17	.12	2	.00	28	310	75	.00	0	.00
18	.06	3	.00	129	1040	702	.00	0	.00
19	.02	2	.00	16	189	12	.00	0	.00
20	.00	0	.00	4.7	30	.38	.00	0	.00
21	.00	0	.00	2.0	12	.06	.00	0	.00
22	.00	0	.00	1.1	10	.03	.00	0	.00
23	5.2	100	9.3	.74	10	.02	.00	0	.00
24	.98	30	.08	.57	4	.01	.00	0	.00
25	.32	18	.02	.48	1	.90	.00	0	.00
26	.19	12	.01	.42	1	.80	.00	0	.00
27	.13	10	.00	.37	1	.20	.00	0	.00
28	.09	8	.00	.33	1	.00	.00	0	.00
29	.08	7	.00	.33	1	.00	.00	0	.00
30	.07	6	.00	.32	1	.00	.00	0	.00
31	---	---	---	.28	1	.10	---	---	---
TOTAL	7.83	---	9.41	258.06	---	1172.51	1.79	---	4.40

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	JULY		AUGUST		SEPTEMBER	
					MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)
1	.00	0	.00	.01	1	.00	.00	0	.00	
2	.00	0	.00	1.9	48	.70	.00	0	.00	
3	.00	0	.00	1.8	42	.37	.00	0	.00	
4	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	
5	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	
6	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	
7	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	
8	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	
9	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.86	40	.09	
10	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	1.3	48	.17	
11	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	1.1	40	.12	
12	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	4.2	82	2.6	
13	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	18	295	22	
14	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	5.8	105	1.7	
15	.28	11	.03	.00	0	.00	2.4	60	.39	
16	1.2	46	.38	.00	0	.00	1.3	50	.18	
17	1.4	54	.41	.00	0	.00	.70	35	.07	
18	.24	14	.01	.00	0	.00	.39	20	.02	
19	.04	2	.00	.00	0	.00	.27	15	.01	
20	2.7	76	1.8	.00	0	.00	.19	10	.01	
21	.87	25	.06	.00	0	.00	.15	10	.00	
22	.32	20	.02	.00	0	.00	.10	10	.00	
23	.27	19	.01	.00	0	.00	.29	16	.03	
24	.29	18	.01	.00	0	.00	.75	34	.09	
25	.18	15	.01	.00	0	.00	6.1	141	3.8	
26	.11	10	.00	.00	0	.00	1.9	56	.30	
27	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	1.0	40	.11	
28	.05	5	.00	.00	0	.00	1.1	41	.13	
29	.04	4	.00	.00	0	.00	.76	32	.07	
30	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.62	30	.05	
31	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	---	---	---	
TOTAL	7.99	---	2.74	3.71	---	1.07	49.28	---	31.94	
YEAR	617.36		1675.15							

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	3.6	97	3.4	3.3	70	.62	.51	18	.02
2	21	292	36	2.5	60	.41	.46	15	.02
3	4.3	48	.63	1.9	50	.26	.40	15	.02
4	8.0	113	21	1.5	50	.20	.37	15	.01
5	7.3	174	4.8	1.3	45	.16	.61	18	.03
6	136	1040	777	1.1	45	.13	.51	18	.02
7	71	553	207	.99	40	.11	.36	14	.01
8	14	261	13	.80	35	.08	.30	10	.01
9	5.8	120	1.9	.76	30	.06	.28	8	.01
10	3.3	75	.67	.68	25	.05	.24	6	.00
11	2.3	58	.36	.82	30	.07	.22	5	.00
12	1.7	52	.24	2.4	65	.57	.22	5	.00
13	1.0	48	.13	4.4	140	13	.22	5	.00
14	.70	40	.08	1.6	60	.26	.23	8	.00
15	.50	30	.04	30	405	66	.29	8	.01
16	.35	25	.02	11	209	7.7	.24	8	.01
17	.33	22	.02	3.7	90	.90	.26	8	.01
18	11	218	52	3.7	70	.70	.26	8	.01
19	3.5	80	.76	2.1	45	.26	.27	7	.80
20	1.6	50	.22	1.4	40	.15	.23	7	.20
21	.94	40	.10	2.2	35	.21	.22	6	.50
22	.65	35	.06	1.1	20	.06	.24	6	.00
23	8.3	150	2.8	.91	35	.09	.22	5	.00
24	23	334	33	1.0	35	.09	.22	5	.00
25	13	221	9.0	.75	30	.06	.35	4	.80
26	5.3	110	1.6	.64	28	.05	.26	4	.50
27	3.4	80	.73	.60	25	.04	.22	4	.10
28	2.8	70	.53	.51	22	.03	.25	3	.90
29	7.0	100	1.4	.51	22	.03	.30	3	.50
30	4.2	90	1.0	.52	20	.03	.31	3	.00
31	4.4	100	1.2	---	---	---	.31	2	.70
TOTAL	370.27	---	1170.69	84.69	---	92.38	9.38	---	5.19

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.37	2	.40	.19	2	.10	.13	6	.80
2	.35	2	.00	.24	2	.10	.12	7	.00
3	.31	2	.00	.48	18	.02	.12	7	.00
4	.36	2	.00	.70	25	.05	.14	7	.00
5	.30	2	.00	.32	12	.01	.12	7	.00
6	.27	2	.00	.19	8	.00	.14	7	.00
7	.27	2	.00	.18	8	.00	.13	7	.00
8	.27	2	.00	.19	7	.50	.11	7	.00
9	1.4	2	.01	.18	7	.20	.12	7	.00
10	.43	2	.00	.18	7	.10	.12	7	.00
11	.27	2	.00	.21	7	.00	.16	7	.00
12	.24	2	.00	.20	6	.80	.13	7	.20
13	.25	2	.00	.18	6	.40	.17	8	.00
14	.24	2	.00	.16	6	.00	.32	10	.03
15	.20	2	.00	.12	6	.00	.41	19	.07
16	.24	2	.00	.12	6	.00	.09	7	.00
17	.27	2	.00	.14	6	.00	.08	6	.00
18	.25	2	.00	.12	6	.00	.08	6	.00
19	.24	2	.00	.12	6	.00	.03	6	.00
20	.22	2	.00	.13	6	.00	.09	6	.00
21	.25	2	.00	.10	6	.00	.08	6	.00
22	.23	2	.00	.12	6	.00	.07	6	.00
23	.28	2	.00	.13	6	.00	.09	6	.00
24	.39	2	.00	.14	6	.10	.09	6	.00
25	.30	2	.00	.17	6	.10	.12	6	.00
26	.26	2	.00	.15	6	.10	.14	6	.10
27	.24	2	.00	.13	6	.10	.13	6	.20
28	.22	2	.00	.13	6	.20	.10	6	.20
29	.21	2	.20	---	---	---	.59	13	.05
30	.25	2	.20	---	---	---	.14	11	.00
31	.21	2	.20	---	---	---	.21	9	.01
TOTAL	9.59	---	1.01	5.42	---	2.88	4.62	---	1.66
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	.17	9	.00	.09	8	.00	2.4	55	.36
2	.13	8	.50	.06	3	.00	1.6	45	.19
3	.11	8	.00	.05	3	.00	1.1	40	.12
4	.17	10	.00	.03	3	.00	.55	30	.04
5	1.6	46	.31	.03	3	.00	.45	20	.02
6	.53	25	.04	.04	3	.00	.27	18	.01
7	.17	11	.01	.38	20	.02	.25	18	.01
8	.15	10	.00	.35	20	.02	.20	17	.01
9	.14	10	.00	11	661	423	1.2	40	.13
10	.10	8	.00	5.8	132	3.1	.25	15	.01
11	.09	7	.00	6.7	123	2.4	.15	10	.00
12	.09	7	.00	2.4	63	.43	.12	9	.50
13	.08	6	.00	32	461	153	.12	9	.00
14	.07	5	.00	23	183	27	.14	9	.00
15	.06	5	.00	4.6	40	.50	.14	9	.00
16	.05	5	.00	1.7	40	.18	.19	9	.00
17	.05	5	.00	.70	30	.06	.15	8	.80
18	.04	4	.20	1.0	30	.08	.12	8	.20
19	.03	4	.20	.51	22	.03	.11	7	.80
20	.04	4	.00	.27	18	.01	.09	7	.00
21	.04	4	.00	.27	16	.01	.07	5	.50
22	.03	4	.00	.25	15	.01	.06	5	.00
23	.03	4	.00	.18	14	.01	.05	4	.20
24	.03	4	.00	.14	12	.00	.04	3	.50
25	.02	4	.00	.11	12	.00	.03	2	.50
26	.02	4	.00	.11	11	.00	.03	4	.00
27	.10	10	.00	.10	10	.00	.08	6	.00
28	.20	8	.00	.09	10	.00	.03	3	.20
29	3.0	75	5.2	.09	9	.00	.02	3	.00
30	1.0	40	.11	.09	8	.00	.01	2	.50
31	---	---	---	6.1	113	3.0	---	---	---
TOTAL	8.34	---	6.57	98.24	---	612.86	10.02	---	5.60

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50055650 QUEBRADA CAIMITO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TOMS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TOMS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TOMS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TOMS/DAY)
1	.00	0	.00	.15	10	.00	2.9	60	.47
2	.01	2	.00	.05	4	.50	1.9	50	.26
3	.02	2	.00	.04	2	.00	1.1	40	.12
4	.01	2	.00	.02	1	.00	.75	35	.07
5	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.58	25	.04
6	.50	37	.43	.00	0	.00	1.5	50	.20
7	.13	10	.00	.01	2	.00	.67	30	.05
8	.04	3	.00	.01	2	.00	.28	18	.01
9	.02	2	.00	.00	0	.00	.15	10	.00
10	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.11	7	.50
11	.01	2	.00	.34	50	.05	.09	6	.50
12	.04	2	.00	.03	4	.00	.07	6	.00
13	.01	2	.00	.01	2	.00	.71	25	.12
14	.02	3	.00	.03	3	.00	.25	18	.01
15	.11	5	.00	.00	0	.00	.07	4	.50
16	.03	3	.00	.30	25	.02	.04	3	.00
17	.01	1	.00	.02	2	.00	.00	0	.00
18	.00	0	.00	.01	1	.00	.00	0	.00
19	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
20	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
21	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
22	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
23	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.05	7	.00
24	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.02	3	.00
25	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.03	5	.00
26	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.01	2	.00
27	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00	.00	0	.00
28	.00	0	.00	7.4	84	26	.00	0	.00
29	.11	8	.50	28	423	149	.00	0	.00
30	5.0	173	21	4.8	120	1.6	.00	0	.00
31	1.1	50	.15	5.0	100	1.4	---	---	---
TOTAL	7.17	---	22.08	46.22	---	178.57	11.28	---	2.85
YEAR	665.24		2102.34						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'58", long 65°55'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank at Highway 919, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Quebrada Don Victor, 1.7 mi (2.7 km) upstream from Rio Gurabo and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) south of Juncos.

DRAINAGE AREA.--16.4 mi² (42.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1971 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 320 ft (98 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Minor diversion from public water supply tank, 0.5 mi upstream, during low flow.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--17 years (1972-88), 54.5 ft³/s (1.543 m³/s), 45.13 in/yr (1,150 mm/yr), 39,480 acre-ft/yr (48.7 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 52 ft³/s (1.47 m³/s), 37,700 acre-ft/yr (46 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 40,000 ft³/s (1,130 m³/s), Dec. 8, 1987, gage height, 25.63 ft (7.812 m), from floodmark and rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement and step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 1.4 ft³/s (0.040 m³/s), Apr. 21, 1988, result of diversion.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate discharges (no stages were recorded) of major floods are as follows: Sept. 6, 1960, 37,100 ft³/s (1,050 m³/s); Oct. 9, 1970, 18,200 ft³/s (515 m³/s).

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,400 ft³/s (96.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct.18	1830	12,200	346	14.55	4.435	Dec. 8	unknown	*40,000	1,130	*25.63	7.812
Nov.24	1445	6,530	185	10.57	3.222	July 7	0045	3,490	98.8	7.74	2.359
Nov.27	unknown	27,500	779	21.99	6.703	Aug. 24	1500	11,300	320	13.98	4.261
Dec. 7	1900	34,600	980	24.17	7.367	Sept.11	1145	4,270	121	8.48	2.585

Minimum discharge, 1.4 ft³/s (0.040 m³/s), Apr. 21, result of diversion.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	13	20	94	44	22	29	6.1	7.8	9.3	175	18	29
2	7.8	18	143	41	22	e28	6.1	5.5	7.7	221	17	25
3	15	17	78	37	26	e15	5.7	4.2	7.0	36	20	23
4	14	54	76	36	20	e13	5.9	3.8	6.9	21	24	22
5	10	53	69	51	23	e13	6.5	4.4	5.9	18	17	21
6	14	53	206	57	19	e12	12	151	5.2	98	15	20
7	14	39	5690	46	17	e12	14	28	4.7	613	71	21
8	8.5	26	e9100	44	21	e12	8.4	12	4.8	44	35	20
9	9.0	23	e150	45	27	13	7.3	8.5	11	30	25	77
10	11	21	e120	47	23	11	6.9	31	14	42	78	50
11	7.0	19	e100	52	25	11	6.5	27	6.1	46	130	783
12	6.4	38	e90	49	22	10	5.9	16	6.5	31	45	300
13	6.0	24	e85	44	50	11	5.7	15	17	25	27	100
14	278	19	e78	42	22	12	5.2	17	11	174	21	105
15	75	18	e73	36	22	10	8.7	20	109	32	23	68
16	52	18	e68	33	20	9.6	8.8	14	108	24	23	54
17	371	23	e66	34	18	10	5.6	14	32	24	28	42
18	1260	19	59	30	17	11	11	13	15	32	27	37
19	140	17	57	29	16	9.3	7.1	13	12	40	19	213
20	54	18	62	27	17	12	5.3	36	157	24	18	68
21	38	15	60	26	15	11	5.7	46	107	19	17	43
22	28	14	80	23	15	11	4.2	15	51	72	65	38
23	26	38	61	23	15	11	5.1	11	27	34	48	35
24	21	2480	52	22	16	9.6	5.4	10	32	22	1260	31
25	27	366	47	22	16	12	4.3	8.0	19	24	259	29
26	26	673	50	21	31	11	4.1	8.6	18	24	59	27
27	29	e9000	54	22	53	13	4.2	11	16	20	57	26
28	34	422	51	22	16	9.2	4.4	5.6	21	34	48	25
29	26	165	45	22	14	7.8	4.4	11	16	31	40	25
30	21	111	40	20	---	8.1	6.3	31	15	25	37	23
31	24	---	44	20	---	6.6	---	25	---	20	29	---
TOTAL	2665.7	13821	17048	1067	640	374.2	196.8	623.4	872.1	2075	2600	2380
MEAN	86.0	461	550	34.4	22.1	12.1	6.56	20.1	29.1	66.9	83.9	79.3
MAX	1260	9000	9100	57	53	29	14	151	157	613	1260	783
MIN	6.0	14	40	20	14	6.6	4.1	3.8	4.7	18	15	20
AC-FT	5290	27410	33810	2120	1270	742	390	1240	1730	4120	5160	4720
CFSM	5.24	28.1	33.5	2.10	1.35	.74	.40	1.23	1.77	4.08	5.11	4.84
IN.	6.05	31.35	38.67	2.42	1.45	.85	.45	1.41	1.98	4.71	5.90	5.40

WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 44363.2 MEAN 121 MAX 9100 MIN 3.8 AC-FT 87990 CFSM 7.39 IN. 100.63

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 13	1305	5.6	235	28.0	MAR, 01	1259	16.6	257	25.0
NOV, 16	1223	18.6	240	26.5	APR, 07	1226	11.2	225	27.0
DEC, 09	--	158	--	24.5	MAY, 04	1317	4.34	265	29.0
JAN, 08	1100	45.1	235	23.5	JUN, 01	0918	10.8	228	25.0
FEB, 03	1401	28.6	240	26.0	JUL, 13	1342	22	250	29.5

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1983 to September 1986.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-49 and automatic sediment sampler.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,600 mg/L October 06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 1 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 46,300 tons (42,000 tonnes) May 18, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.01 tons (0.01) tonne several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1984-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1984	741 (Jun. 10)	1 (several days)	4,990 (Nov. 05)	0.01 (several days)
1985	1,580 (May 18)	2 (several days)	46,300 (May 18)	0.05 (several days)
1986	1,600 (Oct. 06)	5 (several days)	25,100 (May 13)	0.10 (several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	27	23	2.4	24	20	1.3	17	7	.32
2	21	15	.85	18	13	.63	196	165	314
3	24	15	.97	20	12	.65	32	20	1.7
4	20	12	.65	724	494	1640	23	13	.81
5	19	12	.62	775	556	3370	22	11	.65
6	18	12	.58	469	241	312	29	11	.86
7	19	12	.62	61	50	8.2	22	11	.65
8	20	12	.65	41	30	3.3	22	10	.59
9	40	24	4.7	33	20	1.8	20	10	.54
10	20	12	.65	28	15	1.1	20	10	.54
11	17	10	.46	25	15	1.0	20	11	.59
12	26	17	1.2	24	14	.91	19	10	.51
13	20	18	.97	23	14	.87	18	10	.49
14	17	15	.69	22	13	.77	17	10	.46
15	19	17	.87	21	13	.74	18	10	.49
16	21	15	.85	22	12	.71	18	10	.49
17	17	10	.46	21	11	.62	18	9	.44
18	32	31	16	20	10	.54	18	9	.44
19	39	39	10	19	10	.51	17	9	.41
20	19	10	.51	19	9	.46	16	9	.39
21	17	10	.46	18	8	.39	16	9	.39
22	16	10	.43	17	6	.28	18	10	.49
23	15	10	.41	18	10	.49	18	10	.49
24	14	9	.34	17	11	.50	16	10	.43
25	14	9	.34	17	11	.50	15	10	.41
26	44	34	7.7	16	10	.43	16	10	.43
27	17	11	.50	16	9	.39	19	10	.51
28	15	10	.41	15	8	.32	16	10	.43
29	20	12	.65	16	8	.35	17	10	.46
30	23	15	.93	17	7	.32	20	9	.49
31	27	18	1.3	---	---	---	19	9	.46
TOTAL	677	---	58.17	2576	---	5350.08	772	---	330.36

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	17	9	.41	12	2	.06	14	18	.68
2	15	9	.36	12	2	.06	13	18	.63
3	14	8	.30	12	2	.06	12	16	.52
4	14	8	.30	14	3	.11	11	14	.42
5	14	8	.30	12	2	.06	12	11	.36
6	13	8	.28	13	4	.14	12	11	.36
7	13	7	.25	14	3	.11	12	10	.32
8	13	6	.21	13	2	.07	12	10	.32
9	14	5	.19	13	2	.07	12	8	.26
10	16	5	.22	17	5	.23	12	6	.19
11	14	5	.19	22	25	1.5	11	4	.12
12	13	5	.18	18	17	.83	11	3	.09
13	27	21	4.5	134	126	174	11	1	.03
14	30	25	2.0	35	52	4.9	11	2	.06
15	17	10	.46	205	153	507	11	2	.06
16	16	10	.43	603	413	1510	11	3	.09
17	15	10	.41	41	50	5.5	11	3	.09
18	15	8	.32	26	33	2.3	11	4	.12
19	14	5	.19	21	31	1.8	10	4	.11
20	51	51	15	19	31	1.6	10	3	.08
21	20	12	.65	17	31	1.4	10	3	.08
22	17	10	.46	16	31	1.3	10	4	.11
23	14	10	.38	15	30	1.2	10	3	.08
24	13	10	.35	15	30	1.2	10	4	.11
25	18	9	.44	14	26	.98	10	4	.11
26	14	5	.19	14	24	.91	10	5	.14
27	14	4	.15	15	22	.89	9.5	5	.13
28	14	4	.15	15	22	.89	9.0	5	.12
29	13	3	.11	13	20	.70	9.0	5	.12
30	13	3	.11	---	---	---	8.5	4	.09
31	12	2	.06	---	---	---	8.5	4	.09
TOTAL	517	---	29.55	1390	---	2219.87	334.5	---	6.09
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	8.5	4	.09	5.8	1	.02	35	20	1.9
2	8.5	4	.09	5.7	1	.02	26	15	1.1
3	8.5	4	.09	5.7	1	.02	18	10	.49
4	8.5	4	.09	7.1	1	.02	46	45	11
5	8.5	4	.09	5.8	1	.02	21	14	.79
6	8.5	4	.09	5.3	1	.01	128	146	92
7	9.0	5	.12	5.6	1	.02	209	222	270
8	8.2	4	.09	5.8	1	.02	83	70	16
9	7.1	4	.08	6.2	1	.02	43	50	5.8
10	7.2	3	.06	6.3	1	.02	983	741	4990
11	7.8	2	.04	4.2	1	.01	170	181	127
12	7.1	2	.04	5.0	1	.01	66	45	4.5
13	7.3	2	.04	19	1	.05	241	236	626
14	6.6	2	.04	11	2	.06	87	55	13
15	6.4	2	.03	7.4	1	.02	48	35	4.5
16	6.1	2	.03	7.2	1	.02	37	28	2.8
17	6.8	2	.04	6.6	1	.02	33	45	4.0
18	6.5	2	.04	6.0	1	.02	30	20	1.6
19	6.6	2	.04	5.5	2	.03	43	35	4.1
20	9.1	5	.12	5.7	2	.03	34	28	2.6
21	7.4	5	.10	6.6	2	.04	26	18	1.3
22	8.7	4	.09	6.4	2	.03	23	12	.75
23	6.9	2	.04	15	2	.08	20	12	.65
24	6.6	2	.04	9.0	2	.05	19	10	.51
25	6.2	1	.02	17	20	.92	19	10	.51
26	6.0	1	.02	55	61	23	18	10	.49
27	12	1	.03	16	10	.43	17	10	.46
28	14	1	.04	39	33	5.9	17	10	.46
29	6.6	1	.02	21	10	.57	---	25	2.2
30	6.3	1	.02	296	308	1030	20	12	.65
31	---	---	---	75	71	21	---	---	---
TOTAL	233.5	---	1.77	692.9	---	1082.48	2592	---	6182.16

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER		
				MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	19	10	.51	20	10	.54	14	10	.38			
2	30	20	1.6	72	64	18	16	10	.43			
3	17	10	.46	23	12	.75	21	10	.57			
4	18	10	.49	41	37	7.3	25	10	.68			
5	68	69	20	25	18	1.2	55	15	2.2			
6	24	15	.97	19	10	.51	70	35	6.6			
7	19	10	.51	17	10	.46	28	35	2.6			
8	17	10	.46	15	10	.41	18	10	.49			
9	15	9	.36	16	10	.43	16	10	.43			
10	27	15	1.1	15	10	.41	18	10	.49			
11	21	15	.85	14	10	.38	28	10	.76			
12	15	10	.41	14	10	.38	40	33	6.1			
13	14	10	.38	13	9	.32	334	310	1460			
14	24	25	1.6	13	8	.28	686	593	2940			
15	25	20	1.4	13	8	.28	80	70	15			
16	15	10	.41	13	8	.28	195	173	377			
17	14	10	.38	13	8	.28	333	353	696			
18	13	9	.32	13	8	.28	323	423	822			
19	12	8	.26	12	8	.26	138	120	45			
20	14	7	.26	12	8	.26	414	371	855			
21	23	20	1.2	12	8	.26	151	150	61			
22	21	15	.85	13	8	.28	81	70	15			
23	22	10	.59	12	7	.23	65	55	9.7			
24	15	10	.41	12	7	.23	55	45	6.7			
25	13	10	.35	12	6	.19	55	40	5.9			
26	12	10	.32	230	77	31	47	35	4.4			
27	14	10	.38	300	119	59	53	30	4.3			
28	14	10	.38	60	50	8.1	50	30	4.1			
29	54	45	23	40	30	3.2	43	30	3.5			
30	60	64	17	60	25	4.1	51	30	4.1			
31	22	13	.77	20	18	.97	---	---	---			
TOTAL	691	---	77.98	1164	---	140.57	3503	---	7346.43			
YEAR	15142.9		22825.51									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	44	35	4.2	93	100	43	30	18	1.5
2	43	25	2.9	325	250	558	45	44	7.0
3	65	53	9.6	1350	460	811	41	48	5.3
4	46	35	4.3	330	200	203	31	50	4.2
5	42	32	3.6	860	605	1830	29	50	3.9
6	59	45	8.2	920	455	929	28	46	3.5
7	68	65	14	470	180	228	26	42	2.9
8	53	45	6.4	170	65	30	25	40	2.7
9	138	116	71	116	40	13	30	45	3.6
10	121	119	50	112	39	12	28	45	3.4
11	80	62	12	85	39	9.0	205	184	608
12	70	55	10	74	37	7.4	216	345	786
13	96	87	30	67	35	6.3	59	90	14
14	85	103	30	93	85	40	37	60	6.0
15	80	75	16	93	111	32	32	60	5.2
16	62	65	11	60	85	14	28	59	4.5
17	53	40	5.4	57	80	12	30	58	4.7
18	45	30	3.6	54	75	11	23	57	3.5
19	41	28	3.1	47	70	8.9	14	55	3.6
20	51	35	4.8	43	68	7.9	23	40	2.5
21	40	25	2.7	40	62	6.7	22	35	2.1
22	38	22	2.3	39	60	6.3	21	35	2.0
23	36	20	1.9	46	60	7.5	21	33	1.9
24	34	20	1.8	37	50	5.0	24	40	2.6
25	61	93	21	35	52	4.9	31	45	3.8
26	44	86	10	36	50	4.9	26	55	3.9
27	38	50	5.1	35	51	4.8	24	55	3.6
28	44	55	6.5	33	58	5.2	27	47	3.4
29	35	25	2.4	35	60	5.7	21	35	2.0
30	31	22	1.8	33	20	1.8	26	35	2.5
31	32	40	3.5	---	---	---	21	30	1.7
TOTAL	1775	---	359.1	5788	---	4858.3	1254	---	1505.5

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)									
										JANUARY			FEBRUARY			MARCH		
										APRIL			MAY			JUNE		
1	35	44	9.5	17	25	1.1	18	45	2.2									
2	46	55	6.8	14	21	.79	12	42	1.4									
3	25	40	2.7	13	21	.74	13	40	1.4									
4	31	47	3.9	13	22	.77	11	40	1.2									
5	26	30	2.1	12	22	.71	13	30	1.1									
6	29	42	3.3	12	22	.71	16	20	.86									
7	22	42	2.5	11	20	.59	52	71	1.3									
8	21	41	2.3	11	19	.56	36	20	1.9									
9	19	45	2.3	11	19	.56	17	20	.92									
10	20	50	2.7	11	18	.53	14	12	.45									
11	20	50	2.7	12	15	.49	13	11	.39									
12	18	57	2.8	11	15	.45	13	10	.35									
13	18	56	2.7	10	17	.46	12	9	.29									
14	17	56	2.6	12	15	.49	11	9	.27									
15	16	58	2.5	13	15	.53	9.8	8	.21									
16	16	60	2.6	12	15	.49	10	9	.24									
17	16	60	2.6	12	14	.45	11	9	.27									
18	16	50	2.2	13	12	.42	26	24	1.7									
19	16	48	2.1	13	15	.53	13	15	.53									
20	16	48	2.1	21	20	1.1	11	6	.18									
21	16	48	2.1	13	9	.32	10	5	.14									
22	16	48	2.1	12	8	.26	10	5	.14									
23	15	49	2.0	12	9	.29	10	4	.11									
24	15	50	2.0	12	9	.29	9.7	2	.05									
25	15	49	2.0	12	10	.32	9.1	2	.05									
26	18	45	2.2	11	10	.30	11	5	.15									
27	16	40	1.7	22	17	1.4	10	6	.16									
28	16	38	1.6	44	64	15	10	6	.16									
29	15	35	1.4	---	---	---	509	490	2160									
30	14	30	1.1	---	---	---	53	42	11									
31	14	28	1.1	---	---	---	48	65	8.4									
TOTAL	613	---	82.3	392	---	30.65	1021.2	---	2214.22									
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE										
1	23	18	1.1	15	10	.41	24	7	.45									
2	18	10	.49	14	10	.38	23	8	.50									
3	14	9	.34	15	10	.41	21	8	.45									
4	13	8	.28	14	10	.38	20	8	.43									
5	12	7	.23	15	10	.41	21	8	.45									
6	13	7	.25	17	13	.60	20	5	.27									
7	16	5	.22	13	9	.32	20	5	.27									
8	14	5	.19	13	9	.32	25	8	.54									
9	14	5	.19	15	10	.41	21	10	.57									
10	11	10	.30	13	10	.35	20	12	.65									
11	25	30	2.0	15	10	.41	18	11	.53									
12	26	20	1.4	30	20	1.6	19	10	.51									
13	17	10	.46	21	20	1.1	17	9	.41									
14	14	10	.38	245	246	285	17	8	.37									
15	21	10	.57	2250	1090	14100	16	8	.35									
16	27	10	.73	284	298	727	15	10	.41									
17	21	10	.57	751	557	1670	14	10	.38									
18	15	10	.41	3910	1580	46300	14	10	.38									
19	15	10	.41	180	190	92	13	10	.35									
20	12	10	.32	84	70	16	13	9	.32									
21	12	10	.32	63	50	8.5	12	5	.16									
22	13	10	.35	51	40	5.5	12	5	.16									
23	530	372	1500	43	35	4.1	13	5	.18									
24	144	193	149	41	30	3.3	12	5	.16									
25	83	90	20	40	25	2.7	12	5	.16									
26	46	80	9.9	36	20	1.9	11	5	.15									
27	26	20	1.4	32	18	1.6	12	5	.16									
28	20	12	.65	31	20	1.7	11	5	.15									
29	18	10	.49	28	15	1.1	11	8	.24									
30	17	10	.46	27	12	.87	11	10	.30									
31	---	---	---	25	10	.68	---	---	---									
TOTAL	1250	---	1693.41	8331	---	63229.05	488	---	10.41									

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	13	20	.70	18	15	.73	18	12	.58
2	16	15	.65	22	15	.89	17	10	.46
3	12	12	.39	18	16	.78	17	10	.46
4	11	12	.36	16	15	.65	14	10	.38
5	12	12	.39	15	14	.57	17	15	.69
6	11	17	.50	19	14	.72	13	9	.32
7	10	20	.54	27	25	1.8	12	9	.29
8	12	20	.65	20	11	.59	11	77	49
9	14	20	.76	20	15	.81	43	100	12
10	11	15	.45	16	11	.48	18	25	1.2
11	13	15	.53	15	11	.45	22	18	1.1
12	16	15	.65	15	10	.41	631	526	3550
13	12	15	.49	31	25	2.1	554	522	1580
14	11	17	.50	20	18	.97	98	90	24
15	49	83	29	17	16	.73	58	50	7.8
16	63	58	13	16	15	.65	40	35	3.8
17	93	96	69	15	13	.53	30	25	2.0
18	29	25	2.0	15	12	.49	25	15	1.0
19	21	14	.79	17	15	.69	20	12	.65
20	148	199	186	14	8	.30	21	12	.68
21	38	20	2.1	17	7	.32	20	12	.65
22	24	15	.97	16	4	.17	20	12	.65
23	21	11	.62	14	2	.08	24	20	1.3
24	33	25	2.2	13	3	.11	31	20	1.7
25	20	18	.97	16	4	.17	145	182	160
26	30	20	1.6	14	5	.19	42	30	3.4
27	19	10	.51	159	209	232	31	20	1.7
28	28	11	.83	54	105	15	46	35	4.3
29	21	12	.68	18	15	.73	52	40	5.6
30	19	12	.62	20	15	.81	37	25	2.5
31	16	15	.65	15	12	.49	---	---	---
TOTAL	846	---	319.10	722	---	265.41	2202	---	5418.21
YEAR	24682.2		79985.66						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
	OCTOBER			NOVEMBER			DECEMBER		
1	46	40	6.1	90	84	22	29	20	1.6
2	79	75	21	79	65	14	31	20	1.7
3	79	80	27	63	60	10	29	20	1.6
4	77	94	47	58	50	7.8	27	20	1.5
5	180	210	158	64	55	11	41	20	2.2
6	2920	1600	16500	55	45	6.7	38	25	2.6
7	1420	739	4060	50	40	5.4	30	20	1.6
8	428	363	930	45	38	4.6	26	20	1.4
9	136	120	45	42	35	4.0	25	18	1.2
10	95	90	23	40	30	3.2	26	12	.84
11	76	75	15	44	34	4.0	25	14	.95
12	66	60	11	56	45	7.8	34	20	1.8
13	59	45	7.2	51	45	6.2	25	16	1.1
14	53	30	4.3	51	40	5.5	23	14	.87
15	50	20	2.7	385	774	1690	24	15	.97
16	51	40	5.5	130	120	42	23	14	.87
17	72	65	16	74	65	14	22	14	.83
18	201	222	305	200	189	171	24	12	.78
19	80	64	16	63	60	10	23	14	.87
20	56	40	6.0	54	45	6.6	26	15	1.1
21	55	40	5.9	50	40	5.4	22	12	.71
22	47	40	5.1	41	38	4.2	22	12	.71
23	453	343	918	40	35	3.8	22	12	.71
24	1050	737	5200	37	25	2.5	25	13	.88
25	208	211	200	34	20	1.8	21	10	.57
26	150	146	85	31	20	1.7	23	11	.68
27	104	90	25	31	20	1.7	21	10	.57
28	77	60	12	30	20	1.6	21	10	.57
29	478	382	1330	30	20	1.6	19	18	.92
30	112	110	40	30	20	1.6	18	10	.49
31	160	154	70	---	---	---	19	10	.51
TOTAL	9118	---	30096.8	2048	---	2071.7	784	---	33.70

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	24	10	.65	13	8	.28	8.8	5	.12
2	27	12	.87	13	8	.28	9.0	5	.12
3	22	12	.71	12	8	.26	9.1	5	.12
4	22	11	.65	15	10	.41	9.3	5	.13
5	20	10	.54	15	10	.41	11	6	.18
6	18	10	.49	12	8	.26	11	6	.18
7	18	10	.49	11	8	.24	9.0	5	.12
8	17	10	.46	11	8	.24	8.6	5	.12
9	35	20	1.9	11	8	.24	9.0	5	.12
10	27	12	.87	11	8	.24	8.8	5	.12
11	20	10	.54	12	8	.26	9.4	5	.13
12	18	10	.49	12	8	.26	8.8	5	.12
13	17	9	.41	11	7	.21	11	6	.18
14	16	8	.35	10	6	.16	13	6	.21
15	16	8	.35	10	6	.16	38	32	5.4
16	17	8	.37	10	6	.16	13	7	.25
17	61	67	33	12	11	.36	11	6	.18
18	24	12	.78	16	9	.39	8.2	5	.11
19	19	10	.51	12	8	.26	8.2	5	.12
20	17	10	.46	12	7	.23	8.2	5	.11
21	18	10	.49	11	7	.21	8.3	5	.11
22	16	10	.43	11	7	.21	8.8	5	.12
23	15	10	.41	9.9	6	.16	8.5	5	.11
24	17	10	.46	9.7	6	.16	7.4	5	.10
25	16	10	.43	11	6	.18	8.3	5	.11
26	16	10	.43	11	7	.21	17	14	1.1
27	14	10	.38	9.6	6	.16	8.8	5	.12
28	14	9	.34	9.0	6	.15	9.8	5	.13
29	13	8	.28	---	---	---	93	111	77
30	14	8	.30	---	---	---	18	11	.53
31	13	8	.28	---	---	---	35	30	4.6
TOTAL	621	---	49.12	323.2	---	6.75	445.3	---	92.17
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	64	69	29	22	14	.83	42	40	4.5
2	17	10	.46	16	10	.43	57	22	1.2
3	13	8	.28	14	8	.30	53	30	4.3
4	29	28	7.5	16	10	.43	35	25	2.4
5	28	20	2.3	12	8	.26	32	18	1.6
6	23	14	.87	20	12	.65	27	15	1.1
7	14	8	.30	88	90	41	54	47	25
8	23	23	8.8	69	145	93	107	153	155
9	46	40	12	49	39	6.0	141	143	129
10	14	8	.30	308	328	758	204	181	341
11	11	7	.21	215	184	168	51	40	5.5
12	11	7	.21	53	42	6.0	42	30	3.4
13	10	6	.16	851	1020	25100	79	68	26
14	9.5	5	.13	831	472	2120	68	57	12
15	9.3	5	.13	89	75	18	46	30	3.7
16	9.5	5	.13	61	58	9.6	54	46	8.3
17	9.1	5	.12	54	42	6.1	34	22	2.0
18	9.0	5	.12	417	303	1330	33	25	2.2
19	8.6	5	.12	127	140	89	49	49	9.0
20	8.4	5	.11	69	70	13	31	15	1.3
21	8.3	5	.11	66	60	11	28	14	1.1
22	7.8	5	.11	63	82	18	26	14	.98
23	7.4	5	.10	42	30	3.4	25	14	.95
24	7.9	5	.11	36	22	2.1	24	13	.84
25	7.1	5	.11	32	21	1.8	22	13	.77
26	7.1	5	.10	29	18	1.4	23	12	.75
27	10	16	1.3	29	18	1.4	26	12	.84
28	21	13	.74	26	22	2.1	23	12	.75
29	365	471	2320	25	20	1.4	21	12	.68
30	60	51	11	23	12	.75	21	12	.68
31	---	---	---	114	134	113	---	---	---
TOTAL	868.0	---	2396.93	3866	---	29916.95	1478	---	746.84

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056400 RIO VALENCIANO NEAR JUNCOS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	25	12	.81	20	12	.65	22	13	.77
2	21	12	.68	18	10	.49	19	12	.62
3	22	12	.71	13	5	.18	16	10	.43
4	20	12	.65	14	5	.19	15	8	.32
5	19	10	.51	12	5	.16	15	8	.32
6	40	31	4.9	12	5	.16	16	10	.43
7	30	15	1.2	18	10	.41	15	8	.32
8	20	12	.65	42	35	8.0	13	8	.28
9	19	12	.62	19	17	.87	12	8	.26
10	17	8	.37	20	20	1.1	12	8	.26
11	19	8	.41	33	22	2.0	11	8	.24
12	20	8	.43	17	22	1.0	11	7	.21
13	17	8	.37	50	65	48	12	7	.21
14	24	8	.52	49	47	16	18	12	.58
15	24	8	.52	25	12	.39	12	7	.23
16	19	8	.41	18	12	.58	11	7	.21
17	18	8	.39	16	10	.43	11	7	.21
18	18	8	.39	14	12	.45	9.5	7	.18
19	16	8	.35	14	8	.30	9.7	7	.18
20	16	7	.30	13	9	.32	9.5	7	.18
21	16	7	.30	12	10	.32	9.0	7	.17
22	15	7	.30	11	10	.30	11	6	.18
23	20	8	.43	11	10	.30	12	6	.19
24	18	8	.39	11	9	.27	33	18	1.6
25	15	5	.20	11	8	.24	26	16	1.1
26	14	5	.19	9.8	8	.21	16	9	.39
27	16	5	.22	9.5	8	.21	13	8	.28
28	17	6	.28	27	28	8.5	15	7	.28
29	14	5	.19	386	313	976	12	6	.19
30	23	12	.75	29	20	1.6	11	8	.24
31	24	12	.78	20	12	.65	---	---	---
TOTAL	616	---	19.22	974.3	---	1070.28	427.7	---	11.06
YEAR	21569.5		66511.52						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°14'57", long 65°56'44", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left downstream side of bridge on Highway 189, 1.9 mi (3.0 km) southeast of Gurabo plaza, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) northwest of Juncos plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.30 mi² (5.96 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 180 ft (55 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 2,740 ft³/s (77.6 m³/s), Nov. 26, 1987, gage height, 11.04 ft (3.365 m), from rating curve extended above 400 ft³/s (11.3 m³/s) on basis of indirect measurement of peak flow and step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 0.20 ft³/s (0.006 m³/s), Feb. 10, 1987.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov.26	2400	*2,740	77.6	*11.04	3.365	Aug. 24	1430	1,310	37.9	8.76	2.670
Dec. 7	1800	2,190	62.0	10.25	3.124	Sept.11	1100	904	25.6	6.04	1.841

Minimum discharge, 0.26 ft³/s (0.007 m³/s), June 8.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.35	.99	4.2	e3.2	1.6	.68	.59	.39	.36	28	.73	1.9
2	.32	.62	6.4	e3.0	1.7	.65	.58	.38	.32	27	.69	1.8
3	.50	.56	3.8	e2.1	2.1	.63	.54	.37	.30	3.4	.75	1.8
4	.44	1.2	3.6	e2.1	1.8	.64	.50	.35	.29	2.3	.97	1.8
5	.45	.78	3.6	e2.0	1.5	.64	.47	.35	.29	2.0	.71	1.8
6	.39	.80	5.6	e2.0	1.4	.61	.91	.66	.31	6.8	.65	1.8
7	.44	.72	219	e1.9	1.3	.61	.78	.48	.27	13	.68	1.8
8	.45	.61	102	e1.9	1.4	.61	.49	.38	.27	2.5	.76	e1.8
9	.43	.56	5.1	e1.8	1.3	.59	.44	.36	.27	1.9	.76	e5.0
10	.40	.55	e3.2	e1.8	1.2	.58	.42	.67	.29	1.7	19	e2.0
11	.38	.54	e3.0	e1.7	1.2	.58	.53	.53	.31	1.8	4.9	126
12	.37	.53	e2.8	e1.8	1.4	.59	.42	.41	.33	3.0	2.4	e24
13	.36	.52	e2.6	1.8	1.2	.60	.40	.38	.31	5.5	1.7	e3.3
14	.52	.52	e2.4	1.8	1.2	.59	.39	.39	.35	5.0	1.5	e5.0
15	.65	.52	e2.1	1.7	1.4	.55	.48	.38	5.1	1.7	1.4	e3.5
16	.65	1.4	e2.0	1.6	1.3	.56	.43	.37	.98	3.5	1.5	e3.0
17	3.7	1.8	e2.0	1.7	1.2	.56	.40	.38	.61	2.2	1.8	e2.7
18	31	1.2	e3.0	1.7	1.2	.58	.40	.35	.47	1.9	1.7	e2.5
19	3.7	.73	e3.0	1.6	1.1	.59	.40	.42	.41	2.0	1.5	e13
20	.99	.62	e2.9	1.6	1.1	.64	.38	.41	.47	1.2	1.4	e3.0
21	.72	.59	e2.8	1.5	1.1	.61	.38	.36	.53	1.0	1.4	e2.5
22	.63	.58	e2.0	1.5	1.0	.57	.37	.36	.62	4.4	2.1	e2.2
23	.60	3.0	e2.0	1.4	.96	.55	.95	.34	.50	1.5	7.2	e2.0
24	.58	155	e2.0	1.5	1.0	.55	.59	.31	4.5	2.3	e192	e1.8
25	.62	10	e2.0	1.7	.97	.57	.46	.31	2.2	2.2	e76	e1.8
26	.59	94	e1.9	1.6	.90	.62	.39	.31	2.4	1.3	e3.9	e1.7
27	.58	343	e1.9	1.6	3.0	.66	.38	.30	1.3	1.0	2.6	e1.7
28	.99	14	e1.9	1.7	.87	.65	.37	.30	.75	.83	2.4	e1.6
29	.71	6.1	e1.8	1.7	.73	.75	.36	.45	.70	.88	2.3	e1.6
30	.57	5.0	e2.1	1.7	---	.67	.37	.44	.72	1.0	2.1	e1.6
31	1.8	---	e3.2	1.6	---	.61	---	.43	---	.78	2.0	---
TOTAL	54.88	647.04	405.9	56.3	38.13	18.89	14.57	12.32	26.53	133.59	339.50	226.0
MEAN	1.77	21.6	13.1	1.82	1.31	.61	.49	.40	.88	4.31	11.0	7.53
MAX	31	343	219	3.2	3.0	.75	.95	.67	5.1	28	192	126
MIN	.32	.52	1.8	1.4	.73	.55	.36	.30	.27	.78	.65	1.6
AC-FT	109	1280	805	112	76	37	29	24	53	265	673	448
CFSM	.77	9.38	5.69	.79	.57	.26	.21	.17	.38	1.87	4.76	3.28
IN.	.89	10.47	6.56	.91	.62	.31	.24	.20	.43	2.16	5.49	3.66

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 1764.14 MEAN 4.83 MAX 343 MIN .21 AC-FT 3500 CFSM 2.10 IN. 28.53
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 1973.65 MEAN 5.39 MAX 343 MIN .27 AC-FT 3910 CFSM 2.34 IN. 31.92

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS MARCH 1984 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 15	1410	0.55	586	27.5	APR, 06	1239	0.43	594	28.0
NOV, 18	1318	0.95	455	27.0	MAY, 09	1502	0.37	576	27.0
JAN, 08	1422	1.91	600	26.5	JUN, 06	0913	0.34	610	26.5
FEB, 05	1226	1.55	612	26.0	JUL, 14	1347	3.50	311	26.5
MAR, 03	1543	0.63	578	26.0					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: January 1983 to September 1986.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 643 mg/L October 06, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 1,060 tons (960 tonnes) May 18, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.00 tons (0.00) tonne several days.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1984-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1984	328 (Aug. 30)	1 (several days)	224 (Jun. 10)	0.01 (several days)
1985	587 (May 17)	2 (March 12)	1,060 (May 18)	0.01 (several days)
1986	643 (Oct. 06)	2 (September 30)	684 (Oct. 06)	0.00 (several days)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.56	24	.04	.44	22	.03	.53	21	.03
2	.52	24	.03	.45	22	.03	.52	20	.03
3	.51	23	.03	.44	22	.03	.49	20	.03
4	.51	23	.03	.47	23	.03	.49	18	.02
5	.51	23	.03	.44	23	.03	.54	15	.02
6	.50	22	.03	.50	22	.03	.54	12	.02
7	.48	22	.03	.56	24	.04	.51	6	.80
8	.58	23	.04	.52	24	.03	.51	4	.50
9	.60	25	.04	5.8	108	4.6	.54	4	.01
10	.63	25	.04	6.9	132	6.8	.49	4	.01
11	.56	23	.03	2.3	50	.31	.49	4	.01
12	.67	25	.05	1.2	40	.13	.50	4	.01
13	1.1	35	.10	9.5	104	10	.50	4	.01
14	.76	28	.06	1.8	50	.24	.49	4	.01
15	.55	25	.04	28	161	38	.51	4	.01
16	.54	24	.03	44	253	84	.56	4	.01
17	.55	24	.04	1.6	40	.17	.55	4	.01
18	.52	23	.03	.97	33	.09	.51	4	.01
19	.75	28	.06	.81	30	.07	.53	4	.10
20	.91	28	.07	.73	28	.06	.51	4	.01
21	.54	24	.03	.65	26	.05	.49	4	.01
22	.50	23	.03	.63	26	.04	.49	4	.01
23	.51	22	.03	.62	25	.04	.55	4	.01
24	.50	22	.03	.58	25	.04	.53	4	.01
25	.51	22	.03	.57	25	.04	.50	4	.01
26	.50	22	.03	.56	25	.04	.51	4	.01
27	.46	22	.03	.60	25	.04	.54	4	.01
28	.45	22	.03	.59	23	.04	.52	4	.01
29	.44	22	.03	.53	22	.03	.51	4	.01
30	.44	22	.03	---	---	---	.51	4	.01
31	.43	22	.03	---	---	---	.53	4	.01
TOTAL	17.59	---	1.18	112.76	---	145.08	15.99	---	1.77

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.54	4	.01	.53	21	.03	.95	27	.07
2	.55	3	.90	.53	19	.03	.73	22	.04
3	.56	3	.50	.53	18	.03	.52	15	.02
4	.57	3	.20	.51	16	.02	.52	10	.01
5	.57	3	.20	.50	14	.02	.54	6	.01
6	.62	3	.01	.49	13	.02	2.9	55	.96
7	.66	3	.01	.48	11	.01	4.3	63	1.6
8	.62	3	.01	.47	10	.01	2.1	53	.36
9	.64	3	.01	.47	9	.01	.84	33	.07
10	.66	3	.01	.45	8	.01	73	248	224
11	.67	3	.01	.43	8	.01	2.0	50	.27
12	.67	2	.80	.47	8	.01	.98	28	.07
13	.63	2	.70	.92	21	.09	.83	25	.06
14	.55	2	.60	1.0	15	.04	.69	25	.05
15	.53	2	.50	.66	12	.02	.59	24	.04
16	.49	2	.10	.59	10	.02	.55	22	.03
17	.50	2	.00	.54	9	.01	.60	22	.04
18	.51	2	.00	.52	8	.01	.56	20	.03
19	.52	2	.00	.51	8	.01	.56	20	.03
20	.48	2	.00	.50	8	.01	.58	19	.03
21	.46	2	.00	.51	8	.01	.56	18	.03
22	.47	2	.00	.48	8	.01	.56	16	.02
23	.47	2	.00	.55	8	.01	.52	15	.02
24	.46	1	.90	.48	8	.01	.50	14	.02
25	.44	---	---	.49	8	.01	.49	13	.02
26	.48	1	.90	.52	8	.01	.47	12	.02
27	1.1	19	.11	.58	12	.02	.46	11	.01
28	1.1	27	.09	.68	12	.02	.46	11	.01
29	.58	23	.04	.60	10	.02	.61	10	.02
30	.50	22	.03	5.8	81	1.9	.61	10	.02
31	---	---	---	3.7	61	.81	---	---	---
TOTAL	17.60	---	6.64	25.49	---	3.25	99.58	---	227.98
		JULY			AUGUST			SEPTEMBER	
1	.48	9	.01	.60	25	.04	1.3	35	.12
2	.45	9	.01	1.7	32	.15	.80	30	.06
3	.46	9	.01	.64	25	.04	9.8	100	13
4	.47	9	.01	.58	20	.03	2.6	70	.65
5	2.2	49	.34	.59	18	.03	14	113	18
6	.70	27	.05	.50	17	.02	3.6	73	1.0
7	.47	17	.02	.48	15	.02	1.0	35	.09
8	.44	15	.02	.47	14	.02	.73	25	.05
9	.75	20	.04	.46	14	.02	.78	30	.06
10	1.3	37	.13	.42	13	.01	.81	30	.07
11	.76	33	.07	.38	12	.01	.63	25	.04
12	.55	32	.05	.38	12	.01	.70	25	.05
13	.48	32	.04	.39	12	.01	.75	28	.06
14	.70	32	.06	.38	11	.01	2.3	58	.72
15	.99	30	.08	.38	10	.01	.97	35	.09
16	.54	24	.03	.54	9	.01	27	129	49
17	.48	22	.03	.48	9	.01	39	250	49
18	.48	20	.03	.39	10	.01	30	227	31
19	.47	19	.02	.42	10	.01	11	125	5.4
20	.63	18	.03	.45	10	.01	29	202	32
21	.56	16	.02	.43	10	.01	5.7	70	1.1
22	.59	15	.02	.44	9	.01	2.8	58	.44
23	.51	14	.02	.41	8	.01	2.1	44	.25
24	.47	12	.02	.38	7	.01	1.8	40	.19
25	.43	11	.01	.38	7	.01	1.7	30	.14
26	.42	9	.01	12	87	12	1.5	20	.08
27	.45	8	.01	3.8	101	2.2	1.4	20	.08
28	.43	7	.01	.42	50	.06	1.4	18	.07
29	3.4	44	2.2	.28	52	.04	1.3	17	.06
30	1.3	37	.13	79	328	202	1.3	15	.05
31	.65	27	.05	4.1	70	.77	---	---	---
TOTAL	23.01	---	3.58	112.27	---	217.60	197.77	---	202.92
YEAR	623.83		810.08						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	1.3	37	.13	3.0	60	.49	1.5	5	.02
2	1.3	37	.13	48	---	---	4.8	58	1.7
3	1.5	40	.16	116	379	226	2.1	35	.20
4	1.4	40	.15	60	274	76	1.7	12	.06
5	14	118	16	111	467	280	1.6	7	.03
6	3.0	68	.80	140	499	297	1.6	4	.02
7	1.5	40	.16	54	259	87	1.5	4	.02
8	1.3	37	.13	10	113	4.1	1.5	4	.02
9	16	129	19	9.4	130	4.5	1.6	4	.02
10	6.9	92	2.2	18	153	20	1.6	4	.02
11	2.3	52	.32	4.1	65	.72	4.7	48	3.8
12	1.7	45	.21	2.9	60	.47	3.8	66	1.0
13	3.4	65	1.8	2.5	58	.39	1.5	30	.12
14	43	202	89	4.2	85	.96	1.4	20	.08
15	3.7	65	.65	4.0	65	.70	1.3	17	.06
16	2.9	65	.51	2.3	33	.20	1.7	16	.07
17	11	106	13	2.5	20	.14	1.4	16	.06
18	4.3	83	1.3	2.2	15	.09	1.3	16	.06
19	2.0	45	.24	2.0	12	.06	1.3	15	.05
20	1.7	43	.20	1.9	9	.05	1.3	15	.05
21	13	130	18	1.9	9	.05	1.3	15	.05
22	3.0	60	.49	1.9	9	.05	1.2	14	.05
23	1.9	45	.23	2.0	7	.04	1.3	13	.05
24	1.6	42	.18	1.9	7	.04	1.7	12	.06
25	14	141	21	1.9	7	.04	1.6	12	.05
26	2.5	50	.34	2.1	6	.03	1.4	11	.04
27	2.0	45	.24	1.8	6	.03	1.6	10	.04
28	12	131	7.4	1.8	6	.03	1.4	9	.03
29	3.9	90	1.0	1.7	5	.02	1.3	8	.03
30	44	213	86	1.5	5	.02	2.5	38	.48
31	4.4	80	1.2	---	---	---	1.8	45	.22
TOTAL	226.5	---	282.17	616.5	---	999.22	56.3	---	8.56

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	2.1	46	.40	.76	10	.02	1.3	38	.13
2	9.9	120	7.6	.73	10	.02	.86	32	.07
3	1.6	35	.15	.69	10	.02	.81	29	.06
4	1.4	25	.09	.66	10	.02	.84	27	.06
5	1.3	24	.08	.62	10	.02	.88	24	.06
6	1.5	23	.09	.61	8	.01	1.0	20	.05
7	1.6	21	.09	.60	8	.01	1.1	16	.05
8	1.3	20	.07	.59	8	.01	1.1	13	.04
9	1.2	19	.06	.58	8	.01	.88	9	.02
10	1.1	18	.05	.57	7	.01	.87	6	.01
11	1.1	17	.05	.56	7	.01	.86	3	.01
12	1.0	16	.04	.55	7	.01	.87	2	.00
13	.96	16	.04	.53	7	.01	.86	3	.01
14	.95	16	.04	.53	7	.01	.87	3	.01
15	.93	15	.04	.59	7	.01	.87	4	.01
16	.89	15	.04	.61	8	.01	.91	5	.01
17	.89	15	.04	.62	8	.01	.95	5	.01
18	.86	14	.03	.74	7	.01	1.1	6	.02
19	.82	13	.03	.72	8	.02	.92	7	.02
20	.79	12	.03	.74	8	.02	.81	8	.02
21	.78	11	.02	.72	7	.01	.79	9	.02
22	.77	11	.02	.73	7	.01	.78	10	.02
23	.78	11	.02	.70	7	.01	.79	10	.02
24	.73	10	.02	.74	7	.01	.79	10	.02
25	.74	10	.02	.77	7	.01	.75	10	.02
26	.86	10	.02	.78	7	.01	.77	10	.02
27	.79	10	.02	1.0	10	.03	.78	10	.02
28	.80	10	.02	7.0	84	3.1	.98	13	.12
29	.75	10	.02	---	---	---	82	327	227
30	.74	11	.02	---	---	---	1.8	50	.24
31	.74	11	.02	---	---	---	1.9	35	.18
TOTAL	40.67	---	9.28	25.04	---	3.46	110.79	---	228.35
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	.95	32	.08	.36	17	.02	.81	11	.02
2	.83	27	.06	.35	16	.02	.80	11	.02
3	.86	20	.05	.35	15	.01	.80	12	.03
4	.74	23	.05	.32	14	.01	.78	12	.03
5	.72	20	.04	.32	14	.01	.77	12	.02
6	.73	19	.04	.32	13	.01	.76	12	.02
7	.70	18	.03	.30	12	.01	.73	12	.02
8	.68	17	.03	.29	11	.01	.75	12	.02
9	.66	16	.03	.28	10	.01	.73	11	.02
10	.61	15	.02	.28	10	.01	.70	11	.02
11	.58	13	.02	.29	10	.01	.68	11	.02
12	.57	11	.02	.36	10	.01	.67	10	.02
13	.60	9	.01	.35	10	.01	.64	10	.02
14	.56	6	.01	5.6	59	.79	.61	11	.02
15	.61	4	.01	163	418	440	.60	11	.02
16	.82	4	.01	11	110	21	.63	11	.02
17	.62	4	.01	164	587	1060	.63	11	.02
18	.55	5	.01	239	546	796	.63	11	.02
19	.49	6	.01	9.9	80	2.1	.64	10	.02
20	.48	8	.01	3.3	20	.18	.62	10	.02
21	.46	10	.01	2.1	14	.08	.68	10	.02
22	.43	12	.01	1.6	14	.06	.66	11	.02
23	35	160	54	1.4	13	.05	.63	12	.02
24	4.6	109	1.9	1.2	12	.04	.64	12	.02
25	1.5	45	.18	1.1	11	.03	.65	10	.02
26	.66	25	.04	1.0	11	.03	.70	11	.02
27	.51	20	.03	.99	12	.03	.66	11	.02
28	.43	20	.02	.94	12	.03	.62	11	.02
29	.41	19	.02	.89	10	.02	.60	11	.02
30	.39	18	.02	.86	10	.02	.60	11	.02
31	---	---	---	.83	10	.02	---	---	---
TOTAL	57.75	---	56.78	612.88	---	2320.63	20.42	---	0.62

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.68	10	.02	.74	29	.06	.59	6	.01
2	.67	10	.02	.73	10	.02	.61	6	.01
3	.67	10	.02	.68	8	.01	.55	6	.01
4	.67	10	.02	.66	7	.01	.47	6	.01
5	.61	10	.02	.76	8	.02	.51	6	.01
6	.56	10	.02	.59	6	.01	.63	6	.01
7	.57	9	.01	.48	7	.01	.51	6	.01
8	.56	9	.01	.43	6	.01	2.1	42	.50
9	.55	8	.01	.40	6	.01	1.7	20	.09
10	.49	7	.01	.40	6	.01	.65	8	.01
11	.47	7	.01	.38	6	.01	.58	8	.01
12	.47	7	.01	.42	7	.01	17	85	22
13	.46	7	.01	.84	15	.03	34	252	50
14	.47	7	.01	.52	11	.02	3.1	60	.66
15	4.6	64	.59	.47	9	.01	1.7	45	.21
16	1.2	62	.76	.43	6	.01	1.2	37	.12
17	.88	32	.08	.39	6	.01	.90	32	.08
18	.80	30	.06	.44	7	.01	.75	29	.06
19	.90	32	.08	.44	8	.01	.60	26	.04
20	4.4	74	.88	.38	8	.01	.63	27	.05
21	1.1	36	.11	.85	15	.03	.60	26	.04
22	.80	30	.06	.51	10	.01	.60	26	.04
23	.82	30	.07	.43	10	.01	.72	28	.05
24	.81	30	.07	.40	9	.01	2.0	44	.26
25	.82	30	.07	.38	8	.01	27	189	30
26	.81	30	.07	.47	10	.01	1.8	40	.19
27	.73	30	.06	6.5	93	2.1	2.0	48	.44
28	.81	28	.06	1.1	25	.07	4.4	84	1.8
29	.84	31	.07	.68	12	.02	1.8	40	.19
30	.80	30	.06	.54	7	.01	1.1	35	.10
31	.77	29	.06	.51	6	.01	---	---	---
TOTAL	29.79	---	3.41	22.95	---	2.59	110.80	---	107.01
YEAR	1930.39		4022.08						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	2.8	54	.64	4.3	68	.79	2.3	7	.04
2	9.8	109	4.5	3.4	62	.57	2.2	8	.05
3	2.3	45	.28	3.1	59	.49	2.0	6	.03
4	17	95	36	3.0	58	.47	2.0	7	.04
5	17	184	20	3.0	57	.46	2.2	7	.04
6	251	643	684	2.8	52	.39	2.2	7	.04
7	189	542	549	2.7	50	.36	2.3	7	.04
8	54	399	171	2.5	50	.34	2.3	6	.04
9	8.6	100	2.3	2.6	50	.35	2.5	6	.04
10	5.2	80	1.1	2.5	50	.34	2.5	5	.03
11	4.1	65	.72	2.6	50	.35	2.5	5	.03
12	3.6	62	.60	3.2	55	.48	2.4	4	.03
13	3.4	62	.57	4.6	80	.99	2.2	5	.03
14	3.2	60	.52	3.4	20	.18	2.1	5	.03
15	3.2	60	.52	87	359	253	2.2	5	.03
16	3.2	60	.52	12	125	4.1	1.9	5	.03
17	3.1	60	.50	7.6	100	2.1	2.0	5	.03
18	14	132	12	31	228	58	1.9	5	.03
19	5.2	85	1.2	5.2	80	1.1	1.9	5	.03
20	3.4	70	.64	4.7	80	1.0	1.8	5	.02
21	3.2	65	.56	34	185	87	1.8	5	.02
22	3.1	60	.50	4.5	20	.24	1.7	5	.02
23	35	217	56	3.8	12	.12	1.6	5	.02
24	34	218	26	3.4	12	.11	1.6	5	.02
25	10	85	2.3	3.0	11	.09	1.7	5	.02
26	6.2	88	1.8	2.8	10	.08	1.6	4	.02
27	5.1	85	1.2	2.6	8	.06	1.4	4	.02
28	3.6	65	.63	2.5	7	.05	1.4	3	.01
29	21	172	19	2.4	7	.05	1.4	4	.02
30	6.3	90	1.8	2.4	7	.05	1.4	4	.02
31	25	170	43	---	---	---	1.3	5	.02
TOTAL	755.6	---	1639.40	252.6	---	413.71	60.3	---	0.89

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	1.4	5	.02	1.1	7	.02	.88	6	.01
2	1.6	5	.02	1.1	7	.02	.85	6	.01
3	1.4	5	.02	1.1	8	.02	.77	6	.01
4	1.5	5	.02	5.9	61	3.6	.79	6	.01
5	1.5	5	.02	1.9	45	.23	.80	6	.01
6	1.5	4	.02	1.2	25	.08	.80	6	.01
7	1.5	4	.02	1.1	14	.04	.79	6	.01
8	1.5	5	.02	1.1	10	.03	.75	6	.01
9	2.0	5	.03	1.1	9	.03	.72	6	.01
10	1.8	5	.02	1.1	8	.02	.72	6	.01
11	1.6	5	.02	1.1	7	.02	.76	6	.01
12	1.5	5	.02	1.1	6	.02	.74	6	.01
13	1.5	5	.02	1.0	6	.02	.74	7	.01
14	1.4	5	.02	1.0	6	.02	.82	12	.03
15	1.3	5	.02	1.0	6	.02	1.8	49	.25
16	1.4	5	.02	1.0	6	.02	.81	22	.05
17	1.4	5	.02	1.0	6	.02	.75	17	.03
18	1.3	5	.02	1.0	6	.02	.73	17	.03
19	1.3	5	.02	1.0	6	.02	.73	16	.03
20	1.2	5	.02	.99	6	.02	.73	15	.03
21	1.2	5	.02	.95	6	.02	.72	15	.03
22	1.3	5	.02	.94	6	.02	.70	14	.03
23	1.4	5	.02	.90	6	.01	.69	13	.02
24	1.4	5	.02	.88	6	.01	.72	13	.03
25	1.4	5	.02	.85	6	.01	.74	13	.03
26	1.3	5	.02	.83	6	.01	.75	13	.03
27	1.3	5	.02	.82	6	.01	.73	12	.02
28	1.3	5	.02	.91	6	.01	.69	11	.02
29	1.3	5	.02	---	---	---	1.3	32	.17
30	1.2	5	.02	---	---	---	.80	30	.06
31	1.2	6	.02	---	---	---	1.0	23	.07
TOTAL	43.9	---	0.63	33.97	---	4.39	25.32	---	1.09
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	1.1	7	.02	2.2	6	.04	.96	35	.09
2	.73	7	.01	1.7	5	.02	2.8	49	.77
3	.71	7	.01	1.5	5	.02	1.2	30	.10
4	1.0	20	.05	1.4	5	.02	.92	30	.07
5	2.1	40	.39	1.4	5	.02	3.5	101	3.8
6	1.4	25	.09	1.4	5	.02	.99	29	.08
7	.83	10	.02	2.8	52	.48	.91	---	---
8	27	158	72	17	119	19	.87	25	.06
9	3.5	20	.19	41	226	122	4.3	70	1.9
10	1.2	7	.02	21	159	20	1.3	30	.11
11	1.1	6	.02	18	173	14	.96	28	.07
12	.89	6	.01	2.9	60	.47	.91	25	.06
13	.84	6	.01	173	475	667	1.3	35	.12
14	.80	6	.01	87	219	274	1.5	40	.16
15	.84	6	.01	2.4	25	.16	.93	15	.04
16	.89	5	.01	1.4	20	.08	.95	15	.04
17	.82	5	.01	1.1	18	.05	.87	14	.03
18	.76	5	.01	2.8	64	1.5	.84	14	.03
19	.73	5	.01	5.4	80	4.7	.81	14	.03
20	7.4	45	5.3	1.3	20	.07	.80	13	.03
21	1.6	18	.08	1.0	18	.05	.79	13	.03
22	.86	10	.02	.99	15	.04	.78	13	.03
23	.73	10	.02	.92	15	.04	.79	13	.03
24	.69	10	.02	.88	15	.04	.78	13	.03
25	.66	10	.02	.83	15	.03	.76	12	.02
26	.62	10	.02	.84	15	.03	.74	12	.02
27	.69	14	.03	.83	15	.03	.83	13	.03
28	1.3	29	.17	.84	17	.04	.78	13	.03
29	40	175	115	.82	17	.04	.75	13	.03
30	4.7	17	.22	.79	19	.04	.76	14	.03
31	---	---	---	3.1	56	.75	---	---	---
TOTAL	106.49	---	193.80	398.54	---	1124.78	35.38	---	7.87

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50056900 QUEBRADA MAMEY NEAR GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	.75	14	.03	.67	10	.02	1.6	40	.17
2	.75	15	.03	.64	10	.02	.91	15	.04
3	.72	15	.03	.64	10	.02	.79	10	.02
4	.69	15	.03	.64	10	.02	.69	10	.02
5	.70	15	.03	.59	10	.02	.68	10	.02
6	1.1	30	.09	.57	10	.02	.74	10	.02
7	.87	17	.04	.62	15	.03	.66	10	.02
8	.79	16	.03	1.1	25	.07	.62	10	.02
9	.78	15	.03	.75	12	.02	.62	10	.02
10	.76	15	.03	.77	10	.02	.60	10	.02
11	.79	15	.03	2.0	50	.57	.57	10	.02
12	.82	15	.03	.84	7	.02	.56	10	.02
13	.80	15	.03	.74	5	.01	.56	9	.01
14	.72	15	.03	.84	5	.01	.56	9	.01
15	.75	14	.03	1.1	15	.04	.59	8	.01
16	.77	13	.03	.91	10	.02	.55	8	.01
17	.69	12	.02	.75	10	.02	.53	9	.01
18	.64	12	.02	.75	10	.02	.51	9	.01
19	.61	12	.02	.73	10	.02	.50	9	.01
20	.59	12	.02	.70	10	.02	.49	9	.01
21	.59	12	.02	.70	10	.02	.49	10	.01
22	.60	12	.02	.72	10	.02	.52	10	.01
23	.62	12	.02	.72	10	.02	.55	10	.01
24	.59	11	.02	.72	10	.02	.74	10	.02
25	.58	11	.02	.71	10	.02	.68	10	.02
26	.57	11	.02	.68	10	.02	.63	10	.02
27	.57	11	.02	.69	10	.02	.57	8	.01
28	.59	11	.02	11	65	10	.54	6	.01
29	.59	10	.02	55	255	98	.51	3	.00
30	2.0	41	.79	1.6	40	.17	.49	2	.00
31	.92	12	.03	1.0	30	.08	---	---	---
TOTAL	23.31	---	1.63	89.89	---	109.40	19.05	---	0.60
YEAR	1844.35		3498.19						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'30", long 65°58'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 181, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) east of Gurabo, and 4.5 mi (7.6 km) upstream from Rio Grande de Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--60.2 mi² (155.9 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1958 (occasional low-flow measurements only), January to September 1959 (monthly measurements only), October 1959 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 136.58 ft (41.63 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--29 years (1960-88), 138 ft³/s (3,908 m³/s), 31.13 in/yr (791 mm/yr), 99,980 acre-ft/yr (123 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 127 ft³/s (3.60 m³/s), 92,000 acre-ft/yr (110 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 74,600 ft³/s (2,133 m³/s), Sept. 6, 1960, gage height, 27.7 ft (8.44m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 8,000 ft³/s (227 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement at gage height 21.6 ft (6.58 m), contracted opening, culvert and flow over road measurement at gage height 23.76 ft (7.242 m), and estimate of peak flow based on slope-area measurements of Rio Gurabo and Rio Valenciano, 7.0 mi (11.3 km) upstream, adjusted for channel storage and flow from intervening area; minimum discharge, 4.5 ft³/s (0.127 m³/s), Feb. 21, 25, 1968.

EXTREMES OUTSIDE PERIOD OF RECORD.--Approximate elevation to gage datum of the Aug. 4, 1945 flood, as pointed out by local residents, 26.6 ft (8.11 m).

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 18	2100	9,670	274	15.37	4.685	July 7	0600	4,040	114	9.89	3.014
Nov. 24	2015	8,770	248	14.84	4.523	July 14	0345	3,270	92.6	8.79	2.679
Nov. 27	unknown	45,000	1,270	24.35	7.422	Aug. 24	1730	15,800	447	18.18	5.541
Dec. 6	0445	3,340	94.6	8.89	2.710	Sept.11	1415	10,900	309	16.02	4.883
Dec. 8	0100	*50,600	1,430	*25.09	7.647						

Minimum discharge, 15 ft³/s (0.425 m³/s), Apr. 22, 23, June 8, 9.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN VALUES											
	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	50	59	143	394	139	37	23	21	32	570	52	60
2	33	45	455	192	113	50	22	20	23	793	47	55
3	33	40	119	138	147	36	21	17	20	172	44	51
4	57	123	95	116	89	32	20	16	19	87	57	49
5	41	100	79	124	66	32	20	16	18	62	46	46
6	32	235	641	127	69	30	27	218	18	119	41	40
7	35	104	9720	121	52	30	38	155	17	1280	68	42
8	30	60	11500	117	50	30	24	46	16	148	76	45
9	30	51	516	121	57	29	22	29	17	92	49	221
10	29	50	315	121	74	27	20	77	21	96	119	210
11	23	46	227	113	55	27	22	162	18	98	217	2870
12	22	58	186	120	51	27	21	53	53	102	109	930
13	22	63	164	104	89	27	19	32	29	69	58	320
14	256	41	150	107	72	28	18	31	40	780	48	353
15	161	39	143	98	54	26	32	59	585	108	47	232
16	173	44	139	91	62	26	27	41	244	77	45	161
17	667	73	131	89	50	26	20	32	164	66	96	102
18	2100	150	128	90	45	26	20	31	62	72	68	75
19	557	66	146	84	43	25	22	33	43	94	49	e597
20	153	70	179	82	42	26	17	46	272	68	42	e191
21	97	47	173	79	40	27	18	74	251	56	39	e121
22	72	44	212	75	39	26	15	45	162	129	70	120
23	62	181	139	74	37	24	46	29	112	84	131	155
24	70	4620	128	73	39	24	26	26	179	65	3290	101
25	97	1120	121	72	41	24	20	24	159	65	e730	81
26	85	1110	130	73	50	26	18	22	80	62	e166	65
27	78	e19800	129	71	245	29	19	23	75	64	e161	56
28	72	2310	126	73	56	32	18	20	53	59	e135	54
29	70	386	117	74	41	32	17	23	172	73	e113	54
30	53	207	113	73	---	28	16	34	71	71	85	53
31	59	---	179	67	---	28	---	83	---	59	69	---
TOTAL	5319	31342	26743	3353	2007	897	668	1538	3025	5740	6367	7510
MEAN	172	1045	863	108	69.2	28.9	22.3	49.6	101	185	205	250
MAX	2100	19800	11500	394	245	50	46	218	585	1280	3290	2870
MIN	22	39	79	67	37	24	15	16	16	56	39	40
AC-FT	10550	62170	53040	6650	3980	1780	1320	3050	6000	11390	12630	14900
CFSM	2.85	17.4	14.3	1.80	1.15	.48	.37	.82	1.67	3.08	3.41	4.16
IN.	3.29	19.37	16.53	2.07	1.24	.55	.41	.95	1.87	3.55	3.93	4.64

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 91375 MEAN 250 MAX 19800 MIN 17 AC-FT 181200 CFSM 4.16 IN. 56.46
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 94509 MEAN 258 MAX 19800 MIN 15 AC-FT 187500 CFSM 4.29 IN. 58.40

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURAGO, PR--Continued
WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 15	1229	133	174	28.0	APR, 08	1427	31.9	346	31.0
NOV, 17	1352	72.9	325	28.0	MAY, 09	1254	28.3	274	30.0
JAN, 11	1616	108.0	308	26.5	JUN, 06	1200	16.7	351	31.0
FEB, 05	1029	62.2	265	24.0	JUL, 14	1150	609	209	25.0
MAR, 04	1021	31.9	328	25.0					

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- Water years 1984 to 1986

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: October 1983 to September 1986.

INSTRUMENTATION.-- USD-49 and automatic sediment sampler.

REMARKS.-- The suspended-sediment data included in this report is part of a 5-year hydrologic investigation conducted in the Rio Grande de Loiza Basin to account the amount of suspended-sediment transported to Lago Loiza, a water supply reservoir.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATION: Maximum daily mean, 1,870 mg/L May 18, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 6 mg/L August 06, 1985.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily mean, 93,200 tons (84,570 tonnes) May 18, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 0.23 tons (0.20) May 12, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEARS 1984-86.--

Water Year	suspended-sediment concentration (mg/L)		suspended-sediment discharge (tons per day)	
	maximum	minimum	maximum	minimum
1984	732 (Nov. 06)	9 (March 24)	7,030 (Nov. 06)	0.23 (May 12)
1985	1,870 (May 18)	6 (August 06)	93,200 (May 18)	0.44 (August 06)
1986	1,670 (Oct. 06)	12 (several days)	60,800 (Oct. 06)	0.53 (April 26)

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	83	50	11	64	60	10	60	50	8.1
2	60	50	8.1	61	50	8.2	100	50	13
3	82	49	12	52	45	6.3	76	50	10
4	58	48	7.5	1960	514	4320	54	42	6.1
5	52	42	5.9	1520	542	4770	52	42	5.9
6	49	41	5.4	2700	732	7030	70	50	9.5
7	50	40	5.4	297	120	96	52	50	7.0
8	95	59	17	154	80	33	61	50	8.2
9	127	78	24	118	50	16	58	50	7.8
10	76	50	10	101	50	14	53	50	7.2
11	54	45	6.6	89	60	14	51	48	6.6
12	67	54	11	83	60	13	48	45	5.8
13	58	50	7.8	75	60	12	46	40	5.0
14	53	50	7.2	71	60	12	46	40	5.0
15	312	123	297	68	60	11	45	40	4.9
16	129	93	47	69	60	11	50	40	5.4
17	95	70	24	66	50	8.9	49	40	5.3
18	73	70	14	62	50	8.4	46	40	5.0
19	121	83	35	59	50	8.0	45	38	4.6
20	92	71	23	58	50	7.8	42	37	4.2
21	142	114	122	56	50	7.6	44	38	4.5
22	69	60	11	55	50	7.4	45	40	4.9
23	54	45	6.6	53	50	7.2	51	40	5.5
24	47	42	5.3	53	50	7.2	42	40	4.5
25	45	40	4.9	53	50	7.2	39	40	4.2
26	90	65	25	50	40	5.4	36	32	3.1
27	52	42	5.9	49	40	5.3	39	35	3.7
28	46	40	5.0	734	233	1340	38	33	3.4
29	62	48	9.1	178	100	73	39	32	3.4
30	112	73	28	73	50	9.9	43	37	4.3
31	302	154	231	---	---	---	50	40	5.4
TOTAL	2807	---	1032.7	9081	---	17879.8	1570	---	181.5

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	48	40	5.2	27	26	1.9	31	30	2.5
2	37	35	3.5	27	26	1.9	32	30	2.6
3	33	32	2.9	28	26	2.0	30	30	2.4
4	32	32	2.8	29	27	2.1	28	30	2.3
5	31	30	2.5	28	26	2.0	29	30	2.3
6	30	30	2.4	28	26	2.0	29	30	2.3
7	29	30	2.3	35	31	2.9	28	30	2.3
8	33	30	2.7	36	30	2.9	28	26	2.0
9	33	30	2.7	61	40	9.5	29	26	2.0
10	33	30	2.7	107	72	29	28	26	2.0
11	32	30	2.6	87	59	16	27	26	1.9
12	33	30	2.7	66	50	8.9	25	24	1.6
13	52	43	10	233	122	134	24	24	1.6
14	87	66	17	118	75	24	25	24	1.6
15	46	40	5.0	231	104	267	24	24	1.6
16	38	30	3.1	1610	391	3630	24	23	1.5
17	47	30	3.8	111	80	24	24	23	1.5
18	38	33	3.4	65	40	7.0	25	23	1.6
19	34	32	2.9	50	40	5.4	23	22	1.4
20	109	78	52	44	38	4.5	21	20	1.1
21	51	45	6.2	39	38	4.0	20	20	1.1
22	38	35	3.6	37	32	3.2	20	20	1.1
23	34	35	3.2	35	31	2.9	21	20	1.1
24	34	30	2.8	34	30	2.8	24	9	.58
25	36	30	2.9	33	30	2.7	20	16	.86
26	38	30	3.1	32	30	2.6	19	10	.51
27	31	30	2.5	33	30	2.7	18	10	.49
28	31	30	2.5	34	32	2.9	17	10	.46
29	30	29	2.3	32	31	2.7	17	10	.46
30	29	30	2.3	---	---	---	17	10	.46
31	28	26	2.0	---	---	---	17	10	.46
TOTAL	1235	---	165.6	3330	---	4203.5	744	---	45.68
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	16	10	.43	14	18	.78	138	50	19
2	16	10	.43	14	15	.57	111	35	10
3	16	10	.43	13	15	.61	81	25	5.5
4	16	10	.43	12	15	.65	100	36	5.9
5	16	10	.43	11	18	.73	73	25	4.9
6	17	10	.46	11	17	.69	262	110	130
7	18	10	.49	11	17	.69	399	175	258
8	19	11	.56	10	15	.61	254	100	69
9	17	11	.50	9.6	17	.64	155	60	25
10	16	10	.43	11	12	.39	1290	439	2970
11	15	10	.41	10	12	.32	352	159	176
12	15	10	.43	8.6	10	.23	170	110	50
13	14	10	.41	15	12	.49	330	159	262
14	14	10	.38	28	15	1.1	168	95	47
15	14	10	.38	15	12	.49	109	70	21
16	14	11	.42	14	11	.42	88	70	17
17	12	12	.42	13	10	.35	76	70	14
18	12	10	.32	13	10	.35	69	52	9.3
19	12	10	.32	12	10	.32	65	50	8.8
20	13	10	.35	12	10	.32	82	50	8.8
21	14	12	.45	13	10	.35	62	48	8.3
22	14	12	.45	14	11	.42	54	48	8.2
23	14	12	.45	17	20	.92	47	47	7.7
24	13	12	.42	26	25	1.8	44	48	7.6
25	12	12	.42	22	25	1.5	44	49	7.3
26	11	12	.42	80	48	18	40	48	6.5
27	21	21	2.0	54	42	6.1	39	43	5.3
28	40	28	3.0	139	73	56	39	34	3.7
29	20	20	1.1	64	50	8.6	211	104	199
30	15	20	.81	448	195	452	167	96	52
31	---	---	---	362	150	210	---	---	---
TOTAL	476	---	17.95	1496.2	---	766.44	5119	---	4416.8

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1983 TO SEPTEMBER 1984

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	87	70	16	51	50	6.9	33	38	3.4
2	72	60	12	319	150	190	31	30	2.5
3	71	50	9.6	94	75	19	49	41	8.3
4	66	50	8.9	78	70	15	61	20	4.4
5	355	283	273	77	60	12	140	71	68
6	116	85	27	52	50	7.0	101	102	62
7	77	60	12	43	45	5.2	66	30	5.3
8	74	60	12	38	32	3.3	41	20	2.2
9	72	60	12	36	31	3.0	36	15	1.5
10	80	65	14	34	30	2.8	47	18	2.3
11	70	70	13	29	28	2.2	39	20	2.1
12	57	55	8.5	26	25	1.8	96	51	22
13	48	50	6.5	25	23	1.6	383	136	392
14	38	50	5.1	23	23	1.4	972	278	889
15	80	70	15	22	23	1.4	163	120	53
16	55	39	5.8	30	23	1.9	509	176	874
17	45	35	4.3	26	21	1.5	633	337	1540
18	46	45	5.6	23	21	1.3	669	288	801
19	44	38	4.5	22	21	1.2	326	161	182
20	46	38	4.7	24	21	1.4	1010	368	1780
21	43	48	5.6	31	21	1.8	429	190	220
22	79	40	8.5	25	20	1.4	186	120	60
23	65	32	5.6	25	19	1.3	119	80	26
24	51	32	4.4	22	20	1.2	93	70	18
25	43	30	3.6	19	20	1.0	80	60	13
26	39	30	3.2	622	227	2260	67	50	9.0
27	40	30	3.2	839	302	1620	59	40	6.4
28	36	35	3.4	151	95	39	59	40	6.4
29	224	199	505	98	60	16	60	38	6.2
30	269	150	109	149	83	70	64	30	5.2
31	76	60	12	44	50	5.9	---	---	---
TOTAL	2564	---	1133.0	3097	---	4297.5	6701	---	7065.2
YEAR	38220.2		41205.67						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	65	55	9.7	165	96	53	72	55	11
2	55	48	7.1	391	168	259	154	91	63
3	120	87	41	2440	694	5430	147	90	36
4	80	61	16	1180	405	1690	86	65	15
5	95	70	27	2940	754	8540	74	60	12
6	115	83	31	3850	969	11400	67	41	7.4
7	75	58	14	2070	605	4530	63	43	7.3
8	47	40	5.1	599	228	381	59	38	6.1
9	486	202	751	510	248	483	58	40	6.3
10	430	204	351	320	156	135	81	57	13
11	172	100	47	200	140	98	171	93	152
12	160	105	45	150	110	45	334	157	240
13	110	80	24	145	95	37	160	95	60
14	1410	396	3360	240	111	95	76	56	11
15	241	121	77	325	156	153	65	50	8.8
16	161	91	38	148	90	36	65	50	8.8
17	195	105	72	165	95	42	80	58	13
18	119	70	22	160	90	39	61	60	9.9
19	94	65	16	134	85	31	54	62	9.0
20	126	79	28	125	80	27	54	62	9.0
21	125	80	27	115	75	23	48	40	5.2
22	80	55	12	110	70	21	47	40	5.1
23	76	56	11	125	70	24	46	40	5.0
24	68	58	11	109	72	21	54	40	5.8
25	136	83	33	100	70	19	81	57	13
26	95	70	18	211	114	89	70	52	9.8
27	80	60	13	104	70	20	84	59	15
28	123	76	27	91	65	16	104	71	21
29	139	87	33	81	60	13	62	47	7.9
30	145	90	48	79	60	13	79	54	11
31	92	68	17	---	---	---	87	60	14
TOTAL	5515	---	5231.9	17382	---	33763	2743	---	811.4

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	63	52	10	32	25	2.2	99	65	18
2	287	143	136	33	26	2.3	48	42	5.4
3	96	66	18	29	26	2.0	36	35	3.4
4	79	57	12	27	25	1.8	32	30	2.6
5	68	50	9.2	26	25	1.8	28	30	2.3
6	97	65	17	25	25	1.7	71	35	2.0
7	88	60	14	25	25	1.7	77	60	21
8	60	60	9.7	24	25	1.6	152	86	37
9	52	60	8.4	24	28	1.8	79	58	13
10	51	60	8.3	24	28	1.8	47	50	6.3
11	50	60	8.1	26	30	2.1	35	57	5.4
12	44	50	5.9	24	33	2.1	29	45	3.5
13	42	40	4.5	22	40	2.4	28	35	2.6
14	40	35	3.8	22	46	2.7	24	28	1.8
15	40	35	3.8	29	30	2.3	22	24	1.4
16	38	35	3.6	27	25	1.8	22	23	1.4
17	36	35	3.4	27	25	1.8	24	25	1.6
18	36	35	3.4	30	28	2.3	41	30	3.3
19	34	30	2.8	29	26	2.0	45	35	4.3
20	34	30	2.8	45	30	3.6	26	25	1.8
21	32	30	2.6	32	30	2.6	34	25	2.3
22	31	30	2.5	28	25	1.9	23	22	1.4
23	30	30	2.4	25	24	1.6	20	20	1.1
24	30	28	2.3	37	32	3.2	19	18	.92
25	29	25	2.0	37	31	3.1	17	15	.69
26	36	25	2.4	34	30	2.8	16	15	.65
27	35	25	2.4	48	36	5.2	23	25	1.6
28	34	25	2.3	273	129	142	35	27	2.6
29	33	25	2.2	---	---	---	1530	451	3330
30	30	25	2.0	---	---	---	147	88	35
31	30	25	2.0	---	---	---	245	126	116
TOTAL	1685	---	309.8	1064	---	204.2	3024	---	3630.36
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	78	60	13	35	30	2.8	51	19	2.6
2	49	30	4.0	33	30	2.7	49	20	2.6
3	40	30	3.2	40	32	3.5	49	22	2.9
4	35	30	2.8	36	30	2.9	47	23	2.9
5	31	29	2.4	33	30	2.7	45	24	2.9
6	30	28	2.3	38	35	3.6	42	23	2.6
7	32	28	2.4	33	30	2.7	41	23	2.5
8	30	28	2.3	29	30	2.3	43	23	2.7
9	29	27	2.1	28	30	2.3	43	23	2.7
10	27	25	1.8	28	28	2.1	42	22	2.5
11	25	20	1.4	28	26	2.0	41	21	2.3
12	51	40	6.4	45	33	4.0	39	20	2.1
13	33	30	2.7	66	45	8.0	32	20	1.7
14	31	29	2.4	436	203	353	30	20	1.6
15	41	33	3.7	5930	1080	30500	27	20	1.5
16	55	43	6.4	1370	422	3180	27	20	1.5
17	55	43	6.4	2120	597	5150	28	19	1.4
18	46	45	5.6	10900	1870	93200	29	20	1.6
19	36	30	2.9	664	240	473	28	18	1.4
20	27	25	1.8	280	122	76	27	19	1.4
21	29	25	2.0	165	95	42	29	20	1.6
22	25	24	1.6	130	43	15	27	20	1.5
23	1020	262	2120	107	42	12	26	20	1.4
24	426	183	301	93	39	9.8	26	20	1.4
25	206	112	69	84	32	7.3	29	19	1.5
26	133	82	32	76	29	6.0	28	17	1.3
27	68	55	10	69	21	3.9	26	14	.98
28	49	45	6.0	63	18	3.1	23	14	.87
29	42	35	4.0	57	9	1.4	23	21	1.3
30	39	32	3.4	55	8	1.2	20	23	1.2
31	---	---	---	52	11	1.5	---	---	---
TOTAL	2818	---	2625.0	23123	---	133076.8	1017	---	56.45

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	24	36	2.3	29	10	.78	56	18	2.2
2	27	41	3.0	55	19	2.8	45	16	1.8
3	25	51	3.4	39	12	1.3	41	14	1.2
4	27	53	3.9	31	8	.67	32	10	.81
5	22	54	3.2	28	7	.53	82	44	28
6	23	40	2.5	27	6	.44	50	43	7.0
7	21	30	1.7	38	11	1.1	30	28	2.3
8	22	25	1.5	31	9	.75	208	95	146
9	23	22	1.4	30	8	.65	247	122	145
10	24	25	1.6	43	14	1.6	58	46	7.2
11	23	25	1.6	36	11	1.1	50	40	5.4
12	26	25	1.8	32	9	.78	695	194	2070
13	27	27	2.0	49	16	2.1	2380	675	5520
14	24	26	1.9	45	15	1.8	343	157	150
15	101	70	31	32	9	.78	173	102	51
16	218	104	73	27	10	.73	101	83	26
17	195	102	63	26	19	1.3	83	56	13
18	88	62	17	23	16	.99	59	45	7.2
19	48	35	4.0	27	20	1.5	49	40	5.3
20	401	202	472	29	26	2.0	41	32	3.5
21	126	70	24	41	43	4.8	37	30	3.0
22	65	48	8.4	36	40	3.9	35	30	2.8
23	51	38	5.2	27	34	2.5	40	35	3.8
24	77	27	5.6	26	35	2.5	87	69	21
25	53	18	2.6	26	33	2.3	778	301	1130
26	51	17	2.3	31	33	2.8	137	90	38
27	42	13	1.5	466	196	399	98	77	27
28	42	13	1.5	229	119	77	253	126	164
29	49	16	2.1	77	60	7.5	159	97	47
30	41	12	1.3	46	30	4.2	75	70	14
31	32	10	.86	52	34	5.1	---	---	---
TOTAL	2018	---	747.16	1734	---	535.30	6522	---	9643.51
YEAR	68645		190634.88						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	210	123	148	235	150	106	65	50	8.8
2	725	302	907	199	120	64	65	50	8.8
3	205	129	79	177	110	53	65	50	8.8
4	214	135	133	149	90	36	62	50	8.4
5	833	319	921	177	104	59	89	60	14
6	8800	1670	60800	164	100	44	97	60	16
7	5470	1270	26400	139	82	31	82	55	12
8	1900	555	4740	114	80	25	70	55	10
9	413	180	201	104	80	22	69	52	9.7
10	261	130	92	98	70	19	70	50	9.5
11	202	120	65	101	70	19	68	50	9.2
12	168	100	45	173	110	51	74	50	10
13	149	90	36	265	150	139	71	50	9.6
14	136	85	31	198	160	86	61	52	8.6
15	119	75	24	2060	603	5540	60	52	8.4
16	111	75	22	584	232	458	63	53	9.0
17	128	90	31	233	120	75	59	51	8.1
18	587	218	1010	583	248	521	59	50	8.0
19	282	140	107	231	130	81	59	50	8.0
20	148	90	36	190	110	56	63	52	8.3
21	126	80	27	410	183	332	55	50	7.4
22	113	80	24	125	90	30	54	48	7.0
23	1170	411	2890	96	70	18	52	45	6.3
24	1840	560	4820	88	65	15	53	43	6.2
25	860	331	1810	83	50	11	50	42	5.7
26	351	163	176	80	50	11	56	45	6.8
27	317	160	137	78	55	12	49	45	6.0
28	240	140	91	72	50	9.7	47	42	5.3
29	973	398	2210	69	50	9.3	47	38	4.8
30	384	176	204	66	50	8.9	43	35	4.1
31	406	277	368	---	---	---	43	39	4.5
TOTAL	27841	---	108585	7341	---	7941.9	1920	---	257.3

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	44	45	5.3	32	26	2.2	21	20	1.1
2	59	45	7.2	30	26	2.1	21	20	1.1
3	47	42	5.3	31	25	2.1	21	20	1.1
4	48	43	5.6	64	60	10	20	20	1.1
5	48	43	5.6	70	45	8.5	27	21	1.5
6	40	39	4.2	39	38	4.0	25	21	1.4
7	37	38	3.8	32	30	2.6	23	20	1.2
8	35	35	3.3	30	30	2.4	21	20	1.1
9	83	60	13	30	29	2.3	20	20	1.1
10	94	80	20	29	28	2.2	20	20	1.1
11	50	45	6.1	28	30	2.3	21	20	1.1
12	41	40	4.4	27	31	2.3	25	22	1.5
13	36	39	3.8	25	32	2.2	22	25	1.5
14	34	35	3.2	24	30	1.9	38	35	3.6
15	33	30	2.7	24	28	1.8	173	98	64
16	33	30	2.7	25	25	1.7	51	50	6.9
17	76	54	19	25	25	1.7	32	38	3.3
18	56	45	6.8	30	28	2.3	26	30	2.1
19	41	30	3.3	31	27	2.3	20	25	1.4
20	35	30	2.8	28	23	1.7	20	20	1.1
21	37	31	3.1	28	22	1.7	19	18	.92
22	35	30	2.8	27	20	1.5	19	18	.92
23	35	30	2.8	25	19	1.3	16	15	.65
24	43	32	3.7	23	16	.99	19	15	.77
25	46	32	4.0	23	18	1.1	16	18	.78
26	37	31	3.1	24	19	1.2	25	19	1.3
27	31	30	2.5	21	20	1.1	24	18	1.2
28	30	28	2.3	21	20	1.1	19	15	.77
29	30	28	2.3	---	---	---	179	82	82
30	32	28	2.4	---	---	---	84	55	12
31	34	27	2.5	---	---	---	71	55	11
TOTAL	1360	---	159.6	846	---	68.59	1138	---	210.61
		APRIL			MAY			JUNE	
1	138	90	45	55	45	6.7	182	103	55
2	51	32	4.4	32	30	2.6	126	83	31
3	40	28	3.0	21	22	1.2	126	80	27
4	42	40	4.5	19	15	.77	85	50	11
5	129	70	43	15	15	.61	140	88	39
6	132	55	20	21	19	1.1	85	60	14
7	45	38	4.6	205	119	125	71	60	12
8	85	50	11	192	113	159	164	101	59
9	175	109	78	515	177	471	304	324	558
10	44	45	5.3	678	245	861	269	139	153
11	31	32	2.7	818	296	902	124	78	26
12	28	30	2.3	158	100	43	89	70	17
13	26	27	1.9	3090	797	13300	106	80	23
14	24	22	1.4	3050	535	10900	145	85	33
15	23	19	1.2	260	160	112	94	75	19
16	22	18	1.1	174	110	52	156	103	50
17	21	12	.68	136	90	33	96	72	19
18	19	12	.62	464	200	467	81	65	14
19	17	12	.55	249	137	108	102	67	18
20	24	13	.84	160	90	39	73	60	12
21	21	16	.91	136	80	29	60	50	8.1
22	20	18	.97	128	80	28	59	48	7.6
23	16	19	.82	104	75	21	66	43	7.7
24	16	18	.78	88	65	15	51	40	5.5
25	15	18	.73	72	60	12	50	30	4.1
26	13	15	.53	66	50	8.9	51	25	3.4
27	16	15	.65	71	50	9.6	55	22	3.3
28	49	38	5.0	68	50	9.2	66	22	3.9
29	1240	412	4660	75	50	10	61	22	3.6
30	253	200	137	70	45	8.5	57	22	3.4
31	---	---	---	476	230	582	---	---	---
TOTAL	2775	---	5039.48	11666	---	28318.18	3194	---	1240.6

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	51	22	3.0	55	45	6.7	99	75	20
2	50	21	2.8	40	35	3.8	68	50	9.2
3	49	20	2.6	32	30	2.6	48	35	4.5
4	47	20	2.5	29	25	2.0	42	35	4.0
5	45	20	2.4	27	24	1.7	41	35	3.9
6	126	55	50	26	22	1.5	69	50	9.3
7	122	132	53	29	20	1.6	57	35	5.4
8	48	55	7.1	67	45	8.1	39	31	3.3
9	37	32	3.2	27	30	2.2	35	29	2.7
10	34	30	2.8	31	40	3.3	33	25	2.2
11	33	30	2.7	98	78	30	31	23	1.9
12	40	30	3.2	50	40	5.4	29	25	2.0
13	34	30	2.8	39	30	3.2	29	28	2.2
14	34	25	2.3	152	94	78	41	25	2.8
15	73	40	7.9	38	28	2.9	32	25	2.2
16	55	40	5.9	52	35	4.9	29	22	1.7
17	37	28	2.8	33	25	2.2	27	20	1.5
18	36	27	2.6	29	25	2.0	26	19	1.3
19	31	27	2.3	28	25	1.9	25	19	1.3
20	28	25	1.9	27	25	1.8	24	19	1.2
21	28	22	1.7	23	25	1.6	23	19	1.2
22	26	21	1.5	25	25	1.7	24	20	1.3
23	26	21	1.5	30	22	1.8	29	20	1.6
24	25	21	1.4	30	20	1.6	57	25	3.8
25	25	20	1.4	31	21	1.8	49	25	3.3
26	23	20	1.2	27	20	1.5	37	25	2.5
27	24	20	1.3	26	18	1.3	31	22	1.8
28	27	20	1.5	102	57	76	32	22	1.9
29	34	25	2.3	1970	542	5890	28	21	1.6
30	285	169	247	132	80	29	26	21	1.5
31	146	88	45	87	60	14	---	---	---
TOTAL	1679	---	469.6	3392	---	6186.1	1160	---	103.1
YEAR	64312		158580.06						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	27	30	2.2	59	60	9.6	72	75	15
2	25	30	2.0	71	70	13	70	70	13
3	23	27	1.7	72	70	14	79	80	17
4	23	27	1.7	51	56	7.7	72	80	16
5	23	27	1.7	101	90	25	67	66	12
6	22	26	1.5	113	100	31	62	65	11
7	26	28	2.0	211	203	248	93	85	21
8	27	30	2.2	291	268	302	69	75	14
9	30	38	3.1	131	110	39	65	70	12
10	46	45	5.6	199	157	95	69	70	13
11	33	37	3.3	197	164	102	174	147	122
12	27	30	2.2	1530	929	5730	99	40	11
13	24	26	1.7	527	396	1020	92	50	12
14	31	33	2.8	244	197	145	107	90	26
15	51	60	8.3	209	160	90	84	60	14
16	120	110	41	280	217	189	55	85	22
17	66	65	12	186	150	75	73	80	16
18	39	40	4.2	120	100	32	70	75	14
19	29	33	2.6	93	65	16	61	66	11
20	25	29	2.0	93	40	10	65	66	12
21	22	25	1.5	76	28	5.7	63	65	11
22	218	182	220	75	22	4.5	56	65	9.8
23	63	69	13	68	18	3.3	55	60	8.9
24	87	85	20	64	15	2.6	54	60	8.7
25	164	148	122	96	70	18	86	85	20
26	116	114	48	181	159	88	65	70	12
27	176	189	171	218	190	139	84	70	16
28	146	136	70	115	110	34	102	105	29
29	66	70	12	95	95	24	65	70	12
30	61	65	11	96	85	22	57	60	9.2
31	61	62	10	---	---	---	57	58	8.9
TOTAL	1897	---	802.3	5862	---	8534.4	2382	---	549.5

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued
SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	54	55	8.0	70	75	14	44	18	2.1
2	53	52	7.4	44	50	5.9	42	18	2.0
3	50	52	7.0	38	43	4.4	41	18	2.0
4	51	60	8.3	35	30	2.8	76	65	13
5	88	80	19	35	22	2.1	174	157	107
6	119	110	35	39	18	1.9	61	35	5.8
7	187	158	98	38	15	1.5	49	30	4.0
8	66	70	12	35	12	1.1	45	28	3.4
9	71	70	13	31	7	.59	42	25	2.8
10	47	40	5.1	29	6	.47	42	21	2.4
11	44	25	3.0	192	181	139	42	23	2.6
12	41	18	2.0	73	75	15	73	55	11
13	39	15	1.6	136	127	96	47	12	1.5
14	39	18	1.9	154	142	68	42	12	1.4
15	45	25	3.0	101	100	27	42	13	1.5
16	38	25	2.6	64	60	10	95	62	54
17	35	25	2.4	56	45	6.8	152	140	68
18	34	22	2.0	52	39	5.5	77	85	18
19	33	21	1.9	50	38	5.1	37	45	4.5
20	33	20	1.8	48	35	4.5	31	40	3.3
21	31	19	1.6	48	32	4.1	27	35	2.6
22	31	19	1.6	46	28	3.5	26	30	2.1
23	49	35	4.6	44	25	3.0	25	25	1.7
24	54	25	3.6	41	20	2.2	22	20	1.2
25	37	22	2.1	42	18	2.0	24	20	1.3
26	35	22	2.1	43	15	1.7	24	20	1.3
27	33	21	1.9	47	15	1.9	22	20	1.2
28	32	20	1.7	45	15	1.8	21	20	1.1
29	33	25	2.2	---	---	---	20	20	1.1
30	145	134	71	---	---	---	20	20	1.1
31	74	90	18	---	---	---	18	20	.97
TOTAL	1721	---	345.4	1676	---	431.86	1503	---	325.97

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	18	19	.92	29	10	.78	57	60	9.2
2	17	17	.78	30	11	.89	169	152	164
3	18	15	.73	47	25	3.2	310	299	597
4	22	15	.89	44	40	4.8	176	200	93
5	21	12	.68	51	55	7.6	72	45	8.7
6	21	11	.62	348	285	425	59	35	5.6
7	30	11	.89	71	55	11	53	32	4.6
8	19	11	.56	48	31	4.0	47	30	3.8
9	18	11	.53	40	30	3.2	50	30	4.1
10	78	63	59	46	45	5.6	64	30	5.2
11	83	95	31	63	55	9.4	54	35	5.1
12	222	181	220	136	115	42	45	35	4.3
13	210	170	133	57	65	10	78	75	16
14	177	150	155	45	55	6.7	80	80	17
15	128	178	83	39	49	5.2	612	445	2780
16	58	60	9.4	36	42	4.1	316	277	320
17	341	285	532	34	36	3.3	128	110	38
18	88	90	21	53	35	3.1	98	100	26
19	55	60	8.9	72	50	9.7	360	320	750
20	49	45	6.0	379	255	438	1640	1150	7790
21	44	35	4.2	367	296	528	2050	1310	16100
22	41	38	4.2	167	150	68	3950	2370	34000
23	38	33	3.4	109	100	29	393	265	281
24	36	15	1.5	68	70	13	204	160	88
25	34	10	.92	155	150	63	160	130	56
26	33	9	.80	1060	714	5550	140	125	47
27	32	8	.69	474	427	1040	233	197	193
28	31	8	.67	187	180	91	205	183	114
29	30	10	.81	87	85	20	164	140	62
30	29	10	.78	81	70	15	138	110	41
31	---	---	---	57	60	9.2	---	---	---
TOTAL	2021	---	1282.87	4460	---	8423.77	12105	---	63623.6

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1986 TO SEPTEMBER 1987

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	109	40	12	36	35	3.4	54	60	8.7
2	97	15	3.9	43	39	4.5	86	100	23
3	103	15	4.2	51	148	141	46	55	6.8
4	90	25	6.1	211	92	26	37	40	4.0
5	153	130	54	65	62	11	36	37	3.6
6	85	85	20	64	60	10	31	35	2.9
7	84	82	19	56	59	8.9	28	32	2.4
8	105	100	28	48	57	7.4	30	30	2.4
9	72	82	16	46	55	6.8	28	30	2.3
10	69	70	13	54	52	7.6	35	45	4.3
11	53	50	7.2	43	50	5.8	43	50	5.8
12	50	35	4.7	40	45	4.9	28	35	2.6
13	48	28	3.6	45	40	4.9	24	32	2.1
14	47	20	2.5	37	35	3.5	24	30	1.9
15	95	80	21	34	35	3.2	26	30	2.1
16	64	55	9.5	40	35	3.8	24	27	1.7
17	39	15	1.6	31	35	2.9	21	24	1.4
18	43	15	1.7	31	35	2.9	30	25	2.0
19	55	45	6.7	32	33	2.9	45	60	7.3
20	71	70	13	40	32	3.5	39	36	3.8
21	79	70	15	38	32	3.3	25	29	2.0
22	68	70	13	32	30	2.6	30	28	2.3
23	45	42	5.1	29	30	2.3	28	27	2.0
24	46	42	5.2	28	30	2.3	29	35	2.7
25	37	45	4.5	27	30	2.2	32	32	2.8
26	38	50	5.1	33	31	2.8	24	29	1.9
27	43	45	5.2	37	32	3.2	21	28	1.6
28	53	42	6.0	27	31	2.3	20	25	1.4
29	48	40	5.2	26	30	2.1	21	25	1.4
30	48	40	5.2	25	30	2.0	85	70	16
31	34	36	3.3	35	33	3.1	---	---	---
TOTAL	2071	---	320.5	1384	---	293.1	1030	---	125.2
YEAR	38112		85058.47						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCENTRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	50	55	7.4	59	45	7.2	143	130	50
2	33	30	2.7	45	28	3.4	455	386	962
3	33	32	2.9	40	27	2.9	119	100	32
4	57	60	9.2	123	126	61	95	80	21
5	41	37	4.1	100	108	38	79	80	17
6	32	37	3.2	235	306	370	641	670	4020
7	35	37	3.5	104	100	28	9720	4520	424000
8	30	36	2.9	60	60	9.7	11500	5800	476000
9	30	35	2.8	51	50	6.9	516	638	1080
10	29	32	2.5	50	50	6.8	315	250	213
11	23	30	1.9	46	48	6.0	227	195	120
12	22	30	1.8	58	60	9.4	186	160	80
13	22	28	1.7	63	45	7.7	164	140	62
14	256	197	269	41	38	4.2	150	130	53
15	161	145	70	39	35	3.7	143	130	50
16	173	162	111	44	35	4.2	139	120	45
17	667	1110	4220	73	50	9.9	131	120	42
18	2100	1610	25800	150	178	111	128	120	41
19	557	326	957	66	70	12	146	140	55
20	153	75	31	70	65	12	179	145	70
21	97	40	10	47	50	6.3	173	160	75
22	72	40	7.8	44	50	5.9	212	170	97
23	62	40	6.7	181	158	289	139	110	41
24	70	40	7.6	4620	5910	95000	128	110	38
25	97	35	9.2	1120	525	2720	121	110	36
26	85	30	6.9	1110	994	8970	130	110	39
27	78	30	6.3	19800	9220	686000	129	105	37
28	72	98	24	2310	1410	18000	126	100	34
29	70	55	10	386	280	292	117	100	32
30	53	12	1.7	207	140	78	113	100	31
31	59	40	6.4	---	---	---	179	120	58
TOTAL	5319	---	31601.2	31342	---	812075.2	26743	---	907531

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	394	335	430	139	60	23	37	40	4.0
2	192	190	98	113	60	18	50	45	6.1
3	138	70	26	147	115	46	36	15	1.5
4	116	30	9.4	89	80	19	32	10	.86
5	124	25	8.4	66	60	11	32	10	.86
6	127	28	9.6	69	35	6.5	30	10	.81
7	121	28	9.1	52	25	3.5	30	10	.81
8	117	30	9.5	50	20	2.7	30	10	.81
9	121	29	9.5	57	35	5.4	29	10	.78
10	121	29	9.5	74	70	14	27	10	.73
11	113	29	8.8	55	60	8.9	27	10	.73
12	120	30	9.7	51	58	8.0	27	10	.73
13	104	25	7.0	89	85	20	27	10	.73
14	107	22	6.4	72	70	14	28	10	.76
15	98	20	5.3	54	55	8.0	26	10	.70
16	91	18	4.4	62	45	7.5	26	10	.70
17	89	15	3.6	50	35	4.7	26	10	.70
18	90	12	2.9	45	32	3.9	26	10	.70
19	84	10	2.3	43	28	3.3	25	10	.68
20	82	11	2.4	42	20	2.3	26	10	.70
21	79	11	2.3	40	15	1.6	27	10	.73
22	75	10	2.0	39	12	1.3	26	10	.70
23	74	10	2.0	37	12	1.2	24	10	.65
24	73	10	2.0	39	12	1.3	24	10	.65
25	72	10	1.9	41	11	1.2	24	10	.65
26	73	10	2.0	50	20	2.7	26	10	.70
27	71	11	2.1	245	216	222	29	10	.78
28	73	11	2.2	56	80	12	32	10	.86
29	74	10	2.0	41	52	5.8	32	10	.86
30	73	10	2.0	---	---	---	28	10	.76
31	67	12	2.2	---	---	---	28	10	.76
TOTAL	3353	---	694.5	2007	---	478.8	897	---	32.49

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued
SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	23	10	.62	21	12	.68	32	35	3.0
2	22	10	.59	20	11	.59	23	26	1.6
3	21	10	.57	17	10	.46	20	22	1.2
4	20	10	.54	16	10	.43	19	21	1.1
5	20	10	.54	16	12	.52	19	20	.97
6	27	15	1.1	218	163	174	18	20	.97
7	38	25	2.6	155	178	96	17	20	.92
8	24	25	1.6	46	40	5.0	16	20	.86
9	22	20	1.2	29	30	2.3	17	20	.92
10	20	20	1.1	77	85	86	21	22	1.2
11	22	15	.89	162	133	102	18	22	1.1
12	21	15	.85	53	50	7.2	53	49	15
13	19	12	.62	32	38	3.3	29	30	2.3
14	18	11	.53	31	33	2.8	40	50	5.4
15	32	30	2.6	59	55	8.8	585	541	1720
16	27	25	1.8	41	40	4.4	244	213	174
17	20	20	1.1	32	35	3.0	164	168	109
18	20	19	1.0	31	32	2.7	62	60	10
19	22	17	1.0	33	35	3.1	43	40	4.6
20	17	15	.69	46	45	5.6	272	232	341
21	18	16	.78	74	70	14	251	208	182
22	15	15	.61	45	40	4.9	162	140	61
23	46	40	5.0	29	30	2.3	112	120	36
24	26	30	2.1	26	28	2.0	179	158	95
25	20	20	1.1	24	25	1.6	159	144	130
26	18	15	.73	22	22	1.3	80	80	17
27	19	15	.77	23	20	1.2	75	80	16
28	18	13	.63	20	20	1.1	53	50	7.2
29	17	12	.55	23	25	1.6	172	154	88
30	16	12	.52	34	40	3.7	71	70	13
31	---	---	---	83	80	18	---	---	---
TOTAL	668	---	34.33	1538	---	560.58	3025	---	3040.34

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057000 RIO GURABO AT GURABO--Continued
SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	570	420	1180	52	50	7.0	60	65	11
2	793	607	2290	47	50	6.3	55	60	8.9
3	172	145	75	44	50	5.9	51	57	7.8
4	87	80	19	57	50	7.7	49	56	7.4
5	62	70	12	46	50	6.2	46	55	6.8
6	119	103	44	41	45	5.0	40	50	5.4
7	1280	906	5780	68	80	15	42	50	5.7
8	148	60	24	76	60	12	45	50	6.1
9	92	40	9.9	49	50	6.6	221	183	171
10	96	38	9.8	119	119	70	210	212	177
11	98	40	11	217	203	157	2870	1260	25200
12	102	40	11	109	105	31	930	653	2690
13	69	38	7.1	58	70	11	320	256	268
14	780	479	2490	48	60	7.8	353	311	377
15	108	105	31	47	55	7.0	232	208	158
16	77	80	17	45	60	7.3	161	140	61
17	66	75	13	96	100	26	102	105	29
18	72	80	16	68	80	15	75	80	16
19	94	90	23	49	65	8.6	597	300	1270
20	68	80	15	42	60	6.8	191	100	52
21	56	60	9.1	39	60	6.3	121	95	31
22	129	120	42	70	94	36	120	100	32
23	84	100	23	131	143	75	155	175	73
24	65	80	14	3290	1810	50000	101	110	30
25	65	76	13	730	540	1060	81	80	17
26	62	70	12	166	128	55	65	45	7.9
27	64	70	12	161	128	56	56	60	9.1
28	59	60	9.6	135	123	45	54	60	8.7
29	73	85	17	113	110	34	54	57	8.3
30	71	70	13	85	80	18	53	55	7.9
31	59	60	9.6	69	70	13	---	---	---
TOTAL	5740	---	12252.1	6367	---	51817.5	7510	---	30753.0
YEAR	94509		1850871.04						

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50057025 RIO GURABO NEAR GURABO, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18-15'56", long 65-59'04", at bridge on Highway 941, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) west-northwest from gaging station 50057000, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) northwest of Gurabo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--62.8 mi² (162.7 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECALE, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECALE, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
21...	0730	95	254	7.40	27.0	24	4.6	58	68	K9100	4100
DEC 18...	0730	E425	350	6.40	25.0	5.4	4.2	50	43	K1200	720
FEB 1988											
18...	1330	--	382	6.80	29.0	--	4.4	57	--	3200	K1600
APR 08...	0910	25	418	7.40	27.5	17	3.5	44	95	K750	K220
JUN 06...	0910	19	400	7.30	29.5	35	3.7	48	41	4700	290
AUG 18...	1220	E30	330	7.20	28.5	25	4.2	54	16	27000	2700

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
21...	77	3	18	7.7	20	1	4.9	74	<0.5	16	18
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
18...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
APR 08...	130	0	29	13	31	1	4.2	110	<0.5	23	32
JUN 06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG 18...	110	1	24	11	25	1	4.8	100	--	14	22

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
21...	0.10	27	156	40	20	0.88	0.12	1.0	0.44	0.0
DEC 18...	--	--	--	--	16	0.81	0.09	0.9	0.20	0.40
FEB 1988										
18...	--	--	--	--	--	1.08	0.12	1.2	0.38	0.72
APR 08...	0.20	29	242	16	37	0.85	0.15	1.0	0.73	0.77
JUN 06...	--	--	--	--	52	0.53	0.07	0.6	0.13	0.67
AUG 18...	0.10	28	191	--	23	0.88	0.12	1.0	0.58	0.72

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059000 LAGO LOIZA AT DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'49", Long 66°01'00", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at pumpsite at damsite, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) south of Trujillo Alto plaza.

DRANAIGE AREA.--208 mi² (539 km²).

ELEVATION RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1987 to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 97.99 ft (29.867 m) above mean sea level (Puerto Rico Aqueduct and Sewer Authority benchmark); gage readings have been reduced to elevations above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Satellite data collection platform at station. Lake is formed by Loiza Dam, a concrete structure completed in 1954. Useable capacity of impoundment is 30,000 acre-ft (37.0 hm³). Out flow from lake is controlled by five slide gates in powerplant and pump intake structure, four sluice gates, and concrete spillway with eight radial gates. Lake is used for municipal water supply and intermittent power generation.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximun elevation 136.16 ft (41.50 m), July 2; minimun elevation, 125.86 ft (38.36 m), June 12.

ELEVATION (FEET NGVD), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
OBSERVATION AT 24:00 VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1			---	134.74	134.46	135.16	132.30	129.30	128.34	134.17	134.56	133.96
2			---	135.23	135.16	134.41	132.13	129.14	128.59	134.53	134.67	134.23
3			---	134.27	134.07	134.48	131.99	128.88	128.31	135.05	134.90	134.56
4			---	135.02	134.61	134.45	131.79	128.59	128.03	134.83	134.24	134.84
5			---	134.43	134.93	134.39	131.62	128.32	127.72	134.48	134.38	135.06
6			---	134.44	135.15	134.35	131.83	128.96	127.41	134.65	134.43	134.51
7			---	134.54	134.54	134.29	131.89	129.33	127.05	134.81	134.74	134.77
8			---	135.14	134.41	134.23	131.75	129.21	126.68	134.96	135.00	135.09
9			---	134.29	134.56	134.17	131.61	129.48	126.35	134.66	133.96	134.02
10			---	134.94	134.80	134.07	131.41	130.44	126.09	134.51	134.18	133.99
11			---	133.95	134.91	133.97	131.36	131.07	125.93	134.98	133.95	133.99
12			---	134.62	135.17	133.88	131.19	131.14	126.56	134.80	134.42	134.40
13			---	133.95	134.44	133.76	130.98	131.07	126.49	135.15	134.69	135.23
14			---	134.49	134.68	133.63	130.81	130.98	126.41	134.97	134.87	135.25
15			---	134.86	134.89	133.51	130.74	130.97	129.42	134.58	134.39	135.51
16			---	135.12	135.05	133.40	130.72	130.88	130.93	134.94	134.66	135.50
17			---	134.27	134.55	133.37	130.76	130.74	131.36	134.46	133.94	135.50
18			---	134.54	134.56	133.11	131.62	130.62	131.42	134.93	134.95	135.49
19			---	134.77	134.57	132.97	131.68	130.51	131.44	134.48	134.15	134.49
20			---	134.96	134.62	132.93	131.52	130.53	132.29	134.73	134.28	134.46
21			---	135.09	134.63	132.83	131.39	130.61	133.34	134.86	134.38	134.40
22			---	135.17	134.61	132.69	131.21	130.63	133.94	134.58	134.43	134.63
23			---	135.18	134.61	132.52	131.09	130.43	134.26	134.98	133.94	134.41
24			---	135.19	134.66	132.37	130.95	130.22	134.86	134.87	134.21	134.67
25			134.42	134.00	134.69	132.31	130.72	129.97	135.23	134.83	133.89	134.55
26		135.20	134.10	135.16	132.24	130.49	129.74	135.05	134.36	134.45	134.92	
27		134.37	134.23	134.90	132.30	130.28	129.51	134.77	134.57	134.38	134.40	
28		135.11	134.40	135.09	132.46	130.05	129.25	134.86	134.55	133.95	134.41	
29		134.39	134.77	135.12	132.59	129.77	129.06	134.68	134.78	134.75	134.64	
30		134.82	134.94	---	132.56	129.52	128.99	134.59	134.78	134.04	135.00	
31		134.59	135.14	---	132.45	---	129.05	---	134.38	133.96	---	
MEAN			---	134.67	134.74	133.41	131.17	129.92	130.43	134.72	134.38	134.70
MAX			---	135.23	135.17	135.16	132.30	131.14	135.23	135.15	135.00	135.51
MIN			---	133.95	134.07	132.24	129.52	128.32	125.93	134.17	133.89	133.96

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 133.17 MAX 135.51 MIN 125.93

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
50059000 LAGO LOIZA AT DAMSITE, PR
WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'49", long 66°01'00", at pumphouse at damsite, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) south of Trujillo Alto plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--208 sq mi (539 sq km).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987										
05...	1220	--	287	7.00	29.5	0.4	5	27	K60	K140
DEC										
07...	1230	--	178	7.00	26.0	4.4	54	18	300	K180
FEB 1988										
16...	0940	--	215	6.90	25.5	2.0	24	57	K91	K170
APR										
06...	1325	--	317	7.30	27.0	2.0	25	13	K4	K120
JUN										
03...	1140	--	300	7.10	31.0	2.6	35	33	K10	K120
AUG										
05...	1210	--	225	6.30	30.0	3.1	40	28	K8	48

DATE	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CAC03	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
05...	94	<0.5	<1	0.07	0.03	0.10	0.32	0.48	0.8	0.3
DEC										
07...	54	--	6	0.83	0.07	0.90	0.14	0.16	0.3	1.2
FEB 1988										
18...	62	--	33	0.95	0.05	1.00	0.21	0.59	0.8	1.8
APR										
06...	98	<0.5	<1	0.36	0.04	0.40	0.10	0.40	0.5	0.9
JUN										
03...	92	--	4	0.15	0.05	0.20	0.20	0.10	0.3	0.5
AUG										
05...	66	--	6	0.48	0.02	0.50	0.10	0.50	0.6	1.1

DATE	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY-LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1987										
05...	4.8	0.24	80	10	280	310	50	<0.01	3	0.05
DEC										
07...	5.3	0.11	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988										
18...	8.0	0.19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR										
06...	4.0	0.17	<10	<10	100	100	40	<0.01	3	0.05
JUN										
03...	2.2	0.17	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG										
05...	4.9	0.16	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059050 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW DAMSITE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'33" , long 66°00'20", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank of Highway 175; 1.1 mi (1.8 km) downstream of lago Loiza Dam.

DRAINAGE AREA.--209 mi² (541 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1986 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 32 ft (10 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Flow regulated by Lago Loiza Dam.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 124,300 ft³/s (3,520 m³/s), Nov. 27, 1987, gage height, 39.57 ft (12.1 m), from floodmarks and rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of step-back water analysis; minimum discharge, 1.6 ft³/s (0.045 m³/s), July 7, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum discharge, 124,300 ft³/s (3,520 m³/s), Nov. 27, 1987, gage height, 39.57 ft (12.1 m), from floodmarks and rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of step-back water analysis; minimum discharge, 1.6 ft³/s (0.045 m³/s), July 7, 1988.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1937 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	61	66	393	1500	165	83	61	54	42	668	7.3	1030
2	62	66	571	618	78	342	62	51	42	4420	5.8	11
3	61	64	439	838	743	61	61	49	41	254	5.9	10
4	61	65	18	44	53	62	61	42	38	46	370	9.8
5	61	416	348	557	56	62	60	43	37	133	5.7	9.9
6	61	134	801	240	78	63	54	43	37	123	5.7	348
7	62	58	e17800	379	226	62	55	44	38	1430	5.6	21
8	63	71	e40000	65	205	62	45	45	42	123	6.1	11
9	61	71	e10000	850	71	65	42	57	42	171	397	e1000
10	61	67	e1520	78	73	63	45	88	40	202	994	e15
11	63	64	628	811	73	63	48	55	26	5.7	1230	e2750
12	61	60	51	74	76	63	51	49	11	185	45	2810
13	61	61	581	467	647	64	54	49	7.9	5.5	5.2	715
14	61	58	473	88	68	65	74	48	7.2	874	4.9	829
15	62	55	83	67	63	66	75	47	8.4	227	192	943
16	62	55	466	73	68	65	60	43	7.8	5.7	6.8	489
17	808	70	52	505	249	64	60	45	7.5	114	478	831
18	3940	369	254	79	78	64	152	46	7.2	6.6	7.9	6.0
19	588	55	698	78	76	63	76	49	7.2	318	353	1420
20	332	55	689	75	76	62	60	51	7.7	5.6	371	64
21	64	56	761	77	78	62	87	51	17	5.4	5.7	374
22	61	54	767	97	77	62	60	50	8.6	228	213	24
23	66	56	68	113	76	61	58	51	7.6	5.9	827	555
24	89	14100	638	119	74	64	58	49	7.7	135	9750	6.6
25	574	2870	351	513	74	66	56	47	20	83	4600	213
26	63	4110	86	77	173	62	55	45	103	112	421	7.9
27	64	51200	631	73	855	62	54	48	163	7.8	406	418
28	63	6140	63	73	76	58	54	48	8.2	56	449	5.4
29	64	1290	495	78	87	63	52	44	179	200	19	5.2
30	67	116	74	75	---	62	53	43	149	183	517	5.2
31	67	---	905	82	---	61	---	41	---	169	550	---
TOTAL	7894	81972	80704	8863	4792	2247	1843	1515	1160.0	10502.2	22254.6	14937.0
MEAN	255	2732	2603	286	165	72.5	61.4	48.9	38.7	339	718	498
MAX	3940	51200	40000	1500	855	342	152	88	179	4420	9750	2810
MIN	61	54	18	44	53	58	42	41	7.2	5.4	4.9	5.2
AC-FT	15660	162600	160100	17580	9500	4460	3660	3010	2300	20830	44140	29630
CFSM	1.22	13.1	12.5	1.37	.79	.35	.29	.23	.19	1.62	3.43	2.38
IN.	1.41	14.59	14.36	1.58	.85	.40	.33	.27	.21	1.87	3.96	2.66

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 219713.0 MEAN 602 MAX 51200 MIN 4.9 AC-FT 435800 CFSM 2.88 IN. 39.11
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 238683.8 MEAN 652 MAX 51200 MIN 4.9 AC-FT 473400 CFSM 3.12 IN. 42.48

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50059100 RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BELOW TRUJILLO ALTO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'35", long 66°00'15", 100 ft (30 m) downstream of Highway 181 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northwest of Trujillo Alto plaza, and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northeast of Lago Loiza Reservoir.

DRAINAGE AREA.--213 mi² (552 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1981 to current year.

REMARKS: Flow controlled by Lago Loiza reservoir.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
21...	1040	42	188	7.60	28.0	80	5.0	64	70	3400	K6000
DEC 18...	0940	E5.3	215	6.90	25.0	1	6.4	77	<10	34000	K76000
FEB 1988											
29...	0845	95	290	7.60	25.0	1.5	6.3	75	16	K110	K50
APR 22...	1150	72	322	7.80	27.0	160	6.5	81	<10	17000	K15000
JUN 06...	1150	44	343	7.70	31.0	11	8.5	114	35	460	K150
AUG 29...	1150	16	180	7.30	28.0	110	4.5	57	<10	2000	K1500

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	AL-KA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
21...	61	5	15	5.8	15	0.8	3.5	56	<0.5	12	13
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	62	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
29...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
APR 22...	110	0	26	10	22	1	2.2	110	<0.5	18	20
JUN 06...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
AUG 29...	63	9	15	6.1	15	0.9	2.8	54	--	16	11

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
21...	0.10	19	120	14	26	0.92	0.08	1.00	0.10	0.50
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	4	0.99	0.01	1.00	0.12	1.10
FEB 1988										
29...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.66	0.04	0.70	0.59	0.80
APR 22...	0.20	21	180	35	239	0.90	0.10	1.00	0.21	0.29
JUN 06...	--	--	--	--	18	0.87	0.13	1.00	1.00	0.90
AUG 29...	0.20	17	115	5.1	60	0.91	0.09	1.00	0.25	0.45

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

50061800 RIO CANOVANAS NEAR CAMPO RICO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'08", long 65°53'21", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at center pier on downstream side of bridge, on paved secondary road, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) northeast of junction of Highways 185 and 186, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) south of Campo Rico, and 4.4 mi (7.1 km) south of Loiza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.84 mi² (25.48 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1967 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 225 ft (68 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--21 years (1968-88), 28.9 ft³/s (0.818 m³/s), 39.88 in/yr (1,013 mm/yr), 20,940 acre-ft/yr (25.8 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 28 ft³/s (0.79 m³/s), 20,300 acre-ft/yr (25 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 15,000 ft³/s (425 m³/s), Sept. 13, 1982, gage height, 13.1 ft (3.99 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 350 ft³/s (9.91 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurements and step-backwater analysis made in 1981; minimum daily discharge, 0.80 ft³/s (0.023 m³/s), July 24, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	0315	*12,500	354	*12.48	3.804	Aug. 24	unknown	4,910	139	8.40	2.560
Dec. 7	2000	8,920	253	10.94	3.335	Sept. 11	1200	4,870	138	8.37	2.551

Minimum discharge, 3.8 ft³/s (0.108 m³/s), June 11.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	22	6.6	62	464	179	17	e10	6.5	7.5	48	7.8	12
2	11	6.3	58	142	132	19	e9.4	6.5	6.9	87	6.2	11
3	9.0	6.3	53	80	167	17	e9.0	6.5	6.5	26	6.1	11
4	18	9.0	49	66	75	15	e8.8	5.6	6.4	15	11	10
5	17	9.6	56	57	56	15	e8.5	5.7	6.1	11	6.9	9.7
6	9.8	19	59	53	48	14	14	17	5.5	10	5.1	9.5
7	7.8	11	965	49	42	14	10	32	5.2	25	4.5	11
8	7.7	11	590	46	39	14	8.8	10	4.9	13	4.8	14
9	7.5	13	87	46	45	e13	8.3	32	5.0	9.4	5.9	45
10	6.0	13	65	43	42	e13	7.7	244	4.5	9.0	46	72
11	6.1	12	54	42	35	e12	7.5	49	4.4	8.5	30	518
12	6.0	12	46	40	34	e12	8.2	19	5.1	9.4	23	86
13	5.5	12	41	37	34	e11	7.3	15	4.7	8.3	e13	58
14	6.9	11	36	35	35	e11	7.3	18	5.3	80	e10	74
15	17	11	37	32	34	e10	15	28	41	13	e7.5	46
16	47	11	33	32	32	e10	13	17	20	7.9	e7.2	34
17	97	28	30	44	29	e10	8.1	14	11	6.5	e15	28
18	182	77	29	37	29	e9.6	9.6	13	7.7	9.7	e11	25
19	49	30	78	40	27	e9.6	11	14	6.9	10	e8.0	31
20	17	28	147	32	26	e9.2	7.4	13	13	8.0	e7.0	27
21	12	15	82	29	25	e9.2	6.5	13	17	6.0	e6.2	23
22	9.8	14	51	27	24	e11	6.2	12	13	15	e7.0	29
23	8.9	42	40	27	26	e10	22	9.7	8.8	11	e20	25
24	33	453	49	26	28	e9.6	9.0	8.9	15	13	e500	20
25	27	101	41	33	24	e10	8.6	8.9	22	17	e300	19
26	13	61	68	27	37	e11	9.6	8.4	23	8.5	e28	19
27	10	1790	54	25	59	e13	8.3	6.2	14	7.8	e25	18
28	9.2	208	47	26	22	e14	8.1	6.3	9.9	10	e24	17
29	9.5	94	37	38	19	e13	7.9	6.7	25	16	e19	16
30	7.9	72	33	31	---	e12	7.2	8.6	17	14	15	17
31	7.3	---	215	135	---	e11	---	11	---	9.5	13	---
TOTAL	696.9	3186.8	3292	1841	1404	379.2	282.3	665.5	342.3	542.5	1193.2	1335.2
MEAN	22.5	106	106	59.4	48.4	12.2	9.41	21.5	11.4	17.5	38.5	44.5
MAX	182	1790	965	464	179	19	22	244	41	87	500	518
MIN	5.5	6.3	29	25	19	9.2	6.2	5.6	4.4	6.0	4.5	9.5
AC-FT	1380	6320	6530	3650	2780	752	560	1320	679	1080	2370	6650
CFSM	2.28	10.8	10.8	6.04	4.92	1.24	.96	2.18	1.16	1.78	3.91	4.52
IN.	2.63	12.05	12.45	6.96	5.31	1.43	1.07	2.52	1.29	2.05	4.51	5.05

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 13481.9 MEAN 36.9 MAX 1790 MIN 3.7 AC-FT 26740 CFSM 3.75 IN. 50.97
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 15160.9 MEAN 41.4 MAX 1790 MIN 4.4 AC-FT 30070 CFSM 4.21 IN. 57.32

e Estimated

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN
 50061800 RIO CANOVANAS NEAR CAMPO RICO, PR--Continued
 WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 13	1545	5.29	228	29.5	MAR, 02	1231	19.2	257	24.0
DEC, 10	1718	65.5	151	24.5	APR, 04	1620	9.13	233	25.0
JAN, 08	1049	46.8	189	22.0	JUL, 06	1605	10.1	216	29.5
FEB, 05	1048	53.8	170	21.5					

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 19.--Northeastern river basins--Río Herrera to Río Antón Ruíz basins.

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063440 QUEBRADA SONADORA NEAR EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'24", long 65°49'03", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, in Caribbean National Forest, at El Yunque, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) upstream from Rio Espiritu Santo, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Highway 186, and about 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of El Verde.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.01 mi² (2.62 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 1,230 ft (375 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--5 years (1984-88), 7.72 ft³/s (0.219 m³/s), 105.90 in/yr (2,690 mm/yr), 5,590 acre-ft/yr (689 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 2,230 ft³/s (63.2 m³/s), Dec. 7, 1987, gage height, 9.42 ft (2.871 m) from rating curve extended above 20 ft³/s (0.57 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 0.20 ft³/s (0.006 m³/s), July 14, 15, 1985.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov.27	0300	635	18.0	7.39	2.252	Dec. 7	2030	*2,230	63.2	*9.42	2.871
Aug.10	1815	781	22.1	7.68	2.341	Aug.24	1230	871	24.7	7.84	2.390

Minimum discharge, 0.45 ft³/s (0.013 m³/s), June 8.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.5	2.0	2.1	72	56	2.8	2.9	2.3	1.1	7.1	5.6	3.1
2	2.7	1.7	1.5	24	43	2.7	2.3	1.6	1.1	34	4.1	2.5
3	7.7	1.5	2.0	9.7	41	2.4	2.0	1.3	.89	3.3	29	2.3
4	6.9	1.5	1.3	11	13	2.2	2.6	1.2	.71	2.1	8.8	1.9
5	3.5	2.3	.80	7.5	7.7	2.1	2.0	1.1	.66	1.7	4.0	1.6
6	2.1	18	4.8	8.4	6.2	2.0	2.1	1.4	.57	12	3.3	1.6
7	1.7	4.0	216	8.2	6.0	1.9	1.7	1.5	.49	11	11	7.5
8	1.7	2.1	83	8.1	5.0	1.9	1.6	1.1	.48	2.6	4.5	10
9	1.7	1.8	8.6	7.9	7.0	1.7	1.3	1.2	.51	2.0	3.9	35
10	1.4	1.7	5.8	5.9	4.5	1.6	1.1	43	.69	2.2	61	17
11	1.4	1.5	6.1	13	4.5	1.5	.90	14	.64	4.7	34	45
12	1.0	1.4	4.5	5.9	12	1.3	.80	2.8	1.6	5.3	8.2	30
13	.72	1.5	3.3	6.2	8.3	1.3	.69	2.7	1.3	8.9	4.6	33
14	1.4	2.4	2.7	5.2	5.1	1.2	.59	8.2	7.4	24	4.0	16
15	8.4	1.6	21	3.9	17	.99	2.3	22	20	3.1	4.0	18
16	18	1.5	6.4	3.6	6.0	.95	9.4	4.3	2.9	2.5	14	7.1
17	19	27	3.3	15	4.5	.89	1.7	3.1	1.7	2.3	25	4.5
18	10	22	2.7	6.3	8.4	1.1	3.9	2.7	1.3	15	5.4	3.6
19	5.4	10	46	8.0	5.8	.87	5.1	2.3	1.9	12	3.7	9.7
20	3.1	5.0	65	4.3	8.4	3.5	1.8	3.7	5.1	3.7	3.3	4.4
21	3.3	3.1	35	3.6	4.1	1.7	1.2	4.8	17	2.8	3.0	3.1
22	3.2	2.7	15	3.3	3.6	1.4	1.2	2.2	4.4	15	17	2.8
23	2.2	30	7.5	3.2	6.8	.99	.89	2.2	3.3	5.4	8.8	2.8
24	10	67	12	4.0	18	9.4	.70	1.8	2.8	5.1	110	2.6
25	5.9	35	8.9	8.4	6.1	22	9.8	1.5	3.9	4.5	25	2.3
26	5.5	40	23	3.5	9.6	7.6	30	1.4	3.3	9.5	6.4	2.0
27	2.9	145	10	3.5	24	22	5.1	1.3	2.0	3.9	16	1.7
28	3.3	29	18	5.6	3.7	19	2.4	3.0	1.9	9.8	7.1	1.5
29	2.9	6.6	9.0	13	3.1	25	2.1	1.8	4.9	20	4.6	1.3
30	2.2	3.6	6.7	7.5	---	15	2.9	1.9	2.4	25	6.5	1.2
31	2.1	---	37	44	---	5.0	---	1.6	---	5.1	3.8	---
TOTAL	146.82	472.5	669.00	333.7	348.4	163.99	103.07	145.0	96.94	265.6	449.6	275.1
MEAN	4.74	15.7	21.6	10.8	12.0	5.29	3.44	4.68	3.23	8.57	14.5	9.17
MAX	19	145	216	72	56	25	30	43	20	34	110	45
MIN	.72	1.4	.80	3.2	3.1	.87	.59	1.1	.48	1.7	3.0	1.2
AC-FT	291	937	1330	662	691	325	204	288	192	527	892	546
CFSM	4.55	15.1	20.8	10.4	11.6	5.09	3.30	4.50	3.11	8.24	13.9	8.82
IN.	5.25	16.90	23.93	11.94	12.46	5.87	3.69	5.19	3.47	9.50	16.08	9.84
CAL YR 1987	TOTAL 3366.61	MEAN 9.22	MAX 216	MIN .72	AC-FT 6680	CFSM 8.87	IN. 120.42					
WTR YR 1988	TOTAL 3469.72	MEAN 9.48	MAX 216	MIN .48	AC-FT 6880	CFSM 9.12	IN. 124.11					

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063440 QUEBRADA SONADORA NEAR EL VERDE, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1983 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 05	1206	3.34	485	23.0	MAR, 03	1231	2.24	99	20.0
DEC, 10	1045	5.88	60	21.5	APR, 07	0931	1.79	58	20.0
JAN, 07	1213	5.69	63	20.5	JUL, 07	1322	7.18	47	22.5
FEB, 08	1351	4.95	62	20.0					

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063500 QUEBRADA TORONJA AT EL VERDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'43", long 65°49'14", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, in Caribbean National Forest, at downstream side of culvert on Highway 186, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from Rio Espiritu Santo, and about 0.9 mi (1.4 km) south of El Verde.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.064 mi² (0.166 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete broad-V-notch crested weir. Elevation of gage is 876 ft (267 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--5 years (1984-88), 0.35 ft³/s (0.010 m³/s), 74.26 in/yr (1,886 mm/yr), 254 acre-ft/yr (0.313hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 33 ft³/s (0.93 m³/s), Mar. 15, 1987, gage height, 1.94 ft (0.591 m), from rating curve extended above 1.0 ft³/s (0.03 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, no flow for part of each day Apr. 10, 17, 1983.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 13 ft³/s (0.37 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	0745	18	0.51	1.71	0.521	Aug. 10	1815	15	0.42	1.67	0.509
Dec. 7	2115	*22	0.62	*1.78	0.542						

Minimum discharge, 0.04 ft³/s (0.001 m³/s), June 27, 28, 30.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.23	.09	.79	3.6	1.7	.15	.20	.11	.09	.29	.12	.30
2	.13	.10	.67	1.7	1.4	.14	.16	.09	.09	.93	.10	.26
3	.23	.08	.63	1.2	1.9	.13	.15	.09	.09	.11	.55	.22
4	.19	.10	.58	.98	.78	.12	.16	.08	.08	.07	.28	.22
5	.13	.11	.55	.82	.56	.12	.13	.06	.08	.06	.14	.22
6	.08	.62	.63	.74	.49	.11	.12	.07	.08	.44	.12	.22
7	.08	.12	5.3	.64	.41	.10	.12	.07	.08	.36	.19	.38
8	.07	.09	5.6	.57	.31	.09	.12	.06	.07	.10	.12	.43
9	.07	.09	2.3	.56	.30	.09	.12	.10	.07	.09	.11	1.1
10	.07	.08	1.5	.54	.24	.09	.11	.85	.08	.08	1.5	.63
11	.06	.08	1.1	.66	.32	.09	.11	.48	.08	.13	1.1	1.8
12	.05	.08	.83	.41	.37	.08	.11	.13	.10	.13	.47	1.5
13	.05	.12	.71	.42	.28	.08	.10	.16	.08	.20	.26	1.5
14	.06	.13	.63	.36	.20	.08	.09	.27	.20	.62	.25	1.1
15	.12	.08	.96	.30	.34	.07	.23	.48	.56	.12	.22	1.4
16	.66	.08	.60	.29	.20	.07	.93	.22	.12	.09	.31	.89
17	.54	.45	.50	.40	.19	.07	.14	.16	.08	.09	.79	.62
18	.32	.53	.46	.35	.27	.07	.34	.13	.07	.20	.25	.52
19	.18	.38	1.9	.33	.23	.07	.19	.12	.08	.29	.20	.54
20	.13	.23	3.1	.26	.25	.09	.13	.15	.09	.11	.18	.37
21	.11	.16	2.2	.20	.18	.07	.11	.12	.32	.08	.17	.29
22	.11	.15	1.3	.18	.17	.07	.10	.10	.13	.23	.34	.27
23	.09	1.2	.89	.18	.20	.07	.09	.11	.07	.12	.41	.25
24	.77	3.7	.89	.19	.36	.18	.09	.09	.06	.16	2.9	.22
25	.37	2.4	.70	.26	.20	.20	.25	.09	.06	.11	1.9	.21
26	.20	2.7	1.5	.17	.22	.17	.64	.08	.06	.20	.68	.20
27	.13	6.9	.75	.16	.43	.46	.26	.10	.05	.10	.97	.18
28	.15	3.0	.79	.28	.17	.59	.14	.13	.05	.14	.59	.17
29	.13	1.6	.59	.23	.15	1.7	.11	.09	.07	.43	.42	.15
30	.12	1.0	.50	.16	---	.42	.11	.09	.05	.47	.66	.14
31	.11	---	2.2	.89	---	.26	---	.09	---	.15	.35	---
TOTAL	5.74	26.45	41.65	18.03	12.82	6.10	5.66	4.97	3.19	6.70	16.65	16.30
MEAN	.19	.88	1.34	.58	.44	.20	.19	.16	.11	.22	.54	.54
MAX	.77	6.9	5.6	3.6	1.9	1.7	.93	.85	.56	.93	2.9	1.8
MIN	.05	.08	.46	.16	.15	.07	.09	.06	.05	.06	.10	.14
AC-FT	11	52	83	36	25	12	11	9.9	6.3	13	33	32
CFSM	.97	4.64	7.07	3.06	2.33	1.04	.99	.84	.56	1.14	2.83	2.86
IN.	1.12	5.18	8.15	3.53	2.51	1.19	1.11	.97	.62	1.31	3.26	3.19

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 156.91 MEAN .43 MAX 6.9 MIN .04 AC-FT 311 CFSM 2.26 IN. 30.72
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 164.26 MEAN .45 MAX 6.9 MIN .05 AC-FT 326 CFSM 2.36 IN. 32.16

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063500 QUEBRADA TORONJA AT EL VERDE, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1983 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 05	1506	0.13	107	23.5	MAR, 03	1401	0.13	158	21.0
DEC, 10	1325	1.26	81	23.0	APR, 07	1122	0.11	115	21.5
JAN, 07	0907	0.67	104	21.5	JUL, 07	1531	0.17	94	23.5
FEB, 03	1219	1.33	89	21.0					

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'37", long 65°48'49", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, at left abutment, on downstream side of bridge on Highway 966, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Quebrada Jimenez, and 1.9 mi (3.1 km) southeast of Rio Grande.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.62 mi² (22.33 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to April 1963 (annual low-flow and occasional measurements only), August 1966 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 40 ft (12 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharge, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--22 years (1967-88), 58.7 ft³/s (1.662 m³/s), 92.48 in/yr (2,349 mm/yr), 42,530 acre-ft/yr (52.4 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 53.4 ft³/s (1.51 m³/s), 38,700 acre-ft/yr (48 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 20,000 ft³/s (566 m³/s), Dec. 7, 1987, gage height, 14.52 ft (4.426 m), from rating curve extended above 600 ft³/s (17.0 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge, 4.0 ft³/s (0.113 m³/s), July 3-5, 1975, Apr. 14, 15, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,000 ft³/s (85.0 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Nov. 24	1600	3,730	106	7.77	2.368	July 14	0100	3,040	86.1	7.23	2.204
Nov. 25	2200	3,350	94.6	7.48	2.280	Aug. 10	1900	6,270	178	9.36	2.853
Nov. 27	unknown	9,330	264	10.82	3.298	Aug. 24	1315	3,330	94.3	7.47	2.277
Dec. 7	unknown	*20,000	566	*14.52	4.426	Sept. 11	1230	3,650	103	7.71	2.350

Minimum discharge, 7.7 ft³/s (0.218 m³/s), Nov. 13.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	53	11	43	e200	468	29	30	22	13	e100	37	38
2	27	10	e38	e70	319	28	25	17	12	e25	27	32
3	59	9.1	e40	e52	345	25	23	15	12	e18	171	29
4	57	9.7	e44	e45	115	24	24	14	12	e14	100	27
5	36	13	e60	e42	71	23	23	14	12	e13	32	24
6	25	108	e250	e38	53	23	23	20	11	e30	25	23
7	21	e11	e2600	e40	54	22	20	25	11	e21	55	43
8	20	e10	e200	64	42	21	19	16	11	18	43	62
9	26	e13	e70	73	51	20	18	79	11	12	27	257
10	22	e12	e58	57	37	20	17	313	11	13	495	149
11	28	e10	e48	87	40	19	16	91	12	23	283	440
12	22	e9.4	e43	56	68	18	16	22	15	32	94	243
13	19	9.8	e38	54	78	16	15	19	e25	18	40	255
14	23	11	e35	45	45	17	14	50	e41	223	33	134
15	73	10	e37	35	87	16	77	126	e30	15	30	172
16	138	9.2	e31	32	51	16	276	37	e15	12	57	91
17	145	136	e29	84	35	15	25	20	e13	14	188	54
18	60	125	e60	43	57	17	60	18	e12	71	52	45
19	32	62	e110	61	43	15	52	18	e11	98	31	84
20	17	26	e150	34	55	31	23	29	e25	35	27	48
21	14	15	e60	29	32	19	18	31	e17	27	24	33
22	17	13	e40	26	28	16	18	17	e12	90	101	30
23	14	244	e50	25	31	14	17	19	e15	53	64	30
24	104	846	e41	27	106	47	16	28	e21	29	983	27
25	45	396	e68	54	44	162	54	21	e35	41	302	24
26	26	364	e50	28	36	80	167	15	e17	66	71	23
27	16	e1700	e38	28	172	106	66	14	e14	31	146	22
28	16	e150	e34	42	39	138	24	19	e30	47	85	21
29	15	e60	e33	88	31	281	23	17	e20	122	56	20
30	12	e50	e100	51	---	94	23	17	e40	145	79	19
31	12	---	e470	299	---	53	---	17	---	36	42	---
TOTAL	1194	4453.2	4968	1909	2633	1425	1222	1180	536	1492	3800	2499
MEAN	38.5	148	160	61.6	90.8	46.0	40.7	38.1	17.9	48.1	123	83.3
MAX	145	1700	2600	299	468	281	276	313	41	223	983	440
MIN	12	9.1	29	25	28	14	14	14	11	12	24	19
AC-FT	2370	8830	9850	3790	5220	2830	2420	2340	1060	2960	7540	4960
CFSM	4.47	17.2	18.6	7.14	10.5	5.33	4.73	4.42	2.07	5.58	14.2	9.66
IN.	5.15	19.22	21.44	8.24	11.36	6.15	5.27	5.09	2.31	6.44	16.40	10.78

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 27848.0 MEAN 76.3 MAX 2600 MIN 8.0 AC-FT 55240 CFSM 8.85 IN. 120.18
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 27311.2 MEAN 74.6 MAX 2600 MIN 9.1 AC-FT 54170 CFSM 8.66 IN. 117.86

e Estimated

RIO ESPIRITU SANTO BASIN

50063800 RIO ESPIRITU SANTO NEAR RIO GRANDE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1961-66, 1968 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
06...	0915	25	81	7.20	25.0	1.6	9.1	109	20	K600	K1400
DEC											
02...	0855	39	83	6.50	23.0	1.9	8.4	97	15	K1700	K2300
FEB 1988											
11...	0930	34	94	6.30	22.0	2.1	9.0	103	15	2400	380
APR											
05...	0845	23	94	7.90	26.0	1.1	8.8	101	110	K770	880
JUN											
01...	0915	13	112	7.50	24.0	1.0	8.2	100	17	590	K1000
AUG											
09...	0845	24	90	6.20	27.0	1.8	7.6	95	<10	460	7100

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY, WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
06...	25	0	5.5	2.8	6.3	0.6	0.70	25	<0.5	3.8	7.8
DEC											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	26	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	34	--	--	--
APR											
05...	30	0	6.4	3.5	7.7	0.6	0.50	31	<0.5	3.5	10
JUN											
01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	36	--	--	--
AUG											
09...	31	3	6.9	3.4	7.6	0.6	0.50	21	--	3.7	9.4

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
06...	0.10	15	57	3.9	1	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.02	0.28
DEC										
02...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	0.49
FEB 1988										
11...	--	--	--	--	2	--	0.08	<0.10	0.02	0.18
APR										
05...	0.10	18	68	4.3	<1	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.01	0.36
JUN										
01...	--	--	--	--	4	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.03	0.51
AUG										
09...	0.10	15	63	4.1	3	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.03	0.67

K = non-ideal count

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'46", long 65°45'04", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank, at bridge on Highway 988, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) west of Sabana, 2.0 mi (3.2 km) downstream from Rio de la Mina, and 3.2 mi (5.1 km) southeast of Mameyes.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.88 mi² (17.82 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1967 to December 1973. June 1983 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 275 ft (84 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--11 years (1968-73, 1984-88), 58.5 ft³/s (1.657 m³/s), 115.47 in/yr (2,933 mm/yr), 42,380 acre-ft/yr (52.3 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 59 ft³/s (1.67 m³/s), 42,700 acre-ft/yr (53 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 19,800 ft³/s (561 m³/s), Sept. 4, 1973, gage height, 13.02 ft (3.968 m), from rating curve extended above 1,800 ft³/s (51.0 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 5.1 ft³/s (0.144 m³/s), Apr. 8, 9, 1970.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 4,000 ft³/s (113 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Nov. 25	2100	4,090	116	7.48	2.280	Dec. 7	2030	*13,000	368	*11.16	3.402
Nov. 27	0715	9,750	276	10.08	3.072	Aug. 24	1245	7,020	199	8.99	2.740

Minimum daily discharge, 12 ft³/s (0.340 m³/s), Mar. 22, 23.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e96	28	50	302	225	29	29	25	22	85	35	29
2	e50	26	61	141	173	41	25	19	20	113	33	25
3	e32	18	53	77	181	26	24	17	20	23	135	26
4	e88	24	41	74	73	24	29	15	20	26	77	22
5	e50	31	35	62	46	23	70	15	20	24	39	29
6	e40	97	54	78	40	26	51	18	19	118	33	39
7	e33	26	1090	60	43	25	25	16	18	106	52	68
8	e29	18	786	58	35	25	23	16	18	29	31	80
9	e28	18	84	68	45	23	21	15	18	22	27	207
10	e51	17	60	50	32	22	19	260	19	20	242	121
11	e32	15	74	84	33	20	17	53	40	49	94	245
12	e60	16	44	56	62	19	16	26	48	56	38	153
13	e34	19	39	67	111	19	15	29	25	48	24	260
14	e25	31	36	53	45	18	15	79	47	193	22	134
15	e27	24	81	40	99	17	50	210	151	30	24	94
16	75	46	44	35	54	16	45	52	38	23	52	89
17	127	107	31	68	40	16	17	52	24	20	131	58
18	99	105	25	41	57	16	48	32	18	75	25	55
19	45	59	251	53	41	15	48	42	48	73	20	96
20	28	38	297	34	54	43	20	40	26	29	17	55
21	88	28	193	30	32	13	15	62	132	22	14	47
22	39	25	84	28	29	12	14	27	82	88	80	50
23	29	214	65	25	39	12	14	27	89	42	33	56
24	66	464	66	26	76	47	14	23	17	31	731	42
25	43	509	57	31	41	82	38	22	27	61	185	36
26	43	347	120	23	57	23	144	22	29	103	74	e33
27	25	1660	73	33	138	25	53	25	14	31	78	e29
28	31	293	100	36	39	32	27	30	17	51	58	e42
29	27	88	59	71	32	148	23	36	68	132	39	e33
30	21	62	45	36	---	81	34	84	46	103	47	e24
31	29	---	112	121	---	44	---	42	---	32	34	---
TOTAL	1490	4453	4210	1961	1972	982	983	1431	1180	1858	2524	2277
MEAN	48.1	148	136	63.3	68.0	31.7	32.8	46.2	39.3	59.9	81.4	75.9
MAX	127	1660	1090	302	225	148	144	260	151	193	731	260
MIN	21	15	25	23	29	12	14	15	14	20	14	22
AC-FT	2960	8830	8350	3890	3910	1950	1950	2840	2340	3690	5010	4520
CFSM	6.99	21.6	19.7	9.19	9.88	4.60	4.76	6.71	5.72	8.71	11.8	11.0
IN.	8.06	24.08	22.76	10.60	10.66	5.31	5.32	7.74	6.38	10.05	13.65	12.31

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 23602.5 MEAN 64.7 MAX 1660 MIN 9.6 AC-FT 46820 CFSM 9.40 IN. 127.62
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 25321 MEAN 69.2 MAX 1660 MIN 12 AC-FT 50220 CFSM 10.1 IN. 136.91

e Estimated

RIO MAMEYES BASIN

50065500 RIO MAMEYES NEAR SABANA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS JUNE 1983 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 16	1016	32.4	80	24.5	MAR, 02	1017	82.7	119	20.5
DEC, 11	1126	92.8	70	23.5	APR, 06	0956	47.9	78	21.5
JAN, 05	0946	61.2	102	22.0	JUL, 06	1315	67.0	69	28.0
FEB, 04	1041	75	88	21.5					

RIO SABANA BASIN.

50067000 RIO SABANA AT SABANA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'52", long 65°43'52", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on right bank along Highway 988, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) north of junction of Highways 988 and 983 in Sabana, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) south of Luquillo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--3.96 mi² (10.26 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1979 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (80 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--9 years (1980-88), 20.1 ft³/s (0.569 m³/s), 68.93 in/yr (1,751 mm/yr), 14,560 acre-ft/yr (18.0 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 9,010 ft³/s (255 m³/s), Apr. 21, 1983, gage height, 19.35 ft (5.898 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 0.86 ft³/s (0.024 m³/s), Apr. 17, 1983.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 23	2330	1,870	53.0	12.71	3.874	Dec. 7	2400	1,830	51.8	12.65	3.856
Nov. 27	0700	*3,940	112	*15.23	4.642	Aug. 24	1245	2,150	60.9	13.11	3.996

Minimum discharge, 2.2 ft³/s (0.062 m³/s), Apr. 14, 15.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.6	4.2	32	80	81	7.2	3.9	5.2	8.3	54	7.0	10
2	2.8	4.9	46	45	47	8.2	3.4	3.7	6.6	46	6.1	8.6
3	180	3.7	27	20	76	6.7	3.2	3.2	5.9	13	24	9.7
4	13	8.1	18	17	16	6.3	3.4	6.9	5.4	10	16	7.7
5	5.0	8.5	14	17	10	5.9	52	20	5.3	9.0	6.6	6.9
6	3.9	24	19	24	8.7	5.8	21	4.1	4.9	14	5.8	7.2
7	4.1	4.8	309	15	8.0	5.5	4.6	3.5	4.7	24	7.7	13
8	3.4	3.8	426	13	8.0	5.5	3.5	2.9	4.4	8.9	5.4	22
9	4.4	3.9	49	16	8.1	5.0	3.2	2.9	4.3	7.6	5.2	136
10	4.9	4.0	33	13	7.1	5.0	3.0	193	4.0	7.3	124	38
11	4.0	3.4	31	21	8.4	4.8	2.9	57	4.2	12	31	118
12	3.4	3.1	22	15	20	4.6	2.7	13	5.7	8.1	8.6	31
13	4.3	2.9	18	21	86	4.8	2.6	11	4.0	19	6.6	105
14	9.5	4.6	15	14	16	4.5	2.4	12	4.7	81	6.5	72
15	16	3.4	24	11	29	4.5	90	121	68	8.4	8.7	37
16	57	5.7	14	10	15	4.2	23	26	14	7.0	14	38
17	93	14	12	22	10	4.2	12	51	5.7	6.4	79	19
18	89	19	10	11	17	4.0	46	29	4.1	16	9.1	15
19	19	5.8	53	14	13	3.7	11	20	17	25	7.6	17
20	8.7	4.0	115	9.7	17	8.1	5.8	12	16	9.0	5.9	13
21	6.8	3.3	83	8.5	9.3	4.1	4.8	9.6	103	7.0	5.2	17
22	5.7	3.0	22	7.9	8.1	3.6	3.8	7.7	107	22	27	13
23	5.3	177	15	7.5	12	3.3	3.5	8.6	142	14	9.9	26
24	8.6	340	15	7.5	15	9.5	3.5	6.8	36	8.1	376	12
25	6.5	283	12	7.6	11	34	4.6	6.2	14	11	103	10
26	7.6	206	26	8.6	14	11	15	5.5	14	19	25	9.7
27	5.3	807	17	9.7	56	4.6	9.8	6.3	12	8.7	30	8.9
28	4.6	309	31	8.7	10	4.8	13	7.8	10	7.8	16	9.7
29	4.9	82	17	19	8.0	86	10	16	18	47	12	9.2
30	3.8	44	14	8.6	---	18	8.7	138	43	11	14	8.0
31	7.6	---	22	14	---	6.8	---	21	---	8.2	11	---
TOTAL	597.7	2390.1	1561	516.3	644.7	294.2	376.3	830.9	696.2	549.5	1013.9	847.6
MEAN	19.3	79.7	50.4	16.7	22.2	9.49	12.5	26.8	23.2	17.7	32.7	28.3
MAX	180	807	426	80	86	86	90	193	142	81	376	136
MIN	2.8	2.9	10	7.5	7.1	3.3	2.4	2.9	4.0	6.4	5.2	6.9
AC-FT	1190	4740	3100	1020	1280	584	746	1650	1380	1090	2010	1680
CFSM	4.87	20.1	12.7	4.21	5.61	2.40	3.17	6.77	5.86	4.48	8.26	7.13
IN.	5.61	22.45	14.66	4.85	6.06	2.76	3.53	7.81	6.54	5.16	9.52	7.96

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 10733.8 MEAN 29.4 MAX 807 MIN 1.3 AC-FT 21290 CFSM 7.43 IN. 100.83
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 10318.4 MEAN 28.2 MAX 807 MIN 2.4 AC-FT 20470 CFSM 7.12 IN. 96.93

RIO SABANA BASIN

50067000 RIO SABANA AT SABANA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 16	1210	5.48	98	25.5	MAR, 01	1307	7.08	168	23.0
DEC, 11	1305	35.8	88	25.0	APR, 06	1216	10.0	88	24.0
JAN, 04	1239	20.6	101	23.0	JUL, 05	1630	8.51	103	26.5
FEB, 04	1355	14.2	102	23.0					

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'56", long 65°41'42", Hydrologic Unit 21010005, on left bank off Highway 976, 0.1 mi (0.2 km) upstream from Highway 977 bridge, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from Quebrada Peñon, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) northeast of Colonia Paraiso, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) southwest of Fajardo.

DRAINAGE AREA.--14.9 mi² (38.6 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1960-61 (occasional low and peak-flow measurements only), March 1961 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 137.60 ft (41.940 m) above mean sea level. Due to flood damage, gage datum has had changes as follows: Mar. 24, 1961 to May 5, 1969, 138.95 ft (42.352 m); May 6, 1969 to Mar. 16, 1972, 135.05 ft (41.163 m); Mar. 17, 1972 to Mar 25, 1975, 138.60 ft (42.245 m).

REMARKS.--Records fair. Low flow affected by diversions for water supply about 400 m upstream from gaging station (estimated mean daily discharges is 9.0 ft³/s (0.255 m³/s).

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--27 years (1962-88), 68.7 ft³/s (1.946 m³/s), 62.61 in/yr (1,590 mm/yr), 49,770 acre-ft/yr (61.4 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 69 ft³/s (1.95 m³/s), 50,000 acre-ft/yr (62 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 19,600 ft³/s (555 m³/s), Oct. 24, 1974, gage height, 13.62 ft (4.151 m), datum then in use, from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analyses and slope-area measurements of peak discharges; minimum discharge, 0.86 ft³/s (0.024 m³/s), May 3, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 3,500 ft³/s (99.1 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 25	2115	*10,500	297	*12.63	3.850	Dec. 8	0430	7,380	209	10.82	3.298
Nov. 27	2045	7,380	209	10.82	3.298	Aug.24	1830	4,660	132	8.87	2.704
Nov. 28	1500	3,570	101	7.90	2.408						

Minimum discharge, 10 ft³/s (0.238 m³/s), May 9, 10.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	34	29	86	202	185	27	20	16	24	80	23	20
2	19	31	71	159	130	42	18	14	20	68	21	18
3	171	21	70	80	328	26	17	13	18	39	66	18
4	44	57	52	62	80	23	24	14	17	31	54	17
5	26	33	41	58	52	22	332	16	17	28	25	16
6	21	95	77	94	41	21	82	16	16	81	21	16
7	20	27	691	66	37	20	26	14	15	63	28	22
8	47	22	1530	61	33	20	20	12	14	32	21	89
9	29	23	182	70	35	21	18	11	14	28	20	332
10	23	28	128	55	31	19	16	300	15	27	362	122
11	24	21	149	81	29	18	15	150	14	35	82	268
12	27	18	89	56	57	18	14	33	16	33	36	115
13	23	17	73	57	211	18	14	22	18	48	25	385
14	46	20	65	52	52	18	13	77	21	323	24	118
15	175	19	107	42	78	16	54	230	107	32	26	197
16	194	21	67	38	54	16	35	56	28	27	55	72
17	297	96	54	79	36	15	16	62	23	28	239	42
18	562	78	49	41	40	15	32	33	17	37	35	35
19	114	43	157	48	31	14	21	43	26	37	38	81
20	51	42	339	35	38	32	18	37	44	25	34	37
21	53	22	280	32	28	17	14	40	322	23	35	38
22	41	19	113	30	27	14	13	25	397	64	93	30
23	48	383	72	29	34	14	12	23	375	36	75	73
24	37	934	61	29	60	18	12	20	84	27	1010	31
25	60	1190	65	36	32	44	16	18	48	33	216	29
26	38	446	86	27	67	33	130	18	40	36	66	32
27	29	2100	62	59	162	24	52	17	48	26	36	24
28	36	801	72	48	36	26	19	17	39	28	30	44
29	39	197	54	76	29	217	17	33	229	74	29	26
30	28	117	50	37	---	62	19	148	70	41	31	23
31	34	---	108	86	---	30	---	45	---	25	25	---
TOTAL	2390	6950	5100	1925	2053	920	1109	1573	2136	1515	2881	2370
MEAN	77.1	232	165	62.1	70.8	29.7	37.0	50.7	71.2	48.9	92.9	79.0
MAX	562	2100	1530	202	328	217	332	300	397	323	1010	385
MIN	19	17	41	27	27	14	12	11	14	23	20	16
AC-FT	4740	13790	10120	3820	4070	1820	2200	3120	4240	3010	5710	4700
CFSM	5.17	15.5	11.0	4.17	4.75	1.99	2.48	3.41	4.78	3.28	6.24	5.30
IN.	5.97	17.35	12.73	4.81	5.13	2.30	2.77	3.93	5.33	3.78	7.19	5.92

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 35182.1 MEAN 96.4 MAX 2100 MIN 9.2 AC-FT 69780 CFSM 6.47 IN. 87.84
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 30922 MEAN 84.5 MAX 2100 MIN 11 AC-FT 61330 CFSM 5.67 IN. 77.20

RIO FAJARDO BASIN
50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987											
18...	0940	18	128	7.40	27.5	16	7.6	96	20	K910	2300
NOV											
30...	0930	127	96	6.80	25.0	5.2	7.4	89	11	310	2100
FEB 1988											
01...	0925	99	101	6.70	22.5	3.1	8.3	95	<10	K670	2900
APR											
04...	0940	16	130	7.70	24.5	1.4	7.8	93	77	K36	2700
JUN											
02...	0855	26	118	7.30	26.5	1.4	8.2	101	23	K140	930
AUG											
01...	0900	22	118	7.40	26.0	1.2	8.5	104	19	K40	2600

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
SEP 1987											
28...	34	0	7.2	4.0	13	1	2.0	50	<0.5	7.8	13
NOV											
30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	30	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	23	--	--	--
APR											
04...	37	0	7.9	4.2	13	1	1.1	41	<0.5	5.7	13
JUN											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	35	--	--	--
AUG											
01...	32	0	6.7	3.6	11	0.9	1.2	30	--	4.7	12

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
28...	0.30	26	92	4.4	34	--	<0.01	0.20	0.02	0.48
NOV										
30...	--	--	--	--	3	--	<0.01	0.30	0.02	0.28
FEB 1988										
01...	--	--	--	--	2	--	<0.01	0.20	0.02	--
APR										
04...	0.10	27	97	4.2	<1	--	<0.01	0.10	0.09	0.31
JUN										
02...	--	--	--	--	1	--	<0.01	0.30	<0.01	--
AUG										
01...	0.10	24	84	5.0	2	--	<0.01	0.20	<0.01	0.29

K = non-ideal count

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50071000 RIO FAJARDO NEAR FAJARDO, PR--Continued
 WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
SEP 1987 28...	0.5	0.3	2.9	0.07	<1	<100	10	<1	13	30
NOV 30...	0.3	0.6	2.7	0.02	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 01...	<0.2	--	--	0.04	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 04...	0.4	0.5	2.2	0.05	<1	<100	10	<1	<1	<10
JUN 02...	<0.2	--	--	0.02	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 01...	0.3	0.5	2.2	0.02	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE-NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE, TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY-LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
SEP 1987 28...	1600	<5	90	<0.10	<1	1	<10	<0.010	5	0.02
NOV 30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 04...	240	<5	10	<0.10	<1	1	<10	<0.010	4	0.01
JUN 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR-DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO-SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 02...	0855	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR EPOXIDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH-OXY-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL-PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL-TRI-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 02...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH-THA-LENES, POLY-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER-THANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX-APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI-THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T, TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP, TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 02...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO FAJARDO BASIN

50072500 RIO FAJARDO BELOW FAJARDO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'35", long 65°38'47", 1.2 mi (1.9 km) southwest of Playa de Fajardo, and 0.5 mi (0.8 km) east of Fajardo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--23.4 mi² (60.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATUR-ATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987											
28...	1250	12	193	7.90	31.0	5.5	5.2	70	17	K300	K270
NOV											
30...	1210	170	127	6.20	25.5	17	6.2	75	29	K1800	2100
FEB 1988											
01...	1235	101	121	6.90	24.0	3.0	8.6	102	42	2800	2400
APR											
04...	1225	20	180	7.70	27.5	3.0	7.8	98	97	K1500	K99
JUN											
02...	1140	25	146	7.20	29.5	6.6	6.6	86	30	490	210
AUG											
01...	1200	25	147	7.60	29.5	2.5	8.2	107	15	560	K60

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
SEP 1987											
28...	50	0	12	4.9	17	1	1.4	53	<0.5	7.0	26
NOV											
30...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	29	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	29	--	--	--
APR											
04...	50	6	12	4.8	16	1	1.2	44	<0.5	7.9	23
JUN											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	36	--	--	--
AUG											
01...	40	2	9.2	4.2	13	0.9	1.2	38	--	5.9	20

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
28...	0.30	25	130	4.2	4	--	<0.01	0.10	0.07	0.43
NOV										
30...	--	--	--	--	7	--	<0.01	0.40	0.04	0.26
FEB 1988										
01...	--	--	--	--	2	--	<0.01	0.20	0.04	0.16
APR										
04...	0.10	23	114	6.1	1	--	<0.01	0.20	<0.01	--
JUN										
02...	--	--	--	--	10	--	<0.01	0.10	0.03	--
AUG										
01...	0.10	22	98	6.7	5	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.02	0.48

K = non-ideal count

RIO BLANCO BASIN

50075000 RIO ICACOS NEAR NAGUABO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'38", long 65°47'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010001, in Caribbean National Forest, off Highway 191, at El Yunque, 1.6 mi (2.6 km) upstream from confluence with Rio Cubuy, 2.8 mi (4.5 km) north of Florida, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) northwest of Naguabo Plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--1.26 mi² (3.26 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1945 to March 1953 (operated by Puerto Rico Water Resources Authority), annual maximum, water years 1953-62, annual low-flow measurements 1962-66, October 1979 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder, crest-stage gage and sharp-crested weir. Elevation of gage is 2,020 ft (616 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--16 years (1946-52, 1980-88), 15.0 ft³/s (0.425 m³/s), 161.68 in/yr (4,107 mm/yr), 10,870 acre-ft/yr (13.4 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 14 ft³/s (0.40 m³/s), 10,100 acre-ft/yr (12 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 2,860 ft³/s (81.0 m³/s), Apr. 21, 1983, gage height, 8.96 ft (2.731 m), from rating curve extended above 30 ft³/s (0.850 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum daily discharge, 1.5 ft³/s (0.042 m³/s), Mar. 22, Apr. 10, 1946.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 650 ft³/s (18.4 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Dec. 7	unknown	*1,790	50.7	*7.60	2.316	Aug. 10	1815	843	23.9	5.82	1.774
May 10	1615	748	21.2	5.58	1.701						

Minimum discharge, 3.9 ft³/s (0.110 m³/s), June 18.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e16	e6.4	e16	e110	e80	e15	e8.2	6.8	5.6	9.6	6.0	8.6
2	e7.2	e6.1	e15	e35	e25	e10	e7.2	6.4	5.6	36	5.4	8.1
3	e13	e5.8	e20	e17	e18	e9.2	e6.8	6.0	5.6	6.9	26	7.9
4	e17	e5.8	e15	e18	e15	e8.2	e7.6	6.0	5.2	5.8	8.6	7.9
5	e8.2	e6.6	e11	e14	e14	e7.8	15	6.4	5.2	5.4	5.5	7.6
6	e6.6	e26	e15	e15	e13	e8.0	13	14	5.0	12	5.2	7.5
7	e6.1	e16	e220	e14	e12	e7.4	9.1	7.9	4.8	10	9.1	11
8	e6.1	e6.4	e120	e14	e12	e7.4	9.0	7.9	4.8	5.9	6.5	18
9	e6.1	e6.2	e13	e14	e14	e7.2	8.5	6.4	4.7	5.8	6.1	42
10	e5.8	e6.1	e10	e11	e11	e7.0	8.4	94	5.0	6.0	69	28
11	e5.8	e5.8	e11	e20	e10	e6.8	8.2	10	4.5	9.1	46	64
12	e5.3	e5.8	e8.8	e15	e18	e7.0	8.0	8.2	4.8	9.2	11	24
13	e5.1	e6.0	e7.6	e17	e14	e6.8	7.7	6.9	5.1	13	8.1	43
14	e5.8	e6.9	e7.0	e15	e10	e6.8	7.4	15	7.8	34	8.0	20
15	e14	e6.1	e29	e14	e24	e8.0	8.5	26	29	5.5	8.0	12
16	e23	e6.0	e12	e13	e11	e6.6	8.5	8.7	6.1	5.1	16	11
17	e26	e38	e8.6	e22	e9.0	e11	7.4	8.9	4.5	5.1	21	10
18	e16	e33	e8.0	e11	e14	e23	8.1	6.8	4.0	13	8.6	9.6
19	e10	e18	e66	e14	e11	e12	8.3	11	13	8.8	8.2	33
20	e7.5	e10	e76	e9.4	e14	e8.2	7.4	15	11	5.9	7.4	10
21	e7.8	e7.8	e50	e8.4	e9.0	e6.8	7.4	14	31	5.6	6.9	9.3
22	e7.6	e7.2	e23	e7.8	e7.6	e6.2	6.6	7.6	16	18	24	13
23	e6.6	e41	e14	e7.6	e12	e5.8	6.2	7.5	35	7.3	12	12
24	e16	e85	e21	e8.8	e26	e15	6.2	6.7	9.3	6.0	134	9.5
25	e11	e49	e17	e15	e11	e32	6.8	6.4	7.8	5.8	18	8.8
26	e10	e56	e33	e8.2	e15	e15	16	5.7	8.6	10	10	8.5
27	e7.3	e140	e17	e8.0	e43	e33	8.3	5.6	6.1	5.9	10	8.1
28	e7.7	e38	e27	e11	e30	e29	8.2	5.8	7.8	9.6	10	7.9
29	e7.2	e20	e15	e21	e25	e37	7.2	7.6	14	14	10	8.3
30	e6.6	e18	e12	e14	---	e24	9.2	7.1	7.2	15	10	7.9
31	e6.4	---	e52	e35	---	e12	---	6.6	---	6.3	9.2	---
TOTAL	304.8	689.0	970.0	557.2	527.6	399.2	254.4	358.9	284.1	315.6	543.8	476.5
MEAN	9.83	23.0	31.3	18.0	18.2	12.9	8.48	11.6	9.47	10.2	17.5	15.9
MAX	26	140	220	110	80	37	16	94	35	36	134	64
MIN	5.1	5.8	7.0	7.6	7.6	5.8	6.2	5.6	4.0	5.1	5.2	7.5
AC-FT	605	1370	1920	1110	1050	792	505	712	564	626	1080	945
CFSM	7.80	18.2	24.8	14.3	14.4	10.2	6.73	9.19	7.52	8.08	13.9	12.6
IN.	9.00	20.34	28.64	16.45	15.58	11.79	7.51	10.60	8.39	9.32	16.06	14.07

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 5208.8 MEAN 14.3 MAX 220 MIN 3.9 AC-FT 10330 CFSM 11.3 IN. 153.78
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 5681.1 MEAN 15.5 MAX 220 MIN 4.0 AC-FT 11270 CFSM 12.3 IN. 167.73

e Estimated

RIO BLANCO BASIN

50075000 RIO ICACOS NEAR MAGUABO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 13	1106	5.14	67.6	21.5	MAR, 03	0939	9.24	99	19.0
JAN, 15	1142	13.7	71	20.5	APR, 04	1224	19.4	58	19.5
FEB, 08	1105	12.2	68	19.5	JUL, 08	1209	6.12	59	22.0

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 20.--Southeastern river basin--Río Humacao to Río Seco basins.

RIO HUMACAO BASIN

50081000 RIO HUMACAO AT LAS PIEDRAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°10'27", long 65°52'11", Hydrologic unit 21010005, on left bank at downstream side of bridge on Highway 921, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) southeast of junction with Highway 30, 0.8 (1.3 km) downstream from Quebrada Blanca and 0.8 mi (1.3 km) south of Las Piedras.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.65 m² (17.22 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1958 to December 1967 (monthly discharge measurements), July 1974 to September 1977, October 1987 to September 1988.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (79.2 m), from topographic map. Prior to July 1974, crest-stage gage at different datum. July 1974 to September 1977 at site 90 ft (27m) upstream at present datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those above 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s), and estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 20,800 ft³/s (589 m³/s) Sept. 6, 1960, gage height, 34.4 ft (10.485 m), datum then in use, from floodmarks, and rating curve extended above 5,300 ft³/s (150 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum daily discharge, 2.2 ft³/s (0.062 m³/s) July 16, 1974.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,000 ft³/s (28.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 24	0200	1,420	40.2	5.32	1.622	Dec. 8	unknown	*20,000	566	*21.80	6.645
Nov. 27	0700	6,580	186	11.75	3.581	Aug. 24	1515	1,770	50.1	5.90	1.798

Minimum discharge, 5.5 ft³/s (0.156 m³/s), June 8-11.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	e20	e26	22	42	22	16	12	8.5	11	24	17	23
2	e14	e21	35	34	22	15	11	8.3	8.5	27	16	19
3	e16	e18	19	30	27	14	11	7.7	7.9	15	16	19
4	e18	e45	17	31	20	14	11	7.4	7.8	12	16	18
5	e16	e40	15	46	25	14	14	7.6	6.9	11	15	18
6	e14	e80	39	42	20	13	13	42	6.6	33	14	17
7	e15	e45	1180	32	19	13	16	12	6.2	59	17	18
8	e14	e25	1220	33	21	13	11	8.5	5.9	16	16	17
9	e13	e23	87	33	25	13	10	6.9	9.3	13	16	37
10	e12	e21	66	29	21	13	10	12	7.4	25	53	27
11	e11	e20	58	33	24	13	10	14	5.7	19	48	178
12	e10	e23	51	32	21	13	9.9	9.2	7.9	16	22	84
13	e10	e26	46	27	36	13	9.9	8.2	11	16	18	45
14	e18	e19	42	27	19	15	9.5	11	6.3	37	16	35
15	e40	e17	40	25	18	13	10	12	34	15	17	28
16	e30	e19	38	24	17	12	11	11	29	13	18	26
17	e80	e22	35	24	16	13	9.5	8.4	13	16	20	22
18	e200	26	33	23	16	13	12	8.2	12	18	17	21
19	e60	21	32	22	16	12	11	8.7	9.9	17	15	65
20	e37	20	34	22	16	14	9.0	15	34	14	14	37
21	e34	19	33	22	16	14	8.4	11	22	12	14	24
22	e31	19	44	21	15	13	8.0	7.8	36	33	21	22
23	e28	26	31	21	15	11	8.4	7.3	19	22	21	22
24	e31	755	28	21	18	12	9.0	7.3	21	16	275	21
25	e37	158	27	21	17	13	8.5	6.6	15	21	84	19
26	e34	189	28	21	20	12	8.6	8.4	13	16	32	18
27	e32	1670	31	21	39	16	9.2	7.6	13	14	37	18
28	e29	317	33	21	17	14	8.3	7.3	12	42	31	18
29	e26	44	37	21	16	13	8.4	15	11	26	26	18
30	e24	28	36	20	---	12	9.2	30	11	19	25	17
31	e25	---	36	20	---	12	---	20	---	17	22	---
TOTAL	979	3782	3473	841	594	411	306.8	354.9	413.3	654	989	951
MEAN	31.6	126	112	27.1	20.5	13.3	10.2	11.4	13.8	21.1	31.9	31.7
MAX	200	1670	1220	46	39	16	16	42	36	59	275	178
MIN	10	17	15	20	15	11	8.0	6.6	5.7	11	14	17
AC-FT	1940	7500	6890	1670	1180	815	609	704	820	1300	1960	1890
CFSM	4.75	19.0	16.8	4.08	3.08	1.99	1.54	1.72	2.07	3.17	4.80	4.77
IN.	5.48	21.16	19.43	4.70	3.32	2.30	1.72	1.99	2.31	3.66	5.53	5.32

WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 13749.0 MEAN 37.6 MAX 1670 MIN 5.7 AC-FT 27270 CFSM 5.65 IN. 76.91

e Estimated

RIO HUMACAO BASIN

50082000 RIO HUMACAO AT HIGHWAY 3 AT HUMACAO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18 08'49", long 65 49'37", at bridge on Highway 3, 300 ft (91 m) downstream from Quebrada Mariana, and 0.4 mi (0.6 km) south of Humacao.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.3 mi² (44.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-66, 1969 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
08...	1140	25	273	7.40	30.0	57	5.6	74	29	K150000	47000
DEC											
03...	1130	62	214	7.00	27.5	43	6.6	83	21	K17000	4700
FEB 1988											
24...	1105	41	274	6.70	27.0	65	7.3	91	56	K70000	46000
APR											
07...	1115	234	294	7.50	29.0	33	6.2	80	18	320000	290000
JUN											
14...	1045	19	312	7.40	31.0	22	5.1	68	120	320000	K120000
AUG											
18...	1045	28	262	7.30	29.0	20	6.0	78	<10	33000	7000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD MG/L AS CaCO3	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CaCO3	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
08...	81	0	22	6.3	25	1	3.8	84	<0.5	14	26
DEC											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	61	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	83	--	--	--
APR											
07...	76	0	21	5.7	25	1	2.8	88	<0.5	18	27
JUN											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	94	--	--	--
AUG											
18...	74	0	20	5.8	22	1	2.4	75	--	13	21

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
08...	0.20	36	184	12	88	0.77	0.03	0.80	0.61	0.59
DEC										
03...	--	--	--	--	47	0.78	0.02	0.80	0.11	0.49
FEB 1988										
24...	--	--	--	--	172	0.84	0.06	0.90	0.57	0.43
APR										
07...	0.30	33	187	12	120	0.67	0.03	0.70	2.30	1.30
JUN										
14...	--	--	--	--	35	0.39	0.01	0.40	0.84	0.56
AUG										
18...	0.10	34	164	12	31	0.86	0.04	0.90	0.28	0.22

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50083500 RIO GUAYANES AT YABUCOA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'33", long 65°54'03", at bridge on Highway 182, 1.4 mi (2.2 km) west-northwest of Yabucoa plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.2 mi² (44.6 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-62, 1968-70, 1980 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PERCENT SATURATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
14...	1230	281	85	7.20	26.5	95	6.8	84	<10	38000	240000
DEC 15...	1310	99	152	6.50	24.5	62	7.7	93	28	2000	4600
FEB 1988											
23...	1155	40	153	6.60	24.0	7.7	4.3	51	12	2100	K1500
APR 19...	1110	25	115	7.50	27.0	4.2	3.2	40	37	K930	540
JUN 16...	1200	332	81	6.50	27.5	260	5.9	74	<10	61000	510000
AUG 17...	1050	32	157	7.20	26.5	7.5	7.6	94	17	K1700	3000

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
14...	22	2	5.5	1.9	7.6	0.7	2.8	20	<0.5	11	8.8
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	49	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	60	--	--	--
APR 19...	49	0	12	4.7	16	1	1.3	60	<0.5	5.6	12
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	21	--	--	--
AUG 17...	49	0	12	4.7	15	1	1.7	56	--	5.4	10

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
14...	0.10	18	68	52	160	0.56	0.04	0.60	0.15	1.50
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	102	0.49	0.01	0.50	0.02	0.38
FEB 1988										
23...	--	--	--	--	10	0.49	0.01	0.50	0.03	0.27
APR 19...	0.20	37	126	8.5	7	0.29	0.01	0.30	0.09	0.51
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	31	0.37	0.03	0.40	0.08	0.62
AUG 17...	0.10	36	118	10	15	0.65	0.05	0.70	0.21	0.89

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50083500 RIO GUAYANES AT YABUCOA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS-PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO-MIUM, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1987 14...	1.7	2.3	10	0.22	<1	200	<10	1	<1	30
DEC 15...	0.4	0.9	4.0	0.07	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 23...	0.3	0.8	3.5	0.06	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 19...	0.6	0.9	4.0	0.05	<1	100	<10	1	2	200
JUN 16...	0.7	1.1	4.9	0.14	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 17...	1.1	1.8	8.0	0.09	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA-NESE, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE-NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV-ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METH-YLENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB-STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1987 14...	11000	<5	480	<0.10	<1	<1	120	<0.010	7	0.02
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 19...	860	<5	60	<0.10	<1	<1	20	<0.010	<1	0.02
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 17...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR-DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-AZINOM, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI-ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO-SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 16...	1200	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA-CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH-OXY-CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL-PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL-TRI-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 16...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA-THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH-THA-LENES, POLY-CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER-THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX-APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI-THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 16...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO GUAYANES BASIN

50086500 RIO GUAYANES ABOVE MOUTH AT PLAYA DE GUAYANES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'45", long 65°49'42", at old railroad crossing, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) from mouth, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Playa de Guayanes, and 3.5 mi (5.6 km) northeast of Yabucoa plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--34.0 mi² (88.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
08...	0850	43	186	7.60	26.0	13	7.2	88	20	2700	K1400
DEC											
03...	0900	172	182	6.40	25.0	45	6.4	78	18	2200	5700
FEB 1988											
24...	0815	E130	278	6.50	23.5	18	6.2	72	21	2300	K18000
APR											
07...	0830	49	173	7.70	24.0	120	6.7	79	11	5800	8200
JUN											
14...	0830	27	171	7.60	27.0	25	6.2	77	<10	2100	4800
AUG											
18...	0850	E50	162	7.50	27.5	30	6.2	78	<10	2300	3600

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
08...	48	0	12	4.4	16	1	2.2	57	<0.5	7.9	12
DEC											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	45	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
24...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	90	--	--	--
APR											
07...	49	0	12	4.6	18	1	2.2	49	<0.5	9.5	16
JUN											
14...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	57	--	--	--
AUG											
18...	45	0	11	4.2	16	1	2.4	52	--	6.8	12

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
08...	0.20	37	126	15	13	0.29	0.01	0.30	0.02	0.38
DEC										
03...	--	--	--	--	35	0.58	0.02	0.60	0.05	1.70
FEB 1988										
24...	--	--	--	--	30	0.49	0.01	0.50	0.02	0.58
APR										
07...	0.20	32	131	17	168	0.37	0.03	0.40	0.12	0.48
JUN										
14...	--	--	--	--	46	--	<0.01	0.30	<0.01	--
AUG										
18...	0.10	36	120	--	41	0.78	0.02	0.80	0.03	--

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO MAUNABO BASIN

50091000 RIO MAUNABO AT MAUNABO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'24", long 65°54'19", at bridge on Highway 3, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) southwest of Maunabo plaza, and 1.3 mi (2.1 km) upstream from mouth.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.4 mi² (32.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958-66, 1975 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
14...	0845	48	169	7.70	26.0	180	5.0	61	<10	330000	410000
DEC 16...	1215	56	204	6.90	27.0	11	6.8	85	36	2400	510
FEB 1988											
23...	0930	21	247	6.80	23.5	17	7.8	90	18	2300	2600
APR 19...	0900	16	254	7.60	25.5	38	7.0	85	20	20000	7600
JUN 16...	0915	54	165	7.70	25.0	34	6.9	83	<10	4900	21000
AUG 17...	0820	27	233	7.30	25.5	20	6.8	82	16	4600	4800

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
14...	51	0	13	4.6	15	0.9	2.6	57	<0.5	11	13
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	80	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
23...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	88	--	--	--
APR 19...	91	4	20	10	21	1	1.3	79	<0.5	11	17
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	51	--	--	--
AUG 17...	75	0	18	7.2	19	1	1.3	73	--	13	15

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TOMS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
14...	0.20	28	122	16	194	0.27	0.03	0.30	0.07	1.90
DEC 16...	--	--	--	--	16	0.69	0.01	0.70	0.01	0.19
FEB 1988										
23...	--	--	--	--	46	0.39	0.01	0.40	0.02	0.28
APR 19...	0.20	50	183	7.7	217	0.18	0.02	0.20	0.62	0.68
JUN 16...	--	--	--	--	25	0.69	0.01	0.70	0.07	0.13
AUG 17...	0.10	37	156	11	22	--	<0.01	0.50	0.02	--

RIO CHICO BASIN

50091800 RIO CHICO AT PROVIDENCIA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'16", long 66°00'18", at flat low bridge 200 ft (61 m) south of Highway 3, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) above mouth, and 1.5 mi (2.4 km) southeast of Patillas plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.9 mi² (12.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
19...	1015	16	264	8.00	26.5	21	7.4	91	<10	560000	28000
DEC											
01...	0930	26	271	7.00	25.0	3.4	4.0	48	14	K96000	K19000
FEB 1988											
08...	1105	4.6	407	7.30	24.5	15	6.0	72	120	23000	6400
APR											
11...	1055	0.93	900	7.60	30.0	33	1.0	13	200	1400000	K600000
JUN											
07...	1235	E0.50	798	7.30	33.0	29	0.0	0	200	5800000	730000
AUG											
12...	0915	4.8	376	7.60	28.0	6.1	4.6	58	41	5700000	1000000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
19...	75	0	17	7.9	27	1	2.2	80	<0.5	17	20
DEC											
01...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	94	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	150	--	--	--
APR											
11...	160	0	38	16	64	2	9.9	290	<0.5	50	64
JUN											
07...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--
AUG											
12...	100	0	23	11	35	2	2.6	130	--	15	26

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
19...	0.20	29	168	7.1	18	0.69	0.01	0.70	0.94	0.76
DEC										
01...	--	--	--	--	4	0.59	<0.01	0.60	0.63	0.87
FEB 1988										
08...	--	--	--	--	21	0.28	0.02	0.30	2.6	2.4
APR										
11...	0.20	33	459	1.2	56	--	0.04	<0.10	35.0	17
JUN										
07...	--	--	--	--	54	--	0.04	<0.10	18.0	8.0
AUG										
12...	0.10	31	207	2.7	11	0.29	<0.01	0.30	0.03	7.0

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'04", long 66°01'58", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, at foot bridge, off Highway 184, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) upstream from Lago Patillas Dam and 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of Patillas.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.3 mi² (47.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1959 to October 1965 (annual low-flow and occasional measurements only), January 1966 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 235 ft (72 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for July 23 to Aug. 2 and Aug. 11-19, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--22 years (1967-88), 61.3 ft³/s (1.736 m³/s), 45.49 in/yr (1,155 mm/yr), 44,410 acre-ft/yr (54.8 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 61 ft³/s (1.73 m³/s), 44,200 acre-ft/yr (54 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 14,800 ft³/s (419 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 12.45 ft (3.795 m), from rating curve extended above 250 ft³/s (7.08 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 4.6 ft³/s (0.130 m³/s), May 13-16, 1968.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,500 ft³/s (70.8 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 18	0415	4,720	134	10.30	3.139	July 2	0845	4,850	137	10.39	3.167
Nov. 24	1815	3,830	108	9.63	2.935	Aug. 24	1615	4,970	141	10.47	3.191
Nov. 27	1015	*8,130	230	*12.33	3.758	Sept. 11	1145	4,270	121	9.98	3.042
Dec. 7	2315	5,720	162	10.96	3.341						

Minimum discharge, 9.5 ft³/s (0.269 m³/s), June 12, 13.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	55	35	172	96	51	31	34	30	13	350	59	71
2	29	31	126	94	76	34	32	23	13	1320	48	61
3	26	26	94	81	102	30	30	16	13	180	72	55
4	37	37	75	80	58	29	28	13	13	99	75	50
5	43	97	63	83	57	28	28	13	13	74	50	46
6	26	142	72	75	51	28	34	97	12	64	45	44
7	22	81	526	68	41	28	40	42	11	104	53	57
8	20	49	566	66	40	28	32	22	11	57	43	49
9	20	38	204	66	39	27	29	17	13	52	41	71
10	19	33	143	77	40	27	23	22	12	73	182	129
11	17	29	164	91	43	26	21	21	13	60	199	886
12	16	28	134	86	58	25	21	33	13	56	77	506
13	17	27	104	67	81	24	21	19	17	49	53	250
14	38	26	86	64	49	25	19	17	38	75	44	240
15	76	23	76	54	48	23	31	46	371	49	42	148
16	77	54	67	49	45	22	31	33	85	43	50	114
17	243	43	61	45	38	21	29	22	35	42	82	94
18	901	59	56	42	40	21	33	22	22	74	98	81
19	204	46	54	41	38	20	32	58	42	58	55	104
20	104	32	64	38	49	42	21	67	70	48	49	80
21	75	28	77	36	39	28	19	72	128	41	45	66
22	62	25	138	35	35	25	18	39	130	46	265	63
23	52	53	71	34	34	26	17	26	94	80	256	59
24	48	1610	57	33	49	27	15	22	49	74	852	54
25	49	605	51	33	40	34	16	19	31	70	487	50
26	63	568	46	33	34	40	15	17	28	88	184	45
27	66	1730	45	38	46	95	16	19	24	70	121	42
28	59	1350	49	35	35	113	13	17	21	169	108	40
29	61	446	45	40	32	63	19	16	24	114	130	38
30	41	259	39	35	---	42	14	16	105	236	108	37
31	36	---	50	31	---	37	---	16	---	108	84	---
TOTAL	2602	7610	3575	1746	1388	1069	731	912	1464	4023	4057	3630
MEAN	83.9	254	115	56.3	47.9	34.5	24.4	29.4	48.8	130	131	121
MAX	901	1730	566	96	102	113	40	97	371	1320	852	886
MIN	16	23	39	31	32	20	13	13	11	41	41	37
AC-FT	5160	15090	7090	3460	2750	2120	1450	1810	2900	7980	8050	7200
CFSM	4.59	13.9	6.30	3.08	2.62	1.88	1.33	1.61	2.67	7.09	7.15	6.61
IN.	5.29	15.47	7.27	3.55	2.82	2.17	1.49	1.85	2.98	8.18	8.25	7.38

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 23969.9 MEAN 65.7 MAX 1730 MIN 8.5 AC-FT 47540 CFSM 3.59 IN. 48.73
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 32807 MEAN 89.6 MAX 1730 MIN 11 AC-FT 65070 CFSM 4.90 IN. 66.69

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)
OCT 1987											
07...	1100	22	139	7.80	26.0	0.7	8.4	103	280	320	44
JAN 1988											
20...	1030	39	151	7.00	21.0	1.3	9.7	109	580	3600	48
APR											
18...	1100	28	134	8.00	24.5	5.3	7.8	93	570	910	43
JUL											
13...	1330	50	136	8.60	29.5	1.2	7.7	100	590	580	42

DATE	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S102)
OCT 1987											
07...	31	10	4.7	12	0.8	0.8	13	9.6	9.5	0.2	23
JAN 1988											
20...	0	11	5.0	13	0.8	0.6	56	11	10	0.2	26
APR											
18...	0	9.8	4.5	12	0.8	0.5	46	12	9.8	0.1	22
JUL											
13...	0	9.5	4.5	13	0.9	0.7	43	10	10	0.1	25

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITRO-GEN, AM-MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOS-PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHOROUS DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-ORTH, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOS-PHATE, ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P04)
OCT 1987											
07...	94	78	4.60	<0.10	0.04	0.05	0.6	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03
JAN 1988											
20...	105	108	11.2	0.15	0.02	0.03	0.2	0.02	0.02	<0.01	--
APR											
18...	94	99	7.4	0.13	0.03	0.04	<0.2	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.06
JUL											
13...	92	99	13.4	<0.10	0.05	0.06	0.5	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.06

DATE	ALUM-INUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AL) (01106)	ARSENIC DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AS) (01000)	BARIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS BA) (01005)	BERYL-LIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS BE) (01010)	CADMIUM DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CD) (01025)	CHRO-MIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CR) (01030)	COBALT, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CO) (01035)	COPPER, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CU) (01040)	IRON, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS FE) (01046)	LEAD, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS PB) (01049)
OCT 1987										
07...	<10	<1	10	<0.5	3	<1	<3	5	36	<5
JAN 1988										
20...	10	3	11	<0.5	1	<1	<3	1	35	<5
APR										
18...	60	<1	11	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	1	89	<5
JUL										
13...	30	<1	11	<0.5	2	<1	<3	4	41	<5

RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS BASIN

50092000 RIO GRANDE DE PATILLAS NEAR PATILLAS, PR--Continued
(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STROM- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1987 07...	6	12	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1	37	<6	24
JAN 1988 20...	<4	17	<0.1	<10	2	<1	<1	38	<6	10
APR 18...	<4	6	0.2	<10	<1	<1	<1	35	<6	<3
JUL 13...	<4	14	<0.1	<10	1	<1	<1	34	<6	15

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
JAN 1987 20...	1030	22	19	1.14	83
APR 1988 18...	1100	28	15	1.14	56
JUL 13...	1330	50	2.2	0.29	78

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 21.--South coast river basins--Río Salinas to Río Jacaguas basins.

RIO COAMO BASIN

50106500 RIO COAMO NEAR COAMO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18 03'52", long 66 22'10", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 153 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) above Rio de la Mina, and 1.8 mi (2.9 km) south of Coamo plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--46.0 mi² (119.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1978 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987										
15...	1215	9.1	647	8.10	31.0	1.1	6.0	81	40	250 350
DEC										
21...	1140	80	598	7.80	26.0	2.0	11.4	141	86	3800 7300
FEB 1988										
22...	1235	17	684	7.80	27.5	2.0	9.4	118	<10	330 K50
APR										
21...	1125	28	517	7.90	28.0	6.2	6.2	80	<10	100000 26000
JUN										
21...	1205	7.0	646	7.50	29.5	1.2	4.5	59	<10	2500 290
AUG										
16...	1135	3.8	696	7.70	31.5	0.5	5.4	72	21	47000 K17000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
15...	240	18	64	19	36	1	3.6	220	<0.5	32	36
DEC											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	270	--	--	--
APR											
21...	190	9	50	15	27	0.9	2.4	180	<0.5	27	28
JUN											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--
AUG											
16...	270	14	71	23	44	1	4.0	260	--	32	49

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
15...	0.20	31	354	8.7	<1	1.19	0.21	1.4	0.20	0.50
DEC										
21...	--	--	--	--	2	2.53	0.07	2.6	0.07	0.33
FEB 1988										
22...	--	--	--	--	10	1.74	0.16	1.9	0.33	0.37
APR										
21...	0.20	29	285	22	42	1.50	0.10	1.6	0.88	0.72
JUN										
21...	--	--	--	--	5	1.06	0.24	1.3	0.56	0.74
AUG										
16...	0.20	35	413	4.3	4	0.91	0.19	1.1	1.40	0.10

K = non-ideal count

RIO DESCALABRADO BASIN

50108000 RIO DESCALABRADO NEAR LOS LLANOS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'08", long 66°25'34", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on Highway 14, 1.5 mi (2.4 km) west of Los Llanos, and 5.3 mi (8.5 km) east of Juana Diaz.

DRAINAGE AREA.--12.9 mi² (33.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1959-65 (annual low-flow measurements only), 1965 (annual maximum discharge), January 1966 to June 1969, July to December 1969 (maximum discharge only), February 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 220 ft (67 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 30,000 ft³/s (850 m³/s) Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 24.37 ft (7.43 m), from rating curve extended above 10,000 ft³/s (283 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; no flow many days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 8	1645	1,810	51.3	8.23	2.509	Nov. 27	1630	*9,040	256	*16.05	4.892
Oct. 26	2315	2,000	56.6	unknown							

Minimum discharge, 0.32 ft³/s (0.009 m³/s), Aug. 1-3.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1.0	e10	e14	e11	6.2	2.8	1.7	e1.6	.72	1.8	.43	18
2	.80	e7.0	e13	e11	6.3	2.8	e1.7	e1.5	.69	2.1	.41	8.1
3	.90	e5.5	e13	e10	6.0	2.4	e1.6	1.4	.68	1.7	6.4	3.7
4	.72	e4.5	e12	e10	5.6	2.3	e1.6	e1.2	.67	1.5	1.8	3.5
5	.65	e4.0	e12	e9.5	5.5	2.4	1.5	e1.3	.70	1.2	.54	3.3
6	.80	85	e11	e9.2	5.6	2.3	1.8	e1.5	.70	1.0	.50	3.0
7	.80	e6.2	184	e9.2	5.2	2.1	2.4	e1.3	.68	.90	.51	3.2
8	e82	e2.7	e40	e9.0	4.6	2.1	1.8	e1.2	.67	.85	.48	3.8
9	e10	e3.7	e30	e9.0	4.5	2.2	1.7	e1.2	.65	.82	.51	4.1
10	e6.0	31	e28	e8.8	4.5	2.2	1.7	e10	.64	.80	1.4	4.3
11	e4.0	3.5	87	e8.8	4.1	2.1	1.6	e3.0	.78	.80	.67	9.6
12	e3.0	32	38	e8.6	4.2	2.1	1.5	e1.5	1.6	.75	.49	25
13	e2.5	7.9	e20	e8.5	4.2	2.4	1.5	e1.3	1.0	.70	3.0	4.2
14	e2.2	e4.0	e18	e8.4	4.0	2.3	1.6	e1.2	.72	.67	.65	2.8
15	e2.0	e3.0	e17	e8.3	3.8	2.1	1.7	e1.5	.88	.65	.46	2.8
16	e1.8	e2.5	e16	e8.2	3.5	2.0	1.9	e1.3	.91	27	.46	2.1
17	e10	e2.0	e16	e8.1	3.3	2.2	2.5	e1.1	.94	37	.72	24
18	e8.0	e1.8	e15	e8.0	3.2	2.4	e1.7	e1.0	.87	5.3	27	4.0
19	e20	e1.7	e16	e7.8	3.2	2.3	e1.5	e1.0	.94	2.7	.72	2.9
20	e8.0	e1.6	e17	7.7	3.1	2.4	e1.4	e3.0	1.1	2.2	.52	2.7
21	e6.0	e1.5	e15	7.6	3.0	2.4	e1.4	e1.5	1.0	1.8	.52	18
22	e50	e1.4	e14	7.5	2.9	2.2	56	e1.2	.94	1.6	.80	3.8
23	e25	e1.4	e13	7.2	2.9	2.2	2.1	e1.5	1.1	1.5	1.9	2.7
24	e12	57	e13	7.2	2.9	2.2	1.8	e1.2	9.5	1.3	185	3.0
25	e10	10	e12	7.2	2.7	2.2	1.7	e1.0	3.0	1.1	29	3.3
26	e130	5.1	e12	7.0	2.8	2.3	1.7	e.90	1.8	1.0	6.2	8.1
27	e210	697	e13	6.8	2.9	2.2	1.6	e.85	1.8	.97	3.6	3.4
28	e20	32	e14	6.8	2.7	2.7	1.5	.80	1.7	.82	2.6	2.2
29	e10	e20	e13	6.6	2.8	2.2	e1.6	.80	1.6	.74	2.0	1.9
30	e20	e16	e12	6.2	---	2.1	e1.8	.76	1.5	.74	1.6	17
31	e15	---	e12	6.3	---	1.9	---	.72	---	.55	1.5	---
TOTAL	673.17	1061.0	760	255.5	116.2	70.5	105.6	49.33	40.48	102.56	282.39	198.5
MEAN	21.7	35.4	24.5	8.24	4.01	2.27	3.52	1.59	1.35	3.31	9.11	6.62
MAX	210	697	184	11	6.3	2.8	56	10	9.5	37	185	25
MIN	.65	1.4	11	6.2	2.7	1.9	1.4	.72	.64	.55	.41	1.9
AC-FT	1340	2100	1510	507	230	140	209	98	80	203	560	394
CFSM	1.68	2.74	1.90	.64	.31	.18	.27	.12	.10	.26	.71	.51
IN.	1.94	3.06	2.19	.74	.34	.20	.30	.14	.12	.30	.81	.57

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 3682.75 MEAN 10.1 MAX 697 MIN .23 AC-FT 7300 CFSM .78 IN. 10.62
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 3715.23 MEAN 10.2 MAX 697 MIN .41 AC-FT 7370 CFSM .79 IN. 10.71

e Estimated

RIO DESCALABRADO BASIN

50108000 RIO DESCALABRADO NEAR LOS LLANOS, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985, OCTOBER 1987 TO AUGUST 1988

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 08	1131	1.07	604	29.0	MAR, 09	1020	2.32	683	24.0
NOV, 09	0921	4.01	500	25.5	APR, 13	1025	1.63	644	28.0
DEC, 07	1421	110	291	26.5	MAY, 03	1338	1.41	680	31.0
JAN, 20	1306	7.73	656	25.5	AUG, 01	0931	0.51	757	27.5
FEB, 17	1603	3.16	643	26.0					

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50111500 RIO JACAGUAS AT JUANA DIAZ, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°03'16", long 66°30'40", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on Highway 14 bridge, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) west of Juana Diaz plaza, and 4.0 mi (6.4 km) downstream from Lago Guayabal.

DRAINAGE AREA.--49.8 mi² (129.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1984 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 131 ft (40 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor. Flow regulation from Lago Guayabal.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 40,000 ft³/s (1,130 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 29.42 ft (8.967 m) from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and logarithmic extension; minimum daily discharge, 1.2 ft³/s (0.034 m³/s), May 18, 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Maximum discharge, 32,100 ft³/s (909 m³/s), Nov. 27, gage height, 26.97 ft (8.220 m) from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and logarithmic extension; minimum daily discharge 3.4 ft³/s (0.096 m³/s), June 4.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.3	86	325	62	e18	7.2	5.6	4.5	5.1	6.6	8.6	e15
2	6.0	43	282	115	e9.0	7.2	4.9	4.8	5.4	7.1	8.6	e14
3	5.5	63	216	98	e6.0	6.4	4.9	5.2	4.4	6.3	9.8	e13
4	5.5	46	173	65	e5.2	6.4	4.9	5.1	3.4	10	11	e12
5	5.5	41	182	32	e5.0	6.6	6.1	5.5	3.5	14	9.8	e13
6	5.4	224	191	19	e5.4	6.6	6.7	5.8	3.6	7.3	9.3	e11
7	4.9	130	228	17	e9.0	6.6	7.0	6.4	3.7	6.5	8.8	e10
8	34	134	171	20	e6.0	6.6	6.8	6.1	3.8	5.8	9.1	e9.8
9	74	222	107	39	e5.4	6.4	6.7	5.8	3.9	5.3	9.6	e9.8
10	25	122	127	29	e6.0	7.2	6.9	6.9	3.8	5.5	9.3	e11
11	20	99	268	40	e8.0	10	7.0	5.5	3.7	5.3	6.7	e19
12	40	103	510	45	e6.2	10	6.6	5.3	5.7	5.3	5.8	e20
13	22	125	177	19	e6.0	9.3	5.4	5.1	5.2	5.4	6.6	e16
14	22	64	149	22	e6.4	9.0	5.1	4.9	4.3	6.1	6.9	14
15	37	38	145	18	e8.0	8.8	5.2	4.6	4.7	5.3	5.2	15
16	25	21	154	29	e18	8.8	5.4	4.8	5.7	36	5.0	31
17	28	22	146	64	e15	8.8	7.5	4.4	4.7	116	9.2	11
18	102	28	138	26	e9.0	9.1	8.3	3.9	27	21	48	12
19	90	20	142	53	e7.0	8.9	6.7	4.5	6.8	9.6	10	12
20	44	19	133	58	e6.0	8.1	7.7	4.2	6.6	8.0	7.2	13
21	92	17	97	35	e5.4	8.2	7.5	4.1	6.1	7.4	6.1	11
22	191	9.1	126	30	e7.0	8.3	6.7	4.5	5.3	7.4	6.1	14
23	214	5.5	102	9.6	e6.0	8.3	7.5	4.4	5.1	6.9	20	23
24	87	343	71	6.5	e5.4	7.6	7.1	4.7	7.1	7.8	527	23
25	17	264	83	5.1	e5.2	7.6	6.0	4.7	6.1	8.3	177	27
26	27	108	71	13	5.8	7.7	5.1	4.7	5.5	8.4	58	24
27	812	4530	56	26	5.9	7.4	4.9	4.4	5.5	8.2	e25	61
28	188	749	44	31	5.9	7.8	4.8	4.3	5.7	8.3	e21	42
29	118	549	17	e15	5.9	8.6	5.1	4.4	5.7	8.6	e18	25
30	165	376	25	e10	---	8.7	4.9	4.7	5.8	8.6	e16	24
31	228	---	36	e9.0	---	7.9	---	4.8	---	8.6	e17	---
TOTAL	2742.1	8600.6	4692	1060.2	217.1	246.1	185.0	153.0	172.9	380.9	1095.7	555.6
MEAN	88.5	287	151	34.2	7.49	7.94	6.17	4.94	5.76	12.3	35.3	18.5
MAX	812	4530	510	115	18	10	8.3	6.9	27	116	527	61
MIN	4.9	5.5	17	5.1	5.0	6.4	4.8	3.9	3.4	5.3	5.0	9.8
AC-FT	5440	17060	9310	2100	431	488	367	303	343	756	2170	1100
CFSM	1.78	5.76	3.04	.69	.15	.16	.12	.10	.12	.25	.71	.37
IN.	2.05	6.42	3.50	.79	.16	.18	.14	.11	.13	.28	.82	.42

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 29293.5 MEAN 80.3 MAX 4530 MIN 3.6 AC-FT 58100 CFSM 1.61 IN. 21.88
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 20101.2 MEAN 54.9 MAX 4530 MIN 3.4 AC-FT 39870 CFSM 1.10 IN. 15.02

e Estimated

RIO JACAGUAS BASIN

50111500 RIO JACAGUAS AT JUANA DIAZ, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS APRIL 1984 TO SEPTEMBER 1985, OCTOBER 1987 TO AUGUST 1988

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 08	0914	5.42	390	28.0	APR, 13	1254	5.56	361	32.0
NOV, 06	1046	138	225	27.5	MAY, 06	1128	5.48	350	30.5
JAN, 20	1041	56.4	288	24.0	AUG, 03	1504	8.67	355	31.0
FEB, 23	--	5.23	275	24.0					

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Figure 22.--South coast river basins--Río Inabón to Río Loco basins.

RIO INABON BASIN

50112500 RIO INABON AT REAL ABAJO, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°05'10", long 66°33'46", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, at bridge on private road, off Highway 511 at Hacienda La Concordia, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) upstream from diversion canal, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) north of Real Abajo, and 6.1 mi (9.8 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--9.70 mi² (25.12 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--1962-63 (annual low-flow measurements only), February to June 1964 (monthly measurements only), July 1964 to July 1970, April 1971 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 410 ft (125 m), from topographic map. Prior to April 1971 nonrecording gage and crest-stage gage at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--22 years (1965-69, 1972-88), 18.9 ft³/s (0.535 m³/s), 26.46 in/yr (672 mm/yr), 13,690 acre-ft/yr (16.8 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 18 ft³/s (0.51 m³/s), 13,000 acre-ft/yr (16 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 19,000 ft³/s (538 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 25.3 ft (7.71 m), datum then in use, from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 30 ft³/s (0.850 m³/s) on basis of contracted opening and flow-over-road measurements of peak flow; minimum daily discharge, 0.80 ft³/s (0.023 m³/s), July 23, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s), and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	1515	1,820	51.5	14.78	4.505	Sept. 24	1530	585	16.6	7.31	2.228
Aug. 24	1815	*3,480	98.6	*17.94	5.468						

Minimum discharge, 1.8 ft³/s (0.051 m³/s), May 31, June 1.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.3	60	41	14	7.8	8.8	4.5	5.9	2.5	26	4.8	56
2	9.3	57	35	17	8.2	11	4.0	5.6	3.1	23	4.3	43
3	27	53	32	13	9.0	6.2	3.9	5.4	6.7	17	4.3	32
4	19	49	29	13	7.8	5.5	4.0	4.8	4.6	16	6.6	31
5	13	56	28	13	7.5	5.2	4.0	4.4	3.2	28	4.5	34
6	12	53	25	14	7.1	5.0	9.8	5.4	2.7	27	3.8	31
7	27	47	31	14	6.8	5.0	11	5.8	3.4	19	3.7	30
8	60	43	27	12	6.7	5.0	6.2	5.8	5.1	16	3.9	29
9	31	51	23	12	6.9	4.9	5.2	15	3.2	14	3.7	28
10	44	52	28	11	6.9	4.8	4.4	11	2.8	13	26	28
11	33	42	46	11	6.4	4.8	4.0	8.8	3.4	13	12	45
12	37	39	49	12	6.2	4.6	4.6	9.0	26	12	6.5	46
13	62	37	33	11	6.7	4.7	4.5	5.9	17	36	5.3	38
14	55	34	28	11	7.0	5.2	4.0	4.9	8.4	24	4.8	34
15	45	33	25	11	6.2	4.6	3.7	5.3	16	14	5.6	31
16	38	32	24	10	6.0	4.2	5.4	8.5	18	11	4.8	30
17	37	31	22	10	5.8	4.3	14	5.8	9.4	14	7.0	27
18	67	30	20	10	5.4	4.3	16	5.0	16	10	36	25
19	56	29	20	9.9	4.9	3.5	11	5.5	12	8.5	11	24
20	50	28	19	9.8	4.5	4.0	13	5.7	14	7.8	8.3	24
21	47	27	17	9.6	4.6	4.5	8.6	4.8	15	7.1	6.9	27
22	51	26	17	9.6	4.5	4.2	10	4.1	19	7.2	12	38
23	80	28	16	9.4	5.0	3.9	11	3.9	48	7.1	17	42
24	59	73	15	8.9	5.3	3.7	7.9	3.7	46	7.0	274	77
25	48	50	15	8.7	5.3	3.7	6.0	3.3	29	6.2	121	53
26	47	40	15	8.9	5.5	4.2	5.1	3.2	31	7.1	47	39
27	128	351	14	8.4	8.7	5.9	4.6	7.3	22	5.8	46	33
28	97	130	14	8.5	6.3	13	19	3.7	27	5.3	36	34
29	90	78	14	11	5.6	20	13	3.5	31	5.6	25	25
30	90	53	13	8.5	---	7.8	7.5	3.6	21	5.7	21	52
31	95	---	13	7.6	---	5.5	---	3.0	---	5.6	49	---
TOTAL	1561.6	1712	748	337.8	184.6	182.0	229.9	177.6	466.5	419.0	821.8	1086
MEAN	50.4	57.1	24.1	10.9	6.37	5.87	7.66	5.73	15.5	13.5	26.5	36.2
MAX	128	351	49	17	9.0	20	19	15	48	36	274	77
MIN	7.3	26	13	7.6	4.5	3.5	3.7	3.0	2.5	5.3	3.7	24
AC-FT	3100	3400	1480	670	366	361	456	352	925	831	1630	2150
CFSM	5.19	5.88	2.49	1.12	.66	.61	.79	.59	1.60	1.39	2.73	3.73
IN.	5.99	6.57	2.87	1.30	.71	.70	.88	.68	1.79	1.61	3.15	4.16

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 7704.4 MEAN 21.1 MAX 351 MIN 2.8 AC-FT 15280 CFSM 2.18 IN. 29.55
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 7926.8 MEAN 21.7 MAX 351 MIN 2.5 AC-FT 15720 CFSM 2.23 IN. 30.40

RIO INABON BASIN

50112500 RIO INABON AT REAL ABAJO, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
NOV, 24	1156	50.0	220	23.0	APR, 13	1445	7.26	295	33.0
DEC, 28	1155	14.2	266	25.0	APR, 26	1441	4.72	265	28.5
JAN, 26	1043	9.18	288	23.5	MAY, 06	0915	8.13	322	27.5
FEB, 23	1142	5.19	286	25.0	JUN, 27	1111	22.5	228	26.0
MAR, 28	1034	10.2	262	23.5	JUL, 26	1148	7.14	257	27.5

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114000 RIO CERRILLOS NEAR PONCE, PR

Location.--Lat 18°04'15", long 66°34'51", Hydrologic unit 21010004, on right bank off Highway 139, 2.3 mi (3.7 km) upstream from Quebrada Ausubo and 4.6 mi (7.4 km) northeast of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--17.8 mi² (46.1 km²)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987										
20...	0945	59	252	8.30	25.0	190	7.8	95	12	2400 K16000
DEC										
11...	1050	83	255	7.60	26.0	16	8.2	100	38	K680 770
FEB 1988										
05...	1110	13	294	7.70	22.5	19	9.8	112	<10	K36 K30
APR										
15...	1130	14	279	8.60	28.5	7.3	7.8	100	26	K36 K50
JUN										
22...	1155	16	270	8.30	28.0	3.4	8.2	104	<10	K950 430
AUG										
04...	1135	18	273	8.40	28.0	7.3	8.6	109	24	K170 K200

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
20...	120	0	36	6.2	10	0.4	1.5	140	<0.5	17	6.8
DEC											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR											
15...	120	6	36	7.2	13	0.5	1.1	110	<0.5	21	8.8
JUN											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
AUG											
04...	120	5	34	8.2	20	0.8	1.3	110	--	18	9.3

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
20...	0.10	23	185	4.8	471	0.89	0.01	0.90	0.03	0.67
DEC										
11...	--	--	--	--	24	0.89	0.01	0.90	<0.01	0.69
FEB 1988										
05...	--	--	--	--	44	0.19	0.01	0.20	<0.01	0.29
APR										
15...	0.10	23	179	1.9	17	0.09	0.01	<0.10	0.02	0.38
JUN										
22...	--	--	--	--	8	--	<0.01	0.60	0.03	--
AUG										
04...	0.10	21	180	2.0	15	--	<0.01	0.20	0.02	--

K = non-ideal count

50114390 RIO BUCANA AT HWY 14 BRIDGE NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATON.--Lat.18°02'29", long 66°34'58". Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank 200 ft (61 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 14, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) southeast of Escuela Cerrillos, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) northeast of Degetau Plaza in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--24.9 mi² (64.5 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to September 1986 (maximum only), published as "Rio Bucana Floodway Channel at Highway 14 bridge", October 1986 to July 1987 (maximum only), August 1987 to current year.

GAGE.--Water stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 116.40 ft (35.500 m) above mean sea level. Prior to Oct. 1, 1986, crest stage gage located at Highway 14 bridge, at elevation of mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Only minor regulation of low flow at present.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge 17,400 ft³/s (493 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 13.48 ft (4.109 m), (previously published as 129.88 ft (39.59 m) msl) from floodmark and rating curve extended above 200 ft³/s (5.66 m³/s), on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum daily discharge, 5.4 ft³/s (0.153 m³/s), June 7, 1988, result of regulation.

EXTREMES FOR WATER YEAR 1987.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,600 ft³/s (45.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	(m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	(m)
Oct. 27	unknown	*1,980	56.1	*4.98	1.518						

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,600 ft³/s (45.3 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	(m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	(m)
Oct. 8	1915	2,290	64.9	5.33	1.625	Nov. 27	1615	*13,700	388	*12.14	3.700
Oct.10	1815	2,100	59.5	5.12	1.561	Aug. 24	1915	12,600	357	11.66	3.554
Oct.18	1745	1,720	48.7	4.67	1.423	Aug. 31	1800	1,710	48.4	4.66	1.420
Oct.31	1730	2,080	58.9	5.10	1.554						

Minimum daily discharge, 5.4 ft³/s (0.153 m³/s), June 7, result of regulation.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	10	292	87	28	17	9.9	8.2	12	6.4	45	11	323
2	12	170	114	31	16	13	7.6	11	6.9	39	8.9	174
3	39	103	62	28	15	9.9	7.5	9.8	11	30	11	93
4	78	116	50	27	15	9.0	7.5	9.8	10	22	13	64
5	31	321	57	25	15	8.6	7.5	9.2	8.5	36	11	51
6	11	297	44	25	15	8.6	8.0	8.9	6.6	235	11	40
7	20	116	127	24	15	8.6	14	9.2	5.4	58	9.6	37
8	319	68	62	24	14	8.4	8.6	8.6	8.8	29	8.9	34
9	189	51	40	23	15	8.2	7.8	9.7	6.5	20	8.6	27
10	364	49	55	23	15	8.2	7.2	19	5.8	16	13	27
11	196	53	85	21	14	8.2	6.9	15	7.0	13	25	88
12	86	37	80	20	14	8.2	7.5	22	43	13	12	87
13	83	28	58	21	11	8.2	7.4	12	80	47	11	67
14	109	21	48	21	13	8.2	6.9	10	20	73	11	37
15	72	18	43	20	13	8.1	6.9	9.0	14	35	13	36
16	36	19	40	21	12	7.7	6.9	22	73	19	11	46
17	30	17	38	20	11	7.7	11	11	30	34	26	54
18	476	14	36	20	11	9.5	27	8.4	154	50	146	57
19	246	12	35	19	11	8.1	11	9.6	109	18	48	58
20	70	12	34	19	11	7.5	15	9.2	44	16	22	26
21	41	10	32	19	11	7.7	20	8.0	40	14	17	25
22	70	10	31	19	10	7.8	13	8.2	20	15	17	48
23	212	22	31	19	9.7	7.5	32	7.0	97	13	37	45
24	112	588	31	18	9.4	6.8	19	6.1	168	23	2140	321
25	41	275	30	18	9.4	6.4	12	6.8	96	28	1280	360
26	31	75	29	17	9.4	6.7	10	6.7	74	11	386	167
27	610	2800	29	17	11	7.0	9.3	22	57	12	224	98
28	275	707	28	17	11	11	16	11	28	11	161	70
29	146	238	28	17	9.7	16	38	9.4	140	13	103	39
30	213	133	28	17	---	16	14	8.6	65	17	112	39
31	573	---	29	18	---	9.9	---	6.6	---	15	325	---
TOTAL	4801	6672	1521	656	363.6	276.6	373.7	335.8	1434.9	1020	5233.0	2638
MEAN	155	222	49.1	21.2	12.5	8.92	12.5	10.8	47.8	32.9	169	87.9
MAX	610	2800	127	31	17	16	38	22	168	235	2140	360
MIN	10	10	28	17	9.4	6.4	6.9	6.1	5.4	11	8.6	25
AC-FT	9520	13230	3020	1300	721	549	741	666	2850	2020	10380	5230
CFSM	6.22	8.93	1.97	.85	.50	.36	.50	.44	1.92	1.32	6.78	3.53
IN.	7.17	9.97	2.27	.98	.54	.41	.56	.50	2.14	1.52	7.82	3.94

WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 25325.6 MEAN 69.2 MAX 2800 MIN 5.4 AC-FT 50230 CFSM 2.78 IN. 37.84

RIO BUCANA BASIN

50114390 RIO BUCANA AT HWY 14 BRIDGE NEAR PONCE, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 07	1453	10.1	254	29.0	FEB, 22	1425	10.1	304	26.5
NOV, 05	1440	156	295	24.5	MAR, 09	1503	8.07	292	30.5
DEC, 10	1236	35.7	338	25.5	AUG, 03	1201	10.4	289	29.0
JAN, 15	1145	19.6	313	26.5					

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115000 RIO PORTUGUES NEAR PONCE, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'45", long 66°38'01", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on right bank 30 ft (9 m) upstream from bridge on Highway 504, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) upstream from small unnamed tributary, 4.4 mi (7.1 km) upstream from Rio Chiquito, and 4.7 mi (7.6 km) north of Plaza Degetau in Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--8.82 mi² (22.84 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February to June 1964 (monthly measurements only), July 1964 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 470 ft (143 m), from topographic map. Prior to Dec. 4, 1964, non-recording gage at same site and datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharge, which are poor. Some low-flow regulation due to unknown activity upstream.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--24 years (1965-88), 19.0 ft³/s (0.538 m³/s), 29.25 in/yr (743 mm/yr), 13,770 acre-ft/yr (17.0 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 18.5 ft³/s (0.52 m³/s), 13,400 acre-ft/yr (16 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 21,000 ft³/s (595 m³/s), Oct. 7, 1985, gage height, 20.2 ft (6.16 m), from floodmarks at downstream side of bridge, from rating curve extended above 150 ft³/s (4.25 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 1.0 ft³/s (0.028 m³/s), May 29, 1973.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 800 ft³/s (22.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Oct. 10	1600	1,690	47.9	7.68	2.341	July 5	2015	1,110	31.4	6.47	1.972
Oct. 18	1530	971	27.5	6.14	1.871	Aug. 24	1800	2,650	76.2	9.35	2.850
Nov. 27	1630	*2,800	79.3	*9.52	2.902	Aug. 25	0515	1,240	35.1	6.77	2.063

Minimum daily discharge, 2.4 ft³/s (0.068 m³/s), June 11.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12	91	60	12	6.7	6.0	4.0	3.3	2.7	15	6.5	44
2	11	65	56	13	6.9	5.8	3.6	3.1	2.8	12	5.9	31
3	12	45	45	11	7.5	5.6	3.8	3.1	3.8	10	5.7	21
4	15	e42	37	11	6.6	5.4	4.2	2.9	2.9	8.7	4.6	17
5	12	e50	45	11	6.6	5.3	3.8	2.8	2.8	85	3.6	14
6	10	92	32	11	6.4	5.1	4.0	2.9	2.6	63	3.4	12
7	20	54	52	10	6.3	5.2	3.7	3.0	2.6	18	3.1	17
8	45	43	47	10	6.3	5.0	3.4	2.8	2.6	11	2.9	15
9	32	33	31	10	7.3	4.8	3.5	8.2	2.5	8.1	2.6	13
10	193	45	37	9.8	7.0	4.7	3.3	12	2.5	6.8	2.7	12
11	93	60	50	9.7	6.1	4.6	3.4	7.0	2.8	6.9	3.0	54
12	29	39	49	10	6.5	4.6	3.4	4.8	51	10	2.8	82
13	24	30	32	10	7.0	4.5	3.3	3.5	20	7.5	2.7	53
14	24	24	26	10	7.9	4.8	3.2	3.2	9.1	7.5	12	30
15	23	32	22	9.9	6.2	4.7	3.4	8.1	13	6.5	29	31
16	18	42	19	9.4	6.0	4.6	3.4	11	17	13	2.5	50
17	15	16	18	9.9	5.8	4.9	5.5	5.7	7.2	16	5.8	35
18	189	14	17	9.3	5.7	4.9	8.2	5.4	45	6.6	18	25
19	79	12	17	9.0	5.5	4.2	3.8	5.5	22	7.0	6.6	21
20	37	12	15	8.6	5.7	4.7	15	5.5	10	6.4	5.1	18
21	26	12	14	8.2	5.7	4.6	7.5	4.8	9.8	5.5	3.2	17
22	26	11	14	7.9	5.7	4.1	12	4.4	8.2	7.2	3.8	16
23	62	25	13	7.9	5.6	3.9	9.3	4.0	13	7.9	57	15
24	37	220	13	7.7	5.7	4.0	4.3	4.1	65	15	551	55
25	35	103	13	7.7	5.6	3.8	3.6	4.1	26	8.2	375	85
26	41	22	12	7.6	5.5	3.9	3.3	3.9	26	6.6	83	57
27	94	765	11	7.4	7.3	4.6	3.2	7.2	18	6.4	49	32
28	114	234	13	7.2	5.8	4.9	23	4.1	64	6.1	31	24
29	71	99	12	7.6	5.6	9.5	8.2	3.7	42	6.4	23	20
30	54	72	11	7.1	---	13	4.0	3.7	16	6.2	38	25
31	120	---	12	6.7	---	5.1	---	2.8	---	5.4	38	---
TOTAL	1573	2404	845	287.6	182.5	160.8	168.3	150.6	512.9	405.9	1380.5	941
MEAN	50.7	80.1	27.3	9.28	6.29	5.19	5.61	4.86	17.1	13.1	44.5	31.4
MAX	193	765	60	13	7.9	13	23	12	65	85	551	85
MIN	10	11	11	6.7	5.5	3.8	3.2	2.8	2.5	5.4	2.5	12
AC-FT	3120	4770	1680	570	362	319	334	299	1020	805	2740	1870
CFSM	5.75	9.09	3.09	1.05	.71	.59	.64	.55	1.94	1.48	5.05	3.56
IN.	6.63	10.14	3.56	1.21	.77	.68	.71	.64	2.16	1.71	5.82	3.97

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 9189.1 MEAN 25.2 MAX 765 MIN 2.0 AC-FT 18230 CFSM 2.85 IN. 38.76
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 9012.1 MEAN 24.6 MAX 765 MIN 2.5 AC-FT 17880 CFSM 2.79 IN. 38.01

e Estimated

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50115000 RIO PORTUGUES NEAR PONCE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1964 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATUR-ATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
02...	0900	10	288	8.30	23.5	0.5	8.0	95	<10	380	3200
DEC											
11...	0810	33	281	7.50	23.0	3.3	8.7	101	35	K1900	88000
FEB 1988											
05...	0845	6.4	340	7.50	21.0	4.9	8.8	101	29	K82	310
APR											
15...	0855	3.4	340	8.50	25.0	0.4	8.2	100	14	K120	K2200
JUN											
22...	0930	7.1	293	8.40	24.5	1.6	8.3	99	<10	560	690
AUG											
05...	0930	3.9	310	8.40	25.0	0.3	7.9	96	96	310	220

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORPTION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
02...	140	7	42	7.8	9.6	0.4	1.3	130	<0.5	8.3	7.6
DEC											
11...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
05...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
APR											
15...	150	0	47	8.2	12	0.4	1.4	160	<0.5	11	11
JUN											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG											
05...	140	0	44	7.9	11	0.4	1.3	140	--	9.6	9.3

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
02...	0.10	21	176	4.8	<1	0.79	0.01	0.80	<0.01	--
DEC										
11...	--	--	--	--	9	1.09	0.01	1.10	0.01	0.19
FEB 1988										
05...	--	--	--	--	14	0.79	0.01	0.80	<0.01	--
APR										
15...	0.20	22	209	1.9	1	0.69	0.01	0.70	0.01	0.19
JUN										
22...	--	--	--	--	2	1.09	0.01	1.10	0.03	0.27
AUG										
05...	0.10	19	189	2.0	<1	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.02	0.38

K = non-ideal count

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50116200 RIO PORTUGUES AT PONCE, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'20", long 66°36'28", 1,300 ft (400 m) south of Las Americas Avenue Bridge, 1.2 mi (1.9 km) south of CSC 50115900, 0.8 mi (1.3 km) west of Highways 1 and 2 junction, and 0.7 mi (1.1 km) southeast of Ponce.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.9 mi² (49.0 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
15...	0920	31	330	8.60	25.0	3.5	8.0	96	<10	5900	K17000
DEC											
21...	0920	27	510	6.70	24.0	3.1	8.8	105	83	K8100	2200
FEB 1988											
22...	0930	12	536	6.40	23.5	9.4	7.3	85	15	K14000	960
APR											
21...	0910	23	421	8.10	26.0	18	8.0	98	<10	59000	22000
JUN											
21...	0910	20	372	8.20	26.5	7.8	8.5	105	<10	29000	2400
AUG											
16...	0915	6.3	1020	7.70	28.0	38	4.7	60	13	5000	720

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CACO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT (MG/L AS CACO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CACO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
15...	140	6	41	8.0	18	0.7	1.9	130	<0.5	22	13
DEC											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	180	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	160	--	--	--
APR											
21...	150	17	43	9.6	27	1	1.8	140	<0.5	39	24
JUN											
21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG											
16...	160	32	46	12	51	2	2.2	130	--	78	43

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
15...	0.10	21	203	17	2	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.02	0.28
DEC										
21...	--	--	--	--	5	1.08	0.02	1.10	0.04	0.16
FEB 1988										
22...	--	--	--	--	19	0.56	0.04	0.60	0.09	0.41
APR										
21...	0.20	20	243	15	60	0.86	0.04	0.90	0.30	0.30
JUN										
21...	--	--	--	--	42	0.66	0.04	0.70	0.09	0.31
AUG										
16...	0.20	22	334	5.6	22	0.31	0.09	0.40	0.15	0.45

K = non-ideal count

RIO PORTUGUES BASIN

50116200 RIO PORTUGUES AT PONCE, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1987 15...	0.3	1.1	4.9	0.06	<1	200	<10	1	<1	<10
DEC 21...	0.2	1.3	5.8	0.06	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 22...	0.5	1.1	4.9	0.14	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 21...	0.6	1.5	6.6	0.12	<1	<100	<10	1	<1	<10
JUN 21...	0.4	1.1	4.9	0.07	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 16...	0.6	1.0	4.4	0.20	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1987 15...	630	<5	40	<0.10	1	<1	30	<0.010	9	0.01
DEC 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 22...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 21...	1600	<5	80	<0.10	<1	<1	10	<0.010	1	0.02
JUN 21...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 21...	0910	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 21...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 21...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124200 RIO GUAYANILLA NEAR GUAYANILLA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°02'40", long 66°47'53", Hydrologic Unit 21010004, on left bank, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) north of junction of Highways 2 and 132, 0.6 mi (1.0 km) downstream from Quebrada Consejo, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) north-northwest from Plaza de Guayanilla.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.9 mi² (49.0 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1981 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 80 ft (24 m) from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--7 years (1982-88), 24.5 ft³/s (0.694 m³/s), 17.60 in/yr (447 mm/yr), 17,750 acre-ft/yr (21.9 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 14,700 ft³/s (416 m³/s), Sept. 12, 1982, gage height, 20.4 ft (6.21 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and indirect measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 1.6 ft³/s (0.045 m³/s), Aug. 16, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 800 ft³/s (22.7 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 10	1715	1,060	30.0	9.88	3.011	Aug. 24	2030	*4,300	122	*14.12	4.304
Oct. 23	1600	832	23.6	9.35	2.850	Sept. 11	2200	952	27.0	9.64	2.938
Oct. 24	1700	901	25.5	9.52	2.902	Sept. 23	1715	889	25.2	9.49	2.892
Nov. 24	1545	1,210	34.3	10.18	3.103	Sept. 25	1615	982	27.8	9.71	2.960
Nov. 27	1415	2,130	60.3	11.68	3.560						

Minimum discharge, 1.6 ft³/s (0.045 m³/s), Aug. 16, 17.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	10	40	112	21	8.1	6.8	5.2	4.1	3.6	5.1	3.8	20
2	8.4	44	92	20	9.3	8.4	4.9	3.7	2.9	4.4	3.0	24
3	7.4	27	74	18	11	5.1	5.5	3.4	2.8	4.0	e2.8	18
4	7.4	21	59	17	8.6	4.6	5.9	3.4	2.5	4.5	e2.6	17
5	8.9	19	64	17	8.4	4.5	5.9	3.4	2.7	10	e2.4	20
6	6.8	29	50	17	8.2	4.7	6.4	3.4	2.7	22	e2.2	22
7	6.7	44	49	16	8.1	4.8	7.5	3.9	2.5	8.5	e2.1	23
8	127	21	43	15	8.1	4.8	5.7	3.9	5.8	8.9	e2.0	27
9	58	17	36	14	9.6	4.7	5.2	44	3.2	7.3	e7.0	25
10	232	27	60	13	9.8	4.7	4.7	20	2.8	7.7	29	26
11	125	22	60	11	8.3	4.7	4.3	6.1	2.7	6.2	6.3	124
12	41	17	53	11	8.7	4.7	4.4	6.0	3.5	9.0	2.5	104
13	27	22	43	11	8.6	4.7	4.5	4.5	6.1	6.5	2.1	31
14	22	16	40	12	13	5.8	4.3	4.1	4.4	6.0	2.0	21
15	23	14	34	11	10	4.8	4.3	3.9	3.9	5.9	2.0	25
16	21	14	33	11	10	4.5	5.1	4.1	4.2	16	1.7	30
17	18	43	33	11	8.9	6.0	4.3	3.9	3.4	18	14	38
18	113	14	31	10	8.6	5.1	4.7	4.1	3.2	12	51	36
19	42	12	31	10	7.9	4.1	4.2	4.2	6.6	7.5	12	28
20	25	12	30	9.5	7.5	3.9	4.1	4.4	4.4	9.2	10	23
21	118	12	27	9.1	7.1	4.1	7.2	3.7	4.0	8.2	2.9	27
22	43	12	27	8.9	6.8	4.0	9.0	3.5	4.0	6.8	18	65
23	175	45	27	8.7	6.7	3.6	32	3.0	3.6	7.9	66	149
24	227	673	26	8.6	6.6	3.6	10	3.2	6.8	28	762	126
25	59	196	25	8.6	6.6	3.6	4.4	3.2	5.0	13	292	234
26	36	82	24	8.6	7.4	3.6	3.8	3.1	14	7.3	68	114
27	136	818	22	8.4	7.6	3.7	3.7	3.5	12	8.6	35	71
28	41	565	22	8.4	6.4	4.9	30	3.3	12	9.1	27	59
29	30	255	22	14	5.3	14	7.3	3.1	8.2	19	24	46
30	26	153	26	8.9	---	18	5.3	9.3	4.6	9.7	26	39
31	25	---	24	8.0	---	9.0	---	3.4	---	6.5	21	---
TOTAL	1845.6	3286	1299	375.7	241.2	173.5	213.8	180.8	148.1	302.8	1502.4	1612
MEAN	59.5	110	41.9	12.1	8.32	5.60	7.13	5.83	4.94	9.77	48.5	53.7
MAX	232	818	112	21	13	18	32	44	14	28	762	234
MIN	6.7	12	22	8.0	5.3	3.6	3.7	3.0	2.5	4.0	1.7	17
AC-FT	3660	6520	2580	745	478	344	424	359	294	601	2980	3200
CFSM	3.15	5.80	2.22	.64	.44	.30	.38	.31	.26	.52	2.56	2.84
IN.	3.63	6.47	2.56	.74	.47	.34	.42	.36	.29	.60	2.96	3.17

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 11385.6 MEAN 31.2 MAX 818 MIN 4.0 AC-FT 22580 CFSM 1.65 IN. 22.41
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 11180.9 MEAN 30.5 MAX 818 MIN 1.7 AC-FT 22180 CFSM 1.62 IN. 22.01

e Estimated

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124200 RIO GUAYANILLA NEAR GUAYANILLA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO SEPTEMBER 1985, OCTOBER 1987 TO AUGUST 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 09	1106	6.61	367	29.5	MAR, 08	1132	4.88	396	26.5
NOV, 04	1115	20.9	430	26.0	APR, 12	1208	4.43	391	31.0
DEC, 11	0843	57.3	406	24.5	MAY, 05	1226	3.62	396	32.0
JAN, 14	1442	12.7	424	28.5	AUG, 02	1138	2.96	354	31.5
FEB, 19	1245	8.04	367	28.5					

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124700 RIO GUAYANILLA AT CENTRAL RUFINA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'40", long 66°46'49", at dirt road bridge, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) from mouth, 0.9 mi (1.4 km) east of Central Rufina and 0.9 mi (1.4 km) southeast of Guayanilla.

DRAINAGE AREA.--22.8 mi² (59.1 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1960-65, 1974 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATURATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECA, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECA, KF AGAR (COLS./100 ML)
DEC 1987	08...	E75	450	7.50	25.5	78	4.8	58	32	38000	51000
FEB 1988	02...	E0.5	762	7.20	24.5	4.3	3.2	38	42	21000	K14000
APR	12...	E0.44	911	7.60	29.0	4.5	2.2	28	94	K9000	K13000
JUN	08...	0.12	869	7.30	32.0	13	3.4	46	120	K5000	K2000
AUG	02...	E71	1010	7.20	29.0	8.1	3.2	60	140	K300	K1500

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
DEC 1987	170	17	46	12	17	0	2.6	190	<0.5	41	19
FEB 1988	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--
APR	260	0	70	20	53	1	6.7	280	<0.5	78	64
JUN	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	290	--	--	--
AUG	280	0	76	21	67	2	8.5	310	--	75	78

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
DEC 1987	0.10	17	250	--	131	0.09	0.01	1.10	0.18	0.52
FEB 1988	--	--	--	--	8	0.14	0.06	0.20	9.20	3.80
APR	0.20	25	490	--	12	0.49	0.01	0.50	0.10	0.20
JUN	--	--	--	--	10	0.15	0.05	0.20	7.90	17.0
AUG	0.10	26	548	--	10	--	0.02	<0.10	--	--

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO GUAYANILLA BASIN

50124700 RIO GUAYANILLA AT CENTRAL RUFINA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
DEC 1987 08...	0.7	1.8	8.0	0.32	1	<100	30	1	<1	10
FEB 1988 02...	13	13	58	2.50	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 12...	0.3	0.8	3.5	0.04	2	<100	90	2	<1	320
JUN 08...	25	25	110	81.0	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 02...	24	--	--	8.00	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
DEC 1987 08...	2099	9	100	0.10	1	1	20	<0.010	2	0.07
FEB 1988 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 12...	190	<5	240	0.20	<1	1	30	<0.010	13	2.0
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	1000	<1.0	<0.10	<1.0	<0.10	<0.10	<0.10	0.17	<0.10	<0.10

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.10	<0.10	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.01	<0.1

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	<0.01	<1.0	<1.0	<10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

RIO LOCO BASIN

50129700 RIO LOCO AT GUANICA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'33", long 66°54'52", 0.6 mi (1.0 km) northwest of Guánica and 1.2 mi (1.9 km) northeast of Ensenada.

DRAINAGE AREA.--Indeterminate.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1975 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987											
29...	1000	E0.0	19000	7.40	29.5	18	1.0	13	31	K120000	3700
DEC 10...	1340	E90	491	7.60	29.5	21	5.4	70	40	4100	2000
FEB 1988											
02...	1105	0.0	13900	7.20	25.5	7.0	5.2	63	19	33000	4900
APR 14...	1245	0.0	1045	7.80	27.5	2.5	4.2	53	29	K680	420
JUN 08...	1130	0.0	15000	7.50	31.0	4.6	6.0	81	160	3200	K1400
AUG 04...	0900	E0.0	10300	7.40	28.0	5.2	2.2	87	79	410	9600

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
SEP 1987											
29...	370	120	56	57	310	7	13	250	<0.5	100	470
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
FEB 1988Z											
02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--
APR 14...	170	12	34	21	49	2	3.2	170	<0.5	30	71
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--
AUG 04...	1200	1000	100	240	1800	22	58	210	--	480	2900

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
29...	0.30	32	1200	--	16	0.19	0.01	0.20	0.05	0.75
DEC 1987										
10...	--	--	--	--	25	1.29	0.01	1.30	0.01	0.39
FEB 1988										
02...	--	--	--	--	14	0.66	0.04	0.70	0.12	0.68
APR 14...	0.20	25	329	--	7	0.23	0.07	0.30	15.0	4.0
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	5	0.08	0.02	0.10	0.18	0.42
AUG 04...	0.30	22	5730	--	35	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.08	0.42

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO LOCO BASIN

50129700 RIO LOCO AT GUANICA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
SEP 1987 29...	0.8	0.28	5.8	0.23	2	<100	220	1	10	30
DEC 10...	0.4	1.7	7.5	0.12	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 02...	0.8	1.5	6.6	0.12	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 14...	19	19	85	3.3	<1	<100	50	2	<1	320
JUN 08...	0.6	0.7	3.1	0.17	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 04...	0.5	0.6	2.8	0.10	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
SEP 1987 29...	2300	<5	150	<0.10	3	1	20	<0.010	5	0.07
DEC 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 02...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 14...	510	<5	50	<0.10	<1	1	20	<0.010	2	0.03
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	1130	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

Figure 23.--Río Guanajibo basin.

LAGUNA JOYUDA BASIN

50130320 QUEBRADA MAMEY AT JOYUDA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'51", long 67°10'09", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, 1.1 mi (1.8 km) northeast of Joyuda and 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream from Laguna Joyuda.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.38 mi² (0.98 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to September 1988 (discontinued).

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 5.77 ft (1.75 m) above mean sea level.

REMARKS.--Records fair.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 119 ft³/s (3.37 m³/s), May 13, gage height, 16.85 ft (5.136 m), from rating curve extended above 50 ft³/s (1.42 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; no flow many days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT PERIOD.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 12 ft³/s (.340 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 23	1645	23	0.66	15.31	4.666	Aug. 24	2130	45	1.3	15.80	4.816
Nov. 19	1815	37	1.1	15.65	4.770	Sept. 22	1845	37	1.0	15.64	4.767
Nov. 27	1415	*46	1.3	*15.82	4.822	Sept. 23	1745	23	0.64	15.30	4.663
June 21	1415	34	0.95	15.57	4.746	Sept. 25	1815	27	0.78	15.42	4.700

No flow parts or all day Mar. 14, May 4-10, June 7-10 .

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.11	.50	.48	.12	.07	.02	.05	.01	.14	.54	.66	1.8
2	.10	.64	.55	.12	.06	.02	.04	.01	.12	.52	.61	1.4
3	.10	.31	1.4	.13	.05	.02	.04	.01	.10	.49	.62	1.3
4	.10	.16	.52	.12	.05	.02	.04	.0	.09	.50	.62	1.2
5	.09	.10	.39	.12	.05	.05	.04	.0	.06	.57	.52	1.2
6	.08	.09	.32	.11	.05	.06	.04	.0	.01	.54	.46	2.1
7	.08	.09	.25	.10	.06	.06	.03	.0	.0	.49	.46	1.4
8	.09	.08	.27	.09	.07	.05	.03	.0	.0	.46	.37	1.2
9	.08	.07	.26	.08	.06	.03	.03	.0	.0	.45	.25	1.2
10	.08	.07	.27	.07	.05	.03	.02	.0	.0	.46	.98	1.2
11	.08	.06	.26	.07	.05	.03	.02	.62	.0	.50	.63	1.8
12	.06	.06	.23	.08	.06	.03	.02	.27	.30	.52	.54	1.4
13	.06	.59	.23	.10	.06	.06	.01	.28	.27	.55	.52	1.3
14	.07	.14	.24	.11	.05	.0	.01	.59	.21	.48	.54	1.2
15	.07	.06	.23	.08	.05	.01	.03	.30	.17	.41	.57	1.4
16	.07	.05	.23	.08	.04	.04	.03	.24	.15	.42	.51	1.3
17	.07	.06	.21	.08	.04	.05	.02	.21	.15	1.1	.80	1.8
18	.08	.04	.18	.08	.04	.05	.03	.19	.18	.72	.70	1.9
19	.09	3.6	.26	.08	.04	.03	.03	.18	.20	.66	.64	1.5
20	.07	1.0	.20	.08	.03	.03	.02	.18	.70	.64	.59	1.4
21	.96	.24	.17	.08	.03	.03	.01	.16	3.4	.58	.54	1.3
22	.09	.15	.17	.08	.03	.02	.03	.14	2.0	.54	.82	4.7
23	2.9	.08	.18	.08	.03	.03	.03	.14	.87	.50	1.7	4.0
24	.20	3.5	.18	.09	.03	.04	.02	.12	.89	1.1	11	2.2
25	.10	.86	.18	.09	.03	.05	.01	.11	.71	.81	9.3	5.1
26	.08	.68	.15	.10	.03	.05	.01	.28	.65	.73	3.0	2.7
27	.08	11	.14	.13	.03	.04	.01	.23	.60	.68	2.2	2.3
28	.08	2.1	.26	.10	.03	.23	.02	.26	.62	.69	1.8	2.2
29	.08	1.1	.15	.10	.03	.08	.02	.25	.60	.68	1.5	2.1
30	.08	.68	.13	.08	---	.38	.02	.20	.55	.76	1.4	2.0
31	.17	---	.13	.07	---	.08	---	.17	---	.68	1.5	---
TOTAL	6.45	28.16	8.82	2.90	1.30	1.72	0.76	5.15	13.74	18.77	46.35	57.6
MEAN	.21	.94	.28	.094	.045	.055	.025	.17	.46	.61	1.50	1.92
MAX	2.9	11	1.4	.13	.07	.38	.05	.62	3.4	1.1	11	5.1
MIN	.06	.04	.13	.07	.03	.00	.01	.00	.00	.41	.25	1.2
AC-FT	13	56	17	5.8	2.6	3.4	1.5	10	27	37	92	114
CFSM	.55	2.47	.75	.25	.12	.15	.07	.44	1.21	1.59	3.93	5.05
IN.	.63	2.76	.86	.28	.13	.17	.07	.50	1.35	1.84	4.54	5.64

CAL YR 1987	TOTAL	98.30	MEAN	.27	MAX	11	MIN	.00	AC-FT	195	CFSM	.71	IN.	9.62
WTR YR 1988	TOTAL	191.72	MEAN	.52	MAX	11	MIN	.00	AC-FT	380	CFSM	1.38	IN.	18.77

LAGUNA JOYUDA BASIN
50130320 QUEBRADA MAMEY AT JOYUDA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 06	1340	0.084	384	27.0	JAN, 06	1215	0.116	306	24.0
OCT, 14	0815	0.056	350	25.0	JAN, 15	1210	0.081	280	25.0
OCT, 27	0830	0.085	280	24.0	JAN, 26	0730	0.090	292	21.0
NOV, 03	0800	0.192	239	23.0	FEB, 02	1210	0.067	286	24.0
NOV, 13	1216	0.055	309	26.0	FEB, 09	1100	0.061	286	24.0
NOV, 23	0730	0.094	273	22.5	FEB, 16	0738	0.046	292	21.0
DEC, 01	0800	0.574	270	24.0	FEB, 24	0751	0.041	307	22.0
DEC, 07	1350	0.385	285	27.5	MAR, 03	0820	0.029	302	21.0
DEC, 15	1330	0.235	329	28.0	MAR, 22	1320	0.024	301	28.0
DEC, 22	0808	0.192	296	23.0	APR, 07	0849	0.037	238	27.5
DEC, 28	0910	0.143	297	22.0	MAY, 03	1330	0.008	--	--

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50133600 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR SAN GERMAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°07'18", long 67°03'56", at bridge on Highway 347, 2.2 mi (3.5 km) northwest of San German.

DRAINAGE AREA.--45.5 mi² (117.8 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER QUALITY DATA, WATER YEARS OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987											
30...	0855	18	557	8.00	27.0	1.4	3.0	37	16	2900	K820
DEC 1987											
10...	1210	63	524	7.50	26.5	0.7	6.8	84	<10	210	260
FEB 1988											
04...	1135	15	608	7.20	26.0	3.9	3.6	44	30	K66000	K1100
APR											
14...	1045	8.8	712	7.60	27.5	2.1	2.4	30	12	K16000	K1900
JUN											
10...	1105	5.5	577	7.50	28.5	4.4	1.0	13	33	K130000	64000
AUG											
04...	0725	10	441	7.30	26.5	13	4.1	51	23	20000	13000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT TOT (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
SEP 1987											
30...	240	8	26	42	25	0.7	2.4	230	<0.5	29	23
DEC											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	240	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	260	--	--	--
APR											
14...	270	35	30	48	41	1	4.8	260	<0.5	52	42
JUN											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	250	--	--	--
AUG											
04...	160	25	19	28	28	1	3.3	150	--	40	24

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
30...	0.40	34	320	16	<1	0.27	0.13	0.40	1.70	0.60
DEC										
10...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.61	0.09	0.70	0.19	0.31
FEB 1988										
04...	--	--	--	--	--	0.32	0.08	0.40	5.30	0.0
APR										
14...	0.40	35	396	9.4	18	0.17	0.13	0.30	4.00	0.30
JUN										
10...	--	--	--	--	2	--	0.01	<0.10	3.40	2.6
AUG										
04...	0.30	22	247	6.7	16	0.72	0.18	0.90	1.20	0.40

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°09'36", long 67°05'08", at bridge on Highway 348, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) southwest of Rosario plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--18.3 mi² (47.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 50.0 ft (15.2 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 7,480 ft³/s (212 m³/s), Aug. 24, 1988, gage height, 13.64 ft (4.16 m) from rating curve extended above 900 ft³/s (25.5 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis; minimum discharge 8.7 ft³/s (0.246 m³/s), Apr. 15, 1986.EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 1,500 ft³/s (42.5 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	1345	1,630	46.2	7.91	2.411	Aug. 24	1930	*7,480	212	*13.64	4.157
June 20	1645	2,980	84.4	9.85	3.002	Sept. 23	1700	2,040	57.8	8.58	2.615
July 9	1715	2,980	84.4	9.85	3.002	Sept. 25	1745	2,530	71.6	9.27	2.825
July 11	1815	1,990	56.4	8.49	2.588						

Minimum discharge, 8.9 ft³/s (0.252 m³/s), May 8, 9, June 10, 11.DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	38	83	49	23	16	13	e10	12	11	22	18	266
2	41	53	107	23	16	14	e9.4	11	11	21	18	127
3	37	52	70	23	16	12	e9.2	11	11	19	17	80
4	34	43	48	22	15	11	e9.4	11	10	18	17	63
5	32	37	143	22	15	11	e10	11	10	24	16	53
6	30	34	87	21	14	11	15	9.6	9.8	20	16	79
7	37	67	61	21	14	11	12	9.6	13	18	15	56
8	88	47	51	21	14	11	11	9.1	12	17	15	44
9	52	42	45	20	14	10	11	9.7	11	213	14	39
10	178	38	40	20	13	10	10	133	9.4	92	136	38
11	86	34	37	19	14	10	9.8	112	12	169	51	52
12	48	33	34	19	16	10	9.6	38	97	93	27	81
13	39	45	32	19	18	10	9.6	24	35	60	23	43
14	35	128	31	22	15	10	9.3	29	25	39	29	36
15	33	66	30	28	13	10	11	28	15	32	46	137
16	31	59	30	20	13	11	14	17	12	58	36	97
17	31	43	29	24	12	14	29	14	11	64	31	100
18	38	37	28	20	12	13	22	13	52	45	71	153
19	32	32	35	20	12	11	36	12	25	32	38	133
20	28	32	30	18	12	10	22	13	278	27	41	69
21	48	30	28	18	12	9.7	16	12	161	24	35	57
22	58	34	27	18	11	9.6	131	13	63	22	28	91
23	59	28	27	18	11	9.3	93	13	38	21	40	301
24	42	93	27	17	12	10	50	13	40	21	998	195
25	33	83	26	17	12	12	23	13	122	28	645	393
26	36	53	25	17	13	16	17	12	88	25	178	289
27	42	457	24	17	15	14	14	14	40	21	118	173
28	42	142	24	22	12	e12	26	20	31	20	73	119
29	40	70	23	21	11	e11	20	17	31	23	56	97
30	69	54	23	18	---	e12	14	14	24	23	133	83
31	87	---	23	17	---	e13	---	13	---	20	174	---
TOTAL	1524	2049	1294	625	393	351.6	683.3	681.0	1308.2	1331	3153	3544
MEAN	49.2	68.3	41.7	20.2	13.6	11.3	22.8	22.0	43.6	42.9	102	118
MAX	178	457	143	28	18	16	131	133	278	213	998	393
MIN	28	28	23	17	11	9.3	9.2	9.1	9.4	17	14	36
AC-FT	3020	4060	2570	1240	780	697	1360	1350	2590	2640	6250	7030
CFSM	3.00	4.16	2.55	1.23	.83	.69	1.39	1.34	2.66	2.62	6.20	7.20
IN.	3.46	4.65	2.94	1.42	.89	.80	1.55	1.54	2.97	3.02	7.15	8.04

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 14881.7 MEAN 40.8 MAX 457 MIN 7.6 AC-FT 29520 CFSM 2.49 IN. 33.76
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 16937.1 MEAN 46.3 MAX 998 MIN 9.1 AC-FT 33590 CFSM 2.82 IN. 38.42

e Estimated

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS 1979 TO CURRENT YEAR.

PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SUSPENDED-SEDIMENT DISCHARGE: OCTOBER 1985 TO SEPTEMBER 1986

INSTRUMENTATION.--US D-49 SEDIMENT SAMPLER SINCE OCTOBER 1985. AUTOMATIC SEDIMENT SAMPLER SINCE 1986

REMARKS.--sediment samples were collected by a local observer once daily during low flow and more than once daily during high flow events for concentration and particle size analyses. Sediment samples are collected periodically by survey staff. Automatic sediment sampler set to collect samples above 200 cfs.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF DAILY RECORD.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 8,150 mg/L October 7, 1985; Minimum daily mean, 2 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 74,700 tons (67,800 tonnes) October 7, 1985; Minimum daily, 0.05 ton (0.04 Tonne) several days.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--

SEDIMENT CONCENTRATIONS: Maximum daily mean, 1,640 mg/L November 20, 1986; Minimum daily mean, 2.0 mg/L several days.

SEDIMENT LOADS: Maximum daily, 4,700 tons (4,263 tonnes) September 12, 1987; Minimum daily 0.04 ton (0.04 tonne) several days.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987										
01...	1405	39	263	8.50	28.0	0.7	8.0	103	15	K1400 340
DEC										
10...	0940	40	266	7.40	24.0	1.9	8.6	103	15	520 870
FEB 1988										
03...	0925	15	290	7.50	21.5	1.4	9.2	103	12	550 710
APR										
13...	1015	9.6	299	8.50	26.0	1.5	9.2	113	28	K70 210
JUN										
09...	0935	11	284	8.30	26.0	1.9	8.5	104	22	K73 240
AUG										
03...	0915	16	275	8.10	25.0	0.5	7.3	88	17	250 290

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WA1 W1 TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
01...	130	9	22	18	7.8	0.3	1.8	120	<0.5	7.1	7.4
DEC											
10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR											
13...	140	9	28	18	11	0.4	1.2	130	<0.5	9.1	9.7
JUN											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
AUG											
03...	130	0	25	16	9.0	0.4	1.4	130	--	7.5	8.6

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	38	10	1.0	83	81	21	49	35	4.6
2	41	10	1.1	53	36	5.2	107	185	193
3	37	10	1.0	52	35	4.9	70	100	19
4	34	11	1.0	43	30	3.5	48	60	7.8
5	32	11	.95	37	25	2.5	143	439	757
6	30	10	.81	34	22	2.0	87	60	14
7	37	20	2.0	67	77	31	61	25	4.1
8	88	103	54	47	32	4.1	31	15	2.1
9	52	40	5.6	42	22	2.5	45	15	1.8
10	178	402	1160	38	20	2.1	40	14	1.5
11	86	80	19	34	20	1.8	37	12	1.2
12	48	20	2.6	33	20	1.8	34	11	1.0
13	39	15	1.6	45	56	15	32	11	.95
14	35	12	1.1	128	240	384	31	10	.84
15	33	11	.98	66	75	13	30	12	.97
16	31	10	.84	59	40	6.4	30	12	.97
17	31	10	.84	43	30	3.5	29	12	.94
18	38	20	2.1	37	25	2.5	28	11	.83
19	32	18	1.6	32	22	1.9	35	10	.95
20	28	17	1.3	32	21	1.8	30	9	.73
21	48	69	30	30	20	1.6	28	8	.60
22	58	50	7.8	34	20	2.3	27	9	.66
23	59	98	46	28	18	1.4	27	9	.66
24	42	25	2.8	93	89	42	27	8	.58
25	33	15	1.3	83	100	22	26	8	.56
26	36	12	1.2	53	50	7.2	25	8	.54
27	42	20	2.3	457	1510	4750	24	9	.58
28	42	30	3.4	142	200	77	24	10	.65
29	40	30	3.2	70	60	11	23	10	.62
30	69	64	35	54	40	5.8	23	10	.62
31	87	97	32	---	---	---	23	10	.62
TOTAL	1524	---	1424.42	2049	---	5430.8	1294	---	1020.97

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	23	9	.56	16	6	.26	13	4	.14
2	23	9	.56	16	6	.26	14	4	.15
3	23	9	.56	16	6	.26	12	3	.10
4	22	10	.59	15	6	.24	11	3	.09
5	22	12	.71	15	6	.24	11	3	.09
6	21	11	.62	14	6	.23	11	3	.09
7	21	10	.57	14	7	.26	11	4	.12
8	21	10	.57	14	7	.26	11	4	.12
9	20	10	.57	14	7	.26	10	4	.11
10	20	10	.54	13	7	.25	10	4	.11
11	19	10	.51	14	7	.26	10	4	.11
12	19	10	.51	16	8	.35	10	4	.11
13	19	10	.51	18	10	.49	10	3	.08
14	22	15	.89	15	8	.32	10	3	.08
15	28	20	1.5	13	7	.25	10	3	.08
16	20	10	.54	13	7	.25	11	4	.12
17	24	10	.65	12	7	.23	14	4	.15
18	20	10	.54	12	6	.19	13	5	.18
19	20	10	.54	12	6	.19	11	5	.15
20	18	9	.44	12	6	.19	10	5	.14
21	18	9	.44	12	5	.16	9.7	5	.13
22	18	8	.39	11	4	.12	9.6	5	.13
23	18	8	.39	11	4	.12	9.3	5	.13
24	17	8	.37	12	5	.16	10	5	.14
25	17	7	.32	12	5	.16	12	5	.16
26	17	7	.32	13	5	.18	16	6	.26
27	17	6	.28	15	5	.20	14	6	.23
28	22	7	.42	12	4	.13	12	6	.19
29	21	7	.40	11	4	.12	11	5	.15
30	18	7	.34	---	---	---	12	5	.16
31	17	7	.32	---	---	---	13	5	.18
TOTAL	625	---	16.47	393	---	6.59	351.6	---	4.18

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	10	6	.16	12	6	.19	11	6	.18
2	9.4	5	.13	11	6	.18	11	6	.18
3	9.2	5	.12	11	5	.15	11	6	.18
4	9.4	5	.13	11	5	.15	10	6	.16
5	10	5	.14	11	5	.15	10	6	.16
6	15	5	.20	9.6	5	.13	9.8	5	.13
7	12	5	.16	9.6	5	.13	13	6	.21
8	11	5	.15	9.1	5	.12	12	6	.19
9	11	5	.15	9.7	5	.13	11	5	.15
10	10	5	.14	133	272	662	9.4	5	.13
11	9.8	5	.13	112	369	529	12	7	.23
12	9.6	5	.13	38	25	2.6	97	139	156
13	9.6	5	.13	24	15	.97	35	40	3.8
14	9.3	5	.13	29	20	1.6	25	30	2.0
15	11	6	.18	28	20	1.5	15	10	.41
16	14	10	.38	17	8	.37	12	10	.32
17	29	22	1.7	14	7	.26	11	10	.30
18	22	12	.71	13	7	.25	52	113	94
19	36	25	2.4	12	6	.19	25	20	1.4
20	22	10	.59	13	6	.21	278	1060	3890
21	16	6	.26	12	5	.16	161	382	428
22	131	263	530	13	5	.18	63	60	10
23	93	166	78	13	5	.18	38	50	5.1
24	50	50	6.8	13	5	.18	40	50	5.4
25	23	25	1.6	13	5	.18	122	395	936
26	17	8	.37	12	5	.16	88	100	24
27	14	7	.26	14	5	.19	40	30	3.2
28	26	20	1.4	20	10	.54	31	20	1.7
29	20	12	.65	17	9	.41	31	20	1.7
30	14	7	.26	14	7	.26	24	15	.97
31	---	---	---	13	7	.25	---	---	---
TOTAL	683.3	---	627.56	681.0	---	1202.97	1308.2	---	5566.20

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50136400 RIO ROSARIO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

SEDIMENT DISCHARGE, SUSPENDED (TONS/DAY), WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DAY	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)	MEAN DISCHARGE (CFS)	MEAN CONCEN- TRATION (MG/L)	SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (TONS/DAY)
1	22	11	.65	18	9	.44	266	654	1380
2	21	10	.57	18	8	.39	127	50	17
3	19	10	.51	17	5	.23	80	10	2.2
4	18	10	.49	17	7	.32	63	10	1.7
5	24	15	.97	16	7	.30	53	10	1.4
6	20	10	.54	16	6	.26	79	71	46
7	18	10	.49	15	6	.24	56	10	1.5
8	17	10	.46	15	10	.41	44	9	1.1
9	213	1020	6160	14	10	.38	39	8	.84
10	92	200	50	136	1270	3430	38	6	.62
11	169	1080	5040	51	80	11	52	30	4.2
12	93	140	35	27	40	2.9	81	50	11
13	60	60	9.7	23	40	2.5	43	10	1.2
14	39	30	3.2	29	30	2.3	36	8	.78
15	32	20	1.7	46	15	1.9	137	759	794
16	58	85	51	36	10	.97	97	120	31
17	64	60	10	31	15	1.3	100	176	129
18	45	30	3.6	71	60	12	153	240	264
19	32	18	1.6	38	30	3.1	133	110	40
20	27	12	.87	41	20	2.2	69	50	9.3
21	24	10	.65	35	15	1.4	57	20	3.1
22	22	10	.59	28	10	.76	91	122	81
23	21	10	.57	40	25	2.7	301	1340	4890
24	21	10	.57	998	3380	48200	195	364	332
25	28	20	1.5	645	2160	5330	393	1160	5210
26	25	15	1.0	178	329	168	289	641	1140
27	21	10	.57	118	100	32	173	100	47
28	20	10	.54	73	50	9.9	119	20	0.4
29	23	10	.62	56	20	3.0	97	15	3.9
30	23	10	.62	133	470	822	83	10	2.2
31	20	9	.49	174	584	785	---	---	---
TOTAL	1331	---	11379.07	3153	---	58827.90	3544	---	14452.44
YEAR	16937.1		99959.57						

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°08'36", long 67°08'57", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, at bridge on Highway 100, 1.4 mi (2.3 km) west of Hormigueros, and 2.0 mi (3.2 km) downstream from Rio Rosario.

DRAINAGE AREA.--120 mi² (311 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Annual low-flow measurements 1959, monthly measurements April 1959 to November 1967, January 1973 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is at mean sea level. Previous to Nov. 7, 1980, at site 0.3 mi (0.5 km) upstream at datum 7.36 ft (2.243 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--15 years (1974-88), 214 ft³/s (6.060 m³/s), 24.22 in/yr (615 mm/yr), 155,000 acre-ft/yr (191 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 199 ft³/s (5.64 m³/s), 140,000 acre-ft/yr (170 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 128,000 ft³/s (3,620 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 28.50 ft (8.687 m), site and datum then in use, from rating curve extended above 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) on the basis of contracted-opening measurement of peak flow; minimum discharge, 4.6 ft³/s (0.130 m³/s), June 22, 1977.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 2,000 ft³/s (56.6 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Nov. 28	0145	9,410	266	23.52	7.169	Sept. 26	0500	2,120	60.0	18.88	5.755
Aug. 25	0500	*30,400	861	*27.11	8.263						

Minimum discharge, 12 ft³/s (0.340 m³/s), June 5-7.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	109	252	419	66	30	23	69	32	17	36	35	641
2	149	224	484	66	30	29	46	27	16	35	30	492
3	114	208	518	65	34	27	39	24	17	30	27	317
4	98	153	312	62	32	23	41	22	15	27	40	249
5	91	126	308	60	29	22	65	20	14	51	28	204
6	87	112	320	57	28	21	69	19	12	51	25	201
7	87	222	224	56	26	21	50	18	14	35	23	196
8	248	183	207	e53	26	20	36	17	57	27	22	159
9	210	185	189	e53	25	20	30	16	30	113	21	139
10	190	115	171	e53	24	20	27	72	20	186	155	129
11	273	118	160	e52	23	20	24	325	18	133	209	178
12	142	97	149	e52	30	19	23	146	88	172	80	455
13	112	166	140	e52	35	20	21	85	115	90	59	201
14	101	166	133	54	40	23	e20	79	66	68	46	151
15	98	150	127	65	35	20	e24	84	38	51	46	239
16	91	123	123	54	31	19	e30	52	29	49	68	e430
17	90	103	117	53	28	31	e60	41	23	176	96	645
18	99	90	112	52	28	33	e47	35	110	110	324	743
19	113	88	114	47	25	24	e70	31	245	69	337	582
20	87	79	110	43	24	19	58	30	185	55	658	303
21	115	73	100	40	22	17	38	27	293	50	325	296
22	283	73	94	40	20	17	92	24	138	42	268	506
23	407	68	90	39	21	18	264	23	80	38	446	937
24	343	300	88	37	21	19	244	23	82	46	1120	1380
25	181	455	86	35	21	38	98	20	117	55	12900	1100
26	134	280	82	34	23	42	65	20	214	51	2750	1630
27	119	1500	79	37	30	27	49	21	85	37	999	1170
28	112	5290	78	41	27	44	42	23	59	34	595	617
29	102	1340	77	43	23	66	64	32	54	48	460	479
30	119	593	72	40	---	139	40	22	43	46	549	503
31	324	---	70	34	---	221	---	19	---	45	730	---
TOTAL	4828	12932	5353	1535	791	1102	1845	1429	2294	2056	23471	15272
MEAN	156	431	173	49.5	27.3	35.5	61.5	46.1	76.5	66.3	757	509
MAX	407	5290	518	66	40	221	264	325	293	186	12900	1630
MIN	87	68	70	34	20	17	20	16	12	27	21	129
AC-FT	9580	25650	10620	3040	1570	2190	3660	2830	4550	4080	46550	30290
CFSM	1.30	3.59	1.44	.41	.23	.30	.51	.38	.64	.55	6.31	4.24
IN.	1.50	4.01	1.66	.48	.25	.34	.57	.44	.71	.64	7.28	4.73

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 52021 MEAN 143 MAX 5290 MIN 22 AC-FT 103200 CFSM 1.19 IN. 16.13
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 72908 MEAN 199 MAX 12900 MIN 12 AC-FT 144600 CFSM 1.66 IN. 22.60

e Estimated

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN
50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, rECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
01...	0855	107	372	7.80	26.0	21	4.4	54	20	K640	21000
DEC 09...	0900	191	395	6.90	25.0	6.7	5.2	63	88	5500	K16000
FEB 1988											
04...	0930	34	485	7.30	22.5	--	7.5	86	--	K1300	470
APR 14...	0825	21	485	8.00	25.5	3.1	6.8	82	37	330	K1400
JUN 10...	0905	22	421	8.00	26.0	3.5	6.5	80	24	350	940
AUG 03...	1240	25	399	8.20	27.5	14	6.9	87	13	K690	2300

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
01...	180	1	28	27	11	0.4	3.2	180	<0.5	15	12
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	190	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	230	--	--	--
APR 14...	210	0	28	33	17	0.5	2.2	200	<0.5	23	20
JUN 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	170	--	--	--
AUG 03...	180	4	27	27	14	0.5	1.8	170	--	15	14

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
01...	0.10	31	235	68	33	0.54	0.06	0.60	0.12	0.68
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	12	0.64	0.06	0.70	0.11	0.49
FEB 1988										
04...	--	--	--	--	19	1.07	0.03	1.10	0.08	0.22
APR 14...	0.20	32	281	16	5	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.02	0.28
JUN 10...	--	--	--	--	1	0.93	0.07	1.00	0.22	0.38
AUG 03...	0.10	30	234	16	25	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.02	0.48

K = non-ideal count

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

50138000 RIO GUANAJIBO NEAR HORMIGUEROS, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
OCT 1987 01...	0.8	0.68	3.7	0.32	<1	100	70	1	<1	30
DEC 09...	0.6	1.3	5.8	0.32	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 04...	0.3	1.4	6.2	0.61	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 14...	0.3	1.1	4.9	0.35	9	<100	50	1	4	510
JUN 10...	0.6	1.6	7.1	0.40	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 03...	0.5	1.1	4.9	0.31	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
OCT 1987 01...	9700	<5	440	<0.10	<1	<1	30	<0.010	9	0.02
DEC 09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 14...	530	<5	70	<0.10	<1	1	60	<0.010	2	0.04
JUN 10...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 10...	0905	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 10...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 10...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	0.29	<0.01	0.01	<0.01

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

RIO YAGÜEZ BASIN

50138800 RIO YAGÜEZ NEAR MAYAGÜEZ, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°12'31", long 67°07'07", at steel-truss bridge on unnumbered paved road about 800 ft (244 m) south of Highway 106, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) west of Highways 106 and 352 junction, and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) east-northeast from Mayagüez plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--6.7 mi² (17.3 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, K' AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987											
30...	1135	13	290	8.40	25.0	1.6	7.6	91	<10	5600	9600
DEC											
09...	1140	10	278	7.60	23.5	1.9	8.2	96	<10	K900	450
FEB 1988											
03...	1215	2.8	311	7.40	24.0	0.4	9.6	113	<10	220	460
APR											
13...	1305	1.9	310	8.40	27.0	0.3	8.9	111	29	220	280
JUN											
09...	1210	1.6	314	8.20	27.5	2.0	3.9	49	27	220	280
AUG											
02...	1240	3.0	301	8.20	26.5	0.4	8.9	110	<10	350	630

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
SEP 1987											
09...	130	3	35	11	11	0.4	2.3	130	<0.5	7.7	8.9
DEC											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR											
13...	140	0	37	11	13	0.5	2.5	140	<0.5	11	11
JUN											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
AUG											
02...	130	0	34	11	12	0.5	2.4	130	--	8.8	10

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
30...	0.10	30	180	6.2	<1	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.04	0.16
DEC										
09...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.89	0.01	0.90	0.01	0.19
FEB 1988										
03...	--	--	--	--	<1	0.49	0.01	0.50	0.01	0.29
APR										
13...	0.20	30	199	1.0	3	--	<0.01	0.20	0.01	--
JUN										
09...	--	--	--	--	<1	--	<0.01	0.30	0.05	--
AUG										
02...	0.10	28	187	1.5	4	0.39	0.01	0.40	0.01	0.19

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50143000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR LARES, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°15'26", long 66°55'00", at bridge on Highway 124, 0.7 mi (1.1 km) downstream from confluence of Rio Blanco and Rio Prieto, and 3.7 mi (6.0 km) southwest of Lares plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--26.3 mi² (68.1 km²) this does not include 36.2 mi² (93.8 km²) which contributes only during high floods, and 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) which contributes only part of its storm runoff.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1959-68, 1970 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
02...	0750	25	402	7.60	23.5	1.2	7.9	94	16	260	290
DEC											
16...	0940	45	299	7.70	23.5	0.6	9.2	109	38	K150	850
FEB 1988											
04...	1040	23	312	7.70	23.0	0.4	10.2	120	<10	K10	330
APR											
14...	0800	22	272	7.30	23.0	3.2	7.6	89	47	K680	3300
JUN											
09...	1030	12	323	7.80	27.5	1.2	9.2	116	<10	K54	K40
AUG											
04...	1100	22	318	7.50	27.0	3.7	9.5	118	<10	K130	K120

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CAC03)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CAC03)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)
OCT 1987											
02...	130	21	36	10	12	0.5	2.0	110	<0.5	24	9.8
DEC											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
APR											
14...	100	6	27	8.0	14	0.6	2.4	86	<0.5	20	11
JUN											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	110	--	--	--
AUG											
04...	130	15	35	10	13	0.5	1.6	110	--	27	10

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SIO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
02...	0.10	32	192	13.1	<1	0.89	0.01	0.90	0.03	0.17
DEC										
16...	--	--	--	--	4	1.39	0.01	1.40	0.01	0.19
FEB 1988										
04...	--	--	--	--	8	0.89	0.01	0.90	0.02	0.68
APR										
14...	0.20	27	167	10.1	5	1.30	0.20	1.50	0.15	0.05
JUN										
09...	--	--	--	--	1	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.02	1.3
AUG										
04...	0.10	31	196	12	10	--	<0.01	0.50	0.01	--

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°17'05", long 67°03'05", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on right bank, at downstream side of bridge on Highway 108, 0.4 mi (0.6 km) downstream from Quebrada La Zumbadora, 4.4 mi (7.1 km) northwest of Las Marias, 5.4 mi (8.7 km) southwest of San Sebastian.

DRAINAGE AREA.--94.3 mi² (244.2 km²), does not include 36.2 mi² (93.8 km²) which contributes only during high floods, and 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) which contributes only part of its storm runoff.

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1963 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Datum of gage is 103.72 ft (31.614 m) above mean sea level (Puerto Rico Department of Public Works bench mark). Previous to Oct. 30, 1975, a site 600 ft (180 m) upstream at same datum.

REMARKS.--Records fair. Transbasin diversion (except during floods) to Rio Yauco basin for hydroelectric power and irrigation above Lago Guayo, Yahuecas, and Prieto, combined useable storage 17,300 acre-ft (21.3 hm³). Limited storm runoff is contributed to basin by 3.5 mi² (9.1 km²) above Rio Toro Diversion dam.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--25 years (1964-88), 310 ft³/s (8.779 m³/s), 44.64 in/yr (1,134 mm/yr), 224,600 acre-ft/yr (277 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 303 ft³/s (8.58 m³/s), 220,000 acre-ft/yr (271 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 140,000 ft³/s (3,960 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 33.9 ft (10.33 m), from rating curve extended above 4,000 ft³/s (113 m³/s) on basis of slope-area measurement; minimum discharge, 31 ft³/s (0.878 m³/s), Apr. 19, 20, 1965.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 6,000 ft³/s (170 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 27	1900	21,500	609	13.58	4.139	Sept. 23	1830	20,500	581	13.27	4.045
June 25	1845	9,460	268	9.08	2.768	Sept. 25	2100	9,110	258	8.91	2.716
Aug. 24	2100	*32,300	915	*16.65	5.075						

Minimum discharge, 56 ft³/s (1.586 m³/s), Apr. 10-12.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	167	496	348	145	107	84	77	106	99	187	94	975
2	288	265	676	151	107	86	70	85	94	173	91	553
3	350	239	430	138	107	81	69	77	91	163	94	401
4	257	217	300	135	106	77	70	72	90	165	99	348
5	193	184	485	131	103	74	72	74	88	183	92	303
6	163	172	520	131	102	74	111	66	80	175	90	267
7	669	172	354	130	100	76	81	65	81	149	90	289
8	1040	441	290	124	94	73	72	60	89	140	87	247
9	548	1320	261	123	93	74	65	96	82	134	85	226
10	610	594	235	121	94	75	58	611	73	152	287	232
11	934	304	219	116	91	75	58	468	357	138	188	244
12	668	324	207	116	99	75	78	199	867	153	111	468
13	330	292	195	115	105	75	76	141	700	136	99	259
14	285	277	183	128	120	75	67	128	265	145	239	262
15	285	594	179	138	100	73	72	157	174	119	191	455
16	341	464	180	115	94	74	136	135	146	159	133	475
17	236	323	177	124	91	79	100	106	132	352	123	462
18	217	244	172	118	105	76	116	96	120	253	252	847
19	244	216	194	114	95	72	118	91	260	147	154	684
20	212	196	202	111	92	71	150	89	177	126	261	847
21	235	194	183	111	90	70	136	86	272	184	239	854
22	439	187	170	110	91	68	332	83	401	135	154	1090
23	240	208	168	110	89	64	340	83	288	113	163	3550
24	239	447	166	109	88	67	132	85	451	106	5570	2470
25	199	623	162	110	88	67	97	91	1470	110	5780	2640
26	184	314	157	109	87	70	80	254	635	181	1220	2810
27	175	3230	153	104	97	87	74	188	257	119	834	1840
28	168	1910	151	96	92	90	218	229	405	101	865	1230
29	163	926	146	112	84	109	233	223	336	107	531	774
30	162	564	146	113	---	88	156	146	215	104	461	533
31	810	---	145	107	---	97	---	111	---	101	899	---
TOTAL	11051	15937	7554	3715	2811	2396	3514	4501	8795	4710	19576	26635
MEAN	356	531	244	120	96.9	77.3	117	145	293	152	631	888
MAX	1040	3230	676	151	120	109	340	611	1470	352	5780	3550
MIN	162	172	145	96	84	64	58	60	73	101	85	226
AC-FT	21920	31610	14980	7370	5580	4750	6970	8930	17440	9340	38830	52830
CFSM	3.78	5.63	2.58	1.27	1.03	.82	1.24	1.54	3.11	1.61	6.70	9.41
IN.	4.36	6.29	2.98	1.47	1.11	.95	1.39	1.78	3.47	1.86	7.72	10.51

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 86034 MEAN 236 MAX 3230 MIN 60 AC-FT 170600 CFSM 2.50 IN. 33.94
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 111195 MEAN 304 MAX 5780 MIN 58 AC-FT 220600 CFSM 3.22 IN. 43.86

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR--Continued

(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1963 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATURATION)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)
OCT 1987											
01...	0955	170	229	7.40	25.0	6.6	8.4	101	1300	K560	100
JAN 1988											
26...	1050	68	270	7.60	26.0	2.7	8.7	106	200	K170	110
APR											
13...	0915	108	245	8.20	26.5	7.6	8.2	100	350	320	110
JUL											
14...	1030	133	240	8.10	27.0	4.3	8.8	110	250	K190	110

DATE	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD MG/L AS CaCO3	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)
OCT 1987											
01...	4	26	9.0	9.1	0.4	2.1	98	8.9	6.3	0.1	31
JAN 1988											
26...	1	28	10	10	0.4	1.8	100	11	7.8	0.1	31
APR											
13...	5	28	9.9	11	0.5	1.8	100	15	8.8	0.1	30
JUL											
14...	5	27	9.5	10	0.4	1.5	89	14	7.3	0.1	30

DATE	SOLIDS, RESIDUE AT 180 DEG. C DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	NITROGEN, NO2-NO3 DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS NH4)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	PHOSPHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	PHOSPHOROUS DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOSPHOROUS ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS P)	PHOSPHATE, ORTHO, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS PO4)
OCT 1987											
01...	152	152	70	0.64	0.03	0.04	1.0	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.07
JAN 1988											
26...	169	166	31	0.71	0.03	0.04	0.4	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.09
APR											
13...	167	170	50	0.42	0.03	0.04	0.8	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.15
JUL											
14...	154	163	58	0.52	0.03	0.04	0.5	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.09

DATE	ALUMINUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AL)	ARSENIC, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS BA)	BERYLLIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS BE)	CADMIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CD)	CHROMIUM, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CR)	COBALT, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CO)	COPPER, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS CU)	IRON, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, DIS-SOLVED (UG/L AS PB)
OCT 1987										
01...	20	<1	38	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	1	18	<5
JAN 1988										
26...	20	2	34	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	5	18	<5
APR										
13...	20	<1	35	<0.5	<1	<1	<3	2	12	<5
JUL										
14...	60	<1	35	<0.5	1	3	<3	6	35	5

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50144000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR--Continued

(National stream-quality accounting network station)

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	LITHIUM DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS LI)	MANGA- NESE, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS HG)	MOLYB- DENUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS MO)	NICKEL, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS NI)	SELE- NIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS AG)	STRON- TIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS SR)	VANA- DIUM, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS V)	ZINC, DIS- SOLVED (UG/L AS ZN)
OCT 1987 01...	5	37	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	<1	130	<6	<3
JAN 1988 26...	<4	18	0.1	<10	<1	<1	1	140	<6	12
APR 13...	<4	10	<0.1	<10	<1	<1	1	150	9	<3
JUL 14...	10	20	1.2	<10	4	<1	1	140	<6	32

PARTICLE-SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF SUSPENDED SEDIMENT

DATE	TIME	STREAM- FLOW, INSTAN- TANEOUS (CFS)	SEDI- MENT, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	SEDI- MENT, DIS- CHARGE, SUS- PENDE (T/DAY)	SED. SUSP. SIEVE DIAM. PERCENT FINER THAN .062 MM
OCT 1987 01...	0955	170	24	18	65
JAN 1988 26...	1050	68	15	2.8	68
APR 13...	0915	108	24	7.0	45
JUL 14...	1030	133	22	8.0	63

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50146000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR ANASCO, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°16'00", long 67°08'05", at bridge on Highway 430, 0.2 mi (0.3 km) south of Highway 109 at El Espino and 1.4 mi (2.3 km) east-southeast from Anasco plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--139 mi² (360 km²) this does not include 39.7 mi² (102.8 km²), flow is diverted to south coast.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED SATURATION (%)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEMICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987											
30...	1145	296	218	7.10	26.5	34	7.6	94	16	1500	K870
DEC 15...	1210	243	245	7.30	26.0	21	8.1	99	41	K260	440
FEB 1988											
03...	1325	145	247	7.40	24.5	1.1	8.8	105	<10	K100	K120
APR 12...	1210	111	252	7.40	28.0	13	7.7	98	<10	270	K91
JUN 08...	1120	90.7	250	7.00	29.5	12	7.2	93	31	350	K64
AUG 03...	1015	120	254	6.90	27.0	4.3	7.1	87	18	K160	210

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
SEP 1987											
30...	95	6	24	8.5	9.0	0.4	2.2	89	<0.5	8.6	6.9
DEC 1987											
15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	100	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	94	--	--	--
APR 12...	100	0	25	9.7	11	0.5	1.5	97	<0.5	14	8.5
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	96	--	--	--
AUG 03...	100	0	26	9.0	10	0.4	1.6	99	--	11	7.2

DATE	FLUORIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
30...	0.10	29	140	112	67	0.69	0.01	0.70	0.04	0.46
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	54	0.79	0.01	0.80	0.03	0.57
FEB 1988										
03...	--	--	--	--	--	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.01	0.19
APR 12...	0.10	31	166	48	19	0.09	0.01	0.10	0.01	0.19
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	14	--	<0.01	0.10	0.02	--
AUG 03...	0.10	30	157	51	27	--	<0.01	0.30	0.02	0.58

K = non-ideal count

RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO BASIN

50146000 RIO GRANDE DE ANASCO NEAR ANASCO, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
SEP 1987 30...	0.5	1.2	2.4	0.03	<1	<100	60	1	9	20
DEC 15...	0.6	1.4	6.2	0.03	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 03...	0.2	0.8	3.5	0.04	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 12...	0.2	0.3	2.9	0.05	<1	<100	<10	1	<1	650
JUN 08...	<0.2	--	--	0.02	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 03...	0.6	0.9	4.0	0.03	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
SEP 1987 30...	4500	<5	190	<0.10	3	9	20	<0.010	4	0.01
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 12...	1000	<5	100	<0.10	<1	1	10	<0.010	<1	0.01
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	1120	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

Figure 25.--Río Culebrinas basin.

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147600 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR SAN SEBASTIAN, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'51", long 67°02'40", at bridge on Highway 423, 1.3 mi (2.1 km) south of Quebrada El Salto Bridge on Highway 111, and 2.1 mi (3.4 km) west of Central La Plata.

DRAINAGE AREA.--58.2 mi² (150.7 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1979 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPE-CIFIC CON-DUCT-ANCE (US/CM)	PH (STAND-ARD UNITS)	TEMPER-ATURE WATER (DEG C)	TUR-BID-ITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (PER-CENT SATUR-ATION)	OXYGEN DEMAND, CHEM-ICAL (HIGH LEVEL) (MG/L)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREP-TOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
OCT 1987											
01...	1355	70	268	7.70	26.5	3.6	8.7	108	10	1000	K450
DEC											
16...	0730	104	268	7.30	23.5	6.6	7.4	86	33	4600	2700
FEB 1988											
04...	0805	54	336	7.40	22.5	6.1	6.7	77	12	21000	48000
APR											
13...	1435	18	477	7.40	30.0	2.8	6.6	87	210	K650	K40
JUN											
09...	0800	76	320	7.00	25.0	23	6.8	82	21	K10000	5300
AUG											
04...	0800	115	232	6.50	24.5	93	7.2	86	15	K66000	40000

DATE	HARD-NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARD-NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNE-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM AD-SORP-TION RATIO	POTAS-SIUM, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKA-LINITY WAT WH TOT FET (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
OCT 1987											
01...	110	12	36	5.3	12	0.5	2.3	100	<0.5	10	9.7
DEC											
16...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
04...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	130	--	--	--
APR											
13...	140	0	42	7.7	43	2	15	170	<0.5	21	26
JUN											
09...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	120	--	--	--
AUG											
04...	91	4	29	4.4	9.9	0.5	2.7	75	--	12	9.2

DATE	FLUO-RIDE, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI-TUENTS, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DIS-SOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS-PENDED (MG/L)	NITRO-GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO-GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
OCT 1987										
01...	0.10	33	168	168	1	1.14	0.06	1.20	0.04	--
DEC										
16...	--	--	--	--	14	1.14	0.06	1.20	0.10	0.20
FEB 1988										
04...	--	--	--	--	32	0.66	0.04	0.70	0.09	0.41
APR										
13...	0.20	40	303	303	10	0.94	0.26	1.20	1.70	0.90
JUN										
09...	--	--	--	--	29	0.74	0.06	0.80	0.06	0.34
AUG										
04...	0.10	21	140	140	121	0.84	0.06	0.90	0.10	0.50

K = non-ideal count

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147800 RIO CULEBRINAS AT HIGHWAY 404 NEAR MOCA, PR

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'42", long 67°05'33", Hydrologic Unit 21010003, on right bank, at bridge on Highway 404, 0.3 mi (0.5 km) downstream from Quebrada Yagruma, and 2.8 mi (4.5 km) southeast of Moca.

DRAINAGE AREA.--71.2 mi² (184.4 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1967 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 45 ft (14 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records fair except those for estimated daily discharges, which are poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--21 years (1968-88), 305 ft³/s (8.638 m³/s), 58.17 in/yr (1,478 mm/yr), 221,000 acre-ft/yr (272 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 290 ft³/s (8.21 m³/s), 210,000 acre-ft/yr (260 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 69,000 ft³/s (1,950 m³/s), Sept. 16, 1975, gage height, 36.6 ft (11.16 m) from slope-area measurement, but may have been exceeded by flood of Oct. 23, 1974, from rating curve extended above 2,600 ft³/s (73.6 m³/s) on basis of slope-area and contracted-opening measurements of peak flow; minimum discharge, 16 ft³/s (0.453 m³/s), Apr. 17-19, 1979.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 11,300 ft³/s (320 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Oct. 7	2100	25,800	731	27.78	8.467	Aug. 14	2315	13,300	377	23.39	7.129
Nov. 27	unknown	11,300	320	22.46	6.846	Aug. 24	2330	*42,300	1,200	*31.82	9.699
May 26	2015	14,300	405	23.82	7.260	Sept. 2	2015	11,600	328	22.61	6.892
June 24	1845	14,500	411	23.89	7.282	Sept. 20	2045	20,000	566	25.97	7.916
July 26	1830	14,000	396	23.69	7.221						

Minimum discharge, 21 ft³/s (0.595 m³/s), Apr. 9, 10.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	106	e85	e200	115	51	38	26	171	191	206	110	963
2	152	e80	e1100	132	57	36	27	79	152	204	104	2310
3	222	e73	253	83	54	36	28	103	129	407	136	502
4	1260	e86	93	73	82	34	26	110	115	265	181	324
5	252	e76	74	70	55	31	26	83	103	1130	114	281
6	200	e205	e300	70	50	33	26	60	93	351	205	254
7	5040	e125	e700	67	48	31	26	51	86	212	345	295
8	e700	e116	128	64	45	33	25	46	89	181	147	267
9	e300	e96	88	64	47	30	22	53	109	163	117	232
10	e220	e83	76	64	47	31	24	70	78	155	111	284
11	e360	e74	69	62	48	29	23	587	271	149	108	262
12	e250	e73	214	64	64	30	26	341	235	135	108	408
13	e290	e158	196	62	59	28	32	236	389	320	101	269
14	e340	e90	75	64	52	32	29	289	373	194	1570	493
15	e250	e80	103	60	46	30	34	148	243	151	1040	251
16	e390	e73	77	62	46	29	124	944	241	125	186	207
17	e200	e107	71	64	44	33	53	267	565	133	177	192
18	e180	e146	64	65	44	30	127	134	244	211	465	189
19	e175	e111	163	63	40	29	148	103	150	140	192	186
20	e150	e87	130	59	42	30	403	141	157	117	312	3430
21	e145	e78	96	58	40	27	378	133	146	114	323	606
22	e122	e74	79	55	40	28	197	1150	444	120	218	840
23	e120	e72	72	57	38	24	121	373	263	102	170	910
24	118	e426	69	55	40	27	69	274	2200	97	6750	383
25	457	e708	76	53	40	27	70	164	677	112	e1500	320
26	e161	e230	67	54	38	24	95	2440	519	2900	e1100	693
27	e158	e4880	64	54	48	48	73	498	346	243	e1400	318
28	e150	e1240	61	52	44	56	71	487	522	143	e1300	255
29	e348	e394	60	54	39	47	197	392	511	137	e800	399
30	e203	e258	61	54	---	37	264	1070	264	144	e600	241
31	e153	---	80	52	---	30	---	326	---	119	509	---
TOTAL	13172	10384	4959	2025	1388	1008	2790	11323	9905	9180	20499	16564
MEAN	425	346	160	65.3	47.9	32.5	93.0	365	330	296	661	552
MAX	5040	4880	1100	132	82	56	403	2440	2200	2900	6750	3430
MIN	106	72	60	52	38	24	22	46	78	97	101	186
AC-FT	26130	20600	9840	4020	2750	2000	5530	22460	19650	18210	40660	32850
CFSM	5.97	4.86	2.25	.92	.67	.46	1.31	5.13	4.64	4.16	9.29	7.75
IN.	6.88	5.43	2.59	1.06	.73	.53	1.46	5.92	5.18	4.80	10.71	8.65

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 80980 MEAN 222 MAX 5490 MIN 32 AC-FT 160600 CFSM 3.12 IN. 42.31
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 103197 MEAN 282 MAX 6750 MIN 22 AC-FT 204700 CFSM 3.96 IN. 53.92

e Estimated

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50147800 RIO CULEBRINAS AT HIGHWAY 404 NEAR MOCA, PR--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS AUGUST 1981 TO CURRENT YEAR

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 23	1107	121	150	26.5	APR, 13	1920	39.6	301	26.5
DEC, 15	1414	163	312	25.0	MAY, 04	0852	117.3	273	25.0
JAN, 14	0933	65.7	270	23.5	JUN, 07	0851	86.5	324	27.5
FEB, 16	1159	43.5	259	24.0	JUL, 12	0942	135.9	293	27.0
MAR, 09	1014	30.7	337	23.5	AUG, 02	0921	105.4	250	25.5

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50149100 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR AGUADA, PR

WATER-QUALITY RECORDS

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'03", long 67°09'40", at bridge on Highway 2, and 2.3 mi (3.7 km) northeast of Aguada plaza.

DRAINAGE AREA.--97.0 mi² (251.2 km²).

PERIOD OF RECORD.--Water years 1958, 1970 to current year.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DIS-CHARGE, INST. CUBIC FEET PER SECOND	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TURBIDITY (NTU)	OXYGEN, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, DEMAND, (PERCENT SATURATION) (MG/L)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
SEP 1987										
30...	0835	168	272	7.20	25.5	22	7.0	85	14	K8000 52000
DEC 15...	0900	248	345	7.10	25.0	31	7.1	84	56	K10000 K10000
FEB 1988										
03...	1010	26	340	7.00	26.5	4.9	3.2	40	29	20000 86000
APR 12...	0900	23	450	6.70	30.0	6.9	0.1	1	97	45000 K190000
JUN 08...	0825	168	370	7.10	27.5	13	7.3	91	21	K300 K300
AUG 03...	0745	E50	345	6.70	26.0	17	6.6	80	29	K910 2200

DATE	HARDNESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	HARDNESS NONCARBONATE (MG/L AS CaCO3)	CALCIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Ca)	MAGNESIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Mg)	SODIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Na)	SODIUM ADSORPTION RATIO	POTASSIUM DISSOLVED (MG/L AS K)	ALKALINITY TOTAL (MG/L AS CaCO3)	SULFIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS S)	SULFATE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SO4)	CHLORIDE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS Cl)
SEP 1987											
30...	130	17	42	5.4	12	0.5	2.3	110	<0.5	10	11
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
FEB 1988											
03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
APR 12...	180	0	54	11	24	0.8	14	180	<0.5	17	22
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	140	--	--	--
AUG 03...	140	3	48	6.1	13	0.5	2.4	130	--	11	13

DATE	FLUORIDE DISSOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA DISSOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTITUENTS, DISSOLVED (MG/L)	SOLIDS, DISSOLVED (TONS PER DAY)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUSPENDED (MG/L)	NITROGEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITROGEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
SEP 1987										
30...	0.10	28	180	82	37	0.78	0.02	0.80	0.03	0.17
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	63	0.86	0.04	0.90	0.09	1.5
FEB 1988										
03...	--	--	--	--	14	0.27	0.03	0.30	0.03	0.77
APR 12...	0.20	45	311	19	15	--	0.01	<0.10	0.05	3.1
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	20	0.59	0.01	0.60	0.07	0.23
AUG 03...	0.10	29	208	0.0	19	0.78	0.02	0.80	0.10	0.70

K = non-ideal count
E = estimate

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

50149100 RIO CULEBRINAS NEAR AGUADA, PR--Continued

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN, AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	ARSENIC TOTAL (UG/L AS AS)	BARIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS BA)	BORON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS B)	CADMIUM TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CD)	CHRO- MIUM, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CR)	COPPER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS CU)
SEP 1987 30...	0.2	1.0	3.1	0.05	1	<100	10	1	4	20
DEC 15...	1.6	2.5	11	0.06	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 03...	0.8	1.1	4.9	0.12	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 12...	3.2	--	--	1.1	2	<100	40	3	<1	200
JUN 08...	0.3	0.90	4.0	0.06	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 03...	0.8	1.6	7.1	0.08	--	--	--	--	--	--

DATE	IRON, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS FE)	LEAD, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS PB)	MANGA- NESE, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS MN)	MERCURY TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS HG)	SELE- NIUM, TOTAL (UG/L AS SE)	SILVER, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS AG)	ZINC, TOTAL RECOV- ERABLE (UG/L AS ZN)	CYANIDE TOTAL (MG/L AS CN)	PHENOLS TOTAL (UG/L)	METHY- LENE BLUE ACTIVE SUB- STANCE (MG/L)
SEP 1987 30...	1300	<5	70	<0.10	2	1	10	<0.010	1	0.01
DEC 15...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FEB 1988 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
APR 12...	3100	<5	790	<0.10	<1	1	30	<0.010	4	0.08
JUN 08...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
AUG 03...	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	0825	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

DATE	PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	NAPH- THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	PER- THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	TOX- APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL TRI- THION (UG/L)	2,4-D, TOTAL (UG/L)	2,4,5-T TOTAL (UG/L)	2, 4-DP TOTAL (UG/L)	SILVEX, TOTAL (UG/L)
JUN 1988 08...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Water-Quality at
Partial-Record
Stations in
Puerto
Rico

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

Water-quality partial-record stations are particular sites where chemical-quality, biological and or sediment data are collected systematically over a period of years for use in hydrological analysis. The data are collected usually less than quarterly.

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOCATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANSPARANCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PERCENT SATURATION)	COLIFORM, FECAL, 0.7 UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN									
50010720		LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)							
NOV 10...	0725	1.00	229	8.60	28.6	54	9.8	128	K4
MAR 1988 07...	1105	1.00	309	7.80	26.0	51	6.1	76	K2
JUL 21...	0910	1.00	256	7.60	29.4	59	7.5	99	K10
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN									
50025110		LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)							
NOV 1987 12...	0945	1.00	216	8.30	29.2	33	8.4	111	96
MAR 1988 09...	1005	1.00	232	7.60	26.3	43	6.8	84	K13
JUL 07...	0910	1.00	232	8.30	29.7	13	7.9	103	K960
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN									
50039900		LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)							
NOV 1987 13...	1040	1.00	94	6.90	27.6	74	6.7	90	K17
MAR 1988 03...	1040	1.00	91	7.60	22.9	78	7.5	92	K26
JUL 13...	1000	1.00	103	7.40	27.6	50	7.3	97	102
50044400		LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)							
NOV 1987 05...	1040	1.00	346	8.10	28.1	37	11.4	145	K2
MAR 1988 04...	1035	1.00	338	8.80	25.9	12	12.8	157	K25
JUL 12...	0905	1.00	278	6.70	29.7	22	6.4	87	K130
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN									
50057500		LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)							
NOV 1987 06...	0940	1.00	248	7.10	28.7	18	4.1	53	K68000
MAR 1988 03...	1135	1.00	278	8.30	27.6	14	11.2	141	84
JUL 11...	1200	1.00	231	7.10	30.0	7	4.1	54	K15000

K = non-ideal count

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	STREP- TOCOCCI FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)	ALKA- LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CAC03	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
------	--	---	--	--	--	--	--	--

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED

50010720 LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)

NOV 10...	23	99	1	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.03	1.6
MAR 1988 07...	K25	140	2	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	--
JUL 21...	K12	120	12	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	--

RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED

50025110 LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)

NOV 1987 12...	52	80	3	0.39	0.01	0.40	<0.01	--
MAR 1988 09...	K600	75	1	0.47	0.03	0.50	0.01	0.29
JUL 07...	110	81	10	0.19	0.01	0.20	0.01	0.79

RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED

50039900 LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)

NOV 1987 13...	50	30	2	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	--
MAR 1988 03...	K21	32	1	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.02	0.28
JUL 13...	28	33	5	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.04	0.26

50044400 LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)

NOV 1987 05...	K2	120	<1	0.65	0.05	0.70	0.04	0.36
MAR 1988 04...	K44	140	13	0.17	0.03	0.20	0.02	0.28
JUL 12...	32	100	--	0.46	0.04	0.50	0.01	0.19

RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED

50057500 LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)

NOV 1987 06...	4500	82	51	0.44	0.06	0.50	0.64	0.46
MAR 1988 03...	96	93	3	0.40	0.10	0.50	0.01	0.59
JUL 11...	240	69	--	0.43	0.07	0.50	0.60	0.0

K = non-ideal count

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	NITRO- GEN,AM- MONIA + ORGANIC TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, TOTAL (MG/L AS NO3)	PHOS- PHOROUS TOTAL (MG/L AS P)	CHLOR-A PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L)	CHLOR-B PHYTO- PLANK- TON CHROMO FLUOROM (UG/L)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS ASH WT (MG/L)	PLANK- TON BIOMASS DRY WT (MG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50010720	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.3 NR MOUTH NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°22'05"N LONG 066°54'36"W)							
NOV 10...	1.6	--	--	0.04	78.0	0.80	13	280
MAR 1988 07...	0.4	--	--	0.01	14.0	0.50	3.0	260
JUL 21...	0.7	--	--	0.04	33.0	0.90	4.5	250
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED								
50025110	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.3 AT WEST BRANCH NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°19'15"N LONG 066°40'11"W)							
NOV 1987 12...	0.4	0.8	3.5	0.02	12.0	1.20	6.7	280
MAR 1988 09...	0.3	0.8	2.6	0.01	9.90	0.50	2.9	260
JUL 07...	0.8	1.0	4.4	0.04	3.50	-0.10	3.4	280
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50039900	LAGO CARITE NO.3 ON RIO DE LA PLATA NR CAYEY, PR (LAT 18°05'04"N LONG 066°06'03"W)							
NOV 1987 13...	0.2	--	--	0.02	4.80	0.70	2.6	250
MAR 1988 03...	0.3	--	--	0.02	12.0	2.70	7.0	640
JUL 13...	0.3	--	--	0.01	3.40	0.40	0.2	260
50044400	LAGO LA PLATA NO.5 NR MOUTH NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°19'33"N LONG 066°12'28"W)							
NOV 1987 05...	0.4	1.1	4.9	0.12	25.0	1.30	7.8	240
MAR 1988 04...	0.3	0.5	2.2	0.15	110	1.90	8.8	280
JUL 12...	0.2	0.7	3.1	0.18	9.40	1.90	3.6	260
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50057500	LAGO LOIZA NO.4 NR MOUTH NR CAGUAS, PR (LAT 18°16'51"N LONG 066°00'35"W)							
NOV 1987 06...	1.1	1.6	7.1	0.33	3.70	0.80	12	340
MAR 1988 03...	0.6	1.1	4.9	0.27	120	2.40	11	270
JUL 11...	0.6	1.1	4.9	0.33	--	--	--	--

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	DEPTH AT SAMPLE LOCATION, TOTAL (FEET)	SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE (US/CM)	PH (STANDARD UNITS)	TEMPERATURE WATER (DEG C)	TRANSPAR-ENCY (SECCHI DISK) (IN)	OXYGEN, DIS-SOLVED (MG/L)	OXYGEN, (PER-CENT SATURATION)	COLI-FORM, FECAL, UM-MF (COLS./100 ML)	STREPTOCOCCI, FECAL, KF AGAR (COLS. PER 100 ML)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50010790 LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)										
NOV 1987										
10...	0700	1.00	253	8.10	28.3	65	7.1	91	114	K19
10...	0640	31.0	283	7.10	25.9	--	0.0	0	--	--
MAR 1988										
07...	1025	1.00	296	8.20	26.2	53	6.7	83	K8	196
07...	1010	65.0	312	7.10	24.9	--	0.2	2	--	--
JUL										
21...	0950	1.00	259	7.70	29.7	68	8.3	110	46	240
21...	0955	70.0	316	6.50	25.1	--	1.2	16	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED										
50020050 LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)										
NOV 1987										
09...	1045	1.00	134	8.00	24.9	56	8.1	106	52	560
09...	1040	93.0	190	6.70	21.1	--	0.0	0	--	--
MAR 1988										
08...	0945	1.00	137	7.30	22.7	72	5.8	72	K4	K11
08...	1000	92.0	141	6.90	21.3	--	0.0	0	--	--
JUL										
06...	1150	1.00	149	7.50	25.1	26	9.0	118	192	25
06...	1140	73.0	208	7.00	21.2	--	2.0	26	--	--
50027090 LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)										
NOV 1987										
12...	1040	1.00	197	8.30	28.8	56	8.7	114	K8	72
12...	1020	76.0	184	6.70	26.8	--	0.5	6	--	--
MAR 1988										
09...	1050	1.00	216	7.50	26.5	88	5.8	72	21	26
09...	1045	75.0	196	6.80	24.6	--	0.9	11	--	--
JUL										
07...	1000	1.00	224	8.50	30.6	50	8.7	115	K35	K9
07...	0950	75.0	218	6.80	27.3	--	1.0	13	--	--
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50039950 LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)										
NOV 1987										
13...	1000	1.00	98	7.30	27.0	101	7.8	103	K6	K5
13...	0950	70.0	211	6.30	23.3	--	0.0	0	--	--
MAR 1988										
03...	1000	1.00	90	7.80	23.0	77	7.6	93	K7	K7
03...	1015	72.0	97	7.00	21.8	--	0.7	8	--	--
JUL										
13...	0935	1.00	102	7.60	28.1	56	7.4	99	164	29
13...	0930	68.0	136	6.60	22.7	--	1.2	16	--	--
50044950 LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)										
NOV 1987										
05...	0920	1.00	296	7.50	28.1	88	5.1	65	K10	K16
05...	0925	77.0	208	6.80	24.0	--	0.0	0	--	--
MAR 1988										
04...	0920	1.00	317	7.60	25.7	39	6.3	77	K5	60
04...	0915	77.0	184	6.70	23.7	--	0.1	1	--	--
JUL										
12...	1000	1.00	275	7.20	29.9	62	5.0	66	K9	K42
12...	0950	66.0	264	6.70	23.9	--	1.0	13	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50058800 LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)										
NOV 1987										
06...	0845	1.00	197	7.20	28.9	28	5.4	70	K64	K47
06...	0900	45.0	139	6.60	26.3	--	0.0	0	--	--
MAR 1988										
03...	1045	1.00	276	7.30	26.4	28	4.3	53	K11	K33
03...	1050	39.0	252	6.80	25.4	--	0.4	5	--	--
JUL										
11...	1110	1.00	171	7.10	29.7	24	4.3	56	250	K30
11...	1100	40.0	167	6.70	27.0	--	1.4	18	--	--

K = non-ideal count

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	HARD- NESS TOTAL (MG/L AS CAC03)	HARD- NESS NONCARB WH WAT TOT FLD MG/L AS CAC03	CALCIUM DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CA)	MAGNE- SIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS MG)	SODIUM, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS NA)	SODIUM AD- SORP- TION RATIO	POTAS- SIUM, DIS- SOLVEL (MG/L AS K)	ALKA- LINITY WAT WH TOT FET FIELD MG/L AS CAC03	SULFATE DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS S04)
	RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50010790 LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)									
NOV 1987									
10...	120	4	44	3.4	5.5	0.2	2.0	140	11
10...	140	2	51	3.4	5.1	0.2	2.1	120	11
MAR 1988									
07...	140	0	50	3.6	5.8	0.2	2.1	140	11
07...	140	0	52	3.6	5.7	0.2	2.0	130	11
JUL									
21...	130	14	45	3.6	5.5	0.2	1.8	110	11
21...	150	3	55	3.5	4.9	0.2	1.7	140	9.2
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED									
50020050 LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)									
NOV 1987									
09...	55	0	15	4.2	6.2	0.4	1.7	59	4.4
09...	81	0	23	5.8	6.3	0.3	1.7	110	9.1
MAR 1988									
08...	56	0	16	4.0	5.7	0.3	1.2	56	3.9
08...	57	0	16	4.1	5.3	0.3	1.2	64	4.0
JUL									
06...	60	0	16	4.9	6.7	0.4	1.2	61	5.0
06...	68	0	19	5.0	6.0	0.3	1.3	82	2.4
50027090 LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)									
NOV 1987									
12...	75	1	20	6.1	10	0.5	2.3	74	14
12...	68	6	18	5.5	9.1	0.5	2.7	62	11
MAR 1988									
09...	78	0	21	6.1	11	0.6	2.1	73	17
09...	75	0	20	6.2	9.9	0.5	2.0	74	13
JUL									
07...	86	2	23	7.0	11	0.5	2.1	80	16
07...	85	4	23	6.7	9.8	0.5	2.4	88	11
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50039950 LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAVEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)									
NOV 1987									
13...	30	0	6.2	3.6	8.4	0.7	1.5	32	3.7
13...	45	0	10	4.9	8.3	0.6	1.3	82	15
MAR 1988									
03...	29	0	5.7	3.5	7.9	0.7	0.8	30	3.6
03...	28	0	5.8	3.4	7.4	0.6	0.9	34	4.9
JUL									
13...	31	0	6.2	3.8	8.0	0.6	0.8	34	3.8
13...	36	0	7.6	4.2	9.3	0.7	1.7	49	13
50044950 LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)									
NOV 1987									
05...	120	11	27	13	24	1	2.4	110	14
05...	83	0	20	8.0	11	0.5	2.8	98	10
MAR 1988									
04...	120	0	29	12	19	0.8	2.1	130	14
04...	70	0	17	6.6	9.9	0.5	2.7	74	13
JUL									
12...	100	0	24	10	18	0.8	1.9	110	15
12...	97	1	23	9.7	12	0.5	2.5	90	15
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50058800 LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)									
NOV 1987									
06...	63	2	15	6.1	16	0.9	3.2	61	15
06...	49	0	12	4.7	11	0.7	3.4	63	15
MAR 1988									
03...	75	0	18	7.4	17	0.9	3.0	91	17
03...	83	0	20	8.1	20	1	2.5	85	16
JUL									
11...	46	6	11	4.5	11	0.7	2.9	45	15
11...	50	5	12	4.9	12	0.8	2.7	43	20

ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	CHLO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS CL)	FLUO- RIDE, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS F)	SILICA, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L AS SiO2)	SOLIDS, SUM OF CONSTI- TUENTS, DIS- SOLVED (MG/L)	RESIDUE TOTAL AT 105 DEG. C, SUS- PENDE (MG/L)	NITRO- GEN, NITRATE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NITRITE TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, NO2+NO3 TOTAL (MG/L AS N)	NITRO- GEN, AMMONIA TOTAL (MG/L AS N)
	RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED								
50010790 LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)									
NOV 1987									
10...	10	0.1	6.5	154	3	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.01
10...	10	0.1	7.7	174	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1988									
07...	8.4	0.2	6.9	172	3	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01
07...	8.3	0.2	7.9	178	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
21...	8.4	0.1	7.2	150	6	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01
21...	7.8	0.2	7.3	179	--	--	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED									
50020050 LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)									
NOV 1987									
09...	6.3	0.1	16	89	3	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01
09...	5.7	0.1	21	139	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1988									
08...	5.3	0.1	17	90	4	0.09	0.01	0.10	<0.01
08...	5.2	0.1	17	95	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
06...	5.6	0.2	18	96	6	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01
06...	5.3	0.2	20	100	--	--	--	--	--
50027090 LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)									
NOV 1987									
12...	12	0.1	22	131	1	--	<0.01	0.20	0.02
12...	11	0.1	21	116	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1988									
09...	11	0.2	21	137	1	0.48	0.02	0.50	<0.01
09...	9.7	0.2	22	129	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
07...	10	0.2	22	142	6	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01
07...	9.8	0.2	21	132	--	--	--	--	--
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50039950 LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)									
NOV 1987									
13...	11	0.1	17	71	4	--	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01
13...	12	0.1	22	123	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1988									
03...	8.2	0.1	17	66	5	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.02
03...	8.4	0.1	18	68	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
13...	9.8	0.1	18	89	3	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.06
13...	8.5	0.1	17	69	--	--	--	--	--
50044950 LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)									
NOV 1987									
05...	21	0.2	18	186	<1	--	<0.01	<0.10	0.05
05...	11	0.2	20	142	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1988									
04...	21	0.2	19	191	2	0.18	0.02	0.20	0.01
04...	12	0.2	18	123	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
12...	18	<0.1	20	168	7	--	0.02	<0.10	<0.01
12...	13	<0.1	21	154	--	--	--	--	--
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50058800 LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)									
NOV 1987									
06...	16	0.2	22	130	6	0.48	0.02	0.50	0.04
06...	10	0.2	18	112	--	--	--	--	--
MAR 1988									
03...	22	0.2	20	165	5	0.43	0.07	0.50	0.21
03...	19	0.2	21	153	--	--	--	--	--
JUL									
11...	12	0.1	16	96	427	0.64	0.06	0.70	0.14
11...	13	0.1	5.0	97	--	--	--	--	--

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	PCB, TOTAL (UG/L)	ALDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	CHLOR- DANE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDD, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDE, TOTAL (UG/L)	DDT, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- AZINON, TOTAL (UG/L)	DI- ELDRIN TOTAL (UG/L)	ENDO- SULFAN, TOTAL (UG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN										
50010790		LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
JUL 1988 21...	0950	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN										
50020050		LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
JUL 1988 06...	1150	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
50027090		LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
JUL 1988 07...	1000	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN										
50039950		LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)								
JUL 1988 13...	0935	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
50044950		LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)								
JUL 1988 12...	1000	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN										
50058800		LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
JUL 1988 11...	1110	<0.10	<0.01	<0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	ENDRIN, TOTAL (UG/L)	ETHION, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	HEPTA- CHLOR EPOXIDE TOTAL (UG/L)	LINDANE TOTAL (UG/L)	MALA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METH- OXY- CHLOR, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL PARA- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	METHYL TRI- THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	MIREX, TOTAL (UG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)									
JUL 1988 21...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED										
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)									
JUL 1988 06...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)									
JUL 1988 07...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50039950	LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)									
JUL 1988 13...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR NARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)									
JUL 1988 12...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED										
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)									
JUL 1988 11...	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

PESTICIDE ANALYSES OF SAMPLES COLLECTED AT WATER-QUALITY PARTIAL-RECORD STATIONS

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	PARA-	NAPH-	PER-	TOX-	TOTAL	2,4-D,	2,4,5-T	2,4-DP	SILVEX,
	THION, TOTAL (UG/L)	THA- LENES, POLY- CHLOR. TOTAL (UG/L)	THANE TOTAL (UG/L)	APHENE, TOTAL (UG/L)	TRI- TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL (UG/L)	TOTAL (UG/L)
RIO GUAJATACA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50010790	LAGO GUAJATACA NO.1 NR DAM NR QUEBRADILLAS, PR (LAT 18°23'56"N LONG 066°55'23"W)								
JUL 1988 21...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.05	<0.01	<0.05	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN--CONTINUED									
50020050	LAGO GARZAS NO.1 NR DAM NR ADJUNTAS, PR (LAT 18°08'21"N LONG 066°44'35"W)								
JUL 1988 06...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
50027090	LAGO DOS BOCAS NO.1 NR DAM NR UTUADO, PR (LAT 18°20'09"N LONG 066°40'04"W)								
JUL 1988 07...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50039950	LAGO CARITE NO.1 NR DAM NR CAYEY, P.R. (LAT 18°04'39"N LONG 066°06'19"W)								
JUL 1988 13...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	<0.05	<0.01	<0.05	<0.01
50044950	LAGO LA PLATA NO.3 NR DAM NR MARANJITO, PR (LAT 18°20'18"N LONG 066°14'01"W)								
JUL 1988 12...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN--CONTINUED									
50058800	LAGO LOIZA NO.7 NR DAM NR TRUJILLO ALTO, PR (LAT 18°19'29"N LONG 066°00'47"W)								
JUL 1988 11...	<0.01	<0.1	<0.10	<1	<0.01	--	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Ground-Water Records
for
Puerto Rico

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

182422067015100. Local number, 165.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'22", long 67°01'51".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Saltos # 1 (Mateo Perez).

AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation. Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.40 m), cased 16 in (0.40 m) 0-40 ft (0-12.2 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 40-200 ft (12.2-61.0 m). Depth 200 ft (61.0 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 689 ft (210 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Hole on pump base, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum. Prior November 1985, hole on top of pump base, 1.00 ft (0.30 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Formerly published as 182421067015000.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1982 to March 1985. November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 44.06 ft (13.43 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1988; lowest water level measured, 70.60 ft (21.52 m) below land-surface datum, June 18, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	47.67	47.22	46.95	46.74	46.49	46.17	46.11	---	---	45.31	44.97	44.58
2	47.70	47.17	46.99	46.65	46.47	46.25	46.09	---	---	45.28	44.97	44.63
3	47.71	47.12	46.97	46.72	46.40	46.32	46.11	---	---	45.28	44.97	44.59
4	47.62	47.13	46.90	46.81	46.37	46.32	46.09	---	---	45.28	44.99	44.57
5	47.56	47.17	46.91	46.75	46.37	46.28	45.98	---	---	45.27	44.96	44.54
6	47.59	47.22	46.90	46.76	46.39	46.31	45.92	---	---	45.25	44.94	44.52
7	47.57	47.20	46.88	46.69	46.41	46.30	45.88	---	---	45.26	44.93	44.46
8	47.56	47.21	46.83	46.65	46.36	46.33	46.04	---	45.80	45.28	44.91	44.47
9	47.58	47.18	46.78	46.67	46.27	46.40	45.98	---	45.82	45.26	44.92	44.39
10	47.59	47.16	46.76	46.69	46.31	46.27	45.94	---	45.82	45.21	44.89	44.22
11	47.52	47.11	46.74	46.64	46.31	46.29	45.98	---	45.70	45.26	44.86	44.27
12	47.43	47.07	46.70	46.65	46.30	46.30	45.99	---	45.64	45.28	44.89	44.39
13	47.42	47.09	46.79	46.67	46.25	46.24	46.03	---	45.65	45.17	44.92	44.37
14	47.42	47.10	46.83	46.64	46.27	46.12	46.02	---	45.68	45.11	44.91	44.37
15	47.42	47.09	46.86	46.61	46.28	46.29	45.98	---	45.64	45.15	44.87	44.41
16	47.39	47.08	46.81	46.60	46.29	46.43	46.02	---	45.60	45.16	44.85	44.40
17	47.36	47.09	46.78	46.75	46.28	46.48	45.96	---	45.57	45.11	44.83	44.34
18	47.36	47.12	46.79	46.60	46.22	46.46	45.97	---	45.58	45.08	44.78	44.22
19	47.37	47.10	46.86	46.61	46.22	46.39	45.91	---	45.58	45.07	44.78	44.21
20	47.38	47.05	46.86	46.60	46.22	46.43	45.88	---	45.56	45.10	44.77	44.32
21	47.39	46.99	46.79	46.56	46.24	46.45	45.92	---	45.53	45.06	44.75	44.30
22	47.39	46.99	46.83	46.57	46.28	46.41	45.97	---	45.49	45.01	44.72	44.23
23	47.38	46.94	46.82	46.52	46.23	46.36	46.07	---	45.48	45.05	44.74	44.20
24	47.39	46.95	46.79	46.64	46.19	46.31	---	---	45.47	45.03	44.60	44.21
25	47.28	46.85	46.78	46.55	46.10	46.26	---	---	45.42	45.01	44.66	44.19
26	47.23	46.80	46.73	46.58	46.06	46.25	---	---	45.39	44.99	44.60	44.18
27	47.26	46.79	46.70	46.53	46.10	46.13	---	---	45.39	45.02	44.61	44.17
28	47.25	46.81	46.69	46.49	46.12	46.16	---	---	45.39	44.99	44.62	44.17
29	47.28	46.81	46.60	46.50	46.17	46.12	---	---	45.32	44.94	44.60	44.16
30	47.23	46.86	46.65	46.50	---	46.10	---	---	45.31	44.99	44.53	44.12
31	47.22	---	46.77	46.50	---	46.10	---	---	---	44.95	44.54	---
LOW	47.71	47.22	46.99	46.81	46.49	46.48	---	---	---	45.31	44.99	44.63
HIGH	47.22	46.79	46.60	46.49	46.06	46.10	---	---	---	44.94	44.53	44.12

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUAJATACA BASIN

182647066552400. Local number, 202.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'47", long 66°55'24".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Carmelo Barreto Garcia well.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-296 ft (0-90.2 m), diameter 13 in (0.33 m), cased 13 in (0.33 m) 0-550 ft (0-167.6 m), perforated 270-529 ft (82.3-161.2 m). Depth 550 ft (167.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 475 ft (145 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.50 ft (0.46 m) above land-surface datum. Prior July 25, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.30 ft (1.00 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 409.17 ft (124.71 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 25, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 452.80 ft (138.01 m) below land-surface datum, June 26, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	423.06	424.06	424.33	423.27	423.62	425.15	427.48	427.93	425.60	425.32	425.35	427.34
2	423.11	424.09	424.38	423.21	423.66	425.27	427.53	427.88	425.54	425.23	425.39	427.38
3	423.14	424.11	424.39	423.19	423.69	425.34	427.63	427.87	425.48	425.19	425.43	427.41
4	423.15	424.16	424.40	423.14	423.76	425.43	427.69	427.85	425.47	425.16	425.53	427.44
5	423.18	424.21	424.45	423.09	423.82	425.50	427.74	427.82	425.43	425.09	425.58	427.46
6	423.23	424.25	424.47	423.06	423.87	425.54	427.82	427.77	425.38	425.03	425.65	427.52
7	423.26	424.28	424.49	422.99	423.91	425.63	427.88	427.77	425.35	424.98	425.71	427.54
8	423.29	424.32	424.53	422.92	423.93	425.70	427.95	427.79	425.32	424.96	425.78	427.59
9	423.33	424.31	424.51	422.89	423.94	425.74	428.03	427.84	425.34	424.86	425.85	427.62
10	423.37	424.31	424.52	422.88	424.00	425.82	428.08	427.85	425.32	424.81	425.93	427.55
11	423.37	424.31	424.53	422.86	424.05	425.92	428.17	427.87	425.26	424.81	426.00	427.61
12	423.36	424.35	424.57	422.84	424.07	425.93	428.26	427.82	425.25	424.80	426.07	427.59
13	423.39	424.38	424.63	422.82	424.11	425.93	428.32	427.68	425.32	424.76	426.14	427.55
14	423.43	424.42	424.63	422.82	424.17	425.93	428.42	427.56	425.37	424.72	426.22	427.53
15	423.45	424.42	424.62	422.81	424.23	425.93	428.49	427.43	425.37	424.74	426.29	427.50
16	423.47	424.44	424.53	422.82	424.28	426.27	428.59	427.31	425.39	424.76	426.36	427.42
17	423.50	424.49	424.47	422.87	424.34	426.35	428.67	427.01	425.42	424.73	426.44	427.35
18	423.54	424.52	424.39	422.86	424.36	426.43	428.73	426.66	425.47	424.64	426.50	427.25
19	423.58	424.50	424.33	422.90	424.46	426.48	428.78	426.45	425.50	424.63	426.58	427.20
20	423.62	424.47	424.24	422.94	424.49	426.59	428.85	426.29	425.51	424.79	426.64	427.18
21	423.65	424.42	424.13	422.96	424.57	426.67	428.90	426.19	425.52	424.80	426.72	427.13
22	423.68	424.40	424.06	422.97	424.66	426.75	428.94	426.12	425.51	424.81	426.80	427.05
23	423.73	424.33	423.95	422.97	424.69	426.83	428.87	426.06	425.51	424.86	426.89	427.01
24	423.75	424.30	423.85	423.10	424.76	426.87	428.58	426.01	425.55	424.92	426.92	427.00
25	423.76	424.26	423.73	423.13	424.80	426.94	428.34	425.91	425.53	424.96	427.04	426.96
26	423.79	424.24	423.63	423.21	424.85	427.02	428.22	425.86	425.54	425.00	427.09	426.93
27	423.85	424.22	423.55	423.27	424.91	427.09	428.16	425.81	425.55	425.05	427.15	426.92
28	423.88	424.22	423.48	423.32	425.01	427.16	428.09	425.77	425.55	425.13	427.20	426.90
29	423.97	424.24	423.35	423.42	425.11	427.25	428.06	425.72	425.45	425.15	427.22	426.88
30	423.97	424.27	423.34	423.47	---	427.33	428.00	425.69	425.38	425.23	427.24	426.87
31	424.02	---	423.32	423.54	---	427.40	---	425.65	---	425.27	427.29	---
LOW	424.02	424.52	424.63	423.54	425.11	427.40	428.94	427.93	425.60	425.32	427.29	427.62
HIGH	423.06	424.06	423.32	422.81	423.62	425.15	427.48	425.65	425.25	424.40	425.35	426.87

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 425.40 LOW 428.94 HIGH 422.81

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE ARECIBO BASIN

182737066370900. Local number, 204.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'37", long 66°37'09".

Owner: Sucesion Marquez.
Name: Gilberto Rivera well.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Abandoned unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 48.0 ft (14.63 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Air hole on pump base, 0.50 ft (0.15 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 50.00 ft (15.24 m) below land-surface datum, May 14, 1986; lowest water level recorded., 52.28 ft (15.93 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 5-6, 19-20, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	51.79	51.90	51.83	52.07	52.18	52.02	52.11	52.14	51.91	51.95	51.98	51.54
2	51.76	51.86	51.97	52.08	52.13	52.11	52.21	52.11	51.91	51.91	52.01	51.56
3	51.74	51.82	51.94	51.96	52.07	52.12	52.23	52.01	52.00	51.88	52.04	51.61
4	51.62	51.83	52.04	51.95	52.05	52.28	52.22	52.12	52.00	51.88	52.02	51.66
5	51.65	51.83	52.03	51.96	52.04	52.31	52.21	52.17	52.07	51.88	52.00	51.67
6	51.61	51.86	51.94	52.06	52.06	52.32	52.20	52.15	52.10	51.94	52.00	51.66
7	51.51	51.92	52.09	52.06	52.06	52.28	52.18	52.13	52.10	51.96	52.01	51.61
8	51.51	51.91	52.14	52.08	52.08	52.28	52.15	52.11	52.00	52.02	51.98	51.57
9	51.62	52.03	52.15	51.96	52.08	52.31	52.15	52.11	52.09	52.07	51.93	51.51
10	51.70	52.06	52.00	52.04	52.05	---	52.16	52.10	52.10	52.08	51.89	51.44
11	51.74	52.05	52.07	52.02	52.06	---	52.13	51.94	52.13	52.07	51.84	51.44
12	51.77	52.06	52.07	51.98	52.09	---	52.11	51.72	52.11	52.07	51.82	51.35
13	51.77	52.07	52.08	52.07	52.12	---	52.08	51.66	52.08	52.08	51.79	51.33
14	51.76	52.04	52.01	52.09	52.12	---	52.00	51.70	51.98	52.06	51.80	51.42
15	51.80	52.02	52.08	52.14	52.14	---	52.10	51.74	52.07	52.05	51.81	51.50
16	51.77	52.01	52.06	52.11	52.14	---	52.07	51.75	52.05	52.06	51.84	51.53
17	51.73	51.98	52.04	52.09	52.12	---	52.10	51.77	52.05	52.05	51.82	51.62
18	51.72	51.98	52.00	52.11	52.03	---	52.11	51.82	52.08	52.05	51.76	51.68
19	51.70	51.96	52.04	52.08	52.09	---	52.15	51.88	52.08	52.06	51.75	51.72
20	51.68	51.87	52.08	52.09	52.02	---	52.14	51.91	52.10	52.09	51.78	51.71
21	51.66	51.80	52.09	52.10	52.12	---	52.01	51.96	52.10	52.12	51.80	51.74
22	51.66	51.83	52.09	52.07	52.02	---	52.07	51.90	51.97	52.15	51.86	51.73
23	51.70	51.90	52.06	52.09	52.12	---	52.01	51.90	51.97	52.19	51.81	51.67
24	51.73	51.95	52.05	52.07	52.11	52.33	52.11	52.03	52.00	52.19	51.75	51.65
25	51.76	51.96	52.06	52.07	52.11	52.33	52.16	52.05	51.98	52.19	51.68	51.65
26	51.83	51.94	52.06	52.03	52.05	52.30	52.12	52.04	52.00	52.18	51.55	51.66
27	51.87	51.83	52.06	52.04	52.03	52.26	52.00	52.01	51.99	52.18	51.48	51.68
28	51.81	51.83	52.06	52.13	52.07	52.23	52.05	52.10	51.99	52.13	51.43	51.75
29	51.90	51.84	51.94	52.14	52.01	52.18	52.05	52.07	51.99	52.09	51.43	51.81
30	51.94	51.85	51.98	52.15	---	52.15	52.10	52.06	51.98	52.03	51.48	51.87
31	51.93	---	52.01	52.20	---	52.11	---	52.04	---	51.88	51.51	---
LOW	51.94	52.07	52.15	52.20	52.18	---	52.23	52.17	52.13	52.19	52.04	51.87
HIGH	51.51	51.80	51.83	51.95	52.01	---	52.00	51.66	51.91	51.88	51.43	51.33

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182544066341500. Local number, 205.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'44", long 66°34'15".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey.

Name: NC-05 Barceloneta near Cruce Davila.

AQUIFER.--Montebello Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Artesian observation well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), 0-2,564 ft (0-782 m), cased 2.5 in (0.06 m), iron pipe 0-1,075 ft (0-328 m), open hole 1,075-2,564 ft (328-782 m). Depth 2,564 ft (782 m) measured.

DATUM.--Elevation of land surface datum is 312 ft (95.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 6.65 ft (2.03 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation ell.

PERIOD OF RECORDS.--December 1986 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.16 ft (2.79 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 18, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 13.65 ft (4.16 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 9, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	9.59	9.27	9.22	8.87	9.21	8.80	8.99	9.21	8.60	9.23	9.63	10.39
2	9.60	9.42	9.22	8.81	9.29	9.00	8.97	9.18	8.44	9.20	9.78	10.46
3	9.60	9.29	9.20	8.77	9.24	9.00	8.93	9.17	8.49	9.20	9.77	10.43
4	9.61	9.31	9.20	8.73	9.24	8.99	8.97	9.18	8.36	9.22	9.83	10.26
5	9.54	9.34	9.19	8.72	9.22	8.82	9.06	9.15	8.40	9.23	9.75	10.39
6	9.96	9.44	9.19	8.69	9.70	8.73	9.05	8.95	8.55	9.27	9.76	10.47
7	9.78	9.33	9.19	8.73	9.56	8.75	9.02	8.78	8.64	9.30	9.81	10.49
8	9.73	9.31	9.34	8.73	9.55	8.90	9.06	8.46	8.72	9.31	9.86	10.45
9	9.60	9.26	---	8.73	9.51	8.88	9.07	8.27	8.81	9.30	9.84	10.53
10	9.47	9.27	---	8.72	9.52	8.88	9.13	8.10	8.86	9.30	9.88	10.46
11	9.58	9.25	---	8.72	9.52	8.89	9.08	7.92	8.82	9.47	9.91	10.47
12	9.79	9.22	9.33	8.72	9.45	8.87	9.14	7.59	8.79	9.45	9.95	10.53
13	9.70	9.26	9.22	8.72	9.40	8.84	9.17	7.41	8.93	9.39	9.95	10.53
14	9.64	---	9.30	8.70	9.11	8.84	9.18	7.37	8.96	9.47	9.93	10.53
15	9.69	---	9.26	8.51	9.11	8.82	9.21	7.54	8.98	9.54	9.97	10.54
16	9.58	---	9.22	8.54	9.08	9.07	9.26	7.52	8.92	9.38	9.99	10.68
17	9.41	---	9.23	8.50	9.02	8.99	8.96	7.61	8.96	9.35	9.99	10.68
18	9.45	---	9.28	8.51	9.00	9.14	9.18	7.64	8.91	9.36	10.00	10.62
19	9.55	---	9.16	8.57	8.99	8.99	9.05	7.93	8.88	9.44	10.01	10.64
20	9.56	---	9.16	8.51	8.94	8.99	9.05	7.92	9.01	9.49	10.04	10.77
21	9.54	---	9.26	8.46	8.93	9.00	9.02	7.80	9.12	9.60	10.00	10.65
22	9.55	---	9.29	9.43	8.96	8.98	8.93	7.87	9.08	9.60	10.07	10.64
23	9.52	---	9.23	9.41	9.00	---	8.94	8.09	9.18	9.61	10.20	10.69
24	9.44	9.21	9.20	9.41	9.01	---	8.94	7.97	9.13	9.58	10.26	10.52
25	9.25	9.25	9.05	9.41	8.95	8.85	8.94	8.05	9.12	9.57	10.26	10.44
26	9.32	9.30	8.99	9.42	8.90	8.94	9.16	8.12	9.12	9.64	10.26	10.50
27	9.34	9.30	9.07	9.38	8.85	8.94	9.17	8.17	9.19	9.73	10.28	10.57
28	9.34	9.30	9.09	9.36	8.83	8.87	9.19	8.25	9.22	9.72	10.31	10.55
29	9.42	9.30	8.99	9.34	8.85	8.92	9.19	8.28	9.22	9.72	10.26	10.51
30	9.21	9.22	9.09	9.30	---	8.97	9.28	8.33	9.23	9.69	10.37	10.50
31	9.23	---	9.10	9.29	---	8.95	---	8.57	---	9.63	10.44	---
LOW	9.96	---	---	9.43	9.70	---	9.28	9.21	9.23	9.73	10.44	10.77
HIGH	9.21	---	---	8.46	8.83	---	8.93	7.37	8.36	9.20	9.63	10.26

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182757066325600. Local number, 206.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'57", long 66°32'56".

Owner: P.R. Department of Agriculture.

Name: Plazuela No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-85 ft (0-25.9 m), open hole 85-101 ft (25.9-30.8 m). Depth 101 ft (30.8 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 7.0 ft (2.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.75 ft (1.14 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 11, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 5.72 ft (1.76 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 8-9, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.06	5.14	5.09	5.04	5.09	5.37	5.30	5.23	5.25	5.22	5.27	4.73
2	5.03	5.11	5.10	4.84	5.02	5.39	5.32	5.24	5.25	5.22	5.29	4.82
3	4.99	5.09	5.18	4.89	4.95	5.44	5.35	5.22	5.26	5.20	5.30	4.89
4	4.94	5.09	5.21	4.94	4.91	5.50	5.34	5.23	5.26	5.19	5.01	4.97
5	4.90	5.10	5.22	4.99	4.99	5.54	5.33	5.28	5.31	5.21	5.15	5.02
6	4.88	5.12	5.20	5.05	5.08	5.55	5.32	5.27	5.32	5.24	5.22	5.04
7	4.86	5.17	5.25	5.08	5.14	---	5.31	5.25	5.32	5.27	5.30	5.07
8	4.88	5.24	5.28	5.12	5.20	---	5.27	5.23	5.30	5.32	5.28	5.06
9	4.91	5.28	5.30	5.11	5.22	---	5.27	5.21	5.30	5.37	5.25	4.60
10	4.98	5.30	5.24	5.12	5.23	---	5.27	4.84	5.30	5.38	5.22	3.79
11	5.03	5.29	5.23	5.13	5.26	---	5.25	4.58	5.32	5.38	5.19	3.75
12	5.06	5.29	5.22	5.15	5.30	---	5.18	4.50	5.31	5.39	5.17	3.95
13	5.05	5.30	5.24	5.16	5.34	---	5.20	4.66	5.29	5.40	5.15	4.10
14	5.05	5.28	5.25	5.18	5.36	---	5.21	4.76	5.30	5.39	5.15	4.31
15	5.06	5.26	5.20	5.22	5.37	---	5.22	4.84	5.31	5.39	5.15	4.53
16	5.05	5.25	5.17	5.21	5.38	---	4.98	4.89	5.30	5.39	5.18	4.71
17	4.99	5.20	5.14	5.19	5.35	---	5.11	4.94	5.29	5.38	5.18	4.84
18	4.98	5.18	5.12	5.21	5.34	---	5.19	4.99	5.31	5.38	4.62	4.88
19	4.97	5.17	5.15	5.20	5.33	---	5.24	5.05	5.32	5.39	4.73	4.98
20	4.95	5.11	5.20	5.21	5.33	---	5.25	5.09	5.34	5.41	4.85	5.02
21	4.95	5.07	4.92	5.22	5.35	---	5.20	5.14	5.34	5.42	4.98	5.04
22	4.95	5.08	4.99	5.26	5.35	---	5.20	5.17	5.30	5.44	5.07	5.05
23	5.03	5.12	5.03	5.26	5.36	5.70	5.21	5.18	5.28	5.47	4.56	5.03
24	5.07	5.15	5.06	5.25	5.36	5.47	5.23	5.20	4.95	5.47	4.19	5.03
25	---	5.15	5.08	5.19	5.37	5.47	5.26	5.22	5.06	5.47	4.04	5.05
26	---	5.13	5.02	5.23	5.33	5.44	5.23	5.22	5.11	5.46	4.19	5.06
27	---	5.11	4.95	5.27	5.31	5.40	5.19	5.24	5.16	5.45	3.86	5.08
28	5.13	5.03	4.99	5.31	5.34	5.35	5.16	5.25	5.11	5.41	4.10	5.13
29	5.13	5.03	4.99	5.32	5.36	5.29	5.16	5.24	5.15	5.37	4.29	5.18
30	5.16	5.05	5.01	5.32	---	5.26	5.19	5.24	5.21	5.31	4.45	5.21
31	5.16	---	5.02	5.36	---	5.30	---	5.22	---	5.27	4.60	---
LOW	---	5.30	5.30	5.36	5.38	---	5.35	5.28	5.34	5.47	5.30	5.21
HIGH	---	5.03	4.92	4.84	4.91	---	4.98	4.50	4.95	5.19	3.86	3.75

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182710066303700. Local number, 207.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°27'10", long 66°30'37".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Cantito La Luisa.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-30 ft (0-9.14 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 0-126 ft (0-38.4 m), perforated 80-126 ft (24.4-38.4 m). Depth 126 ft (38.4 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 59.0 ft (18.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 36.38 ft (11.09 m) below land-surface datum, May 15, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 89.83 ft (27.38 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	38.52	38.84	38.61	38.45	38.80	38.90	39.15	38.89	38.67	38.90	39.12	38.62
2	38.51	38.84	38.19	38.44	38.78	38.90	39.15	38.90	38.70	38.90	39.12	38.65
3	38.51	38.84	38.33	38.42	38.73	38.91	39.15	38.91	38.74	38.90	39.13	38.68
4	38.49	38.85	38.45	38.41	38.70	38.93	39.15	38.92	38.75	38.89	39.10	38.71
5	38.50	38.87	38.53	38.41	38.67	38.96	39.16	38.94	38.78	38.89	39.10	38.73
6	38.50	38.88	38.56	38.43	38.67	38.98	39.16	38.94	38.81	38.90	39.09	38.74
7	38.50	38.89	38.59	38.45	38.67	38.98	39.16	38.94	38.82	38.91	39.09	38.73
8	38.52	38.91	38.62	38.47	38.68	39.00	39.15	38.94	38.83	38.93	39.09	38.73
9	38.54	38.93	38.65	38.48	38.69	39.02	39.15	38.94	38.84	38.96	39.08	38.72
10	38.57	38.93	38.66	38.46	38.68	39.04	39.16	38.91	38.85	38.98	39.07	38.62
11	38.60	38.93	38.67	38.47	38.69	39.02	39.14	38.36	38.86	38.98	39.06	38.57
12	38.62	38.93	38.68	38.51	38.72	38.98	39.14	38.10	38.87	39.00	39.04	38.53
13	38.63	38.94	38.72	38.53	38.76	38.99	39.12	38.04	38.88	39.01	39.05	38.49
14	38.63	38.94	38.76	38.55	38.79	39.00	39.10	38.06	38.88	39.02	39.06	38.50
15	38.66	38.92	38.70	38.58	38.82	39.00	39.10	38.08	38.89	39.04	39.07	38.53
16	38.64	38.91	38.63	38.60	38.83	39.01	39.00	38.11	38.90	39.06	39.09	38.55
17	38.65	38.90	38.62	38.60	38.83	39.04	38.97	38.15	38.90	39.06	39.08	38.58
18	38.66	38.90	38.62	38.60	38.83	39.04	38.94	38.20	38.91	39.07	39.03	38.61
19	38.67	38.90	38.64	38.57	38.83	39.06	38.92	38.25	38.92	39.08	38.99	38.63
20	38.68	38.89	38.63	38.57	38.83	39.06	38.91	38.32	38.93	39.09	39.00	38.63
21	38.68	38.86	38.57	38.59	38.85	39.08	38.90	38.37	38.94	39.12	39.00	38.64
22	38.69	38.85	38.54	38.60	38.87	39.12	38.86	38.43	38.93	39.13	39.00	38.64
23	38.71	38.86	38.52	38.62	38.88	39.15	38.83	38.48	38.91	39.14	38.93	38.64
24	38.74	38.84	38.52	38.64	38.89	39.17	38.81	38.51	38.91	39.13	38.92	38.64
25	38.75	38.81	38.52	38.66	38.90	39.18	38.83	38.53	38.90	39.16	38.74	38.66
26	38.78	38.80	38.52	38.70	38.90	39.18	38.83	38.56	38.90	39.16	38.66	38.70
27	38.79	38.78	38.49	38.74	38.90	39.18	38.84	38.58	38.90	39.17	38.60	38.71
28	38.80	38.64	38.47	38.77	38.90	39.17	38.84	38.60	38.90	39.15	38.57	38.72
29	38.80	38.60	38.47	38.79	38.90	39.15	38.85	38.63	38.90	39.15	38.56	38.73
30	38.81	38.59	38.46	38.80	---	39.13	38.87	38.66	38.90	39.14	38.58	38.72
31	38.83	---	38.48	38.80	---	39.14	---	38.66	---	39.12	38.59	---
LOW	38.83	38.94	38.76	38.80	38.90	39.18	39.16	38.94	38.94	39.17	39.13	38.74
HIGH	38.49	38.59	38.19	38.41	38.67	38.90	38.81	38.04	38.67	38.89	38.56	38.49

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 38.79 LOW 39.18 HIGH 38.04

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182534066283000. Local number, 208.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'34", long 66°28'30".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Acropolis Manati.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 14 in (0.36 m), cased 14 in (0.36 m). Depth 235 ft (71.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 254 ft (77.4 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.70 ft (0.21 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1986 to May 13, 1988, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 225.95 ft (68.81 m) below land-surface datum, May 31, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 238.33 ft (72.64 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 30-31, Apr. 1-10, 1987.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	236.13	236.35	236.31	235.57	236.20	236.20	236.52	237.56	---	---	---	---
2	236.14	236.35	236.31	235.29	236.08	236.20	236.55	237.59	---	---	---	---
3	236.15	236.35	236.31	235.14	235.90	236.20	236.59	237.63	---	---	---	---
4	236.16	236.35	236.31	235.10	235.69	236.20	236.62	237.66	---	---	---	---
5	236.16	236.35	236.31	235.10	235.59	236.20	236.66	237.69	---	---	---	---
6	236.17	236.35	236.31	235.12	235.59	236.20	236.69	237.74	---	---	---	---
7	236.18	236.35	236.31	235.13	235.65	236.20	236.73	237.76	---	---	---	---
8	236.19	236.36	236.31	235.08	235.68	236.20	236.76	237.81	---	---	---	---
9	236.20	236.36	236.32	235.12	235.70	236.20	236.80	237.83	---	---	---	---
10	236.21	236.36	236.32	235.18	235.80	236.20	236.83	237.88	---	---	---	---
11	236.21	236.36	236.32	235.22	235.87	236.20	236.87	235.69	---	---	---	---
12	236.22	236.36	236.32	235.25	235.90	236.20	236.90	234.13	---	---	---	---
13	236.23	236.36	236.32	235.30	235.92	236.20	236.94	---	---	---	---	---
14	236.24	236.36	236.32	235.37	236.00	236.20	236.97	---	---	---	---	---
15	236.25	236.36	236.32	235.48	236.09	236.20	237.01	---	---	---	---	---
16	236.25	236.36	236.32	235.54	236.11	236.20	237.04	---	---	---	---	---
17	236.26	236.36	236.32	235.61	236.19	236.20	237.08	---	---	---	---	---
18	236.27	236.36	236.32	235.65	236.19	236.20	237.11	---	---	---	---	---
19	236.28	236.36	236.32	235.67	236.19	236.20	237.15	---	---	---	---	---
20	236.29	236.36	236.32	235.71	236.19	236.20	237.17	---	---	---	---	---
21	236.29	236.36	236.31	235.86	236.20	236.20	237.02	---	---	---	---	---
22	236.30	236.36	236.10	235.91	236.20	236.20	237.03	---	---	---	---	---
23	236.31	236.36	235.98	236.00	236.20	236.20	237.06	---	---	---	---	---
24	236.32	236.36	235.89	236.09	236.20	236.24	237.08	---	---	---	---	---
25	236.33	236.36	235.88	236.11	236.20	236.27	237.13	---	---	---	---	---
26	236.34	236.36	235.83	236.19	236.20	236.31	237.16	---	---	---	---	---
27	236.34	236.36	235.81	236.19	236.20	236.34	237.22	---	---	---	---	---
28	236.35	236.36	235.72	236.19	236.20	236.38	237.32	---	---	---	---	---
29	236.35	236.32	235.72	236.20	236.20	236.41	237.38	---	---	---	---	---
30	236.35	236.30	235.82	236.20	---	236.45	237.52	---	---	---	---	---
31	236.35	---	235.74	236.20	---	236.48	---	---	---	---	---	---
LOW	236.35	236.36	236.32	236.20	236.20	236.48	237.52	---	---	---	---	---
HIGH	236.13	236.30	235.72	235.08	235.59	236.20	236.52	---	---	---	---	---

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182634066262500. Local number, 209.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'34", long 66°26'25".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Coto Norte No. 3.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon-Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-495 ft (0-150.9 m), perforated 255-455 ft (77.7-138.7 m). Depth 495 FT (150.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 99.0 ft (30.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.30 ft (0.70 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to October 30, 1987, discontinued.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 71.50 ft (21.79 m) below land-surface datum, July 23, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 81.96 ft (24.98 m) below land-surface datum, June 24, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	80.92	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
3	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
4	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
5	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
6	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
7	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
8	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
9	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
10	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
11	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
12	80.94	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
13	80.96	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
14	80.96	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
15	80.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
16	80.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
17	80.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
18	80.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
19	80.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
20	80.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
21	80.97	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
22	80.85	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
23	80.80	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
24	80.75	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
25	80.74	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
26	80.72	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
27	80.72	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
28	80.71	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
29	80.70	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GRANDE DE MANATI BASIN

182308066260400. Local number, 210.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°23'08", long 66°26'04".

Owner: Gelo Martinez.

Name: Gelo Martinez well.

AQUIFER.--Lares Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 574 ft (174.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 40.56 ft (12.36 m) below land-surface datum, May 22, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 67.67 ft (20.62 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 6, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	57.52	62.34	57.07	49.65	49.76	53.35	58.91	49.26	49.52	50.03	65.04	50.07
2	57.74	62.39	57.33	49.00	49.33	53.66	58.90	49.33	49.50	50.07	65.14	50.88
3	58.13	62.44	58.51	48.59	49.04	53.90	58.96	49.39	49.47	50.10	65.24	52.70
4	58.42	62.50	59.39	48.79	49.05	54.10	59.11	49.45	49.46	50.15	65.30	54.64
5	58.56	62.54	60.08	49.02	49.05	54.26	59.33	49.47	49.45	50.25	65.33	56.65
6	58.73	62.61	60.75	49.29	49.15	54.35	59.58	49.50	49.45	50.49	65.41	58.54
7	58.98	62.67	61.39	49.49	49.39	54.50	59.97	49.52	49.46	51.55	65.48	59.67
8	59.34	62.72	61.86	49.64	49.62	54.67	60.40	49.55	49.52	---	65.44	60.49
9	59.82	62.77	62.12	49.71	49.77	54.82	60.96	49.56	49.58	---	65.49	61.35
10	60.14	62.83	62.28	49.82	49.91	54.99	61.57	49.57	49.66	---	65.55	61.74
11	60.39	62.98	62.36	49.97	50.06	55.22	62.08	49.51	49.69	---	65.58	60.10
12	60.64	63.29	62.44	50.12	50.16	55.49	62.32	48.97	49.71	---	65.63	55.43
13	60.86	63.59	62.54	50.27	50.28	55.74	62.43	49.03	49.69	---	65.68	50.18
14	61.06	63.77	62.60	50.40	50.42	56.02	62.44	49.11	49.69	---	65.73	49.94
15	61.18	63.96	62.66	50.48	50.54	56.34	62.43	49.19	49.69	---	65.78	50.06
16	61.27	64.08	62.72	50.65	50.70	56.66	62.14	49.29	49.71	---	65.81	50.35
17	61.49	64.22	62.81	50.88	50.86	56.96	53.00	49.34	49.71	---	65.87	50.55
18	61.59	64.25	62.91	51.16	51.04	57.15	48.77	49.38	49.75	---	65.90	50.35
19	61.55	64.23	63.11	51.38	51.20	57.31	48.11	49.44	49.79	---	65.88	50.24
20	61.50	64.12	63.20	51.57	51.34	57.48	48.19	49.46	49.85	---	65.83	50.39
21	61.46	64.10	62.13	51.69	51.53	57.67	48.03	49.47	49.86	---	65.79	50.55
22	61.46	64.14	49.92	51.82	51.74	57.82	48.03	49.49	49.90	---	65.77	50.44
23	61.38	64.21	49.21	52.00	51.88	57.95	48.06	49.52	49.91	---	65.76	50.72
24	61.34	64.30	49.26	52.18	52.09	58.13	48.13	49.48	49.90	---	65.71	51.93
25	61.31	64.35	49.51	52.36	52.28	58.32	48.18	49.47	49.90	---	65.98	53.34
26	61.36	64.36	49.60	52.54	52.51	58.58	48.32	49.47	49.93	---	52.72	54.97
27	61.50	64.30	49.44	52.72	52.81	58.75	48.60	49.49	49.96	---	49.15	56.23
28	61.71	63.54	49.33	52.84	53.00	58.82	48.91	49.49	49.99	64.32	49.06	57.34
29	61.96	62.12	49.50	52.99	53.17	58.87	49.08	49.50	49.98	64.57	49.27	58.26
30	62.15	58.77	49.79	53.11	---	58.90	49.16	49.50	49.98	64.79	49.53	58.92
31	62.24	---	49.92	50.15	---	58.89	---	49.52	---	64.92	49.80	---
LOW	62.24	64.36	63.20	53.11	53.17	58.90	62.44	49.57	49.99	---	65.90	61.74
HIGH	57.52	58.77	49.21	48.59	49.04	53.35	48.03	48.97	49.45	---	49.06	49.94

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182647066201700. Local number, 70.

LOCATION.--Lat 18 26'47", long 66°20'17".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Sabana Hoyos.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused artesian well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 0-90 ft (0-27.43 m), perforated. Depth 90 ft (27.43 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 49 ft (14.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of casing wooden cover, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1960 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 21.33 ft (6.50 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 26, 1976; lowest water level recorded, 31.10 ft (9.48 m) below land-surface datum, July 31, 1975.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	27.21	27.32	27.07	26.89	27.14	27.30	27.90	27.42	26.69	27.21	27.54	26.71
2	27.22	27.34	27.05	26.86	27.12	27.33	27.92	27.44	26.71	27.23	27.55	26.73
3	27.23	27.36	27.06	26.81	27.08	27.35	27.93	27.46	26.74	27.24	27.56	26.74
4	27.24	27.38	27.07	26.78	27.05	27.38	27.94	27.49	26.77	27.25	27.52	26.76
5	27.24	27.39	27.09	26.76	27.02	27.40	27.95	27.51	26.79	27.25	27.52	26.78
6	27.27	27.42	27.10	26.76	27.01	27.42	27.97	27.53	26.82	27.26	27.51	26.80
7	27.28	27.44	27.11	26.75	27.00	27.45	27.98	27.55	26.84	27.26	27.50	26.82
8	27.30	27.46	27.12	26.76	27.01	27.46	27.99	27.57	26.87	27.28	27.50	26.84
9	27.31	27.48	27.13	26.77	27.01	27.49	28.01	27.59	26.89	27.29	27.50	26.84
10	27.30	27.49	27.14	26.78	27.03	27.51	28.02	27.51	26.91	27.31	27.49	26.78
11	27.32	27.51	27.14	26.79	27.05	27.54	28.03	26.82	26.94	27.31	27.49	26.74
12	27.33	27.53	27.16	26.80	27.06	27.56	28.05	26.50	26.95	27.33	27.49	26.67
13	27.32	27.55	27.18	26.82	27.08	27.57	28.07	26.40	26.97	27.34	27.50	26.62
14	27.35	27.57	27.20	26.83	27.10	27.59	28.08	26.36	26.99	27.35	27.51	26.59
15	27.36	27.58	27.18	26.85	27.11	27.61	28.09	26.34	27.01	27.38	27.51	26.58
16	27.36	27.60	27.15	26.87	27.13	27.63	27.96	26.34	27.03	27.40	27.52	26.58
17	27.38	27.59	27.13	26.89	27.14	27.66	27.88	26.34	27.05	27.41	27.52	26.59
18	27.38	27.56	27.13	26.91	---	27.68	27.72	26.36	27.07	27.43	27.52	26.59
19	27.38	27.54	27.15	26.93	---	27.71	27.57	26.38	27.10	27.44	27.49	26.60
20	27.37	27.53	27.15	26.94	27.15	27.74	27.48	26.41	27.11	27.46	27.49	26.62
21	27.31	27.52	27.09	26.96	27.17	27.75	27.41	26.43	27.12	27.47	27.49	26.62
22	27.22	27.52	27.03	26.98	27.18	27.77	27.39	26.46	27.13	27.48	27.49	26.64
23	27.20	27.53	26.99	27.00	27.20	27.79	27.37	26.48	27.12	27.50	27.48	26.64
24	27.22	27.53	26.97	27.02	27.21	27.81	27.36	26.51	27.14	27.51	27.46	26.65
25	27.21	27.50	26.95	27.04	27.23	27.83	27.36	26.53	27.15	27.52	27.18	26.66
26	27.23	27.43	26.93	27.06	27.24	27.86	27.37	26.55	27.16	27.54	27.04	26.68
27	27.25	27.40	26.90	27.08	27.26	27.87	27.38	26.58	27.17	27.55	26.94	26.70
28	27.26	27.33	26.89	27.10	27.26	27.88	27.38	26.61	27.18	27.56	26.81	26.72
29	27.26	27.19	26.88	27.12	27.28	27.88	27.39	26.62	27.19	27.57	26.75	26.73
30	27.28	27.10	26.88	27.13	---	27.89	27.41	26.64	27.19	27.54	26.72	26.74
31	27.31	---	26.89	27.15	---	27.89	---	26.66	---	27.52	26.71	---
LOW	27.38	27.60	27.20	27.15	---	27.89	28.09	27.59	27.19	27.57	27.56	26.84
HIGH	27.20	27.10	26.88	26.75	---	27.30	27.36	26.34	26.69	27.21	26.71	26.58

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182615066235300. Local number, 211.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'15", long 66°23'53".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Rosario No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 14 in (0.36 m) 0-200 ft (0-61.0 m), diameter 12 in (0.30 m) 200-250 ft (61.0-76.2 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-250 ft (0-76.2 m), perforated 210-250 ft (64.0-76.2 m), diameter 10 in (0.25 m) 250-270 ft (76.2-82.3 m), open hole; concrete sealed 0-200 ft (0-61.0 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 215 ft (65.5 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.15 ft (0.35 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 191.29 ft (58.30 m) below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 193.10 ft (58.86 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 21, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	192.37	192.47	192.44	192.38	192.62	---	192.96	192.51	192.23	192.47	192.66	192.46
2	192.38	192.50	192.46	192.31	192.62	---	192.96	192.54	192.25	192.47	192.66	192.45
3	192.39	192.51	192.51	192.27	192.62	---	192.96	192.55	192.27	192.48	192.66	192.45
4	192.39	192.56	192.53	192.26	192.58	---	192.96	192.57	192.28	192.48	192.66	192.45
5	192.40	192.58	192.56	192.27	192.55	---	192.96	192.58	192.31	192.48	192.66	192.45
6	192.40	192.60	192.56	192.27	192.50	---	192.96	192.64	192.33	192.48	192.65	192.45
7	192.41	192.63	192.56	192.27	192.50	---	192.95	192.64	192.33	192.48	192.65	192.48
8	192.42	192.64	192.56	192.27	192.50	---	192.95	192.64	192.33	192.50	192.62	192.48
9	192.42	192.66	192.57	192.27	192.50	---	192.94	192.63	192.33	192.50	192.73	192.48
10	192.43	192.71	192.57	192.29	192.50	---	192.94	192.60	192.33	192.49	192.73	192.48
11	192.43	192.71	192.57	192.29	192.50	---	192.94	192.00	192.35	192.51	192.73	192.47
12	192.44	192.71	192.58	192.30	192.50	---	192.94	191.60	192.37	192.51	192.73	192.41
13	192.45	192.71	192.58	192.31	192.50	---	192.93	191.50	192.37	192.51	192.73	192.35
14	192.45	192.71	192.58	192.36	192.50	---	192.93	191.49	192.38	192.53	192.72	192.35
15	192.46	192.71	192.59	192.40	192.50	---	192.91	191.55	192.40	192.54	192.72	192.35
16	192.46	192.71	192.59	192.43	192.52	---	192.75	191.66	192.41	192.54	192.72	192.35
17	192.47	192.71	192.58	192.45	192.52	---	192.59	191.72	192.41	192.58	192.72	192.35
18	192.48	192.71	192.56	192.46	192.54	---	192.51	191.79	192.42	192.58	192.72	192.35
19	192.48	192.69	192.56	192.46	192.54	---	192.44	191.87	192.46	192.58	192.72	192.34
20	192.49	192.68	192.56	192.48	192.59	---	192.40	191.93	192.47	192.58	192.72	192.34
21	192.49	192.65	192.52	192.50	192.64	---	192.34	191.99	192.48	192.61	192.72	192.34
22	192.40	192.63	192.48	192.51	---	---	192.30	192.04	192.43	192.64	192.72	192.34
23	192.39	192.62	192.44	192.51	---	192.93	192.30	192.08	192.48	192.66	192.72	192.34
24	192.39	192.62	192.42	192.51	---	192.98	192.31	192.12	192.49	192.68	192.71	192.34
25	192.40	192.62	192.42	192.51	---	192.97	192.37	192.14	192.49	192.68	192.63	192.34
26	192.41	192.62	192.43	192.51	---	192.98	192.38	192.15	192.49	192.67	192.51	192.33
27	192.41	192.62	192.42	192.54	---	192.98	192.40	192.20	192.49	192.67	192.49	192.33
28	192.41	192.55	192.41	192.58	---	192.98	192.40	192.23	192.48	192.67	192.48	192.33
29	192.43	192.48	192.41	192.59	---	192.98	192.44	192.24	192.47	192.67	192.47	192.33
30	192.45	192.47	192.41	192.60	---	192.97	192.48	192.24	192.47	192.67	192.46	192.33
31	192.46	---	192.40	192.62	---	192.96	---	192.24	---	192.67	192.46	---
LOW	192.49	192.71	192.59	192.62	---	---	192.96	192.64	192.49	192.68	192.73	192.48
HIGH	192.37	192.47	192.40	192.26	---	---	192.30	191.49	192.23	192.47	192.46	192.33

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182515066194000. Local number, 212.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'15", long 66°19'40".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey.

Name: Ponderosa TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone-Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-136 ft (0-41.1 m), perforated 121-131 ft (36.9-39.9 m); bentonite packed 0.5-121 ft (0.15-36.9 m).
Depth 136 ft (39.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 98.0 ft (29.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 63.05 ft (19.22 m) below land-surface datum, July 15, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 74.63 ft (22.75 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 27, 28, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	66.42	66.87	66.81	66.35	66.59	66.95	68.01	67.39	67.30	68.50	67.06	65.74
2	66.44	66.90	66.61	66.28	66.58	67.00	68.02	67.36	67.41	68.55	67.08	65.83
3	66.47	66.93	66.46	66.22	66.56	67.05	68.04	67.35	67.52	68.58	67.09	65.80
4	66.51	67.00	66.35	66.16	66.53	67.09	68.06	67.36	67.62	68.62	67.10	65.78
5	66.54	67.05	66.27	66.10	66.49	67.14	68.09	67.38	67.71	68.66	67.09	65.77
6	66.57	67.11	66.24	66.06	66.46	67.16	68.20	67.39	67.66	68.69	67.07	65.77
7	66.60	67.15	66.20	66.03	66.43	67.19	68.20	67.40	67.71	68.74	67.08	65.78
8	66.64	67.18	66.17	65.99	66.41	67.22	68.20	67.42	67.76	68.76	67.08	65.81
9	66.69	67.21	66.25	65.98	66.40	67.23	68.23	67.47	67.88	68.82	67.11	65.84
10	66.71	67.25	66.33	65.97	66.40	67.26	68.25	67.97	67.90	68.85	67.10	65.83
11	66.73	67.29	66.41	65.96	66.40	67.31	68.27	68.50	67.99	68.89	67.11	65.82
12	66.77	67.33	66.48	65.96	66.40	67.35	68.61	67.79	68.06	68.91	67.13	65.74
13	66.80	67.37	66.56	65.98	66.40	67.38	68.42	66.00	68.15	68.94	67.15	65.67
14	66.85	67.42	66.63	66.00	66.42	67.40	68.41	65.35	67.61	68.97	67.16	65.61
15	66.91	67.46	66.82	66.04	66.45	67.44	68.43	65.08	66.76	67.84	67.18	65.59
16	66.93	67.50	66.80	66.07	66.48	67.48	68.30	64.90	66.34	67.31	67.20	65.57
17	66.98	67.55	66.80	66.11	66.51	67.54	68.10	64.78	66.21	67.15	67.21	65.54
18	67.01	67.55	66.83	66.13	66.53	67.60	67.94	64.70	66.16	67.08	67.22	65.51
19	67.05	67.54	66.87	66.18	66.55	67.67	67.76	64.66	66.13	67.04	67.22	65.50
20	67.07	67.49	66.89	66.21	66.58	67.71	67.62	64.62	66.11	67.01	67.23	65.53
21	67.07	67.47	66.87	66.25	66.64	67.74	67.51	64.60	67.28	66.98	67.24	65.48
22	66.93	67.46	66.83	66.29	66.67	67.79	67.42	64.58	67.86	66.96	67.25	65.46
23	66.85	67.46	66.80	66.33	66.70	67.80	67.36	64.68	67.94	66.96	67.24	65.45
24	66.80	67.46	66.76	66.36	66.73	67.84	67.32	64.62	68.08	66.96	67.23	65.44
25	66.75	67.47	66.73	66.40	66.75	67.87	67.28	64.62	68.17	66.96	67.00	65.44
26	66.73	67.46	66.69	66.45	66.79	67.92	67.24	64.62	68.23	66.97	66.77	65.44
27	66.74	67.45	66.62	66.49	66.83	67.95	67.26	66.00	68.29	66.99	66.61	65.44
28	66.74	67.40	66.55	66.52	66.86	67.97	67.22	66.64	68.35	67.00	66.30	65.46
29	66.77	67.26	66.47	66.52	66.91	67.98	67.20	66.87	68.39	67.13	66.08	65.48
30	66.80	67.01	66.43	66.53	---	67.98	67.78	67.03	68.45	67.04	65.91	65.51
31	66.82	---	66.40	66.55	---	68.00	---	67.17	---	67.05	65.81	---
LOW	67.07	67.55	66.89	66.55	66.91	68.00	68.61	68.50	68.45	68.97	67.25	65.84
HIGH	66.42	66.87	66.17	65.96	66.40	66.95	67.20	64.58	66.11	66.96	65.81	65.44

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 66.92 LOW 68.97 HIGH 64.58

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CIBUCO BASIN

182330066185700. Local number, 213.

LOCATION.--Lat 18° 23' 30", long 66° 18' 57".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Pampano No. 2.

AQUIFER.--Rio Indio Limestone-Lares Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-130 ft (0-39.6 m), diameter 14 in (0.36 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-220 ft (0-67.1 m); open hole 220-330 ft (67.6-100.6 m). Depth 330 ft (100.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 394 ft (120 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 2.95 ft (0.90 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 34.40 ft (10.50 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 6, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 49.55 ft (15.10 m) below land-surface datum, May 1, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	40.96	42.85	43.19	41.93	40.34	40.75	42.92	40.44	37.47	---	43.39	42.95
2	41.01	42.68	43.16	41.38	40.30	40.85	42.95	40.27	37.55	---	43.44	42.76
3	41.22	42.56	43.10	41.18	40.15	40.98	43.03	40.20	37.66	---	---	42.70
4	41.17	42.58	43.06	40.87	40.05	41.07	43.08	40.38	37.85	---	---	42.65
5	41.15	42.61	43.03	40.61	39.92	41.12	43.07	40.41	37.98	---	---	42.62
6	41.30	42.66	43.03	40.44	39.80	41.13	43.07	40.45	38.07	---	43.74	42.62
7	41.40	42.67	42.98	40.20	39.74	41.23	43.07	40.45	38.16	---	43.83	42.63
8	41.47	43.24	42.97	40.05	39.65	41.35	43.12	40.51	38.27	---	43.89	42.68
9	41.56	43.42	42.94	39.92	39.56	41.37	43.22	40.58	38.44	---	43.97	42.16
10	41.76	43.52	42.92	39.85	39.54	41.39	43.29	40.59	38.57	---	44.02	42.62
11	41.80	43.62	42.93	39.76	39.53	41.51	43.37	40.18	38.62	---	44.06	42.58
12	41.86	43.68	42.94	39.45	39.56	41.63	43.46	39.51	38.71	---	44.12	42.24
13	42.00	43.80	43.05	39.53	39.53	41.68	43.35	38.97	38.85	---	44.15	41.86
14	42.12	43.89	43.09	39.48	39.59	41.65	43.55	38.49	39.02	---	44.19	41.62
15	42.13	43.97	43.16	39.48	39.63	41.77	43.58	38.08	39.10	---	44.20	41.45
16	42.11	44.03	43.18	39.48	39.68	41.93	43.18	37.80	39.20	---	44.31	41.27
17	42.23	44.11	43.17	39.52	39.76	42.06	42.82	37.58	39.35	---	44.29	41.14
18	42.39	43.99	43.24	39.51	39.74	42.13	42.48	37.38	39.53	---	44.32	40.99
19	42.41	44.10	43.39	39.57	39.80	42.16	42.22	37.22	39.62	42.20	44.36	40.88
20	42.52	44.05	43.44	39.61	39.90	42.11	41.99	37.07	39.76	42.31	44.40	40.82
21	42.58	44.05	43.25	39.72	39.96	41.91	41.66	36.98	39.81	42.37	44.44	40.21
22	42.56	44.09	43.04	39.78	40.07	42.07	41.42	37.01	39.69	42.47	44.48	40.11
23	42.52	44.04	42.90	39.82	40.07	41.88	41.22	36.99	39.95	42.61	44.51	39.74
24	42.58	44.08	42.80	39.91	40.12	42.19	41.00	36.98	40.09	42.69	44.44	39.53
25	42.63	44.04	42.68	39.95	40.17	42.39	40.80	36.96	40.09	42.79	44.19	39.36
26	42.52	43.91	42.54	39.72	40.22	42.52	40.64	37.00	40.31	42.90	43.72	39.19
27	42.58	43.83	42.40	39.93	40.35	42.59	40.57	37.09	40.43	42.99	43.66	38.85
28	42.57	43.67	42.26	39.96	40.51	42.64	40.47	37.19	40.61	43.07	43.47	38.55
29	42.62	43.34	42.16	40.07	40.66	42.75	40.47	37.27	---	43.15	43.22	38.71
30	42.65	43.13	42.14	40.18	---	42.78	40.44	37.32	---	43.27	43.00	38.70
31	42.73	---	42.15	40.26	---	42.85	---	37.22	---	43.33	42.98	---
LOW	42.73	44.11	43.44	41.93	40.66	42.85	43.58	40.59	---	---	---	42.95
HIGH	40.96	42.56	42.14	39.45	39.53	40.75	40.44	36.96	---	---	---	38.55

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182746066170800. Local number, 214.

LOCATION.--Lat 18 27'46", long 66 17'08".

Owner: Dorado Beach Hotel.

Name: Dorado Beach No. 7.

AQUIFER.--Aymamon Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 18 in (0.46 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 39.0 ft (11.9 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.10 ft (0.34 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.-- November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 18.23 ft (5.56 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 16, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 20.31 ft (6.19 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 8, 1987.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	19.60	19.63	19.34	19.25	19.37	19.77	19.90	19.79	19.57	19.72	19.69	19.19
2	19.55	19.57	19.35	19.21	19.38	19.81	19.96	19.80	19.58	19.68	19.74	19.32
3	19.51	19.52	19.40	19.21	19.36	19.82	19.99	19.79	19.59	19.63	19.75	19.39
4	19.42	19.50	19.42	19.22	19.37	19.80	19.98	19.81	19.59	19.65	19.71	19.43
5	19.36	19.51	19.42	19.23	19.38	19.73	19.97	19.85	19.65	19.70	19.76	19.46
6	19.31	19.56	19.40	19.29	19.42	19.73	19.95	19.82	19.65	19.74	19.80	19.42
7	19.30	19.60	19.46	19.29	19.45	19.75	19.95	19.79	19.65	19.79	19.84	19.37
8	19.30	19.66	19.50	19.32	19.48	19.74	19.91	19.80	19.63	19.88	19.78	19.33
9	19.37	19.68	19.51	19.29	19.48	19.71	19.94	19.83	19.69	19.94	19.72	19.21
10	19.46	19.73	19.46	19.33	19.48	19.75	19.95	19.80	19.74	19.93	19.65	19.00
11	19.51	19.71	19.48	19.31	19.45	19.81	19.95	19.56	19.76	19.93	19.61	19.07
12	19.54	19.74	19.50	19.34	19.43	19.88	19.96	19.45	19.73	19.93	19.61	18.84
13	19.54	19.80	19.57	19.33	19.42	19.92	19.94	19.46	19.73	19.92	19.61	18.82
14	19.54	19.78	19.62	19.31	19.46	19.98	19.98	19.46	19.74	19.89	19.62	18.97
15	19.60	19.74	19.60	19.31	19.52	20.01	19.94	19.43	19.73	19.89	19.64	19.06
16	19.58	19.73	19.52	19.28	19.53	---	19.81	19.43	19.71	19.85	19.66	19.09
17	19.55	19.67	19.43	19.23	19.52	---	19.79	19.40	19.73	19.83	19.64	19.19
18	19.54	19.63	19.39	19.22	19.53	---	19.74	19.44	19.74	19.82	19.59	19.24
19	19.48	19.60	19.40	19.20	19.54	---	19.72	19.49	19.76	19.85	19.58	19.26
20	19.43	19.51	19.48	19.25	19.47	---	19.70	19.51	19.79	19.89	19.64	19.27
21	19.37	19.46	19.42	19.29	19.45	---	19.66	19.54	19.77	19.92	19.69	19.29
22	19.40	19.49	19.39	19.46	19.48	20.02	19.65	19.55	19.72	19.92	19.71	19.17
23	19.45	19.54	19.34	19.46	19.53	20.03	19.67	19.55	19.71	19.96	19.66	19.10
24	19.47	19.62	19.36	19.43	19.54	20.01	19.71	19.58	19.72	19.95	19.51	19.14
25	19.48	19.41	19.40	19.45	19.58	20.00	19.73	19.60	19.73	19.97	19.12	19.14
26	19.51	19.49	19.39	19.45	19.70	19.97	19.72	19.59	19.79	19.95	19.08	19.08
27	19.55	19.48	19.36	19.40	19.76	19.93	19.73	19.64	19.75	19.92	19.03	19.05
28	19.57	19.03	19.35	19.30	19.78	19.90	19.72	19.64	19.76	19.86	19.04	19.11
29	19.62	19.18	19.29	19.30	19.78	19.85	19.75	19.62	19.77	19.80	19.06	19.12
30	19.66	19.27	19.29	19.30	---	19.84	19.78	19.62	19.77	19.72	19.09	19.14
31	19.66	---	19.29	19.35	---	19.90	---	19.59	---	19.66	19.14	---
LOW	19.66	19.80	19.62	19.46	19.78	---	19.99	19.85	19.79	19.97	19.84	19.46
HIGH	19.30	19.03	19.29	19.20	19.36	---	19.65	19.40	19.57	19.63	19.03	18.82

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182530066135400. Local number, 216.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'30", long 66°13'54".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Pozo Navy-Campanillas.

AQUIFER.--Aguada Limestone.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m) 0-106 ft (0-32.3 m), cased 16 in (0.41 m) 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), cased 12 in (0.30 m) 0-106 ft (0-32.3 m), perforated 20-106 ft (6.10-32.3 m), diameter 10 in (0.25 m) 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m), perforated 106-140 ft (32.3-42.7 m). Depth 140 ft (42.7 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 13.0 ft (3.96 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.38 ft (2.86 m) below land-surface datum, June 23, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 14.72 ft (4.49 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 28, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12.22	12.81	12.21	11.87	12.24	11.81	12.25	11.57	11.43	11.89	11.96	10.55
2	12.25	12.81	12.28	11.72	12.16	11.80	12.95	11.59	11.43	11.88	11.99	10.57
3	12.29	12.82	12.37	11.80	12.11	11.97	13.08	11.54	11.35	12.20	11.99	10.62
4	12.30	12.86	12.43	11.80	12.06	12.11	13.13	11.54	11.42	12.38	11.78	10.67
5	12.30	12.90	12.48	11.83	12.07	12.17	13.19	11.50	11.59	12.44	11.79	10.70
6	12.36	12.95	12.44	11.84	12.11	12.20	13.24	11.41	11.56	12.29	11.81	10.74
7	12.39	12.98	12.39	11.86	12.09	12.23	13.28	12.13	11.69	12.20	11.83	10.76
8	12.40	13.01	12.30	11.88	12.08	12.27	13.32	12.23	11.75	12.21	11.67	10.78
9	12.44	13.03	12.30	11.89	12.17	12.29	12.88	12.30	11.85	11.78	11.64	10.61
10	12.48	13.05	12.32	11.90	12.23	12.19	12.87	12.01	11.23	11.75	11.62	10.45
11	12.51	13.10	12.36	11.91	12.25	12.09	12.88	10.99	11.61	11.75	11.99	10.29
12	12.54	13.12	12.40	11.91	12.30	12.07	12.91	10.72	11.91	11.78	12.03	10.07
13	12.57	13.16	12.44	11.93	12.28	12.66	12.90	10.54	11.98	11.77	11.82	10.02
14	12.61	13.19	12.48	11.94	12.13	12.47	12.92	10.46	12.03	11.81	12.07	10.07
15	12.65	13.19	12.39	11.98	12.09	12.46	12.49	10.43	12.10	11.85	12.13	10.12
16	12.67	13.21	12.36	12.02	12.24	12.50	12.22	10.31	11.55	11.88	12.18	10.12
17	12.65	13.06	12.38	12.12	12.29	12.44	12.36	10.48	12.07	11.90	12.16	10.15
18	12.65	12.93	12.43	12.11	12.30	12.53	12.23	10.72	12.14	11.87	12.09	10.17
19	12.59	12.90	12.46	12.09	12.33	12.56	12.03	10.81	12.16	11.86	12.07	10.22
20	12.25	12.86	12.42	12.10	12.37	12.60	11.98	10.88	12.18	11.89	11.79	10.26
21	12.50	12.86	12.17	12.12	12.40	12.64	11.47	10.90	11.49	11.92	11.71	10.26
22	12.59	12.89	12.12	12.16	12.42	12.68	11.42	10.98	11.40	11.93	11.71	10.25
23	12.67	12.90	12.07	12.18	12.42	12.70	11.46	11.03	12.05	12.26	11.50	10.27
24	12.74	12.86	12.06	12.21	12.02	12.72	11.27	10.85	12.16	12.43	11.29	10.30
25	12.72	12.48	11.97	12.20	11.99	12.71	11.39	11.06	12.22	12.48	10.67	10.34
26	12.64	12.47	11.93	12.24	11.98	12.70	11.42	11.10	12.23	12.30	10.65	10.37
27	12.64	12.44	11.89	12.28	11.98	12.68	11.45	11.14	12.26	12.13	10.64	10.40
28	12.67	11.97	11.88	12.30	11.99	12.65	11.49	10.74	12.30	12.12	10.55	10.45
29	12.71	12.01	11.88	12.26	11.90	12.61	11.51	10.79	11.98	12.13	10.52	10.50
30	12.90	12.11	11.91	12.27	---	12.34	11.55	10.83	11.89	12.00	10.49	10.49
31	12.82	---	11.94	12.29	---	12.27	---	10.87	---	11.95	10.51	---
LOW	12.90	13.21	12.48	12.30	12.42	12.72	13.32	12.30	12.30	12.48	12.18	10.78
HIGH	12.22	11.97	11.88	11.72	11.90	11.80	11.27	10.31	11.23	11.75	10.49	10.02

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 11.95 LOW 13.32 HIGH 10.02

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO DE LA PLATA BASIN

182655066142400. Local number, 217.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'55", long 66°14'24".
 Owner: U.S. Geological Survey.
 Name: Monserrate TW-2.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvial Deposits.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) 0-80 ft (0-24.4 m), perforated 10-80 ft (3.05-24.4 m). Depth 80 ft (24.4 m).
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 3.30 ft (1.00 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.50 ft (1.07 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1985 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 0.02 ft (0.006 m) below land-surface datum, May 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 1.92 ft (0.58 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 12, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	1.16	1.15	.67	.61	1.00	1.06	1.34	.95	.96	1.25	1.25	.45
2	1.13	1.13	.77	.53	.92	1.08	1.42	.98	.97	1.22	1.28	.54
3	1.12	1.12	.90	.54	.83	1.14	1.47	.97	1.02	1.18	1.31	.59
4	1.08	1.17	.94	.57	.79	1.21	1.48	.99	1.04	1.23	1.15	.65
5	1.04	1.21	.99	.61	.79	1.24	1.47	1.04	1.10	1.27	1.17	.70
6	1.04	1.26	.89	.67	.83	1.25	1.46	1.00	1.13	1.27	1.15	.70
7	1.06	1.29	.92	.69	.86	1.25	1.47	1.04	1.13	1.20	1.19	.71
8	1.07	1.32	.90	.70	.87	1.27	1.46	1.05	1.13	1.21	1.05	.67
9	1.12	1.35	.85	.68	.88	1.29	1.45	1.09	1.19	1.22	1.04	.55
10	1.14	1.35	.85	.70	.90	1.29	1.46	1.05	1.22	1.21	1.01	.32
11	1.17	1.36	.88	.70	.94	1.23	1.47	.46	1.22	1.22	1.00	.29
12	1.19	1.35	.88	.70	.99	1.22	1.48	.34	1.25	1.22	1.03	.08
13	1.19	1.38	.93	.73	1.00	1.25	1.47	.35	1.27	1.25	1.01	.02
14	1.20	1.38	.97	.72	1.01	1.34	1.49	.35	1.30	1.25	1.06	.15
15	1.23	1.35	.94	.76	1.02	1.32	1.28	.35	1.26	1.28	1.09	.24
16	1.22	1.35	.88	.78	1.04	1.35	.77	.38	1.26	1.28	1.12	.28
17	1.17	1.30	.84	.79	1.03	1.37	.78	.43	1.25	1.27	1.11	.35
18	1.16	1.21	.85	.80	1.01	1.39	.77	.49	1.29	1.25	1.02	.38
19	1.11	1.19	.90	.77	1.00	1.43	.69	.58	1.31	1.25	.98	.42
20	.99	1.14	.94	.81	1.00	1.48	.71	.63	1.33	1.29	1.03	.45
21	1.02	1.11	.78	.85	1.05	1.50	.69	.66	1.28	1.32	1.05	.42
22	1.07	1.13	.73	.87	1.05	1.51	.70	.71	1.19	1.34	1.07	.30
23	1.14	1.18	.65	.87	1.05	1.51	.73	.84	1.16	1.38	.88	.29
24	1.19	1.21	.67	.87	1.03	1.51	.80	.82	1.18	1.41	.74	.30
25	1.17	.88	.67	.89	1.04	1.48	.80	.84	1.19	1.45	.16	.33
26	1.07	.87	.65	.94	1.02	1.46	.81	.84	1.23	1.47	.21	.40
27	1.10	.84	.58	.97	1.01	1.44	.83	.88	1.21	1.42	.22	.43
28	1.11	.19	.59	1.00	1.03	1.41	.86	.91	1.24	1.39	.25	.50
29	1.13	.38	.59	1.01	1.08	1.37	.88	.91	1.24	1.39	.30	.55
30	1.16	.51	.60	1.00	---	1.34	.92	.91	1.24	1.30	.32	.58
31	1.16	---	.65	1.03	---	1.34	---	.91	---	1.24	.38	---
LOW	1.23	1.38	.99	1.03	1.08	1.51	1.49	1.09	1.33	1.47	1.31	.71
HIGH	.99	.19	.58	.53	.79	1.06	.69	.34	.96	1.18	.16	.02

WTR YR 1988 MEAN .98 LOW 1.51 HIGH .02

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

18262306611000. Local number, 218.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°26'23", long 66°11'10".
 Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.
 Name: Levittown No. 7.
 AQUIFER.--Alluvial deposits-Aymamon Limestone.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well.
 DATUM.--Elevation of land surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Hole on pump base, 1.55 ft (0.47 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 6.13 ft (1.87m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 22, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 9.77 ft (2.98 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 23, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	7.58	7.65	7.46	6.90	7.20	7.47	7.85	6.92	7.22	8.15	7.77	6.59
2	7.56	7.64	7.51	6.91	7.19	7.48	7.86	6.96	7.23	8.14	7.80	6.71
3	7.60	7.63	7.58	6.90	7.15	7.54	7.85	6.97	7.27	8.36	7.80	6.77
4	7.56	7.64	7.49	6.89	7.15	7.60	7.84	6.96	7.28	8.41	7.73	6.70
5	7.54	7.66	7.49	6.90	7.15	7.61	7.87	7.01	7.32	8.38	7.74	6.73
6	7.56	7.67	7.38	6.92	7.17	7.64	7.83	6.97	7.38	8.33	7.79	6.71
7	7.56	7.71	7.39	6.91	7.17	7.63	7.85	6.99	7.44	7.85	7.80	6.71
8	7.53	7.75	7.37	6.93	7.20	7.65	7.83	7.00	7.82	7.83	7.48	6.72
9	7.55	7.81	7.34	6.94	7.18	7.70	7.81	7.07	8.11	7.81	7.55	6.61
10	7.55	7.82	7.30	6.96	7.19	7.69	7.81	6.98	8.17	7.78	7.52	6.52
11	7.56	7.85	7.31	6.94	7.22	7.71	7.82	6.70	8.21	7.77	7.50	6.47
12	7.59	7.86	7.31	6.96	7.25	7.72	7.81	6.61	8.23	7.78	7.49	6.23
13	7.63	7.86	7.34	6.97	7.26	8.39	7.79	6.51	8.25	7.77	7.50	6.16
14	7.63	7.87	7.37	6.98	7.28	7.82	7.79	6.48	8.29	7.77	7.48	6.17
15	7.66	7.86	7.34	6.97	7.28	7.78	7.72	6.43	8.29	7.78	7.50	6.19
16	7.67	7.87	7.31	6.98	7.28	7.81	7.14	6.45	7.97	7.57	7.52	6.21
17	7.65	7.80	7.28	7.04	7.30	7.82	7.07	6.46	7.93	7.53	7.50	6.25
18	7.63	7.75	7.26	7.10	7.31	7.85	7.02	6.49	7.95	7.51	7.41	6.28
19	7.62	7.71	7.28	7.03	7.31	7.88	6.94	6.53	7.97	7.73	7.47	6.32
20	7.53	7.64	7.30	7.03	7.34	7.91	6.92	6.60	7.99	7.78	7.51	6.36
21	7.51	7.60	7.18	7.05	7.37	7.96	6.83	6.68	8.14	7.83	7.53	6.39
22	7.52	7.60	7.11	7.07	7.37	7.98	6.82	7.36	8.13	7.79	7.53	6.37
23	7.56	7.61	7.02	7.09	7.40	8.00	6.82	7.50	8.13	7.87	7.36	6.38
24	7.58	7.67	6.99	7.09	7.42	7.96	6.84	7.02	8.15	7.86	7.25	6.42
25	7.59	7.62	6.99	7.11	7.42	7.97	6.85	7.02	8.16	7.92	6.86	6.43
26	7.45	7.59	6.97	7.14	7.43	7.94	6.84	7.06	8.18	7.90	6.76	6.43
27	7.47	7.53	6.94	7.16	7.40	7.93	6.85	7.15	8.16	7.88	6.68	6.38
28	7.50	7.38	6.92	7.16	7.41	7.91	6.86	7.19	8.17	7.87	6.65	6.50
29	7.54	7.30	6.88	7.15	7.46	7.89	6.87	7.17	8.16	7.85	6.62	6.54
30	7.69	7.39	6.88	7.17	---	7.87	6.90	7.07	8.17	7.79	6.59	6.58
31	7.66	---	6.89	7.20	---	7.86	---	7.18	---	7.77	6.59	---
LOW	7.69	7.87	7.58	7.20	7.46	8.39	7.87	7.50	8.29	8.41	7.80	6.77
HIGH	7.45	7.30	6.88	6.89	7.15	7.47	6.82	6.43	7.22	7.51	6.59	6.16

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 7.37 LOW 8.41 HIGH 6.16

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182441066082600. Local number, 219.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'41", long 66°08'26".

Owner: Department of Defense.

Name: Ft. Buchanan No. 1, Buchanan Park well.

AQUIFER.--Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 10 in (0.25 m), cased 10 in (0.25 m) 0-270 ft (0-82.3 m), perforated 46-685 ft (14.0-20.7 m), 88-120 ft (26.8-36.6 m), 160-191 ft (48.8-58.2 m), 240-270 ft (73.2-82.3 m). Depth 270 ft (82.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 66.0 ft (20.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.75 ft (0.23 m) above land-surface datum. Prior June 30, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.59 ft (1.09 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 38.10 ft (11.61 m) below land-surface datum, June 16, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 43.32 ft (13.20 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 15, 1987.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	41.66	40.10	40.38	39.66	40.60	41.67	42.37	40.32	40.31	40.94	40.87	39.49
2	41.71	40.11	40.38	39.53	40.51	41.74	42.35	40.30	40.35	40.94	40.89	39.47
3	41.73	40.24	40.27	39.48	40.43	41.82	42.33	40.35	40.38	40.94	40.90	39.38
4	41.70	40.39	40.21	39.46	40.31	41.86	42.32	40.44	40.44	40.95	40.89	39.35
5	41.68	40.55	40.24	39.47	40.28	41.86	42.29	40.47	40.49	40.96	40.86	39.34
6	41.71	40.71	40.27	39.50	40.28	41.84	42.26	40.47	40.47	40.93	40.84	39.37
7	41.73	40.81	40.22	39.53	40.31	41.86	42.25	40.48	40.52	40.82	40.85	39.40
8	41.66	40.77	40.08	39.59	40.31	41.90	42.26	40.50	40.56	40.68	40.76	39.50
9	41.56	40.75	39.96	39.64	40.32	41.91	42.29	40.53	40.62	40.58	40.70	39.41
10	41.40	40.77	39.94	39.71	40.45	41.95	42.31	40.56	40.69	40.53	40.61	39.08
11	41.23	40.82	39.99	39.77	40.52	42.01	42.29	40.43	40.68	40.54	40.59	38.84
12	41.12	40.92	40.06	39.81	40.58	42.06	42.33	40.24	40.69	40.52	40.62	38.68
13	41.09	41.07	40.21	39.85	40.60	42.07	42.32	40.12	40.73	40.52	40.66	38.49
14	41.12	41.18	40.30	39.84	40.65	42.06	42.36	40.01	40.78	40.57	40.68	38.43
15	41.03	41.30	40.36	39.86	40.71	42.14	42.33	39.89	40.80	40.66	40.70	38.42
16	40.96	41.41	40.27	39.92	40.78	42.24	42.00	39.83	40.81	40.69	40.73	38.41
17	40.84	41.47	40.27	39.97	40.83	42.32	41.72	39.81	40.84	40.69	40.80	38.40
18	40.69	41.44	40.38	40.00	40.87	42.37	41.49	39.82	40.87	40.69	40.76	38.36
19	40.58	41.34	40.48	40.06	40.96	42.36	41.25	39.85	40.88	40.69	40.77	38.37
20	40.54	41.26	40.46	40.10	41.04	42.39	41.02	39.87	40.90	40.70	40.76	38.44
21	40.54	41.24	40.21	40.15	41.12	42.39	40.82	39.88	40.87	40.70	40.76	38.49
22	40.54	41.22	39.99	40.23	41.20	42.42	40.74	39.90	40.86	40.70	40.78	38.52
23	40.57	41.20	39.86	40.27	41.24	42.44	40.72	39.99	40.87	40.74	40.73	38.56
24	40.55	41.14	39.78	40.32	41.30	42.45	40.68	40.02	40.90	40.73	40.54	38.60
25	40.43	40.89	39.74	40.38	41.36	42.47	40.47	40.03	40.90	40.74	40.28	38.63
26	40.15	40.75	39.69	40.49	41.42	42.47	40.32	40.07	40.92	40.75	40.04	38.65
27	40.04	40.59	39.62	40.55	41.51	42.47	40.29	40.13	40.95	40.80	40.00	38.71
28	40.00	40.46	39.61	40.61	41.56	42.46	40.30	40.16	41.00	40.81	39.87	38.76
29	40.02	40.35	39.57	40.60	41.63	42.46	40.32	40.17	40.96	40.83	39.76	38.81
30	40.02	40.30	39.62	40.60	---	42.42	40.33	40.19	40.93	40.86	39.59	38.83
31	40.07	---	39.71	40.62	---	42.40	---	40.23	---	40.86	39.49	---
LOW	41.73	41.47	40.48	40.62	41.63	42.47	42.37	40.56	41.00	40.96	40.90	39.50
HIGH	40.00	40.10	39.57	39.46	40.28	41.67	40.29	39.81	40.31	40.52	39.49	38.36
WTR YR 1988	MEAN 40.62	LOW 42.47	HIGH 38.36									

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182413066044000. Local number, 220.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'13", long 66°04'40".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: Parque San Luis Rey-Americo Miranda

AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits-Cibao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused artesian well, diameter 10 in (0.25 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m) 0-166 ft (0-50.6 m), perforated 39-166 ft (11.9-50.6 m). Depth 166 ft (50.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 16.4 ft (5.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1986 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +2.99 ft (+0.91 m) above land-surface datum, Feb. 6, May 8-9, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 0.90 ft (0.21 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 16, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.22	+ .23	+1.01	+1.04	+ .96	+ .51	+ .29	+1.09	+ .79	+ .75	+ .56	+1.01
2	.27	+ .20	+1.07	+1.04	+1.06	+ .48	+ .28	+1.09	+ .75	+ .78	+ .53	+ .99
3	.19	+ .16	+1.08	+1.04	+1.09	+ .44	+ .27	+1.06	+ .72	+ .78	+ .52	+ .86
4	.12	+ .16	+1.08	+1.05	+1.11	+ .41	+ .26	+1.02	+ .68	+ .77	+ .55	+ .82
5	.03	+ .11	+1.08	+1.04	+1.11	+ .40	+ .25	+ .98	+ .65	+ .74	+ .53	+ .78
6	.02	+ .05	+1.08	+1.04	+1.11	+ .39	+ .25	+ .95	+ .62	+ .72	+ .50	+ .73
7	.02	+ .01	+1.08	+1.04	+1.11	+ .38	+ .24	+ .92	+ .61	+ .84	+ .47	+ .70
8	.00	.00	+1.09	+1.03	+1.11	+ .35	+ .23	+ .88	+ .57	+ .97	+ .44	+ .66
9	.00	.01	+1.10	+1.03	+1.11	+ .35	+ .19	+ .85	+ .55	+ .98	+ .41	+ .86
10	.01	.04	+1.10	+1.02	+1.08	+ .33	+ .16	+ .97	+ .52	+ .98	+ .39	+1.05
11	.01	.07	+1.10	+1.02	+1.02	+ .31	+ .14	+1.09	+ .52	+ .95	+ .47	+1.11
12	.02	.10	+1.09	+1.00	+ .99	+ .29	+ .11	+1.11	+ .51	+ .94	+ .49	+1.12
13	.05	.08	+1.09	+1.00	+ .96	+ .27	+ .12	+1.11	+ .49	+ .91	+ .48	+1.13
14	.07	.09	+1.07	+1.00	+ .92	+ .27	+ .08	+1.12	+ .46	+ .90	+ .47	+1.13
15	.02	.11	+1.07	+1.00	+ .87	+ .25	+ .25	+1.11	+ .51	+ .88	+ .45	+1.13
16	+ .04	.11	+1.07	+ .97	+ .84	+ .21	+ .59	+1.13	+ .54	+ .85	+ .48	+1.13
17	+ .09	.05	+1.06	+ .94	+ .79	+ .18	+ .75	+1.12	+ .53	+ .81	+ .49	+1.13
18	+ .18	+ .02	+1.05	+ .95	+ .78	+ .15	+ .97	+1.12	+ .53	+ .85	+ .55	+1.13
19	+ .24	+ .02	+1.02	+ .94	+ .75	+ .14	+1.09	+1.11	+ .52	+ .81	+ .55	+1.13
20	+ .24	+ .08	+1.05	+ .94	+ .72	+ .12	+1.09	+1.10	+ .52	+ .79	+ .52	+1.12
21	+ .22	+ .11	+1.05	+ .90	+ .68	+ .09	+1.09	+1.11	+ .57	+ .77	+ .49	+1.12
22	+ .20	+ .11	+1.06	---	+ .65	+ .08	+1.09	+1.09	+ .61	+ .77	+ .49	+1.11
23	+ .18	+ .15	+1.07	---	+ .63	+ .07	+1.08	+1.07	+ .60	+ .76	+ .50	+1.11
24	+ .15	+ .24	+1.07	---	+ .63	+ .05	+1.09	+1.04	+ .61	+ .74	+ .68	+1.11
25	+ .22	+ .43	+1.07	---	+ .63	+ .10	+1.10	+1.01	+ .60	+ .72	+ .87	+1.10
26	+ .30	+ .58	+1.06	---	+ .61	+ .15	+1.10	+ .98	+ .58	+ .70	+ .98	+1.09
27	+ .32	+ .80	+1.06	+ .87	+ .60	+ .15	+1.10	+ .95	+ .57	+ .68	+1.00	+1.05
28	+ .31	+ .98	+1.06	+ .85	+ .57	+ .20	+1.10	+ .91	+ .53	+ .64	+1.02	+1.00
29	+ .28	+1.06	+1.06	+ .91	+ .54	+ .25	+1.10	+ .88	+ .67	+ .62	+1.03	+ .97
30	+ .26	+1.06	+1.04	+ .90	---	+ .28	+1.09	+ .85	+ .73	+ .60	+1.04	+ .94
31	+ .24	---	+1.04	+ .90	---	+ .29	---	+ .82	---	+ .58	+1.02	---
LOW	.27	.11	+1.01	---	+ .54	+ .05	+ .08	+ .82	+ .46	+ .58	+ .39	+ .66
HIGH	+ .32	+1.06	+1.10	---	+1.11	+ .51	+1.10	+1.13	+ .79	+ .98	+1.04	+1.13

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO HONDO TO RIO PUERTO NUEVO BASINS

182436066031200. Local number, 221.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'36", long 66°03'12".

Owner: P.R. Highway Authority

Name: Hyde Park TW-10.

AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits-Cilao Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m) U-107 ft (0-32.36 m), perforated 19-107 ft (5.79-32.6 m). Depth 107 ft (32.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 82.0 ft (25.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.70 ft (0.21 m) above land-surface datum. Prior July 28, 1986, top of shelter floor, 3.14 ft (0.96 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 1.34 ft (0.41 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 16, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 15.59 ft (4.75 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 5, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	11.47	9.30	6.33	6.02	6.71	7.67	7.72	5.35	6.59	6.25	7.55	5.49
2	11.60	9.37	5.44	5.45	6.31	7.72	7.77	5.51	6.68	6.27	7.62	5.60
3	11.46	9.47	4.42	5.34	5.78	7.76	7.84	5.71	6.76	6.44	7.67	5.76
4	10.81	9.47	5.05	5.45	5.59	7.79	7.89	5.83	6.88	6.56	7.63	5.87
5	9.33	9.52	5.48	5.63	5.86	7.82	7.96	5.93	6.95	6.66	7.72	6.00
6	9.18	9.63	4.52	5.81	6.15	7.85	8.02	6.01	7.01	6.78	7.79	6.10
7	9.17	8.30	4.98	5.74	6.38	7.91	8.09	6.13	7.09	5.23	7.84	6.19
8	9.24	9.13	3.58	5.86	6.54	7.96	8.17	6.24	7.21	5.56	7.90	6.30
9	9.28	9.44	4.20	5.99	6.67	7.98	8.26	6.26	7.32	5.72	7.96	5.45
10	9.34	9.67	4.71	6.14	6.80	7.99	8.36	5.11	7.34	5.82	7.99	3.97
11	9.39	9.86	5.15	6.21	6.86	8.05	8.45	4.25	7.38	5.95	7.60	2.29
12	9.46	10.04	5.50	6.28	6.88	8.10	8.52	4.55	7.39	6.09	7.53	3.41
13	9.57	9.54	5.73	6.38	6.85	8.14	8.50	4.88	7.48	6.24	7.61	3.43
14	9.67	8.82	5.86	6.10	6.91	8.18	8.57	5.06	7.53	6.29	7.68	4.25
15	9.72	9.63	6.00	6.24	6.95	8.24	4.43	5.22	7.57	6.44	7.74	4.59
16	9.76	9.99	6.08	6.37	7.04	8.32	2.75	5.20	7.60	6.54	7.82	4.81
17	9.47	10.00	6.22	6.48	7.13	8.37	4.20	5.42	7.66	6.64	7.68	4.96
18	9.00	9.85	6.22	6.55	7.17	8.40	2.97	5.61	7.63	6.71	7.44	5.11
19	8.93	9.81	6.36	6.51	7.25	8.43	4.06	5.74	7.61	6.69	7.47	5.23
20	8.93	9.75	5.92	6.52	7.29	8.48	4.56	5.81	7.60	6.78	7.54	5.26
21	8.96	9.80	4.65	6.57	7.33	8.51	4.86	5.46	7.48	6.89	7.62	5.35
22	8.89	9.92	4.65	6.68	7.36	8.56	5.13	5.56	7.10	6.96	7.67	5.44
23	8.90	10.08	5.02	6.80	7.40	8.62	5.32	5.64	7.07	7.03	7.65	5.53
24	8.90	9.86	5.26	6.90	7.41	8.66	5.45	5.68	7.11	7.09	7.31	5.64
25	8.85	8.49	5.47	6.92	7.43	8.43	4.49	5.76	7.12	7.20	4.85	5.73
26	8.84	7.92	5.62	6.99	7.51	8.41	4.42	5.89	7.21	7.27	5.25	5.83
27	8.85	6.30	5.68	7.04	7.55	8.18	4.22	6.02	7.31	7.34	5.44	5.93
28	8.93	5.72	5.72	7.05	7.58	7.97	4.61	6.09	7.40	7.41	5.48	6.05
29	9.01	5.66	5.84	6.98	7.63	7.93	4.96	6.23	6.58	7.44	4.77	6.11
30	9.12	6.05	5.98	6.91	---	7.73	5.18	6.35	6.19	7.48	5.07	6.21
31	9.19	---	6.09	6.95	---	7.68	---	6.45	---	7.47	5.28	---
LOW	11.60	10.08	6.36	7.05	7.63	8.66	8.57	6.45	7.66	7.48	7.99	6.30
HIGH	8.84	5.66	3.58	5.34	5.59	7.67	2.75	4.25	6.19	5.23	4.77	2.29

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 6.94 LOW 11.60 HIGH 2.29

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO GRANDE DE LOIZA BASIN

182515065594100. Local number, 222.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°25'15", long 65°59'41".
Owner: U.S. Geological Survey.

Name: Campo Rico TW-1.

AQUIFER.--Surficial Deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m). Depth 100 ft (30.5 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10.0 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on side of casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum. Prior July 28, 1986,

top of shelter floor, 3.10 ft (0.94 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--February 1986 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 4.42 ft (1.35 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 31, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 7.42 ft (2.26 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 9, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.91	5.73	5.63	5.49	5.72	5.72	5.89	5.93	5.86	5.79	5.70	5.51
2	5.76	5.76	5.63	5.63	5.50	5.75	6.04	5.94	5.86	5.74	5.81	5.65
3	5.76	5.63	5.65	5.66	5.62	5.97	6.10	5.82	5.83	5.72	5.79	5.85
4	5.68	5.57	5.60	5.65	5.67	6.09	6.09	5.88	5.82	5.76	5.96	5.93
5	5.55	5.53	5.60	5.64	5.71	6.14	6.07	5.92	6.00	5.88	6.13	5.93
6	5.48	5.58	5.53	5.67	5.82	6.10	6.04	5.81	5.99	6.04	6.11	5.86
7	5.48	5.63	5.66	5.69	5.83	5.99	5.98	5.77	6.03	6.07	6.15	5.76
8	5.47	5.78	5.67	5.77	5.87	6.09	5.87	5.77	6.02	6.28	6.10	5.68
9	5.57	5.81	5.74	5.71	5.84	6.12	5.96	5.76	6.13	6.36	5.96	5.35
10	5.71	5.91	5.72	5.78	5.81	6.08	5.89	5.79	6.19	6.28	5.81	5.20
11	5.78	5.90	5.53	5.71	5.80	5.89	5.86	5.79	6.23	6.13	5.72	5.35
12	5.74	5.94	5.77	5.80	5.82	5.89	5.89	5.83	6.11	6.10	5.63	5.19
13	5.76	6.03	5.83	5.75	5.81	5.91	5.85	6.04	6.05	6.02	5.55	5.15
14	5.75	5.96	5.87	5.71	5.77	5.87	5.89	6.06	6.03	5.87	5.53	5.34
15	5.74	5.87	5.88	5.70	5.73	5.82	5.72	5.95	6.02	5.90	5.58	5.41
16	5.78	5.86	5.83	5.60	5.52	5.81	5.60	5.90	5.96	5.88	5.65	5.50
17	5.68	5.81	5.69	5.45	5.69	5.85	5.80	5.85	5.97	5.81	5.59	5.63
18	5.66	5.76	5.57	5.39	5.71	5.99	5.77	5.77	6.00	5.86	5.57	5.74
19	5.65	5.75	5.52	5.32	5.68	6.16	5.81	5.81	6.01	5.89	5.66	5.83
20	5.63	5.54	5.64	5.48	5.79	6.24	5.83	5.85	6.06	6.04	5.75	5.81
21	5.60	5.44	5.64	5.58	5.86	6.29	5.78	5.80	6.04	6.16	5.86	5.89
22	5.61	5.43	5.69	5.71	5.85	6.28	5.78	5.83	5.90	6.16	5.98	5.75
23	5.63	5.53	5.65	5.78	5.86	6.29	5.78	5.86	6.00	6.30	5.96	5.61
24	5.63	5.63	5.73	5.81	5.87	6.30	5.83	5.97	6.05	6.33	5.68	5.52
25	5.65	5.75	5.84	5.83	5.85	6.31	5.90	6.00	6.06	6.34	5.64	5.43
26	5.75	5.78	5.84	5.89	5.71	6.17	5.78	5.98	6.11	6.24	5.48	5.36
27	5.75	5.70	5.84	5.87	5.64	6.08	5.78	6.11	6.10	6.17	5.27	5.36
28	5.75	5.62	5.83	5.81	5.67	5.94	5.77	6.10	6.10	6.04	5.19	5.51
29	5.88	5.64	5.71	5.75	5.72	5.87	5.78	6.04	6.04	5.90	5.26	5.56
30	5.75	5.62	5.60	5.71	---	5.88	5.82	6.01	5.97	5.70	5.29	5.69
31	5.74	---	5.51	5.72	---	5.98	---	5.96	---	5.61	5.35	---
LOW	5.91	6.03	5.88	5.89	5.87	6.31	6.10	6.11	6.23	6.36	6.15	5.93
HIGH	5.47	5.43	5.51	5.32	5.50	5.72	5.60	5.76	5.82	5.61	5.19	5.15

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 5.80 LOW 6.36 HIGH 5.15

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO HUMACAO TO RIO SECO BASINS

175858066100200. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 17 58'58", long 66 10'02".

Owner: Doctor Bruno.

Name: Juana 5.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m). Depth 173 ft (52.74 m) reported, 110 ft (33.54 m) measured.

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 127 ft (38.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum. After Aug. 7, 1981, top of 16 in (0.41 m) casing, 1.55 ft (0.47 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--November 1960 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 26.20 ft (7.99 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 10, 1979; lowest water level recorded, 65.95 ft (20.10 m) below land-surface datum, June 2, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	50.02	52.10	51.03	41.34	40.34	42.19	43.74	47.83	51.27	51.50	53.44	49.86
2	50.09	52.22	50.31	41.26	40.20	42.35	43.81	48.00	51.18	51.44	53.49	49.81
3	50.15	52.34	49.65	41.21	40.13	42.48	43.86	48.18	51.13	51.56	53.52	49.77
4	50.23	52.45	49.02	41.17	40.22	42.60	43.92	48.36	51.11	51.70	53.37	49.81
5	50.33	52.58	48.48	41.14	40.40	42.66	44.09	48.52	51.09	51.81	53.01	49.91
6	50.46	52.70	47.99	41.12	40.56	42.68	44.28	48.67	50.94	51.88	52.96	50.03
7	50.57	52.82	47.52	41.10	40.73	42.54	44.48	48.75	50.74	51.93	53.06	50.15
8	50.64	52.93	47.07	41.09	40.92	42.44	44.64	48.79	50.56	51.96	53.18	50.27
9	50.70	53.02	46.60	41.09	41.09	42.63	44.75	48.81	50.34	51.98	53.27	50.36
10	50.78	53.09	46.17	41.10	41.17	42.77	44.84	48.88	50.19	52.03	53.30	50.47
11	50.87	53.16	45.78	41.11	41.19	42.94	44.97	49.02	50.20	52.11	53.17	50.60
12	50.97	53.22	45.45	41.13	41.23	43.05	45.11	49.20	50.40	52.20	52.87	50.72
13	51.09	53.29	45.13	41.16	41.27	43.05	45.27	49.39	50.62	52.30	52.57	50.83
14	51.20	53.35	44.83	41.18	41.09	42.99	45.42	49.58	50.83	52.40	52.36	50.92
15	51.29	53.40	44.55	41.22	40.70	42.91	45.54	49.76	51.04	52.49	52.28	51.03
16	51.37	53.47	44.27	41.26	40.45	42.96	45.63	49.94	51.20	52.58	52.26	51.10
17	51.46	53.54	43.98	41.32	40.41	42.98	45.69	50.11	51.34	52.65	52.20	51.15
18	51.56	53.61	43.68	41.32	40.39	43.06	45.80	50.27	51.46	52.72	51.97	51.20
19	51.65	53.68	43.39	41.30	40.39	43.14	45.97	50.43	51.58	52.80	51.66	51.27
20	51.74	53.74	43.14	41.30	40.59	43.14	46.11	50.58	51.72	52.89	51.32	51.33
21	51.77	53.78	42.93	41.23	40.87	43.19	46.24	50.71	51.86	52.98	50.98	51.39
22	51.78	53.79	42.71	41.11	41.07	43.30	46.39	50.81	51.91	53.07	50.67	51.45
23	51.81	53.76	42.51	41.17	41.15	43.41	46.55	50.88	51.85	53.14	50.35	51.51
24	51.84	53.69	42.31	41.26	41.14	43.47	46.71	50.95	51.88	53.18	50.14	51.58
25	51.85	53.55	42.12	41.32	41.27	43.56	46.88	51.06	51.82	53.24	50.13	51.64
26	51.84	53.41	41.95	41.19	41.48	43.64	47.05	51.15	51.75	53.32	50.14	51.71
27	51.73	53.21	41.79	41.18	41.67	43.68	47.21	51.24	51.64	53.39	50.10	51.77
28	51.70	52.93	41.67	41.23	41.85	43.74	47.37	51.30	51.57	53.45	50.05	51.84
29	51.79	52.33	41.58	41.20	42.02	43.79	47.49	51.38	51.54	53.48	49.99	51.89
30	51.89	51.71	41.53	41.04	---	43.77	47.66	51.42	51.53	53.46	49.94	51.92
31	51.99	---	41.44	40.67	---	43.70	---	51.37	---	53.41	49.90	---
LOW	51.99	53.79	51.03	41.34	42.02	43.79	47.66	51.42	51.91	53.48	53.52	51.92
HIGH	50.02	51.71	41.44	40.67	40.13	42.19	43.74	47.83	50.19	51.44	49.90	49.77

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 48.04 LOW 53.79 HIGH 40.13

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO HUMACAO TO RIO SECO BASINS

180415065513900. Local number, 96.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°04'15", long 65°51'39".

Owner: P.R. Aqueduct and Sewer Authority.

Name: USGS TW-2 or Yabucoa 7.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation water-table well, diameter 16 in (0.41 m), cased 0-10 ft (0-3.05 m), diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased about 0-183 ft (0-55.79 m), perforated 56-81 ft (17.07-24.70 m), 102-123 ft (31.10-37.50 m), 144-181 ft (43.90-55.18 m). Depth 181 ft (55.18 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 25 ft (7.62 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 4.00 ft (1.22 m) above land-surface.

REMARKS.--Observation recording well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 25, 1978 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 13.10 ft (3.99 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 2, 1987; lowest water level recorded, 28.29 ft (8.62 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 20, 1980.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	17.13	17.23	14.26	13.71	14.77	16.10	18.23	18.14	17.55	16.10	19.09	18.66
2	17.14	17.22	14.22	13.74	14.80	16.22	18.25	18.04	17.45	16.06	19.06	18.61
3	17.16	17.22	13.21	13.76	14.84	16.50	18.24	17.99	17.36	16.03	19.04	18.59
4	17.17	17.20	13.10	13.78	14.86	16.55	18.23	17.95	17.30	15.98	19.04	18.55
5	17.19	17.18	13.69	13.80	14.61	16.60	18.21	18.00	17.23	15.93	19.03	18.46
6	17.51	17.16	13.70	13.83	14.70	16.64	18.20	18.05	17.15	15.95	19.02	18.37
7	17.64	17.14	13.12	13.85	14.57	16.64	18.19	18.16	17.16	16.10	19.00	18.29
8	17.55	17.11	13.62	13.87	14.22	16.64	18.19	18.26	17.29	16.31	18.98	18.26
9	17.64	17.10	13.67	13.89	14.29	16.47	18.20	18.29	17.42	16.55	18.95	18.27
10	17.12	17.09	13.56	13.92	14.20	16.53	18.20	18.28	17.47	16.80	18.92	18.26
11	17.16	17.10	13.27	13.94	14.15	16.59	18.18	18.26	17.44	17.03	18.89	18.19
12	17.23	17.13	13.20	13.96	14.12	16.86	18.16	18.25	17.35	17.27	18.90	18.08
13	18.12	17.18	13.14	13.98	14.18	16.91	18.14	18.23	17.26	17.46	18.93	17.97
14	18.19	17.23	13.27	14.01	14.16	16.94	18.10	18.19	17.15	17.63	18.95	17.82
15	18.23	17.28	13.20	14.03	14.54	16.96	18.05	18.17	17.04	17.78	18.97	17.67
16	18.10	17.54	13.17	14.05	14.66	17.02	18.04	18.17	16.96	17.94	19.01	17.52
17	18.16	17.57	13.18	14.07	14.60	17.18	18.03	18.17	16.89	18.07	19.05	17.38
18	18.15	17.57	13.24	14.10	14.17	17.36	18.03	18.16	16.83	18.18	19.09	17.26
19	18.05	17.57	13.14	14.13	15.14	17.52	18.05	18.14	16.77	18.26	19.14	17.15
20	18.12	17.57	13.47	14.15	15.10	17.65	18.09	18.08	16.71	18.39	19.20	17.04
21	17.13	17.58	13.56	14.17	15.24	17.80	18.15	18.03	16.64	18.48	19.27	16.98
22	17.59	17.60	13.45	14.40	15.57	17.94	18.20	17.96	16.56	18.60	19.30	16.94
23	17.46	17.63	13.48	14.41	15.67	18.14	18.28	17.88	16.49	18.69	19.31	16.94
24	17.58	17.62	13.52	14.42	15.56	18.19	18.37	17.82	16.44	18.81	19.31	16.93
25	17.53	17.26	13.55	14.43	15.62	18.23	18.45	17.77	16.40	18.90	19.24	16.92
26	17.49	17.23	13.58	14.46	15.10	18.22	18.46	17.75	16.34	18.98	19.15	16.94
27	17.26	16.57	13.60	14.49	15.18	18.20	18.38	17.72	16.30	19.03	19.06	17.00
28	17.24	16.13	13.62	14.54	16.09	18.17	18.30	17.71	16.24	19.05	18.97	17.10
29	17.22	15.26	13.65	14.60	16.18	18.17	18.24	17.69	16.20	19.09	18.88	17.22
30	17.21	14.68	13.67	14.66	---	18.18	18.18	17.67	16.16	19.15	18.80	17.37
31	17.22	---	13.69	14.72	---	18.20	---	17.62	---	19.11	18.73	---
LOW	18.23	17.63	14.26	14.72	16.18	18.23	18.46	18.29	17.55	19.15	19.31	18.66
HIGH	17.12	14.68	13.10	13.71	14.12	16.10	18.03	17.62	16.16	15.93	18.73	16.92

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 16.83 LOW 19.31 HIGH 13.10

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175829066232200. Local number, 87.
LOCATION.--Lat 17°58'29", long 66°23'22".
Owner: Francisco Alomar.
Name: Alomar 1.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Quaternary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 20 in (0.51 m), iron cased. Depth 112 ft (34.14 m).
DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 35.32 ft (10.77 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Bottom of clean-out shelter door, 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to August 1981, top of recorder shelter floor, 4.00 ft (1.22 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1967 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 8.45 ft (2.58 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 10, 1970; lowest water level recorded, 49.18 ft (14.99 m) below land-surface datum, July 27, 1974.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	27.20	26.47	---	21.96	23.60	24.49	24.13	24.84	25.65	23.13	25.47	23.41
2	27.43	26.77	---	22.23	23.46	24.40	23.85	24.94	25.65	23.02	25.78	23.35
3	27.86	26.87	---	22.10	23.59	24.37	23.47	25.38	25.66	23.03	25.86	23.28
4	27.86	26.58	---	21.98	23.73	24.61	23.72	25.50	24.93	22.78	25.22	23.24
5	27.88	26.58	---	22.03	23.82	24.72	24.12	25.32	24.51	22.46	25.13	23.21
6	27.58	26.18	---	21.98	23.81	24.13	23.99	25.12	24.11	22.64	24.94	23.13
7	27.29	24.95	---	22.03	23.75	23.70	24.19	25.10	24.25	22.36	24.94	23.11
8	27.41	25.30	22.19	22.12	23.72	23.71	24.39	25.03	24.89	22.77	24.86	22.97
9	27.32	25.46	22.14	22.05	23.86	23.61	24.44	25.10	24.79	23.00	24.88	22.94
10	27.28	25.62	22.11	22.02	23.85	24.62	24.45	25.43	24.85	23.08	24.90	22.87
11	27.25	25.72	22.10	22.39	23.84	24.49	24.41	25.28	24.46	23.20	24.97	22.93
12	27.25	25.76	22.07	22.78	23.85	24.47	24.73	25.38	24.20	23.61	25.54	22.95
13	27.70	25.84	22.04	22.85	23.88	24.43	24.79	25.44	24.74	23.80	25.96	22.98
14	28.19	25.86	22.02	22.84	23.86	24.41	24.86	25.36	24.75	24.01	25.91	23.01
15	28.29	25.92	22.00	22.92	23.77	24.54	25.04	25.41	24.75	24.12	25.95	23.05
16	27.83	25.97	21.99	22.90	23.82	24.70	25.00	25.38	24.63	24.30	26.05	23.09
17	26.94	26.41	22.14	22.88	23.86	24.65	25.02	25.86	23.89	24.19	26.29	23.12
18	26.81	26.13	22.07	22.90	23.91	24.70	25.06	25.66	23.84	24.14	25.21	23.15
19	26.85	26.10	22.02	23.02	23.29	24.94	25.31	25.68	23.70	24.15	24.91	23.20
20	26.93	26.26	21.98	23.08	23.98	24.83	25.28	25.60	24.20	24.32	24.87	23.21
21	27.05	26.17	21.96	23.13	24.08	24.37	24.93	25.59	24.58	24.30	24.81	23.19
22	27.12	26.14	22.05	23.27	23.86	24.75	25.75	25.54	24.71	24.39	24.80	23.19
23	27.17	26.13	22.04	23.34	23.96	23.95	25.06	25.87	23.58	24.50	24.73	23.13
24	27.18	26.11	22.00	23.38	24.25	24.50	24.73	25.62	23.90	24.47	24.69	23.31
25	27.19	---	21.95	23.28	24.08	24.63	24.72	25.62	23.79	24.48	24.10	23.23
26	27.47	---	21.93	23.36	24.41	24.70	24.68	25.91	23.12	24.50	23.92	23.24
27	27.00	---	21.95	23.42	24.26	24.57	24.89	26.16	22.59	25.21	23.85	23.34
28	26.42	---	22.27	23.46	24.18	24.40	25.09	26.04	22.39	25.30	23.73	23.35
29	26.42	---	21.96	23.57	24.44	24.74	25.25	25.81	22.71	25.73	23.63	23.63
30	26.43	---	21.97	23.62	---	25.12	25.13	25.71	23.16	25.62	23.50	23.53
31	26.43	---	21.97	23.61	---	25.34	---	25.64	---	25.44	23.54	---
LOW	28.29	---	---	23.62	24.44	25.34	25.75	26.16	25.66	25.73	26.29	23.63
HIGH	26.42	---	---	21.96	23.29	23.61	23.47	24.84	22.39	22.36	23.50	22.87

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180002066132200. Local number, HW-TW-01.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'02", long 66°13'22".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.

Name: Hw-Tw-01.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-39.5 ft (0-12.0 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-38.2 ft (0-11.6 m), screened 32-37 ft (9.75-11.3 m). Depth 39.5 ft (12.0 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 190 ft (58.0 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.48 ft (1.06 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on April 14, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 14, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 19.82 ft (6.04 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 14, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 22.78 ft (6.95 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 23-24, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.98	20.50	21.12	21.93	21.83
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.99	20.52	21.12	21.97	21.81
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.01	20.54	21.12	22.02	21.79
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.04	20.59	21.12	22.07	21.78
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.04	20.62	21.13	22.09	21.79
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.05	20.65	21.14	22.12	21.82
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.05	20.67	21.16	22.16	21.85
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.06	20.70	21.18	22.21	21.90
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.06	20.74	21.20	22.24	21.94
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.07	20.77	21.22	22.27	21.98
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.09	20.78	21.23	22.33	22.05
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.10	20.80	21.24	22.38	22.09
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.11	20.82	21.24	22.42	22.11
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.12	20.86	21.24	22.47	22.14
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.84	20.14	20.89	21.28	22.51	22.17
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.84	20.16	20.90	21.30	22.56	22.20
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.85	20.17	20.91	21.31	22.63	22.23
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.87	20.19	20.93	21.33	22.67	22.26
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.90	20.21	20.94	21.36	22.69	22.31
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.89	20.23	20.96	21.39	22.72	22.38
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.90	20.24	20.97	21.42	22.74	22.42
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.91	20.26	20.99	21.46	22.76	22.46
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.94	20.29	21.01	21.50	22.78	22.49
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.94	20.31	21.02	21.56	22.78	22.53
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.94	20.34	21.03	21.62	22.58	22.57
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.94	20.36	21.04	21.67	22.38	22.61
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.96	20.39	21.05	21.72	22.22	22.66
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.96	20.40	21.07	21.77	22.10	22.70
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.97	20.42	21.08	21.82	22.00	22.73
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.98	20.45	21.09	21.86	21.92	22.76
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.47	---	21.89	21.87	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	20.47	21.09	21.89	22.78	22.76
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.98	20.50	21.12	21.87	21.78

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180017066132100 Local number, HW-TW-02.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'17", long 66°13'21".
Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.
Name: Hw-Tw-02.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-74 ft (0-22.6 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-70 ft (0-21.3 m), screened 60-65 ft (18.3-19.8 m). Depth 74 ft (22.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 224 ft (68.3 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.60 ft (1.10 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on March 30, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 30, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 15.44 ft (4.71 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 30, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 23.72 ft (7.23 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.53	17.05	18.47	19.89	21.41	22.69
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.57	17.09	18.52	19.93	21.46	22.74
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.63	17.14	18.57	19.98	21.50	22.78
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.67	17.19	18.61	20.02	21.55	22.82
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.71	17.25	18.66	20.07	21.60	22.87
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.74	17.28	18.71	20.11	21.65	22.91
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.78	17.33	18.75	20.16	21.70	22.95
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.83	17.38	18.78	20.22	21.76	22.99
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.87	17.44	18.86	20.26	21.78	23.03
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.93	17.49	18.89	20.30	21.82	23.06
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.97	17.54	18.93	20.37	21.87	23.11
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.03	17.58	18.97	20.42	21.92	23.16
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.08	17.63	19.02	20.47	21.97	23.19
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.13	17.67	19.08	20.52	22.02	23.23
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.26	17.70	19.13	20.58	22.06	23.27
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.30	17.76	19.17	20.63	22.11	23.30
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.36	17.79	19.21	20.68	22.16	23.33
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.40	17.84	19.26	20.73	22.21	23.35
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.45	17.89	19.31	20.78	22.27	23.41
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.49	17.92	19.36	20.82	22.31	23.42
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.53	17.97	19.41	20.87	22.36	23.45
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.59	18.02	19.45	20.91	22.41	23.47
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.65	18.06	19.50	20.97	22.46	23.50
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.70	18.11	19.55	21.02	22.50	23.53
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.74	18.15	19.59	21.07	22.41	23.56
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.79	18.19	19.64	21.12	22.36	23.59
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.85	18.25	19.70	21.17	22.42	23.62
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.89	18.28	19.75	21.22	22.49	23.65
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.95	18.33	19.79	21.26	22.54	23.68
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.00	18.38	19.84	21.33	22.58	23.71
31	---	---	---	---	---	15.48	---	18.42	---	21.36	22.64	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	17.00	18.42	19.84	21.36	22.64	23.71
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.53	17.05	18.47	19.89	21.41	22.69

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180001066122000 Local number, HW-TW-03.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'01", long 66°12'20".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.

Name: Hw-Tw-03.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-60 ft (0-18.3 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-59 ft (0-18.0 m), screened 53-58 ft (16.2-17.7 m). Depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 271 ft (82.6 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.42 ft (1.04 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on March 31, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 31, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 23.68 ft (7.22 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 31, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 46.58 ft (14.2 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.89	27.69	32.75	39.16	43.62	45.86
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.04	27.77	32.95	39.35	43.72	45.88
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.22	27.91	33.14	39.55	43.79	45.88
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.35	28.03	33.35	39.73	43.91	45.89
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.51	28.14	33.55	39.92	44.00	45.89
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.64	28.26	33.74	40.11	44.10	45.90
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.80	28.37	33.91	40.29	44.18	45.92
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.97	28.51	34.10	40.47	44.27	45.94
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.10	28.67	34.32	40.64	44.33	45.94
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.26	28.83	34.51	40.79	44.39	45.94
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.37	29.01	34.68	40.96	44.49	45.98
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.54	29.17	34.85	41.13	44.58	46.02
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.68	29.33	35.06	41.27	44.65	46.03
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.83	29.47	35.26	41.42	44.72	46.06
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.95	29.63	35.46	41.57	44.81	46.09
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.07	29.81	35.68	41.72	44.88	46.12
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.20	29.96	35.92	41.84	44.96	46.17
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.31	30.13	36.16	41.98	45.03	46.17
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.43	30.32	36.36	42.12	45.10	46.21
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.52	30.48	36.56	42.24	45.18	46.25
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.63	30.66	36.73	42.34	45.24	46.26
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.76	30.85	36.96	42.48	45.31	46.31
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.89	31.04	37.21	42.60	45.39	46.33
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	26.98	31.23	37.49	42.71	45.44	46.35
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.05	31.40	37.69	42.82	45.53	46.38
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.15	31.59	37.93	42.94	45.60	46.41
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.28	31.79	38.22	43.05	45.67	46.43
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.38	31.97	38.52	43.23	45.72	46.48
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.50	32.17	38.74	43.35	45.78	46.50
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.59	32.37	38.95	43.45	45.81	46.52
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	32.56	---	43.53	45.84	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	27.59	32.56	38.95	43.53	45.84	46.52
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.89	27.69	32.75	39.16	43.62	45.86

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

18000066125200 Local number, HW-TW-04.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'00", long 66°12'52".
Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.
Name: Hw-Tw-04.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-48.5 ft (0-14.8 m) cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-48 ft (0-14.6 m), screened 42-47 ft (12.8-14.3 m). Depth 48.5 ft (14.8 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 177 ft (53.9 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.50 ft (1.07 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on April 5, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 5, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 18.39 ft (5.60 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 5, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 21.79 ft (6.64 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 24, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.02	19.70	20.46	21.10	20.28
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.05	19.73	20.46	21.14	20.24
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.08	19.77	20.45	21.18	20.21
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.11	19.80	20.42	21.22	20.20
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.39	19.14	19.85	20.40	21.25	20.19
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.42	19.16	19.88	20.40	21.28	20.19
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.78	19.17	19.91	20.39	21.31	20.20
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.63	19.17	19.93	20.39	21.34	20.23
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.61	19.17	20.00	20.39	21.37	20.25
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.60	19.18	20.02	20.39	21.40	20.27
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.64	19.19	20.06	20.40	21.42	20.30
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.67	19.20	20.09	20.42	21.47	20.32
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.66	19.18	20.13	20.44	21.50	20.37
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.67	19.18	20.16	20.46	21.52	20.40
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.69	19.21	20.20	20.48	21.56	20.42
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.71	19.22	20.24	20.51	21.60	20.44
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.73	19.22	20.26	20.54	21.63	20.47
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.74	19.22	20.28	20.58	21.66	20.48
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.77	19.33	20.30	20.60	21.68	20.48
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.78	19.34	20.34	20.65	21.70	20.51
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.80	19.36	20.36	20.68	21.73	20.55
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.82	19.38	20.37	20.72	21.76	20.59
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.85	19.43	20.39	20.76	21.78	20.62
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.88	19.45	20.41	20.80	21.79	20.66
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.89	19.49	20.42	20.84	21.58	20.69
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.94	19.55	20.42	20.88	21.18	20.73
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.94	19.56	20.43	20.92	20.90	20.78
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.95	19.58	20.43	20.95	20.69	20.81
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.99	19.60	20.44	20.99	20.53	20.85
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.00	19.64	20.45	21.04	20.42	20.89
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.66	---	21.07	20.34	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.66	20.45	21.07	21.79	20.89
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	19.02	19.70	20.39	20.34	20.19

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175947066130601 Local number, HW-TW-05B.

LOCATION.--Lat 17° 59' 47", long 66° 13' 06".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.

Name: Hw-Tw-05B.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-52 ft (0-15.8 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-51 ft (0-15.5 m), screened 41-46 ft (12.5-14.0 m). Depth 52 ft (15.8 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 145 ft (44.2 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.47 ft (1.06 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on April 13, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 13, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 9.40 ft (2.86 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 25, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 14.73 ft (4.49 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 17, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.72	12.76	12.15	14.08	11.70
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.72	12.79	12.15	14.17	11.85
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.73	12.82	12.26	14.25	11.96
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.76	12.85	12.33	14.24	12.04
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.08	12.87	12.38	14.24	12.12
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.03	12.90	12.42	14.29	12.21
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.48	12.94	12.44	14.34	12.26
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.50	13.01	12.47	14.37	12.29
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.09	13.09	12.50	14.43	12.31
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.66	13.14	12.54	14.44	12.30
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.88	13.19	12.59	14.45	12.25
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.52	13.23	12.64	14.47	12.21
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.52	13.29	12.68	14.52	12.21
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.57	12.52	13.35	12.73	14.58	12.10
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.59	12.53	13.41	12.78	14.63	12.15
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.59	12.52	13.14	12.83	14.70	12.18
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.62	12.52	13.11	12.87	14.73	12.21
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.63	12.53	13.10	12.93	14.66	12.24
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.66	12.51	13.11	13.00	14.62	12.28
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.67	12.43	13.14	13.06	14.61	12.13
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.67	12.44	13.13	13.14	14.64	12.18
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.69	12.46	13.11	13.24	14.70	12.22
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.70	12.49	13.11	13.34	14.30	12.25
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.65	12.51	13.11	13.42	14.18	12.26
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.65	12.54	12.68	13.52	9.78	12.31
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.65	12.55	12.91	13.62	9.58	12.36
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.66	12.60	12.92	13.73	10.05	12.42
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.67	12.63	12.93	13.84	10.50	12.48
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.68	12.67	12.93	13.91	10.91	12.55
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.70	12.70	12.94	13.99	11.22	12.61
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.73	---	13.99	11.50	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.09	13.41	13.99	14.73	12.61
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.43	12.76	12.15	9.58	11.70

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180006066123700 Local number, HW-TW-07.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'06", long 66°12'37".
Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.
Name: Hw-Tw-07.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-88 ft (0-26.8 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-82 ft (0-25.0 m), screened 69-77 ft (21.0-29.5 m). Depth 88 ft (26.8 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 240 ft (73.2 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.48 ft (1.06 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on March 31, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 1988 to September 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 23.79 ft (7.25 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 1, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 30.22 ft (9.21 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 24, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.83	25.38	26.33	28.00	29.22	28.95
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.90	25.43	26.77	28.01	29.26	28.95
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.95	25.48	26.81	28.03	29.32	28.95
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.98	25.55	26.86	28.05	29.36	28.97
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.03	25.59	26.90	28.07	29.39	28.99
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.14	25.62	26.94	28.09	29.44	29.02
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.19	25.64	27.00	28.12	29.51	29.05
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.22	25.65	27.04	28.16	29.55	29.09
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.26	25.67	27.10	28.19	29.61	29.12
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.27	25.68	27.15	28.23	29.66	29.13
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.37	25.69	27.20	28.27	29.71	29.17
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.44	25.88	27.25	28.31	29.75	29.21
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.49	25.92	27.31	28.37	29.80	29.23
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.56	25.96	27.36	28.41	29.85	29.26
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.62	26.00	27.41	28.45	29.90	29.29
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.66	26.04	27.44	28.49	29.94	29.31
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.71	26.08	27.48	28.53	29.99	29.34
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.75	26.12	27.52	28.57	30.02	29.36
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.80	26.16	27.55	28.61	30.05	29.40
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.85	26.20	27.59	28.66	30.08	29.44
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.88	26.24	27.62	28.70	30.12	29.49
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.94	26.28	27.75	28.75	30.16	29.52
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	24.99	26.32	27.70	28.80	30.20	29.55
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.03	26.36	27.75	28.85	30.21	29.59
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.08	26.40	27.78	28.89	29.81	29.61
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.13	26.45	27.81	28.95	29.43	29.64
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.19	26.50	27.85	29.00	29.25	29.68
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.22	26.54	27.88	29.05	29.14	29.73
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.27	26.58	27.93	29.10	29.07	29.78
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.33	26.61	27.97	29.14	29.01	29.81
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	25.33	26.65	27.97	29.18	30.21	29.81
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	23.83	25.38	26.73	28.00	28.97	28.95

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175939066121400 Local number, HW-TW-08.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'39", long 66°12'14".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.

Name: Hw-Tw-08.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-49 ft (0-14.9 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m),

0-49 ft (0-14.9 m), screened 43-48 ft (13.1-14.6 m). Depth 49 ft (14.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 172 ft (52.4 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.55 ft (1.08 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on April 13, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 13, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 12.55 ft (3.82 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 13, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 28.98 ft (8.83 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.68	18.30	21.73	25.55	28.43
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.81	18.39	21.84	25.69	28.44
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.93	18.51	21.96	25.79	28.43
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.06	18.63	22.08	25.93	28.42
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.19	18.76	22.18	26.06	28.40
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.30	18.86	22.31	26.16	28.39
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.42	18.97	22.42	26.28	28.36
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.53	19.08	22.54	26.39	28.36
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.67	19.18	22.66	26.49	28.33
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.79	19.30	22.77	26.57	28.31
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	15.93	19.41	22.91	26.70	28.35
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.06	19.52	23.04	26.82	28.37
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	16.15	19.65	23.17	26.96	28.36
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.66	16.25	19.77	23.91	27.07	28.38
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.77	16.37	19.88	23.59	27.19	28.40
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.88	16.48	19.98	23.66	27.32	28.42
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	12.99	16.58	20.10	23.75	27.46	28.41
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.11	16.69	20.21	23.85	27.58	28.43
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.23	16.83	20.34	23.97	27.68	28.46
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.35	16.94	20.46	24.10	27.80	28.50
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.44	17.05	20.57	24.20	27.91	28.54
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.58	17.18	20.69	24.33	28.03	28.58
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.70	17.27	20.81	24.45	28.15	28.62
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.82	17.38	20.92	24.57	28.26	28.66
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	13.94	17.49	21.03	24.69	28.38	28.70
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.06	17.62	21.15	24.82	28.38	28.74
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.22	17.73	21.27	24.95	28.34	28.79
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.32	17.84	21.37	25.07	28.34	28.84
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.45	17.95	21.49	25.18	28.37	28.90
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.56	18.08	21.60	25.32	28.39	28.95
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.18	---	25.43	28.41	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	18.18	21.60	25.43	28.41	28.95
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	14.68	18.30	21.73	25.55	28.31

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175950066125200 Local number, HW-TW-10.
 LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'50", long 66°12'52".
 Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.
 Name: Hw-Tw-10.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-55 ft (0-16.8 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-54 ft (0-16.4 m), screened 48-53 ft (14.6-16.2 m). Depth 55 ft (16.8 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 159 ft (48.5 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.61 ft (1.10 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on April 5, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 5, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 21.39 ft (6.52 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 5, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 24.79 ft (7.55 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 22-23, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.19	22.87	23.55	24.18	23.58
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.32	22.89	23.53	24.21	23.54
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.31	22.92	23.52	24.24	23.52
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.32	22.95	23.52	24.26	23.51
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.40	22.35	22.97	23.52	24.29	23.50
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.42	22.37	23.00	23.54	24.33	23.50
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.45	22.37	23.02	23.55	24.35	23.50
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.49	22.39	23.05	23.56	24.39	23.50
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.53	22.41	23.08	23.57	24.43	23.50
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.56	22.43	23.12	23.58	24.46	23.49
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.60	22.46	23.14	23.62	24.48	23.52
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.64	22.49	23.16	23.64	24.52	23.53
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.67	22.50	23.20	23.66	24.54	23.53
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.70	22.51	23.24	23.68	24.57	23.53
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.74	22.52	23.26	23.69	24.60	23.53
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.77	22.55	23.27	23.72	24.64	23.54
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.81	22.56	23.29	23.74	24.67	23.55
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.83	22.58	23.32	23.77	24.69	23.55
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.87	22.60	23.35	23.79	24.71	23.59
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.89	22.61	23.37	23.82	24.73	23.60
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.92	22.62	23.40	23.84	24.75	23.61
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.96	22.65	23.42	23.86	24.78	23.63
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.00	22.67	23.44	23.90	24.78	23.65
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.02	22.69	23.45	23.93	24.78	23.67
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.04	22.71	23.45	23.96	24.37	23.69
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.08	22.73	23.47	24.00	24.08	23.72
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.10	22.76	23.48	24.03	23.94	23.76
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	21.93	22.78	23.50	24.06	23.84	23.78
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.13	22.80	23.52	24.09	23.76	23.82
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.17	22.82	23.54	24.13	23.66	23.84
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.85	---	24.14	23.61	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.85	23.54	24.14	24.78	23.84
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	22.19	22.87	23.52	23.61	23.49

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW
 LAND-SURFACE DATUM

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

180012066125500 Local number, HW-TW-11.
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°00'12", long 66°12'55".
 Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.
 Name: Hw-Tw-11.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-94.9 ft (0-28.9 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-94 ft (0-28.6 m), screened 79-89 ft (24.1-27.1 m). Depth 94.9 ft (28.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 240 ft (73.2 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.74 ft (1.14 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on April 14, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 14, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 57.00 ft (17.4 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 14, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 63.86 ft (19.5 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 30, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.60	58.90	60.31	61.58	62.70
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.64	59.00	60.35	61.63	62.72
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.70	59.05	60.38	61.67	62.73
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.75	59.07	60.43	61.71	62.77
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.79	59.07	60.47	61.77	62.78
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.82	59.07	60.52	61.82	62.80
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.85	59.40	60.57	61.87	62.82
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.93	59.31	60.61	61.90	62.85
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.96	59.32	60.65	61.97	62.87
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	58.01	59.35	60.69	62.00	62.89
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	58.05	59.39	60.74	62.04	62.92
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	58.08	59.43	60.78	62.09	62.96
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	58.13	59.48	60.83	62.15	62.98
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	58.16	59.54	60.87	62.20	63.03
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.03	58.19	59.58	60.89	62.26	63.06
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.05	58.25	59.63	60.94	62.30	63.09
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.09	58.28	59.67	60.96	62.36	63.12
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.11	58.32	59.72	61.01	62.41	63.13
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.16	58.36	59.76	61.06	62.47	63.18
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.19	58.40	59.82	61.09	62.52	63.23
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.23	58.45	59.87	61.12	62.58	63.28
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.27	58.50	59.91	61.16	62.63	63.31
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.31	58.74	59.95	61.21	62.68	63.35
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.35	58.35	59.99	61.24	62.71	63.39
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.39	58.57	60.04	61.28	62.76	63.43
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.42	58.62	60.08	61.32	62.75	63.46
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.46	58.65	60.13	61.37	62.71	63.51
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.49	58.76	60.17	61.41	62.70	63.55
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.51	58.80	60.22	61.44	62.70	63.59
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.54	58.84	60.27	61.50	62.69	63.62
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	58.84	---	61.52	62.69	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	58.84	60.27	61.52	62.76	63.62
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	57.60	58.90	60.31	61.58	62.70

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175957066123400 Local number, HW-TW-13.
LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'57", long 66°12'34".
Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.
Name: Hw-Tw-13.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-69 ft (0-21.0 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-4.0 ft (0-1.22 m), screened 4.0-69 ft (1.22-21.0 m). Depth 69 ft (21.0 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 203 ft (61.9 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.47 ft (1.06 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on April 14, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--April 14, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 44.56 ft (13.6 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 25, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 46.95 ft (14.3 m) below land-surface datum, June 8, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.16	46.82	46.81	46.71	46.31
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.20	46.81	46.81	46.71	46.32
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.21	46.85	46.79	46.71	46.36
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.27	46.86	46.79	46.66	46.38
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.35	46.88	46.77	46.65	46.43
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.43	46.90	46.79	46.64	46.47
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.45	46.93	46.77	46.62	46.49
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.48	46.93	46.77	46.63	46.50
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.47	46.95	46.75	46.63	46.51
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.42	46.94	46.75	46.61	46.48
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.43	46.92	46.75	46.62	46.47
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.42	46.92	46.75	46.63	46.48
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.45	46.91	46.75	46.61	46.51
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.46	46.90	46.74	46.58	46.45
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.57	46.47	46.91	46.74	46.57	46.42
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.61	46.49	46.85	46.73	46.56	46.43
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.63	46.50	46.87	46.72	46.53	46.49
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.66	46.51	46.88	46.70	46.53	46.48
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.70	46.55	46.86	46.70	46.55	46.44
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.75	46.57	46.86	46.70	46.57	46.44
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.78	46.59	46.87	46.70	46.57	46.47
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.82	46.62	46.84	46.70	46.56	46.45
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.87	46.64	46.84	46.66	46.57	46.49
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.88	46.65	46.82	46.66	46.54	46.45
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.92	46.68	46.82	46.70	45.86	46.46
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	45.96	46.73	46.82	46.71	45.63	46.49
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.00	46.73	46.82	46.70	46.16	46.50
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.03	46.72	46.82	46.71	46.34	46.50
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.10	46.79	46.83	46.71	46.30	46.51
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.12	46.82	46.79	46.71	46.31	46.50
31	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.82	---	46.71	46.30	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.82	46.95	46.81	46.71	46.51
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	46.16	46.79	46.66	45.63	46.31

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175946066102000 Local number, HW-TW-14

LOCATION.--Lat 17°59'46", long 66°10'20".

Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.

Name: Hw-Tw-14.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-79 ft (0-24.4 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-79 ft (0-24.1 m), screened 71-78 ft (21.6-23.8 m), Depth 79 ft (24.1 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 205 ft (62.5 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.67 ft (1.12 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1987 to September 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 41.1 ft (12.5 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 17, 1987; lowest water level measured, 65.0 ft (19.8 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 8, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Dec. 11	42.81	Jan. 19	45.69	Feb. 22	50.52	May 10	60.01
17	41.10	25	46.56	29	51.69	June 8	61.03
21	41.31	Feb. 4	47.95	Mar. 7	52.84	July 13	62.33
22	41.39	8	48.45	15	54.13	Aug. 8	65.00
Jan. 4	43.43	16	49.58	31	56.45	Sept. 16	63.66
11	44.55						

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO SALINAS TO RIO JACAGUAS BASINS

175955066103000 Local number, HW-TW-15.
LOCATION.--Lat 17° 59' 55", long 66° 10' 30".
Owner: U.S. Geological Survey, WRD.
Name: Hw-Tw-15.

AQUIFER.--Fractured, volcanic rock, water-table aquifer.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 7 in (0.18 m), 0-85 ft (0-25.9 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m), 0-85 ft (0-25.9 m), screened 70-80 ft (21.3-24.4 m). Depth 85 ft (25.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 269 ft (82.0 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 3.60 ft (1.10 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Automatic digital recorder installed on Mar. 30, 1988.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 30, 1988 to September 30, 1988.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 36.20 ft (11.0 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 30, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 48.99 ft (14.9 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 2, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	---	---	---	---	---	---	36.68	41.79	44.80	47.79	48.96	---
2	---	---	---	---	---	---	36.92	41.93	44.89	47.86	48.99	---
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	37.13	42.07	44.97	47.92	---	---
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	37.35	42.19	45.07	48.01	---	---
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	37.55	42.32	45.15	48.07	---	---
6	---	---	---	---	---	---	37.75	42.42	45.24	48.12	---	---
7	---	---	---	---	---	---	37.95	42.55	45.33	48.16	---	---
8	---	---	---	---	---	---	38.15	42.68	45.42	48.27	49.51	---
9	---	---	---	---	---	---	38.33	42.78	45.62	48.31	---	---
10	---	---	---	---	---	---	38.52	42.78	45.72	48.34	---	---
11	---	---	---	---	---	---	38.71	42.87	45.81	48.48	---	---
12	---	---	---	---	---	---	38.89	42.98	45.91	48.55	---	---
13	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.06	43.08	46.01	48.20	---	---
14	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.23	43.19	46.09	48.21	---	---
15	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.40	43.27	46.17	48.22	---	---
16	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.55	43.37	46.26	48.31	---	---
17	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.72	43.46	46.38	48.43	---	---
18	---	---	---	---	---	---	39.87	43.56	46.43	48.50	---	---
19	---	---	---	---	---	---	40.03	43.66	46.54	48.56	---	50.63
20	---	---	---	---	---	---	40.18	43.74	46.68	48.65	---	---
21	---	---	---	---	---	---	40.35	43.82	46.76	48.72	---	---
22	---	---	---	---	---	---	40.50	43.92	46.84	48.75	---	---
23	---	---	---	---	---	---	40.67	44.01	46.95	48.81	---	---
24	---	---	---	---	---	---	40.80	44.10	47.06	48.92	---	---
25	---	---	---	---	---	---	40.96	44.18	47.13	48.94	---	---
26	---	---	---	---	---	---	41.11	44.27	47.22	48.94	---	---
27	---	---	---	---	---	---	41.25	44.35	47.31	48.94	---	---
28	---	---	---	---	---	---	41.39	44.45	47.39	48.95	---	---
29	---	---	---	---	---	---	41.52	44.53	47.53	48.95	---	---
30	---	---	---	---	---	---	41.66	44.61	47.56	48.95	---	---
31	---	---	---	---	---	36.45	---	44.71	---	48.95	---	---
LOW	---	---	---	---	---	---	41.66	44.71	47.56	48.95	---	---
HIGH	---	---	---	---	---	---	36.68	41.79	44.80	47.79	---	---

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
RIO INABON TO RIO LOCO BASINS

180133066503300. Local number, 132.
LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'33", long 66°50'33".
Owner: Pittsburg Plate Glass 4.
Name: Yauco 2.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, cased 20 in (0.51 m) 0-20 ft (0-6.1 m), 12 in (0.30 m) perforated pipe 20-84 ft (6.1-25.61 m), 10 in (0.25 m) perforated pipe 84-190 ft (25.61-57.93 m). Depth 190 ft (57.93 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75 ft (22.87 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of shelter floor, 2.35 ft (0.72 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--July 1972 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, +0.12 ft (0.04 m) below land-surface datum, July 19, 1979; lowest water level recorded, 36.91 ft (11.25 m) below land-surface datum, June 27, 1974.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	12.01	10.11	---	---	7.22	8.42	9.88	9.56	11.69	12.66	12.62	---
2	12.03	10.07	---	---	7.26	8.46	10.01	9.59	11.79	12.58	12.70	---
3	12.08	10.07	---	---	7.30	8.52	10.09	9.61	11.89	12.58	12.73	---
4	12.10	10.00	---	---	7.33	8.57	10.19	9.62	11.95	12.69	12.82	---
5	12.19	10.03	---	---	7.37	8.64	10.26	9.68	12.05	12.25	12.93	---
6	12.28	9.98	---	---	7.40	8.70	10.29	9.73	12.13	12.14	13.01	---
7	12.40	9.84	---	---	7.41	8.74	10.01	9.80	12.22	12.07	13.02	6.55
8	12.50	9.80	---	---	7.43	8.80	10.08	9.85	11.97	12.04	13.11	6.54
9	12.20	9.83	---	---	7.49	8.87	10.17	9.97	12.14	12.02	13.20	6.56
10	12.17	9.84	---	---	7.54	8.94	10.26	9.82	12.27	11.85	13.30	6.50
11	11.63	9.87	---	---	7.59	9.01	10.33	9.89	12.36	11.96	13.39	6.50
12	11.58	9.87	---	---	7.62	9.08	10.40	10.03	12.43	12.08	13.49	6.00
13	11.58	9.92	---	---	7.67	9.16	10.47	10.14	12.42	12.14	13.53	6.09
14	11.57	9.94	---	6.30	7.71	9.25	10.55	10.20	12.41	12.15	13.22	6.18
15	11.59	9.92	---	6.36	7.75	9.32	10.56	10.27	12.48	12.23	13.42	6.25
16	11.59	10.02	---	6.43	7.80	9.40	10.66	10.32	12.52	12.28	13.57	6.17
17	11.58	10.00	---	6.49	7.82	9.47	10.74	10.35	12.56	12.34	13.69	6.10
18	11.58	9.97	---	6.56	7.85	9.50	10.80	10.43	12.59	12.08	12.25	6.13
19	11.10	9.90	---	6.62	7.88	9.57	10.88	10.52	12.43	12.15	12.45	6.20
20	11.07	9.90	---	6.66	7.93	9.67	10.89	10.60	12.47	12.18	12.11	6.24
21	11.04	9.94	---	6.69	7.97	9.73	10.89	10.69	12.62	12.21	12.24	6.27
22	10.80	9.90	---	6.76	8.01	9.81	10.95	10.79	12.70	12.32	12.31	6.19
23	10.81	10.02	---	6.80	8.04	9.86	10.16	10.88	12.78	12.41	11.31	6.00
24	10.68	9.54	---	6.83	8.10	9.97	9.69	10.98	12.86	12.37	10.90	5.26
25	10.36	8.40	---	6.87	8.16	10.04	9.69	11.08	12.34	12.28	---	5.46
26	10.36	8.34	---	6.94	8.21	10.12	9.69	11.19	12.26	12.33	---	5.40
27	10.24	4.62	---	7.00	8.24	10.20	9.69	11.30	12.36	12.44	---	5.57
28	10.18	---	---	7.03	8.32	10.27	9.69	11.38	12.48	12.51	---	5.74
29	10.18	---	---	7.08	8.35	10.31	9.56	11.45	12.57	12.55	---	5.86
30	10.19	---	---	7.12	---	10.38	9.55	11.52	12.61	12.64	---	5.94
31	10.16	---	---	7.19	---	9.84	---	11.58	---	12.50	---	---
LOW	12.50	---	---	---	8.35	10.38	10.95	11.58	12.86	12.69	---	---
HIGH	10.16	---	---	---	7.22	8.42	9.55	9.56	11.69	11.85	---	---

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO GUANAJIBO BASIN

180132067033800. Local number, 143.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°01'32", long 67°03'38".

Owner: Pedro P. Vivoni.

Name: Vivoni, Hacienda Amistad.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of unknown age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused irrigation well, diameter 12 in (0.30 m). Depth: 200 ft (60.98 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 52.5 ft (16.0 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole side of casing, 0.80 ft (0.24 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1981 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 37.36 ft (11.39 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 20, 1985; lowest water level recorded, 39.90 ft (12.16 m) below land-surface datum, July, 27, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	39.39	39.33	38.63	38.61	38.88	39.14	39.38	39.50	39.70	39.49	39.82	39.18
2	39.41	39.28	38.62	38.60	38.90	39.18	39.40	39.47	39.69	39.48	39.84	39.19
3	39.44	39.26	38.61	38.61	38.86	39.22	39.42	39.50	39.68	39.49	39.83	39.16
4	39.41	39.28	38.58	38.62	38.87	39.24	39.41	39.53	39.71	39.48	39.84	39.16
5	39.39	39.28	38.57	38.65	38.88	39.24	39.39	39.52	39.73	39.60	39.83	39.13
6	39.42	39.31	38.56	38.62	38.91	39.22	39.37	39.50	39.71	39.75	39.84	39.13
7	39.42	39.30	38.54	38.62	38.94	39.23	39.36	39.48	39.69	39.78	39.86	39.11
8	39.43	39.30	38.53	38.62	38.93	39.23	39.37	39.49	39.66	39.79	39.86	39.11
9	39.43	39.28	38.52	38.62	38.91	39.19	39.38	39.51	39.68	39.80	39.87	39.06
10	39.45	39.28	38.50	38.63	38.93	39.19	39.40	39.53	39.66	39.78	39.87	38.98
11	39.37	39.25	38.50	38.64	38.95	39.23	39.40	39.56	39.62	39.82	39.85	39.00
12	39.35	39.22	38.50	38.71	38.96	39.23	39.45	39.59	39.59	39.86	39.87	39.03
13	39.34	39.23	38.53	38.70	38.96	39.23	39.47	39.61	39.60	39.85	39.89	39.02
14	39.36	39.24	38.57	38.70	38.99	39.20	39.51	39.59	39.60	39.81	39.88	39.01
15	39.36	39.24	38.58	38.71	38.99	39.24	39.52	39.59	39.59	39.85	39.87	39.02
16	39.36	39.24	38.56	38.71	39.02	39.29	39.53	39.60	39.58	39.86	39.86	39.01
17	39.37	39.22	38.56	38.71	39.03	39.34	39.53	39.58	39.55	39.83	39.84	38.98
18	39.36	39.24	38.56	38.71	39.00	39.36	39.50	39.57	39.55	39.83	39.78	38.94
19	39.34	39.24	38.59	38.72	39.02	39.35	39.51	39.60	39.56	39.84	39.78	38.96
20	39.36	39.22	38.60	38.74	39.02	39.38	39.49	39.59	39.55	39.85	39.76	38.99
21	39.37	39.19	38.59	38.74	39.04	39.37	39.47	39.60	39.55	39.84	39.74	38.99
22	39.37	39.18	38.61	38.76	39.06	39.37	39.51	39.63	39.55	39.83	39.74	38.97
23	39.36	39.16	38.60	38.74	39.04	39.36	39.54	39.65	39.54	39.87	39.70	38.96
24	39.34	39.11	38.58	38.76	39.03	39.36	39.47	39.66	39.54	39.86	39.62	38.97
25	39.32	38.98	38.59	38.76	39.02	39.36	39.47	39.65	39.51	39.86	39.11	38.95
26	39.31	38.93	38.57	38.79	39.01	39.36	39.46	39.66	39.49	39.87	39.15	38.90
27	39.32	38.69	38.56	38.81	39.02	39.36	39.48	39.68	39.49	39.89	39.18	38.89
28	39.30	38.66	38.58	38.80	39.08	39.37	39.49	39.68	39.49	39.88	39.23	38.89
29	39.33	38.64	38.53	38.83	39.12	39.36	39.51	39.68	39.48	39.87	39.22	38.89
30	39.31	38.63	38.58	38.85	---	39.36	39.51	39.68	39.49	39.88	39.17	38.88
31	39.32	---	38.63	38.88	---	39.36	---	39.69	---	39.84	39.17	---
LOW	39.45	39.33	38.63	38.88	39.12	39.38	39.54	39.69	39.73	39.89	39.89	39.19
HIGH	39.30	38.63	38.50	38.60	38.86	39.14	39.36	39.47	39.48	39.48	39.11	38.88

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 39.27 LOW 39.89 HIGH 38.50

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

182018066593200. Local number, 83.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'18", long 66°59'32".

Owner: P.R. Energy and Power Authority.

Name: San Sebastian Well.

AQUIFER.--San Sebastian Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled observation well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 300 ft (91.4 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 230 ft (70.1 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.75 ft (0.84 m) above land-surface datum.

Prior November 1985, top of casing, 2.40 ft (0.73 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Formerly published as 182032066591800.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1967 to January 16, 1985. November 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 21.95 ft (6.69 m) below land-surface datum, May 8, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 40.20 ft (12.25 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 29, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	28.44	28.35	28.09	28.36	29.19	---	30.15	28.55	25.84	26.42	28.20	26.41
2	28.51	28.37	28.15	28.31	29.21	---	30.17	28.52	26.01	26.53	28.28	26.36
3	28.48	28.40	27.80	28.34	29.22	---	30.21	28.53	26.19	26.62	28.32	26.10
4	28.48	28.44	27.77	28.36	29.23	---	30.22	28.56	26.42	26.43	28.31	26.14
5	28.31	28.49	27.84	28.41	29.25	---	30.22	28.56	26.63	26.37	28.35	26.25
6	28.36	28.55	27.89	28.44	29.29	---	30.23	28.58	26.78	26.27	28.40	26.40
7	28.37	28.58	27.82	28.47	29.31	---	30.25	28.61	26.92	26.35	28.34	26.55
8	27.98	28.33	27.77	28.50	29.33	---	30.27	28.67	27.06	26.48	28.34	26.70
9	27.99	28.02	27.76	28.55	29.34	---	30.30	28.71	27.22	26.62	28.40	26.84
10	27.88	27.93	27.80	28.60	29.37	---	30.31	28.74	27.35	26.74	28.43	26.86
11	27.88	27.93	27.85	28.62	29.40	---	30.33	28.77	27.44	26.92	28.45	26.99
12	27.90	27.96	27.92	28.66	29.37	---	30.35	28.56	27.44	---	28.52	26.89
13	27.98	28.04	27.92	28.69	29.38	---	30.29	28.30	27.22	27.13	28.56	26.91
14	27.84	28.11	27.94	28.73	29.40	---	30.30	28.26	27.13	26.87	28.61	27.00
15	27.81	28.18	27.97	28.76	29.42	---	30.30	28.27	26.90	26.93	28.24	27.19
16	27.86	27.97	27.98	28.79	29.43	---	30.19	28.16	26.82	27.03	28.17	27.28
17	27.89	27.75	28.03	28.83	29.46	---	30.16	27.78	26.85	27.11	28.18	27.35
18	27.96	27.74	28.09	28.84	29.48	---	30.14	27.76	26.76	27.18	27.88	27.42
19	28.01	27.73	28.09	28.88	29.51	---	29.86	27.78	26.80	27.26	27.77	27.53
20	28.07	27.76	28.01	28.91	29.51	---	29.70	27.81	26.90	27.37	27.78	27.64
21	28.11	27.84	27.96	28.92	29.54	---	29.37	27.82	26.93	27.44	27.71	27.34
22	28.18	27.93	28.01	28.96	29.58	---	29.28	27.89	26.94	27.55	27.73	27.30
23	28.24	27.97	28.03	28.97	29.59	---	29.22	27.42	26.72	27.65	27.78	27.11
24	28.30	28.05	28.07	29.01	29.61	---	29.20	27.37	26.62	27.71	27.80	27.04
25	28.33	27.93	28.10	29.02	29.62	---	29.19	27.26	26.41	27.79	26.94	27.05
26	28.14	27.92	28.16	29.06	29.64	---	29.17	27.26	26.43	27.88	26.73	27.11
27	28.18	27.96	28.21	29.08	29.65	---	29.19	26.84	26.32	27.92	26.64	27.19
28	28.22	27.96	28.25	29.09	---	---	29.22	26.57	26.38	27.97	26.36	27.29
29	28.28	27.98	28.27	29.13	---	30.12	29.13	26.20	26.31	28.02	26.32	27.37
30	28.31	28.04	28.35	29.14	---	30.11	28.79	26.08	26.33	28.12	26.24	27.31
31	28.36	---	28.39	29.17	---	30.13	---	25.80	---	28.14	26.34	---
LOW	28.51	28.58	28.39	29.17	---	---	30.35	28.77	27.44	---	28.61	27.64
HIGH	27.81	27.73	27.76	28.31	---	---	28.79	25.80	25.84	---	26.24	26.10

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

RIO CULEBRINAS BASIN

182442067091700. Local number, 200 .
 LOCATION.--Lat 18°24'42", long 67°09'17".

Owner: Carmelo Sanchez

Name: Aguadilla Cement Well.

AQUIFER.--Surficial deposits.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Abandoned water-table industrial well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), perforated 11-20 ft (3.35-6.10 m). Depth 20 ft (6.10 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 10 ft (3.05 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Shelter floor on top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 3.25 ft (0.99 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 2.24 ft (0.68 m) below land-surface datum, Aug 25, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 8.46 ft (2.58 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 17, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	5.75	5.63	6.16	6.51	7.10	7.82	7.78	6.84	5.83	6.29	3.78	3.03
2	5.98	5.78	6.20	6.45	7.16	7.88	7.80	6.90	6.00	6.09	3.95	3.10
3	5.60	5.82	6.02	6.51	7.21	7.85	7.84	6.98	6.00	6.21	4.15	2.79
4	5.67	5.87	6.20	6.54	7.16	7.87	7.91	7.01	6.04	6.28	3.89	2.91
5	5.74	6.04	6.21	6.56	7.20	7.86	7.92	7.05	6.11	6.41	4.08	3.03
6	5.78	6.03	6.28	6.59	7.21	7.87	7.91	7.07	6.20	5.96	4.21	3.18
7	5.83	6.05	6.28	6.62	7.24	7.93	7.97	7.07	6.23	5.62	4.31	3.28
8	5.88	5.50	5.76	6.64	7.30	8.01	8.02	6.85	6.29	5.70	3.98	3.34
9	6.02	5.66	5.83	6.67	7.33	7.96	7.96	6.47	6.27	5.84	4.23	3.33
10	5.69	5.23	5.94	6.70	7.36	7.99	7.96	6.47	6.30	5.96	4.36	3.27
11	5.81	5.47	6.03	6.74	7.38	7.99	8.00	6.10	6.33	5.26	4.44	3.43
12	5.96	5.52	6.10	6.79	7.43	7.99	8.03	5.27	5.97	5.44	4.51	3.43
13	6.07	5.65	6.17	6.80	7.41	8.01	8.02	5.20	6.19	5.49	4.52	3.53
14	6.11	5.70	6.28	6.82	7.43	8.05	8.06	5.36	6.11	5.54	4.66	3.45
15	5.83	5.75	6.05	6.85	7.49	8.12	8.03	5.43	5.73	5.64	3.92	3.54
16	5.96	5.82	6.11	6.85	7.51	8.10	7.81	5.64	5.71	5.70	4.16	3.56
17	5.54	5.86	6.20	6.82	7.53	8.12	7.87	5.33	5.84	5.74	4.26	3.72
18	5.65	5.84	6.28	6.89	7.57	8.19	7.96	5.49	5.91	5.85	4.00	3.78
19	5.68	6.01	6.31	6.89	7.58	8.13	7.98	5.68	6.02	5.59	4.21	3.94
20	5.81	6.01	6.09	6.90	7.58	8.14	7.61	5.78	6.13	5.87	4.30	3.90
21	5.82	6.01	6.16	6.93	7.60	8.19	7.66	5.84	5.97	5.92	4.12	3.62
22	5.86	6.06	6.33	6.97	7.64	8.20	7.47	5.90	6.02	5.96	4.34	3.78
23	6.02	6.12	6.33	6.96	7.66	8.26	7.51	5.98	6.06	5.99	3.79	3.88
24	6.05	6.13	6.37	6.97	7.68	8.24	7.55	6.03	5.88	6.06	3.81	3.93
25	6.08	5.83	6.26	7.00	7.76	8.26	7.38	6.11	5.76	6.12	2.24	4.01
26	5.97	5.79	6.33	7.04	7.74	8.24	7.34	6.19	5.90	5.60	2.53	4.12
27	5.98	5.88	6.38	7.06	7.66	8.25	7.03	6.23	6.02	3.68	2.60	4.18
28	6.05	5.92	6.44	7.12	7.71	8.00	6.97	6.25	6.12	3.78	2.67	3.57
29	6.14	5.98	6.48	7.11	7.77	7.71	7.01	6.05	6.24	3.87	2.75	3.63
30	6.17	6.08	6.50	7.06	---	7.73	7.01	5.68	6.22	3.41	2.85	3.63
31	6.17	---	6.52	7.11	---	7.77	---	5.69	---	3.50	2.99	---
LOW	6.17	6.13	6.52	7.12	7.77	8.26	8.06	7.07	6.33	6.41	4.66	4.18
HIGH	5.54	5.23	5.76	6.45	7.10	7.71	6.97	5.20	5.71	3.41	2.24	2.79

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 6.08 LOW 8.26 HIGH 2.24

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

50252000 BONNE RESOLUTION GUT AT BONNE RESOLUTION, ST. THOMAS, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'57", long 64°57'34", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on right bank near Hull Bay Road, 0.5 mi (0.8 km) upstream from Atlantic Ocean, and 2.5 mi (4.02 km) northwest of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.49 mi² (1.27 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--December 1962 to February 1967, March 1979 to April 1981, May 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 280 ft (85 m), from topographic map. December 1962 to February 1967 at site about 100 ft (30 m) downstream at different datum. March 1979 to April 1981 at site about 100 ft (30 m) upstream at different datum.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--10 years (1964-66, 1980, 1983-88), 0.32 ft³/s (0.009 m³/s), 8.87 in/yr (225 mm/yr), 232 acre-ft/yr (0.286 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 0.38 ft³/s (0.01 m³/s), 275 acre ft/yr (0.34 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 1,650 ft³/s (46.7 m³/s), Apr. 18, 1983, gage height, 7.00 ft (2.134 m), from floodmarks, from rating curve extended above 1.0 ft³/s (0.03 m³/s) on basis of critical-depth analysis and slope-area measurement of peak flow; no flow at times in most years.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 50 ft³/s (1.42 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)	Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s)	Discharge (m ³ /s)	Gage height (ft)	Gage height (m)
Nov. 25	2045	333	9.43	3.12	0.951	May 10	1500	265	7.50	3.81	1.161
Nov. 27	2300	*1,440	40.8	*7.66	2.335	Aug. 24	1115	51	1.44	2.46	0.750

No flow many days.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.06	.17	e.06	e.05	.05	.03	.02	.11	.04	.08	.01	e.00
2	.06	.03	e.05	e.04	.04	.03	.02	.14	.03	.06	.01	e.00
3	.08	.02	e.07	e.04	.04	.04	.04	.17	.03	.05	.03	e.02
4	.04	.20	e.05	e.04	.04	.03	.04	.18	.03	.04	.01	e.00
5	.06	.07	e.04	e.04	.07	.04	.05	.16	.03	.04	.01	e.00
6	.06	.04	e.04	e.08	.04	.04	.03	.03	.03	.06	.01	e.00
7	.07	.04	e.05	e.04	.03	.04	.04	.07	.03	.98	.03	e.05
8	.05	.04	e.05	e.05	.03	.03	.05	.76	.03	.04	.02	e.05
9	.04	.05	e.04	e.04	.04	.03	.05	.14	.05	.03	.02	e.14
10	.05	.06	e.04	e.04	.03	.03	.07	10	.03	.03	.02	e.30
11	.07	.06	e.04	e.05	.03	.03	.07	.38	.03	.06	.01	e.20
12	.06	.07	e.12	e.06	.03	.03	.07	.11	.04	.03	.01	e.15
13	.14	.08	e.08	e.04	.03	.03	.07	.07	.04	.47	.01	e.11
14	.06	.10	e.05	e.06	.03	.03	.07	.06	.04	2.4	.01	e.07
15	.04	.10	e.06	e.04	.04	.03	.07	.06	.05	.05	.01	e.06
16	.14	.07	e.05	e.04	.03	.03	.06	.05	.02	.03	2.2	e.08
17	.31	.10	e.04	e.03	.04	.04	.05	.05	.02	.05	.19	e.08
18	.15	.06	e.04	e.03	.03	.08	.07	.05	.02	.02	.02	e.08
19	.07	.04	e.09	e.04	.03	.08	.09	.05	.02	.75	.01	e.08
20	.05	.03	e.10	e.03	.03	.07	.10	.04	.04	.05	.01	e.08
21	.05	.02	e.08	e.04	.04	.09	.11	.05	.02	.02	.01	e.08
22	.05	.02	e.11	e.05	.04	.07	.11	.05	.02	.02	.01	e.06
23	.07	.12	e.06	.06	.04	.03	.09	.04	.04	.02	.02	e.04
24	.04	.27	e.05	.04	.04	.01	.09	.05	.03	.02	4.0	e.03
25	.06	17	e.04	.05	.03	.02	.09	.04	02	.01	.16	e.02
26	.05	12	e.04	.05	.05	.03	.08	.05	.04	.01	.04	e.02
27	.05	e90	e.04	.04	.05	.09	.08	.05	.02	.01	.03	e.02
28	.04	e5.6	e.05	.06	.04	.07	.09	.05	.00	.02	e.02	e.02
29	.03	e.18	e.04	.04	.04	.22	.09	.20	.00	.02	e.03	e.02
30	.02	e.08	e.11	.04	---	.05	.10	.07	.32	.02	e.05	e.02
31	.02	---	e.06	.04	---	.04	---	.05	---	.01	e.04	---
TOTAL	2.14	126.72	1.84	1.39	1.10	1.51	2.06	13.38	1.16	5.50	7.06	15.74
MEAN	.069	4.22	.059	.045	.038	.049	.069	.43	.039	.18	.23	.52
MAX	.31	90	.12	.08	.07	.22	.11	10	.32	2.4	4.0	14
MIN	.02	.02	.04	.03	.03	.01	.02	.03	.00	.01	.01	.00
AC-FT	4.2	251	3.6	2.8	2.2	3.0	4.1	27	2.3	11	14	31
CFSM	.14	8.62	.12	.09	.08	.10	.14	.88	.08	.36	.46	1.07
IN.	.16	9.62	.14	.11	.08	.11	.16	1.02	.09	.42	.54	1.19

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 245.03 MEAN .67 MAX 90 MIN .01 AC-FT 486 CFSM 1.37 IN. 18.60
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 179.60 MEAN .49 MAX 90 MIN .00 AC-FT 356 CFSM 1.00 IN. 13.63

e Estimated

ST. THOMAS U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50252000 BONNE RESOLUTION GUT AT BONNE RESOLUTION, ST. THOMAS, VI--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS MARCH 1983 TO JANUARY 1985, JANUARY 1988 TO AUGUST 1988

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
JAN, 21	1310	--	1564	23.0	JUN, 01	1024	0.03	--	25.0
MAR, 23	0923	0.05	--	23.0	AUG, 25	1153	0.11	--	25.0

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50276000 TURPENTINE RUN AT MARIENDAL, ST. THOMAS, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'48", long 64°52'58", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, on right bank, at Mariendal, 1.0 mi (1.6 km) upstream from mouth, and 3.3 mi (5.3 km) southeast of Fort Christian, Charlotte Amalie.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.97 mi² (7.69 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to April 1969, October 1978 to September 1980, June 1982 to July 1986, July 1986 to current year (high-water discharges only).

GAGE.--Crest-stage gage. Elevation of gage is 40 ft (12 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor, peak discharges only.

AVERAGE DISCHARGES.--10 years (1964-68, 1979-80, 1983-85), 1.22 ft³/s (0.034 m³/s), 5.58 in/yr (142 mm/yr), 884 acre-ft/yr (1.09 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 0.54 ft³/s (0.015 m³/s), 390 acre-ft/yr (0.48 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 9,710 ft³/s (275 m³/s), Apr. 18, 1963, gage height, 11.09 ft (3.380 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 500 ft³/s (14.2 m³/s) on basis of slope area measurement and step-backwater analysis; no flow many days from 1963 to 1969, and in 1984.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 100 ft³/s (2.83 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height		Date	Time	Discharge		Gage height	
		(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)			(ft ³ /s)	(m ³ /s)	(ft)	(m)
Nov. 27	2315	*1,760	49.8	*6.24	1.902	Sept. 9	1030	821	23.2	5.27	1.606

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50295000 GUINEA GUT AT BETHANY, ST. JOHN, VI

LOCATION.--Lat. 18°19'55", long 64°46'50", Hydrologic Unit 21020001, 600 ft (133 m) southeast of Bethany Church, and 1.0 mi (1.6 km) east of Government House at Cruz Bay.

DRAINAGE AREA.--0.37 mi² (0.96 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to October 1967, September 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder and concrete control. Elevation of gage is 260 ft (79 m), from topographic map. Prior to September 1982, at datum 1.00 ft (0.30 m) higher.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--10 years (1964-67, 1983-88), 0.091 ft³/s (0.003 m³/s), 3.34 in/yr (85 mm/yr), 65.93 acre-ft/yr (0.081 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 0.04 ft³/s (0.001 m³/s), 29.0 acre ft/yr (0.04 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 946 ft³/s (26.8 m³/s), Apr. 18, 1983, gage height, 5.33 ft (1.625 m), from floodmark, from rating curve extended above 1.0 ft³/s (0.028 m³/s) on basis of step-backwater analysis and slope-area measurement of peak flow; no flow many days each year.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 10 ft³/s (0.283 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s) (m ³ /s)		Gage height (ft) (m)		Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s) (m ³ /s)		Gage height (ft) (m)	
Nov. 27	2245	*270	7.65	*3.56	1.085	Sept. 9	1000	171	4.84	3.12	0.951
Nov. 28	2000	46	1.30	2.43	0.741						

No flow many days.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.00	.01	.02	.02	.01	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.01
2	.00	.01	.02	.02	.01	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.02
3	.00	.01	.02	.02	.01	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.02
4	.01	.01	.02	.02	.01	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.02	.02
5	.00	.01	.02	.01	.01	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.02
6	.00	.01	.02	.01	.01	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.02
7	.01	.01	.02	.01	.01	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.02
8	.01	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.03
9	.01	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	15
10	.01	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	1.3
11	.00	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.65
12	.00	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.24
13	.01	.01	.02	.01	.01	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.17
14	.01	.01	.02	.01	.01	.0	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.13
15	.02	.01	.02	.01	.01	.0	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.10
16	.02	.01	.02	.01	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.00	.13	.10
17	.02	.01	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.09	.10
18	.02	.01	.02	.01	.00	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.06	.10
19	.01	.01	.02	.01	.00	.02	.02	.01	.00	.00	.06	.10
20	.02	.01	.02	.02	.01	.01	.01	.01	.00	.00	.06	.10
21	.02	.01	.02	.01	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.03	.10
22	.01	.01	.02	.01	.00	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.02	.10
23	.01	.01	.02	.04	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.03	.09
24	.01	.01	.02	.02	.02	.01	.01	.00	.00	.00	.10	.07
25	.01	.03	.02	.02	.03	.0	.00	.00	.00	.00	.02	.07
26	.01	1.7	.02	.01	.04	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01	.07
27	.01	11	.02	.01	.01	.0	.00	.01	.01	.00	.01	.06
28	.01	5.6	.02	.01	.00	.0	.00	.01	.00	.00	.02	.06
29	.01	1.2	.02	.01	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00	.00	.02	.06
30	.01	.03	.02	.01	---	.01	.00	.01	.00	.01	.03	.06
31	.01	---	.02	.01	---	.01	---	.0	---	.01	.01	---
TOTAL	0.30	19.80	0.62	0.41	0.24	0.14	0.23	0.08	0.01	0.02	0.82	18.99
MEAN	.010	.66	.020	.013	.008	.005	.008	.003	.000	.001	.026	.63
MAX	.02	11	.02	.04	.04	.02	.02	.01	.01	.01	.13	.15
MIN	.00	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.01
AC-FT	.6	39	1.2	.8	.5	.3	.5	.2	.02	.04	1.6	.38
CFSM	.03	1.78	.05	.04	.02	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.07	1.71
IN.	.03	1.99	.06	.04	.02	.01	.02	.01	.00	.00	.08	1.91

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 22.66 MEAN .062 MAX 11 MIN .00 AC-FT 45 CFSM .17 IN. 2.28
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 41.66 MEAN .11 MAX 15 MIN .00 AC-FT 83 CFSM .31 IN. 4.19

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50345000 JOLLY HILL GUT AT JOLLY HILL, ST. CROIX, VI

LOCATION.--Lat 17°44'00", long 64°51'47", Hydrologic Unit 21020002, on Mahogany Road at Jolly Hill, 1.8 mi (2.9 km) northeast of Frederiksted.

DRAINAGE AREA.--2.10 mi² (5.44 km²).

WATER-DISCHARGE RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1963 to December 1968. Monthly measurements, 1962, 69. October 1982 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder, crest-stage gage and sharp-crested concrete control. Elevation of gage is 140 ft (43 m), from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Records poor.

AVERAGE DISCHARGE.--11 years (1964-68, 1983-88), 0.159 ft³/s (0.004 m³/s), 1.03 in/yr (26 mm/yr), 115 acre-ft/yr (0.14 hm³/yr); median of yearly mean discharges, 0.04 ft³/s (0.001 m³/s), 29.0 acre-ft/yr (0.04 hm³/yr).

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Maximum discharge, 430 ft³/s (12.18 m³/s), Nov.27, 1987, gage height, 4.14 ft (1.262 m); no flow many days each year.

EXTREMES FOR CURRENT YEAR.--Peak discharges greater than base discharge of 25 ft³/s (0.71 m³/s) and maximum (*):

Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s) (m ³ /s)		Gage height (ft) (m)		Date	Time	Discharge (ft ³ /s) (m ³ /s)		Gage height (ft) (m)	
Nov. 25	0400	33	0.934	2.09	0.637	Nov. 27	2145	*430	12.18	*4.14	1.262
Nov. 26	1330	26	0.736	1.99	0.606						

No flow many days.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.06	.01	5.2	1.4	.84	.34	.16	.16	.05	e.02	e.04	.06
2	.06	.01	4.2	1.2	.81	.33	.16	.14	.05	e.04	e.04	.06
3	.06	.01	3.8	1.0	.78	.33	.14	.17	.04	e.04	e.03	.06
4	.05	.00	3.5	.86	.73	.33	.14	.18	.04	e.04	e.03	.06
5	.04	.00	3.3	.99	.71	.33	.14	.21	.04	e.04	e.04	.06
6	.04	.00	3.2	1.0	.71	.30	.59	.22	.04	e.04	e.04	.05
7	.04	.00	3.4	1.0	.69	.28	.19	.19	.04	e.10	e.02	.04
8	.04	.00	3.5	1.0	.65	.30	.19	.18	.04	e.04	e.04	.03
9	.04	.00	3.0	.99	.64	.27	.20	.18	.04	e.04	e.04	.05
10	.03	.01	2.7	.90	.62	.24	.20	.22	.04	e.04	e.10	.06
11	.03	.01	2.5	.84	.59	.24	.20	.20	.05	e.04	e.07	.15
12	.03	.00	2.4	.84	.57	.24	.20	.20	.05	e.02	e.08	.08
13	.03	.00	2.1	.86	.58	.22	.20	.20	.06	e.04	e.04	.07
14	.03	.00	2.0	.86	.52	.22	.20	.22	.06	e.10	e.04	.08
15	.04	.00	1.8	.85	.52	.21	.20	.22	.07	e.04	e.04	.07
16	.06	.00	1.6	.89	.52	.18	.20	.20	.07	e.04	e.03	.07
17	.05	.00	1.6	.70	.52	.18	.21	.20	.07	e.03	e.07	.07
18	.04	.00	2.9	.75	.52	.17	.25	.20	.07	e.04	e.04	.07
19	.03	.00	3.9	.78	.50	.16	.24	.20	.06	e.05	e.03	.07
20	.02	.00	2.3	.82	.46	.16	.24	.20	.11	e.04	e.02	.07
21	.01	.00	1.5	.82	.43	.16	.24	.20	.12	e.03	e.04	.07
22	.01	.00	1.4	.82	.41	.16	.24	.19	.10	e.04	e.03	.07
23	.01	.12	1.2	.77	.41	.16	.24	.20	e.04	e.04	e.04	.07
24	.01	2.0	1.2	.75	.41	.19	.23	.20	e.07	e.04	.07	.06
25	.01	6.4	1.2	.87	.40	.20	.22	.20	e.04	e.03	.08	.05
26	.01	5.8	1.2	.84	.39	.18	.22	.20	e.04	e.02	.08	.06
27	.01	22	1.1	.82	.39	.18	.21	e.20	e.09	e.02	.06	.06
28	.02	19	1.1	.78	.38	.18	.18	e.22	e.03	e.06	.06	.07
29	.02	8.5	1.1	.81	.36	.22	.18	e.26	e.04	e.03	.06	.07
30	.02	6.0	1.3	.80	---	.19	.18	e.08	e.05	e.03	.06	.07
31	.01	---	1.2	.82	---	.18	---	e.06	---	e.02	.06	---
TOTAL	0.96	69.87	72.4	27.43	16.06	7.03	6.39	5.90	1.71	1.24	1.52	1.98
MEAN	.031	2.33	2.34	.88	.55	.23	.21	.19	.057	.040	.049	.066
MAX	.06	22	5.2	1.4	.84	.34	.59	.26	.12	.10	.10	.15
MIN	.01	.00	1.1	.70	.36	.16	.14	.06	.03	.02	.02	.03
AC-FT	1.9	139	144	54	32	14	13	12	3.4	2.5	3.0	3.9
CFSM	.01	1.11	1.11	.42	.26	.11	.10	.09	.03	.02	.02	.03
IN.	.02	1.24	1.28	.49	.28	.12	.11	.10	.03	.02	.03	.04

CAL YR 1987 TOTAL 213.39 MEAN .58 MAX 22 MIN .00 AC-FT 423 CFSM .28 IN. 3.78
WTR YR 1988 TOTAL 212.49 MEAN .58 MAX 22 MIN .00 AC-FT 421 CFSM .28 IN. 3.76

e Estimated

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

50345000 JOLLY HILL GUT AT JOLLY HILL, ST. CROIX, VI--Continued

WATER QUALITY RECORDS

PERIOD OF RECORD.--WATER YEARS MARCH 1983 TO JANUARY 1985, OCTOBER 1987 TO JUNE 1988

WATER-QUALITY DATA, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988

DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)	DATE	TIME	STREAMFLOW, INSTANTANEOUS (CFS)	SPECIFIC CON- DUCTANCE (UMHOS)	TEMPERA- TURE (DEG C)
OCT, 06	1421	0.04	1116	26.0	JUN, 01	1017	--	1020	25.0
JAN, 19	1420	0.78	812	24.0					

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

**Ground-Water Records
for
U.S. Virgin Islands**

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174225064471900. Local number, 1.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'25", long 64°47'19".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Fairplains 6 (FP6).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 20 ft (6.10 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of pump concrete base, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 15.64 ft (4.77 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 25, 1982; lowest water level measured, a59.08 ft (18.0 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 6, 1987.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 6	a59.08	Mar. 21	a56.07	May 31	a56.90	Aug. 23	17.05
Jan. 19	a56.26						

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174225064472000. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'25", long 64°47'20".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: USGS-10, Fairplains 2 (FP2).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 20 ft (6.10 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at concrete base wall, 3.00 ft (0.91 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 20.82 ft (6.34 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 22, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 25.02 ft (7.63 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 22, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	23.13	23.16	22.48	21.21	21.58	21.82	22.13	21.97	22.42	22.06	21.96	21.49
2	23.18	23.13	22.42	21.24	21.34	21.82	22.04	21.95	22.47	22.04	21.91	21.47
3	23.28	23.11	22.35	21.25	21.32	21.85	21.98	22.04	22.53	22.01	21.86	21.34
4	23.33	23.06	22.32	21.25	21.27	21.88	22.08	22.17	22.42	21.96	21.83	21.32
5	23.36	22.95	22.12	21.25	21.26	21.88	21.99	22.20	22.57	21.93	21.81	21.32
6	23.39	23.05	22.03	21.17	21.23	21.86	21.94	22.13	22.59	22.02	21.82	21.32
7	23.43	23.05	21.94	21.11	21.20	21.85	21.93	22.18	22.73	22.06	21.82	21.32
8	23.45	23.03	21.88	21.15	21.11	21.86	21.95	22.18	22.64	22.03	21.90	21.27
9	23.48	23.04	21.82	21.11	21.13	21.78	21.97	22.04	22.51	22.06	21.93	21.24
10	23.48	23.07	21.79	21.16	21.16	21.73	22.08	22.24	22.45	22.02	21.95	21.23
11	23.48	23.07	21.69	21.07	21.18	21.77	22.09	22.24	22.47	22.07	21.98	21.18
12	23.47	23.05	21.63	21.02	21.20	21.83	22.22	22.38	22.49	22.11	21.95	21.14
13	23.47	22.91	21.58	20.96	21.19	21.84	22.31	22.47	22.46	22.19	21.88	21.10
14	23.46	22.87	21.53	21.01	21.21	21.86	22.37	22.50	22.57	22.19	21.84	21.08
15	23.45	22.83	21.43	21.02	21.22	21.92	22.41	22.37	22.63	22.22	21.82	21.06
16	23.44	22.82	21.51	21.01	21.26	21.98	22.46	22.26	22.67	22.21	21.81	21.07
17	23.42	22.84	21.45	21.13	21.27	21.93	22.46	22.18	22.63	22.18	21.72	21.06
18	23.41	22.84	21.41	21.16	21.58	21.90	22.38	22.17	22.57	22.19	21.70	21.05
19	23.27	22.78	21.34	21.17	21.58	21.88	22.37	22.16	22.64	22.10	21.70	21.02
20	23.15	23.19	21.29	21.15	21.56	21.93	22.34	22.17	22.69	22.03	21.70	20.98
21	23.29	23.27	21.28	20.86	21.47	21.96	22.32	22.14	22.41	21.97	21.69	20.96
22	23.30	23.27	21.27	20.98	21.47	22.07	22.31	22.11	22.30	21.95	21.69	20.94
23	23.32	23.33	21.32	21.18	21.60	22.06	22.27	22.03	22.23	21.99	21.68	20.96
24	23.32	23.28	21.12	21.25	21.50	22.07	22.23	22.01	22.29	22.03	21.61	20.96
25	23.31	23.14	21.24	21.32	21.65	22.10	22.24	22.06	22.30	22.09	21.58	20.96
26	23.30	23.06	21.25	21.38	21.73	22.12	22.08	22.12	22.32	22.11	21.58	20.97
27	23.29	22.89	21.24	21.44	21.75	22.22	22.03	22.25	22.25	22.10	21.54	21.00
28	23.30	22.74	21.23	21.47	21.80	22.21	21.98	22.27	22.17	22.00	21.55	21.01
29	23.28	22.61	21.22	21.53	21.76	22.22	21.99	22.27	22.11	21.93	21.56	21.17
30	23.26	22.56	21.22	21.56	---	22.25	21.99	22.25	22.08	21.97	21.55	21.08
31	23.23	---	21.17	21.58	---	22.25	---	22.27	---	22.00	21.51	---
LOW	23.48	23.33	22.48	21.58	21.80	22.25	22.46	22.50	22.73	22.22	21.98	21.49
HIGH	23.13	22.56	21.12	20.86	21.11	21.73	21.93	21.95	22.08	21.93	21.51	20.94

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 22.02 LOW 23.48 HIGH 20.86

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174243064475100. Local number, 3.
 LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'43", long 64°47'51".
 Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.
 Name: Golden Grove-6 (PW6).
 AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.
 WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.20 m), cased 8 in (0.20 m).
 DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.
 Measuring point: Upper edge of hole at 8 in (0.20 m) casing, 4.20 ft (1.28 m) above land-surface datum.
 REMARKS.--Recording observation well. Estimated record; Jan. 8-18, Feb. 4 to Mar. 21.
 PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.
 EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 13.73 ft (4.18 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 12, 1988; lowest water level recorded, 29.27 ft (8.90 m) below land-surface datum, May 30-31, June 1-5, 1987.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
 INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	26.14	27.02	16.12	15.88	17.90	20.06	21.97	23.12	24.25	24.92	24.81	25.08
2	26.17	27.04	15.11	15.06	18.00	20.13	22.00	23.16	24.27	24.93	24.83	25.09
3	26.21	27.06	14.58	14.43	18.09	20.21	22.05	23.23	24.29	24.94	24.84	25.10
4	26.23	27.09	14.38	14.00	18.19	20.28	22.07	23.27	24.32	24.96	24.86	25.10
5	26.27	27.13	14.48	13.78	18.31	20.35	22.09	23.31	24.37	24.99	24.87	25.11
6	26.29	27.16	14.68	13.88	18.38	20.42	22.12	23.33	24.39	25.01	24.89	25.12
7	26.30	27.18	14.91	14.10	18.45	20.49	22.14	23.36	24.42	25.02	24.92	25.13
8	26.32	27.21	14.86	14.26	18.52	20.56	22.18	23.39	24.44	25.03	24.93	25.13
9	26.37	27.22	14.27	14.42	18.59	20.62	22.23	23.46	24.50	25.04	24.94	25.13
10	26.39	27.24	13.99	14.58	18.67	20.69	22.26	23.49	24.53	25.05	24.92	25.14
11	26.40	27.26	13.86	14.74	18.74	20.76	22.30	23.54	24.53	25.08	24.93	25.15
12	26.45	27.29	13.76	14.89	18.81	20.83	22.36	23.59	24.54	25.12	24.93	25.15
13	26.48	27.32	13.94	15.05	18.88	20.90	22.40	23.61	24.60	25.12	24.94	25.16
14	26.52	27.35	14.21	15.20	18.95	20.97	22.45	23.63	24.64	25.11	24.93	25.17
15	26.55	27.37	14.48	15.36	19.02	21.04	22.50	23.67	24.65	25.07	24.94	25.18
16	26.57	27.38	14.69	15.51	19.09	21.11	22.53	23.72	24.65	24.97	24.95	25.18
17	26.60	27.41	14.89	15.71	19.16	21.18	22.57	23.73	24.69	24.87	24.94	25.19
18	26.62	27.44	15.07	15.88	19.22	21.25	22.62	23.76	24.72	24.81	24.95	25.20
19	26.65	27.46	15.25	16.14	19.29	21.32	22.65	23.80	24.75	24.76	24.96	25.21
20	26.66	27.50	15.43	16.28	19.36	21.39	22.68	23.84	24.77	24.71	24.97	25.21
21	26.68	27.52	15.57	16.42	19.43	21.54	22.71	23.89	24.76	24.68	24.98	25.22
22	26.74	27.53	15.77	16.56	19.50	21.59	22.77	23.95	24.78	24.69	25.00	25.23
23	26.78	27.55	15.92	16.68	19.57	21.62	22.83	23.98	24.79	24.70	25.00	25.24
24	26.81	27.55	16.03	16.84	19.64	21.66	22.86	24.01	24.81	24.72	25.01	25.24
25	26.84	27.33	16.20	16.95	19.71	21.70	22.90	24.02	24.82	24.74	25.02	25.24
26	26.87	25.94	16.35	17.11	19.78	21.73	22.94	24.06	24.83	24.76	25.03	25.25
27	26.89	24.30	16.51	17.26	19.85	21.77	22.99	24.10	24.85	24.78	25.03	25.26
28	26.92	21.85	16.67	17.39	19.92	21.81	23.02	24.13	24.87	24.79	25.05	25.26
29	26.95	19.23	16.81	17.55	19.99	21.85	23.07	24.15	24.89	24.79	25.06	25.27
30	26.97	17.57	17.00	17.71	---	21.88	23.10	24.18	24.90	24.81	25.07	25.28
31	27.01	---	16.69	17.81	---	21.92	---	24.22	---	24.80	25.07	---
LOW	27.01	27.55	17.00	17.81	19.99	21.92	23.10	24.22	24.90	25.12	25.07	25.28
HIGH	26.14	17.57	13.76	13.78	17.90	20.06	21.97	23.12	24.25	24.68	24.81	25.08

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 22.48 LOW 27.55 HIGH 13.76

GROUND-WATER LEVELS
ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174245064475800. Local number, 4.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°42'45", long 64°47'58".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Golden Grove - 1 (PW1).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m), 0-104 ft (0-31.70 m), perforated 64-104 ft (19.51-31.70 m). Depth 104 ft (31.70 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Lower edge of 1 in. (0.02 m) pipe at pump base, 3.40 ft (1.04 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--January 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD: Highest water level measured, a20.76 ft (6.33 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 19, 1988; lowest water level measured, a58.30 ft (17.77 m) below land-surface datum, September 27, 1983.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 6	28.12	Mar. 21	a23.04	May 31	a23.26	Aug. 23	a27.76
Jan. 19	a20.76						

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174303064484400. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'03", long 64°48'44".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Adventure 28.

AQUIFER.--Alluvium of Pleistocene age and marl of Oligocene age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 4 in (0.10 m), cased 4 in (0.10 m). Depth 97 ft (29.6 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 80 ft (24.39 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Upper edge of hole at 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum. Prior June 20, 1983, top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 0.90 ft (0.27 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1973 to March 1974, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 24.90 ft (7.59 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 25, 1982; lowest water level recorded, 40.18 ft (12.25 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 5, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	38.04	38.21	35.84	32.12	30.76	31.36	31.46	31.85	32.42	32.15	31.46	30.84
2	38.07	38.20	35.49	31.88	30.79	31.38	31.47	31.85	32.46	32.11	31.49	30.88
3	38.10	38.19	35.16	31.73	30.76	31.43	31.46	31.91	32.47	32.10	31.54	30.87
4	38.11	38.19	34.87	31.55	30.75	31.46	31.44	31.94	32.51	32.09	31.55	30.92
5	38.13	38.18	34.58	31.39	30.76	31.46	31.43	31.97	32.55	32.08	31.57	30.96
6	38.15	38.18	34.35	31.28	30.77	31.46	31.41	31.97	32.56	32.08	31.62	31.01
7	38.15	38.19	34.13	31.21	30.79	31.46	31.37	32.01	32.57	32.05	31.67	31.01
8	38.17	38.19	33.71	31.14	30.80	31.49	31.36	32.03	32.58	32.05	31.70	31.03
9	38.18	38.19	33.69	31.08	30.82	31.48	31.38	32.07	32.61	32.01	31.71	30.95
10	38.19	38.19	33.46	31.04	30.89	31.49	31.39	32.10	32.63	31.97	31.56	30.83
11	38.20	38.19	33.27	30.99	30.92	31.51	31.39	32.03	32.61	31.98	31.47	30.83
12	38.21	38.19	33.13	30.95	30.94	31.53	31.44	32.06	32.58	31.98	31.34	30.79
13	38.22	38.19	33.04	30.92	30.95	31.52	31.45	32.07	32.54	32.01	31.22	30.72
14	38.23	38.19	32.96	30.90	31.00	31.51	31.48	32.02	32.55	31.93	31.14	30.68
15	38.24	38.21	32.88	30.89	31.03	31.54	31.50	32.08	32.57	31.90	31.11	30.64
16	38.24	38.21	32.80	30.87	31.09	31.55	31.52	32.16	32.56	31.81	31.08	30.60
17	38.25	38.21	32.73	30.85	31.10	31.59	31.53	32.15	32.56	31.69	31.01	30.57
18	38.25	38.21	32.69	30.82	31.10	31.62	31.54	32.16	32.59	31.61	30.98	30.55
19	38.25	38.21	32.67	30.82	31.13	31.62	31.54	32.18	32.60	31.58	31.01	30.54
20	38.25	38.21	32.65	30.80	31.17	31.64	31.54	32.21	32.60	31.57	31.00	30.51
21	38.24	38.21	32.60	30.81	31.21	31.71	31.55	32.24	32.46	31.55	31.02	30.51
22	38.24	38.21	32.57	30.80	31.25	31.71	31.59	32.28	32.40	31.53	30.99	30.46
23	38.23	38.21	32.55	30.77	31.25	31.66	31.65	32.30	32.38	31.52	30.95	30.46
24	38.23	38.22	32.51	30.85	31.24	31.63	31.64	32.34	32.35	31.52	30.91	30.44
25	38.23	38.22	32.49	30.80	31.23	31.62	31.65	32.36	32.31	31.50	30.87	30.41
26	38.22	38.22	32.47	30.80	31.24	31.61	31.70	32.36	32.26	31.51	30.86	30.41
27	38.22	38.18	32.44	30.76	31.25	31.59	31.73	32.37	32.23	31.52	30.85	30.47
28	38.22	38.18	32.43	30.74	31.30	31.55	31.76	32.38	32.21	31.52	30.86	30.47
29	38.22	38.16	32.38	30.73	31.32	31.52	31.79	32.39	32.20	31.48	30.85	30.48
30	38.22	38.16	32.37	30.77	---	31.48	31.82	32.40	32.18	31.43	30.82	30.49
31	38.21	---	32.23	30.78	---	31.45	---	32.40	---	31.44	30.81	---
LOW	38.25	38.22	35.84	32.12	31.32	31.71	31.82	32.40	32.63	32.15	31.71	31.03
HIGH	38.04	38.16	32.23	30.73	30.75	31.36	31.36	31.85	32.18	31.43	30.81	30.41

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 32.76 LOW 38.25 HIGH 30.41

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174525064460600. Local number, 7.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'25", long 64°46'06".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Concordia 14.

AQUIFER.--Sand and gravel.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Depth 85 ft (25.91 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.50 in (0.01 m) pipe on top of pump concrete base, 2.30 ft (0.70 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumpage.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 10.76 ft (3.28 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 19, 1988; lowest water level measured, 41.75 ft (12.73 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 24, 1983.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 6	19.34	Mar. 21	14.26	May 31	18.40	Aug. 23	18.34
Jan. 19	10.76						

174527064460100. Local number, 8.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'27", long 64°46'01".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Concordia 1 (Main pump house).

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Depth 82 ft (25.0 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 40 ft (12.2 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumpage.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 14.03 ft (4.28 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 19, 1988; lowest water level measured, 28.39 ft (8.66 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 8, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 6	19.86	Mar. 21	16.42	May 31	19.02	Aug. 23	18.92
Jan. 19	14.03						

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. CROIX, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

174532064460300. Local number, 9.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°45'32", long 64°46'03".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Concordia 7.

AQUIFER.--Limestone of Tertiary Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-81 ft (0-24.7 m). Depth 81 ft (24.7 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 35 ft (10.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole in pump base, 2.20 ft (0.67 m) above land-surface datum. Previous to Mar. 25, 1982, hole in pump base 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--June 1962 to October 1968, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 1.75 ft (0.53 m) below land-surface datum, May 11, 1966; lowest water level measured, 57.40 ft (17.5 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 5, 1964.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 6	a21.53	Mar. 21	a18.25	May 31	a14.50	Aug. 23	a16.40
Jan. 19	a13.63						

174329064454700. Local number, 10.

LOCATION.--Lat 17°43'29", long 64°45'47".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Barren Spot 5 (PWD-5).

AQUIFER.--Alluvium and marl.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled production water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-130 ft (0-39.63 m), perforated 71-130 ft (21.64-39.63 m). Depth 130 ft (39.63 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 75 ft (22.86 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on top of pump base, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 61.86 ft (18.86 m) below land-surface datum, Mar. 26, 1982; lowest water level measured, a75.52 ft (a23.02 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 8, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 6	a74.25	Mar. 21	a68.55	May 31	a68.55	Aug. 24	a68.18
Jan. 19	a68.52						

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182050064580400. Local number, 1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'50", long 64°58'04".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: USGS-8 (Family well - Thatch Farm).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m) 0-25 ft (0-7.62 m), open hole 25-80 ft (7.62-24.4 m). Depth 80 ft (24.4 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 80 ft (24.4 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.50 ft (0.76 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to Mar. 23, 1982, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Non-potable public-water supply and observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1963 to August 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 2.33 ft (0.71 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 20, 1984; lowest water level measured, 57.94 ft (17.66 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 21, 1987.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 6	32.78	Mar. 21	32.14	June 1	35.63	Aug. 25	36.10
Jan. 19	19.41						

182138064543100. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'38", long 64°54'31".

Owner: Mahogany Run Resort.

Name: Mahogany 15.

AQUIFER.--Fractured rocks.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 145 ft (44.21 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 120 ft (36.6 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.20 ft (0.36 m) below land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.45 ft (3.79 m) below land-surface datum, July 1, 1986; lowest water level measured, 88.62 ft (27.01 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 4, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 8	29.72	Mar. 23	23.49	June 1	32.36	Aug. 25	42.46
Jan. 21	14.19						

182138064542500. Local number, 3.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'38", long 64°54'25".

Owner: Mahogany Run Resort.

Name: Mahogany 16.

AQUIFER.--Fractured rocks.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 145 ft (44.21 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 130 ft (39.6 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) below land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 10.25 (3.12 m) below land-surface datum Jan. 21, 1988; lowest water level measured, 103.85 ft (31.65 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 4, 1984.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 8	35.33	Mar. 23	29.13	June 1	37.83	Aug. 25	45.16
Jan. 21	10.25						

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182136064541900. Local number, 4.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'36", long 64°54'19".

Owner: Mahogany Run Resort

Name: Mahogany 17.

AQUIFER.--Fractured rock.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Depth 145 ft (44.21 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 140 ft (42.7 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing at land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Public water supply. Water levels affected by nearby pumping well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 17.49 ft (5.33 m) below land-surface datum, Dec. 11 1985; lowest water level measured, 60.40 ft (18.41 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 10, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 8	36.70	Mar. 23	31.17	June 1	38.80	Aug. 25	40.60
Jan. 21	20.23						

182029064535200. Local number, 5.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'29", long 64°53'52".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government, V.I. Housing Authority.

Name: Donoe 3.

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rock undifferentiated. Fracture at 165 ft (50.3 m), from drilling log.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), open hole 20-400 ft (6.10-122 m). Depth 400 ft (122 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 235 ft (71.6 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.30 ft (0.70 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 54.24 ft (16.53 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 20, 1984; lowest water level measured, 90.98 ft (27.73 m) below land-surface datum, Apr. 30, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 8	79.40	Jan. 21	66.95	Mar. 22	81.23	Aug. 25	58.59

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. THOMAS, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182038064550300. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'38", long 64°55'03".

Owner: U.S. Government, Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Grade School 3.

AQUIFER.--Volcanic breccia.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 8 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 70 ft (21.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

Prior to June 27, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.90 ft (0.88 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.72 ft (1.13 m) below land-surface datum, May 22, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 35.38 ft (10.79 m) below land-surface datum, July 21, 1982.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	25.99	24.11	8.52	10.75	16.75	19.77	22.82	23.77	23.77	22.80	23.77	21.75
2	26.01	24.16	8.36	10.77	16.95	19.95	22.89	23.77	23.87	22.52	23.95	21.99
3	26.02	24.22	8.33	10.88	17.13	20.13	22.99	23.77	23.94	22.39	24.09	22.22
4	26.03	24.32	8.38	11.02	17.29	20.29	23.11	23.77	24.00	22.37	24.13	22.45
5	26.06	24.18	8.49	11.18	17.42	20.44	23.22	23.80	24.07	22.46	24.09	22.67
6	26.11	24.07	8.60	11.37	17.41	20.59	23.32	23.85	24.15	22.60	24.09	22.85
7	26.16	24.08	8.68	11.57	17.33	20.75	23.38	23.90	24.24	22.72	24.14	23.02
8	26.21	24.18	8.81	11.71	17.32	20.92	23.40	23.91	24.32	22.48	24.23	23.19
9	26.26	24.34	8.88	11.88	17.35	21.06	23.39	23.48	24.38	22.33	24.35	22.75
10	26.33	24.46	9.00	12.01	17.41	21.20	23.37	22.91	24.40	22.32	24.41	18.19
11	26.39	24.60	9.12	12.21	17.50	21.33	23.37	22.43	24.42	22.43	24.40	16.82
12	26.45	24.73	9.05	12.34	17.64	21.45	23.38	22.13	24.42	22.60	24.39	15.53
13	26.50	24.82	9.11	12.50	17.78	21.55	23.42	21.98	24.20	22.76	24.42	14.74
14	26.53	24.90	9.20	12.62	17.88	21.62	23.49	21.93	23.90	22.91	24.47	14.35
15	26.55	24.86	9.38	12.73	17.97	21.70	23.56	21.91	23.69	22.93	24.56	14.30
16	26.49	24.83	9.51	12.95	18.05	21.79	23.63	21.92	23.32	22.96	24.63	14.44
17	26.35	24.84	9.70	13.10	18.15	21.91	23.65	21.95	23.07	23.01	24.15	14.71
18	25.94	24.77	9.89	13.24	18.27	22.00	23.65	22.04	22.55	23.13	23.36	15.01
19	25.42	24.70	10.11	13.40	18.41	22.08	23.63	22.19	22.98	23.24	22.95	15.36
20	25.12	24.67	10.08	13.58	18.60	22.19	23.65	22.30	23.10	22.97	22.77	15.74
21	24.98	24.67	9.67	13.77	18.74	22.24	23.68	22.43	23.12	22.75	22.69	16.13
22	24.84	24.68	9.32	14.02	18.91	22.33	23.72	22.55	22.85	22.66	22.69	16.53
23	24.75	24.70	8.94	14.30	19.05	22.39	23.76	22.67	22.59	22.66	22.74	16.94
24	24.60	24.53	9.00	14.62	19.24	22.48	23.77	22.79	22.44	22.72	22.75	17.35
25	24.37	23.69	9.22	14.96	19.37	22.57	23.76	22.89	22.38	22.83	22.02	17.75
26	24.11	19.41	9.47	15.27	19.50	22.66	23.77	23.01	22.46	22.97	21.48	18.12
27	23.98	17.17	9.71	15.58	19.62	22.70	23.80	23.14	22.58	23.10	21.23	18.50
28	23.94	14.10	9.93	15.86	19.61	22.69	23.81	23.27	22.75	23.23	21.15	18.83
29	23.96	10.93	10.15	16.13	19.65	22.72	23.79	23.41	22.89	23.35	21.20	19.19
30	23.99	9.01	10.40	16.36	---	22.76	23.76	23.53	23.04	23.46	21.34	19.51
31	24.05	---	10.63	16.55	---	22.78	---	23.66	---	23.59	21.54	---
LOW	26.55	24.90	10.63	16.55	19.65	22.78	23.81	23.91	24.42	23.59	24.63	23.19
HIGH	23.94	9.01	8.33	10.75	16.75	19.77	22.82	21.91	22.38	22.32	21.15	14.30

WTR YR 1988 MEAN 20.40 LOW 26.55 HIGH 8.33

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182010064472600. Local number, 1.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'10", long 64°47'26".

Owner: U.S. Government, National Park Services.

Name: NPS-2 (Cruz Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), 4 in (0.10 m) cased, 0-20 ft (0-6.10 m), open hole 20-99 ft (6.10-30.2 m). Depth 99 ft (30.2 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 4.10 ft (1.25 m) above old land-surface datum after 1.40 ft (0.43 m) land fill and 2.70 ft (0.82 m) casing extension occurred. Prior to June 29, 1983, top of 4 in (0.10 m) casing, 1.40 ft (0.43 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping nearby well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--May 1964, discontinued. June 30, 1983 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, +1.41ft (0.43 m) above land-surface datum, May 1, 1986; lowest water level measured, 42.56 ft (12.98 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 30, 1967.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 7	33.18	Mar. 22	32.00	June 2	34.14	Aug. 26	1.23
Jan. 20	3.62						

182109064460300. Local number, 2.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°21'09", long 64°46'03".

Owner: U.S. Government, National Park Service.

Name: NPS-5 (Trunk Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table production well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 0-12 ft (0-3.66 m), open hole 12-60 ft (3.66-18.3 m). Depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 0.70 ft (0.21 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to Mar. 24, 1982 top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.00 ft (0.30 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Active water supply well for recreation facilities at Trunk Bay.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1964 to December 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.83 ft (3.91 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 24, 1985; lowest water level measured, a57.29 ft (17.47 m) below land-surface datum, Nov. 27, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 7	38.16	Mar. 22	a41.80	June 2	40.03	Aug. 26	37.92
Jan. 20	a29.78						

a Pumping.

+ Above land-surface datum.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182116064451000. Local number, 3.

LOCATION.--Lat 18 21'16", Long 64 45'10".

Owner: U.S. Government, National Park Service.

Name: NPS-6 (Cinnamon Bay).

AQUIFER.--Volcanic rocks of Cretaceous Age.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table abandoned production well, diameter 6-in (0.15 m), cased 0-51 ft (0-15.55 m), open hole 51-70 ft (15.55-21.34 m). Depth 70 ft (21.34 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 60 ft (18.3 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Hole on 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 29, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing at land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--August 1964 to December 1969, discontinued. March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 41.12 ft (12.54 m) below land-surface datum, Aug. 15, 1969; lowest water level recorded, 63.15 ft (19.25 m) below land-surface datum, July 1, 1968.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	57.78	57.33	54.48	53.72	---	---	57.04	57.24	57.52	57.59	57.95	57.26
2	57.77	57.34	54.02	53.75	---	---	57.05	57.27	57.51	57.60	57.95	57.26
3	57.75	57.35	53.76	53.77	---	---	57.05	57.31	57.50	57.61	57.95	57.27
4	57.73	57.35	53.65	53.80	---	---	57.05	57.33	57.50	57.62	57.95	57.29
5	57.70	57.35	53.65	53.90	---	---	57.06	57.36	57.53	57.63	57.96	57.32
6	57.67	57.33	53.71	53.98	---	---	57.08	57.39	57.56	57.64	57.98	57.33
7	57.63	57.32	53.76	54.03	---	---	57.10	57.39	57.58	57.65	57.99	57.35
8	57.59	57.32	53.80	54.13	---	---	57.11	57.37	57.58	57.65	57.99	57.37
9	57.57	57.34	53.86	54.20	---	---	57.13	57.37	57.58	57.65	58.00	57.35
10	57.57	57.34	53.90	54.24	---	---	57.14	57.35	57.56	57.68	57.99	56.97
11	57.60	57.32	53.92	54.24	---	---	57.13	57.28	57.56	57.69	57.95	56.47
12	57.62	57.31	53.95	54.21	---	---	57.10	57.18	57.57	57.70	57.88	56.21
13	57.62	57.31	54.01	54.20	---	---	57.07	57.13	57.59	57.74	57.84	55.72
14	57.60	57.33	54.11	54.01	---	---	57.04	57.12	57.60	57.76	57.81	55.45
15	57.59	57.34	54.20	53.89	---	---	57.04	57.12	57.60	57.79	57.81	55.26
16	57.56	57.32	54.31	53.80	---	---	57.02	57.14	57.59	57.80	57.81	55.14
17	57.51	57.31	54.39	53.66	---	---	56.99	57.16	57.56	57.82	57.81	55.06
18	57.42	57.31	54.46	53.53	---	---	56.98	57.20	57.56	57.84	57.74	55.03
19	57.35	57.33	54.60	53.48	---	---	56.96	57.24	57.56	57.86	57.67	55.05
20	57.33	57.35	54.65	53.45	---	---	56.97	57.28	57.57	57.89	57.64	55.13
21	57.32	57.37	54.74	53.41	---	---	56.98	57.31	57.60	57.92	57.61	55.19
22	57.31	57.39	54.78	53.44	---	---	57.00	57.34	57.60	57.94	57.58	55.25
23	57.31	57.40	54.64	53.56	---	56.84	57.02	57.36	57.58	57.95	57.55	55.34
24	57.32	57.37	54.34	53.66	---	56.91	57.04	57.40	57.54	57.96	57.53	55.44
25	57.32	57.30	54.01	53.77	---	56.93	57.04	57.45	57.53	57.97	57.45	55.56
26	57.30	57.19	53.76	53.93	---	56.96	57.07	57.47	57.52	57.98	57.37	55.64
27	57.29	56.96	53.64	54.03	---	56.97	57.10	57.50	57.51	57.98	57.33	55.74
28	57.28	56.65	53.55	54.17	---	56.99	57.13	57.54	57.51	57.98	57.30	55.84
29	57.28	55.94	53.54	---	---	57.01	57.17	57.55	57.53	57.98	57.28	55.94
30	57.30	55.14	53.57	---	---	57.01	57.22	57.56	57.56	57.98	57.27	56.04
31	57.32	---	53.60	---	---	57.02	---	57.54	---	57.96	57.26	---
LOW	57.78	57.40	54.78	---	---	---	57.22	57.56	57.60	57.98	58.00	57.37
HIGH	57.28	55.14	53.54	---	---	---	56.96	57.12	57.50	57.59	57.26	55.03

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182042066454500. Local number, 5.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'42", long 66°45'45".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-6. (Sussanaberg)

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Sounded depth 70 ft (21.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.60 ft (0.49 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 28, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.30 ft (0.40 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 1.33 ft (0.40 m) below land-surface datum, May 18, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 22.78 ft (6.94 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 5, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	19.31	20.09	---	---	8.43	---	14.84	16.85	18.32	19.23	20.14	19.01
2	19.34	20.11	---	---	8.50	---	14.95	16.91	18.43	19.25	20.17	19.01
3	19.37	20.13	---	---	8.70	---	15.04	16.97	18.45	19.28	20.20	19.04
4	19.43	20.14	---	---	8.76	---	15.13	17.04	18.50	19.34	20.23	19.07
5	19.47	20.14	---	---	8.81	---	15.20	17.11	18.55	19.37	20.25	19.10
6	19.50	20.20	---	---	8.80	---	15.23	17.16	18.60	19.40	20.29	19.14
7	19.53	20.20	---	---	---	---	15.30	17.24	18.63	19.44	20.32	19.19
8	19.56	20.21	---	---	---	---	15.38	17.30	18.67	19.47	20.35	19.23
9	19.59	20.23	---	---	---	---	15.43	17.34	18.72	19.50	20.37	4.80
10	19.63	20.24	---	---	---	---	15.52	17.40	18.77	19.52	20.38	4.67
11	19.66	20.25	---	---	---	---	15.59	17.41	18.80	19.55	20.38	4.45
12	19.69	20.27	---	---	---	---	15.67	17.48	18.83	19.57	20.40	---
13	19.72	20.30	---	---	---	---	15.76	17.54	18.88	19.59	20.44	---
14	19.77	20.32	---	---	---	---	15.83	17.57	18.91	19.63	20.46	---
15	19.80	20.34	---	---	---	---	15.89	17.58	18.94	19.68	20.48	---
16	19.81	20.36	---	---	---	---	15.96	17.63	18.94	19.71	20.50	---
17	19.81	20.39	---	---	---	---	16.04	17.68	18.95	19.73	20.48	---
18	19.81	20.42	---	---	---	---	16.10	17.72	18.97	19.75	20.45	---
19	19.82	20.44	---	---	---	---	16.11	17.76	18.99	19.77	20.38	---
20	19.83	20.45	---	---	---	---	16.16	17.80	19.02	19.80	20.35	---
21	19.84	20.48	---	6.91	---	---	16.21	17.84	19.03	19.83	20.34	---
22	19.86	20.51	---	7.05	---	---	16.28	17.90	19.04	19.85	20.34	---
23	19.88	20.54	---	7.18	---	14.01	16.36	17.95	19.04	19.88	20.34	---
24	19.91	20.54	---	7.33	---	14.11	16.40	18.00	19.05	19.91	11.20	---
25	19.92	19.45	---	7.40	---	14.19	16.46	18.02	19.07	19.93	19.31	---
26	19.95	9.71	---	7.59	---	14.31	16.52	18.07	19.09	19.96	19.50	---
27	19.97	8.31	---	7.77	---	14.40	16.58	18.14	19.12	20.00	19.40	---
28	19.99	---	---	7.88	---	14.51	16.65	18.17	19.16	20.03	19.29	---
29	20.01	---	---	8.02	---	14.58	16.73	18.22	19.18	20.05	19.19	13.39
30	20.03	---	---	8.17	---	14.62	16.80	18.25	19.21	20.06	19.13	13.54
31	20.06	---	---	8.30	---	14.73	---	18.29	---	20.11	19.01	---
LOW	20.06	---	---	---	---	---	16.80	18.29	19.21	20.11	20.50	---
HIGH	19.31	---	---	---	---	---	14.84	16.85	18.32	19.23	11.20	---

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182044064454600. Local number, 6.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'46".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-5

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Sounded depth 145 ft (44.2 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.40 ft (0.43 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 18.85ft (5.74m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, a107.4 ft (32.7 m) below land-surface datum, Sept. 19, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 7	42.03	Mar. 22	35.55	June 2	39.74	Aug. 26	41.07
Jan. 20	27.35						

182044064454800. Local number, 7.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'48".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-4

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Sounded depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 0.60 ft (0.18 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 14.48 ft (4.41 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, a50.66 ft (15.44 m) below land-surface datum, Jan. 22, 1987.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 7	31.34	Mar. 22	43.61	June 2	29.26	Aug. 26	26.76
Jan. 20	20.79						

182044064454900. Local number, 8.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'49".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-3.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Sounded depth 110 ft (33.5 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 12.17ft (3.71 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 69.58 ft (21.21 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 27, 1986.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 7	26.75	Mar. 20	59.39	June 2	24.90	Aug. 26	25.18
Jan. 20	17.56						

a Pumping.

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

182044064455000. Local number, 9.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'50".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-2.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Sounded depth 65 ft (19.8 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 17.10 ft (5.21 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 52.84 ft (16.1 m) below land-surface datum, Mar 22, 1988.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 7	38.43	Mar. 22	52.84	June 2	35.14	Aug. 26	35.55
Jan. 20	24.10						

182044064455200. Local number, 10.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°20'44", long 64°45'52".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: DPW-1.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation.

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled public supply water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m).

Sounded depth 60 ft (18.3 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum about 640 ft (195 m) above mean sea level.

Measuring point: Top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 2.00 ft (0.61 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Observation well. Water levels affected by pumping.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--September 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level measured, 16.60 ft (5.06 m) below land-surface datum, July 2, 1986; lowest water level measured, 38.92 ft (11.86 m) below land-surface datum, Feb. 27, 1986

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATIONS

Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level	Date	Water level
Oct. 7	34.40	Mar. 22	30.65	June 2	32.82	Aug. 26	34.24
Jan. 20	22.73						

GROUND-WATER LEVELS

ST. JOHN, U.S. VIRGIN ISLANDS

181956064464500. Local number, 11.

LOCATION.--Lat 18°19'56", long 64°46'45".

Owner: Virgin Islands Government.

Name: Guinea Gut Well.

AQUIFER.--Louisenhoj Formation (Donnelly, 1959).

WELL CHARACTERISTICS.--Drilled unused water-table well, diameter 6 in (0.15 m), cased 6 in (0.15 m). Depth 85 ft (25.9 m).

DATUM.--Elevation of land-surface datum is about 280 ft (85.36 m) above mean sea level, from topographic map.

Measuring point: Bottom of 0.5 in (0.01 m) hole at 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.50 ft (0.46 m) above land-surface datum. Prior to June 28, 1983, top of 6 in (0.15 m) casing, 1.80 ft (0.55 m) above land-surface datum.

REMARKS.--Recording observation well.

PERIOD OF RECORD.--March 1982 to current year.

EXTREMES FOR PERIOD OF RECORD.--Highest water level recorded, 3.05 ft (0.93 m) below land-surface datum, June 13, 1986; lowest water level recorded, 25.25 ft (7.70 m) below land-surface datum, Oct. 2, 1985.

WATER LEVEL, IN FEET BELOW LAND-SURFACE DATUM, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1987 TO SEPTEMBER 1988
INSTANTANEOUS OBSERVATION AT 1200

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	18.69	19.55	7.05	4.94	---	---	9.32	11.82	14.70	16.79	18.40	17.56
2	18.77	19.58	6.75	4.92	---	---	9.51	11.93	14.77	16.88	18.48	17.56
3	18.84	19.61	6.54	4.97	---	---	9.63	12.05	14.82	16.96	18.57	17.56
4	18.91	19.66	6.38	4.98	---	---	9.78	12.17	14.91	17.04	18.64	17.56
5	18.97	19.67	6.30	5.00	---	---	9.89	12.26	15.01	17.12	18.70	17.56
6	19.04	19.64	6.21	4.96	---	---	9.87	12.36	15.11	17.21	18.77	17.56
7	19.10	19.62	6.01	4.92	---	---	9.87	12.45	15.21	17.30	18.86	17.57
8	19.14	19.64	5.81	4.88	---	---	9.93	12.57	15.33	17.36	18.95	17.60
9	19.18	19.67	5.76	4.76	---	---	10.03	12.66	15.46	17.39	19.03	14.40
10	19.21	19.69	5.73	4.71	---	---	10.16	12.75	15.55	17.44	19.06	10.15
11	19.25	19.72	5.71	4.59	---	---	10.25	12.76	15.61	17.48	19.06	8.70
12	19.31	19.73	5.69	4.05	---	---	10.40	12.84	15.71	17.51	19.07	7.93
13	19.37	19.77	5.72	4.14	---	---	10.56	12.94	15.79	17.55	19.11	7.49
14	19.41	19.82	5.71	3.74	---	---	10.66	13.04	15.86	17.59	19.17	7.24
15	19.45	19.85	5.72	3.86	---	---	10.77	13.12	15.89	17.63	19.25	7.09
16	19.45	19.91	5.73	4.01	---	---	10.88	13.18	15.93	17.66	19.31	7.01
17	19.42	19.96	5.74	4.15	---	---	11.03	13.23	16.00	17.68	19.17	6.95
18	19.39	20.02	5.74	4.26	---	---	11.13	13.33	16.06	17.73	18.98	6.90
19	19.41	20.06	5.71	4.36	---	---	10.94	13.37	16.14	17.77	18.86	6.90
20	19.42	20.11	5.57	---	---	---	10.92	13.48	16.23	17.77	18.79	6.85
21	19.43	20.15	5.42	---	---	---	10.92	13.54	16.29	17.78	18.75	6.85
22	19.46	20.20	5.08	---	---	---	10.93	13.66	16.35	17.82	18.73	6.85
23	19.47	20.26	4.52	---	---	8.76	11.01	13.77	16.36	17.86	18.72	6.95
24	19.49	20.26	4.56	---	---	8.88	11.10	13.90	16.39	17.89	18.64	7.09
25	19.47	19.81	4.67	---	---	8.93	11.17	14.00	16.41	17.94	18.08	7.23
26	19.45	16.85	4.76	---	---	9.02	11.27	14.12	16.47	18.01	17.87	7.35
27	19.43	12.21	4.86	---	---	9.13	11.39	14.25	16.52	18.07	17.81	7.48
28	19.45	9.50	4.90	---	---	9.20	11.54	14.38	16.59	18.13	17.72	7.53
29	19.48	8.20	4.93	---	---	9.29	11.64	14.51	16.66	18.20	17.65	7.55
30	19.51	7.43	4.91	---	---	9.23	11.74	14.58	16.74	18.26	17.58	7.96
31	19.53	---	4.94	---	---	9.28	---	14.64	---	18.32	17.56	---
LOW	19.53	20.26	7.05	---	---	---	11.74	14.64	16.74	18.32	19.31	17.60
HIGH	18.69	7.43	4.52	---	---	---	9.32	11.82	14.70	16.79	17.56	6.85

**THIS PAGE WAS LEFT BLANK
INTENTIONALLY**

Page	Page
Access to WATSTORE data	33
Acre-foot, definition of	34
Adenosine triphosphate, definition of	34
Adjuntas, Lago Garzas near	70
Adjuntas, Lago Garzas No. 1 near dam near	381-387
Adjuntas, Río Grande de Arecibo near	71-72
Aguada, Río Culebrinas near	374-375
Agua Buenas, Río de Bayamón near	139-140
Algae growth potential, definition of	34
Analyses of samples collected at water-quality partial-record stations in Puerto Rico	378-387
Añasco, Río Grande de Añasco near	367-368
Aquifer, definition of	34
Arecibo, Río Grande de Arecibo above	79-80
Artesian, definition of	34
Artificial substrate, definition of	44
Ash mass, definition of	35
Bairoa near Caguas, Río	221-222
Bacteria, definition of	34
Bahía de San Juan No. 5 at San Juan	153
Bayamón, at Flood Channel at Bayamón, Río de near Agua Buenas	143-144 139-140
Bayamón basin, Río de, gaging-station records in ground-water records in	138 407
water-quality records in	139-144
Bayamón, Río Guaynabo near	141-142
Bayaney, Río Camuy near	64-6
Bed material, definition of	35
Bed load, definition of	43
Bed load discharge, definition of	43
Biochemical oxygen demand, definition of	35
Biomass, definition of	35
Blanca at El Jagual, Quebrada	160-167
Blanco basin, Río, gaging station records in	298-299
Blasina near Carolina, Quebrada	156-157
Blue-green algae, definition of	41
Bonne Resolution Gut at Bonne Resolution, St Thomas, VI	432-433
Borinquen, Río Turabo at	189-198
Bottom material, definition of	35
Bucaná at Highway 14 near Ponce	330-331
Bucaná basin, Río, gaging-station records in water-quality records in	330-331 328-329
Caguas, Lago Loíza No. 4 near mouth near	378-380
Caguas, Río Bairoa near	221-222
Caguas, Río Caguitas at Highway 30 at	289-220
Caguas, Río Grande de Loíza at	199-218
Caguitas at Highway 30 at Caguas, Río	219-220
Caimito near Juncos, Quebrada	223-230
Campo Rico, Río Canóvanas near	278-279
Camuy basin, Río, gaging station records in	64-67
Camuy near Bayaney, Río	64-65
near Hatillo	66-67
Canal Principal de Diversiones at Lago de Guajataca	58-59
Canóvanas near Campo Rico, Río	278-279
Caonillas above Lago Caonillas near Jayuya, Río	75-76
Carolina, Quebrada Blasina near	156-157
Cataño, Río Hondo at Flood Channel near	136-137
Cayaguas at Cerro Gordo, Río	178-188
Cayey, Lago Carite No. 1 near dam	381-387
Cayey, Lago Carite No. 3 on Río de la Plata near	378-380
Cells/volume, definition of	35
Central Cambalache, Río Grande de Arecibo at	90-91
Central Rufina, Río Guayanilla o Guayanilla at	339-340
Cerrillos near Ponce, Río	328-329
Cerro Gordo, Río Cayaguas at	178-188
Charco Hondo, Río Tanamá at	88-89
Chemical oxygen demand, definition of	36
Chico at Providencia, Río	311-312
Chico basin, Río, water-quality records in	311-312
Chlorophyll, definition of	36
Ciales, Río Cialitos at Highway 649 at	105-106
Ciales, Río Grande de Manatí at	101-102
Ciales, Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 149 at	103-104
Cialitos at Highway 649 at Ciales, Río	105-106
Cibuco at Vega Baja, Río	117-119
below Corozal	114-116
Cibuco basin, gaging-station records in ground-water records in	114-117 399-402
water-quality records in	115-119
Cidra, Lago de Cidra at Damsite near	138
Coamo basin, Río, ground-water records in water-quality records in	413 318-319
Coamo near Coamo, Río	318-319
Color unit, definition of	36
Comerio, Río de la Plata near	125-126
Contents, definition of	36
Control, definition of	36
Control structure, definition of	36
Cooperation	2
Corozal, Río Cibuco below	114-116
Crest-stage station, definition of	36
Cubic foot per second, definition of	36
Cubic foot per second-day, definition of	36
Cubic feet per second per square mile, definition of	36
Culebrinas, at Highway 404 near Moca, Río near Aguada	372-373 374-375
near San Sebastián	370-371
Culebrinas basin, Río, gaging station records in ground-water records in	372-371 428-429
water-quality records in	370-375
Damsite, Lago El Guineo at	99
Damsite, Lago Loíza at	273-274
Damsite, Lago Matrullas at	100
Damsite, Río Grande de Loíza below275
Definition of terms	34-47
Descalabrado basin, Río, gaging stations records in	320-321
Descalabrado near Los Llanos, Río	320-321
Diatoms, definition of	41
Discharge, definition of	36
Dissolved, definition of	37
Dissolved-solids concentrations	37
Diversity index, definition of	37
Drainage area, definition of	37
Drainage basin, definition of	37
Dry mass, definition of	35
El Señorial, Río Piedras at	145
El Verde, Quebrada Sonadora near	282-283
El Verde, Quebrada Toronja at	284-285
Espíritu Santo basin, Río, gaging station records in water-quality records in	282-286 283-288
Espíritu Santo near Río Grande, Río	286-288
Explanation of records	11-33
Fajardo basin, Río, gaging station records in water-quality records in293 294-297
Fajardo below Fajardo, Río near Fajardo	296-297 293-295
Fecal coliform bacteria, definition of	35
Fecal streptococcal bacteria, definition of	35
Florida, Río Grande de Arecibo below Lago Dos Bocas near	77-78
Gage-height, definition of	37
Gaging station, definition of	37
Grande de Añasco basin, Río, gaging station records in water-quality records in	364 362-368
Grande de Añasco near Añasco, Río near Lares	367-368 362-363
near San Sebastián	364-366
Grande de Arecibo at Central Cambalache, Río above Arecibo	90-91 79-80
below Lago Dos Bocas near Florida	77-78
near Adjuntas	71-72
near Utuado	73-74
Grande de Arecibo basin, Río, gaging station records in ground-water records in	78-89 392
water-quality partial-record stations, analyses of samples collected in	378-387 156-277
water-quality records in	71-91
Grande de Loíza at Caguas, Río	199-218
at Quebrada Arenas	158-159
below Damsite275
below Trujillo Alto	278-277
Grande de Loíza basin, Río, gaging station records in ground-water records in	158-279 410
water-quality partial-record stations, analyses of samples collected in	378-387 156-277
water-quality records in	156-277
Grande de Manatí at Ciales, Río	101-102
at Highway 2 near Manatí	107-111
at Highway 149 at Ciales	103-104
near Morovis	96-98
Grande de Manatí basin, Río, gaging station records in ground-water records in	96-108 393-398
water-quality records in	94-111
Grande de Patillas near Patillas, Río	313-315
Grande de Patillas basin, Río, gaging station records in water-quality records in313 314-315
Graphs:	
Ground-water levels at selected wells in Puerto Rico and the US Virgin Islands	8
Monthly-mean discharge of selected streams in Puerto Rico	4
Green algae, definition of	41

Page	Page
Grid showing system for numbering wells and miscellaneous sites (latitude and longitude)	19
Ground-water level, records of	30-32
Ground-water quality, records of	32-33
Ground-water records for Puerto Rico	390-429
Ground-water records for US Virgin Islands	440-455
Ground-water station, definition of	37
Ground-water stations in Puerto Rico, map showing location of	18
Ground-water stations in the US Virgin Islands, map showing location of	18
Guadiana near Naranjito, Río	127-128
Guajataca above Lago de Guajataca, Río	56-57
above mouth near Quebradillas	60-62
at Lares	54-55
Guajataca basin, Río, gaging station records in	56-60
ground-water records in	390-391
water-quality partial-record stations, analyses of samples collected in	378-387
water-quality records in	54-62
Guanajibo near Hormigueros, Río	355-357
near San Germán	348-347
Guanajibo basin, Río, gaging station records in	348-355
ground-water records in	427
water-quality records in	348-357
Guánica, Río Loco at	341-342
Guayanés above mouth at Playa de Guayanés, Río	307-308
at Yabucoa	305-306
Guayanés basin, Río, ground-water records in	415
water-quality records in	305-308
Guayanilla at Central Rufina, Río	339-340
near Guayanilla	337-338
Guayanilla basin, Río, gaging station records in	337-338
water-quality records in	339-340
Guaynabo near Bayamón, Río	141-142
Guinea Gut at Bethany, St John, VI	435
Gurabo at Gurabo, Río	252-270
near Gurabo	271-272
Gurabo, Quebrada Mamey near	242-251
Hardness, definition of	38
Hatillo, Río Camuy near	66-67
Hato Rey, Río Piedras at	149-150
Hondo at Flood Channel near Cataño, Río	136-137
Hondo basin, Río, ground-water records in	406-409
water-quality records in	136-137
Hormigueros, Río Guanajibo near	355-357
Hormigueros, Río Rosario near	348-354
Humacao at Highway 3 at Humacao, Río	303-304
Humacao at Las Piedras, Río	302
Humacao basin, Río, gaging-station records in	302
water-quality records in	303-304
Hydrologic Bench-Mark Network, definition of	38
Hydrologic conditions, summary of	2-10
Hydrologic unit, definition of	38
Icacos near Naguabo, Río	298-299
Identification numbers, stations	11-19
Inabón at Real Abajo, Río	326-327
Inabón basin, Río, gaging station records in	326-327
ground-water station in	426
Instantaneous discharge, definition of	36
Introduction	1
Jacaguas at Juana Díaz, Río	322-323
Jacaguas basin, Río, gaging station records in	322-323
Jagual, Quebrada Blanca at El	160-167
Jayuya, Río Caonillas above Lago Caonillas near	75-76
Jolly Hill Gut at Jolly Hill, St Croix, VI	436-437
Josefina at Piñero Avenue, Quebrada	151
Joyuda, Quebrada Mamey at	344-345
Juana Díaz, Río Jacaguas at	322-323
Juncos, Quebrada Caimito near	223-230
Juncos, Río Valenciano near	231-241
Lago Carite No. 1 near dam near Cayey	381-387
No. 3 on Río de la Plata near Cayey	378-380
Lago de Cidra at Damsite near Cidra	138
Lago de Guajataca, Canal Principal de Diversiones at	58-59
No. 1 near dam near Quebradillas	381-387
No. 3 near mouth near Quebradillas	378-380
Río Guajataca above	56-57
Lago Dos Bocas No. 1 near dam near Utuado	351-387
No. 3 at west branch near Utuado	378-380
Lago El Guineo at Damsite	99
Lago Garzas near Adjuntas	70
No. 1 near dam near Adjuntas	381-387
Lago La Plata No. 3 near dam near Naranjito	381-387
No. 5 near mouth near Naranjito	378-380
Lago Loíza at damsite	273-274
No. 4 near mouth near Caguas	378-380
No. 7 near dam near Trujillo Alto	381-387
Lago Matrullas at Damsite	100
Laguna Joyuda basin, gaging station records in	344-345
Laguna San José No. 2 at San Juan	152
Laguna Tortuguero basin, water-quality records in	112
Laguna Tortuguero outlet near Vega Baja	112
Land-surface datum, definition of	38
La Plata at Proyecto La Plata, Río de	122-124
at Highway 2 near Toa Alta	132-133
at Toa Alta	129-131
near Comerío	125-126
La Plata basin, Río de, gaging station records in	122-133
ground-water records in	403-405
water-quality partial-record stations, analyses of samples collected in	378-387
water-quality records in	123-131
Lares, Río Grande de Añasco near	362-363
Lares, Río Guajataca at	54-55
Las Piedras, Río Humacao at	302
Levels for Puerto Rico, ground-water	390-429
Levels for US Virgin Islands, ground water	440-455
Loco at Guánica, Río	341-342
Loco basin, Río, water-quality records in	341-342
ground-water records in	403-405
water-quality partial-record stations, analyses of samples collected in	378-387
water-quality records in	123-131
Lares, Río Grande de Añasco near	362-363
Lares, Río Guajataca at	54-55
Las Piedras, Río Humacao at	302
Levels for Puerto Rico, ground-water	390-429
Levels for US Virgin Islands, ground water	440-455
Loco at Guánica, Río	341-342
Loco basin, Río, water-quality records in	341-342
Los Llanos, Río Descalabrado near	320-321
Mamey at Joyuda, Quebrada	344-345
Mamey near Gurabo, Quebrada	242-251
Mameyes near Sabana, Río	289-290
Mameyes basin, Río, gaging station records in	289-290
Manatí, Río Grande de Manatí at Highway 2 near	107-111
Maps:	
Location of continuous surface-water stations Puerto Rico	14
Location of ground-water stations in Puerto Rico	16
Location of ground-water stations in the US Virgin Islands	18
Location of maximum concentration of fecal coliform bacteria at sample sites	12
Location of maximum concentration of fecal streptococci bacteria at sample sites	13
Location of surface-water stations in the US Virgin Islands	17
Location of water-quality stations in Puerto Rico	15
Río Camuy basin	63
Río Cibuco basin	113
Río Culebrinas basin	369
Río Grande de Arecibo basin	69
Río Grande de Loíza basin	155
Río Grande de Manatí basin	93
Río Guajataca basin	53
Río Guanajibo basin	343
Río Herrera to the Río Antón Ruiz basins	281
Río Hondo to the Río Puerto Nuevo basins	135
Río Humacao to the Río Seco basins	301
Río Inabón to the Río Loco basins	325
Río de la Plata basin	121
Río Salinas to the Río Jacaguas basins	317
Río Yagüez and the Río Grande de Añasco basins	359
Maunabo at Maunabo, Río	309-310
Maunabo basin, Río, water-quality records in	309-310
Maximum concentrations of fecal coliform bacteria at sampled sites, map showing location of	12
Maximum concentrations of fecal streptococci bacteria at sampled sites, map showing location of	13
Mayagüez, Río Yagüez near	360-361
Mean concentration, definition of	43
Mean discharge, definition of	36
Measuring point, definition of	38
Metamorphic stage, definition of	38
Methylene blue active substances, definition of	38
Micrograms per gram, definition of	38
Micrograms per liter, definition of	38
Milligrams of carbon per area or volume per unit time for periphyton and macrophytes and for phytoplankton, definition of	42
Milligrams of oxygen per area or volume per unit time for periphyton and macrophytes and for phytoplankton, definition of	42
Milligrams per liter, definition of	38
Moca, Río Culebrinas at Highway 404 near	372-373
Morovis, Río Grande de Manatí near	96-98

	Page		Page
Naguabo, Río Icacos near	298-299	Sonadora near El Verde, Quebrada	282-283
Naranjito, Lago La Plata No. 3 near dam near	381-387	Solute, definition of	44
Naranjito, Lago La Plata No. 5 near mouth near	378-380	Special network and programs	11
Naranjito, Río Guadiana near	127-128	Specific conductance, definition of	44
National Stream-Quality Accounting Network, definition of	39	Stage-discharge relation, definition of	44
National Trends Network, definition of	40	Station identification numbers	11-19
Natural substrate, definition of	44	St Croix, VI, Jolly Hill Gut at Jolly Hill	436-437
Networks and programs, special	11	St John, VI, Guinea Gut at Bethany	435
		Streamflow, definition of	44
Organic mass, definition of	35	St Thomas, VI, Bonne Resolution Gut at Bonne Resolution	432-433
Organism, definition of	40	St Thomas, VI, Turpentine Run at Mariendal	434
Organism count/area, definition of	40	Substrate, definition of	44
Organism count/volume, definition of	40	Summary of hydrologic conditions	2-10
Orocovis near Orocovis, Río	94-95	Surface and quality-of-water records for Puerto Rico	53-375
		Surface area, definition of	44
Parameter code, definition of	40	Surface-water quality, records of	25-30
Partial record station, definition of	40	Surface-water records for US Virgin Islands	432-437
Partial record stations in Puerto Rico,		Surface-water stations in Puerto Rico, map showing location of	14
water quality at	378-387	Surface-water stations in US Virgin Islands, map showing location of	17
Particle size, definition of	40	Surficial bed material, definition of	44
Particle-size classification, definition of	40	Suspended, definition of	44
Patillas, Río Grande de Patillas near	313-315	Suspended-recoverable, definition of	45
Percent composition, definition of	41	Suspended sediment, definition of	43
Periphyton, definition of	41	Suspended-sediment concentration, definition of	43
Pesticides, definition of	41	Suspended-sediment discharge, definition of	43
Phytoplankton, definition of	41	Suspended-sediment load, definition of	43
Picocurie, definition of	41	Suspended-total, definition of	45
Piedras, at Hato Rey, Río	149-150		
at Río Piedras	148	Tanamá at Charco Hondo, Río	88-89
at El Señorial	145	near Utuado	81-87
near Río Piedras	146-147	Taxonomy, definition of	45
Piñero Avenue, Quebrada Josefina at	151	Techniques of water-resources investigations, publications on	48-49
Plankton, definition of	41	Terms, definition of	34-47
Playa de Guayanés, Río Guayanés above mouth at	307-308	Thermograph, definition of	45
Polychlorinated biphenyls, definition of	42	Time-weighted average, definition of	46
Ponce, Río Bucaná at Highway 14 near	330-331	Toa Alta, Río de La Plata at	129-131
Ponce, Río Cerrillos near	328-329	Toa Alta, Río de La Plata at Highway 2 near	132-133
Ponce, Río Portugués at	335-336	Tons per acre-foot, definition of	46
Ponce, Río Portugués near	332-334	Tons per day, definition of	46
Portugués at Ponce, Río	335-336	Toronja at El Verde, Quebrada	284-285
near Ponce	332-334	Total, definition of	46
Portugués basin, Río, gaging station records in	332	Total coliform bacteria, definition of	34
water-quality records in	333-336	Total discharge, definition of	46
Primary productivity, definition of	42	Total organism count, definition of	40
Programs, special networks and	11	Total-recoverable, definition of	46
Providencia, Río Chico at	311-312	Total sediment discharge, definition of	43
Proyecto La Plata, Río de La Plata at	122-124	Total-sediment load, definition of	43
Publications on techniques of water-resources investigations	48-49	Tritium network, definition of	46
Puerto Nuevo basin, Río, gaging-station records in	145-151	Trujillo Alto, Lago Loíza No. 7 near dam near	381-387
ground-water records in	408-409	Trujillo Alto, Río Grande de Loíza below	276-277
water-quality records in	146-153	Turabo at Borinquen, Río	189-198
		Turpentine Run at Mariendal, St. Thomas, VI	434
Quality of water records of Puerto Rico, surface and	53-375		
Quebrada Arenas, Río Grande de Loíza at	158-159	Utuado, Lago Dos Bocas No. 1 near dam near	381-387
Quebradillas, Lago Guajataca No. 1 near dam near	381-387	Utuado, Lago Dos Bocas No. 3 at west branch near	378-380
Quebradillas, Lago Guajataca No. 3 near mouth near	378-380	Utuado, Río Grande de Arecibo near	73-74
Quebradillas, Río Guajataca above mouth near	60-62	Utuado, Río Tanamá near	81-87
Radiochemical program, definition of	42		
Real Abejo, Río Inabón at	326-327	Valenciano near Juncos, Río	231-241
Records, explanation of	11-33	Vega Baja, Laguna Tortuguero outlet near	112
Records of ground-water levels	30-32	Vega Baja, Río Cibuco at	117-119
Records of ground-water quality	32-33		
Records of stage and water discharge	20-25	Water-discharge, records of stage and	20-25
Records of surface-water quality	25-30	Water-quality partial-record stations in Puerto Rico,	
Recoverable from bottom material, definition of	42	analyses of samples collected at	378-387
Return period, definition of	42	Water-quality stations in Puerto Rico, map showing location of	15
Río Grande, Río Espíritu Santo near	286-288	Water-resources investigations, publications on techniques of	48-49
Río Piedras, Río Piedras near	146-147	Water year, definition of	47
Rosario near Hormigueros, Río	348-354	WATSTORE data, Access to	33
Runoff, in inches, definition of	42	WDR, definition of	47
		Weighted average, definition of	47
		Wells - Puerto Rico:	
Sabana at Sabana, Río	291-292	Bayamón basin, Río de	
Sabana basin, Río, gaging station records in	291-292	Well 219 - Fort Buchanan No. 1	407
Sabana, Río Mameyes near	289-290	Cibuco basin, Río	
Salvatierra near San Lorenzo, Quebrada	168-177	Well 70 - Sabana Hoyos	399
Salinas basin, Río, ground-water records in	414-425	Well 211 - Rosario No. 2	400
San Germán, Río Guanajibo near	346-347	Well 212 - Ponderosa TW-1	401
San Juan, Bahía de San Juan No. 5 at	153	Well 213 - Pampano No 2	402
San Juan, Laguna San José No. 2 at	152	Coamo basin, Río	
San Lorenzo, Quebrada Salvatierra near	168-177	Well 87 - Alomar 1	413
San Sebastián, Río Culebrinas near	370-371	Culebrinas basin, Río	
San Sebastián, Río Grande de Añasco near	364-366	Well 83 - San Sebastián	428
Seco basin, Río, ground-water records in	411	Well 200 - Aguadilla Cement north	429
Sediment, definition of	43	Grande de Arecibo basin, Río	
Sodium-adsorption-ratio, definition of	44	Well 204 - Gilberto Rivera	392

	Page		Page
Grande de Loíza basin, Río		Wells - US Virgin Islands:	
Well 222 - Campo Rico TW-1	410	St Croix	
Grande de Manatí basin, Río		Well 1 - Fairplains 6 (FP6)	.440
Well 205 - NC-05 Barceloneta near Cruce Davila	393	Well 2 - USGS-10, Fairplains 2 (FP2)	.441
Well 206 - Plazuela No. 2	394	Well 3 - Golden Grove 6 (PW6)	.442
Well 207 - Cantito La Luisa	395	Well 4 - Golden Grove 1 (PW1)	.443
Well 208 - Acrópolis - Manatí	396	Well 6 - Adventure 28	.444
Well 209 - Coto Norte No. 3	397	Well 7 - Concordia 14	.445
Well 210 - Gelo Martínez	398	Well 8 - Concordia 1 (main pump house)	.445
Guajataca basin, Río		Well 9 - Concordia 7	.446
Well 165 - Mateo Pérez, Bo. Salto	390	Well 10 - Barren Spot 5 (PWD-5)	.446
Well 202 - Carmelo Barreto-García	391	St John	
Guanajibo basin, Río		Well 1 - NPS-2 (Cruz Bay)	.450
Well 143 - Vvoni, Hacienda Amistad	427	Well 2 - NPS-5 (Trunk Bay)	.450
Guayanés basin, Río		Well 3 - NPS-6 (Cinnamon Bay)	.451
Well 98 - USGS TW-2 or Yabucoa 7	412	Well 5 - DPW-6	.452
Hondo basin, Río		Well 6 - DPW-5	.453
Well 218 - Levittown No. 7	406	Well 7 - DPW-4	.453
La Plata basin, Río de		Well 8 - DPW-3	.453
Well 214 - Dorado Beach No. 7	403	Well 9 - DPW-2	.454
Well 216 - Pozo Navy - Campanillas	404	Well 10 - DPW-1	.454
Well 217 - Monserrate TW-2	405	Well 11 - Guinea Gut Well	.455
Puerto Nuevo basin, Río		St Thomas	
Well 220 - Parque San Luis Rey	408	Well 1 - USGS-8 (Family well-Thatch Farm)	.447
Well 221 - Hyde Park TW-10	409	Well 2 - Mahogany 15	.447
Salinas basin, Río		Well 3 - Mahogany 16	.447
Well - HW - TW - 01	414	Well 4 - Mahogany 17	.448
Well - HW - TW - 02	415	Well 5 - Donoe 3	.448
Well - HW - TW - 03	416	Well 6 - Grade School 3	.449
Well - HW - TW - 04	417	Yauco basin, Río	
Well - HW - TW - 05B	418	Well 132 - Yauco 2	.426
Well - HW - TW - 07	419	Wet mass, definition of	35
Well - HW - TW - 08	420	WSP, definition of	47
Well - HW - TW - 10	421	Yabucoa, Río Guayanés at	305-306
Well - HW - TW - 11	422	Yagüez near Mayagüez, Río	360-361
Well - HW - TW - 13	423	Yagüez basin, Río, water-quality records in	360-361
Well - HW - TW - 14	424	Yauco basin, Río, ground-water records in	.426
Well - HW - TW - 15	425	Zooplankton, definition of	41
Seco basin, Río			
Well 6 - Juana 5	411		

FACTORS FOR CONVERTING INCH-POUND UNITS TO INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM UNITS (SI)

The following factors may be used to convert the inch-pound units published herein to the International System of Units (SI).

Multiply inch-pound units	By	To obtain SI units
<i>Length</i>		
inches (in)	2.54×10^1	millimeters (mm)
	2.54×10^{-2}	meters (m)
feet (ft)	3.048×10^{-1}	meters (m)
miles (mi)	1.609×10^0	kilometers (km)
<i>Area</i>		
acres	4.047×10^3	square meters (m ²)
	4.047×10^{-1}	square hectometers (hm ²)
	4.047×10^{-3}	square kilometers (km ²)
square miles (mi ²)	2.590×10^0	square kilometers (km ²)
<i>Volume</i>		
gallons (gal)	3.785×10^0	liters (L)
	3.785×10^0	cubic decimeters (dm ³)
	3.785×10^{-3}	cubic meters (m ³)
million gallons	3.785×10^3	cubic meters (m ³)
	3.785×10^{-3}	cubic hectometers (hm ³)
cubic feet (ft ³)	2.832×10^1	cubic decimeters (dm ³)
	2.832×10^{-2}	cubic meters (m ³)
cfs-days	2.447×10^3	cubic meters (m ³)
	2.447×10^{-3}	cubic hectometers (hm ³)
acre-feet (acre-ft)	1.233×10^3	cubic meters (m ³)
	1.233×10^{-3}	cubic hectometers (hm ³)
	1.233×10^{-6}	cubic kilometers (km ³)
<i>Flow</i>		
cubic feet per second (ft ³ /s)	2.832×10^1	liters per second (L/s)
	2.832×10^1	cubic decimeters per second (dm ³ /s)
	2.832×10^{-2}	cubic meters per second (m ³ /s)
gallons per minute (gal/min)	6.309×10^{-2}	liters per second (L/s)
	6.309×10^{-2}	cubic decimeters per second (dm ³ /s)
	6.309×10^{-5}	cubic meters per second (m ³ /s)
million gallons per day	4.381×10^1	cubic decimeters per second (dm ³ /s)
	4.381×10^{-2}	cubic meters per second (m ³ /s)
<i>Mass</i>		
tons (short)	9.072×10^{-1}	megagrams (Mg) or metric tons

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR
Geological Survey
GPO Box 4424
San Juan, PR 00936

OFFICIAL BUSINESS
PENALTY FOR PRIVATE USE \$300
SPECIAL 4TH CLASS BOOK RATE

TERIO